

Optimization of a Perovskite-based Multilayer Microwave Absorber using an Equivalent Circuit Model

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the optimization of a perovskite-based multi-layer microwave absorber is performed to find an optimized value of the impedance step gradient from the refractive index of the constitutive layers. The optimization presented is unique as it is based on maximizing the dissipation and attenuation ability of the absorber along with a constraint of providing an efficient reflection loss in the absorber. This type of approach ensures the maximum absorption rate of the incident EM waves as the penetrating waves get fully dissipated. Objective and constraint functions are derived from the equivalent circuit model of the multi-layer absorber. The equivalent circuit model is formed using the inductive and capacitive effects across the dielectric and magnetic properties of the constitutive layers. The three layers are composed of perovskite materials with different refractive indexes such that the top layer serves as an impedance-matching layer followed by an alternate dielectric and magnetic layer. It is further shown how the capacitive and inductive losses are dominant over each other in the alternate lossy layers. Empirical relations are used to tabulate the refractive index of a range of perovskite compounds from which suitable combinations can be selected as per the obtained value of the step gradient function. The current work presents a simplistic method to design multi-layer microwave absorbers with different material combinations that are beneficial to the practical applications of microwave absorbers.

Keywords-multi layer microwave absorber; equivalent circuit model; perovskite; refractive index

I. INTRODUCTION

Multilayer structures form an important part in the field of microwave absorption. While single layer absorbers may be sufficient for absorber coatings, in applications where heavy exposure of EM radiation is to be absorbed, multilayer absorbers are more efficient [1]. Researchers have used optimization-based approaches like Genetic Algorithm (GA), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and other evolutionary algorithms to design multilayer absorbers using Chew's recursive formula [2-3]. However, the recursive formula used in the above algorithms presents a limitation on the analysis of the individual layers in the multilayer design. Carbon-based absorbers recursive formula was commonly used as the changes in the properties of each layer are marginal and the configuration of each layer is the same with the difference being only in the volume of fillers used. Now, with researchers relying more on the inorganic materials to be used as microwave absorbers, the analysis and modeling theories of multilayer absorbers should be adapted and usually, more prominently used in frequency selective surfaces equivalent circuit models, can help in designing much simplistic models for the optimization of multilayer absorbers [4-5].

In this work, an attempt has been made to analyze and optimize the design of multilayer absorbers. The optimization is done by developing an equivalent circuit model for a three-layer perovskite-based multilayer design. The model takes into account the capacitive and the inductive losses in the alternate dielectric and magnetic layers of the absorber and includes the characteristics and properties of the individual layers. Supporting theories have been provided to understand the role of each layer and the loss mechanism occurring at the alternate layers of the absorber. In the current work, an equivalent circuit model for multilayer absorber is formed by including the dissipation properties of each layer. The reason for choosing perovskite for the absorber design is its inherited dielectric and magnetic properties that can be tuned easily by just changing the composition of the oxide [6]. Hence, in this work an optimized design of a three-layer microwave absorber is presented with different perovskite oxide combination for the individual layers.

II. EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT MODEL

Perovskite oxides are inorganic compounds with a basic composition of ABO_3 type where A and B are cations and O is oxygen. In microwave absorbing perovskite composites,

permittivity and permeability depend on the composition of the perovskite compound, the creation of defects, oxygen vacancies, and influence of cations on the boundary material [7-8].

Fig. 1. Polarization and charge distribution in perovskite composite.

Permittivity and permeability of a perovskite are affected by different properties of the composite [9]. As shown in Figure 1, the permittivity of perovskites is determined mainly by the nature and amount of polarization occurring across the individual unit cell. Dipole and interfacial polarizations contribute mainly to the permittivity. These can be easily induced in a composite structure by using functionally active and oxygen interactive binding materials along with the perovskite filler. Graphene and reduced graphene oxide form one such example [10]. The interaction between the oxygen in the unit cell and the functional group of the binding material creates vacancies and defects thereby increasing the overall permittivity. Similarly, for induced permeability, charge distribution across the B-O-B bond of perovskite plays an important role. In the B-O-B bond of the perovskite p-orbital of oxygen overlaps with the d-orbital of the B cation on both sides, such that the bond is split to an upper and lower energy orbital. If the charge distribution is such that one of the upper energy levels is half filled for one B-O bond while the other on the opposite side is empty, magnetic dipoles get induced across the perovskite unit cell [11-13]. This charge distribution is also affected by the boundary material used in the composite. Based on the above explanation, it can be concluded that permittivity and permeability show trade off characteristics in magnetic and dielectric perovskite composites. Theoretically, this can be understood by considering that in order to have a higher permittivity, the interaction of the oxygen anion with the binding material must increase to create higher polarization. This in turn will weaken the B-O-B bond leading to lower the magnetic charge interaction across the B-O-B bonds decreasing permeability. Hence, in lieu of the above theory presented, maximum amount of dissipation losses can be obtained if separate layers for dielectric and magnetic losses can be combined alternately in multilayer absorbers with the top layer serving as an impedance matching layer to minimize the

reflection loss. This will not only provide the required reflection loss, but also an efficient dissipation mechanism. Using alternate layers of dielectric and magnetic compounds can also reduce the risk of interference when using microwave absorbers in practical applications with devices that are dielectric or magnetic.

In order to formulate an objective function, the equivalent circuit model of Figure 2 is presented, which is based on the dissipation theory explained above. Two objective functions are formulated: one for the overall reflection loss and another for the net dissipation in the absorber. In Figure 2, the first layer provides the impedance matching, with the input impedance of the layer matched with the free space impedance to allow the maximum amount of microwaves to penetrate across the composite with reflection loss less or equal to -20dB as per industrial standards. Below the top layer, there are the dielectric and magnetic dissipation layers represented as lumped capacitor and inductor respectively. In the dielectric layer, dissipation occurs via the formation of dielectric dipoles across the layer [14]. The dipoles are aligned in such a way that the upper layer intersection is positively charged, while the lower is negatively charged and can be shown as a lumped capacitor in the circuit model. The incident microwave charge is stored and dissipated across this capacitor. The third layer is magnetic with the dissipation occurring due to the formation of magnetic dipoles across the layer [15]. The magnetic dipoles are aligned in such a way that the magnetic lines generated due to the dipoles are directed towards the negative intersection of the capacitive layer. The current direction across the layer falls along the negative x axis. Thus the impedance in the magnetic layer is represented as negative induction.

Fig. 2. Equivalent circuit model of the multilayer microwave absorber.

III. OBJECTIVE FUNCTIONS

The objective functions for the multilayer absorber are formulated to find an optimized value of the step gradient by which the refractive index of the consequent layers must increase from the top layer. Let z be the value of the step gradient and n be the value of the refractive index of the top layer. L and C are assumed to be the lumped inductance and capacitance of the magnetic and dielectric layer of the absorber composite given by [16]:

$$L = \mu \frac{Z}{\eta} \text{ and } C = \varepsilon \frac{\eta}{Z} \quad (1)$$

where η is the characteristic impedance of the absorber and Z is the input impedance of the absorber. The attenuation constant α_a of the absorber composite is given by:

$$\alpha_a = \frac{1}{2} G' Z \quad (2)$$

where G' represents the imaginary part of the conductance in the equivalent circuit model. The conductance G' can be presented in terms of L and C as:

$$G' = \frac{-1}{j\omega L} + j\omega C \quad (3)$$

where ω is the angular frequency. With $f=2.54 \times 10^9$ Hz, the angular frequency is given by $\omega=2\pi f=1.59 \times 10^{10}$ rad/s. Combining (1)-(3), the following equation is obtained:

$$f_1 = (1 + \omega^2 LC) Z \quad (4)$$

Substituting L, C from the above equations, (5) is obtained:

$$LC = \sqrt{\mu\varepsilon} = z.n \quad (5)$$

where n is the refractive index value of the absorber composite and z is the step gradient value, which is the input variable in the presented model. Now reversing f_1 for minimization, the objective function is given by:

$$\min. f_1 = -(1 + \omega^2 zn) Z \quad (6)$$

For the second objective function, Reflection Loss (RL) coefficient for the absorber composite is considered [17]:

$$RL = \left| \frac{Z_{in} - Z_0}{Z_{in} + Z_0} \right| \quad (7)$$

The input impedance of the absorber can be written as:

$$Z_{in} = \eta \tanh\left(\frac{\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon} 2\pi f d}{a}\right) \quad (8)$$

Z_0 is the characteristic impedance of free space. For an efficient amount of absorption in the absorber, the characteristic impedance of the microwave absorber η must be such that RL must not be less than -20dB. To obtain the above value, η must be related to Z_0 as [18]:

$$\eta = 1.22 Z_0 \quad (9)$$

Similarly, to optimize the function for reflection loss in terms of the refractive index, thickness is considered constant to simplify the objective function with:

$$d = 2\pi f \quad (10)$$

Substituting (8)-(10) in (7) and assuming $\tanh x \approx x$ for small values of x , the function f_2 for optimizing the RL coefficient can be written as:

$$f_2 = \frac{1.22zn-1}{1.22zn+1} \quad (11)$$

f_2 represents the reflection coefficient of the absorber which depends on the required RL of the absorber as:

$$f_2 = \frac{10^{RL}}{20} \quad (12)$$

Solving (12) for the RL range from -20 to -60dB, the constraint equality for f_2 function comes out to be:

$$0.1 < f_2 < 0.7 \quad (13)$$

IV. DATASET

The dataset for the refractive index of various perovskite oxides is created using an empirical relation between the spatial energy parameter, pseudo lattice constant, and the refractive index of the perovskite oxide. The spatial energy parameter depends on the polarization ability of the elements and the refractive index of the compound. Further, the polarization ability of a perovskite oxide is affected by all its compositional elements. Hence, the effective spatial energy is the sum of the individual polarization energy. The refractive index can be empirically calculated from the effective spatial energy and the lattice constant of the compound as follows:

$$n_2 = n \times \left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right) \quad (14)$$

The lattice constant of the perovskite oxide is taken from [19] and the polarization energy parameter from [18]. P_{Ea}, P_{Eb}, P_{EO} represent the polarization energy parameter in eV of cations A and B and oxygen as anion respectively. ΣP_E is the effective spatial energy parameter, r_0 is the pseudo cubic lattice constant in Å and n is the calculated refractive index. Table I provides the above parameters for different perovskite compounds.

V. OPTIMIZATION-MULTI OBJECTIVE PSO

In the current study, multi-objective optimization is used for optimizing the step gradient for the refractive index value of the microwave absorber composite. In the presented model f_1 is minimized, while f_2 is optimized using the equality constraint. For carrying out the optimization, the object oriented framework is used involving the NSGA-II evolutionary algorithm. NSGA-II has the advantage of providing fast computations and a non-dominated solution set. It is one of the most popularly used GAs which uses the fitness value or the rank of an individual along with the assigned crowded distance to sort out individuals from consecutive generations. It uses the binary crossover operator for mutation and offspring generation. The algorithmic parameters used in the current study are an initial population of 50, 10 offspring in each generation, and termination at the 40th generation. The algorithm is repeated for an initial refractive index range of 1.6 to 2.3. The coding was executed using python in a PC with Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8265U (CPU 1.60GHz) processor with 8GB RAM.

VI. RESULTS

Using the step gradient value and the refractive index value of the top layer, the refractive indices for each layer can be determined as shown above. Suitable compounds as per the calculated values, having the same refractive index value, are picked from Table I. Table II shows the step gradient value obtained for each refractive index value along with possible multi-layer combinations matched from the data in Table I.

TABLE I. SPATIAL ENERGY PARAMETER AND REFRACTIVE INDICES OF VARIOUS PEROVSKITE OXIDES

Compound	P_{Ea}	P_{Eb}	P_{Eo}	r_o	ΣP_F	n
BaFeO ₃	0.271	1.285	6.287	4.102	7.843	1.91
BaMoO ₃	0.271	0.619	6.287	4.177	7.177	1.72
BaNbO ₃	0.271	0.562	6.287	4.212	7.12	1.69
BaSnO ₃	0.271	1.393	6.287	4.223	7.951	1.88
BaHO ₃	0.271	6.728	6.287	4.246	13.286	3.13
BaZrO ₃	0.271	0.507	6.287	4.258	7.065	1.66
BaIrO ₃	0.271	10.411	6.287	4.148	16.969	4.09
BaPbO ₃	0.271	0.867	6.287	4.322	7.425	1.72
BaTbO ₃	0.271	2.848	6.287	4.304	9.406	2.19
BaPrO ₃	0.271	0.82	6.287	4.408	7.378	1.67
BaCeO ₃	0.271	0.607	6.287	4.432	7.165	1.62
BaTiO ₃	0.271	0.889	6.287	4.125	7.447	1.81
BaRuO ₃	0.271	0.743	6.287	4.42	7.301	1.65
SrMnO ₃	0.413	1.174	6.287	3.841	7.874	2.05
SrVO ₃	0.413	0.966	6.287	3.899	7.666	1.97
SrFeO ₃	0.413	1.285	6.287	3.905	7.985	2.04
SrTiO ₃	0.413	0.889	6.287	3.928	7.589	1.93
SrTcO ₃	0.413	0.679	6.287	3.975	7.379	1.86
SrMoO ₃	0.413	0.619	6.287	3.98	7.319	1.84
SrNbO ₃	0.413	0.562	6.287	4.015	7.262	1.81
SrSnO ₃	0.413	1.393	6.287	4.027	8.093	2.01
SrHfO ₃	0.413	6.728	6.287	4.05	13.428	3.32
SrTbO ₃	0.413	2.848	6.287	4.108	9.548	2.32
SrCoO ₃	0.413	1.402	6.287	3.841	8.102	2.11
SrZrO ₃	0.413	0.501	6.287	4.061	7.201	1.77
SrRuO ₃	0.413	0.743	6.287	4.015	7.443	1.85
CaVO ₃	0.727	0.966	6.287	3.784	7.98	2.11
CaZrO ₃	0.727	6.728	6.287	3.934	13.742	3.49
CaHfO ₃	0.727	0.507	6.287	3.946	7.521	1.91
CaRuO ₃	0.727	0.743	6.287	3.899	7.757	1.99
CaSnO ₃	0.727	1.393	6.287	3.911	8.407	2.15
CaTiO ₃	0.727	0.889	6.287	3.813	7.903	2.07
EuTiO ₃	2.036	0.889	6.287	3.801	9.212	2.42
EuAlO ₃	2.036	1.767	6.287	3.643	10.09	2.77
EuCrO ₃	2.036	1.067	6.287	3.736	9.39	2.51
EuFeO ₃	2.036	1.285	6.287	3.771	9.608	2.55
EuGaO ₃	2.036	1.821	6.287	3.742	10.144	2.71
EuInO ₃	2.036	1.062	6.287	3.593	9.385	2.61
CeAlO ₃	0.607	1.767	6.287	3.771	8.661	2.3
GdAlO ₃	2.426	1.767	6.287	3.631	10.48	2.89
GdCrO ₃	2.426	1.067	6.287	3.725	9.78	2.63
GdFeO ₃	2.426	1.285	6.287	3.76	9.998	2.66
LaAlO ₃	0.418	1.767	6.287	3.795	8.472	2.23
LaCrO ₃	0.418	1.067	6.287	3.888	7.772	2
LaFeO ₃	0.418	1.285	6.287	3.923	7.99	2.04
LaGaO ₃	0.418	1.821	6.287	3.894	8.526	2.19
LaRhO ₃	0.418	0.799	6.287	3.947	7.504	1.9
LaTiO ₃	0.418	0.889	6.287	3.953	7.594	1.92
LaVO ₃	0.418	0.966	6.287	3.917	7.671	1.96
LaInO ₃	0.418	1.062	6.287	4.105	7.767	1.89
NdAlO ₃	1.074	1.767	6.287	3.689	9.128	2.47
NdGaO ₃	1.074	1.821	6.287	3.789	9.182	2.42
NdInO ₃	1.074	1.062	6.287	3.999	8.423	2.11
NdCoO ₃	1.074	1.402	6.287	3.701	8.763	2.37
NdCrO ₃	1.074	1.067	6.287	3.783	8.428	2.23
NdFeO ₃	1.074	1.285	6.287	3.818	8.646	2.26
NdMnO ₃	1.074	1.174	6.287	3.818	8.535	2.24
PrAlO ₃	0.82	1.767	6.287	3.725	8.874	2.38
PrCrO ₃	0.82	1.067	6.287	3.818	8.174	2.14
PrFeO ₃	0.82	1.285	6.287	3.853	8.392	2.18
PrGaO ₃	0.82	1.821	6.287	3.824	8.928	2.33
PrMnO ₃	0.82	1.174	6.287	3.853	8.281	2.15
PrVO ₃	0.82	0.966	6.287	3.847	8.073	2.1
SmAlO ₃	1.681	1.767	6.287	3.654	9.735	2.66

SmCoO ₃	1.681	1.402	6.287	3.666	9.37	2.56
SmVO ₃	1.681	0.966	6.287	3.777	8.934	2.37
SmFeO ₃	1.681	1.285	6.287	3.783	9.253	2.45
YAlO ₃	0.455	1.767	6.287	3.608	8.509	2.36
YCrO ₃	0.455	1.067	6.287	3.701	7.809	2.11
YFeO ₃	0.455	1.285	6.287	3.736	8.027	2.15

TABLE II. SUGGESTED COMPOUND LAYERS AS PER THE OBTAINED STEP GRADIENT VALUES

Refractive index n	Step gradient value z	Suggested compound layers		
1.6	2.9	BaCeO ₃	CaHfO ₃	BaHfO ₃
1.7	2.8	BaPbO ₃	EuTiO ₃	SrHfO ₃
1.8	2.6	SrNbO ₃	SrTbO ₃	GdAlO ₃
1.9	2.5	SrTiO ₃	NdGaO ₃	GdAlO ₃
2	2.3	LaCrO ₃	CeAlO ₃	GdCrO ₃
2.1	2.2	CaVO ₃	CeAlO ₃	EuFeO ₃
2.2	2.1	LaAlO ₃	PrGaO ₃	SmVO ₃
2.3	2	SrTO ₃	PrGaO ₃	CeAlO ₃

VII. CONCLUSION

The present work emphasizes on the importance of the use of materials' intrinsic electromagnetic properties in the designing of multilayer microwave absorbers. The provided theoretical framework gives a picture of the way the internal phenomenon of absorption and dissipation in absorbers can affect the output performance parameters. This understanding helps in building mathematical relations and functions which serve as building blocks to advanced computation procedures such as the used optimization. Moreover, the provided database from which perovskite compounds can be selected based on their refractive indices gives a wide range of options for designing and using unconventional combinations of materials as absorbers. The simplistic approach provided here can give more flexibility in the analysis of multilayer microwave absorbers.

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A Stochastic Simulator of a Multi-Component Distillation Tower Built as an Excel Macro

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic process simulation is widely used in teaching controller design, as it allows foreseeing the performance of different control configurations and controller tunings. Currently, most college-level controller design exercises that are based on simulation consider deterministic perturbations (i.e. steps or ramps). In real life however, processes are more likely to face fluctuating, random disturbances, so the use of stochastic simulation in controller tuning exercises would provide students with an experience closer to their future professional practice than that provided by deterministic simulation. However, public institutions attempting to use dynamic, stochastic simulators in teaching, are hindered by the need of buying licenses of simulation packages or specialized programming languages (such as Matlab), as there aren't any dynamic, stochastic simulators available as downloadable freeware. This paper shows a dynamic, stochastic simulator with a friendly interface of a distillation tower, developed as an Excel macro. This simulator has the advantage that it can be used at no cost to educational institutions since Excel is almost universally known and used by college faculties.

Keywords-simulation; stochastic; distillation

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic simulators are very useful in the teaching of process control in college engineering, as they can be used to compare the performance of different control configurations (i.e. the linking of controlled and manipulated variables) and to optimize the tuning of controllers. However, almost all simulation-based learning experiences of control design use deterministic disturbances (e.g. ramp or step changes) to dynamically assess the candidate controller configurations or tunings [1]. In practice, however, process units are subjected to disturbances that are better described as stochastic, varying continuously and in an unpredictable manner. Therefore, the engineering trainee would benefit from performing process control practices including stochastic disturbances. To carry out the said activities however, dynamic process simulators able to incorporate random elements (i.e. stochastic dynamic simulators) are needed. On the other hand, public institutions of higher education in developing countries are facing severe shortages of economic resources. This hinders their ability to

use process simulators in their teaching activities, due to the need of purchasing user licenses. In the case of steady-state simulators, there are a few free software alternatives that have been sufficiently validated (e.g. the COCO simulator [2]), however, this is not the case of dynamic simulators and certainly not of the subset of these able to handle random disturbances. This paper presents the development of a dynamic three-component distillation tower simulator with stochastic elements and a user-friendly interface (allowing user interaction via buttons and dialog boxes) created using Microsoft Excel macro functionalities. This allows the simulator to be run in said software, that is already being used by most developing countries college engineering faculties.

A. Literature Review

Reviews of dynamic simulation applications for optimizing energy and chemical systems are shown in [3, 4], while applications of discrete event simulation to the optimization of industrial systems can be found in [4-6]. Usage of simulation in

specific situations are presented in [7] for sustainable plant design, in [8] for gasifier pressure modeling, and in [9] for analyzing a petrochemical process wastewater plant. Additional applications include treating a desalination plant [10], optimizing the drying of phosphates [11], analyzing the benzene-toluene-xylene separation train from a sustainable point of view [12].

Regarding the software used for the dynamic simulations, Aspen Dynamics and Matlab have been used for studying separation tower trains [13], ChemCAD for modeling polymerization reactors [14], Aspen HYSIS for treating energy-integrated reactors [15], and Matlab and COSMOL Multiphysics for studying catalysts [16]. Additionally, authors in [17] present a proposal for controlling combustion cycles using Aspen Dynamics, authors in [18] simulated a wastewater system using INSEL (Integrated Simulation Environment Language), and authors in [19] modeled a set of CO₂ absorbers for implementing a predictive control scheme, employing ASPEN and Matlab.

Experiences on the didactic use of chemical process simulators are included in [20], where Aspen HYSIS was used for training engineers in the handling of distillation trains and in [21] where Honeywell Unisim Design was used in training operators of an isopropanol plant. Regarding the reports on the development of home-grown process simulators in educational institutions for pedagogical purposes, authors in [22] describe the steady state simulator Lazarus, run in UML and developed as a freeware with the option of incorporating modules from third parties, authors in [23, 24] developed programs to study the dynamics of heat exchanger networks, authors in [25] provided a web-based natural gas distribution system simulator, authors in [26] described the LABVIRTUAL learning platform which includes steady-state simulators, and authors in [27] presented a dynamic reactor simulator programmed in Matlab.

It can be noted that there is a growing preference for using commercial simulation software (e.g. ASPEN) and programming languages with pre-built routines for model construction (e.g. Matlab) in reported research and pedagogical simulation applications. Since both types of software require paid licenses, the reported applications are of little relevance to the teaching in public institutions which strive to optimize the spending of their limited budgets. In contrast, the simulator presented in this paper is programmed in Microsoft Excel. This program, even though not being freeware, is widely available to college staff as it comes with the MS Office packages purchased by institutions for word processing and administrative tasks. Additionally, none of the reported dynamic simulators built for teaching applications incorporates random disturbances. As in practice, process plant operation is affected by random disturbances, using stochastic dynamic simulators in teaching activities related to controller design and tuning, can better prepare the future engineer for operating real plants.

II. CASE STUDY DESCRIPTION

A ten-plate distillation tower fed with a mixture of benzene, toluene and p-xylene is taken as a case study (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Distillation tower case study.

V_R and V_S are, respectively, the molar vapor flow in the rectifying and stripping tower sections, with L_R and L_S being the corresponding liquid molar flows. F , D and B are, respectively, the molar flow of feed, distillate, and bottom product, and q is the feed vapor fraction. The feed mole fraction of component i is $x_{i,F}$ ($i=1,\dots,3$). x_{ij} and y_{ij} denote, respectively, the mole fraction of component i in the liquid and vapor leaving the plates and the reboiler ($j=1,\dots,10,R$). The dynamic model used the following assumptions:

- The molar flows of vapor and liquid in the stripping and rectifying sections are constant.
- The plate (m) and the reboiler (m_R) holdups are constant.
- The mole fractions of the liquid and vapor in equilibrium follow Raoult's law (1):

$$P y_{ij} = P_i^0(T_j) x_{ij} \quad i=1,\dots,3, \quad j=1,\dots,10,R \quad (1)$$

where P is the tower pressure and $P_i^0(T_j)$ the vapor pressure of component i at the temperature T_j of stage j ($j=1,\dots,10,R$). Vapor pressures follow Antoine's relation (2) with A_i , B_i and C_i being component specific constants:

$$P_i^0 = \exp\left(A_i - \frac{B_i}{T_j + C_i}\right) \quad (2)$$

- The tower hydraulics are very fast, with the internal and external flows adjusting to changes in F , q , V_S and r , which is the reflux ratio (L_R/D), according to:

$$V_R = V_S + qF \quad (3)$$

$$D = \frac{V_R}{(1+r)} \quad (4)$$

$$B = F - D \quad (5)$$

$$L_S = V_S + B \tag{6}$$

$$L_R = D r \tag{7}$$

- The mole fractions of the components in the feed $x_{i,F}$ ($i=1, \dots, 3$), may fluctuate randomly.

Mole fractions add to one, so the dynamic model consists of two molar balances for each stage, resulting in 22 ordinary differential equations, i.e. (8)-(13), for $i=1, 2$.

Plate 1:

$$\frac{dx_{i,1}}{dt} = \frac{L_R(y_{i,1} - x_{i,1}) + V_R(y_{i,2} - y_{i,1})}{m} \tag{8}$$

Plate in the rectifying section $j=2, 3, 4$:

$$\frac{dx_{i,j}}{dt} = \frac{L_R(x_{i,j-1} - x_{i,j}) + V_R(y_{i,j+1} - y_{i,j})}{m} \tag{9}$$

Feed plate:

$$\frac{dx_{i,5}}{dt} = \frac{F x_{i,F} + V_S y_{i,6} + L_R x_{i,4} - V_R y_{i,5} - L_S x_{i,5}}{m} \tag{10}$$

Plate in the stripping section $j=6, \dots, 9$:

$$\frac{dx_{i,j}}{dt} = \frac{L_S(x_{i,j-1} - x_{i,j}) + V_S(y_{i,j+1} - y_{i,j})}{m} \tag{11}$$

Plate 10:

$$\frac{dx_{i,10}}{dt} = \frac{L_S(x_{i,9} - x_{i,10}) + V_S(y_{i,R} - y_{i,10})}{m} \tag{12}$$

Reboiler:

$$\frac{dx_{i,R}}{dt} = \frac{L_S x_{i,10} - B x_{i,R} - V_S y_{i,R}}{m_R} \tag{13}$$

Equations (8)-(13) are integrated using an implicit Euler method: Defining a state vector $\mathbf{X} = [x_{1,1}, x_{2,1}, \dots, x_{1,R}, x_{2,R}]^T$, a disturbance vector $\mathbf{D} = [F, q, x_{1,F}, x_{2,F}]^T$, and a manipulated variables vector $\mathbf{U} = [r, V_S]^T$, the value of \mathbf{X} at time $t+h$, is obtained from its value at time t by solving the system of nonlinear equations (14), h being is the step size.

$$\mathbf{X}(t+h) = \mathbf{X}(t) + \frac{d\mathbf{X}}{dt} \Big|_{(\mathbf{X}(t+h), \mathbf{D}(t), \mathbf{U}(t))} h \tag{14}$$

Fig. 2. Main simulator interface.

For simulating a tower with stochastic feed mole fractions, $x_{1,f}(t)$ and $x_{2,f}(t)$ are sampled from their probability distributions (using the methods described in [28]) and are substituted in (14) before solving these equations to calculate $\mathbf{X}(t+h)$. When running a controlled tower, an integral proportional logic (15) changes the reflux ratio r to control the temperature of a given plate in the rectifying section:

$$r = r_0 + K_C \left(e + \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^t e dt \right) \quad (15)$$

where e is the deviation of the controlled plate temperature from its set-point, K_C is the gain of the controller, τ is its reset time, and r_0 the initial value of the reflux ratio.

III. SIMULATOR DESCRIPTION

The simulator is given to the user as a macro-enabled Microsoft Excel file. By clicking the "Begin Simulation/Show Interface" button (Figure 3) the main simulator interface is displayed (Figure 4). The program works in desktop Excel versions supporting visual-basic macros, i.e. those in MS Office versions from 2010 onwards.

Fig. 3. Initial screen when the Excel file is opened.

Fig. 4. Detail of the controls in the steady state interface section.

Fig. 5. Controls for specifying the inlet composition behavior.

Fig. 6. Controls for defining the reflux ratio policy

Initially, only the controls in the "Initial steady state calculation" zone appear active (Figure 4). Through these controls, the user specifies the steady-state condition the tower is in before the dynamic simulation starts. Once the qualities of the feed, reflux ratio, and reboiler boil-up (V_3) have been entered, by clicking the "Calculate steady state" button the initial steady state of the system is calculated. The total error achieved in solving the steady state problem (that is formed by making the derivatives in (8)-(13) equal to zero) appears in the corresponding dialog box. The steady-state composition of the liquid in the plates and the flowrate and compositions of the outlet streams appear in the boxes placed on the plates and close to the outlets of the sketched tower (Figure 2). Once the steady-state solution has been achieved, the buttons associated with the dynamic simulation become active.

The feed flowrate and vaporization and total simulation time are entered in the dialog boxes located to the left of the tower in Figure 2. The probability distributions of the feed mole fractions, which are to be varying randomly, are defined through the controls in the section "Inlet composition behavior" of the interface (Figure 5).

The control ratio to the left in Figure 5 allows selecting how the behavior of the feed mole fractions of benzene and toluene is going to be. These mole fractions can remain constant or follow a probability distribution: uniform (specifying minimum and maximum values), normal (specifying mean and standard deviation), or triangular (specifying minimum, most likely and maximum values). The sampled feed mole fractions are standardized in case their sum exceeds unity and, as can happen when sampling from a normal distribution, if the simulated value is either negative or greater than 1, new values are produced until they lie in the required (0,1) range.

Figure 6 shows the interface section in which the reflux ratio management is defined. It can be set constant (by choosing "manual" and selecting its value) or used to keep the temperature of a rectifying plate close to its temperature at the initial steady state. The controller specifications are also entered here. The total absolute deviation (i.e. the absolute value of the deviation integrated along the simulated time) of the fraction mole of benzene in the distillate, with respect to its steady state value, is displayed in the relevant text box.

Once the simulation is complete, a dialog box asks the user if graphs of the simulation results are to be produced. If "yes" is answered, graphs of the controlled plate temperature and the mole fraction of benzene in distillate against time are displayed. These graphs are produced using the Excel spreadsheet functionalities, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Example of charts produced by the simulator.

To illustrate the simulator results, the top chart of Figure 8 shows the behavior of plate one temperature when the feed mole fractions of benzene and toluene are uniformly distributed between 0.1667 and 0.5.

Fig. 8. Closed loop vs. manual operation contrast

Responses for a constant reflux ratio set to its steady state value, and for a manipulated reflux ratio controlling plate one temperature, with controller gain of 20 and reset time of 0.1h, are included. The bottom chart of Figure 8 shows the

corresponding behavior of the distillate mole fraction of benzene. The total absolute deviation of the distillate benzene mole fraction for the closed loop case is 0.0672, while that for the fixed reflux ratio case is 0.21.

It is easy to visualize the usage of this simulator for training students in controller design under stochastic conditions, through exercises in which they need to tune the controller and select controlled plates so to minimize the benzene distillate composition deviation, and asking them to discuss the effect of the feed composition behavior on the results.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

As there is a lack of freeware dynamic simulators, educational institutions seeking to use them in teaching must purchase licenses. This situation is exacerbated for dynamic simulators capable of including stochastic disturbances, as these are more specialized and have more expensive licenses than deterministic simulators. As in practice engineers need to control plants facing unpredictable, continuously varying disturbances, implementing process control exercises for engineering students using simulated stochastic disturbances can be a valuable preparation for their future practice.

In this paper, a stochastic simulator intended for this purpose is presented. As the simulator runs in Microsoft Excel, that is already used in most engineering colleges, no specific license software is needed for its pedagogical use. A limitation of the simulator, however, is that it only runs in desktop Excel versions. It wouldn't run in Libre or OpenOffice, GoogleSheets, or web-based Excel, as these do not support visual basic macros. It is expected that the work presented here encourages engineering faculties to develop their own simulators.

The interested reader can download the simulator at [29]. The users are encouraged to report any bugs to the corresponding author email address.

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Adaptive Dynamic Cutting Force Control Analysis for Peripheral Milling

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ABSTRACT

The implementation of condition monitoring tools can improve plant availability and lower downtime costs in general. A reliable adaptive control system can prevent machine downtime or undesired situations such as chatter vibration and excessive tool wear, permitting the best utilization of a tool's life. This study used dynamic force analysis to create an adaptive dynamic control system for Computer Numerical Control (CNC) milling to adjust a controlled system for signals from offline measurements that will be processed and supplied back to the machine tool controller to correct cutting parameters. This paper describes a better adaptive control system for peripheral milling with helical end mills based on a dynamic cutting force model. This theoretical model is based on the oblique cutting principle and takes into account the effects of the size of undeformed chip thickness and the effective rake angle. Simulation results showed that the enhanced dynamic cutting-force model accurately predicted cutting forces in peripheral milling.

Keywords-machining process; adaptive control; dynamic force analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Peripheral milling operations are widely used in automobile, aerospace, textile machinery, and other manufacturing industries where 2D contour parts, i.e. engine components, cams, etc., are milled using complex end-mills. In recent years, due to the need to improve the dimensional accuracy of the parts, there is a push towards the reduction of the machining errors commonly generated in the milling process. These errors derive from machine tools, cutters, NC programming, and the machining process itself. The errors of the machining process generated in peripheral milling originate from several sources, such as tool deflection, workpiece deflection, tool wear, friction, tool run-out, and chatter vibration. Of all these, tool deflection due to cutting force is a major problem for precision machining [1]. An accurate dynamic cutting-force model is vital for the precise prediction of tool and workpiece deflection in peripheral milling. Several models based on theoretical assumptions and experimental

observations have been developed to predict cutting forces [2]. In [3, 4], an investigation was presented for a tool condition monitoring system which consisted of a fast Fourier transform preprocessor for generating features from online Acousto-Optic Emission (AOE) signals to develop a database for appropriate decisions. The drawback of modern Computer Numerical Control (CNC) systems is that the machining parameters, such as feed rate, speed, and depth of cut, are programmed offline [5]. As a result, many CNC systems are inefficient to operate under operating conditions that are far from optimal. To ensure the quality of machining products, reduce machining costs, and increase machining efficiency, it is necessary to adjust the machining parameters in real-time to satisfy the optimal machining conditions at any given time as per modern condition monitoring strategies [6, 7]. The control of CNC machining processes is presently receiving significant attention due to the potential economic benefits associated with automated machining. Control techniques that have been developed for machining traditionally require some form of

parameter adaptation, and the solution to this problem is adaptive control. An adaptive control system was introduced to the cutting process in [8].

The most commonly used systems are Model Reference Adaptive Control (MRAC) and Self-Turning Regulations (STR). In [9], an investigation was presented on an adaptive model reference controller approach, simulating, evaluating, and physically implementing it. Continuous monitoring of the machining is necessary for effective automatization where the process takes place without human interference. Most frequently, it is materialized by measuring the cutting forces because they contain more information about the process and the tool condition [10-12]. Despite the initial difficulties in development, a trend towards equipping the CNC machine with modern adaptive systems can be observed [13-15]. The most commonly used Adaptive Control (AC) systems use Adaptive Control Constraint (ACC), with the constraints being the cutting force, displacement due to vibration, spindle deflection, current, and cutting torque. Operating parameters are usually the feed rate, depth of cut, and spindle speed. This study implemented an online adaptive control in conjunction with offline optimization. In this AC system, the feed rate and depth of cut are adjusted online to maintain a constant displacement and cutting force despite variations in cutting conditions.

The modern market forces producers to meet the demands of customers, but the accelerating technological progress still makes this goal very difficult to achieve. The manufacturer must provide a product that meets customers' expectations while maintaining a satisfactory price on both sides. Manufacturing costs have a key influence on the final price of the product, so it is very important to develop new methods to estimate the manufacturing cost and improve the existing ones. This paper presents an improved dynamic cutting-force model for peripheral milling with helical end mills. The theoretical model was based on the oblique cutting principle and included the size effect of undeformed chip thickness and the influence of the effective rake angle.

II. FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES

Two basic models are normally used to describe chip formation in metal cutting:

- Orthogonal cutting, characterized by a normal cutting edge and a chip flow parallel to the direction of tool motion.
- Oblique cutting, characterized by a cutting face inclined by an angle.

A. Geometric Model of Helical End-Mill

The end mill can be divided into a number of slices along its z-direction, as shown in Figure 1 of [16]. Within each slice, the cutting action for an individual tooth can be modeled as for single-point oblique cutting, and the tangential and normal cutting forces at any point on the rake face can be obtained from the oblique cutting model. It is important to note that the tangential and normal directions together with chip thickness vary during the formation of a single chip in milling. Consequently, a dynamic model must account for these variations in the magnitude and direction of cutting forces.

B. Cutting-Force Model

The cutting forces acting on the helical flute's rake face depend on the undeformed chip thickness. If dl is a portion of the developed cutting edge of elemental length, then dz may be considered as the width of an elemental oblique tool with inclination angle β [16]:

$$dz = dl \cdot \cos \beta \quad (1)$$

and the differential area of the undeformed chip cross-section:

$$\begin{cases} dA_y(\varphi_i) = t_i(\varphi_i) dz = t_i(\varphi_i) dl \cdot \cos \beta \\ dl = R d\varphi / \sin \beta \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $t_i(\varphi_i)$ is the undeformed chip thickness. The differential tangential cutting force of the peripheral milling, as can be seen in Figure 1 of [16]:

$$dF_{ti}(\varphi_i) = K_s dA_y(\varphi_i) = K_s t_i(\varphi_i) R \cot \beta d\varphi \quad (3)$$

where K_s is the tangential cutting-force coefficient, which has the same meaning as the total energy per unit volume u . Considering the size effect of undeformed chip thickness and the influence of effective rake angle gives:

$$K_s = u_0 \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_e - \alpha_{e0}}{100} \right) \left(\frac{t_0}{t_i(\varphi_i)} \right)^{0.2} \quad (4)$$

where u_0 is the initial total cutting energy per unit volume, α_e (in degrees) is the effective rake face, α_{e0} (in degrees) is the initial effective rake angle, and t_0 is the initial undeformed chip thickness. To develop the total force applied on the whole cutter, the differential forces are resolved into the feed (y) and normal (x) directions. The differential cutting-force components are just opposite to the corresponding directions of the curvilinear coordinate system (t, r, a).

1) For Down-Milling

$$\begin{cases} F_{ix} \approx -u' f_t R \cot \beta (0.5\varphi_i - 0.25 \sin 2\varphi_i \\ \quad + 0.5556 \cdot c \cdot \sin^{1.8} \varphi_i) \Big|_{\varphi_s}^{\varphi_e} \\ F_{iy} \approx u' f_t R \cot \beta (0.5556 \sin^{1.8} \varphi_i - 0.5\varphi_i \\ \quad + 0.25 \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\varphi_i) \Big|_{\varphi_s}^{\varphi_e} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Because:

$$0 \leq \varphi \leq \psi, \quad \varphi_i = \varphi - \omega t + (i-1)(2\pi/m) \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq \varphi_i \leq \Omega$$

$$\varphi_s = \max \left(0, -\omega t + (i-1) \frac{2\pi}{m} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\varphi_e = \min \left(\Omega, \psi - \omega t + (i-1) \frac{2\pi}{m} \right) \quad (7)$$

2) For Up-Milling:

$$\begin{cases} F_{ix} \approx -u' f_t R \cot \beta (0.5\xi_i - 0.25 \sin 2\xi_i \\ \quad - 0.5556 \cdot c \cdot \sin^{1.8} \xi_i) \Big|_{\xi_s}^{\xi_e} \\ F_{iy} \approx -u' f_t R \cot \beta (0.5556 \sin^{1.8} \xi_i + 0.5\xi_i \\ \quad - 0.25 \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\xi_i) \Big|_{\xi_s}^{\xi_e} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Also:

$$0 \leq \varphi \leq \psi, \quad \xi_i = -\varphi + \omega t - (i-1)(2\pi/m) \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq \xi_i \leq \Omega$$

gives the extreme values of the parametric angle ξ_i as:

$$\xi_s = \max\left(0, -\psi + \omega t - (i-1)\frac{2\pi}{m}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$\xi_e = \min\left(\Omega, \omega t - (i-1)\frac{2\pi}{m}\right) \quad (10)$$

Summing up the cutting forces acting on all the m helical flutes gives the total force applied on the whole cutter:

$$\begin{cases} F_x = \sum_{i=1}^m F_{ix} \\ F_y = \sum_{i=1}^m F_{iy} \end{cases}$$

III. ESTIMATION OF CUTTING-FORCE COEFFICIENTS

The cutter, workpiece material, and cutting conditions of this study were:

- Cutter: a single-fluted carbide end-mill with a helix angle $\beta=30^\circ$, a rake angle $\alpha_r=12^\circ$ and a diameter of 19.06mm.
- Material properties of the carbide cutter: 90% WC, 10% Co, hardness 92 Rockwell.
- Material properties of the titanium alloy: 6% Al, 4% V, Young's modulus=110GPa, Poisson's ratio=0.34, tensile strength=900Mpa.
- Cutting parameters: axial depth of cut $b_a=7.62$ mm, radial depth of cut $d=19.06$ mm (slotting), $\psi=26.45^\circ$, $\Omega=\pi$, spindle rotation speed $n=500$ rpm (cutting speed $V=498.99$ mm.s⁻¹), with a feed rate ranging from 0.0127mm per tooth to 0.2030mm per tooth.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the simulation results in Matlab for a number of particular examples. Figure 1 shows the results of predicting cutting forces for a full immersion up-milling, revealing that when the feed rate is far smaller than the radius of the cutting edge, the ploughing force is dominant and the cutting-force model must be modified.

Figures 2 and 3 show the results on the influence of the cutting angles, feed per tooth, and cutter radius on the cutting force. The values of the instantaneous predicted forces were found as shown in Figure 2 but with different amplitudes. Adjusting the initial total cutting energy per unit of volume and the cutting-force ratio to $u_0=2.109$ Jm⁻³, $c=0.45$, the instantaneous predicted forces were obtained, as shown in Figure 3. A comparison of these results with the cutting forces shown in Figure 1 shows that there is a very good agreement. Figure 3 shows that when the feed rate is greater than 0.0254mm per tooth, the predicted cutting forces are very good approximations of the measured cutting forces, and the improved dynamic cutting-force model can be used to predict the cutting forces. However, when the feed rate is less than 0.0254mm per tooth, the predicted cutting forces are smaller than the measured. This reveals that when the feed rate is far smaller than the radius of the cutting edge, the ploughing force is dominant and the cutting-force model must be modified.

V. CONCLUSION

The adaptive dynamic cutting force control analysis estimation process in manufacturing is a very important stage

of the design construction process, as the decisions made at this stage have a large impact on the product's final price. This study presented a manufacturing adaptive dynamic cutting force control analysis estimation method based on dynamic force analysis. The quality of this method depends on the exponent values. The standard values of exponents are known and described in many publications. These values were compared to values calculated based on a practical simulation of the manufacturing process. The differences between standard and calculated values can be observed. The standard values assigned to the operation should give proper results for every kind of cut type, e.g. rough and finish. Values based on simulation results from real situations are specified for every type of cutting process. This approach can improve the results accuracy of the proposed method based on cost similarity, and finally, this method could help in securing the economic profit of the company.

Fig. 1. Predicted cutting forces for a full immersion up-milling test, $m = 1$, $u_0 = 3.51 \times 10^9$ Jm⁻³, $\alpha_r = 12^\circ$, $b_a = 7.62$ mm, $d = 19.06$ mm, $\psi = 26.45^\circ$.

This study investigated the size effect of undeformed chip thickness and the influence of the effective rake angle in peripheral milling. Verification results showed that the model is suitable for general peripheral milling when the feed rate is greater than the radius of the cutting edge. For fine milling, when the feed rate is less than the radius of the cutting edge, the measured cutting force will be greater than the cutting force predicted by the model. This result shows that the ploughing force is dominant in this condition and the general cutting force model is no longer effective. Case studies reveal that the model may be very effective in reducing the surface form error due to tool deflection if flute number, axial depth of cut, and radial depth of cut are selected carefully.

Fig. 3. Influence of F_t ($m=1$)

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Electrical Behavior of Lanthanum Aluminate (LAO) and Gadolinium Doped Ceria (GDG) Composite Electrolyte for Electrochemical Devices

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ABSTRACT

The LAO-GDC solid composite electrolyte has been proposed for use in Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC). The material conductivity of Solid Carbonate-Ceria (SCC) composite electrolytes is 0.04Scm^{-1} between 400 and 700°C. For this purpose, mixtures of LaAlO_3 (LAO) and gadolinium doped ceria $\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{Gd}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (GDC) were created in weight ratios of 3:1, 2:2, and 1:3. The composite electrolyte material was studied separately to improve conductivity. The phase structure and microstructure were studied using an X-Ray Diffractometer (XRD) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and the electrical behavior was investigated using Impedance Spectroscopy (IS). The SEM and Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) demonstrated a compact structure with an acceptable atomic percentage of constituent elements and a uniform grain distribution. Experimental investigation showed that this composite electrolyte had a high density of LaAlO_3 (LAO)- $\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{Gd}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (GDC) composites and an approximate 97% density of its theoretical. The electrical behavior of LAO-GDC composites had the highest value of 0.1Scm^{-1} at 700°C, which is more extreme than the individual conductivities of LAO and GDC, according to Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) techniques. Among the three composite ratios of the system, only the weight ratio of 3:1 had better conductivity. The LaAlO_3 (LAO)- $\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{Gd}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (GDC) composite material has a higher activation energy of 1.5eV.

Keywords-X-Ray Diffractometer (XRD); lanthanum aluminate (LAO); solid electrolyte; electrical conductivity; solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs)

I. INTRODUCTION

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) have attracted a lot of attention due to their environmental friendliness, low cost, and lack of possible safety risks [1, 2]. Fuel cell electrolytes are the primary focus of research, since they are the base component of SOFCs. ZrO_2 , CeO_2 , Bi_2O_3 , LaGaO_3 , and rare earth zirconates are the most widely used solid oxide electrolytes for SOFCs, with Y_2O_3 stabilized ZrO_2 being the most prominent [2-6]. To achieve high electrical conductivity, YSZ requires a high operating temperature of nearly 1000°C. The high operating temperature does not alone pose a significant challenge in terms of electrode selection, however, the cost of materials will rise as a result [4, 7]. The ionic conductivity of YSZ is lower at low temperatures than that of ceria-based electrolytes such as Gadolinium-Doped Ceria (GDC) [8-11]. The conductivity order of both SDC and GDC is around 10^{-2}Scm^{-1} at 750°C, which is comparatively higher than that of stabilized zirconia [12-13]. The closest ionic radius of Gd^{3+} and Ce^{4+} may cause

the highest electrical conductivity of GDC [14-15]. In terms of price, processing, and quality, ceria-based electrolytes have been evaluated as a low-temperature alternative. In SOFCs, LaAlO_3 may be a good alternative perovskite candidate for the oxide ions conductor (electrolyte) [16-18]. However, in an oxidizing environment, pure LaAlO_3 has lower ionic conductivity and more flexible conduction behavior [19]. The ionic conductivity of electrolytes can be best used through composition change by choosing a suitable aliovalent dopant and its optimum concentration [20]. Doping may be uniform or nonuniform depending on whether to form a solid mixture or a composite [21].

This study focused on a composite material as an electrolyte. In general, composite electrolytes are made up of two phases: one that contains regular oxygen ionic conductors and another that contains inorganic salts or oxides. As a result, LAO-GDG is an effective novel electrolyte with a relatively high ionic conductivity at low temperatures [2, 22]. Due to

their high oxygen ion conductivities, doped ceria and lanthanum gallate are investigated as potential ion conductor materials for LT-SOFCs [23-24]. A combination of lanthanum aluminate (LAO) and GDC was recently proposed as a low-cost electrolyte for SOFCs with significantly improved conductivity. In intermediate/low-temperature SOFCs, composite electrolyte materials have been extensively studied for their excellent consistency, electrical conductivity, and thermophysical properties [25-28]. As LAO has a perovskite structure and GDC has a cubic fluorite structure, their combination, perovskite-fluorite, is a great oxide-ion conductor. The GDC-based composite electrolyte material can be prepared using a variety of synthesis methods. In [4], a mechanical mixing process was proposed to create a $\text{GdSmZr}_2\text{O}_7\text{-(Li}_{0.52}\text{Na}_{0.48})_2\text{CO}_3$ composite oxide ion conductor with a conductivity of 0.54Scm^{-1} at 600°C , which was substantially higher than that of pure $\text{GdSmZr}_2\text{O}_7$ [27]. Most studies recorded low sintering temperatures for composites after mixing with an automated ball mill [4]. The sintering temperatures of composite electrolytes have been reported to be lower than those of ancient oxygen-ion ceramics, such as GDC and rare earth zirconates [27-35]. According to [32], a composite electrolyte based on Samarium-Doped Ceria (SDC)-Yttria Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) exhibits improved electrical conductivity. By molten salt infiltration, a dual composite SDC-LNC was prepared with oxide- and carbonate-ion conductors with a conductivity of 0.46Scm^{-1} at 600°C . Coating YSZ with a new composite electrolyte of Yttria Doped Ceria (YDC) and GDC for LT-SOFC was proposed in [33]. Only one cell evaluation revealed that YSZ with doped ceria composite electrolyte, fitted by the sol-gel dip-drawing process, had better cell output than YSZ electrolyte without ceria substrate separation. However, the interdiffusion of constituents at the boundaries can be a disadvantage of YSZ and doped ceria composites, resulting in a decrease in conductivity [21, 34]. It has been discovered that an SDC-LSGM composite electrolyte with a weight ratio of 9:1 has a high oxide ion conductivity [19, 36].

This study investigated the LAO-GDC composite system in terms of phase formation, elemental analysis, and electrical properties. The composites were made using the solid-state reaction process, however, LAO and GDC were prepared and structurally analyzed separately.

II. METHODOLOGY

A solid-state reaction method was adopted to prepare this LAO-GDC-based composite material whereas the LAO was prepared by the auto-combustion method [37]. The following were used to prepare pure LAO, GDC, and the composite material LAO-GDC: $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 99%), $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 98%), CeO_2 (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich, USA), and Gd_2O_3 (99.9%, Alfa Aesar, USA). Weighted LAO-GDC composites with LAO:GDC ratios of 3:1, 2:2, and 1:3 were produced. Stoichiometric amounts of LAO and GDC powder substances were mixed by a planetary ball mill using zirconia balls with a diameter of 3mm with ethyl alcohol for 24 hours. After the completion of ball milling, the composite powder was crushed manually in an agate mortar for 4 hours. The residual powder was then calcined at 700°C for 8

hours and then uniaxially pressed into pellets under a pressure of 7 tons (0.711kg/cm^2).

The prepared uncured pellets were sintered at a temperature of 1400°C for 12h with a heating-cooling rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Sintered pellet XRD patterns were observed using a Rigaku Miniflex II desktop X-ray diffractometer under Cu-K α radiation (30kV, 20mA) in the $20\text{-}80^\circ$ range. The microstructure of sintered samples was captured using a Quanta 200 FESEM Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The existence of critical elements was investigated using Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The sintered pellets were refined with emery paper to create a clean and smooth surface layer, and then silver (Ag) paste was pasted on both sides of the pellet and fired for half an hour at 700°C . The electrical behavior of these pellets was studied using a Wayne Kerr 6500 P impedance analyzer in the range of $400\text{-}700^\circ\text{C}$ at a step of 25°C in the frequency range of 20Hz to 1MHz. Based on Archimedes' theory, the experimental densities of prepared sintered pellets were calculated using a density measurement instrument (Sartorius, BSA2245CW).

Fig. 1. Solid-state reaction synthesis techniques

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigated LAO-GDC with weight ratios of 3:1, 2:2, and 1:3, called L3G1, L2G2, and L1G3, respectively.

A. Structural and Morphological Properties

Figure 2(a) shows the XRD patterns of all the LAO-GDC structures investigated, and the composites L3G1, L2G2, and L1G3. LAO and GDC phases are represented by the symbols \blacklozenge and $*$, respectively, and the phases of all explored system components are also indicated. The expanded view shown in Figure 2(b) of the more intense peak between $20\text{-}35^\circ$ clearly shows the minor right shifting of the peaks as the GDC doping concentration increased. The intensity of the peak corresponding to a 121 plane decreases with increasing GDC concentration, showing decreasing crystallite size in the SEM micrograph. The XRD phase patterns of LAO and GDC are also listed as references, with single-phase rhombohedral perovskite structure and cubic fluorite structure, respectively, having space groups R-3c and Fm3m that suit well with the JCPDS files no. 82-0478 and 81-0792. The system shows single-phase formation as a result of high-temperature sintered pellets. This study achieved an optimized conductivity of $0.46 \times 10^{-1}\text{Scm}^{-1}$ for the L1G3 system; therefore, the physical behavior of this composite is discussed.

Fig. 2. (a) XRD pattern of LAO, GDC, and their composites L3G1, L2G2, and L1G3, (b) expanded view of the more intense peak between 20-35°C (crystal structure).

Fig. 3. SEM Microstructure of composites (a) L3G1, (b) L2G2, and (c) L1G3. Elemental mapping of composites: (d) L3G1, (e) L2G2, and (f) L1G3.

The XRD pattern of sintered composite pellets consists of perovskite rhombohedral structure (R-3c) LAO as a major phase along with minor GDC cubic fluorite structure (space group, Fm3m). Peaks were indexed using the above-mentioned space group [16, 38]. Using the Archimedes principle, the densities of sintered composite pellets were measured at 6.4, 6.6, and 6.7 g/cm³ for L3G1, L2G2, and L1G3, respectively, which is 97% of the theoretically calculated values. The SEM micrographs of the sintered pellets' rupture surface were logged for all systems. Figure 3 illustrates the SEM micrograph of the fractured samples of all three composites. The SEM image clearly shows hexagonal and cubic grains having dense and well-connected structures. The SEM micrographs clearly show the white color cubic structure of the GDC and are in good agreement with XRD patterns. The captured SEM microstructure shows a very dense and compact shape for

L1G3 than the others, which is congruent with observed experimental density values. Furthermore, SEM micrographs depict comparatively small grain sizes when increasing the GDC ratio. The average particle size of all three compositions was calculated using the linear intercept process, yielding values in the range of 1.27-1.98 nm. The average grain size value for L1G3 was found to be lower than those of the other compositions. Using Scherer's formula, the average crystallite size was calculated to be in the 40-50 nm range [16]. The structure with a smaller particle size or a large grain boundary has more oxygen vacancies resulting in higher conductivity [13, 19, 38]. The Energy-Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) study, shown in Figure 4, shows all the atomic constituents and their atomic percentage. The percentage of the atomic value of O, Ce, and Gd is higher in L1G3. The elemental mapping (Figure 3 (d-f)) for all composite systems showed the presence of all elements in their appropriate ratio which is also confirmed by the EDX study in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. EDS of the composites L3G1, L2G2, and L1G3.

B. Electrical Properties

The electrical behavior of composites was studied using complex plane impedance analysis in the frequency range of 20 Hz to 1 MHz. Two constraints were used to estimate the electrical conductivity: conductance (G) and dielectric constant (D). The real (Z') and the imaginary (Z'') part of impedance were used in the complex plane impedance analysis [16] and can be calculated with the help of the formula given in (1) and plotted on the x and y axes, respectively.

$$Z' = \frac{D^2}{G(D^2+1)} \quad \text{and} \quad Z'' = \frac{Z'}{D} \quad (1)$$

Figure 5 shows the representative Nyquist graph of the L1G3 composite in different temperature ranges of 475-700°C. Complete conductivity is the sum of all individual conductivities attributable to the grain, grain boundary, and electrode-specimen interface in high-, intermediate-, and low-frequency regions, respectively [34, 39-40]. A wide semicircular arc near the origin was observed at low temperatures (400°C), indicating a high-frequency field, due to grain influence.

Fig. 5. Nyquist plots of L3G1 composite in the temperature range of 475-700°C.

Increasing temperature, this large semicircular curve due to grain contribution (near the origin) becomes small at intermediate temperatures and disappears at high temperatures. This movement of the semicircular arc to the right-hand side is due to the relaxation frequency of polarization processes [34, 39-41]. Therefore, with increasing temperature, the semicircular arc related to grain contribution disappears, as shown in Figures 5 and 6 (the latter being plotted in log scale). The semicircular arc due to electrode polarization starts to appear at a high temperature and is visible at ~700°C. At high temperatures (700°C), at first the straight line due to the grain contribution appears, and then the single semicircle, as shown in Figure 6(b), at the in-between frequency indicates that conduction is primarily through grain boundaries [39-42]. Since the ratio of grain boundary resistance (R_{gb}) to grain resistance (R_g) is not important, grains play a significant role in total conductivity at low temperatures, i.e. $R_{gb} < R_g$. However, on increasing temperatures, this ratio increases slowly and becomes large at high temperatures (~700°C), i.e. $R_{gb} > R_g$. Finally, at 700°C and above, the grain resistance (R_g) vanishes, and the overall conductivity of the sample is calculated by the grain boundary resistance (R_{gb}). As a result, at high temperatures, the conductivity due to grain boundary influences conductivity due to the grain (~700°C). The grain resistance (R_g) and grain boundaries resistances (R_{gb}) can be calculated by calculating the intercepts of respective arcs on the real axis (Z').

Temperature dependence activation energy for the composite L1G3 is exposed by the Arrhenius plot with $\log(\sigma T)$ on the y-axis vs $1000/T$ on the x-axis, as shown in Figure 5. A linear relationship (straight line) was observed in the complete temperature range (400-700°C). The activation energy (E_a) of the composite L1G3 is determined by the slope of this straight line, as shown in Figure 5. The formation energy and migration barrier may be triggering the activation energy for conduction. The conductivity of a material is related to the defect and is measured as $\sigma = ne\mu$, where n , e , and μ are the concentration, the charge of the defect, and the mobility, respectively. The concentration n , on the other hand, consists of both thermally activated and athermal defects [41], i.e., $n = n_a + n_t$, where n_t is the concentration of defects that are thermally stimulated in the measurements at predetermined temperatures and n_a is the

athermal concentration involving defects, e.g. prior in the material before the conductivity measurements but at lower temperatures. This study measured samples at intermediate temperatures from 400 to 700°C and therefore the thermally activated defects play an important role, i.e. $n_t > n_a$. Furthermore, since $E_a = E_f + E_m$ [41], the measured value of the activation energies (E_a) was found to be approximately 1.5eV, which is in good agreement with the values of LAO and GDC in [20, 43], and indicates that the activation energy of ionic conduction is comparable to the activation energy of vacancy mobility [19]. The mobility of oxygen ions is a temperature-dependent property that decreases as the temperature increases [44-45]. Equation (2) can be used to express the temperature-dependent ionic conductivity:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{k_B T}\right) \tag{2}$$

where σ_0 is a fixed exponent factor and reverse temperature dependent. The measured activation energy values reveal that the movement of oxide ions is caused by ionic transport [20, 44, 46].

The activation energy of an electrolyte device (oxide ion conductor) is estimated to range between 0.9 and 1.8eV [20, 47, 49-50]. Therefore, the investigated composite system is ionic in nature, and its conductivity is mainly determined by thermally activated oxygen ions [49-51]. The ionic conductivity of all investigated compositions, at 700°C, was found to be of the order of 10^{-1}Scm^{-1} and L1G3 showed the highest conductivity magnitude. The ionic conductivity was found to be related to the development of oxygen vacancies at high temperatures. The conductivity of the investigated LAO-GDC composite systems increases as the GDC ratio increases due to the formation of oxygen ion vacancies, which are primarily formed by Gd^{3+} ions. Consequently, dopant concentration, grain boundaries, and grain size play an important role in determining conductivity and its variation.

Fig. 6. (a) Representative fitted Nyquist plot of L1G3 at 700°C, (b) Arrhenius representation of conductivity of L1G3 at different temperatures (insight).

The influence of Gd^{3+} ions on the lanthanum site plays a role when the conductivity is rising and then falls off activation energy accordingly. The activation energy of pure $LaAlO_3$ was reported as $0.90 \pm 0.01 eV$ [52], while the activation energy of GDC was reported as $0.55-1.04 eV$ [11, 14] and for the LAO-GDC composites was found to be $1.51 eV$. The value of the observed activation energy for this composite shows enhanced ionic conductivity which rises with a rise in the GDC ratio. Furthermore, the improvement in conductivity is consistent with the compact microstructure of the composites. The conductivity of the L1G3 composition was found to be the highest among the three compositions investigated and provides a better option for cost-effective solid electrolyte applications in electrochemical devices.

IV. DISCUSSION

At moderate temperatures, the conductivities of GDC are approximately $10^{-2} Scm^{-1}$, which is inflated when compared to stabilized zirconia. The maximum electrical conductivity of GDC may be a result of the fact that Gd^{3+} and Ce^{4+} have close ionic radii. Ceria-based electrolytes have been examined as a low-temperature alternative in terms of cost, processing, and quality. $LaAlO_3$ might be a good substitute perovskite option for the oxide ion conductor in SOFCs. Improved electrical conductivity can be found in a composite electrolyte made of Samarium-Doped Ceria (SDC) and Yttria Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ).

In this paper, a dual composite SDC-LNC constructed with oxide- and carbonate-ion conductors with a conductivity of $0.46 Scm^{-1}$ at $600^\circ C$ was infiltrated with molten salt. Cell evaluation showed that the sol-gel dip-drawing procedure fitted YSZ with a doped ceria composite electrolyte had better cell output than the YSZ electrolyte without ceria substrate separation. However, YSZ and doped ceria composites may suffer from the inter-diffusion of components at the borders, which would reduce conductivity. An SDC-LSGM composite electrolyte with a weight ratio of 9:1 has previously been found to have a high oxide ion conductivity.

V. CONCLUSION

This study successfully synthesized LAO-GDC composites employing a quick, simple, and efficient solid-state reaction method, with typical crystallite sizes of 41-50nm. LAO and GDC, respectively, made the hexagonal and cubic fluorite structures visible. When these two were joined, LAO-GDC composites showed the same phase. The density of the high-density composite systems sintered at $1400^\circ C$ was 97% of the theoretical. The L1G3 samples had a microstructure that is more dense and fine than the other samples. As the amount of Gd^{3+} doping was increased, GDC's conductivity rose. The L1G3 composition obtained its maximum conductivity of $0.4 \times 10^{-1} Scm^{-1}$ with an activation energy of $1.51 eV$. The LAO-GDC composite is predominantly an L1G3 system, as seen by this peculiar electrical behavior.

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Development of a Geotechnical Database using the Geographic Information System Approach

The Case of Djelfa, Algeria

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ABSTRACT

The present work aimed primarily to carry out a synthesis of the nature of the soil in the town of Djelfa and to develop a database of existing geological and geotechnical data that are available in order to put them at the disposal of all potential users, whether scientific or operational. The carried out work consisted in collecting and organizing the existing geological and geotechnical data on a geographical information system. The criteria were first identified (allowable stresses, allowable depths, etc.) and then maps with the different important factors were developed. Subsequently, these maps were superimposed to arrive, after a succession of generalizations of the geotechnical map, at an official final map with geotechnical terms. The interpretation of the obtained results allows for identifying the contributions and placing limits to the results and then trying to apply this method to other sites presenting similar problems and context. It should be noted that the maps produced are intended to enlighten decision-makers and planners when dealing with areas that are expected to be urbanized. They can also be helpful when conducting a preliminary study before the geotechnical study.

Keywords-geotechnical mapping; GIS; Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA); Djelfa

I. INTRODUCTION

In geotechnics, the physical and mechanical characteristics of the site are acquired from in situ tests and laboratory tests. The existing historical information can be found in the form of hard, electronic and paper copy, site investigation reports. The traditional data collecting procedure can be a laborious job [1, 2]. Over the past four decades, geotechnical information has been integrated into a computerized database management system called Geographic Information System (GIS), which is a process of mapping and integrating computer founded information [3]. It is an excellent means of geographic access to spatial data acquired from different sources because of its ability to manage large amounts of data. It is a tool for capturing, displaying and, analyzing geographically referenced

data [2-6]. GIS played a very important role in geotechnical engineering including preliminary site investigations, better understanding of the scope of possible solutions, the integration of any type of information, interpolation for obtaining data at inaccessible locations and less time may be spent on data analysis and acquisition than on data integration [2, 7].

In the geotechnical engineering field, the traditional procedures for making a soil site investigation require consulting previous conducted geotechnical reports in order to obtain better information of the soil properties. These reports are usually found as the format of electronic and saved paper documents in the archive rooms. However, the data processing can be highly complex and time-consuming due to the reports' condition and abundance.

In order to facilitate the performance of geotechnical engineers as well as to save time and effort, geotechnical data from several years have been collected for building a database and converting them into maps. The resulted maps can be used by geotechnical engineers to obtain a better idea of the site's geotechnical data (the main lithological units, the permissible depths, the allowable bearing capacity, and the aggressiveness rates). The objective behind developing a database for the town of Djelfa is to present and reference all the geotechnical data in GIS. For this, all the data collected were classified in thematic tables in order to be manageable in GIS. Thematic analyses were visualized in the form of maps.

II. STYDY AREA

From a geographical point of view, the Wilaya (Province) of Djelfa is located in the very heart of the high steppe plains (High Plateaus), at an altitude of 1200m. The town of Djelfa is considered a crossroads of transit between the North and the South and between the East and the West within Algeria. This strategic position can itself be a major asset that allows this city to assume the role of a regional hub and capital of the central highlands of Algeria. It must be recognized that this role has been entrusted to it for quite a long time by the regional scheme of the highlands in the central region of the country [8]. The town of Djelfa is bounded by [9]:

- The municipality of Ain Maabed (Daira of Hassi Bahbah) in the North and North-West.
- The municipality of Dar Chioukh in the North-East.
- The municipality of Moudjbara (Daira de Ain El Bel) in the East.
- The municipality of Zaâfrane (Daira de Hassi Bahbah) in the West.
- The municipality of Zaccar (Daira de Ain El Bel) in the South.
- The municipality of Ain El Ibel in the South-West.

The town of Djelfa covers an area of 542.17km². It is characterized by a semi-arid and humid continental climate. The winters are cold and harsh and the summers are hot and dry. The temperature amplitude is relatively high. It is widely acknowledged that, from a geotechnical perspective, both dry and wet climatic periods can trigger shrinkage-swelling phenomena of certain clayey geological formations, which subsequently cause soil settlement [8]. Furthermore, the rainfall in the area under study is marked, from one year to another, by great irregularity. The study area is characterized by sudden precipitations and stormy rains, which accentuates the phenomenon of soil erosion. These precipitations often cause flooding.

III. THE GIS-BASED SPATIALIZATION APPROACH - APPLICATION TO THE STUDY AREA

The approach adopted in this work for the preparation of the geotechnical maps is principally based on GIS. This method allows the development of several maps with the geotechnical characteristics of the town of Djelfa. These maps

were developed based on the Weighted Sum Model (WSM). It is worth specifying that the exploitation of data GIS in the form of a computerized geotechnical map, makes it possible to carry out a fine and detailed spatial analysis of the underground geological formations. Furthermore, one should know that the database can be organized and structured using GIS. Each element of the database (lithology, categories of sites, etc.) comes from the digitization of its source map which is placed in an information layer. Then, each layer is georeferenced in the map projection system (Universal Transverse Mercator - UTM, zone 31) [10, 11].

A. Data Sources

The data from the geotechnical surveys used in this study were provided by the soil reports established by the National Laboratory for Housing and Construction of the Unit of the Wilaya of Djelfa. These data, which are archived in paper format (Soil study, 2010 - 2017) have been analyzed and organized in a database (Access, 2007) in order to obtain recent surveys and the various geotechnical characteristics such as the allowable stresses, aggressiveness rate, site categories, and the allowable depths. The data used were collected from 47 projects and 115 surveys distributed through different under consideration Land Use Plans (LUPs) of the city (Figure 1) [12]. In addition, in order to carry out the geotechnical characterization, statistical treatment was used to determine the average values of the physical and mechanical parameters of different formations. The extreme values were recorded and made available. Afterwards, all these values were analyzed, interpreted, and discussed.

Fig. 1. Geotechnical drilling locations.

B. Layer Maps

It should be emphasized that, in the present article, we tried to develop new working methodologies that are founded on

structural analyses and epistemologies (Access, MapInfo, Map Basic) in such a way that the system (application) that was established can be employed to facilitate the transition between the maps used by the MapInfo software and the databases which were already stored in Access. The layer of soil types (lithology), the layer of allowable stresses, the layer of allowable depths, the layer of site categories, and the layer of aggressiveness rates are shown in Figures 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6, respectively.

Fig. 2. The main lithological units of the study area.

Fig. 3. The allowable bearing capacity map of the study area.

Fig. 4. The permissible depths map of study area.

Fig. 5. The site category map of the study area.

It is worth specifying that the original geotechnical data are considered as entirely satisfactory in this study. However, the number of geotechnical reports could be increased to obtain more information and to achieve a better geotechnical characterization of the study area. For the preparation of the data layers, the continuous surfaces were formed by linear interpolation from the first points (drillings or mechanical boring) and the lines that join these different points.

Fig. 6. The aggressiveness rate map of the study area.

IV. CONCLUSION

The approach adopted in this work for the preparation of the spatial distribution map for the purpose of evaluating the lithology, soil bearing capacity, embedment depth, site category, and soil aggressiveness, is based on the Geographic Information System (GIS). The utilized data were taken from previously established geotechnical reports. These data were then incorporated in the GIS program (MapInfo) in order to draw the initial maps. This study made possible to highlight the advantages of using the above mentioned techniques, namely the low cost, the ease of use of data, and their rapid updating process.

It is worth emphasizing that the study area was divided into four different zones, depending on the effectiveness of the foundations: 1) zones with low soil bearing capacity, 2) zones with medium soil bearing capacity, 3) zones with high soil bearing capacity, and 4) zones with very high soil bearing capacity. Moreover, the lithological map shows that there is a certain lithological diversity, in addition to an alternation of limestone facies with clays. In addition, the aggressiveness map allows asserting that the upper part of the study area is strongly aggressive.

The methodology used in the selected study area can be applied to other regions, and other procedures can be adopted for the selection of sites. This approach can also be used to establish the necessary standards in an appropriate manner.

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NURBS-based Isogeometric Analysis and Refined Plate Theory Application on a Functionally Graded Plate Subjected to Random Loads

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ABSTRACT

In structural design standards, loads are often assumed to be random quantities to give load factors. This study deals with the Stochastic Isogeometric Analysis (SIGA) for a Functionally Graded Plate (FGP) subjected to random distribution loads. The spatial random variation of distribution loads is modeled as a homogeneous Gaussian random field in the plane of the functionally graded plate. The governing equation of the functional grade plate is derived using the NURBS-based isogeometric analysis and the refined plate theory. SIGA is developed based on standard NURBS-based isogeometric analysis in conjunction with the first-order perturbation expansions of random loads. This approach was verified with Monte Carlo simulation, and the numerical results showed the effect of random loads on the variation of displacements and stresses of the functionally graded plate.

Keywords-SIGA; random loads; functionally graded plate; random field

I. INTRODUCTION

Functionally Graded Material (FGM) is a special composite material. Typical FGMs are made of metal and ceramic material components distributed to vary continuously with position along the thickness direction. FGMs are used in mechanical engineering and heavy industry [1-3]. In recent years, studies have investigated structures made from FGMs, such as functionally graded beams [4-8] and functionally graded plates [9-11]. In deterministic structure problems, such as the analysis of beams [12-15], frame structures [16, 17], and plates [18-21], the input data are deterministic, so it is easier to solve than stochastic problems. Several studies investigated the

stochastic structure's problem [22-24] and the stochastic finite element method [25]. In [26], the fluctuation of the eigenvalue of free vibration of non-uniform beams was studied using the stochastic finite element method, considering the randomness of the elastic modulus. In [27], the perturbation technique was applied to develop a stochastic finite element method for the buckling of a functionally graded plate with uncertain material properties in thermal environments. In [28-30], the static and dynamic responses of a beam resting on a foundation or elastic support were analyzed, considering various random parameters. In [31], a formulation was proposed to determine the response variability in a plate structure due to the

randomness of the Poisson ratio using the weighted integral method.

Recently, in addition to the stochastic finite element method, several studies used stochastic isogeometric analysis at uncertain structures. In [32], the Karhunen–Loève expansion was used to develop the spectral stochastic isogeometric analysis for problems of linear elasticity. In [33], the Galerkin isogeometric method was used to solve the Fredholm integral eigenvalue problem. In [34, 35], stochastic isogeometric analysis was proposed for functionally graded plates considering the random field of material properties. This study focuses on developing the stochastic isogeometric analysis for the static bending problem of a functionally graded plate under random loads.

II. FORMULATION OF STOCHASTIC ISOGEOMETRIC ANALYSIS

A. The Non-Uniform Rational B-Spline (NURBS) Functions

The Non-Uniform Rational B-Spline (NURBS) functions are defined via the B-spline basic functions [11, 36-37]. To construct a set of n B-spline basic functions of order p , a knot vector Ξ is defined as a set of coordinates in the parametric space in one-dimensional parametric domain $\xi \in [0,1]$:

$$\Xi = \{\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_{n+p+1}\} \quad \xi_i \leq \xi_{i+1}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n + p \quad (1)$$

where $\xi_i \in R$ is the i -th knot, i is the knot index, and p is the polynomial order. Given the knot vector, the B-spline basis functions are defined recursively starting with piecewise constants ($p=0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$) as follows:

For $p = 0$:

$$N_{i,0}(\xi) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \xi_i \leq \xi < \xi_{i+1}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

For $p = 1, 2, 3, \dots$:

$$N_{i,p}(\xi) = \frac{\xi - \xi_i}{\xi_{i+p} - \xi_i} N_{i,p-1}(\xi) + \frac{\xi_{i+p+1} - \xi}{\xi_{i+p+1} - \xi_{i+1}} N_{i+1,p-1}(\xi) \quad (3)$$

Taking a linear combination of B-spline basis functions constructs B-spline curves where the coefficients of the basis functions are referred to as control points:

$$C(\xi) = \sum_{i=1}^n N_{i,p}(\xi) B_i \quad (4)$$

where B_i are the control points. The B-spline surfaces are defined by the tensor product of basis functions in two parametric dimensions ξ and η with two-knot vectors:

$$S(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m N_{i,p}(\xi) M_{j,q}(\eta) P_{i,j} = \sum_{l=1}^{m \times n} N_l^b(\xi, \eta) P_l \quad (5)$$

where $N_l^b(\xi, \eta) = N_{i,p}(\xi) M_{j,q}(\eta)$ is the shape function associated with control point l .

Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines are defined based on the B-splines by adding an individual weight w_l :

$$R_{l,p}(\xi) = \frac{N_{i,p}(\xi) w_l}{\sum_{l=1}^n N_{l,p}^b(\xi) w_l} \quad (6)$$

The NURBS surface is constructed by combining the rational basis functions and the coefficient at control points B_i :

$$S(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{l=1}^{m \times n} R_l(\xi, \eta) B_l \quad (7)$$

$$\text{with } R_l(\xi, \eta) = \frac{N_l^b w_l}{\sum_{l=1}^{m \times n} N_l^b(\xi, \eta) w_l}$$

B. NURBS-Based Isogeometric Formulations for a Functionally Graded Plate Based on Refined Plate Theory

Fig. 1. Random field of distribution loads on plate.

Consider a functionally graded plate subjected to random loads, with the coordinate system placed at the mid-plane of the plate as shown in Figure 1. The plate displacement fields were calculated using the refined plate theory [38], which allows taking into account the shear deformation effect, and are used to formulate the governing equations as follows:

$$U = u_0 - z \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial x} + \left[\frac{1}{4} z - \frac{5}{3} z \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \right] \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial x}$$

$$V = v_0 - z \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial y} + \left[\frac{1}{4} z - \frac{5}{3} z \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \right] \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial y} \quad (8)$$

$$W = w_b + w_s$$

The linear strains can be obtained by differentiating (8) as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial y^2} \\ -2 \frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$+ \Psi \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial y^2} \\ -2 \frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \chi \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where:

$$\Psi(z) = -\frac{1}{4}z + \frac{5}{3}z\left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2, \chi(z) = 5\left[\frac{1}{4} - \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2\right] \quad (11)$$

Young's modulus E of the functionally graded plate is assumed as:

$$E(z) = (E_c - E_m)\left(\frac{z}{h} + \frac{1}{2}\right)^p + E_m \quad (12)$$

The linear constitutive relation of a plate is given by formulation:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= \frac{E(z)}{1-\nu^2} \\ Q_{22} &= Q_{11} \\ Q_{12} &= \frac{\nu E(z)}{1-\nu^2} \\ Q_{44} &= G_{23} \\ Q_{55} &= G_{13} \\ Q_{66} &= G_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The displacement field \hat{U} of the plate is approximated via the NURBS basis functions:

$$\tilde{U}(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{i=1}^{m \times n} R_i(\xi, \eta) U_i \quad (15)$$

where U_i is the vector of nodal degrees of freedom associated with the control point i :

$$U_i = \begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ v_0 \\ w_0^b \\ w_0^s \end{Bmatrix}_i \quad (16)$$

The governing equation of the functionally graded plate is derived using the virtual work to be:

$$\int_{\Omega} \varepsilon_b^T D^b \delta \varepsilon_b d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \gamma^T A^s \delta \gamma d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} q \delta w d\Omega \quad (17)$$

where the stiffness matrices A^s and D^b are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} D^b &= \\ \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & B_{11}^s & B_{12}^s & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & B_{12}^s & B_{22}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & 0 & 0 & B_{66} & 0 & 0 & B_{66}^s \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 & D_{11}^s & D_{12}^s & 0 \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 & D_{12}^s & D_{22}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{66} & 0 & 0 & D_{66} & 0 & 0 & D_{66}^s \\ B_{11}^s & B_{12}^s & 0 & D_{11}^s & D_{12}^s & 0 & H_{11}^s & H_{12}^s & 0 \\ B_{12}^s & B_{22}^s & 0 & D_{12}^s & D_{22}^s & 0 & H_{12}^s & H_{22}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{66}^s & 0 & 0 & D_{66}^s & 0 & 0 & H_{66}^s \end{bmatrix} & (18) \\ A^s &= \begin{bmatrix} A_{44}^s & 0 \\ 0 & A_{55}^s \end{bmatrix} & (19) \end{aligned}$$

where A_{ij}, B_{ij} etc are parameters of the plate stiffness, defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} \{A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}\} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \{1, z, z^2\} Q_{ij} dz, \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \\ B_{ij}^s &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \psi Q_{ij} dz, \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \\ D_{ij}^s &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} z \psi Q_{ij} dz, \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \\ H_{ij}^s &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \psi^2 Q_{ij} dz, \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \\ A_{ij}^s &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \chi Q_{ij} dz, \quad (i = 4, 5) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The governing equation for bending the functionally graded plate is in the following form:

$$KU = F \quad (21)$$

where $K, U,$ and F denote the stiffness matrix, generalized displacement, and force vector. The global stiffness matrix K is given by:

$$K = \int_{\Omega} \left\{ \{B^0 \quad B^{bb} \quad B^{bs}\} D_b \begin{Bmatrix} B^0 \\ B^{bb} \\ B^{bs} \end{Bmatrix} + (B^s)^T A^s B^s \right\} d\Omega \quad (22)$$

and the load vector is given by:

$$F = \int_{\Omega} q(x, y) \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ R_i \\ R_i \end{Bmatrix} d\Omega \quad (23)$$

III. STOCHASTIC ISOGOMETRIC ANALYSIS

The random field of distribution loads is assumed as a homogeneous Gaussian random field in the plane of the plate:

$$q(x, y) = q_0 [1 + f(x, y)] \quad (24)$$

where $f(x, y)$ is a homogeneous random field with zero mean. The auto-correlation function of the random field $f(x, y)$ is assumed as:

$$R(\xi_x, \xi_y) = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{|\xi_x| + |\xi_y|}{d}\right) \quad (25)$$

where ξ_x, ξ_y are components of the separation vector ξ between two points in the domain of the plate, and σ and d are the coefficient of variation and the correlation distance of the random field, respectively. In this study, the value of the random field in elastic modulus was discretized as a point method by approximation at Gauss points. The set of random variables follows the statistical properties of the random fields:

$$f = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N\} \quad (26)$$

Taking the Taylor series expansion at $f=0$ based on the assumption that all components of the random field f are small, gives:

$$F(f) = F_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial F}{\partial f_i} f_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial f_i \partial f_j} f_i f_j + \dots$$

$$U(f) = U_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial U}{\partial f_i} f_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial f_i \partial f_j} f_i f_j + \dots \quad (27)$$

For the zeroth perturbation equation:

$$K_0 U_0 = F_0 \quad (28)$$

For the first-order perturbation equation:

$$K_0 \frac{\partial U}{\partial f_i} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial f_i} \quad (29)$$

The first-order perturbation solutions are:

$$\mu_U = U_0$$

$$Cov_U = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\partial U}{\partial f_i} \frac{\partial U}{\partial f_j} R_{ij} \quad (30)$$

where:

$$\mu_U = E(U)$$

$$Cov_U = E[(U - \mu_U)(U - \mu_U)^T] \quad (31)$$

denote the mean and variance of the displacement U , respectively, R_{ij} is the covariance matrix of the random variable f , and N is the number of random variables. As U represents nodal parameters at control points, it is not the real displacements at the nodes. So, The mean vector and covariance matrix, using the relation between U and \tilde{U} in (15) can be obtained as:

$$\mu_{\tilde{U}} = \Phi \mu_U$$

$$Cov_{\tilde{U}} = \Phi Cov_U \Phi^T \quad (32)$$

where Φ is the transformation matrix between U and \tilde{U} . The response variability is a ratio of the standard deviation of displacement to the absolute mean eigenvalue as:

$$COV = \frac{\sqrt{Var_{\tilde{U}}}}{|\mu_{\tilde{U}}|} \quad (33)$$

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A. Example 1: Numerical Tests

To evaluate the proposed stochastic isogeometric analysis, this method is compared with the crude Monte Carlo simulation in [39] using the spectral representation method [40]. The random sample function of the Gaussian random fields in (24) can be represented by the cosine series as follows:

$$f(x, y) = \sqrt{2} \sum_{n_1=0}^{N_1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{N_2} \begin{bmatrix} A_{n_1 n_2}^{(1)} \cos(\omega_{1n_1} x + \omega_{2n_2} y + \varphi_{n_1 n_2}^{(1)}) \\ A_{n_1 n_2}^{(2)} \cos(\omega_{1n_1} x - \omega_{2n_2} y + \varphi_{n_1 n_2}^{(2)}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

The phase angles $\varphi_{n_1 n_2}^{(1)}, \varphi_{n_1 n_2}^{(2)}$ are uniformly distributed in the range of $[0, 2\pi]$.

The simply supported rectangular plate was considered subjected to random loads as shown in Figure 2. The elastic modulus and the Poisson ratio were set as $E_0=200 \times 10^5$ MPa and $\nu=0.30$, respectively. The thickness of the plate was $t=10$ mm,

and the coefficient of variation of the random field σ was 0.1. The mean of random loads is unit distributed load.

Fig. 2. Simply supported rectangular plate.

Figure 3 shows the response coefficient of the variation of displacement at the center point P of the plate, obtained by the present approach (SIGA) and Monte Carlo simulation [39] with 10000 samples.

Fig. 3. Response COV of displacement at P as a function of correlation distance d .

Figure 3 shows a good agreement between the SIGA and the Monte Carlo simulation. The coefficient of variation of the displacement trends to the coefficient of variation of the random field of random loads.

B. Example 2

A simply supported square functionally graded plate, made of aluminum and alumina (Al/Al₂O₃), was considered. Material properties were similar to [41], $E_m=70$ MPa and $E_c=380$ MPa and the Poisson ratio was set to 0.3. The plate was subjected to random loads. The mean of random loads was unit distributed load and the power index p was set to 1. Figure 4 shows the COV response with various values of COV for the random fields of random loads obtained for the plane-normal displacement at the center point P of the plate. The response COV is bigger if the COV of the random field is larger. Also, the response COV increases when the coefficient of variation of the random field increases and approaches the coefficient of variation of the random field σ in all cases.

Fig. 4. Response COV as a function of correlation distance.

V. CONCLUSION

This study successfully developed the Stochastic Isogeometric Analysis (SIGA) for a functionally graded plate under random loads with the assumption that random loads are a homogeneous Gaussian random field in the plate plane. The coefficient of variation of the deflection in the center of the plate predicted by SIGA was validated with the results of Monte Carlo simulation. The numerical examples showed good agreement between the COV of displacement predicted by the present study and the Monte Carlo simulation. Also, the numerical examples clearly show that the randomness of load affects significantly the response of the plate. The effect of the correlation distance on the COV of displacement is clear, and the response COV increases when the correlation distances increase.

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A Multilevel Inverter for Grid-Connected Photovoltaic Systems Optimized by Genetic Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This article introduces a grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) source combined with a multi-level inverter. A converter five-level neutral point (NPC) can be used to integrate the PV power into the power grid with minimum harmonic distortions and high power capacity. If the output voltage of the PV generator varies significantly with solar radiation, the output voltage of the ripple must be fixed. For this reason, a regulation loop was used. In this study, we used a classical PI regulator. It is difficult to determine the PI controller transaction values, so Genetic Algorithm was used to optimize the PI controller parameters. The Matlab/Simulink simulation results show the better performance and efficiency of the PI controller optimized by the GA, in comparison to the stand-alone PI controller, regarding stability and accuracy, and the reduction of Total Harmonic Distortions (THD) of the current injected into the grid for any difference in solar radiation.

Keywords-PV array; MPPT; inverter NPC; genetic algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy is a developing sector in which many ongoing natural energy resources are utilized [1], solar energy being the most studied of them. Renewable energy in the coming years must meet, by 2020 and 2050, the 20% and 50% of the total demands, respectively [2].

The inverter is the core of a photovoltaic (PV) system. It converts the continuous current produced by the PV system into alternating current [3-6]. Disadvantages of the two-level PWM inverters are the high switching frequency, the many harmonics, and the large filters used [7]. The benefits of the multilevel converter are that it reduces the voltage of the apparatus, the exit wave of the staircase, and that it lowers the

electromagnetic emissions. Multi-level converters know many industrial uses and high voltage and high output standards are necessary [8]. The topologies for multilevel inverters are: floating capacitor, loopback diode (NPC), and cascaded H-bridge inverter [9]. In the NPC inverter inlet, there is availability on the side of the bipolar common DC bus and it has the flexibility to add multiple PV panels in the system [10]. There is much interest in the NPC inverters topologies due to their low output current and low overall Total Harmonic Distortion (TDH) [11]. NPC supports a variety of classical sinusoidal modulation methods, such as multiple triangle sinusoidal modulation, vector modulation, and selective harmonic elimination [12]. Common strategies for controllers in voltage regulations include the widely used PI controllers

due to their intrinsic simplicity and rapid dynamic response [13].

II. MULTILEVEL INVERTER FOR A GRID-CONNECTED PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM

The proposed diagram shown in Figure 1 [10] consists of 4 main elements: a PV array, dc/dc buck converters, NPC inverter configuration, and an LC filter (filtering inductance and capacitors L_f, C_f are used to filter the current injected into the system).

Fig. 1. The five-level inverter in grid-connected PV systems.

III. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE DIODE-CLAMPED MULTI-LEVEL INVERTER

Authors in [1] proposed the neutral point converter for a variety of applications in 1981. A multi-level inverter structure was used in high and intermediate voltage conditions. The basic architecture for this inverter was addressed in [14-15]. NPC inverters are one of the most widely used PV systems. In [16], the system has significant advantages. The $(n-1)$ capacitors required on the DC bus are part of the multilevel inverter and the required number of switches for each phase is $2(n-1)$. Moreover, there are $2*(n-2)$ diodes in each phase.

TABLE I. COMPONENT COUNT OF TRADITIONAL MLIS [24]

Topology components	Traditional MLIS		
	Diode clamped MLI	Capacitor clamped MLI	Cascaded H-bridge MLI
Main switches	$2(n-1)$	$2(n-1)$	$2(n-1)$
Main diodes	$2(n-1)$	$2(n-1)$	$2(n-1)$
Clamping diode	$2(n-2)$	0	0
Balancing capacitors	0	$(n-2)$	0
DC bus capacitors	$n-1$	0	0
DC sources	1	1	$(n-1)/2$

Fig. 2. The three-phase, five-level, diode-clamped inverter's schematic in Simulink.

IV. PHOTOVOLTAIC GENERATOR

The power available at the terminals of a cell is very low, it is therefore necessary to combine such cells in series and in parallel to obtain satisfactory power modules. This model consists of complex equations whose solution requires many (6) parameters. Another model has a single diode with 5 parameters ($R_s, R_{sh}, I_{ph}, I_0, A$), [18]:

$$I_{Ph} - I_0 \left(\exp\left(\frac{q}{nAKT}(V+R_s I)\right) - 1 \right) - \frac{V+R_s I}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

where I is the current delivered by the PV module, R_{sh} is this shunt resistance, I_{ph} the photoelectrical current, I_0 the saturation current, R_s the series resistance, K is the Boltzmann's constant, and N is the coefficient of the diode ideality.

Fig. 3. Equivalent diagram of a photovoltaic cell.

The parameters of the solar array that identify (1) relate to the solar panel parameters as follows:

$$I_{sc\text{panel}} = N_p I_{sc} \quad (2)$$

$$I_{0\text{panel}} = N_p I_0 \quad (3)$$

$$R_{S\text{panel}} = \frac{N_s}{N_p} R_s \quad (4)$$

$$R_{P\text{panel}} = \frac{N_s}{N_p} R_p \quad (5)$$

The photoelectric current (I_{ph}) depends on irradiation and temperature:

$$I_{ph} = (I_{ph,n} + K_I \cdot \Delta T) \cdot \frac{G}{G_n} \quad (6)$$

$$I_0 = \frac{I_{sc,n} + K_I \cdot \Delta T}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{oc,n} + K_V \cdot \Delta T}{A \cdot V_{th}}\right) - 1} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta T = T - T_n \quad (8)$$

where I_{scn} is the short-circuit current under nominal conditions ($G_n=1000W/m^2, T_n =25^\circ C$). The cell's ambient and nominal temperatures are represented, respectively, by T and T_n , where the current and nominal irradiation are G and G_n , respectively. The short circuit current's temperature coefficient is K_I , while the open circuit voltage's is K_V . V_{th} , given in (1) is the thermal junction constant, equal to $V_{th}=KT/q$, where q is the electron charge.

V. DC/DC BUCK CONVERTER

A boost converter is the most widely used DC-DC converter since its input voltage is smaller than its output voltage. Filters composed of inductor and capacitor combinations are regularly used together to improve the performance of a converter [20]. Thus, in order to improve the solar panel's effectiveness, we use the MPPT technique. There are different techniques to follow the Maximum Power Point (MPP) [21-22]. In this paper, the Perturb and Observe (P&O) technique is used because it is straightforward and simple to use in real time. It is an algorithm based on perturbing and monitoring the solar panel's voltage until it reaches the optimal power level in the flowchart shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Diagram of the P&O method.

Fig. 5. Reference signal and four carrier waves.

VI. COMMANDS AND ALGORITHMS USED

A. Modulation

The proposed control utilizes a modulation technique that uses the sinusoidal PWM (SPWM) [19]. A 5-level voltage waveform requires 4 level-shifted carrier signals as shown in Figure 5. It is the sinusoidal modulation with multiple triangles which allows it. This technique requires (N-1) triangular signals with the same frequency f_p and the same amplitude A_p . These triangular signals are compared, for each phase, with a reference signal of amplitude A_{ref} and frequency f_{ref} . The expressions below provide the modulation rate m_a and the frequency ratio m_f .

$$m_a = \frac{A_{ref}}{(N-1)A_p} \tag{9}$$

$$m_f = \frac{f_p}{f_{ref}} \tag{10}$$

VII. THE GENETIC ALGORITHM

Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are adaptive search algorithms built on the evolutionary principles of natural selection and genetics. The main goal of GAs is to mimic natural system processes that are necessary for evolution. They represent a clever use of a random search inside a defined search area. The core idea of GAs is to maintain a population of knowledge structures that evolve over time through a process of competition and controlled variation. Each population structure represents an answer to a particular problem and a corresponding fitness function, which is used to select which structures are used to generate new ones by genetic processes like mutation and crossover. In order to address concerns with search and optimization, GAs are quite prosperous. Their ability to leverage information about a search space that was previously unknown in order to influence subsequent searches towards beneficial subspaces may be credited with a substantial chunk of their effectiveness. A GA starts off with solutions produced by a population chosen at random. Advances made possible by chromosomes' employment of genetic operators, based on the principles of natural genetic processes. Within the population, evolution via natural selection takes place. In order to finally replace the vanishing relatively bad solutions, comparatively good solutions reproduce at every generation. The environment works as a function of evaluation or fitness to distinguish between good and bad solutions. When a GA is used, a generation is the period of time between the current and the subsequent population. Although the basic GA has a number of modifications, the fundamental mechanism consists of three parts:

- Assessment of each person's fitness.
- Creation of the gene pool.
- Mutation and recombination

TABLE II. THE STRUCTURE OF A SIMPLE GA [23]

1.	Initialization: A set of potential solutions (chromosomes or individuals) forming a population is initialized
2.	Evaluation: Each individual is then evaluated by calculating its quality (fitness value)
3.	Selection: Individuals with higher fitness value are selected for breeding
4.	Reproduction: During breeding, crossover and mutation operators are employed to selected individuals (parents) to produce new individuals (offspring)
5.	Termination: These steps continue over many generations or iterations until the predefined criteria are satisfied

VIII. OPTIMIZING THE PID REGULATOR WITH GENETIC ALGORITHM

The genetic encoding of the chromosome's PID regulator parameters defines the PID regulator parameters. There are two genes on the chromosome: K_i and K_p .

A. Generation of the Initial Population

The chromosomes in the initial population are produced by a stochastic generation. Each allele is defined in the subset:

$$S = [\min K_i \min K_p; \max K_i \max K_p] \tag{11}$$

Fig. 6. Chromosome representation.

B. Fitness Function

The PID regulator is trained with a given number of alleles and is then assessed using predetermined parameters to determine an individual's fitness. The Mean Square Error (MSE) at the conclusion of training characterizes best the quality of a PID regulator. It is the output of the PID regulator.

$$f(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_i - a_i)^2}{N} \tag{12}$$

IX. SIMULATION RESULTS

The main objectives when transferring the PV generated energy into the utility grid are:

- To track the PV's MPP.
- To obtain study voltage.

Control of the inverter output voltage requires a closed loop. The voltage V_a is measured and then compared to the reference voltage $V_{ref}=311V$ which represents the maximum value of the simple network voltage. The counter error signal is injected at the PI controller with chosen parameters: $K_p=0.1$, $K_i=0.01$. GA is used to select the parameters of the PID regulator by minimizing the MSE. Table IV shows the GA parameters used to optimize the PID parameters and Table III gives the PID regulator values.

TABLE III. GA CONTROL PARAMETERS

No of generations	20
Population	70
Chromosome size	2
Crossover	1
Mutation probability	0.08

TABLE IV. GA PARAMETERS USED TO OPTIMIZE THE PID

PID parameter	Value
K_i	0.0011
K_p	0.0218

Figure 7 shows that for a step change in solar radiation (from 200 to 800W/m²), the controller tracks instantaneously the MPP altering thus the DC bus voltage. From Figures 9-12 we can note that the conventional PI has bigger overshoot whereas the proposed PI-GA has better signal reduction of the reference signal for SPWM. Figures 9 and 10 show the 5-level output voltage of the inverter before the filter and after the LC low pass filter. Based on the harmonic analysis, TDH is less in the filtered output voltage of the 5-level inverter. From the FFT

analysis shown in Figure 12, it is observed that the TDH is 0.30%. After comparing the results, we notice that when using the GA, the results were improved and the THD was reduced.

Fig. 7. PV generator output optimal voltage.

Fig. 8. Reference voltage with GA for SPWM.

Fig. 9. Output voltage for a step change in solar insolation.

Fig. 10. Output voltage after filtering.

X. CONCLUSION

In order to secure the dc-ac conversion stage, the current research developed a 3-phase 5-level NPC multilevel grid-connected photovoltaic system. Such a topology is primarily employed to meet the needs of connecting and transmitting high power between the PV system power source and the main grid. When compared to the traditional inverter topologies

utilized in such applications, this topology has impressively demonstrated its efficacy and adaptability and offers various advantages, including a reduction in output voltage harmonics.

Fig. 11. Reference voltage.

Fig. 12. FFT analysis for the 5-level inverter.

Fig. 13. Voltage FFT analysis before filtering.

Fig. 14. Evolution of GA.

Regarding future work, the behavior of various blocks can be further improved, i.e. regarding the dc/dc converter, the

possibility of using a buck/boost converter can be examined and regarding the dc/ac converter new topologies can be inspected. The possibility of practical implementation using the D Space card is also considered.

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Numerical Simulation and Optimization of Methane Steam Reforming to Maximize H₂ Production: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Research in renewable energy, the preservation of the environment, and the reduction of energy generation costs are themes that go hand in hand. In this work, a case study was carried out that aims to maximize the production of hydrogen through Methane Steam Reforming. For this, several numerical simulations, considering a laminar flow regime in a chemical reactor with a catalyst, were developed with COMSOL Multiphysics. After an exploratory study of the data, a systematic optimization was developed using multivariate regression models formed by combinations of input parameters in an idealized reactor. The results showed that the proposed approach is capable of satisfactory optimization.

Keywords- numerical simulation; hydrogen production; optimization; heat transfer

I. INTRODUCTION

Although modeling solute transport in porous media is not a new research branch since there are important records of models dated in 1952 and 1953 [1, 2], research of porous media has been thriving lately, mainly because it widened to solve inherent latent problems in the environmental, industrial, and biological sectors. Contamination of groundwater, diffusion of tracer particles in cellular bodies, underground oil flow in the petroleum industry, and even blow flow through capillaries are only a few relevant studies that have been bringing real and tangible contributions to the society [3, 4]. While the basic laws that govern the flow of fluids are accessible and usually make use of Navier-Stokes' equations, their application is not feasible for multiple complex geometries that are present in a detailed description of the pore structure of a realistic porous medium. This level of detail is not of practical use either, and ends up desiring a description at a level of detail somewhere intermediate between Darcy's law and the pore-level flow [3].

The numerical simulation is very important for solution several engineering problems [5-8], for example, authors in [9] presented numerical models for the resolution of density-coupled flow and transport in porous media based on mixed hybrid finite element and discontinuous finite element methods. The authors stated that the simulation presented a good agreement when tested against the standard benchmarks Henry and Elder test cases. Authors in [10] described heat and solute transport in porous media using partial differential equations of similar form, and the study happened to interpret two push-pull tests of different durations. The authors concluded that longitudinal solute dispersivity is scale-dependent while diffusivity seems not to be. Furthermore, the conductive transport of heat is much more important than the effects of velocity variations through the pore space. The contribution of the temperature in the process was studied in [11-12]. Authors in [13] stated that solutes having a limited mobilization in heterogeneous porous media may end up with subsurface salinization and clear contamination in various environmental

settings. Recent studies brought up that flow and transport driven by pressure waves in porous media under saturated conditions intensively enlarge solute displacement compared to drag-dominant (Darcy) flow and transport, resulting in more thorough remediation. However, the experimental results miss the demonstration of such transport under unsaturated conditions. The authors investigated solute leaching in a flow cell, experimentally modeling solute displacement from an unsaturated, saline, fine-textured soil region to the surrounding coarse-textured soil. They concluded stating that the Pressure-wave Pulse Flux (PPF) treatment led to higher water content at and behind the front, which increased the continuity of the water phase across the fine-textured and coarse-textured soils and enhanced transport. The study is a proof of concept for pressure-wave driven flow to enhance local wetting and solute transport in unsaturated soil.

When it comes to reactors, authors in [14] presented the thermochemical analysis of a packed-bed reactor via multi-dimensional CFD modeling using FlexPDE and COMSOL Multiphysics. The temperature, concentration, and reaction rate profiles for methane production following the Fischer–Tropsch (F-T) synthesis were studied. To this end, stationary and dynamic differential equations for mass and heat transfer were solved via the finite element technique. As a result, all models were in good agreement with the experimental data found in the literature, especially for the 2-D and 3-D dynamic models. In terms of kinetics, the predicted reaction rate profiles from the COMSOL model and the 2-D dynamic model followed the temperature trend, thus reflecting the temperature dependence of the reaction. Based on these findings, it was demonstrated that applying different approaches for the CFD modeling of F-T processes conducts reliable results.

Hydrogen production was studied in [15], since mechanically and chemically stable membranes with high perm-selectivity towards hydrogen are available and are continuously further improving in terms of stability and hydrogen flux. The authors highlight recent advances in hydrogen-selective membranes (from palladium-based to silica and proton conductors) along with the advances in the different types of membrane reactors available (from packed bed to fluidized bed and from micro-reactors to bio-membrane reactors). Meanwhile, the authors in [16] presented the catalytic reforming technology, which is regarded as one of the most popular hydrogen production methods. The introduction of a fluidized bed reactor provides a promising opportunity for the enhancement of catalytic reforming technology due to its good gas-solid contact and heat and mass transfer characteristics. The authors describe how, in order to improve hydrogen production, the strengthening method of reforming technology via hydrogen membrane separation has been developed in the last few years. The development and challenges of catalytic reforming technology using a membrane-assisted fluidized bed for hydrogen production are reviewed.

In the current work, we present a case study to present an alternative for optimizing an idealized chemical reactor. For this, we will use numerical simulations via COMSOL Multiphysics to solve the methane steam reforming chemical reaction given by:

which here will be considered irreversible since the main focus is the optimization of the idealized reactor.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Parameters

Initially, we present the geometry of the case study. This is an idealized reactor with an inlet and an outlet, a region of porous medium (catalyst), and in its center there is a pipe through which a hot fluid passes, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Idealized reactor (left) and inside view of the reactor (right).

For the study presented here, the following characteristics will be considered:

- A two-dimensional study will be carried out and symmetry will be considered in the centerline of the idealized reactor (Figure 2), where L_1 is the length before the catalyst and the measurement between the hot fluid pipe and the reactor shell [m], L_R is the length of the catalyst region [m], L_2 is the length after the catalyst [m], U_0 is the inlet velocity [m/s], and T_{hot} is the temperature of the hot fluid [K].

Fig. 2. Two-dimensional domain with boundary conditions.

- Porosity is considered equal to 0.5 and permeability to 10^{-9} m^2 .
- The formula used to calculate the diffusivity between gases (D_{AB}) is [17]:

$$D_{AB} = 1,053 \times 10^{-3} \frac{T^{3/2}}{P d_{AB}^2} \left[\frac{1}{M_A} + \frac{1}{M_B} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where T is the temperature [K], P is the pressure [atm], M_A is the molar mass of element A (CH_4 , H_2O , CO or H_2), M_B is the molar mass of element B (air) and d_{AB} , is defined by:

$$d_{AB} = (\sum v)_A^{1/3} + (\sum v)_B^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

In this work the values presented in Table I will be considered.

TABLE I. DIFFUSION MOLECULAR VOLUMES [13]

Molecule	Σv	Molar mass
Air	16.2	28.96
CO	18.0	28.01
H_2O	13.1	18.01
CH_4	25.14	16.033
H_2	6.12	2.016

- Due to the high activation energy required for the reaction proposed in (1) to occur, we will consider the inverse reaction to be negligible, and thus:

$$[H_2] = k[CH_4][H_2O] \quad (4)$$

$$[CO] = k[CH_4][H_2O] \quad (5)$$

where k is defined by (5) and using as reference [14], yields that:

$$k = 7.301 \times 10^{-2} e^{-\left(\frac{36150}{8.31 \times T}\right)} \quad (6)$$

B. Governing Equations

For the study of the conservation of motion, Brinkman's equations (laminar flow) will be used:

$$\nabla \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{K}] - \left(\mu \kappa^{-1} + \beta \epsilon_p |\mathbf{u}| + \frac{Q_m}{\epsilon_p^2} \right) \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{F} \quad (7)$$

$$\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = Q_m \quad (8)$$

More details about the terms of (9) and (10) can be found in [15]. Then, to carry out the study of mass transport in porous media, the following equations will be used:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla c_i = R_i + S_i \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -D_{e,j} \nabla c_i \quad (10)$$

$$\theta = \epsilon_p \quad (11)$$

More details about the terms of (9)-(11) can be found in [20]. Finally, for the treatment of the temperature field, the energy conservation equation will be used as follows:

$$d_z \rho C_p \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = d_z Q + q_0 + d_z Q_p + d_z Q_{vd} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{q} = -d_z k \nabla T \quad (13)$$

More details about the terms of (12) and (13) can be found in [21].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the study that will be presented here, three parameters were chosen to be analyzed: the inlet concentration of H_2O [mol/m³] (Case 1), the inlet velocity U_0 [m/s] (Case 2); and finally, the reactor length L_R [m] (Case 3). In all cases, the following parameters will be used as fixed: inlet concentration of $CH_4 = 1 \text{ mol/m}^3$, $L_1 = 0.05 \text{ m}$ and $L_2 = 0.01 \text{ m}$.

It is important to highlight that will be used the medium values of H_2 in the outlet of the idealized reactor in the results presented for the three cases.

A. Case 1: Varying H_2O

In the first case, we were varying the inlet concentration of H_2O in values between 1 and 1000 mol/m³. Besides, $L_R = 0.1 \text{ m}$

and $U_0 = 0.1 \text{ m/s}$ were fixed and 5 different values for T_{hot} were adopted: 973, 1023, 1073, 1123, and 1173K to verify the influence of hot fluid in the H_2 production.

Fig. 3. H_2 production with H_2O (inlet) variation.

In Figure 3, it is possible to note that with the increasing inlet concentration of H_2O , increasing of the H_2 production occurs, however, it is clear that the results of the 5 different values of T_{hot} little differ. In Figure 4, it is clear that near in the region of heating the major concentration of H_2 production occurs.

Fig. 4. H_2 concentration with $H_2O = 1000 \text{ mol/m}^3$ (inlet) and $T_{hot} = 1173 \text{ K}$.

B. Case 2: Varying U_0

In Case 1, it was clear that the major values adopted for H_2O and T_{hot} presented better results for H_2 production, thus, in Case 2 fixed values of $H_2O = 1000 \text{ mol/m}^3$ and $T_{hot} = 1173 \text{ K}$ were adopted. From that, 11 different values of U_0 were analyzed (of 0.005 to 0.1 m/s). As in Case 1, $L_R = 0.1 \text{ m}$ was considered. In Case 1 (Figure 3), within the values of H_2O inlet, the curves show crescent. The opposite occurs in Case 2 (Figure 5), since for the values adopted the curve shows a maximum point in the region of $U_0 = 0.02 \text{ m/s}$ and then the curve becomes decreasing. In other words, the graph in Figure 5 suggests that the region near the $U_0 = 0.02$ is the possible optimum point.

Fig. 5. H₂ production with U₀ variation.

Fig. 6. H₂ concentration (Case 2) with U₀ = 0.02m/s.

Figure 6 shows that the H₂ production into the idealized reactor and is more expressive than that presented in Figure 4.

C. Case 3: Varying L_R

In this last case, L_R varied between 0.01 and 0.1m (10 points). Again, some values will be fixed: T_{hot} = 1173K and H₂O = 1000mol/m³ (inlet). Besides, 3 values will be considered for U₀ (0.005, 0.01, and 0.02m/s).

Fig. 7. H₂ production with L_R variation.

Although the three variations of U₀ were considered to present results expressibly different, the behavior is similar, that is, a behavior of the crescent curve, with a positive derivative and thus proving that the increase in L_R can still cause an increase in H₂ production.

D. Optimization

In order to understand the way the control parameters influence the generation of hydrogen through the chemical reaction proposed in this work (1), from the highest production, H₂ = 0.767mol/m³ (found in the condition L_R = 0.10m, U₀ = 0.02m/s, H₂O = 1000mol/m³, and T_{hot} = 173K among the data set analyzed in the 3 previously described cases), a new set of data was generated in the simulations, varying up and down by p% in the values of the input variables. The process was repeated, from the highest value found, generating a new data set with a sufficient number of points to test regression models with 3 independent variables and their 2 by 2 combinations, which, in this case, were 2 iterations using: p = 0.1 and (again) p = 0.1, thus forming a data set with 16 points. For this new data set, the best fit was obtained using the K-fold cross-validation with 10 folds. The model is expressed by (14):

$$H_2 = 0.5517 + 0.809L_R + 1.715U_0 + 0.000098H_2O \quad (14)$$

The statistics about the quality of fit of the model proposed by (14) are presented in Table II. We observe that the model fits very well to the simulated data, presenting high values of adjusted R2 and cross-validation, indicating that the model presents good capacity of generalization, with Anderson Darling test for normal residuals P-Value equal to 0.0864.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF THE QUALITY MODEL FIT (14)

S	R2	R2(aj)	R2(pred)	10-fold S	10-fold R2
0.0045874	94.72%	93.50%	91.84%	0.0050580	91.61%

It is evident from the analysis of the P-value and the F-distribution (Table III) that the variable that most influences the generation of H₂ is the H₂O inlet concentration while the L_R length is the second more important.

TABLE III. ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR THE PROPOSED MODEL OF (15)

	GL	SQ (Aj)	QM (Aj)	F-Value	P-Value
Regression	3	0.004910	0.001637	77.78	0.000
L _R	1	0.001337	0.001337	63.52	0.000
U ₀	1	0.000269	0.000269	12.79	0.003
H ₂ O	1	0.002087	0.002087	99.16	0.000
Error	13	0.000274	0.000021		
Total	16	0.005184			

The quality of the fit can be seen in Figure 8. It is interesting to observe that the strategy of prospecting for new data in order to obtain a greater production of H₂ appears to be successful because it presents various combinations of L_R, U₀, and H₂O with H₂ greater than 0.767mol/m³ from the initial dataset. Finally, using Minitab's optimizer, it is possible to envision a direction toward greater H₂ production. In Figure 9, it is evident that a greater production of H₂ can be obtained by increasing L_R, U₀, and H₂O. To assess whether these indications are correct, another simulation was performed in

that direction with $L_R = 0.125\text{m}$, $U_0 = 0.025\text{m/s}$, and $H_2O = 1250\text{mol/m}^3$. The simulation result was 0.823 and the prediction of the proposed model for these conditions was 0.818 with a prediction interval (95%) of [0.806, 0.830] showing the ability of the model to reproduce simulation data in laminar flow.

Fig. 8. Quality of model fit to simulated H_2 production data.

Fig. 9. Optimization of the proposed model to maximize H_2 production.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The production of clean energy is one of the main themes nowadays and one of the available alternatives is the production of hydrogen. Although there are a considerable number of techniques and methods developed to design more efficient processes to produce hydrogen - many of them using only the Finite Element Method (FEM), others checking the results of FEM on experiments, the combination of numerical simulations with statistics is not observed in the literature. With that being said, the contribution of this paper is on demonstrating how this powerful combination can enhance the production of hydrogen since it allowed us to figure out precisely the significance of each variable in the system as well as the interaction among them.

In this work, we present an idealized reactor with a heating pipe that would carry out the chemical reaction known as methane steam reforming and generate hydrogen gas with the greatest efficiency. Through the variation of some physical and geometric parameters in the numerical simulation, we were able to present an optimization with high precision and high efficiency in the production of hydrogen by using statistics analysis. Besides, the statistical approach used in this work allowed finding a better optimal point than the one obtained in

the initial exploratory numerical simulation analysis. It is important to point out that the use of statistics aimed at optimizing hydrogen production for the work proposed here is considered somewhat unprecedented since we did not find any work that used this approach.

In future work, an additional analysis could be carried out in maximizing the production of hydrogen with a possible reduction of CO (carbon monoxide) pollutant.

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Critical Analysis of Road Side Friction on an Urban Arterial Road

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ABSTRACT

This study reviews the impact of roadside friction on urban arterial roads in the published literature and aims to identify the various side frictional parameters that impact urban arterial roads. The side frictional parameters are non-motorized vehicles, pedestrian crossing or moving along the road, street vendors, on-street parking, animal movement, and land-use activity. The impact of all these parameters on traffic performance leads to a reduction in capacity, speed (instantaneous speed, journey speed, travel speed, time mean speed, and space mean speed), level of service, delay, travel time, and travel cost. This study considered online published studies from 1995 to 2022. The available effective width and the percentage reduction in road capacity are related. Road capacity is reduced by 3.37% when the effective width is reduced by 2.95%, while road capacity is reduced by 26.08% when the effective width is reduced by 21.81%.

Keywords-side friction; arterial road, speed; capacity; road capacity; level of service; non-motorized vehicles

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficient transportation infrastructure is essential and critical for economic development, particularly in developing countries. Economic development requires more movement of people and things. Rapid urbanization and population growth in urban areas in developing countries, such as India, have resulted in increased vehicular traffic. Vehicle growth is putting more pressure on the transportation infrastructure, particularly in the road transport system, and adversely affects smooth traffic flow. In India, as the road transport system handles more than 85% of passenger travel and 60% of freight flow, roads are dominantly used as a mode of transport and act as a lifeline for accessibility. Urban regions are experiencing more congestion, pollution, and accidents as a result of the increase in traffic. In old Indian cities, most arterial and sub-arterial roads face congestion due to the increase in vehicular population, heterogeneous traffic, and many side frictions.

Side friction is defined as any activity or action that occurs on the side of a road or on the road itself and interferes with the efficient flow of traffic. Side friction refers to activities that cause traffic congestion on the roadway or along its sides. In [1], the effects of side friction on an urban arterial road were explained and defined as any acts related to activities occurring on the roadside or sometimes within the road that obstruct traffic movement. Various side frictions include trading activities/street vendors/street trading, slow-moving cars,

pedestrians crossing or walking along the road, non-motorized vehicles, turning movement, on-street parking/stopping, bus stops/bus bays, land use, animal movement, roadside accessibility, etc. Side friction alters the speed and flow characteristics and reduces the capacity of roads [2], as it significantly impacts traffic movement in various ways, such as reduction in road capacity and carriageway width, impact on travel speed, instantaneous speed/spot speed, Time Mean Speed (TMS), Space Mean Speed (SMS), affecting road performance. Side friction results in increased traveler discomfort, reduced speed behind stopped vehicles and abrupt volume rises on the roadway, traffic jams and time delays, loss of Level Of Service (LOS), and impacts travel time and cost.

The main objective of this study was to examine the side frictional parameters in urban roads as stated by different studies, This study also evaluates the various viewpoints on side friction, how they affect traffic on urban arterial roads, and shows that various side friction activities have different degrees of impact on traffic behavior characteristics.

II. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

This study reviewed 90 studies from 1995 to 2022. However, most studies mainly focused on four side frictional parameters: non-motorized transport/slow-moving vehicle, pedestrian crossing (on or along the road), on-street parking, and street vendors/street traders. Less than 10% of the studies

focused on other side frictional parameters, such as animal movement and land-use activity. Most studies mainly dealt with how 6 side-frictional parameters, namely, non-motorized vehicle/transport and slow-moving vehicles, pedestrian crossing or moving along the road, on-street parking, street vendors/ traders, animal movement, and land use activity impact capacity, its estimation, and the level of congestion, the level of service, delay, and congestion factors. None of the studies dealt with the impact on travel time, the impact of travel speed on cost, journey speed, travel time, flow/capacity ratio, pedestrian activity, bicycle flow, TMS, and SMS. As a result, studies that aim to critically examine the side friction impact on Indian urban roads must incorporate multidimensional metrics. Due to inherent variations that may result in inaccurate conclusions, it is critical to separate the empirical research for developed and developing countries.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study systematically assessed the impact of side frictional in Indian urban roads through published studies in Elsevier Science Direct, IJRSET, IJSRSET, IJSEAT, IJRTE, Doctoral Thesis, and JSTOR databases from 1995 to 2022. Data analysis was performed based on the aim and objectives, and the results are discussed in the result and discussion sections.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature survey revealed that relatively little research has been conducted to date on the measurement of side friction and its detrimental effects on travel time, capacity, LOS, and other factors. Table I shows some Indian and international works that dealt with speed, capacity, LOS, travel time, etc. Although it is generally acknowledged that roadside activities impact the typical traffic stream's speed, capacity, and LOS and increase travel time, there are only a few studies recorded that make an effort to quantify these effects.

TABLE I. IDENTIFICATION OF SIDE FRICTION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Study
Pedestrian movement	[1-28]
On-street parking	[6, 9, 10, 12, 13, 23, 26, 28-47]
NMT/NMV/SMV	[1, 2, 6, 10, 13, 14, 22, 36, 38, 40, 46, 48-51]

V. PEDESTRIAN MOVEMENTS AS A SIDE FRICTIONAL PARAMETER

Pedestrian movements include crossing the street or walking along it. However, both negatively affect the traffic flow, as shown in Table II, and must be avoided. When pedestrians are forced to use the road alongside fast-moving cars because of no sidewalks, as is often the case on urban streets, the average speed of traffic on certain roads is slowed by 7.23km/hr [3].

VI. INFLUENCE OF PEDESTRIAN MOVEMENTS ON VEHICULAR SPEED

In [4], a pedestrian crossing traffic model was proposed for a city street. The volumes of traffic, speeds, and numbers of

people crossing in and out of traffic are the inputs to the model (1) for calculating the average speed of a certain vehicle type:

$$v_j = a_0 - [\sum(a_i \frac{n_i}{v_i})] - (a'k n_{ped}/v_j) \quad (1)$$

where v_i is the speed of a particular vehicle (m/s), v_j is the speed of various types of vehicle, a_0 is the regression coefficient for the free flow speed of the j_{th} type vehicle, a_i and $a'k$ are regression coefficients for the impact of density of a particular vehicle type and pedestrians on the free flow speed of the j -th type vehicle, respectively, n_i is the number of vehicles (v/s), and n_{ped}/v_j is the pedestrian-vehicle interaction factor (m/s).

TABLE II. IMPACT OF PEDESTRIAN MOVEMENT ON SPEED

Study	Pedestrian crossing vol.	Speed Reduction
[1]	100 peds/h	2.5%
[3]	100 peds/h	7.23 km/h
[4]	100 peds/h	4.21%
[5]	100 peds/h	3.52%
[6]	100 peds/h	0.76 km/h
[7]	100 peds/h	5.2%
[8]	100 peds/h	5.9%
[12]	100 peds/h	3.9%
[15]	100 peds/h	2.9%
[17]	100 peds/h	4.44%
[18]	100 peds/h	4.8%
[19]	100 peds/h	5.20%
[20]	100 peds/h	3.33%
[21]	100 peds/h	4.65%

If traffic flow stays the same, this study shows that all vehicle classes, except large trucks, slow down due to an increase in pedestrian cross-volume. However, the model's iteration technique is a disadvantage because it takes a long time to predict the speed. Many studies that estimated traffic speeds on urban roads treated the variable "pedestrian motion" as binary, either missing or present. Only a small number of studies went further and created speed models to measure the speed reduction caused by increasing the intensity of pedestrian activity. This study used a mathematical model to estimate that when the degree of pedestrian crossing along the road is approximately 1360 peds/h, a six-lane divided urban road's capacity decreases by nearly half of what it should be according to IRC recommendations [5]. Furthermore, this study concluded that if the volume of pedestrian crossing volume is around 100 peds/h, it will reduce capacity by 3.52%. The rules of the IRC recognize the connection between a variety of frictional roadside activities on the road and capacity. It is clear from this study that no precise methodology or guidelines have been provided to analyze or quantify each side friction effect on urban streets. In [6], a weighting factor for pedestrian mobility was suggested in addition to other side frictional elements when designing urban roadways, as shown in Table III.

A. Weightage Factors for Elements of Side Friction

In [6], five unique categories were used to categorize the side friction index range, a weighted sum of the side friction components, as: very low, low, medium, high, and very high. Free flow speed was found to be lowered by 18Km/h for two-lane undivided urban roads and by 16Km/h for two-lane

undivided interurban highways with significant side friction and short shoulders. On four-lane roads, it was discovered that the effect of side friction on the free flow speed was only somewhat alleviated. Other studies examined the impact of pedestrian crossings on the performance of an urban road segment.

TABLE III. SIDE FRICTIONAL PARAMETERS WEIGHTS

Event type	Weight factor (WF)
Rate of flow of pedestrian (W + C) (p/h/200m)	0.5
Parked vehicle and parking maneuvers (events/h/200m)	1.0
Entry & and exit of vehicle from road-side (veh/h/200m)	0.7
SMV (veh/h)	0.4

In [7], it was shown that if crossing maneuvers are carried out in an undesignated place, this has a greater impact on stream velocity. In [52], a video evaluation was carried out on two places on a split four-lane city street, where a median opening on one location allowed people to cross. This site's average speed was 7.7km/h slower than the other location, and it was also observed that friction on the sides of the road, such as parked automobiles and people waiting for buses or cars, can narrow the route and slow down the oncoming traffic. Compared to automobiles, pedestrians have less impact on the speed of two-wheelers due to their better maneuverability. This study found that pedestrian crossings caused a 2km/h drop in operational speed. Authors in [8] viewed "pedestrian cross movement" as a yes/no question, without investigating the slowed speed or the increased number of pedestrians crossing the road and without developing an adjustment factor or an empirical model. In [9], the usual speed on urban roads was calculated using the following mathematical model:

$$V_{sim} = 48.7 - 0.011 \times Flow - 0.015 \times Ped \quad (2)$$

$$V = 48.7 - 0.011x_1 - 0.015x_2$$

where V_{sim} is the average travel speed (km/h) from simulation runs, $Flow$ is the traffic flow per hour in both directions of travel, and Ped is the number of crossing pedestrians per hour and km. In [1], a speed model was used, finding that, among all side friction factors, the pedestrian cross movement has the greatest impact on speed. In [10], the "Volume of pedestrian crossing" was considered a design variable in the speed model shown in (3), and another important aspect that affects how fast incoming vehicles approach is parking and stopping on the road:

$$V = 39.46 - 0.13x_2 - 0.13x_3 - 0.28x_4 - 0.013x_5 - 0.15x_6 \quad (3)$$

where V is the average speed (km/h), x_2 is the volume of pedestrian cross movement (ped/h/200m), x_3 is the number of stopping buses (veh/h/200m), x_4 is the number of parking/stopping (veh/h/200m), x_5 is the number of entry vehicles into the street (veh/h/200m), and x_6 is the number of heavy vehicles (veh/h).

In [11], a study was conducted to identify how pedestrian flow on/along highways impacts traffic flow speed, and to analyze aspects that affect the speed of four-lane urban roads in developing countries. This study used videography to conduct preliminary surveys in Mumbai, Bangalore, and Thiruvananthapuram, developed a speed model from the resulting footage, and determined the categorized volume and friction factors. The study was carried out in two different phases. In the first phase, side friction was considered individually, while the second examined the combined effect of all frictions. Multiple linear regression models were used to predict speed individually and in heterogeneous situations, and the analysis was completed using a speed prediction model to evaluate variations in the friction parameters. In addition, the speed prediction model was employed to examine the pedestrian side frictional influence in variations, showing that pedestrian movement is a critical element. This study generated the speed prediction model in which traffic flow speed that is exacerbated by additional pedestrian obstructions can be predicted by:

$$V = 51.14 - 0.35n_{ped} - 0.61n_c - 0.19n_{2W} - 0.16n_{3W} \quad (3)$$

where V is the average speed (km/hr), n_{ped} is the number of pedestrians per minute, n_c , n_{2W} , n_{3W} are the number of cars, two-wheelers, and three-wheelers, respectively.

B. Speed Prediction Model for Stretches with Pedestrian Movement

In [12], a speed forecasting model was developed showing a 0.35Km/h reduction in speed for each additional pedestrian on the road per minute. Studies [2, 12, 52] investigated and analyzed how side friction variables affect travel time and capacity in urban environments, based on data obtained from numerous metropolitan regions, by performing macroscopic and microscopic analyses. These studies examined how every variable on side friction, such as pedestrians, bicycles, and stopped and parked vehicles, affected traffic flow, taking into account the distinct effects of each component. In [52], the relationship between various side friction parameters and the quality performance of traffic flow was investigated on different urban arterial roads, and the impact of varying side friction parameters on the speed-flow relationship was examined. This study delineated the study area roads based on the existence of extensive traffic flow situations using metrics such as the intensity of traffic flow, measured in volume/capacity ratio, traffic distribution based on direction, heterogeneous traffic scenarios, the proportion of heavy vehicles, and the extent of side friction. This study used ANOVA and regression models to determine the relationship between speed-flow and various side frictional characteristics and showed that side friction could affect speed and capacity. In [13], walking and crossing pedestrians were mixed with static roadside friction variables, such as vegetable markets, lay-bys, gas stations, mechanic shops, vulcanizing activities, and mini-marts, finding that T-junctions and bus stops are static features that contribute to traffic congestion. Static factors can be addressed by upgrading the geometric aspects of roads and this could increase the Level of Service (LOS). In [13-14, 29],

road friction elements such as pedestrians, vehicles stopping on shoulders and highways, parking, and access to roadside premises were found on urban roads in Asian countries, and side friction classes were developed for urban and interurban roads based on the weights assigned to each side friction element.

C. Influence of Pedestrians Movement on Capacity

The studies [15-16] are among the few that attempted to determine the effect of pedestrian cross-traffic movement on the capacity of metropolitan roads, as shown in Table IV. A 30–37% decrease in capacity was observed as a result of pedestrian cross movements in [15], while a 32% decrease was discovered in [16]. In [17-18], empirical models that link the volume and capacity of pedestrian cross-traffic movement were presented, such as:

$$C = 1550e^{\frac{-(1.75x_7 + 4.24)x_2}{3600}} \quad (5)$$

where C is the capacity (veh/h), x_2 is the volume of pedestrian cross movement (ped/h), and x_7 is the percentage of drivers willing to give way to pedestrians.

TABLE IV. IMPACT OF PEDESTRIAN MOVEMENT ON CAPACITY

Reference	Ped-crossing volume	Capacity reduction
[4]	Upto 200 ped/h	No impact
[20]	200 ped/h	Negligible
[4]	1550 ped/h	32%
[1]	1550 ped/h	9%
[6]	1550 ped/h	20%
[7]	1550 ped/h	23%
[8]	1550 ped/h	25%
[12]	1550 ped/h	19%
[15]	1550 ped/h	27%
[17]	1550 ped/h	30–37%
[18]	1550 ped/h	32%
[19]	1550 ped/h	32%
[20]	1550 ped/h	33%
[21]	1550 ped/h	14%
[24]	1550 ped/h	11.05-60.73%

In [18], recommended techniques were employed to calculate the side friction factors. The area affected by pedestrian movement can be utilized as a quality variable to calculate Equivalent Pedestrian Units (EPU) for all activities other than walking and serves as a side friction parameter. A speed prediction model was developed to determine the relationship between traffic flow and the individuality of side friction characteristics. The Chi-square test was used to validate the model at the test site and the 14% RMSE test result showed that the predicted speeds were statistically significant. In [19], two urban and interurban arterial roads were surveyed. Various side friction parameters were investigated for urban roads, including pedestrian movement through highways (ped/h), pedestrians crossing highways (ped/h/km), vehicle stops concerning whether the vehicle was stopped on the shoulder or the highway, vehicle parking or unparking (veh/h/km), and vehicles entering or leaving the road. Additionally, several riding frictional factors were examined on interurban roads, such as the number of people walking through and crossing the road (ped/h/km). Furthermore, the study considered the number

of vehicles stopping and parking maneuvers (veh/h/km), the number of vehicles entering or leaving the road premises, and the course of Slow Moving Vehicles (SMVs) (veh/h). After a detailed investigation, employing various parameters and providing their influence, the study showed that the free flow speed was reduced by a factor of 0.76 on interurban roads, and the capacity was reduced by 20%. Similarly, the rate on urban roads was reduced by 0.59. The study also improved the HDM-Q model for the prediction of speed and capacity with different side frictional characteristics. This study discussed several forms of roadside frictional parameters and their impact on urban road capacity, emphasizing the relationship between side frictional parameters, road capacity, and LOS. Studies [20, 21] showed that the decrease in the capacity of urban streets is influenced by the activity along the roadside and varies with the degree of side friction. Roadside activity, such as pedestrian movement, which is especially common in developing countries such as India, contributes to the loss of capacity on urban highways. In [13], static roadside friction factors were combined with pedestrians who were walking and crossing the street.

D. Influence of On-Street Parking on Vehicular Speed

On-street parking has primarily two effects on the capacity of a road. It initially narrows the highway by surrounding the traffic flow and vehicles squeeze into a smaller area slowing the streams, while frequent parking and unparking maneuvers complicate the problem, adding more congestion on the already congested metropolitan highways. These two effects of on-street parking ultimately reduce the capacity of metropolitan roads. The following subsections are devoted to presenting a range of findings on how and to what extent on-street parking affects the capacity of a road.

E. Reduction in the Average Speed due to the Presence of On-Street Parking on Urban Roads

The projected speed reduction due to on-street parking was reported to vary greatly, ranging from 15 to 44% or 5.1 to 21Km/h. This variation can be explained only by the existence of other elements that also significantly affect speed. Several studies investigated these variables and documented the way they alter the impact of on-street parking, as shown in Table V. In [28], it was found that larger roads were less likely to have side friction, in contrast to [6]. Several limitations apply to [6], as the roadside environment varied depending on the type of route, traffic data were collected over a brief period and there are some concerns about the sample size, the behavior of on-street parking was not explained, on-street parking was only taken into account as a categorical variable either as "presence" or "absence", there was no mathematical model to estimate this influence, and it was not evaluated with varied parking intensity. In [22], roadside parking occupancy was divided into three categories: (A) less than 30%, (B) 30-50%, and (C) 50-100% to address the problem, but there was no statistical difference between levels B and C on Free Flow Speed (FFS). Additionally, it was discovered that level A parking had little effect on FFS. Overall, the mean FFS of the streets without on-street parking was found to be 3.7kmph higher than the mean FFS of the streets with on-street parking up to 30% parking occupancy. As in previous investigations, the parking

parameter was once again considered a categorical variable. Some recent studies investigated the variations in speed decrease throughout a wide range of parking intensity. In [23], the average speed was calculated at various volumes to capacity (v/c) levels, observing an almost steady decrease in speed with increasing parking density. This study noticed a pattern of definite speed increase at 75% parking density, but it was disregarded. In [30], the average speed and parking density were also related, finding a 13Km/h decrease in average speed for every 100 vehicles per Km increase in parking density.

TABLE V. IMPACT OF ON-STREET PARKING ON SPEED

Reference	Speed reduction
[6]	5.1km/h
[6]	32%
[10]	5.5km/h
[19]	36%
[43]	15%
[48]	22%
[49]	19%
[50]	27%
[51]	44%

In [31], a quadratic model was developed to describe the association between parking intensity and average FFS, but the study was unable to determine why FFS increased with parking intensity. In [1], the average speed V (km/h) was determined for two- and four-lane undivided urban roads as a function of $FLOW$ (veh/h), carriageway width CW (m), shoulder width SW (m), and side friction $FRIC$ separately. This study showed that there is a strong correlation between on-street parking and traffic congestion. Urban roads account for nearly 14% of all congestion incidents, with parked or parking-related maneuvering cars being the main causes [27].

$$V = 79.6 - 0.008 \times Flow - 0.028 \times FRIC - 6.058 \times CW + 11.8 \times SW \quad (6)$$

$$V = 46.465 - 0.015 \times Flow - 0.011 \times FRIC + 1.36 \times CW + 5.393 \times SW \quad (7)$$

where V is the average speed (km/h), $FLOW$ is in lvu0/h, CW is carriageway width (m), SW is the shoulder width (m), and $FRIC$ is side friction.

In [32, 41], simulation-based techniques were used to evaluate FFS on urban streets and show how, even at low densities, on-street parking can anticipate the change of traffic states from free to congested flow. A Monte Carlo simulation was run with a low traffic density to simulate a free-flow situation, finding that traffic volume significantly lowers when the proportion of parking maneuvers increases, as a 35% proportion of parking maneuvers can eventually cause a 35% reduction in capacity. Parked cars could be the sole source of congestion on urban roads if they are parked irregularly or carelessly. Even a very small number of vehicles might result in significant congestion if they are parked disruptively for an extended time. Additionally, even when every available spot is almost full, a sizable percentage of vehicles still prefer on-street parking, and instead of paying for off-street parking, they would rather continue looking until a spot opened up [4]. When

these park-hunting vehicles are present in large numbers, they can significantly reduce both the capacity of urban roadways and stream transportation. Numerous studies investigated the capacity loss caused by on-street parking, and a significant capacity reduction of up to 90% was documented as a result of on-street parking. On-street parking is typically viewed as "missing" or "present", which is a common limitation of studies, while the effect of parking with varied capacity intensities has not been studied.

F. Decrease in Capacity Brought on by On-Street Parking on Urban Roadways

In [20-21], several forms of roadside frictional parameters were discussed along with their impact on urban road capacity, highlighting the relationship between side friction parameters, road capacity, and LOS. These studies showed that capacity reduction in urban streets depends on roadside activity and varies with side friction. Loss of capacity on urban highways is caused by a variety of factors, including roadside activity such as on-street parking, pedestrian movement, the presence of street vendors, a lack of lateral clearance and lane discipline, and diverse traffic, which is particularly prevalent in developing countries like India. In [53], a microscopic simulation model was developed to investigate the impact of bus stops on mixed traffic movement, focusing on reducing traffic flow rates. The model was validated by collecting traffic data at roadside bus stops and bus bays. This study evaluated the impact of bus stops, which act as side friction on urban traffic. Based on the collected data, several areas for further work were recommended, as very few studies examine mixed traffic situations [20, 53]. In [10], various side friction elements were considered, such as on-street parking, city buses stopping on the roadway, exit/entry vehicles, and vehicles about to turn. The study proposed a novel formula to update the Indonesian highway capacity manual to estimate the speed and capacity of urban highways with significant side friction.

In [21], three different side friction factors were used to conduct a survey and examine their impact on traffic quality performance: on-street parking, bus bay stops, and curbside bus stops. The results of this study showed an average speed drop due to side friction, a reduction in stream speed of 49-57% due to bus stops and bays, and a loss of 45-67% in speed due to on-street parking. Due to the high percentage of heavy vehicles, this study used dynamic and static PCU values. As a result of using these two different types of PCU values, a 10-53% capacity reduction was observed in bus bays and bus stops and about 28-63% due to on-street parking. Authors in [1, 19, 24, 32, 52] investigated urban arterial roads, finding that parked and stopped vehicles act as frictional elements that majorly impact traffic flow, LOS, speed, and delay. On-street parking has been highlighted as a substantial source of side friction in urban arterial roads, and there is a relationship between the presence of on-street parking and the reduction in stream speed. According to the extensive analysis in [24-25], the impact of on-street parking as a side friction element on urban arterial roads results in a slowdown in traffic flow ranging from 15 to 44% or 5.1 to 21km/h. In [54], parking density was considered a side friction element, and after conducting a survey and analyzing the data, the results showed that parking density on

urban arterial roads harms average traffic flow, with a decrease of around 13km/h for every 100 vehicles/km increase in parking density. In [12, 55], various types of roadside frictional activities on urban road links were examined, along with how these side frictional activities impact the speed and capacity of the urban roadway. Kerbside bus stops, bus bays, and on-street parking were some of the considered side frictional elements, and their impact on travel speed and reduction in capacity on urban arterial roads was investigated. The study concluded that the duration of the dwelling time of buses has an inverse impact on capacity, and more extended bus stops on the road act as interruptions for more extended time movement of traffic, affecting travel speed. In [34, 53] various types of side frictional activities were examined, using microscopic simulation models to evaluate how bus stops impact mixed traffic movement and its relation to the reduction in travel speed. In [24, 34], parked and stopped automobiles were studied, along with various other factors. These studies showed that parked and stopped vehicles are critical side frictional elements, as they harm more the regular traffic flow, speed, capacity, and LOS than other side frictional factors, such as pedestrian movements, etc.

In [13-14, 29], T-junctions and bus stops were characterized as static features that contribute to traffic congestion. On the other hand, static factors can be addressed by upgrading the geometric aspects of roadways to increase LOS. Roadside friction elements, such as pedestrians, vehicles stopping on shoulders and roads, parking, and access to roadside premises, were found along urban roads in Asian countries. Based on the weights assigned to each side friction element, side friction classes were developed for urban and interurban roads. In [35], motorcycle taxis were found to add another degree of friction when parking or loading and unloading passengers. In [13, 25, 35-37, 56], on-street parking produced a decrease in stream speed, ranging from 15 to 44% or 5.1 to 21km/h.

G. Non-Motorized Vehicles as a Side Frictional Parameter

All means of transportation that are not propelled by an engine or motor are referred to as Non-Motorized Transportation (NMT) or Non Motorized Vehicles (NMVs). While motorized vehicles are propelled by an engine, NMVs, including bicycles, e-rickshaws, cycle-rickshaws, hand-pulled vehicles, and animal carts, are propelled by humans or are dragged by animals.

H. Influence of Non-Motorized Vehicles on Vehicular Speed and Capacity

In [26], a 6-lane multi-directional road was investigated in Patna city and Pune city. Data were collected using videography to assess the speed variance in vehicle composition and traffic flow rate. This study presented a V-Q relationship for both sites, and variables of flow parameters at the mix flow level were acquired and correlated with the IRC standards. For each category, data on traffic characteristics, flow rate, peak hour factor, and spot speeds were reviewed. The results showed that the effective lane width in Patna city changed from 7.0 to 10.5m, resulting in a 57% capacity reduction and a 14% capacity decline due to the occurrence of NMVs, as shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI. IMPACT ON MNV ON SPEED & CAPACITY

Authors	NMV (%)	Capacity reduction (%)	Speed reduction in %
[2].	15-20%	55%	33%
[22]	14 %	57%	-
[48]	10%	-	20%

In [2], the influence of side friction on urban arterials was investigated. The authors examined numerous studies that characterized the effect of side friction in the decrease in urban arterial capacity, using NMV, passenger car unit, traffic, and shoulder activities as side friction parameters. The study concluded that the presence of side friction degrades the overall performance of traffic parameters, as an influence of NMT, up to 15-20% and reduced capacity and speed by 55% and 33%, respectively. Speed was identified as a critical issue affecting road capacity and LOS. This study showed that mixed traffic, composed of SMVs and NMVs, reduced the width of the effective road due to on-street parking, which acts as a barrier and reduces the road's qualitative performance. In [39], NMVs were also characterized as a source of side friction, and a speed model was proposed for this purpose, based on their ratio. According to the proposed model, a 10% rise in the NMV ratio would result in a 0.8mph (1.2kKm/h) reduction in average traffic flow speed. Furthermore, this study suggested including NMVs in the traffic volume classification because cycle rickshaws generate greater side friction than bicycles.

In [12], it was shown that when public transportation is poorly located or operates inefficiently, it forces the population to use their private vehicles, which causes an increase in heterogeneous traffic flow, slows down the speed of traffic flow, and increases travel time. The study showed that lateral clearance acts as a side friction activity on roads and affects the number of lanes in use and the average speed of vehicles. When traffic volumes are high, drivers tend to shift to the left lane more frequently, which means that the right lane is more likely to be affected by an obstruction. Road capacity and LOS may be affected by the narrowing of the roadway as the number of obstacles along the route increases [32]. Congestion and delays in traffic flow are often the result of poorly placed speed breakers, also known as "road friction" [52].

VII. DISCUSSION

This study examined the impact of various side frictional characteristics on the traffic performance of urban arterial roads, conducting a literature survey. The available literature was investigated under several constraints, such as various roadside activities which act as side frictional parameters and their impact on the traffic performance of urban roads. The side frictional parameters used in the literature are street vendors/traders, pedestrian crossings or moving along the road, NMTs including bicycles, on-street parking/stopping vehicles, land use, animal movement, and roadside accessibility. This study also focused on how various side friction parameters impact traffic performance, such as speed, capacity, and LOS. The considered studies were classified under different approaches, such as distribution by various side frictional parameters, impact on traffic performance, research methodology, and tools and techniques used for the analysis. These classifications identified various side friction parameters

and examined their impacts. The side friction activities identified were NMV/NMT/SMV, pedestrian crossing, street vendors/traders, and on-street parking.

In [38, 48-51], NMT/NMV/SMV dominantly affected traffic performance among all side friction parameters, reducing speed (instantaneous, spot, travel, journey, running, time and space means), capacity, and LOS. These studies used speed prediction models, multiple linear regression models, Chi-square test, PV2 analyses, and Greenshields speed-flow model to evaluate these impacts, and the degree of correlation between NMV/NMT/SMV and traffic performance was identified. The NMVs were classified into various subcategories, using the proportions of NMVs, bicycles, cycle rickshaws, handcarts, and the percentage of NMVs traveling beyond 20% of the roadway width from the edge. The results showed that the correlation between N-3 and N-4 is the highest among all subcategories, while cycle rickshaws and handcarts impact traffic performance more than all NMV/NMT/SMV subcategories. All side friction elements have a direct impact on the traffic performance of urban arterial roads. The NMV parameters N-1 to N-3 and N-5 had a strong positive association. Increases in an individual or the aggregate NMV volume may increase their propensity to move away from the street's edge, resulting in a strong positive association between N-5 and N-1 to N-3. The NMV proportion of N-1 was chosen as the design variable because it had the strongest relationship with the output variable RC compared to the other NMV factors. As a result, N-1 NMVs significantly impact the arterial road capacity. Furthermore, there is a positive relationship between NMVs and on-street parking O-1 [51].

In [10, 16, 17, 19], pedestrian crossing was the second most impacting parameter on traffic performance of urban arterial roads. In [10, 27, 41], it was shown that side friction activities impact LOS. Based on the average delay per stop for any pedestrian crossing at the standard CFI geometries analyzed, the results showed an acceptable pedestrian LOS. Several criteria were related to pedestrian mobility within the roadway, which impacts urban road capacity. The effects of pedestrian crossings on capacity and the correlation value of pedestrian crossing on traffic performance were discovered. In increased pedestrian volumes, people tend to deviate away from the edge of the street, resulting in a strongly positive relationship. In [32], pedestrian volume was divided into pedestrian volume along the roadway and pedestrian cross volume.

On-street parking, legal or illegal, is the third most affecting parameter. This activity affects traffic congestion, which directly impacts LOS, reduces roadway width, and impacts traffic flow speed. The capacity of urban arterial roads decreases as parking maneuvers increase [13, 41-42]. In [11], a correlation was obtained between the available effective width and the capacity reduction percentage. The capacity decline was 3.37% at 2.95% reduction in effective width, and 26.08% at a 21.81% decrease in effective width. In [28, 43-45], on-street parking was correlated with traffic performance. On-street parking can be characterized by the following metrics: parking density O-1, effective parking width O-2, parking area O-3, number of parking maneuvers O-4, and number of unparking plots O-5. As all on-street parking metrics were

found to have a substantial positive correlation (higher than 0.5), they aren't sufficiently independent to be used as integrated design variables. A choice of any parameter O-1 to O-5 can help in making a decision based on the correlation with RC, but O-2 is the best choice since it has the highest correlation with RC. The presence of street vendors and hawkers reduces road capacity, with delays that can exceed 30 minutes [46, 57].

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study critically reviewed the literature on three different side frictional parameters: NMV/NMT/SMV, pedestrian crossing, and on-street parking. The capacity of urban arterial highways decreases as the number of parking maneuvers increases. The effective width is connected with the capacity of a road. An increase in pedestrian volume walking along the road reduces road capacity. Similarly, the capacity of a road is reduced as the proportion of NMVs increases. Road capacity is reduced by 3.37% when the effective width of the road is reduced by 2.95%, while it is reduced by 26.08% when the effective width is reduced by 21.81%. Engineers can use the proposed models to estimate the section's capacity for any level of parking maneuvers in the traffic stream. Stretches with different side frictions and stretches with the combined effect of all components were tested for speed reduction. Side friction had a substantial impact on vehicle speed on urban roads and might also influence the extent to which individual elements influence speed. All traffic-related studies must include side friction factors for effective urban road planning. The capacity of the base and friction sections is determined using speed-volume data acquired from field data. Mathematically, there has been demonstrated that there is a link between pedestrian crossflow and capacity reduction. When the cross-flow of people is limited to 200pph, there is no influence on capacity, but when pedestrian cross-flow is increased to 1550pph, the capacity is reduced by 32%. The capacity figures in a segment that was only open to motorized traffic showed that a percentage of NMVs between 5-25% reduces the capacity of urban arterials by 3.60-35.82%. Rapid volume rises on a road result in congestion in traffic and time delays. LOS, vehicle speed, and capacity reduce while traffic volume and density increase before and after bus stops. Theoretical speed-volume curves are used to estimate the capacity, while the width of the road affects the base segment (PCU/h).

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A Hybrid Optimization Solution for UAV Network Routing

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ABSTRACT

An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) network specifies a novel type of Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET) in which drones serve as nodes and facilitate the retransmission of messages to their final destinations. Aside from its military application, it has recently begun to seep into the civilian sector. Similar to MANET and vehicular ad hoc networks, Flying Ad hoc Networks (FANET) are a subset of ad hoc networks. An FANET is different because it is founded on UAVs. Due to the characteristics of this sort of network, which is defined by a highly changing topology in a 3D environment, we must employ an adjusted configuration method to ensure good routing performance. Therefore, to deal with this problem, a technique that responds to any change in topology by always finding the best route is required. In this work, we propose a new protocol based on the hybrid optimization of the 2-opt heuristic and Honey Badger Algorithm (HBA), called HB-AODV. In order to locate its prey, a badger must move slowly and continuously while using scent markers and mouse-digging skills to catch it. In other words, the most efficient routes in terms of the number of hops are identified. Several simulations were conducted via the 3D version of Network Simulator (NS-2) on different deployment strategies. In comparison to AODV, DSDV, and AntHocNet, the obtained results demonstrated the proposed scheme's good performance in terms of quality of service metrics.

Keywords-ad hoc networks; UAV network ; honey badger algorithm; heuristic ; optimization ; 3D environment

I. INTRODUCTION

At present, wireless technologies offer interesting prospects in the telecommunications area. Ad hoc networks include a set of mobile entities that move arbitrarily, interconnected with each other by wireless technology and organize themselves without a previously defined infrastructure. This type of network has limited bandwidth, energy constraints, limited security, unpredictable topology, and heterogeneous nodes. There are many different ways that ad hoc networks can be put to use. We reference the most well-known example of their application, which is in the realm of military operations, in addition to other tactical applications, such as rescue and research missions. To retransmit messages to their final destinations, UAVs construct a novel type of MANET with drones as nodes [1]. Recent studies have been conducted on the development of collaborative multi-drone systems, where many drones work together to complete a mission with improved performance [2-6].

Many industries, including agriculture, arts (television, cinema, tourism development), cartography (public works, geo-referencing), environment (natural disasters, flora detection, counting and detection of fauna), health- (transportation of emergency materials and medicines), and fire safety, have found use for FANETs. In networks like MANETs, Vehicle Ad hoc Networks (VANETs), or FANETs, each node serves as a terminal or a router. An ad hoc protocol creation must take into account issues such as mobility, unexpected changes in topology, route maintenance, and energy management during packet routing. Routing is a critical problem in ad hoc networks since it ensures that any two nodes in the network are connected at any time, determines valid routes from a source to every precise destination, maintains these routes, and adapts them to topology changes. Proactive, reactive, and hybrid routing methods can be categorized based on how the routes are created and maintained throughout data routing (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Routing protocol classification.

Networks using proactive routing techniques ensure that all feasible destinations can be reached at any given time. Even if a route is never utilized, it is preserved. The paths' update messages interchange continuously, ensuring a permanent update of the routing tables. DSDV [7] and OLSR [8] are two examples of proactive routing protocols. In order to provide routing services in wireless networks, reactive protocols, or on-demand routing protocols, have been introduced. Protocols of this category construct and maintain routes when needed.

Routing information can only be obtained by conducting route discovery procedures when the network needs a route. AODV [9] and DSR [10] are two examples. Hybrid protocols, e.g. ZRP [11], try to combine the advantages of the two prior techniques in order to reap the benefits of both.

Observing nature has led researchers to adapt the principles observed in natural phenomena to develop effective algorithms for solving certain difficult problems. A new era is opening with nature-inspired (bio-inspired) algorithms, which are metaheuristics imitating nature to solve optimization problems. Bio-inspired approaches for solving problems have immense potential for research, specifically in the area of routing for all types of ad hoc networks. Ad hoc network routing issues can be resolved using bio-inspired algorithms. In the current article:

- FANET routing protocols are discussed, including traditional proactive, reactive, and hybrid routing methods as well as bio-inspired methods based on various metaheuristics.
- HB-AODV, a routing algorithm for UAVs networks, is described in detail.
- The proposed protocol has been thoroughly analyzed in the field of a FANET. The findings in NS-2.35, in its 3D version, simulations and deployment strategies, all with random waypoint mobility and Free-Space propagation model, are presented along with the analysis's main conclusions.

II. RELATED WORKS

For their study on traffic monitoring in FANETs, the authors in [12] relied on OSLR routing. From the simulation findings, it is deduced that the OSLR routing protocol is not optimal for low-density, highly dynamic FANETs due to its excessive overhead. However, OSLR allows quick connection and minimal delay. To ensure efficient and secure data transmission in UAV networks, the LTA-OLSR protocol (link-quality and traffic-load aware) was developed in [13]. The Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) of packets is analyzed to determine the quality of the link between a node and its neighbors. With channel contention at the MAC layer and the number of packets held in the buffer in mind, the authors devised a traffic load method to ensure light-load routing. Authors in [14] analyzed FANET connectivity using AODV routing. The simulation findings demonstrate that the AODV protocol delivers excellent network connectivity with a high packet delivery ratio while being responsive to a variety of network conditions. A hybrid of on-demand routing and the Reynolds method for keeping routes and connections up and running for data transmission was presented in [15] as BR-AODV in order to keep communication between UAVs stable despite frequent topology changes. The AODV protocol was used because it enables the UAV nodes to obtain routes on demand, making it ideal for real-time message transmission between UAVs. In terms of packet delivery ratio, end-to-end delay, and packet loss, BR-AODV outperforms AODV.

Link state routing is contrasted with a reactive routing strategy proposed in [16]. For the precision agriculture scenario, in which unexpected climate changes pose a serious

threat to crops and cultivation quality, the Reactive Flooding Routing (RFR) was proposed. UAVs are equipped with a specialized sensor that sends data to farmers in real time. UAV deployment was addressed in [17] to set up a wireless network for usage in situations such as disaster relief, search and rescue, and user connectivity in hostile or remote locations. To account for both ground-to-air and air-to-air propagation, the authors suggested a mathematical approach. Both the traditional CPLEX branch-and-cut algorithm and the hybrid metaheuristic Biased Randomized-Iterated Local Search (BR-ILS) were employed to optimize the mixed integer linear programming formulation. The latter was suggested as a means to simultaneously attain optimal or near-optimal answers at a lower computing cost. The experimental results demonstrated that BR-ILS significantly outperformed CPLEX solver for both small and large-sized instances in terms of performance metrics chosen on cases for which CPLEX could find an optimal solution. Due to the need to maximize the minimal data transmission throughput, the authors in [18] proposed a dual sampling bandwidth efficient transmission technique in relation to the UAV flight trajectory. They devised a recursive algorithm that alternatively optimizes bandwidth scheduling and UAV trajectory to get the best solution. Additionally, the algorithm enabling the Dual-Sampling (DS) technique has been iterated with power balance in mind at every step. While the DS approach consumed the second-least energy over extended time periods, it had the highest max-min average data rate. Authors in [25] employed the Genetic Algorithm (GA) to provide the best data operation routes and extend the life of wireless sensor networks by reducing energy consumption. The GA's performance was compared with that of TEEN algorithm.

In [26], the authors presented a self-organization-based clustering technique for cluster formation and management that was inspired by a behavioral study of Glowworm Swarm Optimization (GSO). The choice of the cluster head and the creation of the cluster both depend on the UAVs' connection with the ground control station as well as the value of their luciferin and the amount of energy they have left over. The technique for managing the cluster uses GSO's behavioral research by continually revising the luciferin value in accordance with the location of the UAVs. In addition, they provided a system for route selection for effective communication that depended on the neighbor range, residual energy, and location of the UAV. The harmony search method was modified in [27] to identify the best solution to the cell placement problem. The experimental results demonstrate that this algorithm is effective for resolving the investigated

problem and is characterized by good performance, solution quality, and optimality likelihood. In the same context, the research presented in [28] presents a Red Deer Optimization Algorithm Inspired by Clustering-based Routing Protocol (RDOAICRP) for reducing the problems of instability and mobility that arise during the process of distributing trustworthy data in FANETs. The proposed algorithm included the advantages of the Red Deer Optimization Algorithm for the selection of cluster heads and the generation of energy-aware clusters. In order to ensure effective communication, this system made use of a function for route recognition that was determined by the distance between the UAVs, the number of nearby neighbors, and the weighted residual energy. The feasibility of the proposed RDOAICRP was investigated using the benchmarked clustering-based routing protocols in terms of the cluster lifespan, the likelihood of successful packet delivery, the amount of energy used, and the amount of the time required for cluster building.

The Cluster Based Routing Protocol (CBRP), a single path MANET protocol, was improved in [29] to employ multiple paths. To lessen network traffic congestion and delay, the traffic will be split up across several paths. For both the multipath and single path CBRP routing protocols in MANETs, an analytical model was utilized to calculate the end-to-end delay and queue length. The analytical findings demonstrated the efficiency of the suggested plan. The authors in [30] proposed a bio-inspired clustering technique for FANETs called BICSF. This approach employs a hybrid process that combines GSO with Krill Herding (KH). The GSO method is used for the generation of energy-aware clusters and the selection of cluster heads in the system. In addition, an effective cluster management algorithm was presented that makes use of the behavioral research of KH. This algorithm makes use of genetic operators such as mutation and crossover in order to locate the UAV. The effectiveness of BICSF is measured in terms of the amount of time it takes to build a cluster, the amount of energy it uses, the amount of time it lasts, and the probability that a delivery will be successful using clustering algorithms based on Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO). Authors in [31] proposed an aware cluster-based route planning scheme, which is an application of Honey Badger Based Clustering with African Vulture Optimization based Routing (HBAC-AVOR) protocol for WSN and validated with comparative simulations in which it performed very well.

The discussed routing protocols are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. RELATED WORK

Ref.	Algorithm	Year	Advantages	Disadvantages
[12]	OLSR on FANET	2018	Quick connection, minimal delay	Excessive overhead
[13]	LTA-OLSR	2018	Light-load	Introduces delays
[14]	AODV on FANET	2018	Excellent network connectivity, with a high packet delivery ratio	Introduces delays
[15]	BR-AODV	2018	High packet delivery ratio, low end-to-end delay and packet loss	Excessive overhead
[16]	RFR	2019	High packet delivery ratio	Introduces delays
[18]	DS technique	2020	Highest average data rate	Consumes more energy
[26]	GSO on FANET	2019	Good cluster construction time	Introduces routing delays
[27]	HAS	2018	Good performance and optimality likelihood	Excessive overhead
[28]	RDOAICRP	2022	Good packet delivery, delay, and energy used	Excessive overhead
[31]	HBAC-AVOR	2023	HBAC-AVOR outperformed existing techniques with maximum lifetime	Introduces more overhead

III. THE HONEY BADGER ALGORITHM (HBA)

In the semi-deserts and tropical forests of Africa, southwest Asia, and the Indian subcontinent, a mammal with black and white fluffy fur called honey badger is found [19]. They are recognized for their brave temperament, a body length of 60 to 77cm, and a weight of 7 to 13kg. This adventurous forager eats 60 various kinds of species, including snakes, even though honey is its favorite food. It is an intelligent creature that can use tools. Only when mating with another badger does it venture out in the open. So far, 12 distinct badger species have been identified. Because cubs are born all year round, badgers have no specific breeding season. Even larger predators could not attack them given the courageous nature of the badgers. These animals can also easily climb trees. The badger uses a mouse's sense of smell to track down its prey. Digging begins the process of locating the prey's approximate position, and the animal eventually captures the prey. When searching for food, it can dig up to 50 holes in a 40-kilometer radius in a single day. The badger likes honey, although it is not very skilled at finding hives to investigate. It uses honey guides (birds) to find their hives and extract the honey. Due to this, a partnership is formed between these two animals, in which they work together to get honey from the hives by using badgers' long claws to open them. The mathematical formulation of HBA [19] follows.

1. Updating the density factor. Randomization is controlled by density factor (α), which ensures a smooth transition from exploration to exploitation. Equation (1) is used to update the decreasing factor, which decreases with time to reduce randomization.

$$\alpha = C * e^{(-t/t_{max})} \quad (1)$$

The t -value corresponds to time-varying randomization to ensure smooth transition from exploration to exploitation which is represented by the current iteration of the algorithm. This value is the principal parameter to calculate the decreasing factor α . $t_{max} = \max$ iterations possible, while C is a constant bigger or equal to 1 (default = 2).

2. Updating agent positions. The digging phase and the honey phase are the two phases of the HBA position updating process (x_{new}).

• Digging phase: A badger engages in activity resembling the cardioid form when digging. Equation (2) simulates the cardioid motion:

$$x_{new} = x_{prey} + F * \beta * I * x_{prey} + F * r_3 * \alpha * di * |\cos(2\pi r_4) * [1 - \cos(2\pi r_5)]| \quad (2)$$

The best position thus far discovered for the prey is at position x_{prey} . β is the honey badger's capacity to gather food (bigger or equal to 1, default = 6), di is the distance between the honey badger and the prey, r_3 , r_4 , and r_5 are different random numbers between 0 and 1. F works similar to the flag that changes the direction of the search. It is determined by:

$$F = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } r_6 \leq 0.5 \\ -1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where r_6 is a random number between 0 and 1.

The prey's odor intensity I , the distance between the badger and the prey di , and the time-varying foraging influence factor α , all have a significant impact on a badger's behavior during the digging phase. A badger may also experience any disturbance F while foraging, which helps it locate its prey even more accurately.

• Honey phase: To recreate the scenario where a badger follows a honey guide bird to the hive, do:

$$x_{new} = x_{prey} + F * r_7 * \alpha * d \quad (4)$$

where r_7 is a random number between 0 and 1. x_{new} denotes the badger's new location and x_{prey} denotes the prey's location. Equations (3) and (1) are used to calculate F and α , respectively. According to (4), a badger explores close to the location where x_{prey} has so far been discovered based on di . At this point, the time-varying search behavior (α) has an impact on the search. A badger might also discover a disturbance F .

The HBA flowchart, including population initialization, population evaluation and parameter update is given in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. HBA steps.

IV. THE PROPOSED HB-AODV APPROACH

The purpose behind using the HBA is that this technique seeks to create a balance amongst the exploration and exploitation stages by traveling the searching space rapidly and avoiding local optimal solutions. In addition, the HBA is

proven effective in resolving empirical problems with difficult searching spaces.

A. Mapping between Communication in HBA and FANET

An analogy between HBA (implemented in HB-AODV) and MANETs is shown in Table II, where the process mapping between them is carried out.

B. Detailed Approach

Our approach begins with the implementation of the HB-AODV protocol step by step and is followed by the creation of simulation scenarios, in order to test how the proposed routing protocol performs. We consider the AODV reactive protocol, the basis of our work is to improve its performance with the HBA metaheuristic. Finding the shortest path from the source node to the destination node is the objective of the HB. The proposed algorithm can be summarized in two phases:

TABLE II. MAPPING BETWEEN HBA AND MANETS

HBA	Ad hoc network
Honey badger	Node
Initial position	Source
Badger food	Destination
Possible path between honey badger and his food	Possible path
Shortest path between honey badger and his food	Shortest path between source and destination

1) 2-opt Heuristic Application for the Construction of the Initial Population

Source-to-destination topology explorations are carried out to identify a population of possible initial solutions as the starting point of the second step. The 2-opt heuristic [20], a powerful local search technique, is then performed. It is typically used to enhance a solution in hybrid techniques. The 2-opt method starts with a predetermined solution and then searches in its neighborhood to optimize the current configuration. The topology is detected following a request triggered by the source node in the event that it requires a route that is unavailable by sending RREQ (route request) reaching the destination d. This occurs when d is not known from before or if the current route to d has expired or is no longer functional. Following a set of requests acquired at the destination level, the population is constructed and processed by the HBA. We modified the format of the RREQ to keep track of the nodes through which it passed [21], by adding a record_path field (see Figure 3), which is a vector of intermediate nodes, its identifier is added in the record_path vector each time an intermediate node receives an RREQ to gradually build a solution.

Fig. 3. The modification of the RREQ packet.

The record_path field is an array containing the identifiers of the nodes starting with the source node (the first box) passing through the intermediate nodes which have received RREQs associated with the source. It ends with the destination

node (the last box) d, where the whole vector represents an initial solution.

In order to generate a population of solutions, the destination saves the RREQ packet header in record_path with the RREQs from the same source and destination. Its solution is sufficient to represent the network in the format of a graph to apply the graph theory. A graph $G = (V, E)$ can be used to depict an UAV network of communicating stations, where the vertex set V represents the stations and the edge set E the communication links [22]. We use this information to define the links between the nodes of the graph to build an adjacency matrix (see Figure 4), following the construction of a population, where each element is a set of links between nodes, being 1 if there is a link and 0 otherwise [26].

Fig. 4. An example of a graph and its adjacency matrix.

The last thing to do in this step is the application of the 2-opt heuristic. The latter checks each solution (route) in the initial population to see if exchanging two edges results in a shorter path during the improvement process. The algorithm keeps running until no further improvement is possible. The algorithm's flowchart is shown in Figure 5. The result is the initial population to be exploited in the second step.

Fig. 5. 2-opt heuristic improvement.

2) Finding the Best Solution by Applying HBA

The HBA metaheuristic is used on the population that was generated in the first step. A method for finding the most efficient path between two nodes is implemented. The number of hops between the source and the destination is the metric to be optimized. The value of the objective function is found in the hop_count field at the level of the RREQ request, and this value is suitable for the new solution calculated by (2) and (4). We have adapted these equations for our problem whilst always preserving the philosophy of the method. New solutions

are generated by using equations, with only intermediate nodes changing while the source and destination nodes kept unchanged. The process of our contribution is described in the algorithm shown in Figure 6. The result obtained by the equations is real and often invalid when compared with the adjacency matrix. In addition, our protocol provides results of positive integer type to approximate the solutions of integer value, followed by a repair process (repair algorithm) to guarantee, with high probability that valid solutions are obtained.

The result is not always valid. To repair invalid solutions, we have used a repair algorithm based on the adjacency matrix [21]. The steps of the repair algorithm are:

- The first step is to see if two consecutive nodes are connected, and if they are, they are kept. If not, move on to the next step.
- The second step is to see if the first node is connected to any of the following nodes. In this case, we only remove intermediary nodes. Otherwise, we'll move on to the next step.
- The final step is to look for a node that connects to the second node in the neighborhood of the first, and then establish a connection between the two.

An explanatory example is given in Figure 8.

Algorithm 1 HB-AODV

```

Input : Initial population, adjacency matrix AM ;
Output : Best route ;
Begin
Find the best route R in the population
for (each population solution m with random positions) do
  for (every x in m) and (x ≠ source) and (x ≠ destination) do
    Update the decreasing factor  $\alpha$  using Eq. 1
    if rand < 0.50 then then
      Update position xnew using Eq 2
    else
      Update position xnew using Eq 4
    end if
  end for
  Get a new route H
  Repair H using AM
  Update the best route by comparing R and H
end for
Save the best route to send packets
End
    
```

Fig. 6. The HB-AODV algorithm.

Fig. 7. An example of HBA application.

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Implementation Details

1) Simulation Platform

Using discrete event simulation, NS-2.35 is a freely available network simulator [23]. Using C++ and OTCL (Object Tool Command Language), NS-2.35 can be used on Windows or Unix systems. The development and implementation of low-level operations are done using C++, while code script simulation is conducted with OTCL (Figure 8). For the purpose of obtaining the third dimension Z for UAV movement, we added the 3D environment to NS-2.35 [24].

Fig. 8. General structure of NS-2.

2) Simulation Parameters

Table III lists the various simulation parameters.

TABLE III. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MOBILE NODES

Parameter	Value
Simulator version	NS-2.35
Routing protocols	AODV, DSDV, AntHocNet, HB-AODV
Topology	1500 * 1500 * 200
Channel type	Channel/WirelessChannel
Mobility model	Random WayPoint (RWP)
Radio propagation model	Propagation/FreeSpace
Packet length	512
Antenna type	Omni directional
Simulation time	300
Number of nodes	15, 20, 25, 35
Transport agent	UDP
Speed (min/max)	5 - 15 m/sec

3) Radio Propagation Model

Since there is only one direct channel between the transmitter and the receiver in the ideal scenario, we used the Free-Space Propagation Model to simulate this situation (FANET case). The communication range is shown in this form as a circle surrounding the transmitter. The receiver receives all the packets that are inside this circle. In any other case, it gets nothing.

4) Mobility Model

We used the RWP model wherein the mobility of the nodes is typically random, and all the nodes are distributed uniformly within the simulation space. The destination and speed of each mobile node that aims to move are random and limited to a well-determined interval. After moving, the mobile nodes are stopped for a determined time. Then, they move again in the same way as before, until the end of the simulation.

5) Performance Metrics

We opted to compare with other routing to verify the effectiveness of the proposed protocol HB-AODV. We mainly considered the following parameters as determining the routing performance:

- Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) is calculated by dividing the number of packets received at the destination by the number of packets sent from the source. The maximum network throughput is limited by the packet loss rate, which is specified by PDR. High PDR is an indication of a more reliable network. PDR is calculated by:

$$PDR (\%) = \frac{\sum_1^n CBR_{received}}{\sum_1^n CBR_{sent}} * 100 \tag{5}$$

- A data packet's average End-to-End Delay (E2ED) is the time it takes to move from source to destination. This metric is determined by subtracting the time it took for the source to transmit the first packet from the time it took it to reach its destination. During the latency of route discovery, the interface queues, the MAC layer retransmission delays, propagation time, and transfer are all included in this calculation. This step is critical in determining the amount of time it will take to discover a new route. Low values of E2ED denote the best possible performance for the network. E2ED is calculated by:

$$E2ED (ms) = \frac{\sum_1^n (CBR_{reception Time} - \sum_1^n CBR_{sent Time})}{CBR_{reception Time}} \tag{6}$$

- Throughput (Thr) is the rate of successfully received packets. Thr is calculated by:

$$Thr (kbps) = \frac{Delivery\ Pachets\ Number}{Reception\ Time} \tag{7}$$

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. PDR

Figure 9 shows how the PDR varies amongst the several routing protocols that were examined with a change in speed. PDR is higher in AODV and HB-AODV than DSDV and AntHocNet. As the number and the speed of nodes increase, HB-AODV continues to deliver satisfactory results that reach 96.73%, due to the use of the reactive approach, removes load from the network. On the contrary, in the proactive or hybrid approach, the update of the routing tables is periodic even if no request for connections (useless calculations are performed to reach destinations not requested) is made. The results of HB-AODV are better than those of AODV in terms of PDR in almost all scenarios. The chosen bio-inspired technique (HBA), dropped fewer packets than the other algorithms.

B. E2ED

Figure 10 shows that HB-AODV and AODV provide good performance in terms of the average E2ED with a change in speed. The reactive approach (with high mobility) finds a way to the destination more quickly. HB-AODV is better than AODV in some cases, due to the enhancement of the initial population using the 2-opt heuristic, and the use of a bio-inspired technique that is a fast and gives the optimum route between two nodes in reasonable time.

Fig. 9. PDR vs. UAVs density and speed.

Fig. 10. E2ED vs. UAVs density and speed.

C. Throughput

Figure 11 shows how the number of nodes affects the throughput with a change in speed of the investigated routing protocols. The AODV and HB-AODV outperform DSDV and AntHocNet in terms of throughput given the behavior of protocols of a reactive and/or bio-inspired nature (combined in the case of HB-AODV), which provides more stable links (large number of received packets) in a short time.

Fig. 11. Thr vs. UAVs density and speed.

By observing the results, we can conclude that when compared to the other routing protocols, HB-AODV provided an excellent compromise between the 3 performance criteria used. We finish by stating that the proposed solution is appropriate for the addressed problem.

HBA is a modern metaheuristic that mimics the foraging behavior of badgers. It shows some efficiency in terms of diversification and intensification whilst exploring the most promising areas using badger scents and by digging or tracking a honey guide bird. The efficiency, which is the goal of our study, was demonstrated by integrating this approach to deal with the routing problem at the UAV networks. We used the 3D version of NS-2 simulator to implement HB-AODV and evaluate its performance so that it could be compared with the existing protocols. Our protocol was compared with the previously mentioned protocols in terms of Quality of Service (QoS) metrics. We found that the proposed protocol performs

efficiently with good results. Its performance is impressive and could still be improved in the future. In addition, it provides packet transmission speed close to AODV's, which is more effective than AntHocNet and DSDV. The monitoring of the results indicates that the HB-AODV is an evolutionary protocol because it presents excellent findings with each extension of the network.

VII. CONCLUSION

The effectiveness of the reactive approach including the bio-inspired aspect for solving the routing problem in UAVs network has been demonstrated in this paper, especially the HB technique, which when implemented in AODV protocol performed better than other routing protocols of various categories (AODV, DSDV, and AntHocNet), due to the rapid reaction (route discovery) and the strength of metaheuristics, as well as the reactive approach that exploits the network only during a connection request. We proposed a new reactive routing protocol which is an improvement of AODV and is based on the bio-inspired honey badger optimization algorithm and 2-opt heuristic. Simulations were conducted in NS-2.35 with the use of the free-space propagation model, which was adequate for FANET features. In comparison to AODV, DSDV, and AntHocNet, the obtained results demonstrated a very high performance of the proposed strategy in terms of PDR, E2ED, and throughput. Future work will include improvements of this approach to support multiple paths for each transmission.

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An Economic and Environmental Study of a Hybrid System (Wind and Diesel) in the Algerian Desert Region using HOMER Software

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new of economic and environmental study of a hybrid system (wind turbine and diesel generator) in Algerian desert regions using HOMER software. The principal interests of the hybrid system are clean production at the place of consumption, the combined use of resources, energy storage, and supply security. Using an experimental device outfitted with Homer software, models were developed and successfully compared to reality. The obtained results confirm that the proposed system proved to be accurate enough to distinguish energy transfers and fast enough to enable optimizing the sizing and handling of the system's energy transfers. The purpose of this paper is to confirm the robustness of the HOMER software and to check the technical, economic, and environmental criteria of the integrated system.

Keywords-HOMER (Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources); Wind Turbine (WT); Diesel Generator (DG); hybrid system (wind-diesel); economic environmental analysis; Cost of Energy (COE)

I. INTRODUCTION

Algeria wants to play a role in the energy transition in Africa and its energy sector development is at a critical stage. The country is noteworthy for its relative size, wealth, location, gas reserves, renewable energy potential, and greenhouse gas

emissions [1-4]. Knowing the disposition of the hybrid systems integrated with renewable energy their contribution on the economic and environmental sides is to compensate the diesel generators in the isolated areas. In recognition of these environmental and economic advantages, several studies have

been carried out in this field. Among the most important of these programs is HOMER [5]. In [6], the analysis of a Wind Turbine (WT) and Diesel Generator (DG) hybrid system was conducted on the economic and environmental sides with HOMER by analyzing the Cost Of Energy (COE) and the quantity of CO₂ associated with this system when it works with the DG only and when it works in its general form. The comparison of COE produced for various cases of operation was used to prove the role of the storage systems. An open topic is the efficiency of the hybrid system to supply an independent electricity network in isolated areas and to provide all the conditions and requirements of the main electricity networks (quality - protection) to compensate for the use of standalone DGs. In these regions, the cost of delivering large production units, the cost of fuel, the difficulty to obtain it, and environmental risks are major setbacks [7-12]. From an economic and environmental standpoint, authors in [13] investigated the costs of electric energy when the system was only powered by DGs and the quantity of CO₂ associated in both cases with HOMER for the electrical installation with a continuous and variable load throughout the year as wind speed changed [13].

Quite recently, considerable attention has been paid to the optimization of hybrid renewable energy systems for off-grid rural electrification [14]. To solve this issue, many researchers have proposed similar methods of optimization in different countries, such as Chad [15] and Côte d'Ivoire [16]. The techno-economic assessment of a 100kW solar rooftop PV system for five hospitals in central and southern Thailand was studied in [17]. It is critical to provide an energy supply that can deliver uninterrupted electric power to meet the load demand as a hybrid system (WT and DG), as has been studied using WT models in different comparative models of wind characteristics between south-western and south-eastern Thailand [18].

Based on the approach presented in the literature, the purpose of this paper is to establish rules and tools for optimizing energy management and the sizing of a WT and DG, coupled to the network, and equipped with an electrochemical storage device. The optimizations will be carried out based on consumption and production deposit data. The optimization criterion will be economic with a view to minimizing the total COE of the system, from its installation to its use over a long period.

II. A REVIEW OF POWER IN ALGERIAN DESERT

The Algerian desert contains several regions in the south that rely in unconnected to the national transport network DGs for the provision of electric power [1]. Algerian isolated desert areas contain climate-convenient locations of renewable energy sources, particularly solar energy, and, to a lesser extent, wind energy (Table I). Figure 1 presents the seasonal variations in the amount of solar energy in the Algerian Sahara. Hybrid systems integrate renewable energy sources. They are being exploited in the Algerian Sahara, where hybrid compact energies and renewable desert areas are isolated. Figure 3 depicts some of the processes involved in the development of hybrid systems that combine renewable energies, i.e. solar and DG, wind and DG, and storage systems.

TABLE I. CHANGES IN WIND SPEED IN SOME ALGERIAN DESERT AREAS

Region	Wind speed (m/s)
Adrar	7
Tindouf	6
Tamanrast	5
Djelfa	4
Ghardaia	3

Fig. 1. Yearly produced power from the system: (a) PV and GD, (b) WT and DG.

Fig. 2. Produced power from various system resources to feed the network in desert areas in Algeria.

The system uses wind energy for the most part of the year due to its better performance compared to the other renewable energy sources (Figure 3). Other hybrid systems involved in feeding the network in these areas include the solar (PV) and DG systems in Tamanrasset, Tindouf, and Djelfa. Several isolated areas in Algeria are located in the desert. The majority of these areas rely on DGs to provide electrical power rather than utilizing hybrid systems that integrate renewable energies. Despite their high climatic efficiency, these regions use solar and private pneumatic energy to a lesser extent. So, Algeria's use of hybrid compact renewable energy systems is limited. Through this study, the effectiveness of hybrid systems for integrating renewable energy with environmental and economic advantages will be demonstrated in order to encourage its integration in the grid, especially in the isolated desert regions of the country. Hybrid system utilization and optimization are required in order to compensate the use of

DGs in the supply of electric power while maintaining the economic, environmental, and performance quality of these technologies [1].

Fig. 3. Seasonal variations of the amount of renewable energy in the Algerian Sahara: (a) Wind speed in Tindouf, (b) wind speed in Adrar, (c) temperature changes in Adrar, (d) solar energy in Adrar.

III. ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE WIND TURBINE AND DIESEL GENERATOR HYBRID SYSTEM

A. HOMER Software Overview

HOMER (Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources) is optimization and simulation software for the study of the production of multi-source energy (PV, wind, network, storage, diesel, etc.). It is mainly intended for mini-network simulation, whether connected or unconnected (off-grid). The main features of this tool are:

- Supports hourly load profiles as well as controllable loads.
- It is able to simulate the behavior of many pieces of production equipment (PV, wind, hydro, biomass generator, diesel, vegetable oil) or storage equipment (electrochemical, flywheel, fuel cells).
- Economic optimization of production systems by comparison of different configurations and architectures.
- Sensitivity analysis with respect to certain input parameters (oil prices, lifetime of the modules, solar radiation, load).

- The user receives the architecture and economic configuration based on HOMER's modeling. It is an aid to decision-making for the design of a mini-network.

B. Basic Standards of Economic Analysis in HOMER

All studies conducted to determine the economic dimensions of a specific installation focus on achieving the lowest possible cost while meeting the requirements (load). A very important factor is the COE which summarizes the standards of economic analysis on HOMER and is subject to the amount of energy produced and the amount of energy consumed at the time. HOMER determines the COE as the average cost of electrical energy produced for 1kWh and sets its value to a cost per kilowatt-hour per dollar (\$/kWh).

C. Description of the Electrical Installation Studied on HOMER

Figure 4 shows an electrical installation studied on HOMER including a type AOC 15/50 WT with a power of 65kW and 2 DGs with power of 150kW and 75kW, respectively. The AC power and the variable load equipment operate variably throughout the year at a rate of 4.9MWh/day, with the storage battery type S4KS25P having an estimated capacity of 1900Ah.

Fig. 4. The electrical installation to be studied on HOMER.

D. Load Variations

The variation of the load of the installation using HOMER is shown in Figure 5. The DMAP is a diagram that shows the time distribution for the variables of each hour during the day of the year using tinted rectangles depending on the value of this variable at that time, as shown in Figure 6. The DMAP is a diagram that depicts the breakdown for the variable at each hour of the year. The wind speed changes for the installation study, in which the property of the power produced by the AOC 15/50 WT is used in terms of wind speed, are shown in Figure 7.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Produced Power by the System throughout the Year

Figure 8 depicts the contribution of the WT to the electrical energy produced by the system, as it effectively compensates for the GDs most of the year, thus reducing the quantity of fuel used, which leads to a reduction in the cost of electrical energy and gas emissions, as shown in Tables II-IV.

Fig. 5. Daily load changes.

Fig. 6. Load variations: (a) Annual variations, (a) Load changes during October and November, (a) DMAP to load variations.

B. Economic Analysis

Table II shows the cost of the power produced and the quantity of fuel used for the hybrid system in various operating scenarios as calculated by the HOMER program. According to Table II, the significant difference occurs when the system is integrated with the WT (WT and two DGs) and is such that the cost of electrical energy in this case is up to 0.217\$/kWh with 131.527L fuel used and a total of 356,700.6kg/year gas emissions compared to their operation by DGs only. The cost

of gas emissions increased in this case to 0.273\$/kWh at 282.154L of fuel used per year, totaling 763.035kg.

TABLE II. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

Case study	Coefficients	COE (\$/kWh)	Diesel (L)
Two DGs, WT, Battery, Inverter		0.201	134.635
Two DGs and WT		0.217	131.527
Two DGs, WT, and Inverter		0.269	274.608
Two DGs		0.273	282.154

C. Environmental Analysis

Table III shows the amount of gases produced by the system over a year for various operating scenarios. The summary of the total gas emissions is given in Table IV,

showing the importance of the storage system in all operation cases. When the system runs by the DG and the storage system, the cost of electric energy is up to 0.269\$/kwh with 274.608L fuel used and 742857kg/year gaseous emissions.

Fig. 7. Characteristics of the wind turbine: (a) Property of the power for the wind turbine used, (b) wind speed according to the height of the turbine used, (c) changes in wind speed during the year, (d) average wind speed during the year, (e) DMAP for wind speed changes.

Fig. 8. Power produced by the system during the year. Environmental rating analysis.

TABLE III. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

Case study	Gas generated (Kg / year)	CO ₂	CO	Unburned hydrocarbons	Particulate matter	SO ₂	Nitrogen oxides
	Two DGs, WT, Battery, Inverter		356.011	879	97.3	66.2	715
Two DGs and WT		347.336	857	95	64.6	698	7.650
Two DGs, WT, and Inverter		723.354	1.785	198	135	1.453	15.932
Two DGs		743.003	1.834	203	138	1.492	16.365

TABLE IV. TOTAL GAS EMISSIONS

Case study of the system	Total gaz emissions (kg/year)
Two DGs, WT, Battery, Inverter	365599.5
Two DGs and WT	356700.6
Two DGs, WT, and Inverter	742857
Two DGs	763035

V. CONCLUSION

This paper analyzes the economic and environmental impacts of hybrid distributed generation (wind turbines and diesel generators) in the Algerian desert region. The dynamic models for the main system components were developed in HOMER software (Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources). The overall energy management strategy for coordinating the power flows among the different energy sources is presented in terms of Cost Of Energy (COE). The simulation results show that the studied hybrid power system with renewable sources has lower operating costs. The economic and environmental reasons and the technical challenges of connecting the hybrid system units in the Algerian desert region are analyzed based on cost factors. The obtained results demonstrate the significant economic and environmental benefits of the hybrid system, ensuring the continuity of electrical energy production throughout the year with the flow of load changes and wind energy at the same time, and the importance of the battery storage system. From these results, this work can be completed using dynamic models for the system components, namely the PV energy conversion system, fuel cell, electrolyzer, power electronic interfacing circuits, battery, hydrogen storage tank, gas compressor, and gas pressure regulator, to exploit the best optimal hybrid system in the Algerian desert region.

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A Three-Dimensional Parametric Study of the Effects of a Fault Rupture on a Multi-Story Building

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ABSTRACT

Earthquake events have shown that besides the earthquake forces, the interaction between the fault rupture and structures could cause a lot of damage. Field observations have revealed the need to design structures for fault-induced loading in regions with active faults. In this study, three-dimensional numerical simulation was carried out to evaluate the performance of a 20-story frame building subjected to the propagation of normal fault rupture. A parametric study was conducted with the propagation of the fault slip (h) with outcrop to the right ($s/B=-1.0$), at the mid ($s/B=0.5$), and left ($s/B=2.0$) of the raft. An advanced hypoplastic sand model (which can capture small-strain stiffness and stress-state dependent dilatancy of sand) was adopted. The Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model was used to capture the cracking behavior in the concrete beams, columns, and piles. The computed results revealed that the performance of the building due to the propagation of the normal fault rupture depends on the position of the outcrop of the rupture with respect to the building. Among the three simulated cases, the maximum differential settlement occurred when $s/B=0.5$. In each case, the lateral movement of the building caused inter-story drift which may induce distress in the structural components of the building. The beams and the columns of the first story were fully damaged in tension when s/B was equal to -1.0 or 0.5 .

Keywords-high-rise building; normal fault rupture; differential settlement; damage

I. INTRODUCTION

High-rise buildings are often planned in areas with intensive active faults [1]. Faults are lengthy areas where the layers of the ground are fractured and produce a zone. These fractures are often slant and are not vertical. Thus, it has become important to investigate the effects of fault rupture causing damage to the infrastructure [2]. With surface rupture there are many unknowns, so a probabilistic analysis is currently the best approach for the development of a range of expected displacements. However, the actual displacement that occurs with surface rupture can vary drastically from the expected values. To understand the failure mechanism of these

foundation systems, including strip and caisson foundations, experimental and theoretical studies have been conducted [3-8]. The position of the foundation relative to the bedrock fault and the magnitude of the bedrock fault movement were found to be crucial influencing factors. In addition, the presence of foundation systems modifies the path of fault ruptures, as the latter propagates from the bedrock to the ground surface. Pile foundations, as deep foundations, behave differently from shallow ones when subjected to faulting-induced deformation [3, 9]. In some specific cases [10], ground movement after an earthquake reportedly caused cracks and deformation of pile foundations. The mechanism behind this type of failure is significant for the performance of structures. Researchers have

recently developed theoretical methods to evaluate the behavior of piles subjected to soil movement induced by normal faults [5]. Although the main characteristics of fault-rupture propagation can be well described by advanced constitutive models, physical modeling is necessary to derive deeper insight into the interaction mechanisms and to offer experimental data for model validation. In addition, very limited field data are available to verify the theoretical methods because it is practically impossible to simulate a bedrock fault movement in the field. Among those numerical studies, however, responses of framed building to excavation were reported in some. However, most of the previous studies have focused on the fault effects on shallow foundations. Therefore, there is a gap of systematic research on the response of a high-rise building subjected to live load and resting on piled raft to the propagation of a normal fault rupture outcrop at different distances from the building. To obtain a satisfactory numerical model of twin excavation effects on high-rise buildings, the analysis needs to take into account the small strain non-linearity of the soil. In view of the aforementioned issues, this study aims to systematically investigate the effects of a normal fault rupture on an existing 20-story high rise building in sand. To achieve these objectives, three-dimensional finite element analysis was conducted.

II. CHARACTERISTICS OF A SOIL-PILE-STRUCTURE SYSTEM

A. General

With the prime objective of investigating the effects of propagation of normal fault rupture on a high-rise building, three-dimensional finite element analysis was adopted in this study. A normal rupture with dip angle of 60° was imposed at the proximity of a 20-story high-rise building which is resting on a 4×4 piled raft foundation in sand (with relative density, $D_r=70\%$). Figure 1(a) illustrates the general setup of the 20-story building founded on the piled raft.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic illustration of a normal fault rupture interaction with a high-rise building, (b) piles arrangement in the raft.

A 60m high, 15m wide 20-story concrete building with 3 spans in each direction was selected in study. The building was founded on a square raft, 15m wide and 1.5m thick, supported by a group of piles in a 4×4 configuration with center-to-center distance of 3.75m (see Figure 1(b)). The diameter (d_p) and the length (L_p) of each pile were 0.8m and 20m, respectively. A normal rupture (having length of fault slip $h=60$ cm) with dip angle of 60° with the horizontal was imposed at the proximity of the building. The prime objective of this study is to assess the impact of normal fault rupture on the 20-story building under dead and live loads. A live load of 5kPa was adopted in this study. With this adopted piled raft system, the numerical prediction showed that settlement of the building due to dead and live load was 8mm (0.8% d_p) which is within the limit of the allowable foundation settlement of 50mm [11]. The parametric study was conducted with propagation of the fault slip (h) with an outcrop to the right ($s/B=-1.0$), at the mid ($s/B=0.5$), and the left ($s/B=2.0$) of the piled raft (where s is the distance between the left edge of the raft and the emergence of the fault at ground surface and B is the width of the raft).

B. Features of the Building

Figure 2(a) shows the sections (with reinforcement details) of a typical beam and column of the high-rise building. The sections were designed by a routine design procedure using SAP2000 based on ACI. All the sections of the beams and columns are rectangular in shape having sizes of 230mm by 600mm and 230mm by 460mm, respectively. Each beam is reinforced with tension and compression steel bars. Tension and compression reinforcement consist of three 12mm diameter bars and three 12mm diameter bars, respectively. The bars have 60mm center to center spacing. These main bars are confined by 10mm diameter stirrups with center to center spacing of 125mm. Each column is reinforced with six 12 mm diameter main bars. These main bars are confined by the lateral ties having diameter 10mm at center to center spacing of 150mm.

Fig. 2. (a) Schematic illustration of a normal fault rupture interaction with a high-rise building, (b) pile arrangement in the raft.

C. Features of the Foundation

The building was founded on a 15m size and 1.5m thickness square raft supported by a group of piles in a 4×4 configuration with center to center distance of 3.75m (Figure 1(b)). The diameter (d_p) and length (L_p) of each pile were 0.8m and 20m, respectively. Figure 2(b) shows the section of a

typical pile with reinforcement. The pile is reinforced with six 20mm diameter longitudinal bars which are equally spaced around the pile. These bars are connected with spirals of 10mm diameter with center to center spacing of 200mm.

D. Characteristics of the Numerical Model

Figure 3 shows the finite element mesh developed in Abaqus software. The size of the mesh numerical run was taken as 120m×60m×30m. The different structural components of the building frame (i.e. beams and columns) and the slabs and raft were modelled by eight-node hexahedral brick elements (C3D8) and four-node shell elements (S4), respectively. The concrete damaged plasticity constitutive model is based on the fracture energy theory and the plastic-damage model of [11] is adopted to simulate the nonlinear behavior of the building frame. Elastic perfectly-plastic constitutive model is used to model the mechanical behavior of steel reinforcements. The detailed steel reinforcement and concrete material properties are listed in Table I. Eight-node hexahedral brick (C3D8) elements were used to model the soil and the piles, while two-node truss elements were adopted to model the steel reinforcements of beams, columns and piles. The size of the elements was chosen as 1.5mm.

TABLE I. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE FRAME OF THE BUILDING

Material	Constitutive model	Input parameter	Value
Concrete	Damage plasticity model	Mass density (kg/m ³)	2400
		Elastic Modulus (kPa)	3.15×10 ⁷
		Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.2
		Dilation angle (°)	30
		Eccentricity	0.1
		Stress ratio	0.666
		Ultimate strength ratio	1.16
		Tensile yield stress (kPa)	1.32×10 ³
Steel reinforcement	Elastic-perfectly-plastic	Compressive yield stress (kPa)	6.17×10 ³
		Mass density (kg/m ³)	7850
		Elastic Modulus (kPa)	2000
		Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.3
		Yield stress (kPa)	4×10 ⁵

Fig. 3. 3D finite element mesh (showing the building and the foundation).

Since the stress-strain relationship of soils is highly nonlinear even at very small strain and the stiffness of the soil depends on the recent stress or strain history of the soil [12], an advanced hypoplastic model was used in this study to simulate the behavior of sand. The basic hypoplastic soil model requires 8 material parameters to describe the non-linear behavior of the sand (ϕ'_c , h_s , n , e_{d0} , e_{c0} , e_{i0} , α and β). Parameter ϕ'_c is soil frictional angle at the critical state. Parameters h_s and n are used to describe the shape of limiting void ratio lines. Parameters e_{d0} , e_{c0} , and e_{i0} are reference void ratios of isotropic normal compression line, critical state line, and minimum void ratio line, respectively. The effects of soil relative density on peak frictional angle and shear stiffness are characterised by α and β . To consider the small strain stiffness and stress path-dependent soil behavior, the concept of intergranular strain is incorporated into the basic model [13], which includes additional five parameters (m_R , m_T , R , β_r and χ). By using the concept of intergranular strain, the modified hypoplastic sand model has the ability to capture effects of shear strain and stress path on soil stiffness. These five parameters were obtained by fitting the stiffness degradation curves of Toyoura sand obtained from the stress-path triaxial tests carried out in [11]. The model parameters were taken from [14]. The authors calibrated and validated all the parameters of the hypoplastic sand model against their centrifuge test results (which was performed to simulate excavation in sand). These parameters are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II. HYPOPLASTIC MODEL PARAMETERS OF SAND

Description	Parameter
Effective angle of shearing resistance at critical state: ϕ'_c	31°
Hardness of granulates, h_s	2.6GPa
Exponent n	0.27
Minimum void ratio at zero pressure, e_{d0}	0.61
Maximum void ratio at zero pressure, e_{c0}	1.10
Critical void ratio at zero pressure, e_{i0}	0.98
Exponent α	0.14
Exponent β	6
Parameter controlling initial shear modulus upon 180° strain path reversal, m_R	11
Parameter controlling initial shear modulus upon 90° strain path reversal, m_T	6
Size of elastic range, R	2×10 ⁻⁵
Parameter controlling degradation rate of stiffness with strain β_r	0.1
Parameter controlling degradation rate of stiffness with strain χ	1.0

The lateral coefficient of earth pressure (K_0) is estimated by the empirical equation $(1 - \sin \phi')$ proposed in [15], where ϕ' is the internal friction of soil at the critical state. Since the internal friction angle of Toyoura sand at the critical state is 31°, thus, the K_0 value is estimated as 0.5.

E. Soil Structure Interactions and Boundary Conditions

When modeling the excavation-pile-soil problem, one of the most important aspects of modeling Soil Structure Interaction (SSI) is to establish the interaction between the pile and the surrounding soil, because relative pile soil movement and separation between the raft and the soil can occur during the propagation of the normal fault rupture. To incorporate the interactions between pile-soil and raft-soil, surface-to-surface contact technique provided in Abaqus software package was

used. The interface was modeled by the Coulomb friction law, in which the interface friction coefficient (μ) and limiting displacement (γ_{lim}) are required as input parameters. A limiting shear displacement of 5mm was assumed to achieve full mobilization of the interface friction equal to $\mu x p'$, where p' is the normal effective stress between two contact surfaces, and a typical value 0.35 of μ for a bored pile was used in all analyses [14]. Roller and pin supports were applied to the vertical sides and the base of the mesh, respectively. Therefore, the movements normal to the vertical boundaries and in all directions of the base were restrained.

F. Fault Simulation

Since the primary goal of this study is the interactive mechanism between the fault rupture and the foundation, the bedrock was simulated as a rigid boundary. To model fault rupturing in the bedrock, the bottom boundary which corresponded to the surface of the bedrock was split into two parts, as shown in Figure. 3. The left part represented the hanging wall (i.e. the moving block), and the other part simulated the footwall. As Figure 3 shows, during the fault rupturing the boundaries of the hanging wall (i.e. the moving block) moved downwards parallel to the dip angle (i.e. $\alpha = 60^\circ$). Note that in order to satisfy the equilibrium, the bottom and left boundaries of the hanging block were subjected to displacement to simulate fault rupturing.

G. Numerical Simulation Procedure

Numerical simulations of three cases were carried out in the following steps:

- Step 1: Initial geostatic stresses were generated in the mesh by applying gravity load. The considered coefficient of lateral earth pressure was 0.5.
- Step 2: The piles were constructed and the raft was placed on the top of the pile group and soil deposit.
- Step 3: The 20-story building was constructed on top of the pile raft. A live load of 5kPa was applied on the floor slab of each story.

Displacements were applied to the base and side boundaries of the hanging wall to simulate a fault rupture in the rock layer beneath, with a dip of 60° (as shown in Figure 3).

III. INTERPRETATION OF COMPUTED RESULTS

A. Evolution of Differential Settlement of the Piled Raft with Propagation of the Fault Rupture

Figure 4 shows the differential settlement (between point A and point B, see the inset) with propagation of the fault slip (h) which has an outcrop to the right ($s/B=-1.0$), mid ($s/B=0.5$), and left ($s/B=2.0$) of the raft. The positive and negative values of the differential settlement represent the tilting of the building towards the hanging wall and the footing wall, respectively. It can be seen from the Figure that the induced differential settlement increased as the fault rupture propagated in all cases. However, no further increment in the differential settlement was induced as the fault rupture increased beyond 0.15m when $s/B=-1.0$, because the location of the outcrop of the fault rupture at the ground surface in that case is 15m away from the

left pile (discussed in section A), hence the piled raft is within the (stationary) footwall and further increase of the fault rupture height did not increase the height of the fault slope. On the other hand, the differential settlement kept increasing when $s/B=0.5$. This can be attributed to the outcrop of the fault rupture which crossed the middle of the piled raft and, as a result, the intensive shear zone due to the fault rupture passed through the middle of the raft (as discussed above). Therefore, the movement of the hanging (moving) wall tended to pull down the piles located to the left of the piled raft middle whereas the piles right to the piled raft middle were fixed within the (stationary) footwall. This results in the maximum differential settlement when $s/B=0.5$. Consequently, substantial counter clockwise rotation of the piled raft (hence building) was induced. The resulting differential settlement caused the distress not only in the RCC frame of the building but also in the pile head accompanied by the extensive yielding in reinforcement of the frame (also discussed above). In addition, significant shear force and bending moment were developed in the piles. In contrast to the two previous discussed cases ($s/B=-1.0, 0.5$), negative differential settlement was induced as the fault rupture propagated beyond 0.15m for $s/B= 2.0$, because the rupture crossed the toe of the right piles and outcrop away from the piled raft and the location of the outcrop of the fault rupture at the ground surface in this case is 15m away from the right pile, hence the piled raft is within the hanging (moving) wall. Consequently, the piles located at the right side of the piled raft were subjected to intensive shear strain. This led the piled raft to rotate clockwise (induced negative differential settlement). Among the three simulated cases, the maximum differential settlement occurred for $s/B=0.5$. The final computed differential settlement values were 14, 48, and -9 mm for $s/B=-1.0, 0.5$, and 2.0, respectively.

Fig. 4. Induced piled raft settlement during the propagation of the fault rupture.

B. Induced Lateral Displacement of the High-rise Building

Figure 5 illustrates the lateral movement of each floor of the building after the occurrence of the fault rupture for $s/B=-1.0, 0.5$, and 2.0. The general trend of the lateral deflection profile

is consistent with differential settlement. It can be seen that the lateral movement of each floor is larger than that of its bottom floor when $s/B = -1.0, 0.5$. The maximum lateral deflection occurred at the top of the building (the roof level of the 20th story), because the location of the outcrop of the fault rupture at the ground surface for $s/B = -1.0$ is 15m away from the left pile, hence the piled raft is within the (stationary) footwall and further increase of the fault rupture height did not increase the height of the fault slope. Therefore, the movement of the hanging (moving) wall tended to pull down the piles located to the left of the piled raft middle whereas the piles right to the piled raft middle were fixed within the (stationary) footwall, resulting in lateral movement of the building. Consequently, substantial counter clockwise rotation of the piled raft (hence building) was induced. The resulting lateral movement caused the distress not only in the RCC frame of the building but also in the pile head accompanied by the extensive yielding in the reinforcement of the frame.

In contrast to the two cases discussed above ($s/B = -1.0, 0.5$), the lateral movement of each floor is smaller than that of its bottom floor when $s/B = 2.0$. Moreover, the largest lateral movement was induced, due to the rupture that crossed the toe of the right piles and the outcrop away from the piled raft. The location of the outcrop of the fault rupture at the ground surface for $s/B = 2.0$ is 15m away from the right pile hence the piled raft is within the hanging (moving) wall. Consequently, the piles located at the right side of the piled raft were subjected to intensive shear strains zone. This led the piled raft to rotate clockwise (induced lateral movement). Among the three simulated cases, the maximum lateral movement values in the 20th floor of the building for $s/B = -1.0, 0.5$, and 2.0 were computed as 100, 270, and 260mm, respectively. In each case, the lateral movement of the building due to the occurrence of the fault rupture caused inter-story drift which may induce distress in the structural components of the building. The inter-story drift of the building can be defined as the ratio of difference of deflections of two storeys to story height.

Fig. 5. Induced lateral displacement.

C. Evolution of Damage (Damage Indices) in the Frame of the Building during the Occurrence of Fault Ruptures

The induced differential settlement and the lateral deflection of the building due to twin excavation can generate substantial plastic strains which can cause cracks in the building. As discussed above, the nonlinear (elasto-plastic) concrete behavior is simulated with a concrete damage plasticity model. In that model, compressive and tensile damage indices (DAMAGEC and DAMAGE T, respectively) range between 0 (no damage) and 1 (full damage). It was observed from the software output that both types of damage occurred only in the beams and the columns of the first story of the building. Therefore, the key locations were selected in the beams and the columns (see inset in Figure 6) to investigate the evolution of the damage during the occurrence of the fault rupture. Figure 6 shows the tensile damage index in the selected locations during the occurrence of fault rupture for $s/B = -1.0, 0.5$, and 2.0 .

Fig. 6. Tensile damage in beams and columns.

In Figure 6, it can be observed that the beams and the columns at the selected locations were fully damaged in tension when $s/B = -1.0, 0.5$. However, the damage evolved earlier when $s/B = -1.0$ than when $s/B = 0.5$. The resulting tensile damage occurred due to the substantial induced differential settlement (see Figure 4) and the lateral movement of the frame (see Figure 5). The induced differential settlement induced additional bending moment at the first story of the building. Because the frame of the building was rigidly connected to the raft, the additional bending moment resulted in tensile damages at the bottom of the column and both the left and right ends of the beam of the first story of the building. In contrast, the magnitude of tensile damage in the frame when $s/B = 2.0$ was smaller than that for $s/B = -1.0$ and 0.5 , due to the smaller differential settlement induced to the fault rupture and the rupture crossed the toe of the right piles and outcrop away from the piled raft. The location of the outcrop of the fault rupture at the ground surface for $s/B = 2.0$ is 15m away from the right pile, hence the piled raft is within the hanging (moving) wall. Consequently, the piles located at the right side of the piled raft were subjected to intensive shear strains. This led the piled raft to rotate clockwise (induced negative differential settlement).

The magnitudes of maximum tensile damage at each location were computed as 1, when $s/B=-1.0$ and 0.5 , implying that the building failed in both these cases.

In addition to tensile cracks developed in the frame of the building, crushing of the concrete at the base of the columns of the first story of the building occurs. The crushing of the concrete is expressed in terms of compressive index (DAMAGEC). Figure 7 shows the compressive damage index in at the base of the column (connection point between the raft and the column) during the occurrence of the fault rupture when $s/B=-1.0$, 0.5 , and 2.0 . Similar to tensile damage index, the compressive indices are larger when $s/B=-1.0$, 0.5 than when $s/B=2.0$. However, the development of crushing of the concrete initiated the fault rupture increased beyond 0.3m in every case. The concrete crushing resulted due to the additional bending moment due to the differential settlement of the building. The resulting additional bending moment due to the fault rupture induced stress in the concrete at the base of the column. The magnitudes of the compressive damage (0.4) are much less than that of the magnitude of full damage (1.0), implying that the failure of the frame occurred due to tensile cracks at the base of the frame.

Fig. 7. Compressive damage in columns.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on sand density and the high-rise building geometry, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The performance of the building due to the propagation of the normal fault rupture depends on the position of the outcrop of the rupture with respect to the building.
- Among the three simulated cases, the maximum differential settlement occurred when $s/B=0.5$. This can be attributed to the outcrop of the fault rupture which crossed the middle of the piled raft and as a result the intensive shear zone due to the fault rupture passed through the middle of the raft. Therefore, the movement of the hanging (moving) wall tended to pull down the piles located to the left of the piled raft middle whereas the piles at the right of the piled raft middle were fixed within the (stationary) footwall.
- In contrast to $s/B=-1.0$, 0.5 , negative differential settlement was induced as the fault rupture propagated beyond 0.15m when $s/B=2.0$ because the rupture crossing the toe of the right piles and the location of the outcrop of the fault rupture at the ground surface for $s/B=2.0$ was 15m away from the right pile, hence the piled raft was within the hanging (moving) wall.
- The lateral movement of each floor is larger than that of its bottom floor when $s/B=-1.0$ and 0.5 . The maximum lateral

deflection occurred at the top of the building (the roof level of the 20th store). In every case, the lateral movement of the building caused inter-story drift which may induce stress in the structural components of the building.

- The beams and the columns of the first story were fully damaged in tension when $s/B=-1.0$, 0.5 . In contrast the magnitude of tensile damage in the frame when $s/B=2.0$ was smaller.
- In addition to tensile cracks developing in the frame of the building, concrete crushing occurred at the base of the columns of the first story of the building.

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Arabic Sentiment Analysis for Twitter Data: A Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Social media platforms have a huge impact on our daily lives. They have succeeded in attracting many people to spend time communicating and expressing themselves. Twitter is a social media platform that could be considered as a source of public opinion about products, services, and events. Sentiment analysis is the art of studying public feelings about certain topics, which may be positive, negative, or neutral. This paper provides a systematic review of Arabic tweet sentiment analysis on papers published from 2012 to 2021 in digital libraries including IEEE Explorer, Science Direct, Springer Link, and Google Scholar. The main aim of this systematic review is to investigate the trends in the topics reported and to highlight potential new research lines. To achieve that, three main stages were implemented: planning, conducting, and reporting the review. Our findings suggest the need for an open-source large Arabic tweet dataset that can be used by researchers. Also, it was found that researchers have used various classification techniques, which led to different results.

Keywords-arabic sentiment analysis; systematic review; social media; twitter

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media are considered a major source of news, marketing, and advertisements. These platforms have huge numbers of users, which are increasing daily. The number of global monthly active users of Twitter recently averaged to 330 million people [1]. Users express their feelings and opinions using short messages called tweets and they can refer tweets to other users, called followers. Therefore, the content of these platforms may be evaluated to extract insights from these data.

Sentiment Analysis (SA), also known as opinion mining, is one of the natural language processing fields. SA focuses on analyzing text to extract people's opinions and emotions and identify these as positive, negative, or neutral [2]. Many researchers have directed their attention to this area and while most research has focused on English, Chinese, and other Indo-European languages, few studies have addressed SA in morphologically rich languages, such as Arabic. The number of Arabic texts existing on the internet has seen a significant increase. According to Internet World Statistics, Arabic is the fourth most commonly used language on the Internet, after English, Chinese, and Spanish, reaching 5.2% of all internet users [3]. Due to the exponential growth in Arabic internet users and Arabic online content, Arabic SA (ASA) has gained the attention of many researchers over the last decade [4].

In this paper, we systematically review the literature in the field of Arabic tweet SA.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE SYSTEMATIC REVIEW METHOD

In this review, the systematic literature review methodology proposed in [5] was followed. It consists of 3 main stages: planning, conducting, and reporting the review. The main aim of this review is to perform a comprehensive review of ASA for Twitter data and cover the methodologies and approaches of data processing, SA techniques and approaches that have been used in the literature, and the challenges ASA faces. Figure 1 illustrates the steps of the systematic literature review methodology, which are explained in more detail in the following sections.

A. Research Questions

In the planning phase, the research questions are specified. In this study, the research contributions are highlighted through answering the following Research Questions (RQs):

- RQ1: What are the different machine learning techniques that have been applied/proposed for ASA?
- RQ2: What data pre-processing techniques have been used for Arabic tweets in ASA research?

B. Search Strategy

After determining the research questions, the search terms and data resources are specified. First, to identify the search terms, the research questions were analyzed and the following search strings were developed: "Arabic", "Arabic text",

"sentiment analysis", "Twitter", and "tweets". Moreover, the Boolean operators "OR" and "AND" were used to search for all possible combinations of these terms. We covered only ASA studies using Twitter data as the application.

Fig. 1. The steps of the systematic literature review methodology.

Secondly, a search was carried out on the following six academic databases: IEEE Explore, ACM, Springer, ScienceDirect/Elsevier, Google Scholar, and Wiley. These were chosen as they are the top databases in the computer science field. The titles, abstracts, and keywords of all indexed papers were searched using the search terms we developed, and the search was conducted on studies from 2012 up to 2021.

TABLE I. SEARCH RESULTS

Database	Relevant search results
IEEE Explore	38
ACM	4
ScienceDirect/Elsevier	9
Springer Link	5
Google Scholar	16
Wiley	1
Total	73

C. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

In this stage, inclusion and exclusion criteria were delineated to thoroughly assess the relevance of the potential primary studies. These were:

- Include papers written in English only.
- Include papers published in journals, conference papers, and book chapters.
- Include papers published from 2012 to 2021.
- Include papers that focus on Arabic text analysis on the Twitter platform. Exclude papers that focus on all other platforms.
- Exclude duplicate papers.
- Exclude secondary studies (i.e. literature reviews).

- Exclude papers that are not peer-reviewed, such as technical reports and theses.

D. Data Extraction

After collecting the data from the above-mentioned databases and extracting the relevant papers based on our inclusion and exclusion criteria, 73 papers were selected for analysis. Table I shows the search results. The papers were classified based on the type and the year of publication. From 2012 to 2021, a gradual increase in the numbers of conference papers and published journal articles was noted, as shown in Figure 2. The number of publications peaked in 2019, with 19 identified publications in total. The average number of publications is around 9 studies per year over the past 10 years. The most common form of publication was conference papers (42), followed by journal articles (30), and 1 book chapter, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Number of publications per year.

Fig. 3. Type of publications.

III. PRIMARY STUDIES AND DISCUSSION

SA is a set of processes that are applied widely in computer science studies to analyze and examine semantics, words, and tweet syntax to determine the emotions in the text [6]. The main purpose of SA using Twitter data is to classify tweets into three polarities (positive, negative, or natural) based on the statements or words contained in that tweet [7]. In this section, the main finding of this systematic review regarding ASA using the Twitter platform are presented and discussed.

A. Arabic Tweet Sentiment Analysis Approaches

We found that ASA approaches can be classified into three main categories: corpus-based, lexicon-based, and hybrid-based. Table II summarizes the reviewed papers based on their

categories, The following subsections discuss each of these separately.

1) *The Corpus-based Approach*

In this approach, the main aim was to collect and use the available Twitter dataset to build machine learning models in order to determine the sentiments of each tweet. Our findings indicate that the most commonly used methods are the supervised learning approach, and in particular Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree (DT), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Ensemble classifiers (bagging and voting), and deep learning [2, 8-11]. Moreover, a few studies used an unsupervised learning approach [12, 13].

In the supervised learning approach, authors in [8] used SVM, multinomial NB and rule-based classification algorithms to classify sentiments based on their collected dataset of 134,194 Arabic tweets, which had been labelled automatically using emojis. They concluded that SVM outperformed the other algorithms used, reaching an accuracy of 75.7%. Authors in [9] investigated the state-of-art English SA techniques and used them for solving the problem of ASA through a Machine Translation (MT)-based approach. They first collected Arabic tweets (a total of 937 tweets), translated them into English, and then applied Stanford sentiment classifiers to classify each tweet, either as positive or negative sentiment. By comparing this method with lexicon-based techniques, they found that their MT sentiment approach outperformed the other approaches. Authors in [2] utilized machine learning algorithms and neural networks to perform SA on health services. They collected Twitter data using trending hashtags about health services, and their results show that the accuracy of the SVM approach outperformed the other algorithms, including CNN and DNN. Authors in [10] collected Arabic tweets related to political events in 2018. They analyzed their dataset using machine learning and data mining algorithms such as NB, SVM, DT, KNN, and ensemble classifiers. They observed that ensemble, and in particular the voting classifier, outperformed the other techniques. Authors in [14] examined tweets on women's issues in Saudi Arabia. They collected their dataset from popular Twitter hashtags, and classified them as positive, negative, and neutral. The NB algorithm was used to automate classification. Authors in [15] built a predictive model and applied it to data gathered from the Gulf region to predict whether a user's tweet indicated a depressed or non-depressed user. They applied the common machine learning algorithms, RF, NB, AdaBoost1 and linear SVM, and concluded that linear SVM outperformed the other classifiers reaching an accuracy of 87.5%. Authors in [16] aimed to investigate sentiments from tweets that were collected from popular hashtags about women's problems in Saudi Arabia. The data was pre-processed and classified, and their results indicated that the NB algorithm achieved greater accuracy than the other classifiers available in Weka.

In a deep learning approach, authors in [17] proposed a Multi-Channel Embedding Convolutional Neural Network (MCE-CNN) for Arabic sentiment classification and thoroughly assessed it using balanced and imbalanced datasets. The MCE-CNN was trained on different sentiment features, including word and character n-grams. Their proposed model

achieved high accuracy. Authors in [18] proposed a sentiment and emotion system for regression and classification tasks using the CNN and LSTM algorithms. They implemented different feature extraction techniques, a word embedding model (Aravec), a document embedding model (Doc2vec), and a set of semantic features such as Deepemoji and unsupervised sentiment Nerous. Their proposed system outperformed the SVM unigrams baseline model's performance applied to the SemEval2018 dataset [19]. Authors in [20] developed a new architecture based on CNNs and RNNs for handwritten Arabic word understanding and classification. The most powerful technique for analyzing Arabic tweets and social media data is the CNN technique. The use of a sub-word-level RNN module and a character-level CNN module helps in gaining a better understanding of handwritten text. This technique is efficient, especially with a short text written in an uncontrolled language format. An approach to tweet-based word correction that uses Arabic text classification to find abusive accounts on Twitter was proposed in [21]. The classification of Arabic tweets without stemming was investigated and compared to classification using stemming. This approach proved better than other popular approaches to Arabic word correction on Twitter. Authors in [22] proposed the classification of Arabic tweets as positive or negative using an improved algorithm. The approach consists of two phases. In the first phase the dataset was prepared by normalization, while the second phase involved classifying tweets using a DMNB approach. The experimental results showed that this improved approach reached an accuracy level up to 87.5%.

In an unsupervised learning approach, authors in [12] used sentiment classification of people's opinions during the Covid 19 pandemic using k-means and mini-batch k-means algorithms on Arabic and English datasets. They observed that k-means classification takes longer than mini-batch k-means classification. Authors in [13] aimed to assess the integration of the similarity functions with pre-processing methods for clustering tweets. K-means clustering algorithms were used to cluster Arabic tweets into two clusters: positive and negative. The results showed that the stemming (pre-processing method) with the Kullback-Leibler divergence function is more effective than other competitive pre-processing techniques.

Other studies compared different approaches. Authors in [23] compared the corpus-based and lexicon-based approaches. For the first approach, they collected 2000 Arabic tweets and used SVM, NB, KNN, and DT algorithms. For the lexicon approach they manually built a lexicon of 3479 words. They concluded that the SVM approach outperformed the others. Authors in [24] applied three types of classification methods (supervised, unsupervised, and hybrid learning) on tweets collected randomly from three different domains (sports, politics, and social). The results indicate that hybrid learning is better than the supervised or the unsupervised approaches in terms of classification accuracy.

2) *The Lexicon-based Approach*

This approach, considered to be unsupervised learning, aims to build a sentiment lexicon of terms and then compute the sentiment of a certain text based on the sentiment values of the terms composing it. Our findings indicate that there are two

different lexicon-based approaches used in ASA: the Double Polarity (DP) [25] and the Simple Polarity (PL) [26] approaches. The latter is based on counting both the positive and negative words in each sentence, while the DP approach is based on the frequencies of positive and negative words in the sentence. In [26], a PL lexicon was built manually, consisting of 3982 adjectives from two Arabic datasets that were classified as positive, negative, and neutral. The authors applied PL to classify individual tweets on the basis of including positive, negative or neutral adjectives. They called their system SAMAR and they concluded that using PL improves the accuracy of ASA. Authors in [27] proposed a

Weighted Lexicon-Based Algorithm (WLBA) for the Saudi dialect. In their approach, the weight of each word was calculated based on the corpus, not upon the lexicon. Moreover, they compared their proposed algorithm with the DP and PL algorithms, and concluded that WLBA outperformed the DP approach, but not the PL approach.

The lexicon-based approach depends on the creation of a lexicon. We found that there are two different methods of lexicon creation: manual and automatic. The manual method is the most popular and it provides more accurate results, but is domain-independent [27-29].

TABLE II. REVIEWED PAPERS CLASSIFIED BASED ON THE APPROACH USED

Approach	Paper	Dataset size	Algorithms	Features	Language
Corpus-based	[8]	134194 tweets	SVM, MNB and rule-based	TF-IDF	MSA, dialects
	[10]	14419 tweets	SVM, NB, NT, KNN, Ensemble (bagging, voting)	TF-IDF	Unspecified
	[14]	9096	SVM, NB	BOW, bi-gram, and tri-gram	Dialects
	[15]	6122 tweets from 89 users	RF, SVM, NB, Adaboost and liner SVM	Unigrams, negative features	MSA, Gulf dialect
	[17]	ASTD dataset, 10000 tweets	MCE-CNN	Word and character n-grams	MSA, dialects
	[20]	ASTD	Stacked model with CNN and gated recurrent unit	Character level model	MSA
	[37]		NB, SVM, multinomial logistic regression, KNN		Dialect
	[64]	ASTD (3,315 tweets)	SVM, recursive neural tensor network	Character n-gram model [3,5], Word n-grams [1,4], count of negated words and positive and negative words based on lexicons from [65-67]	Egyptian dialect
	[68]	2591 tweets	SVM, NB, KNN		MSA and dialects
	[2]	2026 tweets	SVM, NB, LR, CNN, DNN	TF-IDF, word frequency, word2Vec	MSA
	[70]		SVM		MSA, dialects
	[71]	17748 tweets	SVM	TF-IDF	MSA, dialects
	[72]	SemEval, AraSenTi, ASTD	Deep learning, SVM	Word embedding (AreVec), set of related lexicon features	MSA, dialects
	[73]	2.3M tweets on news	Semi-supervised technique		MSA, dialects
	[9]	937 tweets	Machine translation approach, Stanford sentiment classifier		MSA
Lexicon-based	[69]	22550	SVM, NB	Binary model	Jordanian dialects
	[26]	3015 tweets, 2798 tweets	Polarity lexicon of size 3982		MSA, dialects
	[28]	2000 tweets on politics and arts	Manual lexicon of size 4815 words		MSA, Jordanian dialects
	[9]	937 tweets		Machine translation approach, Stanford sentiment classifier	MSA
	[52]		SVM		MSA, dialects
	[73]	5400 tweets and emoji data			MSA, Saudi dialect
	[74]	6000 tweets	Rule-based algorithm	Semantic and lexicons features	MSA, Tunisian dialect
Hybrid-based	[75]	Merging of two available lexicons (MPQA and ArabSenti) with manually collected lexica	SVM, LIBSVM	Stems, Twitter language independent, semantic features	Egyptian dialects
	[53]	4800 tweets	Semantic orientation, SVM, NB	unigram, bi-gram, tri-gram	Egyptian dialect
	[30]	Lexicon of 5376 words	RF, SVM, Max-Ent, bagging, boosting, ANN, DT, NB	POS and lexicon features	MSA, dialect
	[31]	1500 tweets and lexicon of 452 words	Bagging and boosting		MSA, dialect
	[18]	SemEval2018	Regression and classification tasks, CNN, LSTM	Word embedding (AraVec), document embedding (doc2Vec) and a set of semantic features	MSA, Egyptian and Gulf dialects

3) The Hybrid-based Approach

Authors in [30, 31] worked on SA for Arabic tweets using a hybrid approach. In [30], a combination of the lexicon and corpus techniques for ASA was proposed. The authors used a lexicon to replace words in sentences with their sentiment labels to enable classifier algorithms to consider rare and important words in the corpus. They concluded that this hybrid approach outperformed the corpus-based approach, reaching an accuracy of 96.3%. The hybrid approach in [31] comprised machine learning algorithms, the bagging and boosting approaches. The authors started by building a unified dataset of text and audio which was later converted to text, to analyze sentiments. However, some of the audio analysis was not accurate, which had a negative effect on this prediction approach because some audios contained laughing and yelling. Authors in [32] proposed an incremental learning system for sentiment classification. Their system was able to update a lexicon with any upcoming changes. In fact, this system integrated the machine learning and lexicon approaches to improve the accuracy of the proposed system, and it has been tested with different datasets.

B. Tools Used to Collect Arabic Tweets

As we only focus on the Twitter platform, we found various techniques have been used to collect Arabic tweets. Most studies used Twitter's official Application Programming

Interface (API) to collect Arabic tweets [2, 33-39]. Other studies used trending hashtags to extract data manually [8, 40]. Authors in [16] used Keyhole and Netlytic tools to collect their data from Twitter. Authors in [41] developed a Python script connecting with Twitter's official API to collect their data. Authors in [42] developed a Twitter data grabber tool, a small desktop application using C# to connect to the Twitter API to collect their data. Authors in [10, 15] used a Java library called Twitter4J, which can be connected to the Twitter API to collect Twitter data. Authors in [43] used a tool called Archivist4 to collect tweets using hashtags. In fact, Archivist4 can be used to archive and analyze visual tweets using hashtags, usernames, Boolean, and complex search terms.

C. Data Pre-Processing

Data pre-processing is a technique used to prepare data for sentiment classification [78, 79]. The preparation involves cleaning, formatting and sorting the tweets that have been collected from Twitter to be saved in a dataset ready for analysis [45]. Data pre-processing for Arabic tweets includes several steps to clean the data, such as tokenization, stop-word removal, text cleaning, Part Of Speech (POS) tagging, normalization, and stemming. Table III shows the most commonly used methods for data pre-processing found in the papers we reviewed. We note that normalization, text cleaning and tokenization were the most frequently used techniques in these papers. These techniques are described below.

TABLE III. DATA PRE-PROCESSING METHODS USED IN THE REVIEWED PAPERS

Reference	Tokenization	Stop word removal	Text cleaning	POS tagging	Normalization	Stemming
[23]	∅	✓	✓	∅	✓	✓
[10]	✓	✓	∅	∅	∅	✓
[51-53]	∅	✓	✓	∅	✓	✓
[15]	✓	✓	✓	∅	∅	✓
[44, 46]	✓	✓	✓	∅	✓	✓
[54]	✓	∅	∅	∅	✓	∅
[55]	✓	∅	✓	∅	✓	∅
[56]	✓	∅	∅	✓	✓	∅
[42]	✓	✓	∅	∅	✓	✓
[45]	✓	∅	✓	∅	✓	✓
[57]	✓	✓	✓	∅	∅	✓
[8]	∅	✓	✓	∅	✓	∅
[58]	✓	✓	∅	∅	✓	∅
[47, 59]	✓	∅	✓	✓	✓	∅
[30]	∅	∅	✓	∅	✓	∅
[60]	∅	✓	∅	∅	∅	✓
[66]	∅	∅	✓	∅	✓	✓
[61]	✓	∅	✓	∅	✓	∅
[62]	∅	✓	✓	∅	✓	✓
[32]	✓	∅	✓	∅	✓	∅
[63]	∅	∅	∅	∅	✓	✓
[33]	∅	✓	✓	✓	✓	∅

- Tokenization is the process of the segmentation of a stream of text to segments consisting of words or phrases. Each segment is called a token and each token has a meaning and can be used for the later stages of SA [46].
- Stop-word removal involves removing words that have no meaning for polarity classification [42], such as (من، على).
- Text clearing: Arabic tweets may have inconsistent text and can be noisy or incomplete. Therefore, data cleaning tends to remove noise, complete missing values, or correct inconsistent state data [33]. This also including removing Arabic articles [8], such as (ال، بال، كال).
- POS tagging involves mapping words to their tags, such as verbs, nouns and adjectives. There are different types of machine tools for POS tagging [47].

- Normalization: Most reviewed papers applied normalization to Arabic tweets, which includes removing repetitive letters or normalizing similar letters to the same letter [42], such as the letters (لـ) which is normalized to (ل).
- Stemming is the process of transforming a word to its base forms, while the meaning of the words is preserved. For example, in Arabic the word (يكتبو, يكتبو) is replaced with (كتب). As the Arabic language has a complicated morphological structure, stemming is considered a very difficult task. Our findings indicate that there are two popular stemming methods used in ASA: light10 stemming [48] and Khoja's stemmer [49].

IV. CHALLENGES IN ARABIC SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The Arabic language is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. It is the most frequently spoken and written language in the Arab world, especially in the Middle East and North African regions [77]. The Arabic language has 26 letters and is written from right to left. It uses diacritical marks that denote correct pronunciation of a word. In addition, diacritical marks are used to distinguish words that have the same letters but different meanings. Moreover, the Arabic language has three forms: Classical Arabic, which is seen in religious and very formal texts, Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), which is associated with modern news media [77], and dialect or informal Arabic, which is the Arabic spoken with different local accents across the Middle East and North African countries, and has no particular standards [6]. According to [50], Saudi Twitter covers 90% of dialects, compared to MSA. As a result, it is very challenging for researchers to construct models of Arabic text classifiers to use for SA. In terms of translation, when translating Arabic to English, good results may be obtained with MSA, but Arabic dialects are difficult to translate because their meaning is purely context-related [27].

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The Twitter platform is considered a rich source for sentiment analysis. People use social media platforms to express their opinions of products, services, or political events. In this paper, we have provided a systematic review of Arabic tweet sentiment analysis. We have reviewed the main techniques that can be used to prepare the data for sentiment analysis. Moreover, we have presented some of the major tools used for sentiment analysis of Arabic tweets. However, this review has some limitations: it was carried out using six academic databases and we only included papers that were written in English. Also, we did not include a secondary studies paper.

We note from the papers we reviewed that researchers have used various classification techniques, which has led to different results due to the lack of experiments applied to a standardized dataset. In the future, researchers should narrow their research domains and focus on Arabic dialects. They should also investigate complex classification techniques such as ensemble machine learning techniques and deep learning models. Lastly, we noticed that there is a lack of open-source

large Arabic tweet datasets that can be used by researchers. Therefore, more work needs to be done in building large open-source databases of Arabic tweets.

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Temperature Evolution and Heating Rates of Biomass undergoing Ablative Pyrolysis

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ABSTRACT

The ablative reactor may be employed to enable fast pyrolysis to produce bio-oil from relatively large-sized biomass samples. Ablation mainly involves direct compressive force and conductive heat transfer between a hot surface and the biomass materials. Temperature evolution and heating rates are important operating factors in the biomass thermal conversion process. In this work, experimental and analytical investigations were carried out for different vertical dimensions of the biomass samples (2-20mm) and hot plate temperatures (400-550°C). It was shown that the thermal characteristics of the biomass were mainly affected by the transient conditions. It was observed that volatile release occurred during the transient heat transfer periods. It was found that at the maximum hot plate temperature of 550°C, the highest heating rate that could be achieved by ablation was more than 600°C/min.

Keywords-ablation; agricultural residues; clean energy; heat conduction; thermal conversion

I. INTRODUCTION

Biomass is a major source of alternative energy [1, 2]. Utilization of biomass is normally conducted via thermal routes such as combustion, gasification and, slow pyrolysis [3, 4]. Rapid decomposition of biomass can occur at moderate to high heating rates. Fast pyrolysis is a thermochemical process to convert lignocellulosic biomass materials into liquid products. In this reaction route, biomass temperature is raised to 400–600°C in non-oxidizing atmosphere at very fast heating rates (>10–200°C/s) and short reaction times (typically < 2s), releasing volatile gases that can be rapidly condensed into organic liquids or bio-oil [5].

There have been many fast pyrolysis reactors studied including fluidized bed, free-fall, auger, and ablative reactors. Most reactor types require the biomass materials to be grinded into very small sizes of about 1.0mm or less whose cost

represents a significant portion of the total processing cost. Ablative pyrolyzer is a type of moderately fast pyrolysis reactor where raw materials are directly subjected to a hot plate. Thermal erosion or melting of the biomass occurs at a contact layer as it is directly pressed against a hot solid surface. This enables high rates of conductive heat transfer, making the process fast, cheap, and highly efficient. The ablative reactor is able to utilize large pieces of wood [6]. Nonetheless, ablation is surface area controlled, hence, upscaling could be a tough challenge. Several ablative pyrolysis systems have been developed and studied in the past 40 years. The first pioneering work on ablative pyrolysis was conducted in [7]. It was shown that woody biomass could be thermally decomposed by ablation, producing a vaporizing layer of degrading solid. Subsequent experiments on ablative heat transfer were carried out with focus on wood pyrolysis in [8, 9]. Authors in [10] developed an ablative pyrolysis reactor with multiple blades

and reported bio-oil yield of up to 68% w/w. Recently, an ablative reactor for pyrolysis of thick woodchips was developed, achieving bio-oil yield of about 60%. Authors in [11, 12] employed an ablative pyrolyzer to produce bio-oils from various agricultural residues under atmospheric and vacuum conditions. It is clear that temperature characteristic, heating rate, and heat transfer between organic materials and heat sources are considered very important for pyrolysis product distribution. In ablative pyrolysis, it is known that there are steep temperature gradients occurring on the thick biomass surface. This impression could be speculative since there was no or very little data to back up the claim. So far, a modest amount of experimental results regarding the biomass heating characteristics during ablation heat transfer is available in the existing literature.

Therefore, in this work, ablation of thick biomass samples was carried out on a hot plate. Heating rates and temperature profiles at different depths of the biomass samples were measured, evaluated and presented, along with the simplified analytical heat conduction results. Information generated from this work will be useful in adopting the ablative pyrolysis technique to produce organic liquids or bio-oil from biomass.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Thermal Ablation Experiments

The feedstock used in this study was hemp hurds (*Cannabis sativa* L.) collected from Chiang Mai's countryside, Thailand. This plant is a stout and aromatic herb. Its stalk is slender and hollow. It was used in this work to represent an example of agricultural residue available locally. Its physical density was about 85kg/m³. Dirt and other impurities in the feedstock were removed by washing with water, and the feedstock was then naturally dried in sunlight. The moisture content was determined to be 9-10% w/w. The dried samples were cylindrical shaped with about 2mm diameter. Afterwards, they were cut into 40mm long pieces which were stored for later experiments. Figure 1 illustrates the experimental setup. The thermal decomposition of hemp samples was carried out at the hot plate temperatures of 400, 450, and 550°C at 4 different depths of 2, 5, 10, and 20mm inside the biomass samples from the hot plate surface. The hot plate was heated by a cooking gas flame whose temperature was monitored and controlled via an electronic control system actuating the amount of fuel gas flow. The exterior of the reactor chamber except the bottom was fully insulated to minimize heat losses. Biomass temperatures were measured using a type K thermocouple connected to a data logger at 500ms sampling rate. Nitrogen was used at a flow rate of 500mL/min to purge releasing volatiles. Each test case was repeated for at least 3 times.

B. Simplified Heat Conduction Modeling

A simple analytical study was performed for the heat transfer between the hot plate and the cylindrical shaped biomass sample. Conduction is considered as the main heat transfer mode and can be expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r}\right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2}\right) + Q_g = c_p \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where Q_g is heat generation inside the particle.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic diagram, (b) a pictures of biomass on the hot plate, and (c) the experimental setup of the ablative reactor.

We assume that heat is transferred only in one dimension (z-axis) and the system has no heat generation inside the particle. Thus, the expression of conductive heat transfer is equal to the internal energy transfer within the sample body:

$$-kA \frac{dT}{dz} = \dot{m} c_p \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the temperature evolution could be expressed by:

$$T(t) = T_1 - e^{-\left[\frac{kA}{\rho C_p v z}\right]t} \quad (3)$$

where $T(t)$ is the biomass temperature, T_1 is the hot plate temperature, k is the thermal conductivity of the biomass sample, A is the area of biomass surface in contact to the hot plate, ρC_p is the heat capacity of the biomass sample, v is the volume of the biomass sample, z is the depth, and t is the time.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 illustrates the temperature evolution and heating rates in the biomass sample at various vertical locations from the surface contact and temperatures of the hot surface. Overall, the temperature of the biomass body appeared to approach the hot surface temperature exponentially. It changed rapidly at the beginning, and after that it slowed down and stayed stable, like the result of the conduction model [13]. There were two main temperature regions: firstly, the transient or unsteady state occurred in the starting period and subsequently, the constant temperature region or steady state.

The starting time of the steady state was affected by the dimension of the biomass sample. For instance, at 450°C, and the distances between the sample and the hot plate of 2, 5, and 10mm, the steady state was reached within about 170s, while at 20mm, it took around 200s. Small sized biomass was likely to reach the steady state quicker than the bigger samples. Similarly, at the condition described by 450°C, 20mm, the steady state was reached in 160s. On the contrary, at the higher temperature of 550°C, the time to reach the steady state was not obviously affected by the biomass particle dimension. Furthermore, the short depth can approach the hot plate temperature easily. For high heat transfer, smaller sized samples are desired as anticipated. However, in practice, the size of biomass may not be very small because of its processing cost [6]. A reasonable size of the biomass samples should be carefully considered for practical use.

Regarding the hot plate temperature, it had significant effect on conductive heat transfer. Low temperature setting would take longer time to reach the steady state than high temperature setting. As shown in Figure 2, for a distance of 20mm at 400°C, it took 160s to reach the steady state while at 450 and 500°C, it took 140 and 120s, respectively. Similarly, for a fixed depth of 20mm, the time it took to reach steady state was 200s at 400°C, but only 120s at 500°C. The temperature and time data can be used to derive the corresponding heating rates. The factor is useful in determining if slow or fast pyrolysis occurs [14]. Overall, the heating rates were found to fluctuate radically during the transient period, before reaching zero heating rate at the steady state. For instance, at 400°C and 10mm distance, the heating rate (purple lined spots) approached zero in 180min as the temperature (green line) became constant.

The smaller sized biomass samples appeared to experience higher heating rates than the bigger samples, as expected. This was due to the fact that smaller sized samples have lower heat resistance [15], hence, greater heat transfer in the initial stage than the larger sized samples. For example, the heating rates at the time of 20s and hot plate temperature of 450°C were approximately 5.0, 4.3, and 3.6°C/s for the biomass samples

with depths of 2, 5, and 20mm, respectively. At 140s, the biomass samples with depth of 2 and 5mm had the heating rates reaching zero, while the sample with depth of 20mm exhibited a heating rate of about 2°C/s. In addition, it was observed that the release of volatiles from the biomass decomposition occurred mainly during the transient period and it appeared to stop when the steady state was reached [16]. This observation could be useful in designing and operating the ablative pyrolysis system to obtain the fast release of volatiles. At the highest temperature setting and relatively small sized biomass samples of 2 and 5mm, the maximum heating rates obtained were about 11°C/s or 660°C/min at 20 and 50s, respectively. Meanwhile, at the sample depth of 10mm for the same maximum hot plate temperature setting, the heating rate of nearly 10°C/s or 600°C/min was achieved. All the above are considered as fast pyrolysis [14].

Fig. 2. Temperature profiles and heating rates at different pyrolysis temperatures and depths inside the biomass macroparticles.

In this work, a simplified heat conduction analysis was also performed to predict the temperature evolution during the heat transfer between the hot plate and the biomass sample. The results are shown in Figure 3. The temperature profiles show the two regions of transient and steady states. Different biomass sizes spend different time to reach the steady state. The higher depths or bigger biomass samples take longer time

than smaller counterparts in the transient period. For instance, the biomass with 2mm depth reaches the steady state within 100s while the one with 10mm depth takes about 300s to become steady. Volatiles from biomass thermal degradation are released in the transient period. For practical applications, it may imply that larger sized particles undergo longer transient period which could release more volatiles for higher bio-oil yield. Nonetheless, it should be noted that even though the analytical results showed similar patterns of temperature evolution, their values are markedly different. This may be caused by the fact that the biomass properties (density, thermal conductivity, and heat capacity) used in the analytical study differ from the real values [17]. Furthermore, ablative heat transfer in thick biomass samples may not be simply approximated by a one-dimensional, transient heat conduction model. A more complicated heat transfer model should be adopted in future investigation.

heating rates for various biomass types and shapes when undergoing ablative pyrolysis. It can be seen that while the reactor temperatures were in similar magnitude (365 to 800°C), our work appeared to show higher maximum heating rates, up to 660°C/min, compared to 174 and 20°C/min reported in [13] and [6], respectively. This was possibly due to the fact that the biomass size used in this work was the smallest among the compared works. It is also likely that their temperature gradients were not measured directly, but estimated from temperature measurement at points some distance further from the surface than the location done in this work.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF BIOMASS TYPE AND SHAPE, AND THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ABLATIVE PYROLYSIS BETWEEN THIS WORK AND OTHERS

Biomass material (shape)	Heating rate (°C/min)	Reactor temperature (°C)	Dimensions (diam. × length) (mm)	Ref.
Pine wood (chip/rod)	7 – 20	500	2×2 – 35×200	[6]
Beechwood (rod)	n/a	400 – 800	2 – 10 (dia.)	[8]
Pine wood (cubic)	n/a	400 – 600	4.75 – 6.25	[10]
Hard wood (sphere)	50 – 174	365 – 606	n/a	[13]
Hemp residue (rod)	30 – 660	400 – 550	1×2 – 1×20	This work

n/a: not available

Fig. 3. Simulated temperature profiles at different pyrolysis temperatures and depths inside the biomass macroparticles.

Table I shows a comparison, between this work and those available in the literature, of reactor temperature and realized

IV. CONCLUSION

Temperature profile and heating rate are essential factors defining the biomass pyrolysis type of slow and fast pyrolysis. In this work, measurements and simplified analytical studies of biomass heating characteristics for different biomass dimensions and hot plate temperature were carried out. From the findings, it was shown that there were two temperature intervals of transient and steady states identified during the biomass thermal decomposition. The small size and high hot plate temperature enabled the biomass sample to reach the steady state within a very short time. Releasing of volatiles occurred mainly during the transient period. At the highest hot plate temperature of 550°C, the biomass underwent the maximum heating rate around 11°C/s or 660°C/min, in the fast pyrolysis range. This information is useful for utilizing the ablation technique for pyrolysis reactor design.

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GIS-based Selection of Appropriate Landfill Sites: The Case of Communal Grouping in Batna, Algeria

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ABSTRACT

The choice of a landfill site is a complex process that includes various, social, environmental, and technical, parameters which require the processing of a large amount of spatial data. The Geographic Information System (GIS), integrated with its functionalities, represents a powerful and well-adapted tool to solve this problem. This study uses the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to solve the problem of quantifying qualitative features. It enables users to make intuitive judgments about the relative eight of different predetermined criteria or options in Batna, northeastern Algeria and its neighboring municipalities. The superposition of data related to several characteristics, such as geology, hydrology, and land use, allowed us to overcome several difficulties in evaluating the location of sites suitable for establishing landfills. Results show that 88.498km² in total meets the specified exclusion factors, of which 34.098% represent areas of very excellent suitability and 33.741% appropriate areas. Finally, low appropriateness applies to 32.161%.

Keywords-GIS; Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP); landfills; communal grouping; Batna

I. INTRODUCTION

Implementing an environmental management strategy requires detailed, reliable, and well-organized information on the state of the territory and the spatial distribution of socio-environmental problems. Geographic Information System (GIS), Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA), and statistical methods are robust and well-adapted tools for solving the problem of illustrating the multidisciplinary approach in the selection of favorable sites for public landfills. This approach proposes, on

one hand, the GIS approach [1-3] which, through its spatial analysis functions, contributes to the study of a large number of potential sites according to the evaluation criteria (exclusion and appreciation), and on the other hand, the AHP approach, which is one of the most popular and widely employed MCA methods, which is used to rank these alternatives. [4-6].

Rapid urbanization and rapid and erratic population growth have generated huge amounts of municipal waste. Several techniques and methods have been used for solid waste

management, such as collection, transportation, recycling, physical treatment, and landfilling [6, 7]. The latter has been used for many years and is the most common method for the disposal of urban solid waste. The choice of the landfill site is a complex process that includes various social, environmental, and technical, parameters and regulations. This requires processing a massive amount of spatial data [6]. GIS and MCA are widely used tools and methods [8, 9]. GIS specializes in capturing, storing, and analyzing databases and allows the integration of multiple layers of information with different combinations. MCA is designed to produce synthetic information [10] that provides a list of candidate sites based on a combination of selection criteria.

The wilaya of Batna produces about 188 thousand tons of solid waste annually, including 169 thousand tons of household waste. This quantity is expected to increase due to population growth, economic development and, changing lifestyle [11]. Nearly 70% of this waste is concentrated in urban areas, while managing household waste as it is currently conducted is unfavorable to the socio-economic development of Wilaya due to the significant increase in demography and to the change in consumption patterns. The implementation of a GIS prototype as a decision support tool in the field of environmental management is a tool that should allow managers to analyze the information necessary for the selection of appropriate sites for the storage of household waste. It will thus contribute to the protection of the environment and public health and reduce the obligations imposed on future generations by limiting the proliferation of illegal dumpsites [12]. The selection of a suitable site for a landfill consists of a compilation of data related to several disciplines, such as geomorphology, geology, hydrology, climatology, and demography. In the present study, several thematic maps were used, namely the topographic map, the geological map, and the piezometric map adding the use of the digital terrain model extracted from the SRTM image. All these data have allowed the establishment of a database with a spatial reference under a GIS whose purpose is the selection of appropriate sites for the establishment of landfills in Batna and neighboring municipalities.

Fig. 1. The study area.

II. GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA

The wilaya of Batna is located in northeastern Algeria, 435km from the capital Algiers. The study area is situated in the northeast of this wilaya, between 5°5' and 6°2' E longitude and 35°24' and 35°48' N latitude. It extends over the city of Batna (capital of the wilaya of Batna) and neighboring communes, namely Tazoult, Oued Elma, Seriana, Ouyoun El Aassafir, Fesdis, and Oued Echaaba (Figure 1).

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed model for optimizing the location of waste storage sites consists of an overlay of geographic data from several disciplines in a GIS that will serve as a decision support tool. Each information theme used various spatialization techniques to create basic spatial documents in raster or vector format (slope, land use, hydrographic network, road networks). Finally, a set of decision criteria was developed (i.e. exclusion and evaluation criteria). Exclusion criteria are constraints that aim to limit the search for sites in the domain that do not tolerate competition [13]. These criteria are applied to create a constraint map. Six criteria were considered in this study:

- Exclude areas with 500m of proximity to the hydrographic network, with the purpose to avoid the pollution of the aquatic environment.
- Exclude the road network with a proximity of 500m.
- Exclude the urban areas with a proximity of 2000m.
- Exclude wells, springs, reservoirs, and water towers with a proximity of 1000m
- Exclude the protected areas (forests, agriculture) with a proximity of 1000m.
- Exclude areas with a slope greater than 12%.

ModelBuilder is an application to create, modify and manage models. Models are workflows that allow concatenating sequences of geoprocessing tools and injecting the output of one tool into another tool. ModelBuilder can be compared to a visual programming language for creating workflows [14, 15]. Furthermore, ModelBuilder has a simple interface with drop-down menus, toolbar tools, and contextual menu options. The layout of the tools and variables connected is called the model diagram. Figure 2 illustrates the sequences of geoprocessing tools used to determine suitable sites for implementing a public landfill in Batna and the bordering municipalities.

The next step is to examine and evaluate suitable sites for the landfill, considering geo-environmental (soil permeability) and socio-economic (proximity to the road network, slopes) factors. The results of the AHP correspond to scores that sum to 1. The construction of the hierarchy and the structuring of the priorities should ensure the consistency of the homogeneity and relevance of the groupings and the proportional relationship between the important parameters.

Fig. 2. The model determining suitable sites for landfill siting.

TABLE I. DETERMINATION OF THE RELATIVE IMPORTANCE OF FACTORS BY A SCALE OF 1 TO 9 [16]

Degree of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two characteristics contribute equally to the goal
3	Low importance of one characteristic in relation to another	Experience slightly favors one characteristic over another
5	Strong or determining importance	Experience strongly favors one characteristic over another
7	Very strong or proven importance	A characteristic is strongly favored, and its dominance is evidenced in practice
9	Absolute importance	Evidence favoring one characteristic over another is as convincing as possible
2, 4, 6, 8	Values associated with intermediate judgments	When a trade-off is necessary

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results clearly show that most of the study area is excluded according to the previously established model (Figure 3). The results of the AHP method show that the factor of soil permeability has an influence of 55.84% on the final result, and the factor of distance to main roads is 31.96%. Finally, the factor of slope influences 12.19%. Note that CR (Coherence Ratio) must be less than 0.10. A higher CR indicates a higher level of inconsistency. In our case, the CR is equal to 0.018. The weighted overlay scales the input data on a defined scale (graduated by default from 1 to 9), weights the input rasters and groups them. The most favorable locations for each input criterion are re-ranked based on higher values.

In the weighted overlay tool, the sum of the weights assigned to the input rasters must equal 100%. The layers are multiplied by the appropriate factor, and each cell's resulting values are grouped. Weighted overlay assumes that more favorable factors result in higher values in the output raster, thus identifying these locations as the best. As with all weighted overlay analyses, we defined the problem by rendering it into submodels and then identified the input layers. In the case of our study, the input information layers are soil permeability, road proximity, and slope. In our study's case, and after considering the problem, we explicitly focused on the permeability factor (Figure 4).

Fig. 3. Results of the implementation of the exclusion criteria.

Fig. 4. Thematic maps representing the evaluation criteria.

Fig. 5. Final map of suitable sites for landfills.

The following percentages of influence were assigned to the ability cards. The values in parentheses are the percentage produced by division by 100 to normalize the values. These are assigned to each suitability map: soil permeability (50%), road proximity (30%) and slope (20%). As with the assignment of suitability scales, the assignment of weights is a subjective process that depends on the goals of our study. After the spatial analysis of suitability and appreciation, it can be noted that the total area that meets the committed exclusion factors is 88.498km², with 34.098% of that area representing areas of very good suitability, and 33.741% of the area is suitable areas. Finally, 32.161% of the area falls under the low suitability class (Figure 5).

V. CONCLUSION

Site selection is a critical issue in installing a landfill site. The objective of this work was to develop a site selection methodology that will allow the selection of the most suitable areas for installing a landfill. The core of this study is based on the processing of geospatial data related to the study area using a GIS. For this purpose, a set of factors was classified and two categories (exclusion factors and appreciation factors) were defined. A siting methodology for the area is provided by the current study. It can support the decision-makers in solving the waste management problem. The selection criterion of permeability was considered as the most important in this study.

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Finite Element Analysis of a Continuous Sandwich Beam resting on Elastic Support and Subjected to Two Degree of Freedom Sprung Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

This paper has developed a Finite Element Method (FEM) to calculate the dynamic response of a continuous sandwich beam resting on elastic support subjected to moving vehicles. The equation of motion is derived using the classical beam theory and FEM. The vehicle model is a two Degree of Freedom (2DOF) system that moves with a constant velocity. The governing equation of motion is integrated by applying the Wilson- θ time integration method to obtain the dynamic response in each time step. Numerical examples investigate the displacement of the sandwich beam with various values of the structure and vehicle velocity. The effects of the stiffness of elastic support and the vehicle velocity on displacement are studied.

Keywords-FEM; forced vibration; continuous beam; elastic support

I. INTRODUCTION

Structures in the construction industry can be multiform and diverse. The most commonly used structures in civil engineering are columns [1, 2], piles [3], beams [4-8], frames [9, 10], and plates [11-19]. In general, a beam is a flexural member and the normal stress has maximum values at the top and the bottom of the beam. So, sandwich beams will have optimal bearing capacity if the outer layer is a high-strength material. In practice, the fibers at the top and bottom of the

beam can be made of steel and the core layer from concrete or wood. If the sandwich beam is made of a suitable material, it will have a better load capacity, reduced height, and a larger span. Thus, the sandwich beam has many advantages if it is made of appropriate materials. A sandwich beam usually has two layers, i.e. the outer layer and the core layer, as shown in Figure 1.

Structures are subjected to various dynamic loads, e.g. from wind, moving vehicles, impulsive loading, etc. Structure

dynamics have many practical aspects, e.g. the dynamic behavior of beams [20-23] and the dynamics of plates [24, 25]. The dynamic response of an elastic plate in a viscoelastic medium, resting on a viscoelastic Winkler foundation is investigated in [26]. The forced vibration of functionally graded plates resting on a viscoelastic elastic foundation was solved analytically in [27]. The effect of randomness in the elastic modulus on the eigenvalue of free vibration of non-uniform beams is studied using stochastic finite elements in [28]. The variability dynamic response of a beam subjected to a moving load with various uncertain parameters is investigated by Monte Carlo simulation in [29]. The dynamic response of a beam resting on a viscoelastic foundation was analyzed with a novel state-space formulation considering the interaction of the oscillator-beam-foundation system in [30]. The dynamic response of sandwich beams with a viscoelastic core subjected to moving loads was studied by FEM in [31]. An analytical solution was performed to investigate the transient response of sandwich beams in [32]. A new semi-analytical method was applied in [33] to study the dynamics of beams. The transient response of double beams with viscoelastic boundary conditions under a moving load was investigated by the analytical method in [34]. The nonlinear dynamic response of the coupled vehicle-pavement system was computed using the Galerkin truncation method in [35], in which the pavement was modeled as a Timoshenko beam on the six-parameter foundation. The dynamic response of bridges to moving vehicle loads was investigated using a semi-analytical approach in [36]. The arch bridge subjected to the moving loads was modeled as a continuous beam resting on interconnected springs to compute the dynamic response using the analytical method [37]. Author in [38] presented an analytical and numerical method to study the dynamics of a beam-mass system. Experiments and finite element simulations studied the dynamic response of metallic sandwich beams under impact loading in [39].

Fig. 1. Cross section of a sandwich beam.

In this study, FEM is used to study the forced vibration of a continuous sandwich beam resting on an elastic support.

II. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

Let us consider a continuous sandwich beam resting on elastic supports, subjected to moving vehicles, with the coordinate system placed at the mid-plane of the beam as shown in Figure 2.

The deflection w of the beam can be written in a matrix form as [40]:

$$w(x,t) = \{N_1(x) \ N_2(x) \ N_3(x) \ N_4(x)\} \begin{Bmatrix} w_1(t) \\ \theta_1(t) \\ w_2(t) \\ \theta_2(t) \end{Bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

$$= \{N(x)\}\{q(t)\}_e$$

where $\{q(t)\}_e$ denotes the displacement vector of the finite element and $\{N(x)\}$ are Hermite interpolation functions, defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} N_1(x) = 1 - 3\frac{x^2}{L_e^2} + 2\frac{x^3}{L_e^3}; & N_2(x) = x\left(1 - 2\frac{x}{L_e} + \frac{x^2}{L_e^2}\right) \\ N_3(x) = 3\frac{x^2}{L_e^2} - 2\frac{x^3}{L_e^3}; & N_4(x) = x\left(-\frac{x}{L_e} + \frac{x^2}{L_e^2}\right) \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Fig. 2. Continuous sandwich beam resting on elastic supports and subjected to a moving vehicle.

The strain energy of the beam element is:

$$U_e = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_e} \left\{ \int_A \left\{ E_{Face} \left[y \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} \right]^2 \right\} dA \right. \tag{3}$$

$$\left. + \int_A \left\{ E_{Core} \left[y \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} \right]^2 \right\} dA \right\} dx$$

The potential energy of the elastic support is defined as:

$$U_s = \frac{1}{2} \sum k_s [w_0(x)]^2 \tag{4}$$

where k_s is the stiffness of the elastic support.

The kinetic energy of the beam element is given as:

$$\Pi_e = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_e} \left\{ \int_A \left\{ \rho_{Face} \left[\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial t} \right]^2 \right\} \right. \tag{5}$$

$$\left. + \int_A \left\{ \rho_{Core} \left[\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial t} \right]^2 \right\} \right\} dx$$

The governing equation of the sandwich beam is derived as:

$$[M^b]\{\ddot{w}\} + ([K^b] + [K^s])\{w\} = \{N\}^T f_w \tag{6}$$

where $[K^s], [K^b], [M^b]$ are the stiffness matrix of the elastic support and the stiffness and mass matrices of the sandwich beam, respectively.

The equation of motion of the moving mass m_1 and the contact force f_w are determined as follows:

$$m_1 \ddot{y} + c_m (\dot{y} - \dot{w}_m) + k_m (y - w_m) = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$f_w = (m_1 + m_2)g - m_2 \ddot{w}_m - m_1 \ddot{y} \tag{8}$$

where w_m is the vertical dynamic deflection of the beam at mass m_2 .

Combining (6) to (8), the governing equation is obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [M]^b + m^* & [N]^T m_1 \\ 0 & m_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\ddot{w}\} \\ \ddot{y} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c^* & 0 \\ -c_m [N] & c_m \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\dot{w}\} \\ \dot{y} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} [K]^b + [K]^s + k^* & 0 \\ -c_m \dot{x} [\dot{N}]_x - k_m [N] & k_m \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{w\} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [N]^T (m_1 + m_2)g \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} m^* &= m_2 [N]^T [N] \\ c^* &= 2m_2 \dot{x}(t) [N]^T [N]_x \\ k^* &= m_2 \dot{x}^2(t) [N]^T [N]_{xx} + m_2 \ddot{x}(t) [N]^T [N]_x \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

III. SOLVING THE EQUATION OF MOTION WITH THE WILSON-θ METHOD

The equation of motion of the vehicle-bridge interaction can be written in the following general form:

$$[M]\{\ddot{u}(t)\} + [C]\{\dot{u}(t)\} + [K]\{u(t)\} = \{F(t)\} \tag{11}$$

where $[M], [C], [K], \{F(t)\}$ are the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices, and the force vector, respectively. In order to use the Wilson scheme, we introduce the effective stiffness matrix as form:

$$[\tilde{K}] = [K] + a_0 [M] + a_1 [C] \tag{12}$$

$$\text{where: } a_0 = \frac{1}{\beta(\theta\Delta t)^2}; a_1 = \frac{\gamma}{\beta\theta\Delta t} \tag{13}$$

The vector of effective forces at time $t+\theta$ can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\tilde{F}(t+\theta)\} &= \{F(t)\} + \theta(\{F(t+\theta)\} - \{P(t)\}) + \\ &+ [C](a_1 \{\dot{u}(t)\} + a_4 \{\dot{u}(t)\} + a_3 \{\ddot{u}(t)\}) \\ &+ [M](a_0 \{\dot{u}(t)\} + a_1 \{\dot{u}(t)\} + a_2 \{\ddot{u}(t)\}) \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where $a_2 = \frac{1}{\beta\theta\Delta t}$; $a_4 = \frac{\gamma}{\beta} - 1$; $a_3 = \left(\frac{\gamma}{\beta} - 2\right)\frac{\theta\Delta t}{2}$. The values of the parameters are selected as $\gamma = 1/2$, $\beta = 1/6$, and $\theta \geq 1.37$.

The following linear system of equations computes the displacements at time after initialization of displacement, velocity, and acceleration vectors:

$$[\hat{K}]\{u(t+\theta)\} = \{\tilde{F}(t+\theta)\} \tag{15}$$

The vector of acceleration at the time $t+\theta$ is calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\ddot{u}(t+\theta)\} &= a_0 (\{u(t+\theta)\} - \{u(t)\}) \\ &- a_2 \{\dot{u}(t)\} - a_3 \{\ddot{u}(t)\} \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\text{where } a_3 = \frac{1}{2\beta} - 1.$$

Acceleration, velocity, and displacement at time $t+\Delta t$ are calculated from:

$$\begin{cases} \{\ddot{u}(t+\Delta t)\} = \{\ddot{u}(t)\} + \frac{1}{\theta}(\{\ddot{u}(t+\theta)\} - \{\ddot{u}(t)\}) \\ \{\dot{u}(t+\Delta t)\} = \{\dot{u}(t)\} + a_6 \{\ddot{u}(t)\} + a_7 \{\ddot{u}(t+\theta)\} \\ \{u(t+\Delta t)\} = \{u(t)\} + \Delta t \{\dot{u}(t)\} + a_8 \{\ddot{u}(t)\} \\ \quad \quad \quad + a_9 \{\ddot{u}(t+\theta)\} \end{cases} \tag{17}$$

$$\text{where: } a_6 = (1-\gamma)\Delta t; a_7 = \gamma\Delta t; a_8 = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \beta\right)\Delta t^2; a_9 = \beta\Delta t^2.$$

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A. Example 1

Considering the continuous sandwich beam shown in Figure 3, subjected to a moving vehicle with 2DOF. The rectangular sandwich beam has 3 uniform spans of 4m, the dimensions of cross-section are $h=60\text{cm}$, $b=25\text{cm}$, and the thickness of the face layer is 1cm. The parameters for the vehicle in Figure 3 are: $m_1=1680\text{kg}$ and $m_2=840\text{kg}$. The structural properties of the sandwich beam are given in Table I.

TABLE I. MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF THE SANDWICH BEAM

Fiber	Material properties		
	Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Mass density (kg/m ³)
Face layer	Steel	200	7800
Core	Wood	10	700

Figure 4 shows the displacement at the center of the beam for 2 cases of stiffness of elastic support. The speed of the vehicle is set to 5, 10, and 15m/s. The Figure clearly shows that the displacements at the center of the beam are highly similar. So, the effect of speed of the vehicle on the displacement of the beam is small.

Fig. 3. Three-span sandwich beam subjected to a moving vehicle.

Fig. 4. Displacement at the center of the beam for K_{goi} equal to (a) 10^7 , (b) 10^8 N/m.

Fig. 5. Displacement at the contact point with the m_2 mass of the vehicle for K_{goi} equal to (a) 10^7 , (b) 10^8 N/m.

The displacement of the mass of the vehicle m_2 is investigated with vehicle speed values of 5, 10, and 15m/s and stiffness of the elastic support K_{goi} equal to 10^7 and 10^8 N/m. When the speed is slow, the displacement is close to the static displacement. At high vehicle speed, the displacement is fluctuated around the displacement line at low speed.

Figure 6 illustrates the displacement at the center of the beam and at the contact point m_2 of the moving vehicle with speed of 10m/s for 3 stiffening cases of elastic support. As the stiffness of the support increases, the stiffness of the structure increases, leading to a decrease in displacement. When the stiffness of the support is quite large, the displacement at the center of the beam has an almost sinusoidal shape. It is clear that the stiffness of elastic support affects the displacement of the beam.

Fig. 6. Displacements for 3 stiffening cases of elastic support: (a) at the center of the beam, (b) at the contact point.

Fig. 7. Displacements of sandwich beam resting on elastic support.

B. Example 2

In this example, the dynamics of a sandwich beam is investigated by replacing two rigid supports of the example 1

with elastic supports as described in Figure 7. The displacements at the center of the beam and at the contact point are shown in Figure 8 for 3 stiffening cases of elastic support. Figure 8 clearly shows that the displacements are greatly increased. It also shows the strong influence of the stiffness of the elastic support on the displacements. Increased stiffness causes the displacement to decrease drastically.

Fig. 8. Displacements for 3 stiffening cases of elastic support. (a) at the center of the beam, (b) at contact point.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The forced vibration of continuous sandwich beams traversed by a moving vehicle has been studied in this paper. Finite element method based on the classical beam theory was used to derive the governing equations of motion of the sandwich beams. The governing equations were solved with the Wilson method. Numerical examples were employed to investigate the effects of vehicle velocity and the stiffness of elastic support on the displacement response of the beam. The result of the numerical examples showed that changes in the stiffness of the elastic support have a significant effect on the displacement response of the beam.

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Alternative Construction using BIM in Old Educational Buildings

Case Study: The Deanship Building of the Materials Engineering Department, University of Technology, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

The current study analyzes historic educational buildings to discover the optimum combination of improvements for optimal energy cost. The analysis was conducted using BIM technology and associated programs such as Auto Desk Revit 2020 and Auto Desk Insight 360 to determine the optimal strategies by which the most applicable alternative construction materials and procedures are considered to obtain environmentally and economically sustainable old educational buildings. The analysis showed that several approaches may reduce the cost of electrical energy usage and generator fuel in aged schools. Optimal changes lead to such reductions. Altering wall and roof materials minimizes electrical energy usage. The findings reveal that altering the lighting efficiency (0.3 W/sf) in the best way decreases the cost of electrical energy consumption by about 65,575,500 Iraqi Dinars (ID), and reduces the cost of fuel energy consumption by approximately 510,000 ID.

Keywords-BIM; historic buildings; construction projects; sustainable design; energy efficiency; Autodesk Insight 360 Cloud

I. INTRODUCTION

Given the importance of the energy industry and the occurring economic downturn in Iraq, the goal of this research is to look into the possibility of using environmentally friendly alternatives in old buildings, like schools, in order to cut down the amount of money these buildings spend on electricity and generator fuel. Building Information Modeling (BIM) capabilities will be used to construct and maintain schemes that are grounded in reality via the 3D visualization of the structures. This will replace any schemes that are either missing or have not been fully explained. Rivet 2020 and Autodesk Insight 360 cloud were utilized in order to conduct an analysis of a wide variety of sustainable design options.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Construction projects are dissimilar in size, type, location, site conditions, inputs and outputs, something that makes each project unique and consequently the standardization of construction processes becomes extensively difficult and risky [1]. The construction industry is one of the most important industries, as it plays a significant part in the provision of

buildings, public institutions, and infrastructure, as well as in the alleviation of poverty. [2].

Technology is the use of scientific effects for practical purposes. The word "technology" can also mean a group of tools and techniques that work together, like those used in construction [3]. The capacity of anything to be utilized without entirely depleting it or deteriorating is one definition of sustainability. Another definition is the capacity of something to continue existing or functioning for a significant amount of time [4]. Different kinds of goods, stakeholders, processes, and working conditions set the construction business apart from others [5]. A sustainable building is one that generates stakeholder value and contributes to the well-being of present and future generations by minimizing its environmental impact over the course of its entire lifespan. This is done by making the most of the building's economic value and improving human, natural, manufactured, and financial capital [6]. BIM [7] is an approach that is enabled by Information Technology (IT), and it requires applying and maintaining an integral digital representation of all building information in the form of a data repository throughout the various phases of a project's

lifecycle [7]. The term BIM refers to a system that encompasses everything having to do with the various phases of a building project. It's a central repository of project information where stakeholders may access financial details [8]. BIM is a system that looks at every part of a construction project and uses the information to help make better decisions at every stage [9]. To increase the level of performance in a construction project throughout its life cycle, BIM is a complete and coherent system for all parts of the project. This system includes a set of effective rules, processes, and computer applications [8]. Implementing and maintaining an integrated digital representation of information across several project phases is a part of this [10]. BIM is a useful tool for simulating the conditions of a construction site in a virtual setting, where potential dangers can be found and fixed before they become big problems [11].

Construction of a green building is an ongoing process that begins with careful preplanning and continues long after the construction completion. The primary goal of most green construction projects is to reduce the building's energy consumption. The two main approaches to lowering energy use are active and passive design techniques [5]. A green building is one that uses sustainable methods in its planning, construction, and day-to-day operations to lessen or get rid of the impact the building has on its surroundings and the people who live there [12]. Sharing ideas and traditions makes people's lives more interesting and opens their minds to new things. Sharing cultural heritage also helps strengthen economies and communities [13]. The majority of the energy used currently by homes goes toward heating. The effects of electrical power use are expanding in commercial and industrial structures. Lighting, ventilation, and air conditioning, along with use-specific gadgets like computers and manufacturing gear, all account for a significant portion of an industrial facility's total energy consumption. This is especially true for newly built structures, since their heating needs are far less than those of older structures. Powering electronics, such as refrigerators and washing machines, use a lot of electricity. In places where heating is more important, like in the climate of central Europe, there are clear seasonal differences in how much energy the buildings use [14]. Since far-off energy and fresh-water sources would necessitate more energy for transferring electricity and water into cities, minimizing the demand for natural resources and limiting natural resource consumption is the primary challenge in the development of green buildings. To lower the ever-increasing energy demand, it is important to use new building system designs and renewable energy sources when possible [15]. A building is considered energy-efficient if its design and construction result in a considerable decrease in the amount of energy required for its operation and maintenance. Every facet of a building's development is attended to from the very beginning of each project by a dedicated staff. People who will be working and living in the building are parts of the team, along with architects, engineers, developers, owners, and, the future tenants. They collaborate to establish targets for resource conservation, productivity, and innovative space use. Buildings that use a collaborative strategy may be up to 70% more efficient than traditional commercial buildings [16]. A Net

Zero or Zero Energy Building (ZEB) is a residential or commercial building with greatly reduced energy needs through efficiency gains such that the balance of energy needs can be supplied by renewable technologies. Energy efficiency in buildings means using less electricity, gas, and other fossil fuels. This is done by using high-performance equipment, appliances, products, and design strategies to reduce and control how much electricity is used [6]. The research on the utilization of building energy (Building Energy Efficiency) also defined as greening or modernizing of a building (Building Retrofit), or the process of modifying the structure of the building referring to changes that increase its energy efficiency [17]. One of the most energy demanding sectors in modern agriculture, the greenhouse industry is in definite need of energy consumption reduction [18]. Energy consumption in new commercial buildings may be reduced by 20% – 30% on average, and by over 40% for particular building types and locations, with the help of conventional energy efficiency technologies like thermal insulation, low-emissivity windows, window overhangs, and day lighting controls. Increasing a building's energy efficiency might raise the initial expenses, but the money saved on energy bills over the building's useful life can more than make up for it. One of the biggest advantages of sustainable design over traditional building methods is that it saves money on energy costs over the whole life of a building [5]. The energy consumption in the residential sector is very complex due to the large variety of construction types, sizes, thermal envelope materials, and the very wide variety of occupant behavior [19]. According to Green Globes, energy consumption is the single most influential factor in determining a building's overall sustainability. As such, it is given the most weight in Green Globes' three rating systems for buildings: Existing Building (EB), New Construction (NC), and Sustainable Interiors (SI) [20]. Most of a building's electricity bill goes toward running the air conditioner and lights. The energy requirements of a building can be drastically reduced through the use of passive design optimization in conjunction with building system optimization. BIM software can help architects, engineers, and building owners evaluate different design options and their effects on energy consumption, day lighting, thermal comfort, etc. [21]. Creating energy by burning fossil fuels results in the emissions of carbon dioxide. By cutting down the energy use, we may lessen that impact on the environment and cut down the human-caused causes of global warming, as well as the pollution that causes heat waves and other urban problems [22].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study strategy is mostly made up of two parts that are based on previous studies about BIM technology and take into account different ways to control how much energy a building uses.

A. Part One (Theoretical Study)

Relevant literature, including theses, books, journals, and websites was reviewed.

B. Part Two (Practical Study)

By examining the building in Autodesk insight 360 Cloud, a feature included in Revit 2020, sustainable design solutions

were assessed. This study includes an energy audit that is completed in line with ASHRAE 90.1. The process used to conduct this analysis is outlined below.

- Autodesk Revit 2020 was used to create a three-dimensional building information model for the project.
- We made sure that each of the rooms has enough space.
- The energy settings changed and some information was provided, such as the location of the project and the kind of project it will be.
- Energy analysis was conducted in the cloud with Insight 360 by using Rivet 2020 to create an energy model and selecting the optimization panel.
- An investigation on the amount of energy that was used was conducted, with the findings being shown in the cloud by Autodesk Insight 360.
- The research results gave information about the different aspects of different design options and how those options affect the total amount of energy used (EUI).
- Using the cloud-based version of Autodesk Insight 360, the various ways in which energy efficiency may be improved via sustainable design were demonstrated and compared.

The results of the investigation were based on net-zero scenarios.

IV. CASE STUDY

The Deanship Building of the Materials Engineering Department of the University of Technology was the case study. The Department was established in 1999/2000, and the first B.Sc. group graduated in 2002/2003. In the department, evening classes first began in 2000/2001. The Deanship Building is one of Technology University's instructional buildings. This building has 4 levels and occupies a total area of 3368m². The segment building is made up of two structures joined together by a bridge.

Fig. 1. The case study building.

A. Creating the 3D Visualization for the Case Study

Visualization is a technique that is used to the benefit of the client in order to acquire knowledge of the construction projects, and this is something that can be readily done when applying BIM. The usual techniques involve the preparation of drawings in just two dimensions, which the clients may find difficult to grasp due to the fact that it is hard to generate a realistic mental picture of the complicated projects based simply on the drawings alone. With the help of Autodesk Revit 2020, the researchers were able to make a picture of the case study.

Fig. 2. Rendering of a case study in Revit 2020.

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study are derived from the energy settings in Revit 2020 and the scenario that was chosen from Autodesk Insight 360 on the web. Figure 2 depicts the case study model that was carried out in the Insight 360 cloud. The results showed the following:

A. Roof Construction

Green roofs provide a number of advantages, including shielding a building from UV radiation and temperature extremes and reducing the amount of heat that escapes and enters the structure. Roof construction demonstrates the overall resistance of roofs to heat gains and losses. This study compares and contrasts different ways to insulate a building and how well they reduce the amount of energy used. Figure 3 and Table I show that Roof Construction-R 10.25-inch SIP has fewer costs (electrical and fuel) than the other types of thermal insulation. R-value is a measure of the insulation used.

TABLE I. ANNUAL COSTS OF VARIOUS ROOF CONSTRUCTION TYPES

Roof Construction	Electric (\$)	Fuel (\$)
Uninsulated	228711	4568
R10	227492	4522
R19	227361	4547
R38	227310	4535
R60	227300	4572
R 10.25- inch SIP	227267	4520
R15	227347	4542

Fig. 3. Roof construction.

B. Infiltration

Holes in the building envelope are a common cause of unintended air flow into or out of climate-controlled spaces. Figure 4 and Table II shows that Infiltration ACH-2.0 has fewer costs of electricity, fuel, and energy than the other types of infiltration ratings.

Fig. 4. Infiltration.

TABLE II. ANNUAL COSTS OF VARIOUS INFILTRATION TYPES

Infiltration	Electric (\$)	Fuel (\$)
0.17 ACH	227078	4530
0.4 ACH	226997	4540
0.8 ACH	226792	4553
1.2 ACH	226609	4559
1.6 ACH	226419	4571
2.0 ACH	226365	4529

C. Lighting Control System

This improvement included the installation of a regulation system for the building's lights, which combined presence

detectors with twilight sensors in order to reduce the amount of electricity that was used. It's a typical occupancy sensor system that changes the lighting depending on how much daylight is available. In addition to day lighting apertures like skylights and windows, a day lighting management system often incorporates a lighting control system that is sensitive to the presence of daylight. When daylight alone provides enough light, this method may reduce the amount of electricity needed for electric lighting. This lighting system is able to recognize when a certain area is unoccupied and alter the level of illumination accordingly. Occupancy sensors are used in this process. The lights will either gradually dim or turn off completely in order to reduce cost. Another benefit is that it makes it easy to have the lights turn on automatically when the device detects people, which could also make the area safer. Figure 5 and Table III show that the Occupancy Control system has fewer costs (electrical, fuel, energy) than the other types of lighting control systems for buildings.

Fig. 5. Day lighting and occupancy controls.

TABLE III. ANNUAL COSTS OF VARIOUS DAY LIGHTING AND OCCUPANCY CONTROL TYPES

Day lighting and occupancy	Electric (\$)	Fuel (\$)
None	226997	4540
Daylighting control	226997	4540
Occupancy control	219687	4517
Daylighting and occupancy control	219689	4519

D. Lighting Efficiency

Lighting efficiency provides information on the power consumption as well as the average internal heat gain and power consumption of electric lighting per unit of floor area. In addition, it is a representation of the amount of electricity used. Figure 6 and Table IV show that a lighting efficiency system of -0.3W/sf has the lowest cost (electric, fuel, and energy) than the other considered types of lighting efficiency systems.

Fig. 6. Lighting efficiency.

TABLE IV. ANNUAL COSTS OF VARIOUS LIGHTING EFFICIENCY TYPES

Lighting efficiency	Electric (\$)	Fuel (\$)
0.3 W/sf	183228	4496
0.7 W/sf	190027	4587
1.1 W/sf	196789	4507
1.5 W/sf	203557	4505
1.9 W/sf	210262	4498

Fig. 7. Operating schedule.

TABLE V. ANNUAL COSTS OF VARIOUS OPERATING SCHEDULE TYPES

Operating schedule	Electric (\$)	Fuel (\$)
24/7	319692	11251
12/7	277194	7351
12/6	264673	6636
12/5	235477	6631

E. Energy Operating Schedule

This study highlights the many different operating schedules that may be used in buildings, as well as the degree to which different operational schedules can affect energy consumption and the intensity of energy use. Figure 7 and Table V show that the (12/5) operating schedule has less cost (electric, fuel, energy) than the other types of operating schedule systems (12 means that there are 12 working hours in total every day, while 5 means that there are 5 working days in total).

VI. ENERGY SIMULATION

After the 3D BIM model has been finished in Revit 2020, it was transferred to Green Building Studio (GBS) by using the Green Building XML (gbXML). This allowed coming up with different design options and give information about how much energy and water are being used efficiently. gbXML is an open schema that was developed to make simpler for engineering analysis tools to utilize BIM to access building data. The file was imported from the website of Autodesk Green Building Studio (the GBS cloud).

TABLE VI. ANNUAL COST SAVINGS

Alternative Type	Alternative Name	Annual electric cost of the alternative (ID)	Annual electric cost Savings (ID)	Annual fuel of alternative (ID)	Annual fuel cost saving (ID)	Annual energy cost saving (ID)
Roof construction	R 10.25- inch SIP	226267* 1500 = 340,900,500	678* 1500 = 1,017,000	4520* 1500 = 6,780,000	316* 1500 = 474,000	1,491,000
Infiltration	2.0 ACH	226365* 1500 = 339,547,500	580* 1500 = 870,000	4529* 1500 = 6,793,500	307* 1500 = 460,500	1,330,500
Lighting Efficiency	0.3 W/sf	183228* 1500 = 274,842,000	183228* 1500 = 65,575,500	4496* 1500 = 6,744,000	340* 1500 = 510,000	66,085,500
Day lighting and occupancy	Occupancy controls	219687* 1500 = 329,530,500	7258* 1500 = 10,887,000	4517* 1500 = 6,775,500	319* 1500 = 478,500	11,365,500
Operating Schedule	12/5	225477* 1500 = 353,210,500	1468* 1500 = 2,202,000	4631* 1500 = 9,946,500	205* 1500 = 307,500	2,509,500

*1500 represents the factor of converting the ID to \$

VII. CREATE DESIGN ALTERNATIVES

GBS allows producing a variety of design options that have the potential to enhance the building's overall energy performance. Many different options, which are provided by GBS, were chosen based on an analysis by Autodesk Insight 360 and their impact on the amount of energy used and the amount of carbon emissions produced by the case study. Some of these options are orientation, window ratio, window shades, lighting control for the HVAC system, type of window glass, and type of wall. Equations (1)-(2) will be used to compute the yearly energy savings.

$$\text{Annual Electric Cost saving (ID/year)} = \text{Annual Electric Cost of Building} - \text{Annual Electric Cost of Alternative (Researcher)} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Annual Fuel Cost saving (ID/year)} = \text{Annual Fuel Cost of the Building} - \text{Annual Fuel Cost of Alternative (Researcher)} \quad (2)$$

For example, the current yearly cost of electricity was 340,422,000 ID and the annual cost of fuel was 7,254,000 ID (Maintenance division / University of Technology). Table VI illustrates the annual cost savings for fuel and electricity.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This article gave a summary of the procedure that was used to establish a set of assessment criteria for historical structures. These criteria were utilized in the evaluation of historical and archaeological buildings. By using modern research methods, the authors of this study are making an effort to define relevant instruments and procedures that may be of assistance in the energy management. The main conclusions from the current research are:

- BIM is a very useful tool for a wide range of assessments, each of which helps find new ways to improve the energy efficiency of a project.
- Lighting efficiency of 0.3 W/sf has the greatest annual electric cost saving of 65,575,500 ID and infiltration of 2.0 ACH has the lowest with 870,000 ID.
- Lighting efficiency of 0.3 W/sf has the greatest annual fuel cost saving of 510,000 ID and 12/5 Operating Schedule has the lowest annual fuel cost savings with 307,500 ID.
- The results indicate that there is a clear difference between the estimated and the actual consumption of electricity and fuel energy. This is shown by the fact that there is a plain separation between the two. Based on these results, it seems that using BIM during the design stage is a great way to figure out how well a building uses energy.

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An Experimental Study on the Effect of Plastic Waste Powder on the Strength Parameters of Tuff and Bentonite Soils Treated with Cement

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ABSTRACT

This experimental study investigated the effect of plastic waste powder on the strength and swelling behavior of tuff and bentonite soils treated by cement since the plastic powder is highly compressible and does not absorb much water. This study aimed to improve the tuff and bentonite soils used in construction by adding plastic waste powder in various ratios (5, 10, 20, and 25%) and a low cement content (2.5%). Atterberg limit, swelling consolidation, and loading-unloading tests were performed to determine the optimal composition of the mixture. The results demonstrated that as the plastic powder content increases, the liquid limits, swelling pressure, swelling potentials, and duration to swelling peak decrease. This reduction is particularly notable for the soil with the highest swelling potential. Compression and recompression indices increase significantly with the content of plastic powder due to its high compressibility. The findings suggest that plastic powder with low cement can be utilized as a soil modification reinforcement material, but with a content that shouldn't significantly alter the compressibility of the mixture.

Keywords-tuff; bentonite; plastic powder; cement; compressibility; swelling behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

Stabilized soil is a composite soil created by combining and enhancing the qualities of its various components. Soil swelling caused by a change in moisture is known to cause great stress and serious damage to structures. Expansive soils are known to be shrink-swell or swelling soils. Many studies investigated stabilization and strengthening techniques in order to improve the mechanical and geotechnical characteristics of soils in terms of performance and strength [1, 2], density and compaction [3, 4], compressive strength [5, 6], consolidation [7], durability [8], permeability [9], and micro-structure [10]. Soils made of tuff are categorized as clay soils. When dry soil is in contact with water, it undergoes alteration and may swell and then contract after drying. As a result of this phenomenon, there is considerable pressure, which causes the constructions to fracture [11]. Bentonite soils can be improved in terms of mechanical performance by adding polypropylene polymer matrices [12]. These methods include stabilizing the soil with chemical additives, replacing the soil partially, surcharge loading, and controlling compaction. Plastic is a petrochemical

product, which today constitutes most of the physical goods of daily life due to its low cost, multiple uses, lightness, and resistance to breaking. This excessive consumption makes it difficult to control and deal with the huge amounts of plastic waste generated. The annual global production of plastic waste is estimated at 2.01 billion tons [13]. Since 9% of this plastic waste is recycled [14], the rest can be found in both marine and terrestrial environments. Plastic waste should be adequately recycled in order to reduce its harmful effects on the environment. The majority of industrial and packaging processes use plastic in a variety of forms such as polyethylene, polycarbonate, low- and high-density polyethylene, polystyrene, polyvinyl chloride, and polypropylene [15-17]. Recently, plastic waste has been used to improve soils, and its effectiveness in improving tuff soils has already been tested [18-21]. As sustainable development principles with consequent economic growth for all is essential, sorting waste helps to preserve the environment by reducing the amount of plastic waste deposited in the nature. By promoting a circular economy based on the reduction, reuse, and recycling of plastic

waste, sorted plastic products can be reused and transformed into new raw materials.

This study combined tuff and bentonite soils with plastic waste powder in ratios of 5, 10, 20, and 25% of total soil weight and treated with low cement content. The results in terms of consistency limits, odometer tests, compression, and recompression tests showed that mixing the tuff soil with plastic powder reduces the heave and swelling pressure. Additionally, the reduction in swelling pressure is a little more significant for soils with 10, 20, and 25% plastic powder. The compression and recompression indices increase progressively with the plastic powder content for both soils.

II. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A. Materials and Methods

1) Investigated Soils

Two soil samples were studied. The first soil sample was tuff from the region of Mascara in the northwest of Algeria and the second was bentonite made from the Maghnia quarries in northwestern Algeria. These two soils were subjected to several laboratory tests to determine their properties using the standard procedures approved by AFNOR and ISO standards NF P 94-051, NF P 94-054, NF 94-056, NF P 94-057, and NF P 94-068. Table I shows the properties of the investigated soils.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF THE INVESTIGATED SOILS.

Properties	Tuff	Bentonite
Liquid limit (%)	27.5	28
Plastic limit (%)	14	13
Plasticity index (%)	23.19	83
Specific gravity	1.92	2.61
Grains sizes analysis		
Sand (%)	17.3	12.3
Silt (%)	27.4	19.5
Clay (%)	55.3	68.2
Volume of blue VB (cm ³)	5.3	38.6

Fig. 1. Grain-size distributions for used materials.

The specific gravity of the tuff and the bentonite soils was 1.92 and 2.61, respectively. Figure 1 shows the particle size distribution of the soils. Table II shows the chemical analysis of

the tuff sample according to the NF EN 1744 standard. According to the USCS soil classification system, tuff soil is defined as low-white clay. The main constituent of tuff soil was 70.25% calcite with a ratio of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ equal to 3.60. The bentonite of Maghnia is defined as a high-plasticity clay. Its main constituent was silica with 65%, with a ratio of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ equal to 3.76. Fe_2O_3 , CaO, MgO, and Na_2O are high in bentonite soil.

TABLE II. CHEMICAL COMPOSITIONS OF SOILS

Property	Tuff	Bentonite	Cement
SiO_2 (%)	9.56	65	20.18
Al_2O_3 (%)	2.65	17.25	5.26
Fe_2O_3 (%)	0.58	2.10	2.91
CaO (%)	70.25	5	59.20
MgO (%)	2.61	3.10	3.05
Na_2O (%)	4.90	3.2	0.15
K_2O (%)	1.38	1.7	0.25
Loss in ignition (%)	8.09	2.65	9.0

2) Plastic Waste Powder

One hundred used caps of plastic water bottles were mechanically shredded at room temperature to create the used plastic fiber. Since the plastic chips were elongated particles between 1 and 10mm in length with an average of 5mm, it was impossible to determine their gradation curve as in normal aggregates. Additionally, the sample also contained plastic powder, which tended to lump together and comprised about 60% of its weight. Natural resources such as cellulose, natural gas, and crude oil can be converted to plastics using a polycondensation or polymerization process [22]. The plastic powder can be obtained by breaking and grinding waste plastic. The plastic powder has a qualitative weight of 0.93gm/cm³, 0.015% water absorption, 54MPa ultimate tensile strength, and 110-450Mpa modulus of elasticity [23]. Figure 2 shows a sample of the plastic powder.

Fig. 2. Plastic waste powder

B. Mixtures Design

1) Preparation of Soil-Plastic Powder Mixtures

The samples were prepared in an optimal protector with a water content that corresponds to liquid reduction. The water content of the samples was removed by drying at 35°C. The samples were considered completely dry after 24 hours. Since the qualitative weight of the plastic powder is less than half that of the soil, the mixing rates were high, up to 25% of the plastic powder. The mixtures were prepared with 15% of the water

content and were pressed in the standard proctor in five layers to ensure a uniform dry density. The assembly of samples required sitting with 1Kg due to the great difference in the qualitative gravity of the components. After soil pressure and mixtures, the uninterrupted cylindrical samples were released from the mold using a hydraulic crane. The samples were wrapped in plastic to prevent losing water.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Consistency Limits

Atterberg limit tests were performed to determine the consistency limit values of the soils and their mixtures according to the AFNOR NF P 94-051 methods. Figures 3 and 4 show the effects of plastic powder on the consistency limits of the tuff and bentonite mixtures, respectively.

Fig. 3. Consistency limits for tuff and its mixtures.

Fig. 4. Consistency limits for bentonite and its mixtures.

The liquid limits for both soils and their mixtures decreased gradually when the plastic powder content increased. The results of the Atterberg limit tests indicate that bentonite has lower plasticity than tuff soil, which makes it less susceptible to

plastic powder than tuff. The kind [24], composition, cation exchange capacity, and metal content ratios of the mixtures could all contribute to changes in their plastic limits [25-27].

B. Odometer Tests

1) Swell-Consolidation Tests

Swell-consolidation tests were performed according to the AFNOR XP 94-91 standard on all compacted specimens. These tests were conducted in a conventional odometer of 50mm diameter and 20mm thickness. Since the composite samples were made as described above, the initial void ratio (e) varied depending on the amount of plastic powder used. The specimens were statically compacted in the odometer into five layers, each 4mm thick, to ensure uniform dry density. Heave was allowed under a seating surcharge resultant to the odometer (approximately 7.5kPa). Following the final heave (ΔH), the samples were compressed under increasing vertical pressure until the initial void ratio (e) was reached for the mixtures, as well as the swelling potential (S percent) and swelling pressure (p_s). Reports on the puffs included information like the percentage increase in the thickness of the sample when submerged (ΔH) compared to its original thickness (H). The swelling pressure (p_s) was determined as the compression of the initial vacuum ratio (E) of the samples obtained from the E-Log P. It is necessary to remember that the compression of the soil and the plastic powder, as well as the water in the pores, is small compared to the compression of the soil skeleton.

2) Effect of Plastic Powder Fibers on Swell Potential

Figures 5 and 6 show the variation in the swell potential (S) versus time for the tuff soil samples compared to the samples mixed with 5, 10, 20, and 25% plastic powder and 2.5% cement. The test results indicate that tuff soil gives a swell potential of 3.75% reached in 22 days without treatment, while bentonite gives 13.35% in 25 days without treatment. The final swelling of the samples decreases and reaches the same time for the compound samples with 5% plastic powder, and at a lesser time for samples with 10, 20, and 25%.

Fig. 5. Effect of the plastic powder content on the swell potential of tuff.

Fig. 6. Effect of the plastic powder content on the swell potential of bentonite.

It can be observed that the swell potentials of tuff and bentonite can be significantly reduced using plastic powder and low-cement (2.5%) mixtures. For the two soils, the reduction of the swell potential gradually increases with powder content. The reduction in the swell potential of tuff soil varied from 21.6% to 25.8% for mixtures with 10 and 20% powder content, respectively, and is approximately 11.7% for mixtures with 10% powder content. All samples were prepared at a 15% water content and since plastic powder absorbs at least 3% of its weight, the water-to-tuff ratio at the start of the test was about 0.11, 0.18, 0.22, and 0.26 for the samples with 0, 5, 10, 20, and 25% of plastic powder, respectively. These may be the reasons for the reduction of the reach time in achieving the maximum heave. For bentonite with 5% plastic powder, the reduction of swell potential was about 6.5% with 10% plastic powder and about 23% for the samples having more. A further reduction in the swell potential of Bentonite was obtained with increasing duration. The swell potential of bentonite with 25% plastic powder decreased to 2.25% in 12 days. This lowering of the reached time was due to the initial water-to-bentonite ratios, which were approximately 0.11 and 0.26 for samples with 0 and 25% plastic powder, respectively. The reduction in the swell potential of the mixed bentonite samples compared to pure bentonite increased gradually from 6 to 89% when the powder content increased from 5 to 25%. This was also confirmed in [28] and [29] by testing the effects of plastic powder on clay.

3) Effect of Plastic Powder on Swelling Pressure

Figures 7 and 8 show the swelling potential and swelling pressure for the tuff and bentonite specimens. Swelling pressure (ps) decreases with the addition of plastic waste powder. Figure 7 shows that the swelling pressure was 48kPa for the pure tuff specimens, while the swelling pressure values for the composite specimens with 5, 10, 20, and 25% plastic powder content were 46, 40, 32, and 31kPa, respectively. Figure 8 shows that the plastic powder content reduces swelling pressure in the bentonite composite. The swelling pressure for the pure bentonite specimen was 153kPa, while the swelling pressure for bentonite with plastic powder content at

5, 10, 20, and 25% were 137, 120, 118, and 117kPa, respectively. The swelling pressure values of tuff were less than half that of bentonite. The reduction in swelling pressure of the composite samples with 25% of plastic powder was approximately 30% and 54% for bentonite and tuff, respectively.

Fig. 7. Effect of plastic powder content on the swell potential and pressure of tuff soil.

Fig. 8. Effect of plastic powder content on the swell potential and pressure of bentonite soil.

C. Loading-Unloading tests

Given that plastic powder is compressible and its specific gravity is less than half of the soil, supplementary testing was conducted following the odometer protocol conditions to obtain additional information on the mechanical behavior of the soil and its mixtures. The compression (C_c) and recompression indices (C_r) were determined according to AFNOR XP 94-090-1 for soil and composite samples.

1) Effect of Plastic Powder Compression Index

Figures 9 and 10 show the compression indices for tuff, bentonite, and their mixtures with plastic powder. It is common knowledge that compression index (C_c) is the semi-logarithmic fall of the linear percentage of the pressure void ratio curve.

The C_c values are relatively small because the remolded C_c is always smaller than the undisturbed ones. The values varied from 0.2491 to 0.5230 for bentonite and its mixtures, and from 0.22 to 0.403 for tuff and its mixtures. For the two soils, C_c gradually increases with plastic powder content. Similar results were obtained in [30] and [31].

2) Effect of Plastic Powder Recompression Index

Figures 9 and 10 present the recompression (swell) index and the decompression index C_r for tuff and bentonite soils and their mixtures with plastic powder. In general, the C_r values of the recompression index are approximately 5 times smaller than the compression index C_c , as in [32]. For all tested samples, C_r was about 3.5 or 4 times smaller than C_c and increased with plastic powder content. The values of the decompression index C_r ranged from 0.0829 to 0.1712 for bentonite and its mixtures and from 0.050 to 0.1480 for tuff and its mixtures.

Fig. 9. Effect of plastic powder content on compression and recompression index of tuff soil.

Fig. 10. Effect of the plastic powder content on compression and recompression index of bentonite

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results, it can be concluded that mixing tuff soil with plastic powder reduces heave and swelling pressure, due to the use of plastic powder in place of swellable soils and the resistance it provides to swell when in contact with soil fibers. The reduction of swell potential for 5% plastic powder content is about 1.4 for the soils with low plasticity compared to high plasticity. For 10, 20, and 25% plastic powder content the reduction is about the same in the two clayey soils. The reduction in swelling pressure is slightly more significant for tuff soil with 10, 20, and 25% plastic powder than for bentonite soil with the same contents of plastic powder. The opposite was observed for mixtures with 10% plastic powder. Since plastic powder absorbs water at most 3.4% of its weight, composite samples reach a final heave in less time compared to pure clay. This time gradually decreases with the plastic powder content. The compression and recompression indexes gradually increase with the plastic powder content for the two clayey soils and exceed the double for 25% of plastic powder content. Plastic powder with low cement (2.5%) significantly reduces the likelihood of swelling regardless of soil elasticity, but increases the compression of the mixtures. Using plastic waste as a substitute for synthetic fibers creates a cost-effective product that protects the environment from waste, conserves natural resources, and retains mechanical qualities suitable for use in non-structural applications. Instead of using expensive synthetic fibers to support fragile soils, this initiative aims to deposit plastic waste economically and efficiently and reuse it in soils, resulting in an inexpensive but effective product for soil stabilization.

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Techno-Economic Feasibility Assessment for the promotion of Grid-Connected Rooftop PV Systems in Botswana: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of the present study is to investigate the solar energy potential and evaluate the economic viability of a 5kW grid-connected rooftop photovoltaic (PV) system as an electricity generation source in three selected regions (Gaborone, Maun, and Tshabong) in Botswana for the first time. In this study, NASA POWER data were used for evaluating the solar potential in the selected regions. The results showed that the selected locations are suitable for the installation of various scales of PV systems due to the high global horizontal solar radiation. RETScreen Expert software was used to assess the techno-economic feasibility of the proposed systems. The performance of the proposed systems with various PV technologies (mono-crystalline silicon and poly-crystalline silicon) is analyzed. Furthermore, economic and financial indicators such as net present value, annual life cycle savings, payback, benefit-cost ratio, and cost of energy production were calculated. The results indicate that the proposed system is very promising for all the selected locations. Additionally, it was found that the PV projects with poly-Si technology produced a large amount of energy and have a low electricity cost compared to mono-Si technology. The results suggest that grid-connected rooftop PV systems have a significant role in covering the electricity demand and in reducing carbon dioxide emissions, especially in high population density and rural regions. This study provides some useful recommendations for decision-makers regarding the development and deployment of PV energy technology in Botswana.

Keywords-Botswana; solar energy potential; grid-connected; rooftop PV system; PV technology; RETScreen software

I. INTRODUCTION

Population growth and the rising living standards led to growing demand of energy, primarily electricity, in a global scale. It is known that environmental pollution impacts human health through emissions of harmful gases caused by conventional energy generation from fossil fuels. Thus, finding alternative energy sources to reduce fossil fuel consumption and environmental pollution is essential. Renewable energies

such as solar energy have grown due to the growing demand [1] and solar energy has been widely utilized globally to generate electricity and reduce emissions. It is an inexhaustible and environmentally friendly energy source. Authors in [2] report that solar power will reduce the emission of about 69-100 million tons of CO₂, 68-99 thousand tons of NO_x, and 126-184 thousand tons of SO₂ by 2030. Authors in [3] concluded that solar energy has significant potential to meet the world's electricity requirements in the future. Authors in [4] mention

that solar energy technologies have a huge potential to mitigate climate change by reducing energy-related emissions.

Generally, solar PV produces electrical power directly from sunlight [5-8]. Authors in [5] evaluated the performance of a 6.4kW grid-connected PV system and wind system at three locations in Northern Cyprus. The results showed that the most economical option for electricity production in the selected locations is the PV system due to the low electricity prices and the recovery of the initial investment. Authors in [7] investigated the economic and environmental feasibility of a 2-10kW grid-connected rooftop PV system in Greece. The results showed that the successful development of small-scale residential solar energy systems in the country depends on increasing energy selling prices and/or reducing costs in the production of PV systems. Authors in [8] evaluated the feasibility of a 5kW grid-connected rooftop PV system in Lebanon. The results showed that the amount of output from the solar system can help reduce the shortage of energy in the region.

A. Energy Situation in Botswana

Botswana is located between 22.3285° S and 24.6849° E. The country is landlocked in Southern Africa bordering Zimbabwe and South Africa. Presently, fossil fuels and coal are the main sources of electrical energy in the country [9]. Access to electricity in Botswana has reached 77% of the population in urban areas, while in rural areas it is still limited to 37% according to the World Bank. The overall electrification rate at the national level is 60%. Botswana relies mainly on electricity, coal, fuel wood, and oil for its energy requirements. With these sources, CO₂ emissions have increased over the years according to the World Bank database. Furthermore, more than 50% of Botswana's energy requirements are imported from South Africa and Zambia according to United Nations Environment Program. Besides, electricity consumption has been rising over time. For example, the electricity consumption was 586.84kWh/capita in 1981 and 1815.55kWh/capita in 2014 according to the World Bank database. This has exacerbated the electricity deficit over the years. According to electricity information released by the International Energy Agency, population and economic growth have led to an increase in electricity consumption in the country. Therefore, utilizing renewable energy would reduce the consumption of conventional fuels and be a clean source of electricity generation in the country. According to the Wind Power Density (WPD) classification [10], Botswana is placed in class 1 (poor) based on the obtained values of WPD at 10m and 50m. Moreover, the specific PV power output is within the range of 4.74-5.47kWh/kWp according to the World Bank Group (global solar atlas). Moreover, Botswana receives approximately 3200h of sunshine annually and has high insulation on a horizontal surface of 21MJ/m². The average daylight hours in Botswana range from 9.9h in summer to 8.2h in winter. Consequently, Botswana has an abundant solar energy potential compared to wind energy. The country is a suitable region for installing PV systems due to the high value of global solar radiation and has a great chance of utilizing solar power in order to reduce the amount of imported energy from the neighboring countries [11]. Additionally, installing a

solar system in the country is technically reliable due to the high value of average daily radiation on the horizontal surface [12].

Several studies have investigated the potential of solar energy in the country [13-19]. For instance, authors in [13] estimated the potential of concentrating solar power in Botswana using the Geographical Information System (GIS). The results indicated that the country has a huge concentrating solar power that will be able to meet the maximum energy demand. Authors in [14] examined the status of solar pilot projects at different locations in Botswana. They concluded that solar home systems in rural areas will significantly enhance socio-economic benefits and assist the sustainability of solar power generation in the country. Authors in [15] evaluated the technical performance of solar water heaters in Gaborone, Botswana. Authors in [16] analyzed the energy requirements of a non-electricity off-grid village in Botswana. Authors in [17] designed a hybrid solar-wind system for rural electrification in Botswana using the HOMER software. The results showed that the optimal model (solar-wind-battery system) employed 100% renewable energy, resulting in zero carbon emissions. The results indicated that the minimum and maximum output power of the PV system occurred during June/July and December/January, respectively. Authors in [18] utilized Simulink's single diode model design to present the PV module voltage output and the annual maximum power output profile of the PV module for variable temperature and irradiance. The results demonstrated that the voltage output is generally constant throughout the year while the maximum power from the solar module closely follows the solar radiation profile. Authors in [19] calculated the size of PV panels, batteries, and integrated collector-storage solar water heaters based on the demands for electricity and hot water.

B. Research Gap and Objectives

To the best of our knowledge, there is not any study that investigates the economic feasibility of a grid-connected rooftop PV system in Botswana. The findings of the literature review reveal a clear lack of proposed solar PV systems as a power source for households in Botswana. Thereby, there is no doubt that a comprehensive economic and environmental study must be conducted to obtain results that could be a roadmap for solar energy investments in the country. Consequently, it can be concluded that the small-scale solar systems in the country can not only bridge the energy gap but would also reduce the environmental impact. Therefore, the present paper aims to evaluate the techno-economic and environmental feasibility of small-scale rooftop grid-connected solar systems at different locations and climate conditions in Botswana. To achieve this, the solar radiation data are analyzed to classify the solar resource in the selected locations. Moreover, the techno-economic feasibilities for the rooftop solar systems at three comparative locations were developed for various policy scenarios, based on variations in financial parameters using RETScreen Experts.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

Figure 1 shows the locations of the three regions considered in this study. The solar radiation data were taken from the NASA POWER data over 16 years (2005-2020).

Fig. 1. Location of the selected regions used in this work. Screenshot from Google Earth. © TerraMetric, Map data © AfriGIS (Pty) Ltd.

1) Gaborone

Gaborone (24.6282°S, 25.9231°E) is the capital and largest city of Botswana with a population of over 200,000. It is located in the southern part of the country. The monthly variation of Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) and Average Temperature (AT) are illustrated in Figure 2. The minimum and maximum values of GHI are recorded in June and October with values of 121.43kW/m² and 217.30kW/m², respectively. The annual value of GHI is estimated to be 2094.52kW/m². The solar resource at this location is categorized as outstanding (2035.9-2221.8kW/m²) [19]. Additionally, it is found that the monthly value of AT is within the range of 13.24-25.20°C with an average value of 20.69°C.

2) Maun

Maun (19.9953°S, 23.4181°E) is located in Northwest Province. It is the capital of the Northwest Province with a population of 55,784. As can be seen in Figure 2, the monthly value of GHI varies from 138.56kW/m² to 227.41kW/m² with an average value of 182.35kW/m². The solar resource at this location is also classified as outstanding (annual GHI = 22188.16kW/m²) [19]. The maximum mean AT is recorded in October with a value of 28.03°C, while the minimum value of 16.72°C is recorded in July.

3) Tshabong

Tshabong (26.0208°S, 22.4113°E) is located in the Kalahari Desert with a population of 8,939 according to the 2011 census. The monthly value of GHI is within the range of 117.99-250.38kW/m² with an average of 188.52kW/m² as shown in Figure 2. The annual value of GHI at the selected location is 2262.25kW/m². The solar resource at this location is categorized as superb (>2221.8kW/m²). Additionally, it is found that the monthly value of AT is within the range of 12.93-27.89°C with an average value of 21.58°C.

B. On-grid Photovoltaic System

Grid-connected PV systems have PV panels that supply the required power during the day and are connected to the local electrical grid to be supplied with power at night. Moreover, the excess power from the PV system is fed back to the grid when the power generated is more than the load required [20]. In general, the grid-connected PV system consists of solar panels, inverters, a power-conditioning unit, and grid-connection equipment. To get more power from the PV arrays, the PV panels should have high cell efficiency and a high operating temperature. The inverter is one of the most crucial components of a grid-connected system because it converts Direct Current (DC) to Alternating Current (AC). In addition, electricity meters are utilized to read the flow of electricity to and from the grid. Recently, on-grid PV systems have attracted substantial attention due to the advantages of their compatibility with the electricity grid. In this system, the output power of the PV system is connected directly to the grid and the household. The electric energy produced by the PV system can cover the energy demand of the household. When the produced energy by the PV system is high, the remaining produced energy can be fed into the grid through an electric meter. This system comprises PV panels, which absorb sunlight and produce direct current, an inverter that is used to convert the direct current to alternating current, a distribution controller, and load as shown in Figure 3. Generally, it is necessary to estimate the optimal sizing of grid-connected PV systems as the first step to meet the energy demands of the household. According to [21], the amount of output energy by the PV system (E_{PV}) should be greater than the amount of electricity taken from the grid (E_{grid}) as shown in (1). In this case, the energy demand of the household can be shared between the PV system and the electric grid.

$$E_{PV} > E_{grid} \quad (1)$$

The generated energy from the PV system is utilized to cover the household/building instantaneous electricity load and the surplus energy is injected into the grid (i.e. if the load of the building at time t is greater than the generated PV electricity, the required energy is absorbed from the grid. In general, the effect of the ambient temperature is one of the most important factors that affect the output power of the PV system (P_{PV}), which can be expressed as [22]:

$$P_{PV} = \eta_{PV} \eta_{in} A_{PV} \gamma \frac{G}{G_{STC}} [1 + \gamma_T (T - T_{STC})] \quad (2)$$

where η_{PV} is the PV module efficiency, η_{in} is the inverter efficiency, G_{STC} is the Standard Test Conditions (STC) irradiance (1kW/m²), T and T_{STC} are the PV cell operating temperature in °C and the PV cell STC temperature (25°C), respectively, γ_T is the module's maximum power temperature coefficient (%/°C), and γ is the derate factor to account for the losses in system performance given by [23]:

$$\gamma = \gamma_{DC} \gamma_{AC} \gamma_{AGE} \gamma_{ext} \quad (3)$$

where γ_{DC} is the DC power derate factor to account for factors like module mismatch, diodes and connection losses, and DC wiring losses, γ_{AC} is the AC interconnection derate factor with a value of 0.99, γ_{AGE} is the derate factor to account for the loss

in system performance with age, and γ_{ext} represents the losses due to external factors like dust, shading, snow cover, or anything else that would vary the power output of the PV module to deviate from that expected under ideal conditions.

Fig. 2. Monthly mean variation of GHI and AT for all selected locations during the 2005-2020 period.

Moreover, (4) is used to estimate the PV cell operating temperature (T) [24]. Furthermore, the solar radiation incident (G) on the tilted angle (ϕ) can be determined by (5) [25]:

$$T = T_a + \frac{G}{0.8} (T_{NOCT} - 20) \tag{4}$$

$$G = G_d \left[\cos(\theta) + C \cdot \cos^2\left(\frac{\phi}{2}\right) + \rho \cdot \left(\cos(\chi) + C \cdot \sin^2\left(\frac{\phi}{2}\right) \right) \right] \tag{5}$$

where T_a is the ambient temperature, T_{NOCT} is the nominal operating cell temperature, G_d is the direct normal irradiance, θ is the angle between the tilted surface and the solar rays, C is the diffuse portion constant, ρ is the reflection index, and χ is the zenith angle. θ , χ , and the sun azimuth angle ξ can be obtained from:

$$\cos(\theta) = [\cos(\phi) \cdot \cos(\chi) + \sin(\phi) \cdot \sin(\chi) \cdot \cos(\xi - \zeta)] \tag{6}$$

$$\cos(\chi) = \sin(\delta) \cdot \sin(\lambda) + \cos(\delta) \cdot \cos(\lambda) \cdot \cos(\alpha) \tag{7}$$

$$\tan(\xi) = \frac{\sin(\alpha)}{\sin(\lambda) \cdot \cos(\alpha) - \cos(\lambda) \cdot \tan(\delta)} \tag{8}$$

where ζ is the plat azimuth angle, δ is the solar declination angle, λ is the latitude, and α is the solar angle, defined by:

$$\alpha = \frac{360}{24} [(LST + EOT - 4L + 60t_z) - 2] \tag{9}$$

where t_s is the solar time depending on Local Standard Time (LST), longitude L , time zone t_z , and EOT is the Equation Of Time that accounts for the irregularity of the earth's speed around the sun.

Fig. 3. Components of an on-grid PV system.

Moreover, the maximum power (P_{max}) of the developed on-grid solar PV system can be estimated as a function of global solar radiation G_{sr} ($\text{kWh/m}^2/\text{d}$), solar radiation at standard test conditions P_i (kW/m^2), PV derating factor f_{PV} , household daily power consumption E_{AC} (kWh/d), and inverter yield η_{inv} . This relationship can be expressed as [22]:

$$P_{max} = \frac{E_{AC} P_i}{G_{sr} f_{PV} \eta_{inv}} \tag{10}$$

The average daily output of the PV system coincides with the utility's peak demand period, therefore decreasing the capacity losses in the utility distribution network and improving the delay issues of the Transmission and Distribution (T&D) network [26-28]. Moreover, this system does not require batteries hence it has lower cost than an off-grid PV system [28].

C. RETScreen Expert Software

RETScreen Expert is a renewable energy management tool developed by the Canadian government. It is a decision support tool that is utilized to determine the potential of energy, costs, savings, greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction, and economic viability [29, 30]. RETScreen uses global meteorological data collected from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) database. RETScreen is commonly employed to explore the feasibility of grid-connected wind and PV power systems. For instance, authors in [30] used RETScreen to evaluate the techno-economic feasibility of a grid-connected PV system in Nigeria. Authors in [31] utilized RETScreen to investigate the potential of PV systems for electricity generation in various locations in Libya. Authors in [32] evaluated the cost-benefit of 100MW Solar PV in Pakistan using RETScreen. In the current study, the initial and operations and maintenance costs were assumed based on the previous studies related to techno-economic feasibility in African countries. Capacity Factor (CF), GHG reduction (A-GHG), and economic assessment parameters: Net Present Value (NPV), Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Simple Payback (SP), Equity Payback (EP), Annual Life Cycle Saving (ALCS), and Benefit-Cost Ratio (B-C) are determined using the equations below.

$$CF = \frac{P_{out}}{P \times 8760} \quad (11)$$

$$A - GHG = [(Base\ case\ GHG\ emission\ factor) - (Proposed\ case\ GHG\ emission\ factor)] \times \text{End use energy delivered} \quad (12)$$

$$GHG - E - RC = \frac{ALCS}{\Delta_{GHG}} \quad (13)$$

$$NPV = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{C_n}{(1+r)^n} \quad (14)$$

$$LCOE = \frac{\text{sum of cost over lifetime}}{\text{sum of electricity generated over the lifetime}} \quad (15)$$

$$SP = \frac{C - IG}{(C_{ener} + C_{capa} + C_{RE} + C_{GHG}) - (C_{o\&M} + C_{fuel})} \quad (16)$$

$$EP = \sum_{n=0}^N C_n \quad (17)$$

$$ALCS = \frac{NPV}{\frac{1}{r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+r)^N}\right)} \quad (18)$$

$$B - C = \frac{NPV + (1 - f_d)C}{(1 - f_d)C} \quad (19)$$

where P_{out} is the energy generated per year, P is the installed capacity, N is the project life in years, C_n is the after-tax cash flow in year n , r is the discount rate, C is the total initial cost of the project, f_d is the debt ratio, B is the total benefit of the project, IG represents the incentives and grants, C_{ener} is the annual energy savings or income, C_{capa} is the annual capacity savings or income, C_{RE} is the annual Renewable Energy (RE) production credit income, C_{GHG} is the GHG reduction income, $C_{o\&M}$ is the yearly operation and maintenance costs incurred by the clean energy project, C_{fuel} is the annual cost of fuel, which is zero for renewable projects, and Δ_{GHG} is the annual GHG emission reduction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RETScreen Expert software was utilized to evaluate the viability of small-scale rooftop PV systems in three selected locations in Botswana.

A. Technical Viability

In this study, 5kW grid-connected fixed solar tracking mode is considered for all the selected locations with the solar PV modules tilted to an angle of 25° and azimuth angle of 180°. These angles were chosen based on the highest value of solar irradiance and electricity exported to the grid for each location. In this study, the solar module CS6X-340M-FG, manufactured by Canadian Solar, was used (Table I). The output AC power, the DC-AC conversion efficiency, and the capital cost of the inverter are the main factors when selecting a suitable inverter. GROWATT 5500MTL-S DUAL MPPT 6KW SOLAR INVERTER was selected (Table II). In general, the solar resource assessment is the first step of the PV system design. Figure 4 depicts the monthly average daily global irradiation on a horizontal surface and the global radiation on a horizontal surface and a 25° inclined plane for all chosen sites. It is observed that June is the period with the lowest solar irradiation in Botswana. The minimum tilted solar radiation was found to be 5.52kW/m²/d for Gaborone, 5.57kW/m²/d for Maun, and 5.40kW/m²/d for Tsabong. The maximum value of tilted solar radiation was recorded in September (i.e. 6.69kW/m²/d) for Gaborone, August (i.e. 6.91kW/m²/d) for Maun, and December (i.e. 6.96kW/m²/d) for Tsabong.

TABLE I. SPECIFICATIONS OF THE SELECTED PV MODULE

PV module technology	Mono-Si	Poly-Si
Manufacturer	Canadian Solar	Canadian Solar
Model	mono-Si - CS6X-300M	poly-Si - CS6X-310P
Nominal power [W]	300	310
Open-circuit voltage [V]	45	44.9
Short-circuit current [A]	8.74	9.08
Voltage at point of maximum power [V]	36.5	36.4
Current at point of maximum power [A]	8.22	8.52
Module area [m ²]	1.919	1.918
Efficiency [%]	15.63	16.16

TABLE II. SPECIFICATIONS OF THE SELECTED INVERTER

PV module Technology	Value
Rated Power [W]	6000
Min PPT Voltage [V]	100
Max PPT Voltage [V]	550
DC Startup Voltage [V]	100
DC Shutdown Voltage [V]	80
Max Input Voltage [V]	550
Max DC Power [W]	6500
Max AC Power [W]	5000
Max DC Current [A]	30
Warranty [year]	10
Efficiency [%]	97.9
Cost [USD]	550

The performance of the PV systems in terms of PV output and CF is dependent on the orientation angles [33]. Thus, the Electricity Exported to the Grid (EEG) and the CF were

estimated at a tilted angle of 25° and an azimuth angle of 180° for all selected locations. It should be noted that fixed-tilt mounting systems are simpler, cheaper, and require less maintenance compared to tracking systems. The mean monthly value of EEG for all the selected locations is shown in Figure 5. The following are observed:

- In Gaborone, the EEG is within the range of 664.01-793.74kWh for mono-Si and 686.14-820.20kWh for poly-Si.
- In Maun, the EEG varied from 604.69 to 834.89 kWh for mono-Si and from 624.84 to 862.72kWh for poly-Si.
- In Tsabong, the EEG ranged between 665.26 and 828.70kWh for mono-Si and from 677.11 and 856.33kWh for poly-Si.

- The maximum amount of EEG is recorded in August while the minimum value is recorded in June for Gaborone.
- The lowest and highest values of EEG are recorded in February and August, respectively for Maun.
- For Tsabong, the highest and lowest values of EEG occurred during June and December, respectively.
- The poly-Si technology delivered higher energy to the grid than the mono-Si technology.

The annual value of EEG and CF for each location is shown in Table IV. It was found that the maximum annual EEG value of 9159.63kWh for poly-Si and 8864.16kWh for mono-Si occurred at Tsabong. The CF values were within the range of 19.84-19.78% with an average value of 19.81%. It was noticed that the CF of poly-Si technology is a slightly higher than mono-Si technology. These results can be supported by [34, 35]. The authors in [34] found a CF of 15.37% for mono-Si technology and 15.41% for poly-Si technology, while the authors in [35] estimated that the CF value for mono-Si and poly-Si technology is 11.47% and 12.9%, respectively.

Fig. 4. Monthly average daily global radiation on a horizontal surface and a 25° tilted plane.

TABLE III. THE ANNUAL VALUE OF EEG AND CF OF EACH LOCATION

Location	PV technology	EEG [kWh]	CF [%]
Gaborone	Mono-Si	8854.36	19.80
	Poly-Si	9149.50	19.82
Maun	Mono-Si	8836.07	19.78
	Poly-Si	9130.61	19.80
Tsabong	Mono-Si	8864.16	19.82
	Poly-Si	9159.63	19.84

B. Economic Sustainability

The techno-economic feasibility for rooftop PV systems at the three selected locations was evaluated for different values of electricity export rate (0.03-0.21 USD/kWh with a step of 0.03 USD/kWh). The assumed input financial parameters included 7.2% inflation rate, 3.75% discount rate, 9% reinvestment rate, 25 years of project life time, 70% debt ratio, 0% debt interest rate, and 20 years of debt payments, based on previous studies. Based on these input parameters, NPV, ALCS, SP, EP, LCOE, and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) were estimated BY RETScreen. The NPV was determined for each location and the calculated values of Electricity Export Rate (EER) are listed in Table V. It was found that the NPV for each value of EER is positive, which indicated that the project is potentially feasible [36, 37]. There is a strong correlation between NPV and EER. IRR was estimated to evaluate the economic viability of the project [30, 36], as it provides the true return of interest generated by equity over the life of the project [29]. The results showed that increasing the rate of exporting electricity led to an increase in IRR. In addition, it was observed that the IRR of the three locations is higher than the required rate of return of the project. Furthermore, ALCS was calculated by using NPV, discount rate, and project lifetime. It was found that ALCS is within the range of 70.35-3099.09 USD/year. Additionally, the results of economic viability using poly-Si technology are higher than those for mono-Si technology (Table V).

TABLE IV. ANNUAL VALUE OF EEG AND CF FOR EACH LOCATION

Location	Parameter	PV technology	Electricity export rate [USD/kWh]						
			0.03	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.15	0.18	0.21
Gaborone	Pre-tax IRR-equity	Mono-Si	5.96	17.78	28.38	39.00	49.74	60.58	71.49
	Pre-tax IRR-assets		-0.64	5.98	10.65	14.62	18.27	21.75	25.14
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]		1171.19	8959.66	16748.13	24536.60	32325.08	40113.55	47902.02
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]		73.00	558.47	1043.94	1529.41	2014.88	2500.35	2985.81
	Simple payback [Year]		31.68	15.84	10.56	7.92	6.34	5.28	4.53
	Equity payback [Year]		17.94	7.09	4.13	2.88	2.20	1.78	1.49
	Benefit-Cost (B-C) ratio		1.46	4.55	7.63	10.72	13.80	16.89	19.97
	Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0466	0.0466	0.0466	0.0466	0.0466	0.0466	0.0466	
	Pre-tax IRR-equity	Poly-Si	6.42	18.49	29.44	40.42	51.54	62.76	74.04
	Pre-tax IRR-assets		-0.35	6.33	11.07	15.13	18.86	22.44	25.92
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]		1430.81	9478.89	17526.98	25575.07	33623.15	41671.24	49719.33
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]		89.18	590.84	1092.49	1594.14	2095.79	2597.44	3099.09
	Simple payback [Year]		30.66	15.33	10.22	7.66	6.13	5.11	4.38
	Equity payback [Year]		17.23	6.78	3.97	2.77	2.12	1.72	1.44
Benefit- Cost (B-C) ratio	1.57		4.75	7.94	11.13	14.32	17.51	20.69	
Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451		
Maun	Pre-tax IRR-equity	Mono-Si	5.93	17.73	28.32	38.91	49.63	60.45	71.33
	Pre-tax IRR-assets		-0.66	5.96	10.62	14.59	18.24	21.71	25.09
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]		1122.57	8844.16	16565.75	24287.34	32008.92	39730.51	47452.10
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]		70.35	554.23	1038.11	1521.99	2005.87	2489.75	2973.63
	Simple payback [Year]		1.87	7.36	9.75	11.31	12.47	13.41	14.19
	Equity payback [Year]		31.74	15.87	10.58	7.94	6.35	5.29	4.54
	Benefit- Cost (B-C) ratio		1.44	4.50	7.56	10.62	13.68	16.74	19.80
	Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0468	0.0468	0.0468	0.0468	0.0468	0.0468	0.0468	
	Pre-tax IRR-equity	Poly-Si	6.39	18.45	29.37	40.33	51.43	62.62	73.87
	Pre-tax IRR-assets		-0.37	6.30	11.04	15.09	18.82	22.39	25.87
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]		1379.95	9358.93	17337.90	25316.88	33295.86	41274.83	49253.81
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]		86.48	586.49	1086.50	1586.51	2086.52	2586.53	3086.54
	Simple payback [Year]		30.72	15.36	10.24	7.68	6.14	5.12	4.39
	Equity payback [Year]		17.27	6.80	3.98	2.78	2.13	1.72	1.44
Benefit- Cost (B-C) ratio	1.55		4.71	7.87	11.03	14.19	17.35	20.51	
Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0453	0.0453	0.0453	0.0453	0.0453	0.0453	0.0453		
Tsabong	Pre-tax IRR-equity	Mono-Si	5.97	17.80	28.42	39.04	49.80	60.66	71.57
	Pre-tax IRR-assets		-0.63	5.99	10.66	14.64	18.29	21.78	25.17
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]		1147.11	8893.24	16639.37	24385.50	32131.63	39877.76	47623.89
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]		71.88	557.30	1042.72	1528.14	2013.56	2498.98	2984.40
	Simple payback [Year]		31.64	15.82	10.55	7.91	6.33	5.27	4.52
	Equity payback [Year]		17.92	7.08	4.13	2.88	2.20	1.78	1.49
	Benefit- Cost (B-C) ratio		1.45	4.52	7.59	10.66	13.73	16.80	19.86
	Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0467	0.0467	0.0467	0.0467	0.0467	0.0467	0.0467	
	Pre-tax IRR-equity	Poly-Si	6.43	18.52	29.47	40.47	51.61	62.84	74.12
	Pre-tax IRR-assets		-0.34	6.34	11.08	15.14	18.88	22.46	25.95
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]		1405.31	9409.65	17413.98	25418.32	33422.65	41426.99	49431.33
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]		88.07	589.66	1091.26	1592.86	2094.46	2596.06	3097.66
	Simple payback [Year]		30.62	15.31	10.21	7.66	6.12	5.10	4.37
	Equity payback [Year]		17.21	6.77	3.96	2.76	2.12	1.71	1.44
Benefit- Cost (B-C) ratio	1.56		4.73	7.90	11.07	14.24	17.41	20.58	
Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451	0.0451		

The economic viability of a project is estimated by determining the payback period [30. 36]. Table IV lists the payback period including EP and SP for all selected locations. It is found that the EP is within the range of 1.44-17.99 years. The developed PV project with mono-Si technology in Maun has the longest EP and SP of 17.99 years and 31.74 years, respectively, followed by one in Gaborone. The proposed project with poly-Si technology at Tsabong has the shortest EP of 1.44 years and SP of 4.37. The results reveal that the increase in EER will lead to a decrease in EP and SP. Besides, the results demonstrate that the SP value exceed the lifetime of the project (25 years) when the EER is equal to 0.03 USD/kWh. This indicates that installing PV projects at the

selected locations is not economically viable when the EER is equal to 0.03 USD/kWh. In addition, the value of B-C, which is utilized to determine the cash flow generated viability, is higher than 1 as shown in Table V. These findings indicate the feasibility of the projects [27]. Moreover, the LCOE sets a minimum selling cost of electricity that may result in an NPV of zero. Table V shows the LCOE for each location with various PV technologies. It is observed that the LCOE is within the range of 0.0451-0.0468 USD/kWh. These values are within the range of 0.0199-3.165 USD/kWh [38]. Besides, the LCOE of PV systems is less than the current electricity tariffs in Botswana (0.098 USD/kWh for households and 0.117 USD/kWh for businesses).

Fig. 5. Monthly average value of EEG on a 25° tilted plane.

C. Climate Co-Benefits Assessment

In addition to economic feasibility, an estimate of the environmental benefits in terms of reduced GHG emissions of the proposed system would be attractive. The climate co-benefits in terms of GHG emission reduction were calculated using RETScreen for each location and are listed in Table VI in multiple equivalent formats. The results indicate that a large amount of CO₂ emissions can be avoided by implementing the developed PV project in each considered location. It is noticed that the PV projects with poly-Si technology have the highest amount of CO₂ emission reductions. It should be noted that the total amount of CO₂ emission reduction for each location is determined based on the electricity generated annually [39]. Tsabong and Maun have the highest and lowest amount of CO₂ emission reduction, respectively.

TABLE V. GHG EMISSION REDUCTION (tCO₂)

Location	Annual GHG emission reduction [tCO ₂] equivalent to	PV technology	
		Mono-Si	Poly-Si
Gaborone	Gross annual GHG emission reduction	15.83	16.35
	Care and light trucks not used	2.90	3.00
	Liters of gasoline not consumed	6800.39	7027.07
	Barrels of crude oil not consumed	36.81	38.03
	People reducing energy use by 20%	15.83	16.35
	Acres of forest absorbing carbon	3.60	3.72
	Hectares of forest absorbing carbon	1.46	1.50
	Tons of waste recycled	5.46	5.64
Maun	Gross annual GHG emission reduction	15.79	16.32
	Care and light trucks not used	2.89	2.99
	Liters of gasoline not consumed	6786.35	7012.56
	Barrels of crude oil not consumed	36.73	37.96
	People reducing energy use by 20%	15.79	16.32
	Acres of forest absorbing carbon	3.59	3.71
	Hectares of forest absorbing carbon	1.45	1.50
	Tons of waste recycled	5.45	5.63
Tsabong	Gross annual GHG emission reduction	15.84	16.37
	Care and light trucks not used	2.90	3.00
	Liters of gasoline not consumed	6807.92	7034.85
	Barrels of crude oil not consumed	36.85	38.08
	People reducing energy use by 20%	15.84	16.37
	Acres of forest absorbing carbon	3.60	3.72
	Hectares of forest absorbing carbon	1.46	1.51
	Tons of waste recycled	5.46	5.65

IV. CONCLUSION

The solar energy potential and techno-economic feasibility of grid-connected rooftop PV systems at three selected locations in Botswana were investigated in this study. For this purpose, the annual value of GHI was estimated to categorize the solar resource in the selected locations. Furthermore, the feasibility of a grid-connected PV system was assessed utilizing RETScreen. Based on the value of GHI, the selected regions are suitable for installing large-scale or small-scale PV systems. The results demonstrated that small-scale PV projects are feasible and economical viable. Besides, the price of the electricity generated by PV systems is less than that of the conventional system. It can be concluded that the developed systems provide a very good insight into the economic feasibility of such project for all the considered locations. Consequently, a huge potential of solar energy exists in the country, which if used effectively can play a vital role to overcome the current energy deficit.

V. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study has some limitations that may be addressed in the future. The impact of meteorological parameters including air temperature, and relative humidity on the performance of the PV system was neglected. The influence of these parameters can be addressed using HOMER [41]. The financial parameters were assumed based on previous studies. Therefore, the impact of policy changes and critical variables such as the initial costs of the project, inflation rate, and discount rate on the feasibility of grid-connected rooftop PV systems should be investigated in the future. Moreover, the interaction between the distribution network and the PV system must be realized in order to understand the impact of the grid-connected PV systems on the distribution network.

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Maize Yield Prediction using Artificial Neural Networks based on a Trial Network Dataset

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ABSTRACT

The prediction of grain yield is important for sowing, cultivar positioning, crop management, and public policy. This study aims to predict maize productivity by applying an artificial neural network and by building models of multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) using public data and maize experimental networks. The dataset included parameters of climate, soil water balance, and agronomic characteristics from maize hybrids of an experimental network of two agricultural years. The climatic and soil balance water parameters were divided according to the maize plant development stages. Six databases were obtained by combining the imputation of missing data with the agronomic characteristics of the maize hybrids, the climatic parameters/soil water balance, and the complete database with both. Hyper parameterization of the models was obtained using GridSearch and k-fold cross-validation. The models with imputation were more accurate than those without it. The model with climate data/soil water balance and the complete model with imputation presented the smallest errors of 71 kg ha^{-1} . In all the models, cultivars, locations, and their interactions were important, and different climatic conditions had the greatest weight in predicting productivity. It was concluded that the MLP models performed adequately and captured the non-linear effects of the interaction between the environment and maize hybrids. Climatic and soil balance water parameters at different stages of maize plant development explain the productivity of maize hybrids more than the agronomic characteristics of the cultivars.

Keywords-artificial neural networks; deep learning; multilayer perceptron; agricultural productivity

I. INTRODUCTION

Interpretation of the genotype x environment interaction is essential to increase productivity with the positioning of the cultivar in the microregion and its predictability of performance according to the sowing date [1]. Traditionally, analysis methods of the genotype x environment interaction have been used for the positioning of cultivars, however, the interpretations obtained after obtaining data and generalizations about the environment do not allow the application or extrapolation of results for all regions [2-3]. However, when

the environments are well characterized, conclusions on cultivar performance are extrapolatable, as used nitrogen levels in rice [4] or used water deficit environments in maize [5]. The simulation models of plant growth in response to climate, soil, and cultivars allow identifying the best sowing times, which are made available annually for different cultures and locations, such as the Agricultural Zoning of Climatic Risk, and have helped Brazilian farmers in all grain-producing locations [6-7]. However, even with agricultural risk zoning, weather conditions are unpredictable, and productivity losses are common in different regions, locations, and years when this

information is not available in real time. Production losses caused by drought in the Paraná-La Plata basin, Brazil, have reduced soybean and maize production and affected global and South American agricultural markets during the past ten years, with the 2020-2021 drought imposing a 2.6% reduction in the cereal harvest compared to the previous year [8].

The multilayer perceptron (MLP) is an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) that can be used for productivity estimates. It uses the factors that affect productivity as an implicit function of the network input. MLPs have been successful in creating predictive models using plant development parameters, soil characteristics, management, climatic conditions, and geographic positions with a small mean error for yield prediction [9-11]. The predicting maize productivity using ANN can generate information for public policy on the production and supply of this important crop for local and national food security. The prediction can also generate real-time information for managing corn crops to increase productivity and sustainability.

ANNs are being applied with different models or architectures to solve common problems in plant breeding and genotype x environment interactions and other agriculture situations. This can be observed when determining drought tolerance indices for durum wheat and identifying their efficiency in relation to other methods [12], parents for crossings in breeding programs [13] and, selected soybean plants in segregating populations of different maturity groups [14]. A machine learning approach was used in the automatic irrigation system based on humidity and temperature in the soil in [15]. The deep convolutional neural network architecture is very efficient to identify plants in the different stages including seedling of weed plants [16]. In addition, the estimate of maize productivity as a function of leaf chlorophyll content, measured in three stages of plant development, was determined by an ARN-MLP and was adequate, considering that in the stage of development of the plant with six leaves (V6), it explained 50% or more of maize productivity data [17]. In turn, arabica coffee production was predicted to meet the market demand using ANNs with data on productivity, rainfall, relative humidity, and minimum and maximum temperatures. An adequate prediction accuracy was obtained with an R^2 of 0.8524 and RMSE (root-mean-square deviation) of 0.0784 tons, demonstrating the potential of ANNs in determining the yield of the coffee cherry [18].

Therefore, the objective of this study was to predict maize productivity by applying ANNs and building MLP models while using public data and maize experimental networks.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The variables for the analysis in this study were divided into agronomic, climatic, and soil water balance parameters.

The agronomic characteristics of maize hybrids were obtained from the Performance of Maize Hybrids at the Second Season, with 38 hybrids in 2018 and 32 hybrids in 2019 in 9 locations and 4 replications/locations in the Bernardino de Campos, Capão Bonito, Cândido Mota, Cruzália, Ibirarema, Manduri, Maracá, Palmital, and Pedrinhas Paulista in the middle region of the Paranapanema Valley, state of São Paulo

[19-21]. The agronomic characteristics evaluated were plant height, ear height, the ratio between ear height and plant height, the number of lodged plants, number of broken plants, number of days to flowering, plant population, productivity, grain moisture at harvest, and ear index per plant. The daily climate parameters were total precipitation, maximum, average, and minimum temperatures, average atmospheric pressure, average dew point temperature, average and minimum relative humidity, average wind speed, and maximum wind gust. The daily soil water balance variables included water storage, actual evapotranspiration, soil water deficit, soil water surplus, and evapotranspiration. Total precipitation, water storage, and water surplus in the soil were considered at the cumulative sum of each plant development stage. The average for each period was considered for the other climate and water balance variables. Daily climatic and soil water balance data were obtained from automatic stations (Ourinhos A716, Itapeva A714, Avaré 725) at the National Institute of Meteorology (INMET), which provides a variety of daily meteorological data on a platform [22]. As the INMET does not have meteorological stations in some municipalities, it was necessary to consider data from the nearest stations, covering distances from 27 to 95km. Water balance variables were subdivided according to the growth and developmental stages of the maize plant.

The developmental stages of the maize were plant emergence (VE), 4 leaves with a visible leaf collar (V4), 8 leaves with a visible leaf collar (V8), tasseling (VT), silk and blister (R1 and R2), milky and dough grains (R3 and R4), dent grains (R5), and physiological maturity (R6). The cultivars had the same 120-day cycle, and the stages were considered with the same periods for all cultivars. The days for each stage were VE from the emergence to the 10th day, V4 from the 11th to the 40th day, V8 from the 41st to the 50th day, VT from the 51st to the 60th day, R1 and R2 from the 61st to the 75th day, R3 and R4 from the 76th to the 90th day, R5 from the 91st to the 105th day, and R6 from the 106th to the 120th day.

The database was processed before the effective implementation of the models and comprised up to 2392 data from 17 experiments on the performance of maize hybrids at the second season in 2018 and 2019. The necessary procedures for data preparation were the imputation of missing data, coding of categorical variables, and normalization (Figure 1). The database contained missing data on flowering and grain moisture, representing 6% of the total database. The iterative imputation algorithm was used to impute these data, and the necessary parameterization for the execution of the iterative imputation was the neural network's own MLP with a δ_{\min} of 0.1. The parameter δ_{\min} defines the number of iterations performed by the iterative imputation and the minimum acceptable error in relation to previous iterations.

The regressor defined for the predictions in the MLP with the hyperparameters for data imputation had three hidden layers, 64 neurons per layer, the ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activation function in the hidden layer, 300 epochs, ADAM optimizer, 0.001 rate learning curve, MSE (Mean Squared Error) cost function, and the Glorot normal-weight initialization method. This regressor was chosen based on the

ability of ANNs to capture nonlinear relationships between data [23]. The dataset was divided into two groups: one with all variables with complete data and the other with only variables with missing values. Therefore, two MLP models were built to estimate the variables of both sets using the same hyperparameters. For model training, each dataset was partitioned into training and testing sets. The training set had 80% of the examples, and the test set had the 20%. After inputting the data, transformations were applied to the categorical variables, cultivars, and years. The codification adopted transformed them as a function of annual productivity, given the variable of interest:

$$Location_r = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l p_i - p_{year} \quad (1)$$

where l is the number of observations carried out in the r^{th} Location, p_i is the i^{th} productivity of the Location, and p_{year} is the average of the observations made.

$$Year_s = \frac{1}{a} \sum_{j=1}^a p_j - p_{year} \quad (2)$$

where a is the number of observations carried out in the s^{th} Year, and p_j is the j^{th} productivity of the Year.

$$C_k = p_k - p_{Location} \quad (3)$$

$$cultivar_e = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^e c_k \quad (4)$$

where p_k is the k^{th} observation of the productivity of cultivar c_k , $p_{Location}$ is the average productivity of a given location and, e is the number of observations of the cultivar, and c_k is the k^{th} difference between p_k and $p_{Location}$.

In all the above equations, the categorical variables are functions of the observed average productivity, allowing the attribution of an evaluation to these variables. In the normalization procedure, the network input dataset was normalized by MinMax scaling. The dataset was separated into 3 distinct bases: agronomic characteristics, climatic/water balance parameters, and complete with all variables with or without missing data imputations. In addition, 6 network models were implemented for the same purpose, with the task of predicting productivity as the model output. The necessary hyper parameterization in the 6 models was defined using Grid Search and k-fold cross-validation to find a set of hyperparameters with the smallest error in the cost function. For this purpose, a set of hyperparameters was previously considered to be tested by Grid Search and evaluated by k-fold cross-validation. $k = 5$ was considered for k-fold cross-validation, which is one of the values commonly used in the literature [24].

The input hyperparameters for GridSearch were 3 hidden layers with 32, 64, and 128 neurons per layer, the ReLU activation function in the hidden layer, 300, 600, and 900 epochs, the ADAM optimizer, learning rates of 0.005, 0.003, and 0.001, the MSE cost function, and the Glorot normal weight initialization method.

Fig. 1. The proposed methodology.

The MLP experiments were performed on the services provided by Google Research, Google Collaboratory, or Colab, which is a host of services based on the Jupyter notebook, where it is possible to interactively execute codes in the Python language, in addition to having a set of tools for the development of deep learning models [25-26]. Six models were constructed using TensorFlow and Keras [27-28]. The k-fold cross-validation used in model validation matched that of the machine learning library scikit-learn, which has a set of tools for developing machine learning models [23]. The SHapley additive exPlanations (SHAP) method was applied so that the model with the best performance could be interpreted agronomically [29].

III. RESULTS

The hyperparameters of the models without imputation, with the lowest RMSE among the 142 models trained using Grid Search and k-fold cross-validation, are listed in Table I. The AGR_M model required a greater number of layers and a larger batch size than the CLI_M and COP_M models, demonstrating a greater requirement of hyperparameters for model adjustment. A hidden search is computationally expensive, which makes it impossible to apply the method to a large number of hyperparameters [30]. Therefore, there is a possibility that the hyperparameters are not the global optimum but local optima due to the small set of hyperparameters. However, the use of the grid search is justified by its computational cost [30].

The learning curves of the AGR_M, CLI_M, and COP_M models with MSE show concise training without much variation between training and validation and without overfitting to training data, with training time up to 1000 epochs (Figure 2). In the CLI_M model, closer values were obtained between the training and validation sets, as can be observed in the distance between the training and validation curves. In addition, there was variation at the beginning of the adjustment of the models, which is evidenced by the epochs where the adjustments of the functions began, remaining below 100 epochs for AGR_M and COP_M, and close to 250 for CLI_M. The possible causes for this are the hyperparameters used in the models, such as the batch size, number of layers, and database. The COP_M model presented an intermediate distance between the training and validation cost functions.

This occurred when the data of agronomic characteristics were included, bringing data variation to the adjustment of the functions. However, they lose the advantage of the greater adjustment of the climatic data of the CLI_M model.

In the model validation dataset, the AGR_M obtained the highest RMSE (201 kg ha⁻¹) and the CLI_M model had the lowest RMSE (191 kg ha⁻¹), demonstrating the best fit in relation to the first (Table II). Model-associated errors (MSE) were relatively similar, with a tendency to be greater in the AGR_M model than in the others, demonstrating the lowest fit and highest hyper parameterization of the ANN. Based on Pearson's correlation statistics, all models obtained similar values close to 1. In the training dataset, the AGR_M model presented the lowest RMSE and MSE values, characterizing its better performance in the adjustment in relation to the other two models that were very similar, with the smallest variation of the dataset. In turn, this situation is reversed, in validation, when the AGR_M model presented the highest RMSE and MSE values.

TABLE I. HYPERPARAMETERS OF MODELS WITH LOWER ERRORS BY GRID SEARCH AND K-FOLD CROSS-VALIDATION WITH (I) AND WITHOUT (M) IMPUTATION FOR PREDICTING GRAIN YIELD (KG.HA⁻¹)

Hyper parameters	AGR_M	CLI_M	COP_M	AGR_I	CLI_I	COP_I
Hidden layers	2	1	1	2	1	1
Neurons	64	64	64	128	128	64
Epochs	1000	1000	1000	1000	600	1000
Batch size	128	32	64	128	32	64
Learning rate	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.001

Fig. 2. Cost function (MSE) training and k-fold cross-validation without data imputation for AGR_I, CLI_I and COP_I models.

When imputing the missing data in the base, another set of hyperparameters was needed to reach the local optimum when submitted to grid search (Table II). This indicates that the missing data complement new standards for the adjustment of the models and that each one of them was changed differently with a greater number of hidden layers, neurons/layer, epochs, and batch size for AGR_I, a smaller number of layers, batch size, epochs, and larger neurons/layer for CLI_I, and fewer

hidden layers and neurons/layer for COP_I among the 142 models trained by grid search and k-fold validation (Table I). The changes between the non-imputed and imputed models were in the number of neurons, epochs, batch size, and learning rate, requiring a new ANN architecture. Considering that each neuron corresponds to a hyperplane, a greater number of 128 neurons for the AGR_I and COP_I models is necessary to properly separate the instance space. Only COP_I remained with the same number of neurons as the models without data imputation, characterizing the explanation of model adjustment using climate variables.

To predict the behavior of parents for breeding programs, the architecture of the ANN was optimized using 3 layers: the first with 64 neurons, the second with 32 neurons, and the third with 16 neurons, with the ReLU activating function having the highest accuracy of prediction [13]. The learning rate of AGR_I was 0.005, demonstrating that the model was "stuck" in poor locations with a lower learning rate. Only CLI_I managed to converge in a smaller number of epochs, and 600 epochs reinforced the quality of the climate data for predicting productivity with the imputed data. The impact of data imputation on model training showed that the MSE in 1000 epochs was lower than that of the models without data imputation for AGR_M and COP_M (Table I). However, the training was less consistent, as can be seen by the requirement for a greater number of epochs to start the adjustment of the imputed models AGR_I, CLI_I, and COP_I compared to the non-imputed models AGR_M, CLI_M, and COP_M (Figures 2 and 3). One possible reason for this is that imputation increases data variability.

TABLE II. METRICS OF MODELS WITH AND WITHOUT IMPUTATION FOR PREDICTING GRAIN YIELD (KG.HA⁻¹)

Metrics	AGR_M	CLI_M	COP_M	AGR_I	CLI_I	COP_I
RMSE Validation	201	191	197	80	71	74
MSE Validation	414	365	390	87	60	60
Correlation Validation	0.99	0.99	0.99	1	1	1
R² (%) Validation	0.9875	0.9819	0.9842	0.9978	0.9975	0.9983
RMSE Training	162	177	172	49	75	69
MSE Training	264	315	295	25	56	48
Correlation Training	1	0.99	0.99	1	1	1
R² (%) Training	0.9912	0.9890	0.9907	0.9994	0.9986	0.9987

The curves of the models with imputation show that CLI_I training and validation are closer than those of AGR_I and COP_I (Figure 3). In addition, the number of epochs needed to converge was smaller, so, it can be inferred from this model, with or without imputation of data, that climate explains the behavior of productivity. The imputed model that obtained the lowest RMSE was CLI_I with 71 kg.ha⁻¹, demonstrating an adequate fit with an error of just over one bag of maize per hectare (Table II). It is also possible to notice that the training and validation errors are similar, demonstrating that the model

can generalize productivity prediction. However, AGR_I obtained the highest validation RMSE (80 kg ha^{-1}), which allows adjusting the model to the training examples. The COP_I model obtained a validation RMSE of 74 kg ha^{-1} . However, it tended to increase the error (MSE) during training. In all models, there was a high correlation, with no significant differences with the models without data imputation. The AGR_I model, when compared to the AGR_M model, showed more overfitting to the training data (Figures 1 and 2). Like AGR_M, the AGR_I model presents the same situation as the agronomic characteristics, which are not sufficient to explain productivity. This suggests that more agronomic traits are needed to increase grain yield prediction and that climate variables are fundamental for hybrid yield estimation. This can be confirmed by the COP_I and COP_M models, which consider all variables in the database; therefore, the training and validation curves are closer to each other.

Fig. 3. Cost function (MSE) training and k-fold cross-validation validation with data imputation for AGR_I, CLI_I and COP_I models.

Based on the metrics of the models, the imputation of data obtained superior performance compared to the base with missing data. The models with imputation presented RMSE up to 3 times lower than those without, which suggests that the problem in question requires a reasonable amount of data so that the performance of the ANN is increasing, but due to database reduction and imputation, the MLP models are adequate. The models with and without imputation obtained an RMSE very close to 1% and 3% of grain yield which is considered very good. In the Syngenta Crop Challenge 2018, with a productivity data set of 2,267 maize hybrids in 2,247 locations between 2008 and 2016, the of [10] was considered one of the best, with an RMSE of 12% of the average yield using forecast weather data.

Using another strategy, maize yield prediction was performed with machine learning with different models, and the best of them, Stacked LASSO, presented a Mean Bias Error (MBE) of 53 kg/ha and a Relative RMSE (RRMSE) of 9.5% [32]. For the soybean crop, annual productivity was predicted in the region of the Brazilian states of Maranhão, Tocantins, Piauí, and Bahia as a function of monthly climate variables (air temperature, precipitation, and global radiation) and water

balance components (cultivation evapotranspiration, storage, actual cultivation evapotranspiration, water deficiency, and surplus) during plant development through a deep artificial neural network [33] with a dataset size of 920 examples, the obtained RMSE was $167.85 \text{ kg.ha}^{-1}$. The unprecedented differential in the strategy of using climatic variables subdivided into maize plant development stages that are differentially sensitive to water stress was assertive. This can be the main reason why, even with a smaller database, the RMSE of the models was smaller than that found in the literature.

Despite the generalization of the positioning of cultivars by different methodologies, either the traditional methods of adaptability and stability or ANN models, the germplasm of the species must have a genetic response to the common stress in the region, as verified by the authors in [34, 35], who identified maize cultivars with different responses to nitrogen. Authors in [36] identified the response of maize cultivars as a function of organic fertilization, and in [37] identified different responses of maize cultivars to irrigation with saline water. Therefore, without genetic control of tolerance or resistance to stress, the differences between cultivars do not affect productivity, and it is simply dependent on the environment, being high when this is favorable. However, when tolerance or resistance to stress has genetic control, the environment with or without the presence of stress does not affect the productivity of the cultivar, as it is due to its genes. Due to the importance of the cultivar in the models, it can be stated that there are differences between the cultivars how they interact with the environment.

MLP models with different precisions do not allow us to identify which agronomic or climatic variables are the most important for predicting productivity. This can be achieved with SHAP analysis applied to the COP_I model, identifying the variables with the greatest impact on the model (Figure 4). The most important variables were the cultivar, the average productivity of the cultivars/site, and the site itself (edaphic conditions), which is consistent with the agronomic explanation of the productivity of the cultivar, the physical and climatic environment, and the interaction of the cultivar with the environment [38]. The cultivar defines the productive potential of the environment and its limitations in certain environments. The adaptation of cultivars to the environment is related to their genetic adaptation to the soil, water regime, plant development cycle, absorption and use of nutrients, and tolerance to insects, pests, and diseases [39]. Cultivar, productivity/location (prod_local), and location had the greatest impact on the output of the variable in the COP_I model. The prod_local defines the average productivity that can be obtained in a given location, showing the effect of the climate \times soil \times cultivar interaction. The local variable defines the edaphic conditions, latitude, and altitude of the environment. This means that the model was able to capture edaphic effects on productivity and the interaction between the cultivar and the environment. The environment, represented by the effect of climate and local conditions, is an important factor that can vary over time, and edaphic conditions are fixed between harvests [38]. EPH (ear/plant height) ratio is an important characteristic of grain yield and is directly related to plant lodging, which directly interferes with harvesting when

performed mechanically. However, it should be considered that the agronomic characteristics present genetic correlations, which are determinants in the expression of the phenotype when evaluated under a certain stress, which is also a cause of productivity [40]. In the results found, the evaluated agronomic characteristics and the cultivars were presented in a similar way, not being related to the climatic variables that explain productivity. relative humidity (RH), excess precipitation in the soil (EP), EPH ratio, total daily precipitation (TP), minimum daily temperature (MT), soil water storage (WS), deficit precipitation in the soil (DP), wind with maximum daily gust (WG), evapotranspiration (EV), emergence (VE), fourth leaf (V4), eighth leaf (V8), tassel (VT), silk and blister (R1_R2), physiological maturity (R6).

Fig. 4. Average impact of the variables on the output of the COP_I model.

In the emergency stage, only the relative air humidity (HR_VE) is important. The emergence of seedlings and their establishment provide the formation of a stand, which is the main component that explains productivity and is affected by HR_VE. Relative air humidity plays an important role in plant transpiration and soil evaporation, making plants more sensitive to a lack of precipitation [41].

In the vegetative phase, during the fourth-leaf stage, only excess precipitation (PS_V4) was highlighted, and in the eighth-leaf stage, the total daily precipitation (PT_V8), minimum daily temperature (MT_V8), water storage (WS_V8), and precipitation deficit (PD_V8) were highlighted. MT_V8 and PS_V4 act together in plant growth and development, where the number of plants per hectare and plant height is defined. Relative air humidity plays an important role in plant transpiration and soil evaporation, rendering the lack of precipitation more sensitive [41]. The minimum daily temperature is an important factor for the metabolism of corn and the entire C4 plant, inhibiting the rubisco enzyme that affects carbohydrate production, which is closely related to productivity [42]. The variables PS_V4, PT_V8, WS_V8, and PD_V8 related to precipitation are fundamental for the development of the plant and the prediction of productivity, requiring 3–4 mm in the initial stages of the corn plant and reaching the need close to 6–8 mm being the main parameters associated with the limitation of grain yield [43].

In tasseling, relative air humidity (AH_T), wind with maximum daily gust (WG_T), and precipitation deficit (PD_T) were important. The variable AH_T during this phase can affect grain production by reducing plant fertility in dry

environments typical of the second crop sowing in February in São Paulo State, Brazil [44–45]. Wind gusts can damage maize plant leaves, break plant culms, or bed down plants, causing a direct loss of harvest [46]. These results are consistent in predicting the performance of maize productivity and temperature in the flowering phase, and the frequency and the amount of water received during the vegetative phase, and grain filling were identified as the main environmental factors [47]. The lack of precipitation is considered the most important environmental parameter in bolting, delaying the coincidence of receptivity between male and female flowers and preventing fertilization [44, 48].

In the reproductive phase, in the silk and blister stage, relative humidity (RH_R1_R22), water storage (WS_R1_R22), and evapotranspiration (EV_R1_R22) were important. At the physiological maturity stage, total daily precipitation (TP_R6), minimum daily temperature (MT_R6), and excess precipitation (EP_R6) were important for predicting the model in the final stage of maturation and were related to plant physiology at this stage. This is justified by the intense water, thermal, and relative humidity requirements of the air at the beginning of filling and grain formation of the corn plant. Note that the 30 days referring to the reproductive stages R3 to R5 did not influence productivity prediction.

Different climatic and water balance variables had different impacts on the stages of maize plant development, indicating that the partitioning of these variables must be carried out to increase the accuracy of the models.

IV. DISCUSSION

The different ANN architectures of the models demonstrate a greater need for data or hyper parameterization for the AGR_M model than for the other models due to the greater number of hidden layers and batch size. The CLI_M model had the lowest data requirement for productivity prediction, characterizing the importance of environmental data in relation to hybrids when they were evaluated in groups with the same cycle. However, all three models without imputation showed good error estimates with values around 200 kg.ha⁻¹, which is considered small in yields that reach at least 6000 kg.ha⁻¹, representing only 3%.

The AGR_M, CLI_M, and COP_M models with 3 hidden layers did not obtain optimal hyperparameters defined by the grid search and k-fold cross-validation in the databases without data imputation. Only the models with 1 or 2 hidden layers obtained optimal hyperparameters, and therefore, the models with 3 layers were discarded. This may have occurred because the model tended to overfit the training data.

The AGR_M model required a larger batch size than the other two models for more consistent training, because the agronomic characteristics of the hybrids, such as the same cycle, height of plants and spikes, and grain productivity, are similar or very close, because Brazilian legislation requires that the new cultivars must be at least equal to those on the market in terms of productivity, even though the germplasms that originated from different hybrids have some similarity between the companies. Therefore, the agronomic characteristics of the hybrids do not concisely explain the different yields between

the environments since none of the hybrids capitalized on the genotype × environment interaction between the evaluated microregions. This similarity between the hybrids required different batch sizes of the CLI_M and COP_M models for adjustment.

The MLP-ANN models with imputation (I) showed lower errors than the models without imputation (M), lower ANN architecture requirements, and even fewer epochs. The set of routines for maize hybrid evaluation is more suitable for use in MLP-ANN models when data imputation is applied. Different architectures of the MLP-ANN models with smaller batch sizes, layers, or epochs occur for the CLI_M and CLI-I models. They also present the smallest errors and converge in models more assertively even with climate data from distant meteorological stations, from 27 to 100 km. This characterizes the robustness of the MLP-ANN models and the importance of climate data in predicting productivity in relation to the agronomic data of hybrids that present significant differences in their productivity [17, 18].

The AGR_M and AGR_I models that are based only on the agronomic data of corn hybrids require a greater process capacity and more complex models with larger batch sizes, layers, and times. The AGR_I model had the lowest precision (0.005) among all models. The accuracy of the models characterizes their adequacy. It was also found that, in several scientific publications in experiments evaluating the productivity of maize hybrids, the coefficients of variation were equal to or less than 12%, which can characterize minimal significant differences between the hybrids than 600 kg.ha⁻¹, considering yields from 5 ton.ha⁻¹. Significant differences between corn hybrids in experiments as to their yields were detected when their differences were greater than 12%, as verified in 143 experiments in 15 years of publications with the maize crop for the grain yield, in which the average coefficient of variation was 11.87% [49].

When dealing with both agronomic and climatic characteristics, the COP_M and COP_I models bring to their iterations the difficulties encountered with the AGR models. However, with data imputation, the AGR_I model presents an MSE close to the COP_I's but requires a greater number of epochs. The low RMSE values can be explained by the methodology used to evaluate the climatic data in the different stages of plant development, which were strategically correct and possibly the cause of the success of the ARN used. This was confirmed by the importance of different climatic parameters and water balance as variables of importance in the construction of the model. This also allows the model to be used in advance according to the stages of development of the plant, allowing for more assertive decision-making in different scenarios and moments of the crop. Therefore, those in charge of the crop can obtain new information at the time of sowing and at the time of cultural practices and fertilization during the vegetative phase, where it is still possible to manage the crops when they are not irrigated. When crops are irrigated, it is possible to manage the application throughout the plant's development, especially at the most critical times, such as grain filling.

The models can detect the non-linear effects between climate, soils, and genotypes, especially when climate information is included in the model or when they are sufficient to predict grain yield, even with several hybrids that have the same cycle.

The results of the models are adequate, even considering the limited amount of data analyzed on the ANNs and their application in the processes of the improvement programs without the need for modifications in the processes. The ANN models can identify important variables during the development stage of the plant, and it is observed that climatic and water balance variables are important. The water balance variables are important at all the stages of maize plant development and demonstrate the availability of water that is stored in the soil and that can be used by the plant, being the main environmental parameter limiting productivity [48].

New environmental parameters can be incorporated into the ANN models, further increasing their accuracy. An ANN based on a graph-based framework developed by Graph Neural Network-Recurrent Neural Network (GNN-RNN), using geospatial and temporal information to predict crop productivity was proposed in [11].

V. CONCLUSION

- The implemented ANNs managed to extract a pattern in the data even if the locations of the experiments and cultivars were different, which shows the capacity of the ANNs in the generalization of productivity prediction.
- The ANN models are well suited for predicting corn yield and present concise training, even with a limitation in the amount of data, when exclusively using the agronomic characteristics of the hybrids. This limitation is overcome when climatic data are incorporated into the model because most of the variation in productivity is due to these parameters.
- The imputed climate model was the most homogeneous in its performance and was the most suitable for productivity prediction.
- The SHAP analysis is important for the agronomic understanding of the results and is completely consistent with the knowledge of the ecophysiology of corn plants under stress.
- Multilayer perceptron models present adequate performance and capture the non-linear effects of the interaction between the environment and maize cultivars.
- The climatic parameters of each stage of maize plant development explain the productivity of the cultivars more than their agronomic characteristics.

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A Numerical Study addressing the Stress Distribution in Circular Steel Tube Confined Concrete Columns considering Various Concrete Strengths

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ABSTRACT

The axially compressive behavior of Steel Tube Confined Concrete (STCC) columns has been experimentally investigated by many researchers throughout the world. However, it is extremely complicated to measure the stresses of steel tubes and concrete core in real tests. Therefore, to investigate the fundamental behavior of STCC columns under axial compression, this paper presents a numerical study that explores the stress distribution in steel tubes and concrete core. The circular STCC columns with the use of Normal Strength Concrete (NSC), High Strength Concrete (HSC), and Ultra-High Strength Concrete (UHSC) were simulated in a Finite Element Model (FEM) in ABAQUS. The material model for confined concrete incorporating a wide range of concrete strength values was developed in the simulation. The obtained from FEM curves of load versus strain of circular STCC columns were compared with those measured in real tests to verify the accurateness of the FEM. Deriving from the results of FEM, the stress states and their distribution in outer steel tubes and concrete core along the column height were described. Also, the longitudinal stresses on the cross-section of the concrete core were calculated corresponding with the load stage to quantify the strength enhancement of the concrete core due to the confinement effect from the steel tube. Furthermore, the confining pressure provided by the outer steel tube and impacting on the concrete core was plotted. Based on the findings in this paper, the effect of various concrete strengths on the stress distribution in circular STCC columns was investigated.

Keywords-steel tube confined concrete; NSC; HSC; UHSC; ABAQUS; FEM

I. INTRODUCTION

It is widely known that the confinement effect in Concrete Filled Steel Tube (CFST) columns can result in remarkable improvements in compressive strength and ductility [1-11]. Therefore, CFST columns have been extensively applied in civil engineering projects. For this column type, when the steel tube and the concrete core are loaded simultaneously, the confining stress induced by the steel tube is less effective as compared to the case where only the concrete core is loaded [5-11]. If the ductility and strength of composite columns are considered as critical design factors, it is suggested that the load should be applied on the concrete core only in order to form Steel Tube Confined Concrete (STCC) columns [9]. Many previous studies have conducted experimental tests on the axial compressive behavior of STCC columns [1-4], but they have mainly focused on the use of Normal Strength Concrete (NSC) or High Strength Concrete (HSC). Recently, several studies have reported the test results of circular STCC columns infilled with Ultra-High Strength Concrete (UHSC) under axial compression [5, 10, 11, 19]. According to them, the

confining stress level in STCC columns depends on concrete strength. The dilation of concrete under compression is higher with lower concrete strength, thus the interaction between the concrete core and the steel tube becomes stronger. For STCC columns, at the ultimate state, the concrete core is subjected to triaxial stress, while the steel tube is under biaxial stress. In real tests, it is complicated to measure all stresses in the concrete core and in the steel tubes. Accordingly, the confining stress induced by the steel tubes and imposed on the concrete core is hardly calculated. Therefore, many studies have attempted to use Finite Element Models (FEMs) to simulate the mechanism in STCC columns. Based on the FEM results, all stresses on STCC columns can be quantified. Authors in [12] presented an FEM in ATENA-3D software to investigate the effect of concrete strength on the compressive behavior of STCC columns. Authors in [9] developed an FEM using ABAQUS software to analyze the mechanisms of STCC short columns under axial compression, however they only focused on NSC. Authors in [13] introduced an analysis of circular STCC stub columns with some modifications to the Drucker – Prager

model in ABAQUS, and they quantified the lateral confining pressure and the interface shear stress between the concrete core and the steel tube. Authors in [15] investigated the effect of friction on axially loaded STCC short columns by utilizing an FEM. Equations considering the friction coefficient were developed to predict the load bearing capacity of STCC short columns.

From the literature review, it is apparent that numerical studies on the mechanical performance of STCC columns remain very limited with only a handful of studies considering the STCC columns with the use of NSC or HSC. Therefore additional research should be further carried out to better understand the compressive behavior of STCC columns when UHSC is infilled. Furthermore, the majority of the existing studies were concerned with the comparison of load versus displacement or load versus strain curves of STCC columns between the FEMs and the test results and very few studies dealt with the stress distribution in the steel tubes and the concrete core of STCC columns. The interaction between the concrete core and the steel tubes through the confining stress is complex and can't be measured experimentally. To address the aforementioned research gap, this paper aims to develop an FEM in ABAQUS software to simulate the mechanism of circular STCC stub columns with a wide range of concrete strengths, i.e. NSC, HSC, and UHSC. The constitutives of confined concrete were proposed based on some previous studies and some modifications to Concrete Damaged Plasticity Model (CDPM). The established FEM was verified against the collected test results. Subsequently, the confining stress and the distribution of axial load in the concrete core and the steel tube were clarified. Finally, the biaxial stress state of the steel tube was quantified by plotting the longitudinal and hoop stresses along the height of the columns.

II. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL DESCRIPTION

A. General Description

The circular STCC short columns were simulated using FEM in ABAQUS (version 6.11) [28]. Due to the symmetrical nature of the circular column, only one-eighth of the column was modelled. CAX4R elements with reduced integration and 4-node axisymmetric elements were used to model the steel tubes and the concrete core. Based on the mesh convergence studies, the element size was chosen as $t/5$, where t is the thickness of the steel tube. For short columns with the ratio of L/D (length to outer diameter) smaller than 4, the initial imperfections can be ignored in FEM. Surface-to-surface contact was employed to model the interaction between the steel tubes and concrete core. A contact surface pair including the inner surface of the steel tubes and the outer surface of the concrete core was defined. The concrete surfaces were chosen as master surfaces, while the steel surfaces were treated as master. As suggested in [18], the friction coefficient between the steel tube and concrete was taken as 0.6. Two Reference Points (RPs) were created at the center of each upper and lower cross-section. Boundary Conditions (BCs) were assigned to both reference points, while the load was applied downward at the upper reference point. The "rigid body" constraints were employed to tie the reference points to both the end surfaces of the concrete core. To ensure the load was applied only on the

concrete core, only the end surfaces of the concrete core were fixed against all degrees of freedom except for the displacement at the upper loaded end. Figure 1 shows the FEM including mesh type, boundary conditions, and loading application.

Fig. 1. Typical FEM of a circular STCC stub column.

B. Material Models

The stress – strain relationship ($\sigma - \epsilon$) proposed in [22] was adopted for the material model of the steel tube. This model covers a wide range of steel yield strength (f_y) from 200 to 800MPa. CDPM provided in ABAQUS was employed to simulate the compressive behavior of confined concrete. The key parameters in CDPM include the uniaxial compressive stress – strain relationship, compressive damage variable d_c , ratio of the second stress invariant on the tensile meridian to that on the compressive meridian K_c , ratio of initial equibiaxial compressive yield stress to initial uniaxial compressive yield stress σ_{b0}/σ_{co} , dilation angle ψ , fracture energy G_f , viscosity, and eccentricity α . The values of K_c , ψ , and σ_{b0}/σ_{co} were calculated by using the equations suggested by [20-22], while the remaining parameters such as α , d_c , G_f , and viscosity were defined as the default values in Abaqus. The stress – strain relationship for NSC, HSC, and UHSC after taking into account the confinement effect was developed for circular STCC short columns, as can be seen in [22]. The $\sigma - \epsilon$ curve includes three stages:

The ascending branch (OA) is expressed by the equations proposed by [23]:

$$\frac{\sigma}{f_c} = \frac{A \times X + B \times X^2}{1 + (A-2) \times X + (B+1) \times X^2} \quad 0 < \epsilon \leq \epsilon_{c0} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$A = \frac{E_c \times \epsilon_{c0}}{f_c'}; B = \frac{(A-1)^2}{0.55} - 1; X = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_{c0}} \quad (2)$$

The strain ϵ_{c0} at the peak stress of the unconfined concrete is calculated by [24]:

$$\epsilon_{c0} = (-0.067 \times (f_c')^2 + 29.9 \times f_c' + 1053) \times 10^6 \quad (3)$$

The confined strain at the point B (ϵ_{cc}) is determined using the equation proposed in [25]:

$$\frac{\epsilon_{cc}}{\epsilon_{c0}} = 1 + 17.4 \times \left(\frac{f_B}{f_c}\right)^{1.06} \quad (4)$$

$$f_B = \frac{0.03 \times f_y}{e^{0.02 \times \frac{D}{t}}} \quad (5)$$

where f_B is the confining stress at the point B and determined by (5) suggested by [26].

The descending branch (BC) is expressed by an exponential function proposed by [27]:

$$\varepsilon_{c0} = (-0.067 \times (f'_c)^2 + 29.9 \times f'_c + 1053) \times 10^6 \quad (6)$$

where α and β are factors determining the shape of the descending branch.

III. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL VERIFICATION AND MECHANISM ANALYSIS

The established FEM was used to simulate 3 circular STCC short columns, taken from previous studies, under axial compression. Specimens C2-30-3D-C and C1-100-3D-C reported in [16] and NB4.0-UHFB reported in [17] were considered. It is noted that, NSC (C30, $f_c = 32.7\text{MPa}$) and HSC (C90, $f_c = 105.5\text{MPa}$) were used for the specimens C2-30-3D-C and C1-100-3D-C, respectively, while UHSC (C150, $f_c = 174.2\text{MPa}$) was used for NB4.0-UHFB. Dimensions and material properties of the selected specimens are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. FEM verification and stress distribution on the cross section at different points. (a) Test C2-30-3D-C, (b) Test C1-100-3D-C, (c) Test NB4.0-UHFB.

In order to verify the accuracy of FEM, the load versus strain ($N-\epsilon$) curves of the 3 specimens obtained from FEM were compared with those measured by the test results. It can be seen in Figure 2 that, in the ascending phase, the FEM results agree well with the measured results, but in the descending phase, there is a slight difference between the predicted and the measured curves. For the descending phase of specimens C1-100-3D-C and NB4.0-UHFB, the ($N-\epsilon$) curves in FEM exhibit similar behaviors with the real tests. There is a loss of load after the peak load, followed by a horizontal branch. Overall, it can be observed that FEM predicts well the complete ($N-\epsilon$) curves of all tested specimens.

Figure 2 also illustrates the distribution of the axial load between the concrete core and the steel tube and the confining stress provided by the steel tube. For NSC filled in steel tube (C2-30-3D-C), at the ultimate state, the concrete core contributed approximately 70% to the total load. However, it is observed that the concrete core carries almost the entire load for the case of HSC and UHSC. At the ultimate state, 90% of the total load was carried by the HSC core in specimen C1-100-3D-C and UHSC core in specimen NB4.0-UHFB. Furthermore, the steel tube in the case of HSC and UHSC core tends to carry less axial load before the peak stress as compared to the case of NSC. Accordingly, in the ascending branch of the ($N-\epsilon$) curves, the confining stress in the case of NSC core is more intense and develops faster than in the case of HSC and UHSC. In the plastic stage, the confining stress steadily increases after reaching a stable value. Figure 2 demonstrates the distribution of longitudinal stress in the concrete section (at the top surface of the column) corresponding to three points (1, 2, and 3) in the ($N-\epsilon$) curves. For the NSC core, the confining stress reaches the maximum value of 8.2MPa, which is twice the maximum value of the confining stress in the case of HSC and UHSC core. It can be seen in Figure 2 that the longitudinal stress across the concrete section is uniform along the axis of cylinder and increases gradually when the distance apart from the center of section increases. The longitudinal stress in the concrete section for the NSC core was significantly larger than that for HSC and UHSC cores. This implies that the confinement is more effective with lower concrete strength. These findings are in good agreement with the research results in [1, 8, 12-15, 22].

Figure 3 shows the distribution of longitudinal stress and hoop stress in the steel tube at the ultimate state. The ratios of stress to yield strength of steel tube (σ/f_y) were plotted along the height of the columns (h/H). It can be observed that the distribution of stresses in the steel tube is non-uniform. The longitudinal stress of the steel tube is zero and the hoop stress is relatively high at both ends of the columns. The longitudinal stress increases and the hoop stress decreases towards the column mid-height. Also, at the mid-height of the columns, the maximum value of longitudinal stress is achieved, while the hoop stress is significantly reduced. The hoop stress was maximum at $H/10$, which is quite near to the end surface of the column. The maximal values of longitudinal stress and hoop stress were about $0.55f_y$ and $0.9f_y$, $0.50f_y$, and $0.9f_y$, and $0.40f_y$ and $0.9f_y$ for NSC, HSC, and UHSC cores, respectively. The distribution of longitudinal stress in the steel tube along the column height is in line with the results reported in [9, 13, 14],

however there is a difference in the distribution of hoop stress in the steel tube between this study and the results in [9, 13, 14]. The maximum value of hoop stress in this study is generally smaller than that in [9, 13, 14]. For example, authors in [9] stated that the hoop stress is highest at the column ends. It should be noted that the confining stress depends mainly on the hoop stress. Based on the FEM results, it can be identified that confining stress is maximum at $H/10$ for circular STCC columns.

Fig. 3. Distribution of stresses in the steel tube at the ultimate state.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions deriving from the FEM results of the current study are:

- The established FEM with some modifications to CDPM in ABAQUS can predict well the compressive behavior of circular STCC columns with the use of NSC, HSC, and UHSC. The distribution of stress in the concrete core and steel tube, and the confining stress can be quantified by using this FEM.
- The confining stress or confinement effect is more effective with lower concrete strength.
- The axial load carried by the concrete core becomes smaller with increasing concrete strength.
- The longitudinal stress of the steel tube is zero at both ends of the columns and increases towards the mid-height of the column, while the hoop stress is maximal at the position of $H/10$ and decreases towards the mid-height of the column.

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Effect Factors on Unconfined Compressive Strength of Soil-Cement Columns: The Case Study of Ba Ria, Vung Tau, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the effect of the curing environment on the unconfined compressive strength of soil-cement samples and in finding the optimum output mix ratio and estimating the effect of silica fume in the admixture. This work is based on the data from the Cai Mep-Thi Vai inter-port road project and results from laboratory experiments. The results show that the specimens with the highest strength were cured in soil, lowered in city water with NaCl 2.5% and then NaCl 5%. The optimum silica fume admixture ratio equals to 1% (in comparison with the weight of cement content).

Keywords-soil cement; soil improvement; unconfined compressive strength; mixture ratio; silica fume; soft soil

I. INTRODUCTION

The deep soil mixing method or soil-cement column method is an advanced technology in which the cement is blended with in-situ soft soil. Materials in dry and slurry form could be used in the soil-cement method. The hollows are made by using a rotated mixing machine which combines several types of cutting tools. The cementitious materials are also injected during the execution process. Currently, there are many researched and developed deep mixing terminologies [1, 2]. The three main developing phases include: chemical mixing (lime cement or soil cement), mixed-in-place columns, and soil mixing.

In these terminologies, the Deep Soil Mixing (DSM) has certain advantages such as: rapid stabilization, accelerated construction in site, higher soil strength at lower cost. Authors in [3-5] showed that DSM is suitable for application in some problematic soils, especially expansive soils. Typical DSM has been applied in reclaimed and soft native soils in the

transportation sector in Japan [6]. The DSM technique is an advanced technology of improvement. Some projects in Vietnam have used this method, e.g.: the Ba Ngon harbor project (Khanh Hoa province), Can Tho airport, Bac Lieu airport, etc. More and more projects use this technology for soft soil treatment.

II. INVESTIGATION OF THE REACTION IN SOIL CEMENT COLUMNS

Portland Cement (PC) is created in a controlled chemical process with the combination of aluminum, calcium, iron, silicon, and other compounds. In order to construct Blended Portland Cement (BPC), an amount of gypsum, and several minerals are mixed with PC or clinker in the hydraulic adhesive process [3, 4].

Hydration reaction and hydrated cement (to form primary cementitious product): When using cement to stabilize the ground, minerals on the cement surface react with the hydrated

cement from the pore water of the soil quickly to form three compounds: calcium hydroxide, hydrate calcium silicate, and hydrated calcium aluminate. The first cementitious products are the primary cementitious product. Water and cement react as described below:

The structure and strength in the soil matrix are determined by the hydration process which makes agglomeration, and cation exchange, and stabilizes the soil clay and flocculation.

III. EFFECT FACTORS ON UNCONFINED AXIAL COMPRESSION OF SOIL CEMENT SAMPLES

Many soil types such as sandy sand, soft clays, clayey silts, clays, and sands are in turn used to test with the soil-cement column method [7-10]. In these studies, some major soil factors that have the main influence on the compression development of soil-cement columns are I_L (Index liquid), W_n , F_c , and pH.

Authors in [11, 12] showed that some soils have $I_L > 15\%$ and $pH < 5$, and the unconfined axial compression strength becomes too low, even though they had high other stabilizer properties. The main reason is the reduction of the ion Ca^{2+} for the pozzolanic reactions process. Authors in [8] also showed that with more organic content, the unconfined compress strength decreases. The interference of organic contents in compression gain are not entirely understood, however authors in [13, 14] pointed out that the mechanisms of organic properties are:

- The structural composition and cementing compound can be changed by organic matter via the hydrated process and other extraneous matter.
- The organic matter can hold more than 10 times its dry weight in water, therefore the hydration may be faced with a water limit.

The axial compression could be augmented by some parameters of soil such as soil minerals, sand consistency of fine, plastic index, etc. [5, 8, 9]. Soil cement column quantity depends on the type of clay or sand and the characteristics of each soil, which is especially important given the low pH values (from 5.4 to 5.8) in Mekong Delta, Vietnam [15].

Some of the conditions at the site during the treatment process such as the mixing duration, the rate of installation, the shape of the mixing, etc. affect directly the unconfined compressive strength of soil-cement columns [1, 10, 15-16]. However, not much research has been conducted on the effect of these characteristics of soft soil, as it is difficult to reflect these characteristics in lab conditions.

IV. LABORATORY ASSESSMENT OF THE CASE STUDY RESULTS

The road in port terminal Cai Mep-Thi Vai along the Thi Vai River helps to develop and connect the traffic infrastructure and the industrial areas. Soft soil improvement in the area utilizes soil-cement columns. The road cross-section is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Embankment supported by deep mixing in a component project.

A. The Effect of Cement Content on the Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)

In general, UCS varies from 900.4 to 1320.4kPa at 28 days, and from 1256.2 to 1732.5kPa at 60 days. The optimum cement content is 240kg/m^3 (1175 – 1300kPa). It is lower than that in [17] (300kg/m^3).

Fig. 2. The effect of cement content on (UCS) at 28 days.

Fig. 3. Variation of UCS with water/cement ratio at 28 days.

B. Variation of UCS with Water/Cement Ratio

The optimum water/cement ratio is 0.8. Increased water/cement ratio means increased water content. Water content is needed to be enough for the hydrate reaction to occur. If the added water content is superfluous, it will make holes full of water in the product, decreasing its strength (Figure 3).

C. Variation of UCS with Silica Fume/Cement Ratio

The highest UCS occurs when silica fume/cement equals to 1%. If silica fume/cement ratio is more than 1%, the UCS will decrease (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Variation of UCS with silica fume/cement ratio at 7 days.

In summary, the UCS with silica fume/cement=1%, at 7, 14, 28, and 60 days ranges between 129 and 125%, 112 and 124%, 125 and 138%, and 113 and 135%, respectively. The strength of the soil-cement column increases the stability in the soil environment more than in other environments. Pozzolanic reaction occurs between $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and silica fume to increase the strength of the specimen when silica fume is added. When the silica fume addition is more than 1% and if the mixed process is not widespread, it will surround the cement gain, preventing the hydrate reaction.

D. Variation of UCS with Curing Time

The longer the curing time the higher the strength of soil cement samples is. The strength develops fastest from 0 to 7 days (equal to around 40% to the strength at 60 days) and then increases in a slower pace (see Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Variation of UCS with curing time for various soils.

In comparison with its values at 7 days, UCS is around 163 – 192% at 28 days. These values are bigger than the ones obtained in [5] (140 - 150%). Authors in [11] reported strength ratio at 7 to 28 days about (12.0 - 210%). The test result depends on the type of cement, the type of soil treatment, the water/cement ratio, etc. UCS varies from 121 to 131% at 60 days.

V. ANALYSIS AND VARIATION OF CORE SAMPLING AT SITE

A. Effect of Cement Content

The optimum cement content equals to 240kg/m^3 . This value is the same with the laboratory research result.

Fig. 6. Variation of USC with cement content.

B. Variation of UCS with Water/Cement Ratio

Maximum strength of soil cement column is reached when the water/cement ratio is 0.7 and lowers a bit when water/cement ratio is 0.8. UCS decreases remarkably when the water/cement ratio is 0.9.

Fig. 7. Variation of UCS with water/cement ratio at 14 and 28 days.

C. Relation between Stress and Strain

The variation of UCS with strain can be seen in Figure 8.

VI. VARIATION RESULT COMPARISON BETWEEN LABORATORY AND FIELD

The strength of laboratory mixed specimens and mixed field samples was compared in order to determine the correlation between them (Figure 9).

Fig. 8. UCS vs strain at 28 days.

Fig. 9. Laboratory and field UCS result comparison: (a) 220kg/m³ cement content, 0.7 water/cement ratio, (b) 240kg/m³ cement content, 0.7 water/cement ratio, and (c) 260kg/m³ cement content, 0.7 water/cement ratio.

In the same mixture steps, the results in the laboratory are often more worked-out than in the field.

VII. CONCLUSION

The main conclusions derived from the research results of this study are:

1) Optimum Mixture Ratio

The optimum cement content in laboratory and field mixed specimens is equal to 240kg/m³. The optimum water/cement ratio is 0.8 in laboratory mixed specimens and 0.7 in the field mixes.

2) Effect of the Curing Environment

The curing environment affects negligibly the compression values of soil cement columns. The highest strength of specimens is cured in soil environment, whereas it is lower in city water with NaCl 2.5% and 5%.

3) The Effect of Silica Fume

The optimum silica fume admixture equals to 1% of the weight of cement content for 60 days of curing in the laboratory. More research regarding long term curing is needed in order to evaluate the effect of silica fume. The pozzolanic reaction between Ca(OH)₂ and clay material is crucial, especially in the research area, where the type of clay is montmorillonite which is the most active clay.

4) Variation between the Strength of Cement Column in the Site and in the Laboratory

The strength of soil-cement columns depends heavily on contraction. In the current study, the strength of specimens mixed by the contractor A varied from 100 to 115% of the values of laboratory-mixed specimens. The values of the specimens mixed by the contractor B may varied from 42 to 67%.

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Torque Control of an In-Wheel Axial Flux Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor using a Fuzzy Logic Controller for Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the control design of an in-wheel axial-flux permanent magnet synchronous motor with one stator and one rotor, using a fuzzy logic controller for electric vehicles. In this controller, the surgeon ambiguous inference file is built by two input vectors, the stator current error and the derivative of the stator error. These input variables include five membership functions: Negative Big (NB), Negative Small (NS), Equal Zero (ZE), Positive Small (PS), and Positive Big (PB). The fuzzy logic controller was implemented using a 5×5 matrix to meet the required output stator voltage of the controller. The fuzzy logic torque controller was compared with the PI controller in stator current response, torque, and speed. The proposed controller was evaluated using simulation results from MATLAB/SIMULINK.

Keywords-AFPMSM; fuzzy logic; PI; FOC; Electrical Vehicles (EVs)

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric cars are a revolutionary trend in today transportation. Electric cars have advantages compared to cars with internal combustion engines as they eliminate complicated gearboxes and emissions and are environmentally friendly [1-2]. The powertrain structure of Electric Vehicles (EVs) tends to use an in-wheel distributed electric drive system consisting of multiple motors, which ensures traction at the front or rear of a car on two or four wheels, using a front, rear, or four-wheel drive system [3-4]. This electric powertrain improves driving performance by differentiating between wheels, makes full use of vehicle energy, improves transmission efficiency, increases range, eases braking, has good heat dissipation, and is more convenient for installation and maintenance [5-6]. The Axial Flux Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (AFPMSM) is widely used in in-wheel motor drive systems because it has short shaft length characteristics, is lightweight, has good vibration resistance, and has a long service life, thus improving reliability and safety [7]. Although AFPMSM motors enhance the performance of EVs, each vehicle should have installed multiple motors, resulting in a complex control system [8]. In-wheel motors increase the cost of a vehicle and have high requirements for control procedures, such as power balancing, electronic differential, and energy recovery. In addition, electric car in-wheel motors require small size, light weight, small torque, high efficiency, large overload capacity, and wide speed range [9]. Therefore, scientists have been interested in studying the control of traction and torque of in-wheel

AFPMSMs and their response to wheels. Torque and speed controllers are controlled based on Direct Torque Control (DTC) and Field-Oriented Control (FOC). These controllers are designed using linear and nonlinear control methods such as PI, LQR, dead beat, sliding mode, flatness, fuzzy [10-14], or hybrid controllers such as fuzzy-neural, fuzzy-sliding, and PI-fuzzy [14-17]. However, the torque response has a slight pulsation, and the actual speed response quickly and accurately tracks the required speed [17-20]. Therefore, the study of intelligent control solutions to improve an integrated in-wheel AFPMSM torque in an EV should be combined with the required components and physical properties, such as brake and accelerator pedals, road inclination, and wind resistance. Consequently, these parameters are necessary to improve the performance and torque of EVs.

This study presents the control design of an in-wheel AFPMSM, one stator, and one rotor, using a Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) for EV systems. In this controller, the surgeon ambiguous inference file is built by two input vectors, the stator current error and the derivative of the stator error. These input variables include five membership functions, Negative Big (NB), Negative Small (NS), Equal Zero (ZE), Positive Small (PS), and Positive Big (PB). The FLC was implemented with a 5×5 matrix so that the output stator voltage of the controller is met. The fuzzy logic torque controller was compared with the PI controller in stator current response, torque, and speed.

II. MODEL AND CONTROL OF THE ELECTRIC CAR POWER SYSTEM

A. Mathematical Model of an AFPMSM

It is possible to utilize the standard PMSM model for an AFPMSM. Stator parameters, such as the inductor calculation, change between the two models. Furthermore, the Back-EMF produced by an excitation coil and a permanent magnet is the same. Therefore, the radial PMSM of a AFPMSM and the model are mathematically related. The stator voltage equation in the d - q frame of reference is given by:

$$V_q = R_q + \frac{d}{dt} \lambda_q + \omega_e \lambda_d \quad (1)$$

$$V_d = R_d I_d + \frac{d}{dt} \lambda_d - \omega_e \lambda_q \quad (2)$$

The stator voltage equation is as follows:

$$\underline{u}_s^s = R_s \cdot \underline{i}_s^s + \frac{d\psi_s^s}{dt} \quad (3)$$

where R_s is the stator resistance and ψ_s^s is the stator flux. Then, converting (3) from the phase winding system of the stator to the coordinate system, quasi-rotor flux gives:

$$\underline{u}_s^f = R_s \cdot \underline{i}_s^f + \frac{d\psi_s^f}{dt} + j\omega_s \psi_s^f \quad (4)$$

The relationship between stator and rotor flux is described by:

$$\psi_s^f = L_s \underline{i}_s^f + \psi_p^f \quad (5)$$

where ψ_p^f is the polar flux vector. Since the d -axis of the coordinate system coincides with the axis of the polar flux, the perpendicular component (q -axis) of ψ_p^f will be zero. Thus, the flux vector has only real components.

$$|\psi_p^f| = \psi_p \quad (6)$$

The equation of flux components is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_{sd} = L_{sd} i_{sd} + \psi_p \\ \psi_{sq} = L_{sq} i_{sq} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where i_{sd} , i_{sq} are the d and q coordinate stator currents, and L_{sd} , L_{sq} are the d and q coordinate inductance. Substituting (5) and (6) into (4) and passing through the d - q coordinate system gives the system of equations of the PMSM motor:

$$\begin{cases} u_{sd} = L_{sd} \frac{di_{sd}}{dt} + R_s i_{sd} - \omega_e L_{sq} i_{sq} \\ u_{sq} = L_{sq} \frac{di_{sq}}{dt} + R_s i_{sq} + \omega_e L_{sd} i_{sd} + \omega_e \psi_p \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The torque of the motor is described by:

$$T_m = \frac{3}{2} P_p [\psi_f i_{sq} + (L_{sd} - L_{sq}) i_{sd} i_{sq}] \quad (9)$$

The motor torque is comprised of two components: the primary component $\psi_f i_{sq}$ and the reactive component. To create a control system, the stator current vector must be adjusted so that the vertical current vector is parallel to the polar flux. Therefore, there is a torque-generating current

component, not a magnetizing current component, and motor torque is given by:

$$T_m = \frac{3}{2} P_p \psi_f i_{sq} \quad (10)$$

B. Mathematical Model of the Electric Vehicle

The gearbox model shows the angular speed and torque relationships according to the gear ratio $k_{gear} < 1$, as shown in:

$$\begin{cases} T_m k_{gear} = T_{Wh} \\ \omega_{Wh} = \omega_m k_{gear} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where T_m is the motor torque, T_{Wh} is the torque acting on the wheel, $T_i = T_{Wh}$ is the load torque, and J is the inertia torque of the motor. Applying Newton's second law in the rotation of the motor gives:

$$T_{em} - T_{Wh} = J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} \quad (12)$$

The drive wheel model can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} v_{Wh} = \omega_{Wh} R_{Wh} \\ T_{Wh} = T_L = F_t R_{Wh} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The vehicle will act on the road surface with a force F while the wheel is resting on it with a force N and is being propelled by a torque T_{wh} . In contrast, the road surface will act against the vehicle with a point of the same value in the opposite direction of F_r . In this scenario, the reasonable force that propels the car at speed is the frictional force F_t given by:

$$F_t = m_v \cdot g \cdot \mu \quad (14)$$

where μ is the grip coefficient. The following equation results from applying Newton's second law to the parts of the outside force operating on the vehicle's body:

$$m_v \frac{dv_{ev}}{dt} = F_t - F_{aero} - F_{roll} - m_v \cdot g \cdot \sin(\alpha) \quad (15)$$

Air resistance is given by:

$$F_{aero} = \frac{\rho C_d A F}{2} (v_{ev} + v_{wind})^2 \quad (16)$$

In some cases, the wind speed can be set to $V_{wind} = 0$. The rolling resistance exists in the case of an underinflated tire and can be given by:

$$F_{roll} = f_r F_{zY} \quad (17)$$

$$F_{zY} = m_v g \cos(\alpha) \quad (18)$$

where F_{zY} is the vertical surface reaction and f_r is the rolling resistance coefficient.

III. FLC TORQUE CONTROLLER DESIGN

The FLC controls the system by calculating the necessary voltages u_{sd} and u_{sq} so that the difference between the currents i_{sd} and i_{sq} is as tiny as possible. The exactly planned i_{sd} and i_{sq} stator currents are used to regulate the motor's torque control current. This paper outlines the modern controller design for the i_{sd} and the control strategy for an in-wheel AFPMSM, one stator, and one rotor, utilizing an FLC. This controller uses the stator current error and the derivative of the stator error as the two input vectors to build the ambiguous inference file.

Fig. 1. (a), (b) Inputs, (c) output, and fuzzy rules of the FLC controller.

The input variables include five membership functions: Positive Big (PB), Positive Small (PS), Equal Zero (ZE), Negative Big (NB), and Negative Small (NS). Table I and Figure 1 show the FLC constructed using a 5×5 matrix. The FLC consists of 25 rules, which are implemented as follows:

- If (input 1 is NB) and (input 2 is NB), then (output is NB)
- If (input 1 is NB) and (input 2 is NS), then (output is NB)
- If (input 1 is NB) and (input 2 is ZE), then (output is NB)
- If (input 1 is PB) and (input 2 is PB), then (output is PB)

TABLE I. MATRIX OF FLC CONTROLLER

Input 1 (e) / Input 2 (Δe)	NB	NS	ZE	PS	PB
NB	NB	NB	NB	NS	ZE
NS	NB	NB	NS	ZE	PS
ZE	NS	NS	ZE	PS	PB
PS	ZE	ZE	PS	PB	PB
PB	ZE	PS	PB	PB	PB

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Building Trajectories of Accelerator, Brake, and Operating Modes of Electric Vehicles

The trajectories of accelerators and brakes of electric cars are built according to a function $F(x1, x2, \dots, xn)$. Figure 2 shows the trajectories of the accelerator and brakes. The F function can be obtained experimentally and the output is calculated by looking up or interpolating the defined table using the block parameters according to a method, such as linear (linear gradient), Lagrange (Linear Lagrange), closest point, block spline, and Akima spline interpolation. The F cos function can range in size from 1 to 30. The first and second inputs define the row and column dimension breakpoints, respectively. Figure 3 shows the determination of the accelerator and brake trajectories.

Fig. 2. The trajectories of the accelerator and brakes.

Breakpoints	Column	(1)
Row		--
(1)	0	0
(2)	0.1	8.2
(3)	0.2	14.35000...
(4)	0.30000...	20.5
(5)	0.4	32.8
(6)	0.5	41
(7)	0.6	61.5
(8)	0.7	82
(9)	0.8	123
(10)	0.9	164
(11)	1	205

Breakpoints	Column	(1)
Row		--
(1)	0	0
(2)	0.03	0
(3)	0.04	-8.2
(4)	0.3	-10.25
(5)	0.4	-12.2999...
(6)	0.5	-41
(7)	0.6	-51.25
(8)	0.7	-82
(9)	0.8	-123
(10)	0.9	-164
(11)	1	-205

Fig. 3. The parameters trajectories of accelerator and brakes.

B. Simulation Results and Evaluation

Figure 4 shows the control structure of the traction drive system for electric cars using the in-wheel AFPMSM, and Table II displays the simulation parameters.

The proposed controller was simulated in MATLAB to evaluate its effectiveness for the traction transmission system in electric cars using an in-wheel AFPMSM, with the following simulation scenario:

- Assume the speed of the wind is 0.
- The car moves on a flat road, but at $t = 3.5s$ to $4.3s$, the car goes downhill.
- At time $t = 0s$, the car starts to accelerate and the accelerator value increases from 0 to 1 after 0.45s. Torque reaches a maximum of 205Nm and remains there for 2s.
- At $t = 2s$, the vehicle starts to decelerate, and the brake reaches a value from 0 to 1 at $t = 3.5s$. The torque gradually decreases to -205Nm and returns to 0 at $t = 4.66s$.

Fig. 4. The control structure for electric cars using an in-wheel AFPMSM motor, based on a FOC method.

TABLE II. PARAMETERS FOR AFPMSM

Motor parameters	Value Symbol	Value
Power	P_{dm}	35Kw
Rated speed	N_{dm}	1800rpm
Rated voltage	U_{dm}	275V
Number of pole pairs	Z_p	8
Magnetic flux density	ψ	0.0437
Maximum torque	P_{max}	205Nm
Armature resistance	R_s	0.0101Ω
Shaft inductance d	L_d	2.4368e-4H
Shaft inductance q	L_q	2.9758e-4H

Table III shows the parameters of the simulated PI controller. Figures 6 and 7 show the stator current responses of the FLC and the PI controller. These figures show that the stator current response in the steady-state method is fast (0.4s) and accurate in the steady-state mode (the actual signal follows the set call). However, the proposed FLC gives better results than the PI controller in over-regulating (no over-throttling), while the PI controller with an over-regulating current at an over-regulating time is 10%. Table IV presents the evaluation criteria for the stator current responses of the PI and the FLC controllers.

TABLE III. PARAMETERS FOR THE PI CONTROLLER

Controller	K_i	K_p
Current controller I_d	7.103004e+2	0.8779
Current controller I_q	1.0615e+3	1.0744

TABLE IV. RESULTS OF EVALUATION RESPONSIBILITY

Controller	PI	FLC
Stator current i_{sd}		
Accelerated setting time (s)	0.4	0.4
Over-adjustment	10%	0%
Stator current i_{sq}		
Set-up time (s)	0.4	0.4
Over-adjustment	10%	0%

Fig. 5. The MATLAB/SIMULINK control structure for electric cars using an in-wheel AFPMSM.

Fig. 6. Stator current responses (a) i_{sd} and (b) i_{sq} for the PI controller.

Fig. 7. Stator current responses (a) i_{sd} and (b) i_{sq} for the FLC controller.

Figures 8 and 9 show the comparison of the torque and speed responses of the FLC and the PI controller. These figures show that the torque of the two controllers has the same form as the i_{sq} current. The FLC has less pulse rate (3%) for the torque response than the PI controller (8%). Table V shows the torque and speed response criteria of the PI and the FLC controllers.

TABLE V. RESULTS OF EVALUATION RESPONSIBILITY

Controller	PI	FLC
Torque responses		
Shape	Same as i_{sq} current response	Same as i_{sq} current response
Torque ripple	8%	3%
Speed responses		
Accelerated setting time	2.2 (s)	2.2 (s)
Over-adjustment	0%	0%

Fig. 8. Torque responses of the PI controller.

Fig. 9. Torque responses of the FLC controller.

Figure 10 shows the speed responses of an electric car transmission system using the PI controller and the FLC. The actual speed response of an electric car in both cases is in line

with the set requirements, and the speed response does not have too much speed adjustment at starting, accelerating, and decelerating.

Fig. 10. Speed responses of the PI controller and the FLC.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an in-wheel AFPMSM motor torque controller design for a traction drive system using a fuzzy logic control method. The proposed controller was compared with the PI controller and its efficiency was demonstrated through MATLAB simulations. The proposed controller provides better torque and speed response results than the PI controller in terms of steady-state time, over-adjustment, and torque pulsation. However, this controller has a complicated design, so it is necessary to study more simple but intelligent control solutions in the future.

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Influence of the Incorporation of Alluvial Sand on the Mechanical Behavior of Marl Soil

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to evaluate the mechanical behavior of marl soil by replacing it with alluvial sand at 3, 5, and 10% by weight for a possible application in road geotechnics. After a geotechnical characterization of the materials used, the mixtures were characterized by the Atterberg limits test, the soil compressibility test, and the shear strength test. The results obtained showed that replacing a part of marl soil with alluvial sand had a positive impact on its mechanical behavior, as it improved cohesion and shear strength while significantly reducing compressibility and plasticity. These results confirm the possibility of using alluvial sand as a fine soil reinforcement or stabilization material.

Keywords-marl soil; alluvial sand; mechanical behavior; improvement

I. INTRODUCTION

Soils are universally found in nature and used in many areas of human activity, particularly in geotechnical engineering. Soils play a supporting role for various structures in civil engineering or public works and are also the basic elements of a wide range of geotechnical constructions. Fine soils contain notable proportions of clays and silts that influence their intrinsic geotechnical properties. These soils deform under applied loads with amplitudes that can go from a few millimeters to a few meters. They also swell and become plastic in the presence of water, shrink with drought, and expand under the effect of freezing. Soil improvement, also known as soil treatment or stabilization, is a technique that has been introduced for many years with the primary goal of making soils capable of satisfying clay soil criteria [1]. This treatment is often performed to increase strength, reduce or increase permeability, reduce compressibility, and minimize the sensitivity of fine soil to changes in water content. Therefore, it is necessary to use other exterior materials to improve the geotechnical performance of the site [2]. Several studies have been conducted on the phenomena related to this type of soil. The soil treatment techniques vary according to their character, such as the treatment by adding rubber fiber [3],

natural or produced and product materials [4-6], and the use of waste tires, ashes and sewage sludge, which have shown good potential for soil stabilization [7].

The use of sand as a stabilizing material is a fairly recent technique and has not been widely used yet. This technique consists of replacing part of the soil with sand. Studies on this subject showed that the addition of sand reduces the plasticity of the mixture (clay-sand), thus reducing its swelling potential [8-10]. This study aims to investigate the effect of the addition of coarse alluvial sand on the mechanical behavior of marl soil to use it in road construction.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used two main materials in the composition of the test soils: alluvial sand and marl soil. The marl soil used came from Gueddid in the Djelfa region, Algeria, where it was extracted at a depth of about 1m. After extraction, the soil was placed in plastic bags and transported to the laboratory for preparation and execution of geotechnical identification and characterization tests. This soil was extracted in its natural red color state in compact clods, therefore, it is difficult to mix it with sand to produce the test soils. For this purpose, a laboratory procedure was followed to transform it into a very

fine powder, as shown in Figure 1, without modifying the chemical nature of the grains. Granular analysis was carried out by sieving grains superior to 80µm, according to NF P 94-056 [11]. On the other hand, a sedimentation method was carried out for grains with a diameter lower than 80µm, according to NF P 94-057 [12]. Figure 2 shows the particle size distribution of marl soil.

Fig. 1. Marl soil.

Fig. 2. Granular distribution of alluvial sand and marl soil.

The alluvial sand (Figure 3) used for soil reconstitution was extracted from Wade Messaad in Djelfa, and is commonly used to produce concrete on construction sites. The standardized test by dry voice according to NF P 18-560 [13], determines the distribution of the grains of sand according to their sizes, as seen in the granular curve shown in Figure 2. Table I summarizes the results of the sand equivalent test, specific gravity, and apparent density of this alluvial sand.

Fig. 3. Alluvial sand.

TABLE I. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ALLUVIAL SAND

Characteristic	Specific weight (g/m ³)	Apparent density (g/m ³)	Sand equivalent test (%)
Value	2.91	1.48	94.6

The main objective of the experimental study was to evaluate the effect of adding coarse alluvial sand at different percentages on the mechanical properties of marl soil, such as Atterberg limits, soil compressibility as determined by an odometer test, and shear strength using the direct shear test. The experimental study was conducted at the NLHC in Djelfa, Algeria. The samples were prepared in the following way:

- Soil samples were dried for 24 hours.
- Preparation of marl and alluvial sand mixtures with mass percentages of the latter being 0%, 3%, 5%, and 10%.
- Humidification of the samples to a water content of 20%.
- Mixing of the samples.
- Compacting samples by static compression.
- Sampling using identical volumetric rings of samples of the same mass, height, and section.

The Atterberg limits were tested according to NF P 94-051 [14]. The test was carried out in two phases. The first was to study the Liquidity Limit (LL) of the water content, where a groove of standardized dimension, made in the soil and arranged in the Casagrande cup, closes under the action of 25 shocks applied in a standardized way. The second phase examined the Plasticity Limit (PL) of the water content, where a soil cylinder of diameter 3mm, made manually, cracks when it is lifted. Figure 4 shows a sample of the soil studied during the test.

Fig. 4. Procedure of the Atterberg limit test.

The odometer compression test is fundamental in the soil compressibility test, according to XP P 94-090-1[15], as it is a direct application of consolidation theory. This test allows an evaluation of the amplitude of the settlements of the structures, as well as their evolutions. The study of ground deformation can be reproduced in the laboratory thanks to the Terzaghi odometer. This device simulates the following configurations: a very large horizontal surface compared to its thickness, a uniform vertically applied load, and the possibility of zero horizontal displacements. The apparatus for axial loading a cylindrically shaped specimen placed in a rigid cylinder and measuring the variation ΔH of the height H separates the upper and lower faces of the specimen, which eventually becomes submerged, are in contact with draining disks. Figure 5 presents the test procedure.

The direct shear test was performed according to the NF P 94-071-1 [16] standard. This test determines the mechanical properties of the soil through the rectilinear shear of a sample

under constant load. The shear test was used to plot the intrinsic curve of the soil under study and determine its internal friction angle ϕ and its cohesion C . Figure 6 shows a mixture of the studied soils after the test.

Fig. 5. Compressibility test on a soil sample studied during its execution.

Fig. 6. Soil sample studied after the direct shear test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Atterberg Limit Test Results

Figure 7 shows the results of the Atterberg limit test for the studied mixtures. The results show that the plasticity index decreased in all mixtures as the alluvial sand content increased, from 24.4% to 19.2% after adding 3% sand and continuing to decrease until 11.5% for 10%. This indicates a change in consistency after the addition of sand and an improvement in soil workability. Several studies have also shown the same trend [5, 7].

B. Compressibility Test Results

Figures 8 and 9 show the initial and final void index and compressibility curves, respectively, of the mixtures. The results show that the coefficient of compressibility decreases with an increase in alluvial sand content, and therefore the compression of the soil decreases when the sand content increases.

The classification of soils according to their compressibility and void ratios was given in [17]. The compression coefficients C_c of the studied soils can be determined from the curves in Figures 8 and 9. Table II illustrates the classification of the studied mixtures. The results obtained show that the marl-sand soil mixtures are classified as moderately compressible soils.

Fig. 7. The plasticity index and the limits of liquidity and plasticity of the studied soils.

Fig. 8. Ratio of initial and final voids of mixtures.

Fig. 9. Compression index of mixtures.

TABLE II. MIXTURE CLASSIFICATIONS

Mixture with sand content (%)	$C_c / (1 + e_0)$	Soil class
0	0.159	Moderately compressible
3	0.169	Moderately compressible
5	0.1233	Moderately compressible
10	0.063	Moderately compressible

C. Shear Strength Test Results

The shear test evaluates the mechanical characteristics of soils, i.e. the cohesion C , the angle of friction ϕ , and the shear strength τ_{max} at the moment of failure. All tests for the different mixtures were carried out the same way as for the case of pure marl soil. Figure 10 shows the friction angle and the cohesion of the studied mixtures. The results show an increase in the angle of friction and a decrease in the cohesion of soils with an increase in the alluvial sand content. The angle of friction increases from 26.58° for pure marl soil to 30.82° , 36.21° , and 40.42° for soils with alluvial sand content of 3%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. This indicates that the incorporation of alluvial sand improves the shear strength of the marl soil.

Fig. 10. Angle of friction and cohesion of mixtures.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the mechanical behavior of marl soil treated with alluvial sand at a content of 3, 5, and 10% by weight. The main conclusions of this experimental study are:

- Changes in the Atterberg limits increase the liquidity limit and the plasticity limit, and, as a result, the plasticity index decreases. The decrease in the plasticity index indicates an improvement in soil workability.
- The compressibility coefficient of the mixtures decreases as the alluvial sand content increases.
- The angle of friction increases proportionally with the content of alluvial sand in the mixtures, whereas a rapid decrease in cohesion was observed when the alluvial sand content increased. This suggests that the addition of alluvial sand increases the shear strength of the marl soil.

The advantages of improving fine soils by using local materials are technical and economic, as they improve both stability and cost, which are very important factors to consider in a project.

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Prediction of the Adhesion Strength of Coating in Plasma Spray Deposition

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this work is to validate the existing plasma spray mathematical models, using a calculation method and the comparison with experimental data, in order to determine their validity. A preliminary evaluation of the adhesion based on the velocity and temperature of the particles is useful to be calculated by using the mathematical model. Given the thermal-physical properties and chemical composition of a Fe-based amorphous X-5 powder, a modified model was suggested. For comparison, a series of experiments using plasma spraying of the X-5 powder were conducted. The significance of the current study consists of the model validation by using the data of the plasma spraying of the Fe-based amorphous material as a potential substitution for saving production costs by using ordinary air as the plasma generation gas. The findings show the discrepancy between the models and the experimental results. The prediction of adhesion using the mathematical models does not cover essential parameters such as the enthalpy of the particle stream. It is necessary to improve the mathematical models, including the modified one, based on the experiment results, with different pairs of particles and substrate materials. The proposed formula is applicable during the preliminary design of the spray process and the development of a new torch construction.

Keywords-adhesion; coating; particle velocity; particle temperature; validity; prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Plasma spray deposition is an additive manufacturing technology whose application range extends beyond the traditional thermal spraying approach, including the plasma spraying approach, which relies heavily on melting. The plasma energy encourages the nitriding process to modify the structure and mechanical properties of the surface, but the temperature and chemical process prevail [1]. Many engineers and researchers have worked to produce thermal spray technology without melting, and the velocity of the particles is the primary driver in creating the deposition. Cold Spraying (CS) is the term for this procedure. Particles stick to and deposit onto a substrate in CS without melting, allowing functional coatings to be deposited. In recent years, technologies that use particle kinetic energy in addition to thermal energy, such as High-Velocity Oxy-Fuel (HVOF) flame spraying and thermal spraying, have been developed. The most common example of these new approaches is the CS method. The natural oxide film on the surface is damaged by repeated particle impacts during the activation phase, known as incubation, and an increase in chemical activity due to the creation of the nascent surface is critical to adhesion. Due to the quick impact of the solid particles, it was inferred that the contribution of atomic diffusion to adhesion is low. Plastic deformation occurs when the substrate material and particles undergo explosive bonding upon particle contact, undulating in

a wavy pattern, and layers are created by mixing in tiny interfacial areas [2]. During this collision, however, severe plastic deformation caused by particle impact might dramatically affect the bonding process, causing shear instability. The natural oxide films on the particle and substrate are removed, and the surface is activated, resulting in the formation of a strong sticky area. The particle and substrate constituent parts are in intimate contact, as shown in TEM images, in the absence of inclusions such as the oxide at the adhering interface. As a result, surface activation is a critical element in particle adhesion mechanisms, and the CS technique's massive plastic deformation following impact significantly adds to this surface activation. Figure 1 depicts a method in which plastic deformation is triggered by the kinetic energy released by the collision of CS material particles. A material jet in the outer peripheral direction caused by thermal shear instability breaks and eliminates the particles and oxide coating on the substrate surface. A new chemically active surface is revealed, and the new surfaces are strongly connected to each another.

In recent publications, some mathematical models describing the plastic deformation have been introduced, including the thermal spraying when the heating particles deposit on the substrate. However, the main disadvantage of these models is the lack of technological parameters, which limits their application in the prediction of adhesion strength in coatings as a significant criterion for deposition evaluation. In

this context, a new modified mathematical model dealing with the sufficient prediction of adhesion strength must be introduced and validated. In the event of a disagreement, the empirical formula should be considered the most important recommendation.

In this paper, the digital method for the calculation of the predicted adhesion by the digital own program PROGX100 is described and the amorphous powder X-5 is proposed for the plasma spraying, while in the experimental part the relationships between enthalpy and air flow rate and between adhesion, power of plasma, and velocity of particles were specified, while some significant recommendations and the direction of future studies are presented.

II. METHODOLOGY

Significant plastic deformation was found at the interface edge due to the presence or absence of the remaining oxide film, and fracture and strong bonding were observed due to the ease with which the oxide film was removed. On the other hand, the quantity of plastic deformation in the area of the particle center was tiny hence the oxide film persisted even after the impact, generating a very weak bond. According to [3], in addition to substrate hardness, particle velocity and spray angle can influence deformation behavior and the ultimate state of the oxide film. The equation in [1] justifying the role of the critical velocity (V_{cr}) as the condition governing the feasibility of bonding was impacted by a rise in the local temperature beyond the melting point.

$$V_{cr} = 667 - 14 \times \rho_p + 0.08 \times T_m + 0.1 \times \sigma_u + 0.4 \times T_{pi} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_p is the density of the particle, T_m is the melting point of the particle, σ_u is the tensile strength of the particle, and T_{pi} is the initial temperature of the particle.

Due to adiabatic deformation, when particles hit at high speeds, the particle temperature quickly rises to the melting point. During the collision, much of the kinetic energy of the particle will be transformed into heat, encouraging plastic deformation. Softening is expected to produce particles that constitute the material jets. The Johnson-Cook (JC) model [4] is widely used in manufacturing to simulate high-speed deformation and can be used for high-velocity particle spraying [5, 6]:

$$\sigma = \left[A + B \times \varepsilon_p^n \right] \times \left[1 + C \times \ln \times \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}_p}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right] \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_{ref}}{T_m - T_{ref}} \right)^m \right] \quad (2)$$

where σ is the flow stress, A , B , C , m , and n are the material constants, ε_p^n is the plastic strain, $\dot{\varepsilon}_p$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ are the actual strain and the reference strain rates, respectively, and T , T_m , and T_{ref} are the actual, melting, and reference temperatures, respectively. The restriction of models (1) and (2) is the practical reference because, in the thermal spray, the activation energy and temperature of the contacting surface at the time of the impact must prevail. In this regard, the Kudinov V.V. model should be examined since it simplifies the computation of adhesion in terms of its prediction for designing the thermal process [7]:

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = [N_0 - N(t)] \times \nu \times \exp \left[- \frac{E_a}{k \times T_k} \right] \times \exp \left[\frac{S}{k} \right] \quad (3)$$

where E_a is the activation energy in this case, ν is the frequency of the atoms own oscillation, T_k is the contact's absolute temperature, N_0 is the number of atoms on the surface of the substrate or particle that make up the mutual physical contact, $N(t)$ denotes the number of atoms energized during the activation time t , S denotes the activation entropy in the chemical reaction zone, and k is the Boltzmann constant. Since the predominant metal has a BCC or FCC crystal structure, (3) will be transferred to the new type:

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = [N_0 - N(t)] \times \nu \times \exp \left[- \frac{E_a}{k \times T_k} \right] \quad (4)$$

The rate of the chemical interaction on the phase boundary is defined by the relative adhesion of the particle with the substrate:

$$\frac{\sigma(t)}{\sigma_{max}} = \frac{N(t)}{N_0} \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma(t)$ is the adhesion resulting for duration t , σ_{max} is the maximum adhesion obtaining for the entire cycle of the spraying. The influence of the particle velocity on the adhesion can be calculated according to [8]: $\sigma = V^2 \times \rho$, where V is the particle velocity and ρ is the density of the particle material. By the integration, (4) will be changed as follows:

$$\frac{\sigma(t)}{\sigma_{max}} = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{\nu \times t}{\exp \frac{E_a}{k \times T_k}} \right] \quad (6)$$

In (6), it is accepted that [7]:

$$E_a \approx k \times T_k \times (\ln t_0 + 30), \quad t_0 = \left(\frac{h}{2\alpha} \right)^2 \times \frac{1}{a_1} \quad (7)$$

For most of the materials, $\nu = 10^{13} \times c^{-1}$; $h = 0.1 \times d$, where d is the diameter of the particle and $E_a \approx 1.35 - 1.65$ eV.

Equation (7) describes the change in adhesion depending on the activated temperature during the collision of the particle with the substrate. On the other side, the quantity T_k can be calculated with respect to the known equation [7]:

$$T_k(t) = T_0 + T_k^0, \quad T_k^0 = \frac{(T_m - T_0) \times K\varepsilon}{K\varepsilon + F(\alpha)} \quad (8)$$

where h is the height of the solidified particle in the collision on the substrate, t_0 is the time during which the particle is solidified and the constant contact temperature T_k is activated, T_0 is the initial temperature of the substrate, and a_1 is the coefficient of the thermal conductivity of the particle. $\alpha = f(K\varepsilon, K_L)$ and α varies in 0 - 1 depending on $K\varepsilon$ and K_L .

$$K\varepsilon = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} \times \sqrt{\frac{a_2}{a_1}}; \quad K_L = \frac{c \times T_m}{1.77 \times L} \quad (9)$$

where $K\varepsilon$ is the criterion of the thermal activity of the particle in relation to the substrate, K_L is the criterion defining the latent heat of fusion of particle material, λ_1 and λ_2 are the coefficients of the thermal conductivity of the particle and the substrate, respectively, a_1 and a_2 are the coefficients of the thermal diffusivity of the particle and substrate, L is the latent heat of the fusion, c is the heat capacity of the particle, T_m is the

melting point of the particle material, $F(\alpha)$ is the integral of the probability, and $\alpha = f(K\varepsilon, K_L)$, the root of the function.

$$K\varepsilon + F(\alpha) = K_L \times \frac{e^{-\alpha^2}}{\alpha} \tag{10}$$

α can be defined by using the φ - α diagram [7], where α is the abscissa of the intersection between the two curves [7]:

$$\varphi = K\varepsilon + F(\alpha) = \varphi(K\varepsilon; \alpha) \tag{11}$$

$$\psi = K_L \times \frac{e^{-\alpha^2}}{\alpha} = \psi(K_L; \alpha) \tag{12}$$

The temperature during the solidification of the particle is defined by [7], with T_l being the temperature of the particle:

$$T_k = \frac{T_1 \times K\varepsilon}{K\varepsilon + F(\alpha)} \tag{13}$$

Given the properties of the particle and the substrate materials, the prediction of the change in adhesion in thermal spraying can be calculated using (6)-(9). The second method is to use (10) and (11) to find the root of the contacting temperature given $K\varepsilon$ and K_L . Since the adhesion depends not only on the heating effect, but also on the plastic deformation during the collision of the melting particle on the substrate, it is useful to consider a modified model for the prediction of changes in the adhesion:

$$\frac{\sigma(t)}{\sigma_{max}} = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{v \times t}{\exp \left[\frac{3 \times (\xi - \chi \times \frac{\sigma}{B})}{q \times \alpha \times T_k} \right]} \right] \tag{14}$$

where ξ is the strain in which the atomic bond is unstable, $\chi = \frac{\Sigma}{\sigma}$ is the coefficient of the local overload, Σ and σ are the local and average tensile strengths. In case of the collision of the melting particle on the substrate: $\chi = 1$; $q = \alpha_s/\alpha$, where α_s and α are the coefficients of thermal extension on the surface and in the volume of the stiff body.

The theoretical value of the predicted adhesion is calculated using (13) and (14) by the digital program PROG100, given the thermal-physical properties of the materials as follows: The substrate is mild carbon steel, and the particle material is Fe-based amorphous powder X-5 [9]. The chemical composition of powder X-5 is given in Table I.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF X-5 (%WT)

C	Cr	B	Mo	Ni	Mn	Si	Nb	V	W	Fe
0.73	5.0	0.25	4.20	-	1.25	0.84	0.54	1.20	-	remain

III. EXPERIMENTAL PART

The general scheme of the plasma spraying system can be seen in [10]. G1 is the source of power, G2 is the plasma torch, R1 and R2 are the rotameters, V1 and V2 are the valves, N1, N2, N3, N4, and N5 are the nipples, T1 is the thermometer, and T2 is the throttle. The power source is a direct current source with a steep volt-ampere slope, an idle voltage of 300V, and a voltage adjustment limit of 50 to 600V. The plasma arc is conducted according to a two-step scheme. Water serves as the coolant, with inlet and outlet via valve V1 and rotameter R1.

The thermometer T1 is used to measure the temperature and provide the data needed to calculate the enthalpy of the plasma jet. The accuracy degree of this rotameter is 2.5%. The water flow pressure at the inlet is 0.4-0.6MPa. The primary gas and secondary gas are fed through the V2 valve. The flow rate of gas is determined by the rotameter R2. The throttle T2 is used to smooth the current pulsation. The plasma spraying of powder X-5 experiment was carried out under the following conditions: Atmospheric plasma spraying was utilized (SG-100 TAFA-Praxair, USA). The primary gas was air, and the carrier gas was nitrogen. The chemical composition of Fe-based powder was analyzed by energy dispersive spectroscopy with the SM-6510LV. The experimental data are shown in Table II. To measure the velocity of spraying particles, the special high-speed camera Shimadzu HPV-1 was used [11]. It is useful to mention that the velocity of the particle stream was measured instead of that of separate particles. The measurement was conducted based on the principles of photogrammetry [12].

The average mass temperature of a plasma jet is evaluated indirectly by enthalpy. Because deposition is a continuous process of buildup from the particle stream, it is preferable to compare the average mass temperature to the temperature of the individual particle. The plasma stream containing the particles is a non-equilibrium system with temperature fluctuations over spatial and temporal scales [13]. The enthalpy is defined as the effective power of the plasma jet divided by the consumption of the primary gas [14]. The adhesion strength of the coatings on the steel substrate was determined by the Universal Compression Testing Machine (Model HT-2101A-300, Taiwan) according to the ASTM C633 standard. Experiments were conducted with a measurement error of about 2.5%. The empirical equation was derived using the least squares method. On one side, the theoretical calculation using the mathematical models derived with the assumption of separate particles during the collision on the substrate. But on the other side, the experiment was conducted in real conditions when the plasma stream included numerous particles with their own velocity and temperature. The significant value of the validation underlies this work, helping reduce the existing gap between the mathematical models and the experiments. The context stimulates the new modified model as it approaches the real condition and applicable empirical equations for the prediction of the adhesion of the coating.

A. Case Study 1: Plasma Spray of Amorphous Powder X-5

The influence of the plasma power and the flow rate of the air on the enthalpy will be investigated in this case. The interval of variation for the flow rate of the air is 0.5g/s in the range of 0.5–3.0g/s. Particle size ranges between 40 and 100µm. The spray distance is 120mm. Increased power of the plasma stream is expected when the flow rate of the air increases, resulting in the elevated enthalpy of plasma stream with particles (Figure 1) [9]. In Figure 1, x, ●, and ■ denote current of 120, 180, and 220A, respectively.

B. Case Study 2: Investigation on Adhesion

The material used was again X-5 powder, with particle size ranging in 40–100µm, with 9mm nozzle diameter. The current varied as: 120, 150, 180, 220, and 240A. The flow rate varied

between 0.46 and 3.17g/s. The results of the measurement of adhesion bond and velocity are shown in Figure 2.

C. Case Study 3: Relation between Particle Velocity and Air Flow Rate

This series of experiments occurs when the gas flow rate and the power of the plasma stream (via the current) are changing simultaneously. The data from the measurement of the particle velocity will be used for the evaluation of the adhesion of the coating. The experiment parameters were: X-5 material, size of particles: 40–100µm, nozzle diameter: 9mm (Figure 3).

Fig. 1. Relation between enthalpy, plasma power, and air flow rate.

Fig. 2. Relation between adhesion, plasma power, and particle velocity.

Fig. 3. Relation between particle velocity, plasma power, and air flow rate.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theoretical result calculation according to (13) and (14) gave the values shown in Table II, given: $q = 5$, $\xi = 0.2$, $\chi = 1$, $\alpha = 0.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{°K}^{-1}$, $T_0 = 300 \text{°K}$ (without the preheating) for X-5 powder.

TABLE II. CALCULATION OF RELATIVE ADHESION

No	T_f, K	$V_{particle}, \text{m/s}$	$d, \mu\text{m}$	$\sigma(t) / \sigma_{max}, \%$
1	960	5	70	100
2	960	10	70	100
3	960	15	70	100
4	960	20	70	100
5	960	25	70	100
6	960	30	70	100
7	960	35	70	100
8	960	40	70	100
9	960	45	70	100
10	960	50	70	100
11	960	75	70	100
12	960	100	70	100
13	960	125	70	100
14	960	150	70	100
15	960	175	70	100
16	960	200	70	100

From Table II, the relative adhesion is monovalent (100%) when the particle velocity is changing, which is inconsistent over the course of the experiment in Case Study 2. When the particle's velocity is low, its kinetic energy is also low, resulting in low plastic deformation and a significantly lower level of dislocation in the structure. This effect probably caused the reduction of the adhesion between the coating and the substrate. This could be taken into account by the coefficient in (14). In Case Study 1 (see Figure 1), the increase in the flow rate had a positive influence on the particle velocity and its temperature (indirectly via the enthalpy of particle flow). However, there is a shroud surrounding this increase, in which the enthalpy of the particle decreases due to the particle's short in-flight time. To create a high density and a good adhesive bond in the coating, one should increase both the velocity and the enthalpy of the particle. However, it is difficult to assess their partial contribution theoretically. As the velocity is increasing, there is a small difference in adhesion bonds for small velocities (less than 40m/s), but in the intensive case, the adhesion bond is approaching the value of 80MPa, which exceeds the maximum limit reported in recent publications [15]. When changing adhesion bonds, the maximum number of them (the pick) tends to shift toward higher velocity as plasma power increases. This means that the adhesion bond depends on both velocity and enthalpy (plasma power). Except for very low air flow rates, the tendency of the wear resistance to change with the flow rate of the air almost coincides with the change in the adhesion bond. This can be understood, due to the fact that the low velocity impacts not only the good coherence bond, but also the poor adhesion bond. Based on the experimental results in Figures 1-3, an empirical formula demonstrating the relationship between adhesion bond, velocity, enthalpy, and current was proposed in [16]:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{V^{x_1} \cdot \Delta H^{x_2} \cdot I^{x_3} \cdot x_4 + V^{x_5} \cdot \Delta H^{x_6} \cdot I^{x_7} \cdot x_8} \tag{15}$$

where: $x_1 = -1.454$, $x_2 = 0.926$, $x_3 = -0.398$, $x_4 = 0.003$, $x_5 = 0.836$, $x_6 = -1.182$, $x_7 = -0.9$, and $x_8 = 3598$. V denotes the velocity [m/s], ΔH [J/g] the enthalpy, and I the adhesion bond [MPa].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the analysis of some mathematical models related to the plastic deformation applicable in the case of plasma spray deposition revealed their limitations for the prediction of the adhesion strength of the coating due to the lack of specific technological parameters such as the power of plasma, the velocity, and the enthalpy of the plasma stream, including particles. The newly modified model takes into account some specific physical and mechanical properties of the material and approaches more the real conditions of the collision of the heating particle onto the substrate. However, the discrepancy with the experiment results requires a significant improvement. Meanwhile, the plasma spraying of Fe-based amorphous powder using ordinary air as a plasma generation gas once again proved the importance of the velocity and enthalpy of the particle stream for the strengthening of the adhesion since they positively encourage the plastic deformation according to the Johnson-Cook model. It is useful to note that as plasma power increases, the maximum values of adhesion shift to higher powers that can reach 80MPa when the power of plasma is approaching 80kW. To the best of the author's knowledge, the empirical formula (15) showing the relative correlation between qualitative parameters of the coating and spray process parameters, including the current, flow rate, plasma power, enthalpy of the torch, and velocity of the particles, had not been published before. This formula can be applied to the preliminary design of not only the plasma gun construction but also the technological process of the deposition. It is useful to continue the research in the future to cover the gap between the mathematical models and the empirical equations in the applicable prediction of the adhesion of the plasma-sprayed coatings. It is necessary to include the technological parameters of the spraying process into the model instead of the typical physical and mechanical properties of the given materials.

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Traffic Accident Traits and Driver Characteristics Implication on Road Accidents using Descriptive Analysis: A Cross Sectional Study in Sulaymaniyah, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

The current study focuses on disclosing the types and causes of traffic events in the Sulaymaniyah governorate and their association with driver implications. The study was conducted between September 2019 and August 2020 in cooperation with the General Directorate of Traffic. A total of 573 traffic accident forms were directly collected at the site of crash events. The result shows that the collision type of Road Traffic Accidents (RTAs) is the most frequent type, accounting for 64.6% of the total. Higher incidence of RTAs was recorded in pickup, taxi, and motorcycle automobiles than in private cars. The analysis showed that the driver's faults are responsible for 81.4% of RTAs followed by road issues, mechanical car faults, and environmental factors which were responsible for 15%, 2.4%, and 1.2%, respectively. The most important driver factors accountable for RTAs were overspeeding, low level of education, gender, young age, and alcohol intake. Driver age group 19-33 is highly associated with RTAs with the peak occurring at the age of 21 years.

Keywords-Road Traffic Accidents (RTAs); drivers; risk factors

I. INTRODUCTION

Sulaymaniyah is one of the biggest cities in Iraq and the occurrence of transportation accidents is frequent. Officially, the total number of wheeled motor vehicles, excluding motorbikes, registered at the General Directorate of Traffic in Sulaymaniyah Governorate is around 600000, thus approximately 1 in 10 people own a car [1]. Despite great efforts to reduce and control Road Traffic Accidents (RTAs), they are still considered a major issue, due to the increasing daily occurrences and their severity [2]. Following the African region, the Eastern Mediterranean Region was classified by the World Health Organization as having the highest number of fatalities due to road mishaps in the world. Among Eastern Mediterranean counties, Iraq is in the top two of the list of

RTA-related fatalities [3]. Alertly, the ministry of health in the Kurdistan Regional Government reported that RTAs are regarded as the most common cause of citizen deaths. Each year, traffic crashes cause approximately 850 deaths and 10,000 injuries [4]. Furthermore, the statistical data of Sulaymaniyah Medicolegal Institute showed that RTAs are the most common type and the leading cause of civilian deaths. The causative risks of RTAs can be broadly categorized as human, vehicle, and environmental factors [5, 6]. Age, sex, education, medical conditions, and driving speed are key human-related factors, while environmental causes involve defective and narrow roads, poor lighting, lack of familiarity, and bad weather [1, 7-10]. Authors in [7, 11] confirm that human errors comprise the major cause of RTAs. Driving speed is considered as a potential causative factor or RTAs

[12]. The environmental factors are the least participating risk of RTAs and are responsible for only about 5% of RTAs [1, 7, 9].

The aim of this study is to present an overview of RTAs in Sulaymaniyah governorate and analyze the role of drivers' contribution to the occurrence of RTAs.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Study Area

Sulaymaniyah was selected as the study area for several reasons: it is the biggest touristic city of Iraq and has a very large concentration of urban population. Geographically, the city is surrounded by four mountains and has a semi-arid climate with very hot dry summers and cool wet winters. The city was visited by more than 750,000 tourists in 2021 [13].

B. Data Collection

The case study was conducted in the Sulaymaniyah Governorate from September, 2019 to August, 2020 including the period of Covid-19 lockdown from March to July. A questionnaire was developed and administered in people involved in RTAs in the Governorate. The questionnaire form used included a diagram of the accident and information about the location, the date and time, weather conditions, car type and model, the sex and age of the people involved, the cause and the type of the accident, the type and license number of the drivers, the type of road, and the number of injuries and/or deaths. A copy of the accident report was stored in nearby traffic police stations. All forms were filled by trained traffic police personnel. The completed forms were transmitted to the department of forensic medicine for analysis. The questionnaire can be seen in the Appendix.

C. Data Analysis

During the pre-processing stage, wrong and missing values in any section of the filled form were dealt with. Records with inappropriate or incomplete values were removed from the dataset. In addition, during the analysis for the cause of accidents, uninsured cases or cases not categorized in the major causative factors were excluded. SPSS program (Ver.23.0) was used to analyze the data. Descriptive analyses were achieved calculating frequency, percentage, and cross tabulations.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RTAs are caused most probably by increased car ownership rate, lack of road discipline, and improper roadway features. Throughout the study period, 573 RTA cases were collected and analyzed. We can see from Figure 1 that the most common type of RTA is collision, which accounted for 64.6% of the total number of accidents and the least is road departure accounting only for 4.0%. The second most common type of RTAs is rollover, while run over (pedestrian impact) and fixed object collision have almost the same rates. Roughly, the findings of [4], which was conducted in the north Iraq (including Sulaymaniyah), are almost similar to our results except for fixed object collision that was not considered.

Fig. 1. The investigated types of RTAs.

TABLE I. VEHICLES TYPE INVOLVED IN RTAS

Variables	Frequency (%)
Number of vehicles	
One	225(39.5)
Two	348 (60.5)
Total	573 (100)
Vehicle type	
Private	474 (51.5)
Taxi	121 (13.1)
Pickup vehicle	129 (14.0)
Truck	79 (8.6)
Motorcycle	101 (11.0)
Government vehicle	18 (1.9)
Total	921 (100)

Table I presents the number and the type of vehicles participating in RTAs. In 474 (51.5%) of RTAs, private cars, the primary type of personal transportation, were involved, which is considered as a rationally normal percentage because the number of private cars is 12 times more than the other types of automobiles on Sulaymaniyah roads [14]. This is consistent with the findings in [7], which was conducted in the capital. Compared to other types of vehicles, accidents resulting from pickup cars are higher, account for approximately 14.0% of the total. On the other side, taxis were involved in 13.1% of the cases. This may be interpreted from the fact that taxis tend to be more time on the road than the other car types. According to police traffic data, the ratio of motorcycles in all sorts of vehicles is roughly 2% [14]. Surprisingly, the percentage of motorcycles participating in RTAs is quite bigger (11.0%) and can be regarded threatening, and may be related to the divers' age, since most of motorcyclists are under 19 years old [3]. Authors in [15, 16] pointed out that motorists have the primary contribution to road crashes during the recent years. The current investigation showed that 8.6% of RTAs happened in trucks and that governmental vehicles participated in the least accidents (1.9%), which can be explained by the fact that they spend less time on roads and take more responsibility during driving.

Figure 2 shows the percentage of accidents considering causative factors. The reasons for mishaps can be divided into drivers, roads, vehicles, and weather condition faults. The investigated data of this study depicted that the human factor is responsible for 81.3% of traffic events. This finding is very close to the ones of [4, 7, 17].

Fig. 2. Causes of RTAs.

The second most highly ranked causal factor for RTAs is vehicle faults. Absence of standard support and lack of periodic vehicle maintenance are the main possible factors for car faults that prompt unexpected malfunctions [4, 18]. Furthermore, it is revealed that weather and road mishaps account for 2.4% and 1.2% of RTAs, respectively, indicating that adequate engineering and proper roadway structure and control of roads by traffic police play a positive role in reducing the number of RTAs, although it has been reported that road status is a basic risk factor of accidents [18, 19]. Additionally, minimal causative error is caused by environmental effects (1.2%) expressing that seasonal changes of Sulaymaniyah weather did not have a great impact on RTAs in general. The present study confirmed similar findings that the drivers have the largest contribution to the occurrence of accidents [11]. Therefore, the most significant attributing risk factors related to driver errors were further investigated.

TABLE II. CONTRIBUTING RISK FACTORS RELATED TO DRIVERS

Variable	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Male	880 (95.6)
Female	41 (4.4)
Education status	
Illiterate	384 (41.7)
Basic school	362 (39.3)
Preparatory school	100 (10.8)
University or higher	76 (8.2)
Speed	
Allowed speed	265 (28.8)
High speed	656 (71.2)
Alcohol drinking	
Yes	277 (30.1)
No	644 (69.9)
Driving license	
Yes	749 (81.3)
No	172 (18.7)
Driving experiences (years)	
1 to 5	386 (41.9)
6 to 10	346 (37.5)
11 to 15	98 (10.6)
16 and more	90 (9.8)

The results in Table II show that some contributing risk factors of RTAs, such as sex, level of education, speed, driving under the effect of alcohol, driving experience, and owing driving license.

The percentage of female drivers in Sulaymaniyah Governate in 2020 is 14.7% according to traffic police data registration. Accordingly, the ratio of male to female drivers is nearly 6 to 1. However, Table II shows that the percentage of male drivers participating in the investigated accidents is 95.6% with only 4.4% being female. This high percentage is in line with the findings in [20, 21]. The level of education has an important effect on RTAs as can be seen in Table II, with the illiterate, or basic educated drivers taking the lion's share with the number of accidents declining with the increasing level of education. Safety education for drivers regarding safe driving and proper vehicle maintenance should start at the student age [22, 23]

The speed of a car plays an imperative role in the occurrence of all types of RTAs [24]. The present study noted that the speed of 656 out of 921 vehicles at the time of mishaps exceeded the upper limited speed at the site of the event. Accordingly, our recorded data validated the findings of [25], where over speeding was considered as the main risk factor of RTAs. Further, it is scientifically proved that driving under the effect of drugs, particularly alcohol, is highly dangerous, especially for young drivers [25, 26]. In Iraq, the alcohol value allowed for driving is below 60gm/dl. This study found out that 30.1% of the tested drivers were under the effect of alcohol.

Driving experience was categorized in four groups as shown in Table II. The highest rate of RTAs (41.9%) was recorded for drivers with less than 5 years of driving experience, suggesting that the young drivers are usually at a higher risk. Meanwhile, the smallest number of accidents (9.8%) happened to drivers with more than 15 years of experience. Similar findings were reported in [22]. Moreover, 18.7% of drivers did not have a driving license. Authors in [23] reported that a high proportion of RTAs occurred to unlicensed drivers.

Fig. 3. Age distribution of drivers in RTAs.

In terms of age, the driver age distribution in Figure 3 shows that the bulk majority of the age of drivers participating to RTAs ranges between 19 and 33 years, with the peak being 21. Obviously, the conclusion that younger drivers are at higher risk of mishaps is evident. Young drivers have less experience, are more active, and tend more to make more car trips for educational, occupational, and social purposes. This finding is compatible with [16, 20], and with what is globally recognized [27]. Meanwhile, only a small portion of RTAs occurred in drivers under the age of 18, which is in accordance with what is

internationally found [3]. This result can be attributed to the fact that the drivers within this age group are not permitted to hold a driver’s license according to Iraqi rules stating that the minimum age for getting a driver’s license is 18. Notably, the number of RTAs obviously declines with age, mainly due to the limited number of trips that individuals in this age group make [28].

Fig. 4. Frequency plots of RTAs per (a) time (24h) and (b) day.

The trend timeline in Figure 4(a) displays a peak of RTAs in midnight. The number decreases in early morning hours to its least record and after that increases to late afternoon with a rapid drop of events during the evening. Finally the number of RTAs rises steeply before levelling off at midnight. Two peak time occurrences of maximum accidents were recognized at 16 and 21 hours with the only causative probability being that most people going back to home after work at around 16:00 and that as Sulaymaniyah is a big city with many tourists and a

good night weather, making many trips on the road during night-time is accustomed. Previous conducted studies analyzed that the larger proportion of RTAs happened during daytime [4, 7]. The contrary present study findings may be attributed to the night activities in Sulaymaniyah. On the other hand, it is clearly visible from time plot that the minimum occurrence of RTAs was recorded at the evening as this is logically the resting time of daily human activity. Figure 4(b) provides an overview of the total number of RTAs per days of the week. We can see that the frequency of RTAs in working days is nearly the same with weekend days showing a bit higher percentage. The smallest number of RTAs occurred on Mondays. This finding is in contradiction with [29, 30] in which most RTAs occurred on Thursdays, because in Sulaymaniyah region wedding tradition and funny trips are not confined in a specific weekday.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, focus was given on the causes and attributing risk factors in various types of RTAs. During the study period car collision was the most common type of accident and road departure the least. Consistent with previous research, our data confirm that driver-related factors were the main cause of RTAs. Driver errors are the most common cause of RTAs, followed by defects in vehicles, poor road infrastructure, and bad weather. In particular, the focal point was to analyze the factors related to human causes of RTAs. The most RTAs occurred among illiterate drivers. Accidents were nineteen times more likely in males than in females. Moreover, less driving experience, driving under the effect of alcohol, and overspeeding are considered as the most crucial risk factors. RTAs are skewed toward involving people in younger age groups. Finally, surprisingly, the majority of crush accidents were recorded during Fridays and night periods. As a proposal, RTAs can be greatly reduced by proper education, raising awareness, and training of safety standards.

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APPENDIX

Road Traffic Accident Survey Questionnaire

This form will be fill by an allowed employee in departmental traffic bureau
Date:

Form No:

Part one: Accident Information

Information about the accident

Time: Day: Date: Location:

Type of accident a. Collision b. Roll over c. Road departure d. Run over (pedestrian) e. Run over (fixed object)

Cause of Accident a. Human b. Road c. Vehicle d. Weather

Number of vehicles involved in the accident:

Amount of speed during the accident a. Allowed speed b. High speed

The weather during the accident: a. Normal b. Rain c. Snowing d. Frizzing road e. Foggy

Number of people involved:

Number of casualties a. Injuries b. Deaths c. Safe

Reason for being safe: a. Seat belt b. Car seat c. Motor protective equipment

Part Two: Driver Information

Gender: Male Female Year of Birth:

Which one of the following is your level of education:

a. Illiterate b. Basic school c. Preparatory school d. Bachelor

* Please write down your degree (certificate) in education, if none of the above is applicable.....

Marital status: a. Single b. Married d. Other
 Do you have a job? Yes No
 If your answer is Yes: a. Public sector b. Private sector
 Car type: Model year of the car:
 Did the driver have a driving license : Yes No
 If your answer is Yes, please answer the next two questions.
 Years of driving experience: Class of the driving license:
 Was the driver under the influence of alcohol during the time of the accident? Yes No
 Was alcohol test done on the driver? Yes No
 Is the driver registered in any insurance company Yes No
 Is the car registered in any insurance company Yes No

If there were other cars involved, the same information was filled and for the other drivers.

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Multi-level Association Rule Mining for the Discovery of Strong Underrepresented Patterns

The Case Study of Small Dairy Farms in Tanzania

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ABSTRACT

Increasing the milk production of small dairy producers is necessary to cover the increase in milk demand in Tanzania. Currently, the population of people in both Tanzania and the world has increased and is predicted to increase more in the year 2050. The use of multilevel association rule mining methods to mine strong patterns among smallholder dairy farmers could help in identifying the best dairy farming practices and increase their milk production by adopting them. This study employed multi-level association rule mining to discover strong rules in three clusters, resulting in three levels of rules in each cluster. These three clusters were high, medium, and low milk producers. Rules were obtained for feeding practices, milk production, and breeding and health practices. These rules represent strong patterns among smallholder dairy farmers that could help them improve their dairy farming practices and have a gradual increase in milk production, from low to medium and from medium to higher milk production. Smallholder dairy producers would be provided with recommendations on their dairy farming practices, using rules based on the cluster to which they belong that could help them achieve higher milk production.

Keywords-association rules mining; dairy farming; smallholder dairy producers; milk yield

I. INTRODUCTION

Association rules are if-then statements that show the probability of relationships between data items or variables within large datasets [1, 2]. Association rule mining is used to discover interesting patterns between item sets in large databases [3-5]. The patterns discovered from association rule mining can be represented as rules, trees, or clusters which a user can interpret into knowledge [3]. Pattern matching is essential to identify relationships in datasets, and association rule extraction is among the most common techniques used in text mining [6]. Association rule mining provides association rules that exceed the user-specified minimum support and the minimum confidence level threshold [7].

A minimum of 145 days is required for small dairy farmers to learn farming strategies from other farmers in order to increase milk production [8]. This is a lot of time for a farmer who also needs to perform other activities. To minimize learning time, recommendations can be derived for small farmers using association rule mining methods. Association rule mining can mine data at single and multiple levels of abstraction depending on the approach used [9]. As sparse data

make it difficult to identify strong rules in low or original abstract layers, there is a need to mine strong rules from multiple abstract layers. Mining association rules in multiple abstract layers and formulate multilevel association rules is called multilevel association rule mining [10]. Recommendation systems use collaborative, content-based, and demographic filtering methods to search and filter large volumes of data and suggest items to users [11, 12]. The Syragri recommender system was created to provide recommendations to farmers on their practices. In [13], a hybrid approach was used for recommendation modeling to provide new items not rated by a user or rated by some users. As Indian farmers face various problems, such as insufficient harvesting and transportation methods, the government seeks ways to help them. The Collaborative Recommendation System for Agriculture Sector (CRSAS) was developed using English, Hindi, and Marathi to provide recommendations to farmers on various available agricultural programs and increase their knowledge of available government schemes [14]. Trustworthy recommendation systems are important and improve the ability of users to use them due to factors such as accuracy and good explanations [15].

The Tanzanian population was 34,443,603 in 2002, 44,928,923 in 2012, and was projected to increase to 59,441,988 in 2021 [16]. Currently, Tanzania's population increased to 61,741,120 people in 2022 [17], while the population worldwide is expected to increase to 8.9 billion people in 2050 from 7.9 billion in 2014 [18]. As the population and the per capita income increase, the demand for protein nutrients increases [19]. Ruminants, including cows, can be fed human-inedible plants such as alfalfa, pasture, and hay and produce high-quality protein products such as milk and meat [18]. These high-quality protein nutrient products would help meet the demands of an increasing population of people. Therefore, milk production as a protein source needs to be increased to meet the demands of the population. Small dairy farmers produce food for substantial populations of the world with small land holdings of less than 2 hectares [20]. Smallholder dairy farmers use low production costs, such as low-cost feeds and low technology, to produce milk which is cost-advantageous and helps solve the problem of food insecurity by providing milk proteins [21]. The challenges that small farmers face include poverty, food insecurity, lack of knowledge, lack of technical know-how, and poor support service [20, 21].

In [22], the K-Means and Self-Organizing Map (SOM) models were used to group small Tanzanian dairy farmers into six clusters from PEARL data. Farmer groups are a good tool to facilitate the development of small dairy farmers from subsistence to commercialization [22]. Multilevel association rule mining through the Apriori algorithm can be used to identify strong rules among various farmer groups that will ease the provision of recommendations to particular groups. Grouping farmers into appropriate farm groups, based on their characteristics, could simplify the use of interventions and strategies to improve milk production [22]. Recommendation systems have been currently used to develop models using big data to facilitate decision-making activities, including increasing farm yields [13]. Farm groups can be analyzed in more detail and hence, recommendations can be provided on how to increase milk yield. These recommendations would guide farmers to improve from low to medium and then achieve high milk production. Given these advancements, this study presents a multilevel association rule analysis as a data mining method to discover important underrepresented patterns in small dairy producer systems. Tanzania's dairy farmers were used as a case study but this method can be replicated in any country with similar characteristics.

II. METHODOLOGY

The extraction of rules in the dataset was performed using a multilevel association rule mining method with multiple levels of abstraction [9]. The application of multilevel mining of rules is increasing, as it is necessary to acquire precise information in various fields [23]. Many strong association rules are not obtained at a single level of abstraction [24]. Multi-level association rule mining requires viewing rules among dairy farmers at different multiple levels of abstraction. This study adopted a pre-clustered dataset with 6 dairy production clusters [22]. The 6 clusters were evaluated based on their dairy production performance using traits such as vaccination

frequency and milk production [25]. This study used 3 clusters to represent high, medium, and low dairy producers. High dairy producers were identified as cluster 1 (1180 households), medium dairy producers were identified as cluster 2 (516 households), and low dairy producers were identified as cluster 3 (295 households). In [25], cluster 1 had the best performance of 53%, while clusters 2 and 3 had 43% and 33% performance in product traits, respectively. The dataset consisted of 38 production traits that were represented with categorical data values. Table I shows the production traits, data types, and range of values of this dataset.

This study used the Apriori algorithm used to mine the association rules. This algorithm generates sets of frequent item sets in a database in iterations using a bottom-up approach by adding one item at a time [3]. The evaluation metrics used were the support, confidence, and lift values. Support and confidence are the two basic metrics in identifying association rules [2-4] while this study aimed to have a lift value greater than 1 to indicate stronger rules [7-26]. Support is defined as the proportion of records that contain $X \cup Y$ to the overall records in the database, whereas confidence is defined as the proportion of the number of transactions that contain $X \cup Y$ to the overall records that contain X [4]. Lift can be interpreted as the deviation of the support of the whole rule from the support expected under independence, given the support of both sides of the rule [7], while X and Y are antecedents and consequents of the extracted association rule, respectively.

Rule: $X \Rightarrow Y$

$$\text{support}(XY) = \frac{\text{support sum of } XY}{\text{Overall records in the database}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{confidence} \left(\frac{X}{Y} \right) = \frac{\text{support}(XY)}{\text{support}(X)} \quad (2) [4]$$

$$\text{lift}(X \Rightarrow Y) = \frac{\text{support}(X \cup Y)}{(\text{support}(X) \text{ support}(Y))} \quad (3) [7]$$

Filtering of the rules was performed in various groups to obtain the important rules in each category with minimum support and minimum confidence for each cluster. Minimum support was selected based on the frequency of items in the various groups to extract the association rules [10]. Three levels of rules were obtained in each cluster. The dominating production traits were removed after levels 1 and 2 to obtain more rules with unique production traits in all clusters. Minimum support and confidence were also reduced at levels 2 and level 3 of all clusters to obtain unique rules.

III. RESULTS

Multilevel association analysis was performed for the 3 clusters. For each cluster, level 1 included rules on feeding and yield practices, level 2 included rules on health and breeding practices, and level 3 consisted of rules on breeding and yield practices.

A. Cluster 1: High Milk Producers

1) Level 1

Level 1 included 81 rules from the high milk-producing cluster, with minimum support of 0.6 and minimum confidence of 0.95, and lift range between 1.003 and 1.29. Strong rules

with lift values of 1.29, high confidence levels above 99%, and support range of 61-73% were found. The use of only stall-feeding systems in the rainy and dry seasons and bull breeding for the last calving had a high lift value of 1.29 with a support of 67%. Farmers owned 1 to 3 cows, they had frequent visits from 1 to 9 extension officers per year, no land for fodder production, no employees, and no training in dairy care at a

high lift value of 1.29 with support ranging from 61% to 69%. Other traits included farmers preferring bull breeding, 1 to 7 years of attending school, no fodder purchases, and no household members participating in the farmer groups, so the practice of farm activities usually depends on the basic knowledge of dairy farming.

TABLE I. PRODUCTION FEATURES USED IN MULTILEVEL ASSOCIATION RULE MINING

S/N	Production features	Data type	Range of values
1	Feeding system used during rainy season	Nominal	Mainly grazing, mainly stall, only ggazing, only stall feeding
2	Feeding system used during the dry	Nominal	Mainly grazing, mainly stall, only ggazing, only stall feeding
3	Reasons for choosing management (feeding) system	Nominal	Prevents diseases, cheap, extension officer advice, geographic conditions, insufficient land, large tracts of land, other reasons
4	Months which crop residue used for feeding	Discrete	1-12
5	Months which concentrates are used for feeding	Discrete	1-12
6	Months which fodder/feeds were purchased	Discrete	1-12
7	Watering frequency of the cattle	Discrete	1-4
8	Distance to water source (kn)	Interval	Less than 1, 1-3, 3-5, 6-10
9	Area under fodder production (acres)	Interval	Less than 0.5, 0.5-1, 1.1-2.5, 3.5-5, 5.5-10
10	Breed rank 1	Nominal	Ayrshire, cross, don't know, Friesian, Holstein, Jersey
11	Breed rank 2	Nominal	Ayrshire, cross, don't know, Friesian, Guernsey, Holstein, Jersey, other
12	Breed rank 3	Nominal	Ayrshire, cross, don't know, Friesian, Guernsey, Holstein, Jersey
13	Traits rank 1	Nominal	Milk quantity traits, body weight traits, calving traits, carcass traits, dairy type traits, disease traits, growth rate traits, milk feed traits, milk quality traits, reproductive traits, udder traits, other traits
14	Traits rank 2	Nominal	Milk quantity traits, body weight traits, calving traits, carcass traits, dairy type traits, disease traits, growth rate traits, milk feed traits, milk quality traits, reproductive traits, udder traits, other traits
15	Traits rank 3	Nominal	Milk quantity traits, body weight traits, calving traits, carcass traits, dairy type traits, disease traits, growth rate traits, milk feed traits, milk quality traits, reproductive traits, udder traits, other traits
16	Breeding method used during last calving	Boolean	Bull or artificial insemination
17	Preferred breeding method	Boolean	Bull or artificial insemination
18	Distance to breeding service provider	Interval	Less than 1, 1-5, 6-15, 16-30, above 30
19	Frequency of deworming cattle	Discrete	0-4
20	Self-deworming service	Boolean	Yes or No
21	Frequency of spraying cattle for pest control	Discrete	0-7
22	Frequency of vaccinating the cows	Discrete	0-4
23	Frequency of visit by extension officer	Interval	None, 1-9, 10-29, 30-49, 50 and above
24	Training	Nominal	No training, one day training, one week training, two weeks training, more than one month training
25	Experience in dairy farming	Discrete	3, 8, 13, 18, 23, 28, 35, 45, 50
26	Years of schooling of smallholder farmers	Interval	0, 1-7, 8-11, 12-16, above 16
27	Number of employees	Discrete	0-3
28	Household member in a farmer group	Nominal	Head household, son, spouse, daughter, other
29	Total land holding	Nominal	Average, below average, large
30	Total number of cattle	Interval	1-3, 4-6, 7-10, 11-16, 17-20, above 20
31	Number of livestock	Interval	1-20, 21-40, 41-60, 61-80, 81-100, hundreds, thousands
32	Preferred buyers	Nominal	Dairy chilling plants, hotels, individual consumers, milk collection center, other institutions, private milk traders
33	Distance to milk buyers	Interval	1-10, 11-20, above 20
34	Distance to market	Interval	Less than 1, 1-5, 6-10
35	Milk reserves for home consumption	Nominal	Above average, average, low
36	Liters of milk sold	Nominal	Above average, average, below average
37	Peak milk production of best cow	Nominal	Above average, average, below average
38	Number of milking cows	Interval	1-3, 4-8, 9-15

2) Level 2

At this level, the minimum support was adjusted to 0.22, the minimum confidence to 0.7, and the lift range was 1.02 to 1.43 for the 86 rules obtained. At lift values of 1.3, farmers dewormed their cattle 3 times a year, their distances to the market and the breeding provider were 1 to 5 kilometers, they sprayed their cattle 6 times a year, and did not self-deworm on

their cattle. At lift values greater than 1.2, the cattle vaccination frequency was twice a year, the liters of milk sold by farmers were average, farmers used concentrate for 3 months, and their owned total land was average. At 1.1 lift, the number of livestock was not identified, the preferred buyers were individual consumers, the watering frequency was twice a day, and the milk production of the best cow was average.

3) Level 3

Level 3 had 84 rules, where the minimum support was 0.164, the minimum confidence level was 0.67, and lift range was between 1.04 and 3.57. Strong rules were aligned from 80% to 100% confidence level with lift values greater than 1.9 and low support from 16.4%. These rules included preferred breed rank types and milk quantity traits in trait rank 1, while farmers owned 4 to 6 cattle and had 8 years of experience in dairy farming. The preferred breed rank types were identified at a lift of 3.5, where breed rank 1 was Friesian, breed rank 2 was Ayrshire, and breed rank 3 was Jersey. Some farmers had no preferred breed types in all 3 breed ranks but had eight years of experience in dairy farming at a lift of 2.0. Farmers preferred milk quality traits in trait rank 2, had average liters of milk sold, and animals were fed crop residue for 6 months with a lift value of 2.0. Some farmers also had 13 years of dairy farming experience and chose the feeding system for disease prevention.

B. Cluster 2: Medium Milk Producers

1) Level 1

In level 1, 0.4 minimum support and 0.86 minimum confidence level were used to obtain 100 rules from medium milk producers at a lift range between 1.07 and 1.39. Strong rules were located in two parts. The rules of the first part had a confidence level of 100%, 0.4-0.41 support, and 1.39 lift range. The preferred breeding method was artificial insemination at a confidence level of 100%, and farmers owned 1 to 3 milking cows. The rules of the second part had support and confidence levels between 0.4-0.42 and 0.87-0.91, respectively, with a lift range of 1.08 to 1.34. Farmers used artificial insemination in the last calving and were not members of farm groups at a lift value of 1.39. At lift values more than 1.3, the preferred buyers were individual consumers, the distance from the water source was less than 1km, and the watering frequency for the cattle was once per day. Farmers had average peak milk production for their best cows and the distance to the breeding service provider was 1-5km at a lift value of 1.1. At a 0.46 support, farmers received 1-9 visits from extension officers.

2) Level 2

The production traits that dominated level 1 were reduced in level 2. The minimum support used was 0.2, the minimum confidence level was 0.6, and 83 rules were obtained for a lift range between 1.02 and 3.15. Strong rules were determined for support between 0.22 and 0.35 and confidence levels from 0.85 to 1.0. Support was low but the confidence and the lift of the rules were high. Gaps in the 3 breed ranks were observed in both antecedents and consequents with a high support of 0.3 and lift of 3.0. However, at 0.25 support and lift above 3.0, the preferred breed in breed rank 1 was Friesian, breed rank 2 was Ayrshire, and breed rank 3 was Jersey. Farmers using Ayrshire and Friesian breeds performed deworming 3 times a year at a high lift above 2.0. Farmers did not purchase fodder and had low residue milk with a high lift of 1.5. Farmers with milk quantity traits in trait rank 1 performed deworming 3 times per year with a high lift above 2.0. Milk quality traits preferred in traits rank 1 and Friesian breed were observed with a high lift of 2.0.

3) Level 3

The production traits that dominated level 2 were reduced in level 3. A minimum support of 0.125 and a minimum confidence level of 0.6 were used in the mining process, the lift range obtained was between 1.01 and 2.66, and 70 rules were obtained for medium milk producers at this level. In these rules, most farmers preferred milk quality, milk quantity, and udder traits. Farmers who preferred milk quality traits in rank 2 had 1 to 20 cattle with a lift value of 2.0. In rank 1, farmers preferred milk quantity and had low residue milk for home consumption at a lift value of 2.0. Farmers did not have land for feed production, did not purchase feed, preferred udder traits in rank 3, and household members had attended school for 1-7 years at a lift value of 2.0. The preferred feature in rank 1 was the dairy type with a high lift of 2.5. At 1.5 lift, farmers purchased concentrates throughout the year and had a spraying frequency 2 per year. Other production traits included the use of crop residues for 4 months, farmers owned area for feeding production from 0.5 to 1 acres, and household members who had attended school for 8-11 years.

C. Cluster 3: Low Milk Producers

1) Level 1

At this level, the minimum support was 0.73, the minimum confidence level was 0.9, the lift range was between 1.004 and 1.14, and 76 rules were established. Farmers preferred and used the bull breeding method in the last calving and had no employees at a high support of 0.77 and lift above 1.1. Farmers did not have training in dairy farming at 0.75 support, did not carry out self-deworming at 0.75 support and above 1.1 lift, and did not have members in farmer groups at 0.74 support. Farmers used only stall feeding in both rainy and dry seasons, owned 1 to 3 milking cows, and had frequent visits, between 1 to 9, from extension officers at 0.74 support and 1.05 lift.

2) Level 2

The production traits that dominated level 1 were reduced in level 2. The minimum support was 0.34, the minimum confidence level was 0.72, the lift range was between 1.01 and 2.07, and 57 rules were obtained. Strong rules with a lift value of 2.07 were located at a confidence level of 1.0 and a support range from 0.36 to 0.39. No preferred breed type was identified at 2.0 lift and 0.37 support. The total land owned by farmers was below average and the distance to the market was 1-5km with 1.1 lift and 0.35 support. The vaccination frequency was twice a year and the watering frequency was once a day at 1.1 lift and 0.35 support. There was no distance to the buyer at 1.1 lift and 0.39 support. The liters of milk sold by the farmers were average and the household members had attended school for 1 to 7 years.

3) Level 3

The dominating production traits at level 2 were reduced in level 3. The used minimum support was 0.27, the minimum confidence level was 0.64, the lift range was between 1.03-1.85, and 51 rules were extracted. Farmers chose their feeding system due to insufficient land at 1.8 lift and preferred the trait of milk quality at 1.7 lift. Farmers performed spraying of cattle twice per year at 1.6 lift and deworming 3 times a year at 1.4

lift. At 1.2 lift, farmers used concentrates for 3 months, had low residue milk, their distance to the breeding service provider was 1-5km, and did not purchase fodders. Unique production traits included individual consumers as buyers and average milk production of the best cow.

Table II shows a summary of all the rules obtained in multilevel association rule mining from small dairy farmers in Tanzania.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF RULES OBTAINED IN MULTILEVEL ASSOCIATION RULE MINING

Clusters	Levels	Number of rules	Minimum support	Minimum confidence level	Lift range
High producers (cluster 1)	Level 1	81	0.6	0.95	1.003 to 1.29
	Level 2	86	0.22	0.7	1.02 to 1.43
	Level 3	84	0.164	0.67	1.04 to 3.57
Medium producers (cluster 2)	Level 1	100	0.4	0.86	1.07 to 1.39
	Level 2	83	0.2	0.6	1.02 to 3.15
	Level 3	70	0.125	0.6	1.01 to 2.66
Low producers (cluster 3)	Level 1	76	0.73	0.9	1.004 to 1.14
	Level 2	57	0.34	0.72	1.01 to 2.07
	Level 3	51	0.27	0.64	1.03 to 1.85

IV. DISCUSSION

Most milk producers in all clusters practice only stall-feeding systems in both dry and rainy seasons. Feeding adequate meals to cattle with the required nutrients could help increase milk production. Milk production drops during the dry season for most farmers due to inappropriate methods to cope with it [21]. Apart from stall feeding, small dairy farmers provide crop residues and concentrates to their cattle. High milk producers provided crop residues to their cattle 6 months a year, medium milk producers provided crop residues for 4 months, while crop residues were not identified in small producers. The adoption of methods to produce and store crop residues is important and should be encouraged, including the treatment of crop residues for use during the dry season [21]. Farmers in high and low milk-producing clusters use concentrates for 3 months per year, but the medium milk-producing cluster has farmers who use concentrates for 3 to 12 months a year. Most farmers do not have or possess less than 1Km² of land for fodder production, which is insufficient for their cattle. In addition, farmers do not purchase fodder for their cattle. The results on the feeding systems highlight a major challenge towards higher productivity, as the practices are not in agreement with the available studies [21, 27-28]. With a zero-grazing set-up, a minimum of 1 acre of Napier grass per cow was emphasized to be adopted by small farmers as the primary source of fodder in Kenya [27]. Planting Napier grass on 1 acre with good management can help small farmers to feed 2 dairy cows during a year [28]. Effective feed production technologies have not been adopted due to cost, insufficient land, and high labor demands [21]. High milk producers have a higher watering frequency than the others, as they provide water at least twice a day.

Most farmers in high- and medium-producing clusters have 3 preferred breeds: Friesian, Ayrshire, and Jersey. Low milk producers did not have preferred breed types, raising questions about their dairy orientation and breeding selections [29]. The use of improved crossbreeding types is preferred to increase milk production compared to pure exotic breeds that have low production due to the production environments that are highly resource deprived. Improved breeds that are well suited for the environment of Tanzania, such as Friesian, Ayrshire, and

Jersey, have been proven to be among the top 10 effective in dairy production [29]. Farmers in high and low clusters preferred the use of bull breeding while farmers in the medium cluster preferred artificial insemination, which is an efficient and effective tool to increase milk production by breeding many cows with semen from good breeds in different geographic locations. Studies have indicated that artificial insemination is more effective than bull breeding because, in the former case, semen is better examined for diseases, quality, and fertility [30]. These results still yield uncovered service gaps for the farmers as they still rely on poorly performing breeding methods.

Most high milk-producing farmers prefer milk quantity, milk quality, and udder traits. Farmers in the medium-producing cluster prefer milk quality, milk quantity, dairy type, and udder traits. Farmers in the low-producing cluster prefer milk quantity and quality. In Tanzania, small dairy farmers prefer mostly cows with high milk production genetics but at an affordable price [31]. Farmers choose the best traits to increase milk production. This can be seen in high and medium producers who are much more aware of the good traits of their cattle than low producers.

Farmers in high and low milk production clusters carried out deworming of their cattle 3 times a year, but farmers in the medium cluster carried out deworming 3 to 4 times a year. Farmers in the high milk-production cluster spray their cattle 6 times a year, medium producers spray their cattle twice a year, and low-milk producers do not spray their cattle. The vaccination frequency in all clusters is twice a year. Most farmers in all clusters have 1 to 9 extension visits.

Insufficient and inadequate inputs such as feed, breed, health, and services such as lack of extension visits lead to the inability to control cattle diseases, poor livestock farming, and lack of knowledge and information [32]. Most of the farmers in all clusters did not perform cattle self-deworming, had not attended training, had no employees, and were not members of farmer groups. Farmers in the high cluster have more experience in dairy farming, from 8 to 13 years, than farmers in the medium and low clusters.

In terms of education level, farmers in high and low clusters attended school for 1 to 7 years, while farmers in the medium cluster attended school for 8 to 11 years. This highlights the gap between experienced farmers with low education levels against those who have significantly attained formal education. Although there were no significant differences in formal education between high and low producers, more research is needed to determine whether formal education can promote the adoption of improved technologies, such as the use of improved breeding methods [30]. The trained farmers were shown to have higher milk production than the others in Temeke [33]. Knowledge of how to conduct dairy farming practices is important to achieve high milk production. Farmers' knowledge in terms of receiving frequent extension visits has shown concern in the health of their animals; high milk producers were more experienced than the others, and hence had more knowledge in breeding practices.

Farmers in all clusters owned 1 to 3 milking cows with their best average production quantity of milk. The best cows from most small dairy farmers with high milk production in Tanzania produced 14.45 ± 5.12 L milk per day, the best cows from most small farmers with medium milk production small farmers produced 11.08 ± 4.29 L milk per day, and the best cows from low milk producers produced 9.15 ± 3.25 L milk per day. The cattle keepers in Tanzania sell small amounts of milk to consumers and have not met the demand for milk in a country where the population, income, and urbanization continue to increase [32]. The liters of milk sold by most farmers are average in all clusters. The preferred buyers in all clusters are individual consumers at distance ranging between 1 and 5 km. An increase in the quantity and quality of milk production can be achieved by an efficient milk collection system and the production of dairy products that could meet customer needs [34]. More farmers in the market will trigger more milk production since they will be confident in selling their products. Milk reserves for home consumption were low for the high and low clusters whereas the medium had a mix of farmers with average milk reserves.

The data mining process extracts useful information from large datasets that can uncover hidden patterns and is also called Knowledge Discovery or Knowledge Extraction [35]. Association rule mining enabled the mining of association rules from a dataset that identified underrepresented patterns among small farmers. This rule-based engine gives farmers a platform to learn various farming techniques from each other in their respective farm groups while extension officers can provide timely assistance [25]. Therefore, recommendations can be provided to the farmers according to their various practices.

V. CONCLUSION

It is necessary to provide farmers with knowledge about the production traits that can help them achieve higher milk production. This knowledge will not only increase production, but can also contribute to market products, employ personnel, and reduce poverty and food insecurity. Training small dairy farmers is also important with the available technology, such as feed technology, in a way that is easily accessible. The use of a rule-based engine to assign farmers to farm clusters enables

them to connect with the extension officers and enhance the information sharing and engagement. In a rule-based engine platform, farmers can receive recommendations based on the cluster to which they belong, as they are already available. A future study should investigate the use of these rules to provide recommendations to farmers based on these production features.

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A Comparative Study of the Dam Stability at Various Stages using Numerical Modeling and in Situ Measurements

The Case Study of the Taksebt Dam, Tizi Ouzou, Algeria

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ABSTRACT

Earth dams remain the most used means of water mobilization in Algeria, due to their lower cost compared to concrete gravity dams and their capacity to resist better to seismic excitations. A study of the hydraulic structure was carried out in this paper, according to simple rules and empirical approaches. During the last decade, several high earth dams have suffered significant failures of the upstream or downstream slopes at the end of construction, after the initial impoundment, and under seismic loads. To prevent this occurrence or to minimize the damage in these hydraulic structures, a reexamination of the earth dams' behavior using more elaborate calculation methods is necessary. The purpose of the current study is to numerically model the behavior and analyze the stability of earth dams in terms of displacements at the end of construction, after the initial impoundment, during an earthquake, and compare these displacements with those measured in situ. A case study was conducted for the Taksebt - Tizi Ouzou dam by using the Plaxis 2D calculation code and the finite element method. The comparison of the obtained results shows a close concordance with the monitoring results of the dam carried out by various specialized organizations.

Keywords-earth dam; failure; stability; slope; earthquake; finite element modeling; Plaxis

I. INTRODUCTION

Homogeneous or zoned earth dams are important constructions commonly used in Algeria [1, 2]. These structures are subjected to displacements during construction, at the initial impoundment, and throughout the years of exploitation. Their safety requires monitoring of their behavior in order to prevent hazards susceptible to happen. The in-situ monitoring from geotechnical and geodetic measuring devices is doubtless the most used and most reliable means nowadays [3, 4]. However, this technique is not sufficient and cannot escape some difficulties of interpretation of some local aspects inside the dam body, which can neither be measured nor interpreted from in-situ measurements [5, 6]. One of the possibilities to improve the knowledge on the behavior of earth dams is to generate information from an analysis of the phenomena that intervene inside the dam and its different boundaries [7]. In this concept, numerical modeling and simulation form an essential tool, which allows the prediction of the response and the behavior of the dam with respect to various loading cases [8, 9]. The finite element method is widely used in the modeling and simulation of complex physical phenomena. It is very well suitable for the modeling of earth dams by considering loading conditions, complex boundaries, irregular geometries, and material characteristics. It enables simulation of their behavior using various behavior laws, resulting in a more realistic imaging [10, 11]. Based on these considerations, it can be concluded that the measurements provided by geotechnical and geodesic methods and the results obtained by FEM can only be complementary [12]. The prediction of the dynamic response of an earth dam to seismic loads is an important issue in the safety assessment of these structures in seismic zones. The failure of a dam or a dike, when it occurs, usually has heavy consequences, either in terms of cost or in terms of human lives [8, 9, 13].

Numerical modeling is one of the most complex applications in the study of zoned earth dams. This study involves different numerical models, associated to each load case and submersion level. It requires the recognition of the various geotechnical characteristics, the variation of which is

depending on the considered zone state (dry or submerged) and on the behavioral models to be retained.

The purpose of this paper is to present a methodology for modeling a zoned earth dam to simulate its behavior in terms of displacement for stability verification using FEM through Plaxis software and compare these displacements with those measured in situ [14]. The Taksebt zoned earth dam is considered as the case study. The calculation of the displacements of the dam is carried out in three steps: after the completion of its construction, during its initial impoundment, and during an earthquake.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Taksebt dam is located on the Oued Aissi, main stream of the Oued Sebaou [15], 10km southeast of the Tizi-Ouzou city and at 100km from the Algeria Capital. This dam is an embankment made of silty-gravelly alluvium with a core of degraded clay, its crest level is 171.5m, and its height from the valley bed is 76m. The regular annual volume of sand is $180 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ with a total capacity of $175 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ and a watershed of 448 km^2 . The dam is mainly made of several materials placed in layers 0.3m thick and its foundation is mostly composed of weathered shale. The physical and mechanical characteristics of the materials used are presented in Table I. Sealing is provided by a centered clay core 53m in width at the base and 8.6m in width at the top [15].

The analysis of the static behavior of the dam is carried out by the finite element method with Plaxis using triangular elements with two degrees of freedom per node, i.e. the displacements U_x along X and U_y along Y. The transversal profile of the considered dam has an asymmetrical trapezoidal shape and it will be modeled by a 2D plane geometric model. The reference model is realized by triangular elements with 15 nodes, in a total of 926 elements and 7589 nodes. We adjusted the fineness of the mesh (global coarseness), as shown in Figure 2. The Mohr-Coulomb model was used on all layers of the dam to calculate displacements and safety factors at the end of construction and during reservoir filling [10, 16].

TABLE I. MATERIALS OF TAKSEBT DAM AND ITS FOUNDATION

Material type	Saturated unit weight (kN/m ³)	Cohesion (kN/m ²)	Friction angle (°)	Modulus of elasticity (kN/m ²)	Permeability (m/s)
Clay core	19.7	10	15	15000	10^{-8}
U/S D/S rockfill	23.1	2	30	90000	10^{-5}
Filter	21.2	2	32	120000	10^{-5}
Drain	21.8	2	28	30000	10^{-3}
Riprap	22.5	2	40	190000	10^{-3}
Upstream cofferdam	22.3	5	35	190000	10^{-2}
Alluvium	21.5	2	38	30000	10^{-5}
Weathered shale	21.8	20	28	300000	10^{-8}

The settlements at the end of the construction of the hydraulic structure may vary significantly from one structure to another [11]. They depend, among other factors, on the compressibility of the materials used, the height of the structure and the level of compaction. The settlements related to the filling may reach up to 1 to 2% of the height of hydraulic structure for central core dams. These settlements are typically more favored when the height of the hydraulic structure is high

and the rockfill has low compressive strength. In general, for earth dams with a central core, there is an acceleration of the settlement of the structure crest due to the pressure exerted by the water [13]. To study the seismic response of the dam, the system was applied to the accelerations of the Boumerdes earthquake on May 21st 2003, as shown in Figure 2 recorded at station No. 2 of the Keddara dam (the east west E.W. Component), the velocity of the recorded peak is estimated at

0.10m/sec, the acceleration at peak is 0.338g. The viscous damping ratio was equal to $\xi = 5\%$. The values of Rayleigh coefficients were $\alpha_R = 0.19$ and $\beta_R = 0.012$ and the values of the integration parameters are taken as $\gamma = 0.5$ and $\beta = 0.25$ with $\Delta t = 0.005$ time step [17].

MATERIALS	LEGEND
Clay core	
U/S D/S Rockfill	
Filter	
Drain	
Riprap	
Upstream cofferdam	
Alluvium	
Weathered Shale	

Fig. 1. Finite element mesh of the Taksebt dam with its materials.

Fig. 2. Recording of the E.W. component of the Boumerdes earthquake (May 21st, 2003. Acceleration).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Displacements at the End of the Construction of the Dam

Figures 3 and 4 show the vertical and horizontal displacements at the end of the dam construction. The maximum obtained displacements show the cumulative displacement during the construction phases. The maximum horizontal displacement is equal to 0.43m and the maximum vertical displacement is equal to 0.58m which means a settlement that represents 0.76% of the dam height. The maximum settlement calculated is 0.68m at the bottom upstream side of the dam, representing 0.89% of the dam height. It is inferior to 2% of the dam height, which is in accordance with the expected behavior of a rockfill dam with a clay core during the filling operation.

Fig. 3. Vertical deformations at the end of the construction.

Fig. 4. Horizontal deformations at the end of the construction.

B. Settlements after the Initial Impoundment

Figures 5 and 6 show the vertical and horizontal displacements of the dam body for the normal reservoir level of 165m.

Fig. 5. Vertical deformations for the normal reservoir level of 165m.

Fig. 6. Horizontal deformations for the normal reservoir level of 165m.

C. Settlements at the end of the Earthquake

The obtained results of the vertical and horizontal displacements are shown in Figures 7 and 8. The maximum horizontal displacement is approximately 0.42m and is located in the downstream side near the crest. The maximum vertical settlement is approximately 0.07m and is located in the upstream side near the crest. The crest of the dam is displaced toward downstream by 0.37m [9].

Fig. 7. Vertical displacements at the end of the earthquake.

Fig. 8. Horizontal displacements at the end of the earthquake.

Fig. 9. Comparison between the calculated and measured displacements at the crest of the dam during the earthquake.

Fig. 10. The displacement on the earth dam's crest.

Fig. 11. Comparison between calculated and measured displacements at the crest of the dam during its initial impoundment.

Figures 9 and 11 show the comparison between the calculated and the measured displacements at the crest of the dam during the Boumerdes earthquake in May 21st, 2003 and between the calculated and measured displacements at the crest of the dam during its initial impoundment, respectively. Figure 10 shows a real picture of the displacement on the dam's crest.

Concerning the vertical displacements at the level of the crest after the initial impoundment, Figures 9 and 11 show that on the upstream side, the calculated displacements are inferior

to the measured ones. This can be explained by the deformation due to the creep of the rockfill, which is not considered by the calculation model. On the contrary, on the downstream side, a slight swelling of the wet clay that is not loaded can be seen.

IV. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the dam in the three stages of its life (at the end of the construction, after the initial impoundment, and under seismic loading) gave the following results:

The maximum displacements obtained show the cumulative displacement during the construction phases. The maximum horizontal displacement is equal to 0.43m and the maximum vertical displacement is equal to 0.58m which means a settlement that represents 0.76% of the dam height.

On the first filling of the reservoir, it was concluded that the displacements are maximum on the upstream side of the dam. The settlement calculated at the crest of the dam is less than 2% of the height, which is in accordance with the expected behavior of a rockfill dam with clay core.

The maximum settlement calculated at the crest is approximately equal to the settlement measured in situ but slightly less. This can be explained by the deformation due to the creep of the rockfill which is not considered by the calculation model.

For the seismic computations, this work gives encouraging results: very good seismic stability of earth dams is found, and the displacements observed do not affect the stability of the structure. The numerical results obtained are in perfect accordance with the in-situ observations and the results of expertise carried out by various organizations.

Predicting the values and location of maximum displacements in earth dams is critical to the appropriate design of the instrumentation system for monitoring the actual behavior. In seismically active areas, earth dams are constructed using deformable materials that eventually must adjust to the varying loading conditions caused by the tectonic activity.

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Anti-Vibration Control of Turntable Ladders by a Steel Rope-Hydraulic Control System

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ABSTRACT

Anti-vibration control of turntable ladders is effective by controlling the steel ropes inserted in the hollow handrails. Previous studies that considered idealized conditions, such as ignoring friction, piston mass, and hydraulic oil compressibility, can not be strongly generalized. This study addresses these problems by describing in detail the equipment serving the anti-vibration solution, building a mathematical model for the steel rope hydraulic control system considering the above factors, and controlling the rapid extinguishing of vibrations on a model simulated in Matlab-Simulink. Furthermore, the simulation of the relationship between the control signal and oil flow through the proportional distribution valve produced a signal flow curve that was asymptotic to the actual. The results showed a difference compared to previous studies. Although the solution was only implemented on the lowest ladder section with the most unfavorable conditions, the time for vibration on the top ladder reached amplitudes of 3 and 5mm in 3 and 5s for empty and full baskets, respectively.

Keywords-aerial extension ladder; anti-vibration control; dynamic equation; steel rope hydraulic control; turntable ladder

I. INTRODUCTION

The study on vibration reduction, fast vibration quenching, and anti-swing for load transport equipment has high scientific and practical significance. Various control methods have been proposed to bring the load to the desired position quickly and accurately [1-4]. This activity makes more sense for turntable ladders because they transport rescued people and should help them feel safe in a rescue basket. Authors in [5-7] presented effective control methods to eliminate vibrations on turntable ladders. In [8-11], a new solution was presented to eliminate vibrations and overcome large static displacements on ladders, putting steel ropes inside the hollow of the handrails. These steel ropes were tensioned and controlled by small hydraulic cylinders mounted on the handrail tops, using the available hydraulic power of the truck. This method showed that the tension of the steel ropes had a positive effect on the anti-vibration on the top ladder [8] and the control of the steel ropes rapidly reduced the vibrations on the ladder [9]. In [10], stress reduction on key ladder elements and significant reduction of static displacements were demonstrated by evaluating the ladder structure with additional steel ropes according to the standards [12-13]. The hydraulic circuit design and cylinder control according to the control principle [9] were presented in [11]. However, the control system model in [11] was not very accurate and comprehensive, as it did not consider the elasticity of hydraulic oil, ignored friction forces and the mass of the piston rod, and used approximate mathematical models for the flow-signal curve. This study investigated the detailed structure

of the anti-vibration device, the dynamic model of the steel rope hydraulic control system, the establishment of a mathematical model of the system with an accurate flow-signal curve, and the practice of controls for rapid suppression of vibrations on turntable ladders.

II. STEEL ROPE-HYDRAULIC CONTROL SYSTEM

Figure 1 shows the structure of the devices attached to the hollow handrails of a ladder, omitting the ladder structure. The hydraulic cylinder is integrated with the position sensor mounted on the lower end of the handrail.

Fig. 1. Added components into a hollow handrail.

A threaded joint connects the piston rod to one end of the steel rope. The steel rope with a high damping coefficient is threaded in the handrail and supported by supports. The

supports are lightweight plastic evenly spaced to eliminate the rope sag. The other end of the rope is fixed by a threaded joint to the other end of the ladder. Additional devices were implemented in the lowest ladder section for anti-vibration to match the size of the 30m set including the three ladder sections described in [14]. The control on the third ladder is the most effective [9]. The most effective vibration control is when placing the actuator closest to the fixed end of a cantilever

beam [15]. Figure 2 shows the mechanical model of the ladder structure, the steel rope, and the force generated by the cylinder. The control system commands the actuator to generate a force to reduce vibration. This force moves with a variable velocity rule that follows or nearly follows a predefined rule. Based on the data in [8-11], all parameters in this model were entirely determined.

Fig. 2. Multi-body dynamics model of ladder set and steel rope in hollow handrails.

Figure 3 shows the model of the steel rope hydraulic control system. During the operation of the proportional directional valve, when the P-A ports are connected, the high-pressure hydraulic oil pushes the piston to the left to pull the steel rope. In contrast, when the A-T ports are connected, the oil in the cylinder chamber flows to the tank through the pressure sequence valve due to the tension of the rope pulling the piston. In this model, k_{c3} and c_{c3} are the stiffness and damping coefficients of the ropes in the third ladder section, A_p , p_p are the area and the pressure of the oil chamber, and x_p and x_r are the displacements of the piston and the remaining fixed end of the steel rope, respectively.

III. EQUATION OF MOVEMENT

According to [9], during the vibration control performance, the acceleration vector of the addition motion is determined as:

$$\ddot{\eta} = -M(t)^{-1}C(t)\dot{\eta} - M(t)^{-1}K(t)\eta + M(t)^{-1}(F + k_{FD}k_{contr}D) \quad (1)$$

where $\ddot{\eta}$, $\dot{\eta}$, and η are the acceleration, velocity, and displacement vectors of the addition motion of the rigid bodies, $M(t)$, $C(t)$, and $K(t)$ are the mass matrix, the damping matrix, and the stiffness matrix, D is the load matrix including T_i (bending moment) and D_i (damping load) caused by the steel rope in the i -th ladder section, F is the load matrix excluding the load components caused by the steel rope, and $k_{FD} = \partial F(t)/\partial D$ with $F(t)$ being the total generalized load matrix.

$$k_{contr} = \text{diag}[1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ k_{T3} \ k_{D3}] \quad (2)$$

where k_{T3} and k_{D3} are the controlling factors corresponding to T_3 and D_3 in the third ladder section, respectively. The motion equation of the piston is given by:

$$p_p A_p - k_{c3} \Delta l_{ca3} - c_{c3} \Delta \dot{l}_{ca3} - F_f = m_p \ddot{x}_p \quad (3)$$

where Δl_{ca3} , $\Delta \dot{l}_{ca3}$ represent the length change range and the length change speed of the steel rope, F_f is the friction force, m_p is the piston mass, and \ddot{x}_p is the piston acceleration. The exact determination of the friction force is very complicated and it is necessary to conduct experiments on each specific object. To simplify the simulation, it was determined as follows [16]:

$$F_f = \begin{cases} F_s + c_p \cdot |p_p A_p| & \text{for } \dot{x}_p > v_0 \\ (F_s + c_p \cdot |p_p A_p|) \frac{\dot{x}_p}{\dot{x}_0} & \text{for } -\dot{x}_0 \leq \dot{x}_p \leq v_0 \\ -F_s - c_p \cdot |p_p A_p| & \text{for } \dot{x}_p < -v_0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3. Mechanical model of steel rope-hydraulic control system.

where v_o is the velocity whose value is a very small positive around zero, $F_s=10^5 A_p$, and $c_p=2\%$. The change range of the steel rope length during work is given by:

$$\Delta l_{ca3} = x_p + x_{p0} - x_r \quad (5)$$

and the length change speed of the steel rope is given by:

$$\dot{\Delta l}_{ca3} = \dot{x}_p - \dot{x}_r \quad (6)$$

with x_r being the longitudinal displacement of the upper end of the handrail. The dynamic equation for the oil compressibility inside the cylinder chamber can be written as [17]:

$$\dot{p}_p = \frac{\beta_o}{V_c} (Q_x - \dot{V}_c) \quad (7)$$

where \dot{p}_p denotes the change rate of the chamber pressure, β_o is the oil bulk modulus, V_c denotes the oil volume, and Q_x denotes the rate of flow entering the chamber.

$$V_c = V_{oc} + A_p(x_p + x_0) \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{V}_c = A_p \dot{x}_p \quad (9)$$

where x_0 is the oil length in the cylinder chamber when it is set to create the initial tension load, x_p is the displacement of the piston, and V_{oc} is the oil volume in the pipe.

Replacing (8) and (9) in (7) gives:

$$\dot{p}_p = \frac{\beta_o}{(V_{oc}+A_p x_0)+A_p x_p} (Q_x - A_p \dot{x}_p) \quad (10)$$

The flow rate depends on the pressure drop which is the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet ports and the corresponding nominal flow. This is detailed in:

$$Q_x = Q_{Nom}^* \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\Delta p_x}{\Delta p_{Nom}}} \quad (11)$$

where Δp_{Nom} is the pressure drop when the flow rate is nominal, and the command signal is maximum, $\Delta p_{Nom}=5 \times 10^5 \text{Pa}$, Δp_x is the pressure drop when working, and Q_{Nom}^* is the flow rate depending on the command signal. Q_{Nom}^* is determined as:

$$Q_{Nom}^*/Q_{Nom} = f(u) \quad (12)$$

where $u=U/U_{max}$, U is the control voltage, U_{max} is the maximum control voltage, and Q_{Nom} is the nominal flow at U_{max} .

Equation (10) is rewritten in the case of the piston pulling the steel rope:

$$\dot{p}_p = \frac{\beta_o (f(u) \cdot Q_{Nom} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{p_{oh}-p_p}{\Delta p_{Nom}}} - A_p \dot{x}_p)}{(V_{oc}+A_p x_0)+A_p x_p} \quad (13)$$

and in the case of the steel rope pulling the piston:

$$\dot{p}_p = \frac{\beta_o (f(u) \cdot Q_{Nom} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{p_p-p_{ou}}{\Delta p_{Nom}}} - A_p \dot{x}_p)}{(V_{oc}+A_p x_0)+A_p x_p} \quad (14)$$

with p_{oh} and p_{ou} being the pressure at P and T ports, respectively.

IV. ANTI-VIBRATION CONTROL

Based on the parameters and the original characteristic

curve of the proportional directional valve presented in [18], to simplify the numerical simulation process in its half corresponding to the positive signal, (12) can be approximated as:

$$\frac{Q_{Nom}^*}{Q_{Nom}} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } 0 \leq u < \frac{1}{10} \\ \frac{327u^2}{100} - \frac{63u}{100} + \frac{3}{100} & \text{for } \frac{1}{10} \leq u \leq \frac{25}{100} \\ \frac{37u}{30} - \frac{7}{30} & \text{for } \frac{25}{100} < u \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Figure 4 shows the original flow curve and the approximate curve generated by (15). They almost coincide.

Fig. 4. Flow characteristic according to command signal percentage.

The steel rope hydraulic control system model was established in Matlab-Simulink, as shown in Figure 5. The main parts of this model are:

- Ladder structure model: a subsystem created from the ladder dynamic model in Matlab-Simulink, as presented in [9].
- Signal generator: The velocity sensor at the top of the third ladder section provides a signal to the control signal generator, which is the original signal that is smoothed and amplified before reaching the valve. As the original signal is taken from the ladder structure model, the phase delay of the control signal must be considered. Here, the tensioner model starts 30ms after the ladder model. A delay time of 4ms was selected. When the amplitude of the vibration at the top ladder is small enough, the signal generator will stop working. This amplitude value can be preset.
- Function blocks of the hydraulic devices: They determine the dynamic parameters of the piston and the oil pressure in the chamber through (3) and (13)-(15).
- Damping load block: It receives the piston and rope end velocity signals and creates the damping force ($c_{c3} \dot{\Delta l}_{ca3}$).
- Rope tension block: It has the function of generating rope tension ($k_{c3} \Delta l_{ca3}$) based on the longitudinal deformation of the steel rope.

Table I shows the modeling parameters. The largest vertical vibration at the top ladder may occur when the ladder is horizontal and fully extended. Therefore, this study implements anti-vibration control in this ladder state.

Fig. 5. Steel rope-hydraulic control system model in Matlab-Simulink.

TABLE I. MODEL PARAMETERS OF CONTROL SYSTEM

β_o (Pa)	x_0 (m)	x_{p0} (m)	m_p (kg)	A_p (m ²)
1.8×10^9	0.02	0.01	1.1	10^{-3}
V_{oc} (m ³)	p_{oh} (Pa)	p_{oi} (Pa)	c_{c3} (Ns/m)	k_{c3} (N/m)
2.1×10^{-3}	21×10^6	5×10^6	1650	1.29×10^6

Figures 6-12 show the parameters obtained during the control process, including control signal, oil flow, oil pressure, friction force, piston speed and displacement, and damping force in the empty basket case. Figure 13 shows the displacement graphs on the top ladder for both basket cases. Despite the control signal's late start and phase delay, the vibration control through the steel rope hydraulic system was highly effective. Compared to [9] and [11], these results overcome the expected effect after control. In the empty basket case, the vibration amplitude after only 3s of control reaches 3mm for the top ladder instead of 67mm. The control systems in the other studies need more than 8s to achieve this amplitude. In case of a full basket, the vibration amplitude of the top ladder after 5s of control reaches 5mm compared to the others that need more than 14s to achieve such amplitude.

Fig. 6. Control signal percentage.

In addition to the steel rope having the effect of damping, the hydraulic equipment also suppresses the vibration when operating. The pressure and flow rate values for the cylinders presented in Figures 7-8 are suitable for the hydraulic system of a turntable ladder. The speed and displacement of the piston shown in Figures 10-11 are also consistent with the kinematic parameters of a piston used to control a precise motion system.

Fig. 7. Oil flow through a proportional directional valve.

Fig. 8. Oil pressure in the cylinder chamber.

Fig. 9. Friction force between piston and cylinder.

Fig. 10. Piston velocity.

Fig. 11. Piston displacement.

Fig. 12. Damping force.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper presented a new approach to anti-vibration methods for turntable ladders. It also shows the feasibility of carrying out the novel control solution presented in [9] with available devices in the market. A steel rope hydraulic dynamic model, including tension and damping load of steel

the ropes, friction force between the piston and the cylinder, oil compressibility, piston mass, and the proportional directional valve characteristics, was established and simulated. This model was combined with the ladder set's multi-body dynamics model to control the vibration's rapid quenching at the top ladder with a unique signal generator. Friction, oil compressibility, and the inertia force of the piston significantly influence the damping of the ladder's vibrations. This model extinguished vibrations by controlling the steel rope hydraulic system more efficiently, controlling only the steel ropes. The vibration reduction rate was approximately three times faster than in other studies.

Fig. 13. Displacement of the top ladder.

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Reliability-Based Optimal Integrated Microgrid Scheduling in Distribution Systems

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a reliability-based optimal scheduling model of integrated microgrids. The proposed model is capable of delivering optimal scheduling of each individual microgrid and aggregated system. In addition, it is compatible with both grid-connected and islanded operation modes. The developed problem formulation of the proposed model takes into account the reliability indices SAIDI, SAIFI, and CAIDI to evaluate the reliability of the integrated system. Numerical simulations on a modified IEEE-33 bus test system, involving four integrated microgrids, were performed to investigate the advantages and the robustness of the developed model. Furthermore, the impact of merging Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs) on the optimization outcome is examined, which demonstrates its significant effectiveness in improving the power systems' reliability.

Keywords-distributed energy resource; grid-connected operation; integrated microgrids; islanded operation; optimal scheduling; reliability indices

I. INTRODUCTION

Continuously optimizing and developing distribution systems' reliability is significant in the power systems optimization segment. Power outages may cause serious and massive difficulties for the end-users, such as the disruption of industrial, commercial, educational, and health systems [1-4]. The reliability of the distribution systems can be assessed and evaluated by reliability indices, including but not limited to, System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI) to measure the aggregated duration of an interruption, Customer Average Interruption Duration Index (CAIDI) to measure the average time of restoration, and System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI) to measure the average number of times customers experience outages during the study period [5-6]. Consequently, several studies have been conducted toward improving and assessing distribution systems' reliability. Authors in [7] investigated the impact of the integration of a large-scale solar photovoltaic (PV) system with wind turbines on the system reliability. An IEEE-40 bus test system was utilized in the proposed study, and the zone branch methodology was performed to evaluate the system reliability. Authors in [8] investigated the potential capability of the vehicle-to-grid with the grid-connected battery swapping station in improving the reliability of distribution networks by proposing a comprehensive methodological framework based on quantitative and Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) methods. Authors in [9] proposed an Electric Vehicle (EV) charging station placement strategy based on a Voltage stability, Reliability, and Power loss (VRP) index for distribution networks considering the impact of the resulting fast EV

charging station loads. In [10], a new approach based on a general probability formulation was developed to capture the availability of generation and transmission capacities and the randomness related to the load level. In addition, it was developed to calculate various quality measures and reliability indices. Authors in [11] solved the reconfiguration problem of distribution systems to improve the reliability indices and minimize the total active power losses based on a proposed Mixed Integer Second-Order Conic Programming (MISOCP) model.

Microgrids, as an intelligent technique to integrate Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), can significantly improve the range-specific reliability of the system within the microgrid's served area [12-15]. DERs could include renewable units, dispatchable Distributed Generators (DGs), and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs) [16-18]. Microgrids support the islanding operation capability [19-21]. Nevertheless, in some conditions, microgrids can provide ancillary services to other parts of the distribution network by supplying their excess generation back to the utility grid. The impact of the microgrids on the distribution networks' reliability is discussed in [22-24]. In [22], the impact of the microgrid control strategies during the islanded operation mode on distribution network reliability was investigated based on a probabilistic methodology and the use of the sequential Monte Carlo simulation. Authors in [23] developed a probabilistic approach for the optimal operation of active distribution networks based on the multi-microgrid framework considering technical indices of the system such as the system reliability and efficiency, and solved the problem by the non-dominated

genetic algorithm-II. Authors in [24] proposed an improved binary genetic algorithm approach to determine the optimal control and scheduling of DERs in hybrid microgrids to reduce the negative impact of outages on customers and improve system reliability.

Nonetheless, the integrated operation of the microgrids opens the horizon to further advantages. Enabling the local power exchange among the integrated system can significantly impact the microgrids' total operation costs by permitting their excess generation to be sold during the islanded operation. In addition, it will positively impact the distribution networks' reliability by supplying power to other parts with power deficiency. In this paper, the impact of the integrated microgrids on the power distribution networks' reliability is investigated based on the developed model. The contributions of the developed model are summarized as follows: (i) it significantly minimizes, individual- and integrated-base, microgrids' total operation cost, (ii) it distinctly improves the overall reliability of the distribution network, (iii) it explicitly supports the optimal operation of BESS in the integrated system, and (iv) it efficiently enables optimization during the islanded operation.

II. MODEL OUTLINE

The proposed reliability-based optimal integrated microgrid scheduling model ensures minimizing each individual microgrid's operation cost and the aggregated total operation cost of the integrated system. In addition, it significantly expands the reliability of the distribution network including the integrated microgrids. In the grid-connected mode, each microgrid in the system optimally schedules the local dispatchable DGs and BESS, and exchanges the power conventionally with the utility grid, i.e. imports power when needed and exports its excess generation, to increase its economic benefits from this process. On the other side, in the islanded mode, i.e. when the upstream grid faces interruptions or disturbances, all microgrids would be switched into the islanded operation mode. However, during the islanded mode, the integrated microgrids would exchange the power locally to support each other and to supply the other parts of the distribution network that are electrically connected to the microgrids. It is worth mentioning that the microgrids are typically connected to the other parts of the distribution network by the Points of Common Coupling (PCC), as depicted in Figure 1. The primary aim of this process is to minimize the amount of the load curtailments in the distribution network, i.e. to maximize the entire distribution system reliability, which will be evaluated by calculating the formulated reliability indices. Nevertheless, the impact of exchanging the power locally calls attention to the total operation cost, which is predicted to be further minimized due to the export of further excess generation. One-hour time periods are considered over a 24-hour scheduling horizon when solving the given problem. In addition, 25 different operation scenarios were applied to investigate the robustness of the proposed model. Shorter time periods could be deployed for more accurate results in order to follow fast changes in the proposed model without loss of generality.

Fig. 1. IEEE-33 bus distribution test system involving four integrated microgrids.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The objective of the reliability-based optimal integrated microgrid scheduling problem is to minimize the microgrids' total operation cost and to improve the integrated system reliability, as in (1):

$$\min \sum_m^M \sum_t^T \sum_s^K \left(\sum_i^{DG} F_{mi}(P_{mits}) I_{mit} + \rho_{mt} P_{mts}^M + \sum_{n,n \neq m}^M \lambda_{mnt} P_{mnts}^G + v_{mt} LS_{mts} + \gamma_{mt} \kappa_{mts} \right) \quad (1)$$

The first term in the objective function refers to the microgrids' dispatchable DGs, which includes the generation cost and the commitment status throughout the specified horizon. The second term refers to the cost of the power exchange with the utility, which could be a revenue once the power flow direction is from the microgrids to the utility, i.e. as it would be considered a negative cost. The third term represents the local power exchange among the integrated microgrids, i.e. it will be a cost for the buyer microgrid and a revenue for the seller microgrid. The fourth term represents the load curtailments, where it is multiplied by the Value Of Lost Load (VOLL). The last term is included as an auxiliary value of the reliability indices in the proposed model.

These cost expressions are calculated based on investigated operation scenarios that define the operation mode, i.e. grid-connected or islanded. The operation modes are recognized in the objective and in the developed constraints by the scenario index s , where $s = 0$ refers to the grid-connected mode and other values of s refer to the islanded operation mode over the selected horizon. The proposed objective is subjected to a set of linearized power flow constraints [25], and the following operation constraints: the power balance constraint, dispatchable DGs constraints, BESS constraints, and reliability indices constraints.

$$\sum_i^{DG} P_{mits} + \sum_i^S P_{mits} + P_{mts}^M + P_{mts}^G + LS_{mts} = D_{mts} \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (2)$$

$$-P^{M,max} U_{ts} \leq P_{mts}^M \leq P^{M,max} U_{ts} \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (3)$$

$$-P^{G,\max}(1 - U_{ts}) \leq P_{mits}^G \leq P^{G,\max}(1 - U_{ts}) \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (4)$$

Constraint (2) represents the integrated system power balance equation to guarantee that the total power generated and imported matches the local demand. However, it is worth mentioning that the non-dispatchable generations, such as PVs and wind turbines, have predicted values based on the units' characteristics and the historical data, hence, they are handled as constant negative loads in the problem formulation. In addition, it is noted that the load curtailment variable is included to the power balance constraint to achieve a feasible solution during the islanded operation. The power exchange of the integrated system with the utility grid is subjected to a maximum power exchange limitation, as in constraint (3), and is further imposed to zero (using a binary islanding indicator) once the system operates in the islanded mode. The local power exchange among the integrated microgrids is subjected to the line flow limits of (4). Nevertheless, the binary islanding indicator is added to the constraint to impose the local power exchange to zero during the grid-connected mode due to the fact that each microgrid in the system prefers to export or import power with the utility when it would be more economically beneficial. For example, when the local hourly bid price is higher than the hourly market price, the microgrids with power deficiency would prefer to import power from the utility. On the other side, when the local hourly price is lower than the hourly market price, the microgrids with excess generation would prefer to export power to the utility.

$$P_i^{\min} I_{mit} \leq P_{mits} \leq P_i^{\max} I_{mit} \quad \forall m, \forall i \in G, \forall t, \forall s \quad (5)$$

$$P_{mits} - P_{mi(t-1)s} \leq UR_{mi} \quad \forall m, \forall i \in G, \forall t, \forall s \quad (6)$$

$$P_{mi(t-1)s} - P_{mits} \leq DR_{mi} \quad \forall m, \forall i \in G, \forall t, \forall s \quad (7)$$

$$T_{mi}^{\text{on}} \leq UT_{mi}(I_{mit} - I_{mi(t-1)s}) \quad \forall m, \forall i \in G, \forall t, s = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$T_{mi}^{\text{off}} \geq DT_{mi}(I_{mi(t-1)s} - I_{mit}) \quad \forall m, \forall i \in G, \forall t, s = 0 \quad (9)$$

Dispatchable DGs' optimal operation is subjected to the following constraints. The capacity limit of each dispatchable DG is subjected to minimum and maximum limitations, as in (5), and is further subjected to the commitment status using the binary variable. Generated power by dispatchable DGs is also subjected to the ramp up and down rate limits, as in constraints (6) and (7). In addition, they are subjected to the minimum up and down time limits once they are switched ON/OFF, as in constraints (8) and (9). Dispatchable DGs could be also restricted by fuel and emission constraints, which are however neglected in this paper.

$$P_{mits} \leq P_{mit}^{dch,\max} u_{mit} - P_{mit}^{ch,\min} v_{mit} \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, \forall s \quad (10)$$

$$P_{mits} \geq P_{mit}^{dch,\min} u_{mit} - P_{mit}^{ch,\max} v_{mit} \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, \forall s \quad (11)$$

$$C_{mits} = C_{mi(t-1)s} - P_{mits} u_{mits} \tau / \eta_i - P_{mits} v_{mits} \tau \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, \forall s \quad (12)$$

$$C_{mi}^{\min} \leq C_{mits} \leq C_{mi}^{\max} \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, \forall s \quad (13)$$

$$T_{mi}^{ch} \leq MC_{mi}(u_{mits} - u_{mi(t-1)s}) \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, s = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$T_{mi}^{dch} \geq MD_{mi}(v_{mits} - v_{mi(t-1)s}) \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, s = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$u_{mits} + v_{mits} \leq 1 \quad \forall m, \forall i \in S, \forall t, s = 0 \quad (16)$$

BESS is subjected to maximum and minimum charging and discharging limits, as in constraints (10) and (11). The stored energy in the BESS is computed based on the charging and discharging processes over the specified horizon, considering the BESS efficiency, as in constraint (12). The BESS is further restricted by the minimum and maximum capacity limits, as in constraint (13). In addition, BESSs are restricted by minimum charging and discharging time limits, as in constraints (14) and (15). Moreover, they are regulated by adding the binary variables u and v to ensure that they operate only in one mode (i.e. either charging or discharging), at each time-period, as in constraint (16).

$$0 \leq Ni_m \leq LS_{mits} / w_m \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (17)$$

$$0 \leq ri_m \leq 60(1 - U_{ts}) \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (18)$$

$$SAIDI = \sum (ri_m Ni_m) \kappa_{mits} / NT_m \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (19)$$

$$SAIFI = \sum Ni_m \kappa_{mits} / NT_m \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (20)$$

$$CAIDI = \sum (ri_m Ni_m) \kappa_{mits} / \sum Ni_m \quad \forall m, \forall t, \forall s \quad (21)$$

Reliability indices are formulated in (17)-(21). The number of interrupted customers who have suffered from power outages for each sustained interruption event is computed by (17). The restoration time for each interruption event, once the outage occurs, is formulated by (18). The reliability indices SAIDI, SAIFI, and CAIDI are computed by (19), (20), and (21), respectively. The auxiliary binary variable κ is added to provide value and significance of minimizing the reliability indices in the objective.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A modified IEEE-33 bus test system was utilized to investigate the proposed reliability-based optimal integrated microgrid scheduling problem. The investigated test system involves four integrated microgrids, named MG 1 to 4, as demonstrated in Figure 1. In addition, the test system involves 33 buses, 32 distribution lines, and 11 fixed loads [26]. The total number of served customers, in the proposed study is assumed to be 50,000. Furthermore, based on the declared average annual electricity consumption per customer by the U.S. Energy Information Administration for residential sector, i.e. 10,715kWh [27], the parameter w for the hourly average power consumption per customer is assumed to be 1.223kW. The microgrids' hourly fixed load and the forecasted hourly market price for the 24-hour period can be found in [26]. In addition, it is assumed that the price of the power exchange among the integrated microgrids λ is higher than the forecasted market price by 10% in (\$/kWh).

The aggregated hourly forecasted fixed load for buses beyond the area covered by the microgrids is shown in Table I. The characteristics of the microgrids' dispatchable units are illustrated in Table II, which includes the cost coefficient (\$/kWh) of all dispatchable DGs, the ramping rates (kW/h), the up/down time limits (h), and the minimum and maximum capacity limits of the DGs (kW). The impact of installing BESSs is considered, and the BESS characteristics are shown in Table III. The BESS efficiency η is assumed to be 90% [16]. It is worth mentioning that the proposed problem is solved for one complete operational day over a 24-hour horizon considering 25 islanded operation scenarios (i.e. one scenario presents the grid-connected operation, while the other scenarios present a power outage for every hour). Moreover, a relatively small VOLL of \$10/kWh is assumed [28], to specify the value of the undesired load curtailment. The proposed problem is programmed and solved in CPLEX 11.0 [29]. The following case studies are investigated:

Case 0: Optimal individual scheduling without BESS: In this case, the microgrids are optimally scheduled independently, i.e. there is no power exchange at all among the microgrids in the system, based on the islanded operation scenarios horizon and without installing BESSs. The optimal scheduling results of the microgrids ensure minimum operation cost and maximum reliability "locally", i.e. within the microgrids' served area. However, the other parts of the distribution network would not gain any advantages from this process. The microgrids' total operation costs are computed as \$176.72, \$191.25, \$543.96, and \$641.86 for MG 1, MG 2, MG 3, and MG 4, respectively (Table IV). Three islanded operation scenarios are arbitrarily nominated to investigate the reliability of the entire distribution network, i.e. islanded hours 9, 16, and 17, by calculating the reliability indices. Table V illustrates and summarizes the results of the reliability indices calculations in this case. The reliability indices SAIDI, SAIFI, and CAIDI are calculated as 3.78min, 0.03776, and 100.23min, respectively.

Case 1: Optimal integrated microgrid scheduling without BESSs: In this case, the local power exchange among the integrated microgrids is activated by utilizing the distribution network's lines. This case study investigates the impact of exploiting the unused capacity of the microgrids on the distribution system. Enabling local power exchange could significantly impact the microgrids' total operation costs and the overall reliability of the system. Comparing the microgrids' total operation costs in this case study with the obtained results in the base case, the microgrids' total operation costs are computed as \$71.56 (-59.51%), \$133.76 (-30.06%), \$499.04 (-8.26%), and \$587.36 (-8.49%) for MG 1, MG 2, MG 3, and MG 4, respectively, as shown in Table IV. Furthermore, this pointedly influences the reliability of the distribution network by supplying the fixed load on buses beyond the microgrids' covered area in case of outages. The reliability indices SAIDI, SAIFI, and CAIDI in this case are calculated as 3.02 (-20.11%), 0.02992min (-20.76%), and 99.95min (-0.28%), respectively, as illustrated in Table V.

TABLE I. FIXED LOAD ON BUSES BEYOND THE MICROGRIDS COVERED AREA

	Fixed load over 24h							
Time (h)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Load (kW)	744	741	738	738	738	738	781	763
Time (h)	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Load (kW)	761	763	773	773	775	773	773	773
Time (h)	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
Load (kW)	775	758	744	741	741	741	738	733

TABLE II. CHARACTERISTICS OF MICROGRIDS' DISPATCHABLE UNITS

DG	MG 1	MG 2	MG 3	MG 4
	Price (\$/kWh)			
DG 1	0.065	0.072	0.085	0.089
DG 2	0.039	0.064	0.065	0.069
DG 3	0.017	0.019	0.025	0.029
	Minimum – maximum capacity (kW)			
DG 1	20 – 100	14 – 70	20 – 100	30 – 150
DG 2	20 – 100	16 – 80	40 – 200	50 – 250
DG 3	40 – 200	30 – 150	80 – 400	60 – 300
	Minimum up/down time (h)			
DG 1	3	4	5	3
DG 2	3	4	4	3
DG 3	1	2	2	1
	Ramp up/down rate (kW/h)			
DG 1	50	35	50	75
DG 2	50	40	100	125
DG 3	100	75	200	150

TABLE III. MICROGRIDS' BESS CHARACTERISTICS

Microgrid	BESS characteristics			
	Storage	Capacity (kWh)	Min.Max. ch/dch Power (kW)	Min. ch/dch Time (h)
MG 1	BESS	100	4 – 20	5
MG 2	BESS	50	2 – 10	4
MG 3	BESS	60	8 – 20	4
MG 4	BESS	120	16 – 40	5

TABLE IV. SUMMARY OF TOTAL OPERATION COST

Microgrid	Total operation cost		
	Case 0	Case 1	Case 2
MG 1	\$176.72	\$71.56 (-59.51%)	\$41.39 (-76.58%)
MG 2	\$191.25	\$133.76 (-30.06%)	\$118.75 (-37.91%)
MG 3	\$543.96	\$499.04 (-8.26%)	\$489.77 (-9.96%)
MG 4	\$641.86	\$587.36 (-8.49%)	\$561.45 (-12.53%)

TABLE V. SUMMARY OF RELIABILITY INDICES CALCULATIONS

Index	Reliability Indices		
	Case 0	Case 1	Case 2
SAIDI (min)	3.78	3.02	2.66
SAIFI	0.03776	0.02992	0.02641
CAIDI (min)	100.23	99.95	99.31

Case 2: Optimal integrated scheduling considering the impact of BESSs: In this case, the impact of installing the BESSs on the optimization outcome is investigated. The microgrids' total operation cost is computed as \$41.39 (-76.58%), \$118.75 (-37.91%), \$489.77 (-9.96%), and \$561.45 (-12.53%) for MG 1, MG 2, MG 3, and MG 4, respectively, as shown in Table IV. The achieved results show further minimization in the microgrids' total operation costs due to the exploitation of BESSs in storing energy during lower hourly market prices and exporting it back to the utility grid

during higher price periods. The optimal scheduling of the power exchange between the microgrids and the upstream grid is illustrated in Figure 2, while Figure 3 demonstrates the BESS optimal scheduling results. Moreover, the examined distribution network's reliability is obviously improved. The reliability indices SAIDI, SAIFI, and CAIDI are calculated as 2.66min (-29.63%), 0.02641 (-30.06%), and 99.31min (-0.92%), respectively, as illustrated in Table V. Accordingly, the integration of BESSs in power systems significantly expands the anticipated outcome and enhances the optimization results.

Fig. 2. Optimal power exchange with the utility grid in Case 2.

Fig. 3. Optimal BESS scheduling in Case 2.

V. DISCUSSION

Microgrids can promote the anticipated minimization of the total operation cost and maximize the local points of reliability. However, further benefits can be achieved once the microgrids are integrated with each other. This paper investigates the potential impact of the integrated system on the microgrids and on the entire distribution system by the proposed optimization model. In addition, it examines the optimal operation of BESSs and investigates their impact on the optimization results. Moreover, the probability of the islanded operation of the integrated system is efficiently inspected in the proposed optimization model using the developed islanded operation scenarios. The proposed model is mathematically formulated as a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem and is solved using CPLEX.

The key features of the proposed optimization model can be outlined as follows:

- It significantly minimizes the total operation cost of each microgrid and of the whole integrated system.
- It explicitly enhances and improves the integrated system's reliability.
- It supports the optimal operation of BESSs.
- It considers optimal islanded operation.

Nonetheless, the proposed model is generic, and larger test systems and additional reliability indices can be carried out without loss of generality.

VI. CONCLUSION

An efficient reliability-based optimal scheduling model of integrated microgrids was developed in this paper. The proposed model was capable of optimally minimizing the microgrids' total operation costs and significantly boosting the overall reliability of the integrated system including the microgrids and the other parts of the power distribution grid. In addition, it was capable of identifying the optimal scheduling of the integrated system during the islanded operation. Numerical simulations on a modified IEEE-33 bus test system were performed to investigate the merits and the effectiveness of the proposed model in improving the system's power distribution reliability. The reliability indices SAIDI, SAIFI, and CAIDI were calculated by the formulated problem in all the considered case studies. Furthermore, the impact of installing Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs) was also studied and examined, and their significant weight, in minimizing the microgrids' total operation costs and enhancing the overall reliability of the power distribution system, was emphasized.

NOMENCLATURE

Indices:

- ch* Superscript for BESS charging mode.
- dch* Superscript for BESS discharging mode.
- i* Index for DERs.
- m,n* Index for microgrids.
- s* Index for scenarios.
- t* Index for time.

Sets:

- DG Set of dispatchable units.
- M Set of microgrids.
- K Set of islanded operation scenarios.
- S Set of energy storage systems.
- T Set of time periods.

Parameters:

- DR* Ramp down rate.
- DT* Minimum down time.
- F(.)* Generation cost of dispatchable units.
- MC* Minimum BESS charging time.
- MD* Minimum BESS discharging time.
- NT* Total number of customers served for the area.
- ri* Restoration time for each interruption event.
- U* Islanding state (0 when islanded, 1 otherwise).
- UR* Ramp up rate.
- UT* Minimum up time.
- w* Average power consumption per customer.
- ρ* Forecasted market price.
- λ* Price of local power exchange.
- γ* Auxiliary value of reliability indices.
- η* Battery energy storage efficiency.
- υ* Value of lost load.

Variables:

- C* Stored energy in battery energy storage systems.

D	Forecasted load demand.
I	Commitment state of dispatchable units.
LS	Load curtailment during islanded operation.
N_i	Number of interrupted customers for each sustained interruption event.
P	DER generated power.
P^G	Local power exchange among the microgrids.
P^M	Power exchange with utility grid.
T^{ch}	Number of BESS successive charging hours.
T^{dch}	Number of BESS successive discharging hours.
T^{on}	Number of successive ON hours.
T^{off}	Number of successive OFF hours.
κ	Auxiliary binary variable for reliability indices (1 during outage, 0 otherwise).
τ	Time period.
u	BESS discharging state.
v	BESS charging state.

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Building Applications and Developing Digital Signature Devices based on the Falcon Post-Quantum Digital Signature Scheme

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ABSTRACT

Falcon is an efficient and secure postquantum signature scheme for services based on quantum computing. It employs the hash-and-sign approach in conjunction with the Gentry, Peikert, and Vaikuntanathan (GPV) framework on Number Theory Research Unit (NTRU) lattices. This study evaluated the operation procedure and the capacity to run the Falcon scheme using a key length of 1024 bits on different hardware and software platforms, such as personal computers and Raspberry Pi 4 and Windows, Ubuntu, and Android operating systems. The following results were obtained: file sizes ranged from 30 to 5449268KB, digital signature times ranged from 50 to 19500ms, and signature verification times ranged from 14 to 19000ms. The results show that the Falcon post-quantum signature scheme works stably and ensures execution speed on different platforms, similar to current digital signature schemes.

Keywords-post-quantum; signature; falcon; NTRU lattices; Raspberry Pi 4 Model B

I. INTRODUCTION

With the emergence of quantum computers, traditional cryptography is gradually losing its security elements, and becomes a threat to the security of asymmetric cryptosystems and digital signatures based on number theory in quantum computers, such as RSA, DSA, Diffie-Hellman, ElGamal, and elliptic curve variants [1-4]. Post-quantum cryptosystems must ensure their security properties even in the face of quantum computers [4-5]. The Falcon scheme is one of the post-

quantum digital signature schemes nominated in the post-quantum cryptography competition that can be used on NIST quantum computer systems as of 2017 [1]. NIST has presented several cryptosystems that can meet the security requirements against quantum computing systems, known as post-quantum cryptography, such as NTRU, Rainbow, Classic McEliece, Falcon, etc. [1]. In particular, the Falcon digital signature is one of the schemes that has many security advantages against quantum computer systems [6-7].

The GPV framework theory for lattice-based digital signatures was presented in 2008 [2]. The design of the Falcon signature scheme was based on the lattice theory for the digital signature scheme [2]. This lattice theory is constructed by first initializing it with the NTRU lattice and the trapdoor sampler "Fourier Rapid Sampling" [8-9]. The complexity of the Falcon signature scheme is based on the openness of finding the Short Integer Solution (SIS) when solving the NTRU lattice problem [10]. This is a current open problem. This problem has been solved in cases where the boundary conditions of the equation are small, but the solution is still challenging when the boundary conditions of the equation are large, even with the help of a quantum computer.

This study investigated and assessed the design and implementation of the Falcon digital signature scheme for key generation, digital signature, and signature verification on hardware (Raspberry Pi 4 Model B [11-13]) and software (Windows, Ubuntu, Android), using experiments to assess its performance.

II. THE FALCON SCHEME

A. Mathematical Basis of the Falcon Post-Quantum Signature Scheme

In the Falcon digital signature scheme, the GPV framework theory is used to build a lattice-based digital signature scheme. The framework can be described as having the following components:

- The public key is a matrix with full rank $A \in Z_q^{n \times m}$, $m > n$, that creates a lattice \mathcal{A} .
- The secret key is a matrix $B \in Z_q^{n \times m}$ that creates an orthogonal mesh Λ_q^\perp . Here, Λ_q^\perp is the orthogonal grid symbol of the lattice \mathcal{A} modulo q and the orthogonal mesh satisfies the following property: with every $x \in \mathcal{A}$ and $y \in \Lambda_q^\perp$, then the condition $\langle x, y \rangle = 0 \pmod q$ is satisfied. Equivalently, the orthogonal rows of A and B satisfy:

$$B \times A^t = 0 \quad (1)$$

- Perform signature for message m : the signature form is a short integer value $s \in Z_q^m$, so that $sA^t = H(m)$, therein $H: \{0,1\}^* \rightarrow Z_q^n$ is a hash function. Then, for A , the validation of signature s is performed simply by checking if s is a short integer value that satisfies the condition $sA^t = H(m)$.
- Signature verification: The signature validation process is more complicated. At first, the user has to calculate the pre-image value $C_0 \in Z_q^m$ to satisfy $C_0A^t = H(m)$. This is entirely possible with linear algebra calculus tools as C_0 is not required to be short and $m \geq n$. Then, B is used to compute the orthogonal closing vector $v \in \Lambda_q^\perp$ close to C_0 . The validity of the signature is determined by $s = c_0 - v$. When c_0 and v are close enough (small $c_0 - v$) then:

$$sA^t = c_0A^t - vA^t = c - 0 = H(m) \quad (2)$$

As a result, s is short. This shows that the Falcon signature scheme has the advantage that the signature must be short.

In the GPV frame, v is calculated based on the algorithm randomness generated in the algorithm variant to find the nearest plane corresponding to v [14]. As the algorithm to find the primitive nearest plane is vulnerable to an attack on the corresponding basis set of the secret corresponding to B , the schema is unsafe. However, this was improved when the algorithm was used with a given m and sampling s according to the demand distribution [15]. The spherical Gaussian distribution on the translated lattice is $C_0 + \Lambda_q^\perp$. This method was proven to not reveal information about B , and it was the first algorithm to use trapdoor sampling sets.

Afterward, choosing a cryptosystem for the GPV frame is a requirement. The Falcon post-quantum digital signature scheme used an NTRU lattice in addition to a ring structure. The purpose of this idea was to help reduce the size of public keys with computational complexity $O(n)$ and speed up the scheme by reducing the computational complexity to $O(n/\log n)$. In terms of the theory of lattice on rings, the NTRU lattice has been proven to be the smallest standard grid, i.e. the smallest set that has many good properties. The good cryptographic properties of the NTRU lattice on this polynomial ring are shown by the following property: The public key is a remainder of a simple (one-variable) polynomial on the ring of polynomial $h \in Z_q[x]$ whose largest degree is $n-1$. With the advantages of the NTRU lattice when applying such public key generation, the GPV framework used with the NTRU grid ensures the security of the Falcon scheme [9]. The NTRU grid is represented as:

$$\varphi = x^n + 1, (n = 2^k) \quad (3)$$

The secret key of NTRU is a set of four polynomials $f, g, F, G \in Z[x]/(\varphi)$, that satisfy:

$$fG - gF = q \pmod \varphi \quad (4)$$

where the polynomial f must be invertible modulo q . For the public key, the polynomial h can be calculated by:

$$h \leftarrow g \cdot f^{-1} \pmod q \quad (5)$$

The polynomial h is called the public key. Thus, for the Falcon scheme, the public key is the polynomial h and the secret key is a set of the four polynomials f, g, F, G .

B. Prove the Correctness of the Key Generation Process

The two matrices $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & h \\ 0 & q \end{bmatrix}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} f & g \\ F & G \end{bmatrix}$ must be on the same lattice. In this case, if the polynomials f and g are produced with a sufficiently large entropy, then the generated public key h guarantees good pseudo-randomness [9]. However, in practice, even if f and g have relatively small entropy, it is still difficult to find the corresponding small polynomials f' and g' satisfying the condition $h = g' \cdot (f')^{-1} \pmod q$. This makes the NTRU lattice difficult to solve when the lattice is large enough, increasing complexity and ensuring its safety against quantum computers.

C. Implementation of the Falcon Post-Quantum Signature Scheme

The Falcon key generation, digital signature, and authentication are built on top of the GPV framework and implemented as follows:

- For the key generation, the public key is $A = [1 | h^*]$, which is equivalent to knowing the polynomial h .
- The secret key is: $B = \begin{bmatrix} g & -f \\ G & -F \end{bmatrix}$
- For the key validation, A and B are orthogonal through the expression: $B \times A^* = 0 \text{ mod } q$.
- For the digital signature, the signature of the message m takes the form of a salt r along with a pair of polynomials (s_1, s_2) satisfying:

$$s_1 + s_2 h = H(r || m) \tag{6}$$

Since s_1 is completely determined by m , r , and s_2 , the signature is a pair (r, s_2) .

D. Selecting a Set of Parameters to Ensure the Safety of the Falcon Scheme

The input parameters to the Falcon signature scheme are important to ensure a secure digital signature process. The scheme is built on the GPV framework on defining the sample for the trapdoor sampler. The inputs to the trapdoor sampler include matrix A , trapdoor function T , and objective value c . The output is a short vector s that satisfies:

$$s^t A = c \text{ mod } q \tag{7}$$

Calculating this output value is equivalent to finding a vector $v \in A_q^t$ that has a value close enough to c_0 . This shows that the tailgate sampler is important. These input parameter values are taken to ensure the quality of the trapdoor sampler based on efficient matrix calculations, and the "quality" of the sampler must be guaranteed: The shorter the vector s , i.e. the closer v is to c_0 , the safer the sample.

E. Theoretical Security Assessment for the Falcon Post-Quantum Digital Signature Scheme

With theoretical safety criteria, the NIST has made several evaluations of current trapdoor samplers. Table I details the survey, analysis, and performance evaluation in terms of speed, outputs, and compatibility with the NTRU lattice.

TABLE I. COMPARE SAMPLING ALGORITHMS [1]

Sampling Algorithm	Speed	Output s short	NTRU lattice compatibility
[15]	No	Yes	No
[17]	Yes	No	Yes
[18]	Yes	Yes	No
[8]	Yes	Yes	Yes

In the implementation of the algorithm presented in [5], matrix B is taken as a trapdoor and then the algorithm generates vector s with normalized form $\|B\|_{GS}$. The process of generating a short vector s increases the security of the

algorithm. This process has a computational complexity in time and space of approximately $O(m^2)$ [16].

The algorithm proposed in [17] is a version of the algorithm for finding the nearest plane at random. In [17], it was shown that this algorithm was equivalent to [15], and the output s was also a vector, but expressed in a normalized form $\|B\|_2$. But, as s is represented in its second normal form, the security will not be equal to [15]. In terms of complexity and processing time, this algorithm has time and space complexity of $O(m \log m)$. The algorithm in [17] allows sampling the trapdoor from the trapdoor of A simply and efficiently. However, this algorithm is not compatible with the NTRU lattice and does not achieve a small enough initial vector s to correspond to the NTRU lattice built, according to the GPV framework [18]. The algorithm "fast Fourier transform for the nearest plane" proposed in [8] was a variant of the algorithm "find the nearest plane of Babai" with a lattice on a polynomial ring. In this algorithm, recursion is very similar to a fast Fourier transform, which is the reason for the algorithm's name. The algorithm was built based on the trapdoor sampling method with assurance according to the [15]. This shows that the algorithm in [8] works as efficiently as the algorithm in [17] and can be used with the NTRU lattice.

According to Table I, the "fast Fourier transforms for nearest plane" algorithm on the NTRU grid [8] is the most suitable for the objectives of this study. After generating the key according to the NTRU lattice, the polynomials f, g, F, G will be converted to a canonical form for use as a new secret key of the form $sk = (\hat{B}, T)$. Matrix \hat{B} is calculated according to:

$$\hat{B} = \begin{bmatrix} FFT(g) & -FFT(f) \\ FFT(G) & -FFT(F) \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

The calculation of the falcon tree T is performed in 2 steps. At first, T -tree is calculated from $G \rightarrow \hat{B} \times \hat{B}^*$ as an unnormalized Falcon tree. Then, normalization is performed on T -tree, according to standard deviation σ . The key generated in this way ensures compactness and allows fast signature generation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Design and Build Falcon Post-Quantum Digital Signature Application on Windows, Ubuntu, and Android OS

The Falcon post-quantum digital signature module used in this study includes the following modules: quantum key generation (based on NTRU lattice combined with the falcon tree), Falcon digital signature (according to the GPV framework built on NTRU lattice with trapdoor sampling "Quick Fourier Transform Sampling"), and Falcon digital signature authentication. Figure 1 shows a working model of the Falcon post-quantum digital signature. On the first start of the Falcon, after entering the input file, the program generates a key according to the above algorithms if no standard set of keys has been generated or set before. The private part of this key will be used to digitally sign the file, and the digital signature of the original file along with the public key will be transmitted to the recipient so that he can verify it.

The program module was designed with 2 main interfaces: Figure 2 shows the interface for the digital signature process

according to the Falcon digital signature scheme to (a) sign and protect a file against post-quantum algorithms and (b) validate it. To sign a file, a user has to select it, type the filename to save the signed one, and press the "Sign" button. If the key exists, the program will immediately return the signing result. If not, it will generate a quantum key as described above. If the generation of the digital signature is successful, the signature will be printed along with the time elapsed for its generation. When authenticating a signed file, a user has to select it along with the public key of the signature and then click the "Verify" button. The program will automatically verify the signature, showing the appropriate message and the time elapsed for the validation procedure. The application was built in Python/Tkinter [19] and tested on Windows, Ubuntu, and Android, as shown in Figure 3.

4 Model B connected to a wifi router. Users accessed the system's IP address to utilize the service, as seen in Figure 4. To use the program, the system must be powered on, as seen in Figure 6(a), then access the system's IP address from the client and log in, as seen in Figure 6(b). After a successful authentication, the user can use the services using a pre-initialized key saved on the device, as seen in Figure 6(c). The user then can upload the file to the system, which will digitally sign it with a pre-initialized key and return the signed file to download.

Fig. 1. Falcon Post-quantum digital signature operation model

Fig. 3. Executing the application in (a) Ubuntu, (b) Android, and (c) Windows.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of Falcon digital signature system operation using a Raspberry Pi 4.

Fig. 2. Implemented (a) Falcon Post-Quantum digital signature and (b) signature authentication interfaces.

B. Development of Falcon Post-Quantum Digital Signature Device on Raspberry Pi 4 Model B Hardware Platform

In addition to evaluating the software, this study built a digital signature mechanism using a Raspberry Pi 4. The Falcon digital signature system was installed on a Raspberry Pi

Fig. 5. Flowchart of key generation, key storage, and key use on the server.

This procedure uses four algorithms. The key generation algorithm is:

- Require: Request the creation of a new account.
- Ensure: a secret key sk , a public key pk .

1. Random $\phi = x1024 + 1$
2. Calculate $q = 121024 + 1$
3. Compute NTRU polynomials f, g, F, G verifying:
 $fG - gF = q \text{ mod } \phi (sk)$
4. Calculate $pk: h \leftarrow g \cdot f^{-1} \text{ mod } q$
5. Save sk, pk for this account in a yaml file.

The signing algorithm is detailed as:

- Require: A message m , a secret key sk .
- Ensure: A signature sig of m .
1. Random salt r
 2. Hash the message m with salt $r: H(r||m)$
 3. Repeat the signing procedure until finding a signature that is short enough (both the Euclidean norm and the byte length)
 4. Return: a signature sig of m

The verification algorithm is:

- Require: A signature sig of m , a public key pk , a message m'
- Ensure: accept or not
1. Unpack the salt r and the short polynomial $s2$
 2. Compute $s1$ and normalize its coefficients in $(-q/2, q/2]$
 3. Check that the $(s1, s2)$ is short
 4. Check that $s1 + s2h = H(r||m')$
 5. If all checks are passed, accept

The login verification algorithm is:

- Require: Username, password
- Ensure: accept or not
1. Check whether the username is in the database (yaml file)
 2. Hash the password (hp')
 3. Check that $hp' = hp$ (hp is the hash password for username in the yaml file)
 4. If all checks are passed, accept

Fig. 6. (a) Raspberry Pi 4 System startup, (b) login, and (c) digital signature interface.

To evaluate the performance of the system, different file types were digitally signed on these platforms with a key length of 1024 bits. Table II shows the results obtained for the Falcon

post-quantum signature process and verification. These results show that the execution time for the Falcon digital signature system on various platforms demonstrates the program's efficacy and stability. Digital signing takes 50–19500ms, signature authentication takes 14–19000ms, and the signature size is 1.28KB for file sizes ranging from 30 to 5,449,268KB, on different hardware (personal computer and Raspberry Pi 4) and software (Windows, Ubuntu, and Android). It is clear that the digital signature speed is related to the size of the file but always yields the same signature file size. The Falcon post-quantum cryptography can be used securely for quantum computers, as it has shorter execution times than the Rainbow post-quantum cryptosystem on the same machine [1]. This can be explained by Rainbow ($O(n^3)$) having more computational complexity than Falcon ($O(n/\log n)$).

TABLE II. FALCON SIGNATURE AND VALIDATION TIMES ACROSS PLATFORMS AND RAINBOW

File type	Capacity (KB)	Signature time (ms)	Authentication time (ms)	Signature size (KB)
Windows 10 [16Gb RAM – 2.3Ghz (8 CPUs)]				
jpg	124	50.896	14.994	1.28
exe	636,133	2314.817	2230.037	1.28
rar	2,977,754	11073.385	10615.610	1.28
iso	5,449,268	19448.226	19014.150	1.28
Ubuntu 20.04.4 – VMWare [16Gb RAM – 2.3Ghz (2 CPUs)]				
jpg	127	57.470	13.882	1.28
rar	40,803	208.493	164.825	1.28
exe	636,133	2481.803	2446.245	1.28
deb	3,335,876	12502.191	11989.483	1.28
Android [6Gb RAM – Snapdragon 695 5G]				
pdf	6758.4	164.661	99.195	1.28
rar	39,843	294.353	229.441	1.28
apk	357,808	1445.067	1350.679	1.28
mp4	1,184,891	4783.171	4470.747	1.28
Raspberry Pi 4 Model B [4Gb RAM - ARM Cortex-A72]				
File type	Capacity (KB)	Signature time (ms)	Signature size (KB)	
jpg	4,855	246.922	1.28	
mov	102,363	911.44	1.28	
rar	134,607	1128.04	1.28	
exe	636,133	4632.76	1.28	
Rainbow - Windows 10 [16Gb RAM – 2.3Ghz (8 CPUs)] [1]				
File type	Capacity (word)	Signature time (ms)	Authentication time (ms)	
Text	500	108.3	38.8	
Text	1000	46.4	37.4	
Text	10000	20.7	28.9	

The Fortify Static Code Analyzer toolkit v.22.1.0.0166 was used to validate the code structure, showing that the code was created securely. These results show that this application has reasonably fast post-quantum digital sign and verification speeds, which meet the current user requirements.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the mathematical assessment and security guarantees for the Falcon post-quantum digital signature system and tested its schema's key generation, and digital signature and validation processes. The results obtained with a key length of 1024 bits for the Falcon schema on both hardware and software (running on Windows, Ubuntu, and Android platforms) for file sizes between 30-5,449,268KB.

The time to perform a digital signature was approximately 50-19,500ms, the time to perform signature authentication was approximately 14-19,000ms, and the signature size was 1.28KB. These results demonstrate that the Falcon post-quantum digital signature method has steady performance and guarantees the same execution speed as existing digital signature systems on a variety of platforms. Future work should investigate the use of the Falcon post-quantum digital signature on more hardware platforms and its integration into commercial applications.

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The Effect of Cavitation Water Jet Shock as a Newly Technology on Micro-Forming Process

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ABSTRACT

This article proposes a novel technology called water jet cavitation shock micro-forming to fabricate micro-features on 304 stainless steel foils with a thickness of 100 μ m, using a cavitation nozzle with an incident pressure of 8 to 20MPa. This study investigated the surface morphology of the formed part, the influence of incident pressure, target distance, and impact time on the forming depth, and an analysis of the punching phenomenon of the formed components. The experimental results after the water jet cavitation shocking indicated that the surface morphology of the formed part of the 304 stainless foil sample had good quality and no conventional defects such as die scratches and cracks. Furthermore, when the incident pressure was 20MPa, the height of the uniform-shaped spherical cap exceeded 262 μ m. The forming depth increased with increasing incident pressure and impact time. Under an incident pressure of 20MPa, with the increase of target distance, the average depth of the formed part increased at first and then decreased. Finally, the analysis of the blanking phenomenon indicated that when the incident pressure increased to 30MPa, the workpiece was completely blanked. This is mainly because, under this incident pressure, the shockwave pressure generated by the collapse of the bubble deforms the workpiece beyond the stress limit of the material itself.

Keywords-novel technology; cavitation nozzle; incident pressure; surface morphology; shockwave

I. INTRODUCTION

Water jet technology is a cold working method that has been applied to a variety of industries, including civil engineering, architecture, and manufacturing. In this technology, water is discharged from nozzles under big pressure. This technology has been used to investigate water jet flows and develop new usages [1]. Cavitating jet in air [2], multifunction cavitation [3-6], and Water Jet Cavitation (WJC) [7, 8] are some of the available water jet processing methods. This study investigated WJC technology, which involves processing a workpiece surface using a high-speed underwater cavitation jet in a water-filled tank. The impact pressure slightly deforms the material surface layer plastically by generating a restraining force between the lower layers and the surface and causes a peening (forming) effect that increases the pits' depth hardness near the surface and applies compressive residual stress.

Many studies have investigated micro forming using various forms of applications for plastic deformation of metal foil. In [9], a study was conducted on a metallic foil using a micro-energy ultraviolet pulse laser shock for micro-pattern transfer. The experimental results indicated that the depth of the micropattern increased with increasing single pulse energy and the ratio of overlap in a certain range. This revealed that the depth formed of aluminum foil printed on a #400 mold was greater than that in #1000 and more sensitive to the pulse energy and the rate of overlap. In [10], a novel laser shock technology was also used to study the deformation behavior of pure copper foil. The results showed that after each shock, the formed area increased, and, at the same time, the undeformed area decreased until it disappeared. The power density of the laser can be applied to improve the accuracy dimension, surface roughness, and micro-hardness of micro-parts. The impact of the base metal surface roughness and the spread behavior of the bag-8 was studied in [11], and the optimum surface roughness found in Rz was 0.92 [12]. In [13], the degradation of the micro-mold surface was investigated using laser dynamics in forming and its effects on the material. The experimental results showed the avoidance of growth, coalescence, and nucleation under repeated shock loading form surface degradation on micro-mold. Laser shock waves can be used for micro-coining to replicate features on the metal surface. In [14], laser shock hydraulic forming was proved to have a good matching influence and can prevent or even suppress copper foil springback, which is appropriate for forming features of the large-region array. In [15], the punch force behavior was investigated during the micro v-bending of the copper foil. The results indicated that the free-bending and the coin-bending stages were part of the punch force profile. The application of laser technology has been studied extensively and has become more mature and applied to many processes, such as laser welding, laser shock peening, and laser shock forming [16-17].

To the best of our knowledge, there are no reports of metal foil micro-forming using water jet cavitation shock. This paper introduces a new process technology called cavitation water jet shock micro-forming. This process has the advantages of being low-cost, having good processing flexibility, and dramatically

improving formability. The versatility and low cost of water-jet cavitation technology make it superior to conventional micro-forming such as laser micro-forming, which is more expensive, requires high-skill labor, etc. Additionally, as the interface between fabrication tools and the work components is liquid-to-solid, the manufacturing friction is reduced, negating the need for lubrication during the forming process. This study aims to demonstrate the feasibility of this process. Water jet cavitation shock micro-forming is based on high-pressure shocks as a source for the forming energy created through the collapse of cavitation bubbles. During this process, a high-speed jet of water is injected into a water-filled chamber, and cavitation occurs in the shear layer around the jet. This type of jet is called a cavitation shock water jet. During the process, cavitation bubbles are generated by injecting high-speed water through a nozzle into a chamber filled with water. The cavitation bubbles periodically flow out from the nozzle and spread over the surface of the material to be processed, using the cavitation bubbles generated in the jets as the driving force, and applying high-pressure shock generated by the collapse of the bubbles [18, 19]. In the process of acting on the surface of the material, high-pressure shock waves propagate into the interior of the metal foil.

This study investigated the cavitating water jet shock micro-forming technique to examine the processing parameters on the surface morphology of the formed part, the effect of incident pressure, impact time, and target on forming depth, and analyze the blanking phenomenon using 304 stainless steel foil.

II. FORMING MECHANISM AND ITS APPARATUS

As illustrated in Figure 1, the typical application of the water jet cavitation shock micro-forming system is mainly composed of a jet-generating device and a forming device. The incident pressure drives the flow of water at a high speed through the cavitation nozzle, aggregation occurs when there is a large number of cavitation nuclei, the low-pressure region inside and outside the cavitation nozzle develops, and finally, the high-velocity liquid flow forms cavitation bubble groups. Adjusting the standoff distance, when the cavitation bubble groups approach the surface of the sample, the environmental pressure around the cavitation bubble groups is suddenly increased due to the huge turbulent pressure pulsation causing the collapse of the cavitation bubble groups and releasing the high-pressure shocks (cavitation bubbles collapse loads) at the moment of collapse [20, 21]. These high-pressure shocks act on the surface of the material and propagate into its interior, while, due to the high concentration of energy [22-24], they are confined to a very small area, and when the peak value of the collapse pressure exceeds the Hugoniot Elastic Limit (HEL) of the material, the metal foil is yielded and plastically deformed. The peak stress of the shock wave decreases as the shock wave propagates deeper into the metal foil. The plastic deformation of the metal foil continues until the peak stress falls below the dynamic yield strength. Since the loading direction is downward and the metal foil is free at the bottom side, the metal foil will bend downward and fill the die.

The forming device is installed on the platform. The quality of the initial interface between the metal foil and the micro-die

is very crucial, so the two surfaces should be attached and bonded to each other. The forming device consists of a locking block, mask, seal ring, metal foils, and micro-die. At the initial stage, the foil was placed on the top of the die, completely covering its openings. The metallic foil flatness should be guaranteed during the process. Next, the mask is placed on the foil and the micro-die had the same axial hole at the center. Finally, the initial contact between the foil and the micro-die is very important, therefore, the two surfaces were firmly locked by a locking block to prevent material wrinkling. In addition, a seal ring was also applied between the foil and the mask to ensure effective sealing.

Fig. 1. (a) The formation system of water jets cavitation shock micro-forming and (b) forming device.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Material

This study used 304 stainless steel foils due to their technical and economic advantages, as they are widely used in a variety of industrial applications, especially in the manufacture of micro-device components. These steel foils have good processing properties, high durability, good thermal conductivity, high temperature, corrosion resistance, good workability, need little maintenance, are nonmagnetic, are easy to weld and shape, and are completely recyclable (100%). Tables I and II show the chemical composition and the mechanical properties of the 304 stainless steel, respectively. The 304 stainless steel foil samples having 100µm thickness were cut into 50×50mm square specimens. The square samples were cleaned from dirt with anhydrous alcohol and the residual liquid was wiped off the surface.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF 304 STAINLESS STEEL

Element	C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cr	Ni
Wt (%)	≤ 0.8	≤ 2.0	≤ 0.045	≤ 0.03	≤ 1.0	≤ 18.0	≤ 8.0

TABLE II. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 304 STAINLESS STEEL

Elastic modulus (GPa)	Poisson ratio	Yield strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Extension rate (%)
194	0.3	≥ 205	≥ 520	≤ 40

B. Experimental Setup

Figure 2(a) shows a schematic diagram of the experimental setup of the water jet cavitation shock micro-forming equipment used for the process. Tap water was stored for at least 24 hours before the experimental test in a large tank of 2.5×2×1.5m at a room temperature of 25±2°C. A transparent water tank with a square horizontal cross-sectional area of 500×500×900mm was used to carry out the experiments. For transparent flow purposes, the tank was made of acrylic resin. The nozzle used in this experiment was designed regarding the angular nozzle for producing the periodic behavior of the jets of cavitation as shown in Figure 2(b) [25]. The nozzle was fixed in water at room temperature. The pumped water was discharged at an incident pressure of 8-20MPa. The throat nozzle diameter was 1.5mm and the throat length L was 12mm with an expansion angle θ of 30°. The optimal nozzle size ratio was $d:L=1:8$ [26]. The distance between the sample workpiece was 120mm. Inside the test cell, the sample was placed perpendicularly to the cavitating jets. The axial distance S_L between the micro-die cavity and the jet axis was fixed at 10mm (the eccentricity S_L was 10mm). Pressure was attached to the nozzle through the inflow hole. A duration time of 120s was selected for this experiment with incident pressures of 8, 12, 16, and 20MPa.

According to (1), the cavitation number is a measure of the flow's resistance to cavitation and is roughly equal to the ratio of the incident (upstream) to downstream pressures.

$$\sigma = \frac{p_1}{p_2} \tag{1}$$

In this instance, p_1 denotes the incident pressure and p_2 denotes the downstream pressure. Incident pressure is one of the crucial factors in the process of water-jet cavitation shock micro-forming. The downstream pressure p_2 was maintained at 0.1MPa, while the incident pressure p_1 was set to 8, 12, 16, and 20MPa [19], resulting in cavitation numbers of 0.0125, 0.0083, 0.0063, and 0.005, respectively.

Fig. 2. (a) Experimental system of water jets cavitation shock micro-forming, (b) nozzle geometry diagram.

C. Forming Device

According to Figure 3, the forming tool includes a locking block, mask, seal ring, workpiece, and micro-die. The top of the die was covered with foil, totally enclosing the die apertures, assuring it was flat. The mask was then positioned on the foil with the identical axial hole in the center as the micro-die. The initial interface between the foil and the micro-die is

particularly important for preventing material wrinkling, hence, the two surfaces should be firmly linked to one another by a locking block. In addition, a seal ring was placed between the mask and the foil to provide an efficient seal.

Fig. 3. The forming device.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the surface morphology of the formed part, the influence of incident pressure on forming depth, the influence of impact time on forming depth, the effect of target distance on forming depth, and an analysis of the punching phenomenon.

A. Surface Morphology of Formed Part

In the process of metal foil micro-forming, a good forming effect can be obtained by selecting the appropriate process parameters [27]. A 304 stainless steel foil with a size of 50×50mm was selected for micro-forming experiments. Figure 4 shows the 304 stainless steel foil at incident pressure of 20MPa, target distance of 120mm, impact time of 2min, and eccentricity of 14mm. Figure 4(a) shows that the finished surface of the 304 stainless steel foil-formed parts was better than the surrounding unformed parts and had better outline shape and surface quality. In addition, it was observed that the edge of the formed part had no wrinkles, fractures, or other phenomena, indicating a better surface quality than the traditional micro-forming method [28].

Fig. 4. (a) Micro-formed sample, (b) 3D surface morphology of formed parts, and (c) section profile curve of formed parts.

Figure 4(b) shows that the 304 stainless steel foil obtained a good geometric shape during this forming process. The center area of the formed part has the darkest color, indicating that a

strong plastic deformation occurred during the process. Around it, the color gradually becomes lighter and the amount of deformation gradually decreases. Figure 4(c) shows the typical cross-sectional profile curve of the micro-formed part. Its cross-sectional shape is like a "spherical coronal cone" with a diameter of 1.2mm. In addition, the cross-sectional curve of the formed part had a smooth profile, without abrupt changes, and a good forming effect, which indicates that the material flows into the die uniformly during the forming process. The maximum forming depth of the formed part was 268.9μm.

B. Effect of Incident Pressure on Forming Depth

In the experiment of cavitation water jet shock metal foil micro-forming, the forming depth of the foil can be an evaluation index of its forming quality. The incident pressure is one of the key parameters of the cavitation water jet shock micro-forming experiment, so it is necessary to analyze its effect on the deformation of the foil. To make the test results comparable, the other process parameters were fixed and only incident pressure was adjusted to 8, 12, 16, and 20MPa. The target distance was 120mm, the impact time was also 2min, and the eccentricity was 14mm. The results showed that when the incident pressure was 8, 12, 16, and 20MPa, the corresponding average forming depths were 89.2, 145.9, 169.9, and 226.6μm, respectively. Figure 5 shows the variation in the forming depth. This indicates that the plastic deformation of the 304 stainless steel foil increased non-linearly with incident pressure [29]. The forming depth improved at a decreasing rate when the incident pressures increased from 8 to 16MPa and increased sharply when the incident pressures changed from 16 to 20MPa. This could be attributed to the following reasons:

- When the incident pressure is less than 16MPa, the cavitation bubbles mostly collapse before reaching the material surface under the standoff distance of 120mm, hence, the shock energy was relatively low and the improvement of the forming depth was not high. Although the cavitation bubbles have a larger size and collapse on the material surface, they produce greater shock energy which increases the forming depth sharply when the incident pressure increased to 20MPa.
- The dynamic yield limit of the material increases due to the residual stress and the hardened effect during the shock-forming process. Therefore, a stronger force is needed to produce continued deformation.

C. Effect of Target Distance on Forming Depth

Incident pressure was set to 20MPa, impact time was set to 2min, and eccentricity to 14mm and the influence of target distance (80, 100, 120, and 140mm) on the forming depth was studied. The depth was measured and its average value was calculated. Figure 6 shows the average depth curve of 304 stainless steel foil-formed parts at different target distances. Under an incident pressure of 20MPa, with increasing target distance, the average depth of the formed part increases first and then decreases. When the target distance was 120mm, the average depth of the formed part was the largest, reaching 226.6μm. This was mainly due to the increase in the target distance that increased the shockwave pressure acting on the workpiece surface. However, with an increasing target

distance, most of the cavitation bubbles collapse before reaching the surface of the workpiece, so the impact energy was relatively low as the depth increased.

Fig. 5. The maximum depth with different incident pressures.

Fig. 6. The average depth depending on different target distances.

D. Effect of Impact Time on Forming Depth

To investigate the influence of impact time on the forming depth of the 304 stainless steel foil, the incident pressure was 8, 12, 16, and 20 MPa, the target distance was 120mm, the eccentricity was fixed at 14mm, and the impact time was 40, 80, 120, and 160s, respectively. Figure 7 shows that under the same incident pressure (8 MPa), the average forming depth of the formed part increased nonlinearly with increasing impact time. With an incident pressure of 8MPa, when the impact time increased from 40 to 160s, the forming depth increased from 40.4µm to 116.1µm, which is almost three times the initial value. However, with increasing time, the growth rate of forming depth gradually decreased. When the incident pressure increased from 12 to 16MPa, the change in the average forming depth followed the same trend. In addition, when the incident pressure was 20MPa, forming depth increased from 91.8µm at 40s impact time to 252.7µm at 160s, which is also approximately a three-time increase. These results show that the incident pressure and the impact time directly determine the forming effect of the metal foil. In addition, it was found that in the subsequent impact process of the cavitation water jet, the

growth rate of the forming depth of the material gradually reduced. This can be attributed to the fact that as the entire forming device was placed in water, the forming depth also increased with increasing impact time. Furthermore, since it is difficult to achieve complete sealing, a small amount of tap water will flow into the pit, thereby gradually reducing the impact effect.

Fig. 7. The average forming depth depending on different impact times.

E. Analysis of the Blanking Phenomenon

In the micro-forming process of metal foil impact by cavitation water jet, the analysis of the causes of material failure and the mechanism behind it helps to understand the impact process conditions and improve the forming quality of the material. In high-speed impact, the material is damaged by crack initiation and propagation, but when cavitation collapses, shockwave and inertia act on the target and at the same time a variety of damages such as adiabatic shear instability, breakage, and spallation would also occur. When the target distance was 120mm, the eccentricity was 14mm, and the incident pressure exceeded a certain value, the foil had a severe shear effect and a cut-off at the edge of the die. Figure 8 shows the blanking effect of the 304 stainless steel foil under an incident pressure of 30MPa.

Fig. 8. The morphology of punched hole at the bottom: (a) Front, and (b) reverse side.

Figure 9 shows an SEM image of the back of the punched round hole under the corresponding conditions. When the incident pressure increased to 30MPa, the workpiece was

completely blanked. This is mainly because, under this incident pressure, the shockwave pressure generated by the collapse of the bubble deforms the workpiece beyond the limit stress of the material itself. At the edge of the cavity, the stress value was obtained, which completely exceeds the shear fracture limit of the cavity, leading to the fracture of the material and the complete blanking process.

Fig. 9. SEM for punched bottom circle: (a) Whole view, and (b) local magnification view.

V. CONCLUSION

This study conducted experiments using a cavitation water jet shock micro-forming on a 304 stainless steel foil. The single characteristic micro-forming experiments were carried out, and the impact micro-forming law of the cavitation water jet was analyzed and studied from the aspects of incident pressure, target distance, impact time, and the analysis of the blanking phenomenon. The results showed that the proposed method could obtain micro-formed parts with good surface quality and relatively uniform impact depth formed parts. The forming depth gradually increases with increasing incident pressure and impact time, however, it increases first and then decreases with increasing target distance. In addition, the analysis of the blanking phenomenon showed that when incident pressure continues to increase, there was a risk of cracking at the rounded corners of the micro-formed parts. When the pressure increased to 30MPa, a punch sample of the 304 stainless steel foil of 100µm thickness could be obtained.

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A Comparative Analysis of Seismic Site Response in Time and Frequency Domains

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ABSTRACT

This study aims primarily to perform a comparative analysis of the seismic response of a soil profile, in the time and frequency domains, in order to evaluate the seismic response of soil subjected to seismic excitation. After a few remarks made on the responses given by the linear elasticity method for this type of problem, it was considered necessary to use SHAKE 2000 and PLAXIS in this study. The obtained results were then compared with those of the available theoretical predictions. Rock elasticity, viscous damping and damping by hysteresis, and the nonlinearity of the ground were then taken into account. In addition, comparisons between recorded responses were also conducted.

Keywords-dynamic analysis; soil damping; finite elements; site response

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI) problems involve determining the reaction of a building under the seismic effect and defined by the free surface of ground without any structure [1]. Variations in free surface seismic responses, which are used as the input motion, must satisfy the so-called free-field motion equations which can be obtained from the ground response analysis [2-3]. Thus, according to the literature, before studying the soil-structure interaction system, a free field response is required. It should be known that the dynamic finite element analysis can be considered as one of the most comprehensive available tools in geotechnical problems [4]. It is an approach capable of providing insight into the distribution of stresses in soil or the deformations, and the loads applied to structural components that interact with the soil. But, this technique requires the availability of an appropriate soil model, with sufficient information on soil properties, provided by performing different experiments. Here, the seismic input motion ought to be appropriately determined. The response of a finite element model [5] is also conditioned by the adjustment of several parameters that affect the sources of energy dissipation in the time domain analysis. Furthermore, the amount of damping exhibited by a discrete numerical system can be determined by the proper choice of the constituent

model (material damping), the integration scheme of equations, and the boundary conditions (numerical damping). In addition, material damping models the viscous and hysteresis energy dissipation effects in soils. Note that the numerical damping appears as a consequence of the numerical algorithm for the dynamic equilibrium solution in the time domain [6]. Moreover, the boundary states can influence the numerical model and convey the specific energy of waves outside the time domain [7-8]. In this article, the free field surface is exclusively taken, and the responses provided for different domain analyses are interpreted and compared.

II. PROFILES OF THE SOIL UNDER STUDY

For the purposes of this study, it was considered necessary to examine different soil profiles that are characterized by an increasing level of heterogeneity. The soil includes a homogeneous viscoelastic layer (denoted HOM profile), a linear elastic layer with increasing stiffness at depth, and finally a non-linear soil layer (denoted SDS for Stress Dependent Stiffness profile) [9-10].

A. Homogeneous Viscoelastic Layer

The soil stiffness is displayed by a constant value of shear modulus G . In the present case, the homogeneous linear viscoelastic profile is placed on a rigid rock and is then

examined. The soil profile characteristics are shown in Figure 1(a). Such a system can be entirely presented through its amplification function $A(f)$. On the other hand, Figure 2 shows the graphical representation of the amplification function in relation to frequency, while admitting that the soil layer considered has the adopted characteristics. The two verticals refer to the first and second natural frequencies of the soil profile.

Fig. 1. Soil profiles: (a) Physical characterization, (b) shear wave propagation velocity of the profiles, (c) shear modulus of the soil.

Fig. 2. Amplification function of a homogeneous viscoelastic soil layer on a rigid rock.

B. Stress Dependent Stiffness Layer

Stiffness is a function of the average effective stress p' , and therefore of the depth. A linear relation describes the evolution of the shear modulus G as a function of depth z ($m = 1/2$):

$$G = G_0(1 + az)^{2m} = G_0(1 + az) \tag{1}$$

Afterwards, it was decided to adopt a single value for the density ρ . The velocity of shear wave propagation was then obtained by:

$$V_s = V_{s0}(1 + az)^m = V_{s0}(1 + az)^{1/2} \tag{2}$$

where V_{s0} is the shear wave velocity at the free surface, an a is a coefficient that represents the level of soil heterogeneity

C. Non-Linear layer

The average value curves for sand, similar to those proposed in [11], were then considered. Figure 3 shows the graphical representations of these curves. It is important to emphasize that the variation of the initial shear modulus according to depth is identical to that of the SDS profile.

Fig. 3. Curves representing the adopted shear modulus (solid line) and damping factor (broken line), calculated by Hashash's MRDF model.

III. THE INPUT SIGNAL

In numerical calculations, the seismic loading is often imposed as an accelerogram at the base of the geometrical model (the rock). In order to clarify and better understand the impact of the seismic signal on the nonlinear soil response, two acceleration histories were used [12]:

- The first signal corresponds to the W-E component of the acceleration recording that was made at the Tolmezzo station for the main shock of the Friuli earthquake in Italy that occurred on May 6, 1976. It is denoted as TMZ-270. The data were recorded at a frequency of 200Hz, for a whole of 7279 recording points. The peak of horizontal acceleration, even to 0.315g was obtained after $t = 3.935s$. It is worth noting that most energy is within a frequency range among 0.8 and 5 hertz.
- The second signal corresponds to the W-E component of the acceleration recording that was made at the Station of Kedarra 1 for the main shock of the earthquake that occurred on May 21, 2003, in Boumerdès (Algeria). The data were recorded at a frequency of 200Hz for a total of 7000 recording points. The maximum horizontal acceleration, equal to 0.331g, was reached after $t = 7.415 s$.

Fig. 4. TMZ-270 seismic input signal: (a) Acceleration history, (b) Fourier spectrum.

Fig. 5. Kedarra-1 seismic input signal: (a) Acceleration history, (b) Fourier spectrum.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With regard to the soil profile interaction with the acceleration history, different analyses were performed in order to show the influence of some numerical parameters. In the present case, the response found from the HOM and the SDS profiles are presented. The equivalent linear approach for the time domain analyses with the PLAXIS code was used [13-14]. The obtained responses were compared with those resulting from the frequency domain analysis, carried out with SHAKE [15]. Lastly, comparisons of various calculated soil responses supplied were reviewed and interpreted.

A. Linear Analysis of the HOM Linear Profile

Linear analysis was carried out in the frequency and time domain. The obtained results were compared with of the homogeneous elastic profile resting on a rigid rock in order to show the effect of the various origins of energy dissipation on the finite element model and to explain the choices made for a good numerical modeling process. The frequency-domain and time-domain responses of linear analyses carried out in SHAKE and PLAXIS, respectively, are illustrated in Figure 6 which depicts the amplification function and the maximum acceleration profiles.

Fig. 6. Comparison between the numerical and the reference solutions: (a) Amplification functions, (b) maximum acceleration profiles for TMZ-270 input motion.

B. Linear Analysis of the SDS Profile

Linear analysis was performed in the frequency domain for TMZ-270 and Keddara-1 motions in SHAKE software. The obtained responses were used as a basic response for the finite element analysis. The Rayleigh coefficients ($\alpha_R = 1.224$, $\beta_R = 2.441 \times 10$) were determined arbitrarily by selecting the first natural frequency f_1 of the layer, and the mean $(f_2 + f_3)/2$, of the 2nd and 3rd natural frequencies of the soil [16-17]. Numerical damping was assumed to be equal to zero. Figure 7 shows specific gaps observed on the amplification functions, around the third natural frequency of the layer. Nevertheless, it turned out that there was a good agreement between the maximum acceleration profiles, which proves the effectiveness of the adopted lateral boundary conditions.

C. Analysis using the Equivalent Linear Approach for the SDS Profile

To simulate the non-linearity of the ground under periodic stress, it was deemed necessary to use the most common method, which in this case is the equivalent linear approach.

This method was applied in the SHAKE software. The PLAXIS software does not allow equivalent linear analysis. In order to carry out an operation, the domain must be separated into sub-layers. A different material is indicated for each sub-layer. Consequently, the only eventual way out is to first perform equivalent linear analysis with the assistance of SHAKE including an auto-iterative procedure. The output profiles of $G(z)$ and $D(z)$, obtained from SHAKE, determine the PLAXIS material parameters. The initial shear modulus and damping constant profiles as well as those derived from the SHAKE analysis are plotted in Figure 8. The resulting curves represent the data profile for PLAXIS. Thus, the values accepted for the Rayleigh damping parameters are clearly reported.

Fig. 7. Comparison between the linear analyses in the frequency domain and time domain of the SDS profile: (a) Amplification functions, (b) maximum acceleration profiles of TMZ-270 seismic motion, (c) maximum acceleration profiles of Keddara-1 seismic motion.

Fig. 8. Profiles of the soil parameters adopted by the equivalent linear approach: (a) Shear modulus, (b) damping, (c), (d) Rayleigh parameters.

Figure 9 presents the responses achieved from the numerical tests of the equivalent linear approach when using the time investigation scheme. In addition, the average constant acceleration and the Rayleigh parameters of each sub-layer were evaluated. The 1st and 2nd natural frequencies of the subsoil, as indicated in Table I, are considered as the reference frequencies. It should also be noted that the calibration of the analysis parameters in the time domain are based on the results of the frequency domain. Note also that the two types of equivalent linear approaches provide the same seismic excitation, particularly with regard to maximum accelerations.

TABLE I. REFERENCE FREQUENCIES FOR THE EVALUATION OF RAYLEIGH NUMERICAL DAMPING - SDS SOIL LAYER

Abbreviation	Type of analysis	f_1 (Hz)	f_2 (Hz)
Lin	Linear	6,48	15,15
Lin Equi	Linear equivalent	4,72	16,99

The maximum values of the amplification function determined with finite element software are near to those obtained with the SHAKE, particularly close to the reference frequencies. These responses show that, as indicated, the soil parameters determined for each sub-layer are in accordance with the deformation rate generated by the seismic movement.

Fig.9. Comparison between the peak acceleration profiles obtained by equivalent linear analysis in the frequency and time domain of the SDS profile using (a) TMZ-270, (b) Keddara-1 seismic motions.

D. Nonlinear Analysis of the SDS Profile

It is recognized that the equivalent linear approach ensures satisfactory results, particularly for the site seismic effect, although this approach is an estimate of real nonlinear treatments. A new approach consists of analyzing the results of a real nonlinear profile, based on numerical integration in the time domain. DEEPSOIL [18] solves 1D problems related to wave propagation in a nonlinear medium. Estimates were computed in the time domain, and the constitutive modeling was implemented according to the modified hyperbolic modeling. Note that this software was used first to deal with the problem of vertically propagating S-waves in the non-linear SDS profile on a hard rock, and then to make a comparison of the obtained responses with those resulting from the equivalent linear model [19-21].

Figure 10 presents the peak acceleration profiles and response spectra that were computed by SHAKE and DEEPSOIL, by suggesting the shear modulus and damping constant curves shown in Figure 3 for hard rock.

Fig. 10. Comparison between the maximum acceleration profiles obtained by the equivalent linear analyses (SHAKE) and by the non-linear analysis (DEEPSOIL) of the SDS profile, using: (a) TMZ-270, (b) Keddara-1 seismic motions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study showed that one-dimensional nonlinear soil response analysis provides a more accurate characterization of true nonlinear soil behavior in comparison with the equivalent linear procedures. However, the use of nonlinear software remains limited, resulting in insufficiently documented and imprecise choice of code application parameters and official procedures of used software.

In the current study, linear responses were employed in the frequency domain for the evaluation of energy dissipation sources in association with dynamic finite elements analysis. The calculations carried out using the PLAXIS indicated that the adopted numerical model was rightly chosen. Both were applied for the evaluation with Rayleigh damping parameters, while considering numerical dissipation for the time integration scheme, and also for lateral boundary conditions, to minimize the impact due to wave reflection. The obtained results are quite encouraging for using such methods whenever finite element seismic analyses are carried out in various types of geotechnical systems, i.e. retaining walls, tunnels, etc.

In finite element software, such as the PLAXIS, the filtering input for transforming the input motion from the rock outcrop to the interior is not taken into account. Besides, the input seismic motion can be simply converted to the outcrop interior with the help of other software (like the SHAKE) and by submitting the filtered signal to the base of the soil profile, in order to simulate an elastic rock using the finite element model.

Finally, the non-linear behavior of the soil was also examined. The numerical parameters of a two-dimensional soil profile using the finite element method developed in PLAXIS should be calibrated first using the equivalent linear approach applied in SHAKE. Then, the non-linear approach, in DEEPSOIL, followed. The obtained responses were compared with those obtained by the equivalent linear approach. The maximum acceleration values at the surface of the equivalent linear analysis remain higher than those resulting from the non-linear analysis. This can be attributed to the greater amplification of the soil motion by frequencies near the first frequencies of the seismic excitations used.

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Numerical Investigation of the Axially Compressive Behavior of Circular Concrete Encased Steel Composite (CESC) Columns

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ABSTRACT

This research presents a numerical investigation of circular Concrete Encased Steel Composite (CESC) columns. To simulate the circular CESC columns under axial compression in the previous tests, a Finite Element Model (FEM) with some modifications of material models for the steel and concrete was established in ABAQUS software. The curves of load versus longitudinal displacement and the ultimate loads obtained from the FEM were compared with those measured in previous tests. The numerical results agreed well with the test results. Furthermore, the distribution of the stresses on the cross-section at different heights and the effect of initial imperfections were observed by the FEM results. A highly confined concrete zone enclosed by steel web and steel flanges was observed. Finally, the established FEM was used in the parametric study that investigated the influence of concrete strength, steel yield strength, and spacing of the spiral hoops.

Keywords-composite columns; FEM; CES; ABAQUS; concrete; steel

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete Encased Steel Composite (CESC) columns are being widely applied in heavy-loading structures such as in top-down construction methods, high-rise buildings, or support structures [1, 3-4, 24-28]. The utilization of circular CESC columns in construction was found to be necessary due to their ability to support higher loads than the rectangular or square CESC columns and their aesthetical appearance. A steel section is constructed inside the reinforced concrete to form a CESC column, thereby fully exploiting the advantages of steel and concrete materials [1, 24-26]. Ductility and seismic resistance can be greatly enhanced by the use of a steel section, while the concrete works as a protective layer for the steel section against buckling, fire, and aggressive environments [1-2, 8, 19, 28-30]. For these reasons, several attempts have been made to test the structural behavior of CESC columns [1-5, 8, 13-14, 24, 27, 29-30].

The testing equipment for CESC columns requires very high capacity and complexity, thus restricting the range of parameters. Therefore, many efforts have been undertaken to simulate the behavior of CESC columns through Finite Element Models (FEMs). Authors in [4] presented a FEM to analyze the pin-ended axially loaded square CESC short and long columns using various concrete strengths (20-110MPa) and various steel yield strengths (275-690MPa). Authors in [11] introduced a new simplified technique of FEM

incorporating the confinement effect of square CESC columns to construct strength interaction diagrams. Authors in [7] constructed FEMs to compare the difference between square CESC columns and reinforced concrete columns with different concrete strengths. Authors in [15] constructed a FEM to study the buckling resistance of CESC columns using concrete strength up to 100MPa. Authors in [9] conducted simulations to address the impact of concrete strength, steel strength, and column slenderness on the performance of square CESC columns. Authors in [10] simulated a square CESC long column with 3.6m length and a steel column made of welded H-profile with the same length under axial compression and uniaxial bending to compare the difference between CESC and pure steel columns. Authors in [12] constructed a FEM of square CESC columns using Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) to verify the test results and the effect of tensile strength of FRC.

The literature review revealed that the majority of existing numerical investigations of the behavior of CESC columns were concerned with square sections, while the studies on CESC columns with circular sections are extremely limited. As compared to square or rectangular sections with the same dimensions, the use of circular sections results in some beneficial characteristics for CESC columns such as higher confining stress induced by steel profile and transverse reinforcements, higher strength and ductility, and better

architectural performance [5, 7, 18, 20]. Only two test results of circular CESC columns were reported in [7]. For this reason, there is a need for the study of circular CESC columns, in general, and FEM studies for circular CESC columns, in particular. To fulfill this gap, this paper presents a FEM to simulate the circular CESC short columns. Firstly, the FEM was established in ABAQUS software with some modifications to material models. After this, the accuracy of the FEM was checked by comparing it with the test results of [7]. The distribution of stresses on the cross-section at different heights was also plotted. Finally, the effect of the concrete strength, steel yield strength, and spacing of spiral hoops on the load versus displacement response of circular CESC short columns was determined by conducting a parametric study.

II. DESCRIPTION OF FEM

A. Configuration of Test Specimens

Test specimens reported in [7] were used for the simulation. Two circular CESC short columns using an I cross-shaped steel section were constructed for testing under concentric loading. Table I shows the geometry and the dimensions of the columns and Table II demonstrates the properties of the materials used for the test specimens.

TABLE I. DIMENSIONS OF TEST SPECIMENS

Specimens	Diameter (mm)	Height (mm)	Steel section
HSRC-SP1	411	1233	2H206×120×12×12
HSRC-SP2	411	1233	2H206×120×12×12

Specimens	Longitudinal reinforcement	Spiral hoop	Spacing of spiral hoop (mm)	Ultimate load (kN)
HSRC-SP1	20d10	d10	50	11363
HSRC-SP2	20d10	d10	50	10890

TABLE II. MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF TEST SPECIMENS

Specimens	Concrete strength f_c (MPa)	Yield strength of steel section f_y (MPa)	Yield strength of longitudinal reinforcement $f_{y,r}$ (MPa)	Yield strength of spiral hoop $f_{h,h}$ (MPa)
HSRC-SP1	37	517	426	426
HSRC-SP2	37	517	426	426

B. Mesh and Finite Elements

The circular CESC columns consisted of concrete, steel section, longitudinal reinforcements, and spiral hoops. The solid element C3D8R (8-node brick element) was selected for simulating the concrete and the embedded steel profile. The truss element T3D2 (2-node) was selected to simulate the embedded longitudinal reinforcements, while the B31 beam element was adopted for modeling the spiral hoops. After the performance of different mesh sizes, a reasonable aspect ratio of solid element size of 1:3 was assumed. A coefficient of friction of 0.25 [4] was chosen in the "surface-to-surface contact" to simulate the interface of the concrete and the steel profile. It should be noted that this friction coefficient is adopted by numerous studies. Master and slave surfaces were assigned to the concrete and the encased steel section, respectively. Figure 1 shows the finite element mesh and type.

Fig. 1. Finite element mesh and type

C. Boundary Conditions and Loading Application

Two loading plates were simulated at both ends of the column and tied to the end surface of the concrete and steel section to ensure a uniform load transfer to the whole section of the column. Two reference points (RP1 and RP2) were located in the middle of the upper and lower loading plates, respectively. A rigid body constraint was assigned between the reference point and the surface of the loading plate for easier loading application. All degrees of freedom of loading plates were fixed, while the axial displacement of the upper loading plate was set free to permit the axial movement. The numerical analysis in ABAQUS [21] was carried out using displacement control. An implicit procedure with the Newton-Raphson method [21] was adopted for the analysis. Figure 2 demonstrates the modeling of boundary conditions, the interaction between structural steels and concrete, and the loading application.

Fig. 2. Boundary condition and loading application.

The buckling mode was determined by eigenvalue buckling analysis of the simulated columns. The eigenmode 1 as the first buckling mode was adopted to incorporate the geometric initial imperfection for nonlinear inelastic analysis of the composite column. The value of the initial imperfection for each column was selected as $L/500$ and $L/1000$, in which L is defined as the column length.

D. Material Models

The behavior of structural steels (steel section, longitudinal reinforcement, and spiral hoop) was simulated using the stress-strain model [22] as seen in Figure 3. The value of Poisson’s ratio was set as 0.3 for steel. In Figure 3, f_y represents the yield stress and ϵ_y denotes the strain at f_y . The modulus E_l was taken as $0.01E_y$, while the modulus of elasticity E_y of the first elastic stage was set as 200GPa.

Fig. 3. Stress-strain model for structural steels.

The nonlinearity of the concrete was simulated using the Concrete Damage Plasticity Model (CDPM). Some parameters of CDPM employed to model the triaxial stress state of the concrete are:

- Angle of dilation $\varphi=30^\circ$.
- Eccentricity $\epsilon=0.1$.
- Ratio of $f_{bo}/f_c=1.16$, where f_{bo} is the biaxial compressive yield stress.
- Ratio of the second stress invariant on the tensile meridian for the yield function $K=0.667$.

Furthermore, the viscosity parameter $\mu=0.0001$ was used to ensure the convergence. The CEB model [23] was adopted to estimate the curve of stress versus strain ($\sigma_c-\epsilon$) of the concrete. The CEB model [23] is applicable to various concrete strengths (10-100MPa). The ($\sigma_c-\epsilon$) curves can be drawn using the equations of the CEB model [23]:

$$\sigma_c = f_c \left[\frac{\left(\frac{E_{it}}{E_0}\right) \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0}\right) - \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{E_{it}}{E_0} - 2\right) \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0}\right)} \right] \quad \text{For } \epsilon \leq \epsilon_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_0 = 0.7(f_c)^{0.31} \times 10^{-3} \quad (2)$$

$$E_{it} = 22000(f_c/10)^{0.3} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_c = \frac{f_c}{1 + \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0} - 1\right)^2} \quad \text{for } \epsilon > \epsilon_0 \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = (\epsilon_0 + 0.001)/\epsilon_0 \quad (5)$$

where ϵ_0 is the longitudinal strain at f_c , E_0 is defined as the secant modulus at f_c , and E_{it} is the tangent modulus.

The curve of stress versus plastic strain of concrete ($f_c = 37\text{MPa}$) for the test specimens in [7] used as input in ABAQUS is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Stress – plastic strain relation of concrete.

III. FEM VALIDATION

The load versus displacement ($L-D$) curve and the ultimate load obtained from FEM were compared with those measured in the tests conducted in [7] to evaluate the suitability of the FEM. Figure 5 shows the $L-D$ curves of the FEM and the test results of [7]. It can be seen that the $L-D$ curves from the FEM matched well with the test results. Furthermore, the FEM $L-D$ curves of FEM with and without imperfections were plotted. Figure 5 shows that there is no significant change in the $L-D$ curves with and without initial imperfections in FEM. The ultimate loads measured in the tests (N_{Test}) and FEM (N_{FEM1} and N_{FEM2}) are compared in Table III. It is evident that the ultimate loads of FEM are close to those obtained from the tests in [7] with FEM underestimating the ultimate loads with a difference ranging from 5% to 9%.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the $L-D$ curves between FEM and the experimental results from [7].

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF THE ULTIMATE LOADS BETWEEN FEM AND THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Specimens	N_{Test} (kN)	N_{FEM1} (kN) (with imperfection)	N_{FEM2} (kN) (without imperfections)	N_{FEM1}/N_{Test}	N_{FEM2}/N_{Test}
HSRC-SP1	11363	10406	10393	0.92	0.91
HSRC-SP2	10890	10406	10393	0.96	0.95

Based on the FEM results, the stress state of the concrete of circular CESC columns in [7] is demonstrated in Figure 6. It can be observed from the stress in the 3-3 direction of the concrete that the I cross-shaped steel section provides a good confinement effect to the concrete. The stress concentration of the concrete inside the steel section is maximal at both ends and decreases to the middle of the column. A highly confined concrete zone is observed as seen in Figure 6. This zone is enclosed by steel web and flanges. This result is in line with the FEM result reported in [8].

Fig. 6. Stresses in the concrete and the confined concrete zone.

IV. PARAMETRIC STUDY

The verified FEM was adopted for the parametric study to determine the effect of f_c , f_y , and s on the $L-D$ curves of circular CESC short columns. All columns for the parametric study have the same diameter of 270mm and the same height of 800mm ($L/D = 2.96$). A steel section of 70×140×10×12 was chosen for the I-cross shape. The grade of the steel section is S355. The diameter of longitudinal reinforcement is d13 with a S500 grade. The diameter of spiral hoops is d10 with a S500 grade. Various concrete strengths (30, 100, 150MPa) and steel yield strengths (350, 550, and 650MPa) were modeled. The spacing of spiral hoops was taken as 30, 60, and 90mm. Eight longitudinal reinforcements were constructed for the columns. Figure 7 describes the circular CESC columns for the parametric study.

Fig. 7. The circular CESC columns for the parametric study.

Fig. 8. Results of the parametric study using the verified FEM.

The results of the parametric study are illustrated in Figure 8. As expected, higher values of f_c and f_y result in higher composite column strength. When increasing f_c from 30 to 100MPa and from 30 to 150MPa, the loading capacity of the column was improved by about 76% and 123%, respectively.

The descending stage of the $L-D$ curves of the columns using higher values of f_c was steeper than that when using lower values of f_c . When increasing f_y from 350 to 550MPa and from 350 to 650MPa, the strength enhancement of the CESC columns was about 13% and 19.7%, respectively. Unlike the effect of f_c , there was no significant improvement in the ductility of the columns with increasing yield strength f_y . Similar to the effect of f_y , smaller spacing of spiral hoops leads to higher column strength. Increasing the spacing of spiral hoops from 30 to 60mm and from 30 to 90mm decreased the column strength by about 4.7% and 7.8%, respectively. The quantitative value of strength improvement with increasing concrete strength f_c was higher than that with increasing f_y or decreasing s . There is no significant difference in the slope of the descending stage of the $L-D$ curve with changes in f_y and s .

V. CONCLUSIONS

Deriving from the numerical results and analysis, the following conclusions can be indicated:

- The FEM results agreed well with the test results in [7]. Therefore the established FEM is reliably adopted to analyze the compressive behavior of circular CESC stub columns.
- Distribution of the stresses on the cross-section at different column heights was observed in the FEM results. A highly confined concrete zone can be observed in FEM. This zone is enclosed by steel web and steel flanges.
- Increased concrete strength, steel yield strength and decreasing spacing of spiral hoops, improve column strength.
- The shape of the descending branch in the $L-D$ curves and the strength enhancement are significantly affected by the changes in concrete strength.

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Improvement of Classification Accuracy of Four-Class Voluntary-Imagery fNIRS Signals using Convolutional Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

Multiclass functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS) signal classification has become a convenient way for optical brain-computer interface. fNIRS signal classification with high accuracy is a challenging assignment while the signals are produced by means of voluntary and imagery movements of the same limb. Since the activation in time and space of voluntary and imagery movement show a similar pattern, the classification accuracy by the conventional shallow classifiers cannot reach an acceptable range. This paper proposes an accuracy improvement approach with the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). In this work, voluntary and imagery hand movements (left hand and right hand) were performed by several participants. These four-class signals were acquired utilizing fNIRS devices. The signals were separated based on the tasks and filtered. With manual feature extraction, the signals were classified by support vector machine and linear discriminant analysis. The automatic feature extraction and classification mechanism of the CNN were applied to the fNIRS signals. From the results, it was found that CNN improves the classification accuracy to an acceptable range, which has not been achieved by any convolutional network.

Keywords-fNIRS; voluntary and imagery fNIRS signal; classification accuracy; conventional classifiers; Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

I. INTRODUCTION

Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) is a remarkable notion of current neuro-computational research that offers the scope to

control the computer with brain commands. Research and development regarding BCI can strongly contribute to neuro-prosthetics applications [1-2]. A brain-controlled computer needs to read the brain functionalities properly. The brain

functionalities can be assessed by both invasive and non-invasive procedures with non-invasive procedures being the primary choice of modern BCI [3]. Electroencephalography (EEG) and magneto-encephalography (MEG) are well-known noninvasive methods based on electric impulsive signals of the brain. Due to some questionable features like noise sensitivity, poor spatial resolution, and motion sensitivity, these modalities should be replaced by some newer ones [4-5].

To meet the challenge of overcoming the previous limitations, functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS) is a widely used noninvasive optical modality that can measure functional neuro-activations based on the hemodynamics of the brain tissue [6-7]. Although this modality is comparatively slower than the EEG and MEG regarding the brain response, due to very high spatial resolution and robust activation level, fNIRS gets significant importance in BCI research and applications [8-10]. For BCI the brain is to be stimulated externally or internally, with procedures termed as stimuli. Most of the stimuli are provided to the brain in BCI research by imagery or voluntary motor actions [11]. These movement-related functions of the brain correlate with the motor cortex which is located in the frontal lobe of the brain. There are several research works related to movement-related (either voluntary or imagery) hemodynamics classifications for BCI applications.

The activation patterns of the voluntary and imagery movement-based stimuli are widely examined in [12-15]. These studies suggested that several areas in the motor cortex and some prefrontal cortex become active due to movement execution and imagination. Voluntary and imagery movement-related tasks were not classified by machine learning algorithms. In [16], the two-class problems of imagery left and right-hand wrists movement were classified with the Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) method. Three classes of BCI were studied in [17], with two classes being motor imagery tasks. Voluntary movement-related tasks of the left and right hand were classified in [18] from the fNIRS signals of optimally selected channels. Multiple motor imagery tasks (movements of the left hand, right hand, left foot, and right foot) were classified in [19]. In these works, authors classified either the voluntary or imagery movement-related fNIRS signals. To the best of our knowledge, no work classified fNIRS signals regarding both voluntary and imagery movement stimuli. This is a challenge for the researchers to find the voluntary and imagery movement related fNIRS signal, simultaneously, because the activation area of the voluntary and imagery movement by an organ is the same in the brain [13] and their activation strengths are alike. This is a challenge for signal classification at high classification accuracy that was considered to be solved in this work.

In this work, both voluntary and imagery movement fNIRS signals were classified separately utilizing Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Support Vector Machines (SVM). We found satisfactory results for two class voluntary and two class motor imagery fNIRS signals. Additionally, we made it a four-class problem adding the voluntary and imagery fNIRS signals together and thereafter we classified the signal utilizing the same procedure applied with LDA and SVM. In this approach,

the classification accuracy was only 55-65%. This is a great barrier to implementing neuro-rehabilitate prosthetics where several events occur and the classification must be accurate and precise. To improve the classification accuracy for such a problem, we deployed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) which has an automatic feature extraction capability. Since the fNIRS signals are of multiple channels, the time series data of the change in the concentration of oxidized hemoglobin (HbO₂) and deoxidized hemoglobin (dHb) are used to prepare two-dimensional data. These data were used to prepare topographic images of the hemodynamic activations and are fed to the proposed CNN structure. Our proposed CNN method can classify the 4-class fNIRS signal with 86.14% (on average) accuracy which is a significant improvement. Therefore, the contribution of this research work can be summarized as:

- Developing a shallow deep neural network to classify multiple class fNIRS signals with high accuracy.
- Proposing a method for effective BCI for same limb voluntary-imagery fNIRS signal classification in subject dependent and independent approach.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this research is available in [20], and was collected with permission from the authors. According to the description given in [20], the participants were healthy. In their experiment, four types of tasks were performed by the subjects: left hand (LH) movement, right-hand (RH) movement, imagery left-hand (iLH) movement, and imagery right-hand (iRH) movement. Therefore, the subjects performed two voluntaries and two imagery hand movement tasks in different sessions. In each trial, a subject performed a 10-second task of two different movements with 20 seconds of rest after each task. At first, 20 seconds passed at the resting condition to correct the baseline values of the data. A 10-second task followed. This task might be LH or iLH. This was followed by another 20-second resting period, which was followed by another 10 second task which was either RH or iRH. This trial was repeatedly performed. Each subject performed 5 trials in each session. As a whole, sixteen (16) sessions (8 voluntary and 8 imagery) were performed by every participant in a total of 40 trials of each task. Eventually, 40 trials of 4-class data were acquired from every subject. The fNIRS data were acquired using fNIR devices [21], which have 4 NIR sources and 10 detectors. The optode of this device covers 16 channels. The device provides a measure of continuous real-time concentration change in the values for HbO₂ and Hb. The Cognitive Optical Brain Imaging (COBI) studio software was used to log the fNIRS data in computer memory [22].

B. Methods

In this section, all the data processing steps from signal acquisition to event classification for the performance test are explained. After designing the data acquisition protocol, data from prefrontal hemodynamics were collected. Then, in order to reduce dimensions, data compression using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) was applied. After that, the

baseline of fNIRS data was corrected. As a part of the pre-processing, these data were filtered. Then the data were separated into some sequential events and some prominent features were extracted. Using these features, classification accuracy was calculated. The main steps of the proposed data processing methods for the fNIRS data classification are presented briefly in Figure 1. The Figure is mainly focused on the conventional data classification technique. The steps are also described concisely with technical details in this subsection. Feature extraction and classification procedure by CNN are also discussed in order to clarify how this proposed method customized the CNN structure for achieving the objectives of the proposed method.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the total signal processing steps to create a machine learning-based predictive model and the accuracy of the testing data.

1) Data Compression

Since the data were acquired with 16 channels, the processing could face the issue of high dimensionality. To check the actual dimensions, the data were transformed by PCA and it was found that the actual dimension of the data was 4 instead of 16. The result of PCA is shown in Figure 2 with a similar channel number of ilk dimension. The resulting 4 dimensions are termed as Left Lateral (LL: channel 1, 2, 3, 4), Left Medial (LM: channel 5, 6, 7, 8), Right Medial (RM: channel 9, 10, 11, 12), and Right Lateral (RL: 13, 14, 15, 16). The signals having the same dimension were averaged. Therefore, the 16-channel configuration becomes compressed from $i \times 16$ to $i \times 4$. This compression helps reduce the feature dimension, which is very important for achieving high classification accuracy in the machine learning approach.

2) Filtering and Baseline Correction

Since fNIRS electrodes collect data from the human body, the signal is full of artifacts and noises. So, removing different types of noises is the first step of data processing. The fNIRS data can be affected by three types of noise [23]. These are motion artifacts, physiological signals, such as heart rate and respiration, and instrument and environment-related noises. Motion artifacts occur due to head movement and it results in fNIRS detectors shifting and losing contact with the skin exposing them to ambient light or light emitted directly from the fNIRS source. These types of motion artifacts can be easily recognized because they cause sudden, large spikes in the raw fNIRS data. Rapid head movements can cause the blood to move toward or away from the area that is being monitored,

rapidly increasing or decreasing blood volume. As the dynamics of this type of motion artifacts are slower than LED pop, they can be confused with the actual hemodynamic response due to brain activation. Physiological signals such as heart rate (over 0.5Hz) and respiration (over 0.2Hz) are at higher frequency ranges than hemodynamic responses, thus they should also be eliminated. So the raw fNIRS signals were filtered by a Savitzky-Golay filter of the 3rd order with 21 frame length (equivalent to 0.1Hz cut-off FIR low pass filter in 2Hz fNIRS signal) [10]. The raw noisy and filtered data of fNIRS are shown in Figure 3. Then, the data were separated in each trial. Every trial of the fNIRS data was corrected by subtracting the baseline from the original signal. The baseline was calculated by averaging the data of the first task.

Fig. 2. Principle component 1 vs. component 2 presents the actual signal dimensions in eigenspace.

Fig. 3. The raw fNIRS signal with physiological artifacts and the filtered signal after the Savitzky-Golay filtering technique.

3) Feature Extraction

When the input data are too large to be processed and are suspected to be redundant, then they can be transformed into a reduced set of features. Analyzing a large number of input variables requires a large amount of memory and computation power. It also over-fits the classification algorithms. The selected features are expected to contain the relevant information from the input data so that the desired task can be performed by using this reduced representation instead of the

complete initial data. In this study, mean, slope, standard deviation, and skewness were extracted as the dominant features. Since the fNIRS signal does not exhibit complexity like EEG, MEG, or fMRI, simple time domain features are enough to represent the signal characteristics [23]. In this experiment, we have worked with the above features. Before training the machine learning-based network, all the values of the training features were normalized between 0 and 1.

$$\pi' = \frac{\pi - \pi_{\min}}{\pi_{\max} - \pi_{\min}} \quad (1)$$

where π' are the feature values that are rescaled between 0 and 1. On the other hand, $\pi \in R^n$ are the actual values of the features. The maximum and minimum values of the features are presented as π_{\max} and π_{\min} respectively.

4) Classification Methods

Classification is the process of predicting the class of given data points. Classes are sometimes called targets. Classification predictive modeling is an important task of approximating a mapping function from input variables to discrete output variables. A training process continues until the model achieves the desired level of accuracy on the training data for the SVM- and LDA-based predictive models. Since the machine learning models (SVM and LDA) gave lower accuracy in multiclass (4-class classification) problems, CNN (a deep neural network) is applied.

C. Deep Neural Network-based Classification

A deep neural network needs no extracted features because it extracts features from its own. A CNN is one of the best formats of deep neural networks. In this work, CNN is utilized for fNIRS data classification. Since the feature extraction and classification process are included in the CNN structure, it is very important to prepare the input layer and output layer of CNN. The fNIRS data preparation to run the CNN and the structure of the proposed CNN layers are described briefly below.

1) Input Preparation

CNN is applied when the inputs are images or a two-dimensional matrix. When the computer sees an image, it will see an array of pixel values depending on the dimension of images. The image dimension is 32×32 . So it will see an array of $32 \times 32 \times 3$ numbers for RGB values and $32 \times 32 \times 1$ for grayscale images. Each of these numbers is given a value from 0 to 255 that describes the pixel intensity at that point. CNN consists of convolutional, nonlinear, pooling, and fully connected layers. In convolutional layers, a convolutional filter whose width is equal to the dimension of the input and kernel size is convolved with the input data. To build the feature map, the output of the convolutional layer is converted by an activation function similar to ANNs'. After each convolutional layer, additional subsampling operations such as max-pooling and softmax are performed to enhance the performance [24-25]. As with ANNs, hyper-parameters such as learning rate, batch size, and the number of epochs should be investigated for the CNN to improve its classification performance.

2) Structure of the CNN Layers

In this research, at first any two events: motor imagery hand movement or motor execution hand movements were classified by two shallow neural networks (SVM and LDA), with satisfactory accuracy. But when the 4-event classification was performed, the accuracy became very low, which means shallow neural networks like SVM and LDA cannot be utilized for more than 2-class events. To improve this result, the CNN algorithm is proposed. A general structure of a CNN is given in Figure 4 including its main layers.

Fig. 4. Layers (convolutional, ReLU, pooling, and fully connected) of a CNN.

Deep learning is a class of machine learning algorithms that uses a cascade of multiple layers of nonlinear processing units for feature extraction and transformation. A CNN is highly capable of automatically learning appropriate features from the input data by optimizing the weight parameters of each filter, using forward and backward propagation to minimize classification errors.

a) Convolution Layer

The convolution layer is the first layer to extract features from an input image (as given in Figure 4). Convolution preserves the relationship between pixels by learning the image features using small squares of input data. It is a mathematical operation that takes two inputs, the image matrix and a filter or kernel. Consider the dimension of an image matrix is $h \times w \times d$ and the filter's is $f_h \times f_w \times d$. So, the output of the matrix dimension is $(h - f_h + 1) \times (w - f_w + 1) \times 1$.

A very important note is that the depth of the filter should be the same as the depth of the input image. So for a $5 \times 5 \times 3$ image, the dimension of the filter is $5 \times 5 \times 3$. Starting from the first position of the input image, the filter is sliding or convolving around the input image, it is multiplying the values in the filter with the original pixel values of the original image. The method used in this work to prepare the input images from the data (HbO_2 and Hb) is illustrated in Figure 5. The way convolutional filters worked on the images is shown in Figure 6. This multiplication is all summed up and a single number will be found. It should be remembered that this single number is only for when the filter is on the starting corner of the input image. This process is repeatedly performed for every location of the image.

Fig. 5. The input data consisting of the concentration changes of HbO₂ (red) and Hb (blue) overall channels. A convolutional filter runs through the input data along the vertical axis.

b) ReLU Layer

ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) layer induces nonlinearity in the values of the incoming layer. The ReLU function only passes the values x which are greater than zero:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Other functions are also used to increase nonlinearity, for example $f(x) = \tanh(x)$, $f(x) = |\tanh(x)|$, and the sigmoid function $f(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^x}$. ReLU is often preferred to other functions because it trains the neural network several times faster without a significant penalty to generalization accuracy.

c) Pooling Layer

This layer reduces the number of parameters if the images are too large. Spatial pooling is also called downsampling and reduces the dimensionality of each map, but retains the important information. Spatial pooling can be of different types: Max pooling, average pooling, and sum pooling. In this work, the max pooling layer is used.

d) Fully Connected Layer

This layer takes the output of the convolution, ReLU, and pooling layers as input. With the fully connected layers, we combine these features to create a model. Finally, we have an activation function such as softmax or sigmoid to classify the outputs.

e) Cross Validation

k -fold cross-validation is used to estimate the classification performance of the predictive model. The first step in this process is to divide the data into k folds, where each fold contains an identical amount of input data. One fold is used as a test dataset, while the remaining folds are used as training sets. Afterward, a classification procedure is applied to the

selected test and training sets. This process is performed for each of the k folds. In this study, 5-fold cross-validation was performed. The parameters of different layers and the structure of the proposed CNN are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. CNN LAYER PARAMETERS

Parameters	Value
Matrix input layer	384×384
Convolution layer 1	2, 8
Max-pooling layer 1	2 (pool size)
Convolution layer 2	4, 16
Max-pooling layer 2	2 (pool size)
Fully connected layer	4
Learning rate	0.01
Epoch	15
Validation frequency	3

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The activation due to imagery movement planning occurs in the prefrontal cortex which can be measured by the increased concentration of HbO₂. For the left-hand and right-hand imagery movement planning, the activation level is found to be increased in the concentration of HbO₂ in the right hemisphere and left hemisphere, respectively. Since 4 different portions are selected to observe the actual concentration change in HbO₂ of LH and RH movement planning. The variation of HbO₂ concentration in the LL, LM, RM, and RL portions of the prefrontal cortex due to planning movements of LH and RH of a randomly selected subject is presented in Figures 6 and 7.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the concentration changes in HbO₂ between LH and RH movement planning in (a) LL and (b) LM portion of the prefrontal cortex.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the concentration changes in HbO₂ between LH and RH movement planning in (a) RM and (b) RL portion of the prefrontal cortex.

It is easily observable from Figures 6 and 7 that all the proposed portions of the prefrontal cortex exhibit significant variations in the concentration of HbO₂.

Fig. 8. Training and validation progress with loss reduction process in CNN.

Fig. 9. Classification accuracy comparison of SVM, LDA, and CNN.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY OF LDA AND SVM FOR 2-CLASS AND 4-CLASS fNIRS SIGNAL

Sub	SVM classification accuracy (%)		LDA classification accuracy (%)		SVM 4-class classification accuracy (%)	LDA 4-class classification accuracy (%)
	LH vs RH	iLH vs iRH	LH vs RH	iLH vs iRH		
1	80	77.5	90	81.5	45.45	47.5
2	83.5	80	92.5	82	52.27	45
3	78	69.5	78	69.5	50	45
4	80	72	85	73.5	54.54	55
5	83.5	81.5	88.5	80	52.27	52.5

As a result, all these portions should have to be taken into account as a significant source to discriminate the imagery activities. Accordingly, features were extracted from the fNIR signals of LL, LM, RM, and RL. The features were used to train SVM and LDA separately to check the feature-dependent accuracy of the predictive model. Several time domain features like variance, total summation, and kurtosis did not return good classification accuracy except mean and slope. The classification accuracies for two classes by SVM and LDA were satisfactory. But for 4 classes, the classification accuracy was very low. The results are given in Table II. Therefore, CNN was applied in order to improve the classification accuracy for the 4-class problem.

The training progress of CNN is shown in Figure 8. Here, both training accuracy and loss are shown graphically for a randomly chosen subject. The classification accuracy of the applied CNN is presented in Figure 9 along with the results of SVM and LDA. From the results given in Figure 9, it was found that the classification accuracy of CNN for the 4-class fNIRS signal is way more satisfactory than the results of LDA and SVM.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research work investigates how CNN can enhance the classification accuracy with data of more than two classes when the SVM and LDA classification accuracy is very low. The results show that for iLH, iRH, LH, and RH on five subjects, the CNN-based scheme provides 86.24% (on average) accuracy, whereas, in the case of SVM and LDA, the average classification accuracy is 50.9% and 49%, respectively. In the case of subject-independent data, CNN shows 83.33% accuracy. This result revealed that CNN can lead to the practical development of a BCI system. Since classification accuracy is the most essential factor to design a practical BCI

device, we will try to explore further improvements in the accuracy of fNIRS-based BCI by implementing several deep learning-based algorithms. We can also try to merge some other modalities with fNIRS and check whether this process provides better accuracy or not.

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Controller Design based on Fractional Calculus for AUV Yaw Control

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ABSTRACT

This research presents a fractional order integral controller strategy, which improves the steering angle for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs). The AUV mathematical modeling is presented. A Fractional Order Proportional Integral (FOPI) control scheme is implemented to ensure the yaw angle stability of the AUV steering under system uncertainty. The FOPI controller is validated with MATLAB/Simulink and is compared to the conventional Integer Order PI (IOPI) controller to track the yaw angle of the structure. The simulation results show that the proposed FOPI controller outperforms the IOPI controller and improves the AUV system steering and the overall transient response while ensuring the system's stability with and without external disturbances such as underwater current and different loading conditions.

Keywords-Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV); Nelder Mean Simplex (NMS); fractional calculus; FOPI

I. INTRODUCTION

Water covers more than 70% of Earth's surface and the oceans holds nearly 96.5% of all the Earth's water. The scientific area of exploration of new resources in the ocean is in rapid increase. However, investigating under sea water levels can have some limitations with manned or human operated systems, while the use of Automatus Underwater Vehicles (AUV) can provide huge benefits in terms of reducing the risk of human lives, exploring deep sea levels, underwater surveillance, and cost saving [1]. AUVs are unmanned robots that have the capability to move under the water surface typically on a pre-defined mission, with satellite networks used for communication. In the modeling and design stage, an important aspect is the mission requirements and objectives. Additional details on the process of designing underwater vehicles can be found in [2]. Underwater vehicles can be categorized into two major types, Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) or manned vehicles, which need a human to function and send control instructions in order to operate. The other type is the AUV or unnamed vehicles, which can completely function independently. Currently, AUV's are rapidly used in a wide range of applications, which include environmental monitoring, underwater surveillance, scientific research, anti-submarine warfare, oceanographic discovery, subsea structure inspection, oil and gas natural research exploration, etc. [1].

The dynamics of underwater vehicles are well-known to contain significantly nonlinear dynamics and are dependent on a variant number of the system parameters. These nonlinearities can generate system uncertainties, time-varying

dynamic model and severe effect by external disturbances such as unpredicted under water current, waves and environmental disturbances [1]. Controlling the AUV system is a challenging problem, and high control accuracy is needed to keep the system safe and stable when threatened by unpredicted factors. In order to handle AUVs' uncertainty and disturbance and to enhance their tracking performance, numerous control methods have been applied to ensure the stability of AUV systems, including the LQR control [3], neural networks [4], fuzzy control [5], PI/PID control [6], and Sliding Mode Control (SMC) [7]. Research findings on non-integer controllers indicate better quality control than Integer Order (IO) controllers. Some studies showing the advantages of implementing this control technique to stabilize the steering system of AUV's are [8-12].

In this paper, a control method is proposed that is essentially found in fractional calculus theory, a non-integer or fractional order control. At present, fractional order controller based on Nelder-Mead Simlex (NMS) algorithm has not been utilized for controlling and stabilizing the yaw angle of AUV's. The main contribution of this research is the development of a Fractional Order Proportional Integral (FOPI) controller scheme applied to enhance the steering stability and yaw angle for AUV dynamics with disturbances being present. The performance of the AUV structure and transient response is improved by designing the coefficients of the FOPI controller using the NMS method. The proposed controller is examined and its effectiveness to maintain the system stable with uncertain conditions such as underwater currents and load variation is shown.

II. AUV MODELING

A. AUV Dynamics (Coordinate System)

To derive a mathematical model and the equations representing the AUV structure, analysis of the system dynamics and kinematics is demonstrated, as three subsystems are considered. Figure 1 shows the two coordinate systems describing the movement of the AUV in 6 Degrees Of Freedom (DOF). The O-xyz axis is the motion coordinates and is static to the underwater vehicle, which is denoted as the body-fixed reference system. The movement of the body-rigid system is demonstrated to the earth (E) fixed system (ϕ, θ, Ψ) [13,14]. Thus, a non-integer order PI with feedback control scheme would be implemented to the AUV structure to achieve robust yaw angle stability with/without disturbances. Table I indicates the used AUV parameter values.

Fig. 1. AUV 6-DOF coordinate system.

B. AUV Kinematics

The physical demonstration of the AUV structure and the equation of motion follow fixed body dynamics. Consequently, it is valuable to utilize the physical system components by diminishing the number of coefficients needed to control the system. Thus, it is the main incentive for the development of the vertical description of the equations of motion, which are successful for computer processing [13]. The 6-DOF AUV equation of movement follows fixed body dynamics. $\dot{\eta} = [\eta_1 \ \eta_2]^T$, $\eta_1 = [x \ y \ z]^T$ is the position vector and $\eta_2 = [\varphi \ \theta \ \psi]^T$ is the orientation vector of the body and earth fixed reference system. The linear and angular velocities are specified as $v_1 = [u \ v \ w]^T$, $v_2 = [p \ q \ r]^T$ where $v = [v_1 \ v_2]^T$.

The two essential equations to model the AUV dynamical system are obtained from Newton's laws of motion. These equations can be defined as [13]:

$$\dot{\eta} = J(\eta) v \quad (1)$$

$$M\dot{v} + c(v)v + D(v)v + G(\eta) = \tau \quad (2)$$

where $J(\eta)$ is the transformation matrix, τ is the control input matrix, M , $C(v)$, $D(v)$, and $G(\eta)$ symbolize mass, Coriolis forces, damping matrix, and the gravitational matrix respectively.

By including in the AUV system non-linear equations of motion, the kinematics equation can be expressed as [13]:

$$\dot{v} = M^{-1}[C(v)v + D(v)v + G(\eta) + \tau_r] \quad (3)$$

TABLE I. AUV PARAMETERS

Parameter	Name	Value	Unit
M	AUV mass	50	kg
Y_v	Cross flow drag	-131	kg/m
$Y_{\dot{\eta}}$	Cross flow drag	-0.632	kg.m/rad ²
N_r	Cross flow drag	-94	kg.m ² /rad
N_v	Cross flow drag	-3.2	kg
$X_{\dot{u}}$	Additional mass	-0.9	kg
$Y_{\dot{r}}$	Additional mass	1.93	kg.m/rad
$Y_{\dot{v}}$	Additional mass	-36	kg
$N_{\dot{r}}$	Additional mass	-4.9	kg.m ² /rad
I_z	Moment of inertia	3.45	kg.m ² /rad
u_0	AUV speed	10	m/s

C. AUV Model Decoupling

Due to the AUV system extreme nonlinear dynamics and coupling, a reduced system model is considered and linearized for the controller design, to ensure the stability and control of the AUV steering system. The vehicle model can be reduced and decoupled to study the yaw angle steering behavior. By considering the following three states, the sway v , yaw velocity r , and the yaw rate $\dot{\psi}$. The steering movement can be acquired from the rudders and fins. Also, by disregarding the gravity forces, system damping and assuming an equilibrium point, the AUV system model can be decoupled as follows:

$$[m - Y_{\dot{v}}]\dot{v} = (X_{\dot{u}} - m)u_0 r + Y_v v + Y_r r, \quad (4)$$

$$[I_z - N_{\dot{r}}]\dot{r} = (Y_{\dot{v}} - X_{\dot{u}})v r + Y_r u_0 r + N_v v + N_r r + \tau_r \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{\psi} = r$. The linear AUV system can be expressed in state-space as:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu, \ y = Cx + Du \quad (6)$$

where:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{Y_v}{m - Y_{\dot{v}}} & \frac{(X_{\dot{u}} - m)u_0 + Y_r}{m - Y_{\dot{v}}} & 0 \\ N_v & \frac{Y_{\dot{r}}u_0 + N_r}{Y_{\dot{v}} - X_{\dot{u}}} & 0 \\ \frac{I_z - N_{\dot{r}}}{0} & \frac{I_z - N_{\dot{r}}}{1} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

$$B = G(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \ u = \tau_r. \quad (8)$$

From the state-space model in (7)-(8), the transfer function of the yaw angle control can be computed as follows:

$$G(s) = \frac{0.1198 s + 0.2064}{s^3 + 10.67 s^2 + 13.35 s} \quad (9)$$

where a fractional controller is developed and applied to the AUV system dynamics in a feedback formation as shown in Figure 3.

III. FRACTIONAL ORDER PI CONTROL

The controller technique implemented in this study is based on fractional calculus, a non-integer or fractional order PI control. For AUV dynamics structure, it is crucial for the control scheme to track the required vehicle position and yaw angle in a precise manner to help the system obtain steering stability. By introducing fractional integral and differential operators, the perception of only IO operators can be stretched over a wider range, which results in better accuracy in system modeling or control. One critical advantage of a fractional system is the memory and hereditary annotation, which can be described with fractional order calculus theory. However, for classical IO plants the memory aspect and hereditary annotation are of a major concern [11]. Fractional calculus theory is a general notion to fractional order of differentiator and integrator simple operator ${}_aD_t^\beta$ defined in (10) [10]:

$${}_aD_t^\beta = \begin{cases} d^\beta/dt^\beta & \Re(\alpha) > 0, \\ 1 & \Re(\alpha) = 0, \\ \int_a^t (dt)^{-\beta} & \Re(\alpha) < 0. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where a and t are bounds of the process and β indicates the fractional component. β is assumed real, but it can be an imaginary component [10].

Fractional operators can be applied directly to systems or can be approximated as IO operators applied into the system. Further, a control system can be controlled by either an IO or non-integer order controller, hence the system plant can also possibly be derived as a fractional or classical IO system. Four distinct combinations can occur to implement a fractional order control: fractional order controller with a fractional order plant, fractional order plant with an IO controller, IO plant with a fractional order controller, and IO plant with an IO controller [14]. In this paper a linear fractional order controller scheme is developed and the controller would be implemented to an IO plant (AUV system).

Describing the control options by implementing a non-integer order controller in a graphic representation, Figure 2 indicates that all IO PID controllers are special cases of the non-integer order PID controller. It can be observed in Figure 2 that the IO PID controller only transforms at four rigid points, whereas any point on the graphical plane can be used with a fractional order PID controller, i.e. the control order can interchange continuously and smoothly throughout the entire shaded region, which makes the fractional order PID design more flexible more effective with system uncertainties than IOPIID [17]. Thus, in this study, the value examined for the fractional order integral operator λ , lies in region [0-1] shown in Figure 2, since the system requires a lower order integral value to improve the transient response and maintain stability. The differential equation of the fractional order PI^λ control is provided by:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + \frac{K_i}{D^\lambda} e(t) \quad (11)$$

By applying the Laplace transformation to (11) and with the assumption of zero initial conditions, the transfer function can be obtained as [16]:

$$G_c(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s^\lambda} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the range values of the FOPID controller.

A block diagram representation of the FOPI controller for a closed loop structure is shown in Figure 3, where the plant is the AUV system dynamics and $G_c(s)$ is the non-integer controller expressed as:

$$G_c(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s^\lambda}. \quad (13)$$

and λ is the non-integer operator.

The added tunable component λ with the FOPI control in comparison to the IOPI control generates more flexibility in controlling the structure and at the same time enhances the control quality implementation and helps minimizing the steady-state error and improves the transient response of the AUV system. Proper tuning of the FOPI controller is required to meet the system specifications. With a FOPI controller, reaching closed-loop zero steady-state error and diminishing the amplification of high-frequency disturbances can be achieved for the AUV system. Moreover, when using the IOPI control there would be a lagging phase of 90° for the system, while with the FOPI scheme, it delivers a reduced constant lagging phase to the system due to the fractional element λ which improves the transient response of the system dynamics as compared to the IOPI control.

Fig. 3. FOPI structure applied for the AUV.

IV. THE NELDER-MEAD SIMPLEX METHOD

The simplex algorithm developed by Nelder and Mead in 1965 has been widely used to solve parameter estimation and optimization problems. The Nelder-Mead Simplex (NMS) has been applied by the United States army Corps Engineers for

hydrologic engineering center-hydrologic modeling system (HEC-HMS) software as a search technique for optimizing the hydrologic parameters [18]. In this research, the value of the fractional operator λ is tuned using the NMS method. The NMS method can solve unconstrained optimization problems of the form $\min_x f(x), x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. There are four basic operational steps of the NMS algorithm: reflection, expansion, contraction, and shrinking as demonstrated in Figure 4 [10, 18].

The five stages for implementing the NMS algorithm are [18]:

1. Order. Order $n + 1$ vertices in order to meet:

$$f(x_1) \leq f(x_2) \leq \dots \leq f(x_{n+1})$$

2. Reflect. Calculate the reflection point x_r :

$$x_r = \bar{x} + \rho(\bar{x} - x_{n+1}) \quad (14)$$

where:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i, \quad (15)$$

is the centroid of the n best points.

Then, $f_r = f(x_r)$. If $f_1 \leq f_r \leq f_n$, set the point x_r and terminate the iteration.

3. Expand. If $f_r < f_1$, evaluate the expansion point x_e by:

$$x_e = \bar{x} + \chi(x_r - \bar{x}) \quad (16)$$

Then compute $f_e = f(x_e)$. If $f_e < f_r$ then set $x_{n+1} = x_e$ and terminate the iteration. Otherwise, set $x_{n+1} = x_r$ and terminate the iteration.

4. Contract. If $f_r \geq f_n$, compute a contraction between \bar{x} and the best of x_{n+1} and x_r :

- Outer contraction. If $f_n \leq f_r < f_{n+1}$, compute:

$$x_c = \bar{x} + \gamma(x_r - \bar{x}) \quad (17)$$

then determine $f_c = f(x_c)$. If $f_c \leq f_r$, set $x_{n+1} = x_c$, and terminate the process, else proceed to the next stage performing a shrinkage.

- Inner contraction. If $f_r \geq f_{n+1}$, execute the inner contraction by computing:

$$x_{cc} = \bar{x} - \gamma(\bar{x} - x_{n+1}) \quad (18)$$

Then compute $f_{cc} = f(x_{cc})$. If $f_{cc} < f_{n+1}$, set $x_{n+1} = x_{cc}$, and terminate the iteration. Else proceed to the next stage performing a shrinkage.

5. Shrink. Calculate n new points by:

$$x_i = x_1 + \sigma(x_i - x_1), \quad (19)$$

where $i = 2, \dots, n + 1$. Then compute f at those vertices.

The scalar coefficients ρ , χ , γ , and σ denote the coefficients, expansion, contraction, and shrink reflection, respectively. These coefficients should obey:

$$\rho > 0, \chi > 1, 0 < \gamma < 1, \text{ and } 0 < \sigma < 1.$$

Fig. 4. NMS flowchart.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fractional order PI controller has been applied for AUV dynamics using MATLAB/Simulink and the FOMCON toolbox. Figure 5 shows the Simulink model for the AUV system yaw angle response for the PI/FOPI controller, as a step disturbance is added to emulate an underwater current disturbance applied to the AUV system. The FOPI control is developed with the vehicle travelling at a speed of 10m/s, and maintains the yaw angle and steering stability for the AUV structure. The FOPI controller was designed using NMS with the minimum integral square error, as the bound of fractional integral inspected between the closed interval [0, 1]. Further, by applying the NMS technique the local minimization can be reached by eliminating the smallest needed vertex in a given function. The integral term λ of the fractional controller is optimized to be 0.1 with $k_p = 200$ and $k_i = 79$. Hence, the developed fractional controller is compared to the classical Integer-Order PI (IOPI) controller.

A. Simulation Results with the FOPI Controller for Different AUV Travelling Speeds

Figure 6 shows the simulation results of the AUV operating at different speeds with the FOPI controller. It is demonstrated that the vehicle reaches the desired steering angle of 40° in 3s with a 50% increase and decrease in the AUV speed. As the speed is increased, the overshoot slightly increases, while the system still maintains its regulation to reach the desired yaw angle response.

B. Simulation of the Yaw Angle of the AUV with PI/FOPI Controllers

Figure 7 displays the response of yaw angle with the FOPI and IOPI controllers being applied for a desired yaw angle of 40° . The response indicates improved performance of the FOPI over the IOPI controller, with a faster time response, settling time, lower overshoot, and increased damping. Table II shows the performance comparison of the transient response of the controllers. We can see that the fractional controller has better performance in any feature.

Fig. 5. Simulink model of the yaw angle for AUV using PI/FOPI.

Fig. 6. Yaw angle for different AUV speeds with FOPI controller.

Fig. 7. Yaw angle of the AUV with FOPI/IOPI controller.

TABLE II. TRANSIENT RESPONSE

Response info	Controller	
	IOPI	FOPI
Settling time	4.75	1.48
Rise time	0.46	0.39
Overshoot	16.1	6.8
Undershoot	0	0
Peak	46.17	42.95

C. Simulation of the Yaw Angle of the AUV under the Presence of Disturbancet

Figure 8 presents the yaw angle response with an external disturbance, such as ocean current waves, being applied on the AUV system. It is seen that the FOPI controller outperforms the IOPI in terms of time response, overshoot, and settling time to reach the desired yaw angle with the presence of external disturbance. Table III shows the response comparison between the controllers. It can be seen that the fractional controller improved the transient response in all aspects.

Fig. 8. Yaw angle with external disturbance applied to the AUV.

TABLE III. TRANSIENT RESPONSE WITH SYSTEM DISTURBANCE

Response info	Controller	
	IOPI	FOPI
Settling time	4.55	1.51
Rise time	0.47	0.38
Overshoot	9.3	17.1
Undershoot	0	0
Peak	43.66	46.97

D. Simulation of the Yaw Angle with Load Variation on the AUV System

Figure 10 demonstrates the response of the UAV with the load being increased and decreased by 50% along with the presence of disturbances. The FOPI controller shows its robustness in handling uncertain environmental disturbances with different loading conditions, in stabilizing the system, and in achieving the desired yaw angle with improved time response, settling time, and minimized overshoot in comparison with the classical IOPI controller.

Fig. 9. FOPI/IOPI control of the yaw angle for AUV with varying loads.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a non-integer (fractional) order controller is implemented on the AUV dynamical system. It is demonstrated that the proposed FOPI control, which adds an additional tuning parameter, improves the system transient response, stability, and the yaw angle control of the AUV structure. The underwater vehicle yaw angle control is a very challenging problem and with the FOPI controller the system can preserve improved regulation and faster time response under system uncertainties and disturbances such as, underwater current waves and load variations. The FOPI controller was compared to the classical integer order controller, and the simulation results confirm that the fractional controller outperforms the IOPI controller and provides improved time response and reduced system overshoot and settling time to achieve the desired yaw angle. Regarding future work, the applied fractional order controller can be applied to an AUV system modeled as a fractional order system, which can provide more precision and accuracy to the system model dynamics and thus, improve the system overall performance.

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A Deep Learning-Based approach to Segregate Solid Waste Generated in Residential Areas

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ABSTRACT

Residential waste is a substantial contributor to solid waste generation, which is approximately around 36.5 million tons annually in India. The waste created in households is not separated at the source. All waste is accumulated in a single waste bin and stashed in a nearby public waste bin, resulting in a massive amount of waste being dumped in landfills and also infused with other types of waste, causing environmental pollution. The core objective of this research is to develop a household waste segregator using the TensorFlow object detection model and Arduino microcontroller. The SSD MobileNet V2 model has been trained with a household dataset consisting of paper, plastic, metal, organic waste, glass, and one more additional empty class to detect whether waste is placed for detection or not. This proposed system can predict the waste class and segregate it into their specific dustbin with mean Average Precision (mAP) and recall of 86.5% and 88.3%, respectively. Waste segregation and recycling can reduce landfills, lower carbon footprints, increase recycling, recover value from garbage, and lower greenhouse gases emitted from waste. Segregation at the source will reduce the cost of the segregation process carried by the municipal solid waste management.

Keywords-deep learning; waste management; computer vision; embedded system; Arduino

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the Indian Central Pollution Control Board's (CPCB) annual report, the country generates 160038.9 TPD (tons per day) of solid waste, of which 152749.5 TPD is collected with a collection efficiency of 95.4%, 79956.3 TPD is processed at 50%, and 29427.2 TPD is landfilled at 18.4%, , and 31.7% (50655.4 TPD), remains unaccounted for [1]. Authors in [2] published a spatio-temporal approach to reduce the waste dumped into landfills. Waste segregation is the biggest issue encountered in solid waste management, which is the process of accumulating, transferring, processing, and discarding solid waste in a municipality under the purview of a municipal authority. The waste could be collected door to door or by placing public trash bins. The collected waste would be transported to the municipal storage area where they will be processed and the unprocessed waste would be dumped into landfill sites (there are 3184 such dumpsites in India). So far, the waste is segregated manually at the storage location. Even though the government takes necessary actions to segregate waste at the source, only a few states can achieve it. In the long run, it is hard for people to maintain separate bins for each waste, so commonly all waste are dropped into a single bin and are handed to the municipal waste collection units. As an

outcome, more amount of waste gets dumped into landfills. Authors in [3] proposed a reversal approach to handle the municipal solid waste generated in South Africa. Authors in [4] proposed a real-time deep learning system to sort waste disposed of in public places. Authors in [5] developed a robot that can classify waste as organic and non-organic using computer vision [5].

Over the past decade, the implementation of deep learning in real-time applications has increased drastically. Researchers have been using artificial intelligence techniques to unravel day-to-day problems. Deep learning is the subsidiary of machine learning. Machines can perform tasks such as prediction, classification, pattern recognition, and clustering [6, 7] when trained. Deep learning offers cutting-edge approaches to fully comprehending human behavior [8]. TensorFlow is a free and open-source AI and machine learning software library that is used many scenarios but emphasizes especially on deep neural network training and inference [9]. Nowadays, machines can extract significant information from digital images, videos, and other visual inputs utilizing an area of artificial intelligence termed as computer vision, and they can act based on that information. The model developed in this work will be trained using a learning method named transfer learning. In this

method the intelligence of one model is transferred to a new model [10], assuming that the model can be thus trained faster and achieve better results quicker than other training methods. Authors in [11] developed a model using a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to classify different types of plastics in waste. To improve the classification accuracy, authors in [12] developed the WasteNet model using deep learning with high accuracy. Authors in [13] compared the Support Vector Machine (SVM) with CNN based on waste classification performance. The pre-trained ResNet-34 model [14] was used to classify the waste data collected from the waste bin and the system does not have any segregation unit. Authors in [15] developed a model with transfer learning to classify public waste images. The smart waste separator in [16] has been used to classify waste based on shape. The model was developed using Hu's invariant moments and K-nearest neighbor algorithms. Authors in [17] developed the model RecycleNet to perform classification, especially for recyclable waste with a test accuracy of 81% [17]. Authors in [18] developed a deep learning model that can detect and classify waste into seven categories. In [19], images of solid waste were classified using the Gabor Wavelet Transformation (GWT), which combines an image with Gabor wavelet kernels of various scales and orientations. Authors in [20] implemented a waste segregation model with Internet of Things (IoT) and deep learning. Machine learning and IoT were used in [21, 22] to isolate the biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste and also to detect the presence of harmful gases in the bin. To segregate waste, the model should be trained on the dataset collected from the area in which the segregator needed to be placed. The current work is mainly focused on segregating household waste.

II. MODELING OF THE WASTE SEGREGATION SYSTEM

In this work, an automatic household waste segregator is proposed. This system can classify household waste into five categories, i.e. paper, plastic, organic, glass, and metal. The dimensions of the segregation system are displayed in Figure 1(a). The system has two units: one fixed and one movable as illustrated in Figure 1(b). The movable unit of the segregation system has three major parts: (i) platform, (ii) metal track, and (iii) dustbin. The platform of the waste segregation system can move bi-directionally in a metal track and the dustbins are placed below the track. The position of each dustbin is marked in the aluminum using black color and Arduino can identify the position of the dustbin using an infrared sensor. Waste needs to be placed on the movable platform and the camera placed over the platform would capture the frame and forward it to the custom-trained object detection. The model has been trained in Google Colab using the TensorFlow object detection Application Programming Interface. The object detection model would identify the category of waste and transmit the data to the Arduino through serial communication. Arduino will use infrared sensors and motors to control and modify the position of the platform based on the information collected. The mobility of the platform is controlled by 2 DC motors connected to wheels and 2 more supporting wheels. When the position of the platform matches the position of the dustbin, the waste will be dropped into the dustbin using the slider which is also controlled by the Arduino.

Fig. 1. Waste segregation system: (a) dimensions, (b) block diagram, (c) graphical representation.

III. OBJECT DETECTION MODEL

TensorFlow pre-trained object detection model was used in the automatic household waste segregator. The household waste image dataset was collected using a webcam, with a pixel size of 640×480 and the dataset was trained and tested with 3 pre-trained object detection models. Based on the average precision, average recall, and F1 score, SSD MobileNet V2 FPN Lite 640×640 was preferred for this work. Figure 2 represents the performance evaluation of the models for the household waste image dataset. MobileNet V2 has higher precision, recall, and F1 score than ResNet 50 and EfficientDet D0.

Fig. 2. Evaluation of the pre-trained models.

A. SSD MobileNetV2

The MobileNetV2 has been designed to be implemented in low-powered devices with moderate performance on classification, as shown in Figure. 2. MobileNet is small in size and consumes low computing power. While compared to the architecture of the MobileNet V1 model, the main difference is the inclusion of 1x1 Expansion and 1x1 projection layers. Table I represents the transformation of data fed into the bottleneck residual block. Where $m \times n$ represents the size of the input block, k is the size of the input and the output channel, and s is the value that represents the stride.

Fig. 3. MobileNet V2 block.

TABLE I. BOTTLENECK RESIDUAL ARCHITECTURE

Input	Operator	Output
$m \times n \times k$	1x1 pointwise conv2D, RELU6	$m \times n \times (t \ k)$
$m \times n \times (t \ k)$	3x3, depthwise $s=s$, RELU6	$(m/s) \times (n/s) \times (t \ k)$
$(m/s) \times (n/s) \times (t \ k)$	1x1 pointwise conv2D	$(m/s) \times (n/s) \times k$

The bottleneck residual block has three layers, the 1x1 expansion layer expands the input value based on the expansion factor which has a default value of $t = 6$.

Consider stride=1 in Figure 3. The input fed to the expansion layer is 1x160x160x24. The input channel 24 is multiplied with the expansion factor and the output of the layer

is 1x160x160x144. The output forwarded to the 3x3 Depthwiseconv2D layer applies filters to the input 1x160x160x144, which is forwarded to the 1x1 Projection Layer. In this layer, the input will be reduced to 1x160x160x24 due to the bottleneck feature. In Figure 3, Stride=1 is the Bottleneck residual block and Stride=2 is the formation used to reduce the features of input data [23]. MobileNet base network is used to extract the features from the input image, and the features extracted from the image are forwarded to the SSD network as presented in Figure.4.

Fig. 4. SSD MobileNet architecture.

B. Data Collection and Labelling.

The household waste image dataset was collected using a webcam and the pixel size was determined to be 640x480. The dataset consists of 6 classes, i.e. Organic, Paper, Metal, Glass, and Plastic waste. One additional class (Empty) was included for determining whether the waste holding platform is free. In [24-26], ultrasonic sensor and PIR sensor are used to detect the condition of the platform or waste holding area, to detect whether the waste is placed or not for prediction. This method will eliminate the usage of the ultrasonic sensor in detecting the presence of waste. Altogether 1188 images were collected for training the object detection model. In Figure 5(a), the number of images per class was presented and the images were labelled using labelling software as shown in Figure 5(b). Once the image was annotated LabelImg will generate an annotation file with an XML extension. For training the object detection model, Google Colab platform was preferred. Google provides 16Gb of workstation GPU free of cost. Training the model using GPU will reduce the training period and correspondingly supports achieving the loss convergence faster. However, authors in [27] suggested an algorithm that can generate better results even in non-GPU machines [27]. The model was trained for 5000 steps with a batch size of 4. The number of training steps was limited to avoid overfitting. A momentum optimizer with a cosine decay learning rate of 0.08 is used in the training process. The model was trained with a batch size of 4, which helps the model to be well generalized and also consumes less GPU. It consumes more time for computation but this offers better results in the case of a low dataset scenario. Training stops when the total loss of the model drops to 0.2. The frozen inference graph was generated after the training and was downloaded from Google Colab.

Fig. 5. (a) Dataset distribution, (b) LabelImg interface.

IV. AUTOMATIC HOUSEHOLD WASTE SEGREGATOR PROTOTYPE

A. The Prototype

Most of the parts of the prototype are made up of plastic, except the track which is made up of aluminum. The platform is placed over the track and dustbins were placed below. There is a ridge in the track that holds the wheel of the platform in position. This ridge is responsible for the linear mobility of the platform. The position of the components is shown in Figure 6. The object detection python script was running on the laptop, the webcam captures real-time video from the waste platform. If the waste is not placed in the platform, the object detection model will send class Empty to the controller through serial communication using the PySerial library. The communication takes place with a baud rate of 115200 bps. When a sample waste is placed on the platform, the object detection model sends the prediction results to the controller. From the perspective of the controller side, the controller waits for the incoming serial data. Most of the time the controller receives Empty. During that period, the controller stays still. If the controller receives other class names like Metal, Plastic, Paper, Glass, and Organic as input, the controller will initiate the function to activate the motors in the platform. The infrared sensor in the platform form will locate the position of the respective dustbin with the black mark placed in the tracks. Once the position is reached, the motor of the slider gets activated and the waste will be dropped in the dustbin. After this, the platform moves back to the starting position. Figure 6 illustrates the process of segregation. In Figure 6(a), the platform is in the initial position holding paper waste, whereas in Figure 6(b) the platform moves to the paper waste dustbin.

Fig. 6. (a) Initial platform position, (b) platform dropping waste, (c) front view, and (d) top view of the household waste segregation system.

B. The Algorithm

Step 1: Initiate a webcam interfaced with a laptop, and capture video.

Step 2: Predict the video input, and send the predictions to the Arduino controller.

Step 3: Controller reads the serial data.

- if *serial data* = *Empty* then do nothing.
- if *serial data* = *Organic* then put motors forward until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=1, slider open, drop waste and close, motor reverse until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=1.
- if *serial data* = *Metal* then put motors forward until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=2, slider open, drop waste and close, motor reverse until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=2.
- if *serial data* = *Glass* then put motors forward until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=3, slider open, drop waste and close, motor reverse Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=3.
- if *serial data* = *Plastic* then put motor in reverse until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=1, slider opens, drop waste

and close, put motors forward until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=1.

- if *serial data* = *Paper* then put motor in reverse until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=2, slider open, drop waste and close, motors forward until Dustbin ID = IR sensor variable=2.

Step 4: The controller reads the serial data.

In the track, from the initial position of the platform, there will be 3 markings on the right side and 2 markings on the left side as shown in Figure 6(a)-(b). Figure 6(c) shows the front view and Figure 6(d) the top view of the waste segregation system.

Fig. 7. (a) Loss of the model, (b) glass, (c) organic, (d) plastic, (e) empty, (f) metal, (g) paper.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Object Detection Model

The model has been trained on the household waste image dataset in Google Colab for 5000 steps. The frozen inference graph generated from the training process was subsequently imported and utilized within Python scripts for object

detection. These scripts were executed via Jupiter Notebook on a local machine. The total loss is the sum of classification loss, localization loss and regularization loss. The classification and localization loss are 0.05 and 0.01, demonstrating the model's competence in object classification and localization. The losses at 5000 steps are displayed in Figure 7(a) and Table II. The model performance was evaluated using 120 waste images and

was found to have a mean average precision of 86.5% at an Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold of 0.50:0.95, with an average recall of 88% in the same IoU range, as presented in Table III. The model's precision and recall can be improved by increasing the sample size of the dataset or modifying the hyperparameters to increase the model's learning rate and detection efficiency. Figure 7(b)-(g) displays the real-time detection results, with lower confidence scores for the Empty class compared to other classes. This discrepancy is attributed to the comparatively small dataset of 121 images used for Empty class training compared to other classes. Although the confidence score can predict the class more accurately, a confidence threshold of 0.6 was defined for this model, meaning that the bounding boxes are drawn only when the detection confidence score exceeds 60%.

TABLE II. TOTAL LOSS FOR 5000 STEPS

Metrics	Intersection over Union range (IoU)	Value
Mean average precision	0.50:0.95	0.865
Average recall	0.50:0.95	0.883

TABLE III. MEAN AVERAGE PRECISION AND AVERAGE RECALL

Step	Classification loss	Localization loss	Regularization loss	Total loss
5000	0.053084	0.018455	0.130954	0.202493

B. Segregation of Waste

When the Arduino microcontroller receives the data from the object detection model, it activates the motor and moves to the corresponding dustbin. The shown above algorithm, programmed in the controller, locates the position of each dustbin based on the black marking placed in the metal track over each dustbin shown in Figure 6(a)-(b), based on the position of the black marking from the center point Dustbin ID was assigned.

The infrared sensor is used to track the corresponding dustbin by detecting the black marks placed, once the platform reaches the destination, the slider will open and waste will drop into the dustbin. Then the slider will close as shown Figure 8(a)-(b). After the waste is segregated into the dustbin, the platform moves back to the initial position and the process is repeated as illustrated in Figure 8(c). In all conditions, Dustbin ID will be the same for reaching the dustbin as and the starting point.

VI. COMPARISON WITH OTHER WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

In the existing waste management systems, the work stops after training and evaluation of the deep learning model. Only a few works have developed the hardware for waste segregation. In all segregation systems, the hardware starts the segregation process only after the waste is placed in the waste holding area. The waste placed, can be detected by an ultrasonic sensor and a passive infrared sensor (PIR) [24-26]. A comparison between the proposed and existing systems is shown in Table IV. In the proposed system, the sensor used to detect the presence of waste was eliminated. Instead, images of the empty waste

holding platform were collected and included in training, as shown in Figure 7(e). The object detection model itself can detect the presence of waste and also predict its category.

Fig. 8. (a) Controller receives serial data, (b) platform reaches to initial position, (c) comparing dustbin ID with black mark count value to initiate waste drop sequence.

VII. CONCLUSION

This article outlines a household waste segregation system utilizing the TensorFlow-based object detection model, SSD MobileNet V2 640x640. The model is pre-trained and fine-tuned on a custom household waste dataset to enable real-time waste segregation. The dataset is comprised of 6 classes, including five major waste categories, namely paper, plastic, organic, glass, and metal. The sixth class, "empty", was added to detect the presence of waste without the need for an ultrasonic sensor. Within each class, multiple waste items are included, regardless of their features. For instance, the plastic waste category includes images of various products with

differing shapes, sizes, and colors, such as dairy product covers, chocolate wrappers, toothpaste tubes, soft drink bottles, hair conditioner containers, water bottles, and grocery product wrappers. This heterogeneity in waste generated by households is a result of varying geographical locations and lifestyles, and thus requires a large and diverse dataset and training in a TPU environment. TPUs demonstrate improved results and faster convergence compared to GPUs, even with larger batch sizes. To optimize the practical implementation of this system, it is

necessary to minimize the prototype size. Although the waste segregation process is automated, the disposal process still requires manual intervention, with the segregated waste being handed over to the municipal waste collection unit. In the future, mobility can be added to the dustbin through a path guidance system, and a network connecting household bins to municipal waste collection units can be developed to further automate and improve the reliability of the system.

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM WITH EXISTING WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Ref.	AI architecture	Segregation mechanism	Methods used to detect the presence of waste	Type of waste
[13]	CNN with 11 layers and SVM	No	-	Metal, paper, plastic, glass, cardboard and general waste
[12]	WasteNet	No	-	Metal, paper, plastic, glass, cardboard and other waste
[28]	-	No	-	General waste
[14]	CNN	No	-	Metal, paper, plastic, glass, cardboard and common waste
[29]	-	No	-	General waste
[21]	-	No	-	General waste
[24]	CNN	Yes	PIR	Metal, paper, plastic and glass
[25]	MobileNet	Yes	Ultrasonic sensor	Metal, paper, plastic
[26]	MobileNet	Yes	Ultrasonic sensor	Metal, paper, plastic, glass, cardboard
Proposed	MobileNet	Yes	The object detection model alone can detect the presence of waste	Organic, metal, glass, paper and plastic

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The corresponding author contributed in data collection, model training, hardware design, and drafted the manuscript. The second author supervised the process and proofread the manuscript for publication.

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Multiple Response Prediction and Optimization in Thin-Walled Milling of 6061 Aluminum Alloy

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the multi-objective optimization method for thin-wall milling of 6061 aluminum alloy is addressed. The technological parameters including the cutting speed V_c , the feed of tooth f_z , and the width of cut a , are considered input variables, while the manufacturing responses are surface roughness R_a , production rate MRR, and flatness deviation FL. The goal is to find the optimum cutting parameters to minimize R_a and FL and maximize MRR, at the same time. To solve this problem, the desirability function approach was used based on Taguchi orthogonal array. Twenty-seven experiments were conducted and the measured data were collected. The mathematical regression models for responses R_a , MRR, and FL were then generated and evaluated by using the analysis of variance method. Then, the multiple objective optimization problems were solved by using the desirability function approach. The optimum cutting parameters set are $V_c=120\text{m/min}$, $f_z=0.06\text{mm}$, and $a_r=0.13131\text{mm}$, corresponding to $R_a=0.1613\mu\text{m}$, $\text{MRR}=17197.45\text{cm}^3/\text{min}$, and $\text{FL}=0.0995\text{mm}$.

Keywords-thin-walled milling; multiple objective optimization; desirable function approach; Taguchi method; 6061 aluminum alloy

I. INTRODUCTION

The 6061 alloy is an important product line in aluminum manufactured products [1]. Aluminum and its alloys rank second (after steel) in use as structural metals [2], due to properties that make them suitable for many different uses [3].

Some of the important properties of 6061 alloy are its light weight, high strength, good chemical corrosion resistance, and good weldability [4]. Therefore, 6061 alloy is often used in the transportation industry (e.g. in auto parts, motorcycles, cycle frames, and motorcycle frames) and especially in the marine or aerospace industry [5]. The development of the aviation

industry has led to an increasing demand for aluminum alloy machining, in which the milling of thin-walled parts plays a particularly important role [6]. However, the manufacturing of thin-walled parts is complicated by the possibility of deformation during the machining process [7]. Thin-walled products are often difficult to cut due to the complex dynamics involved. During the cutting process, the cutting dynamics for the products varies however it is invariant for the machine tool [8]. On another hand, permanent deformation of the structure can occur and this can cause a proportion of rejected products [9].

In the demand of the growing global market for aluminum alloy thin-walled products, there are several studies focused on optimizing the structure to improve the surface roughness, the load capacity, and the durability of the thin-walled components by reducing deformation and vibration during the cutting process [7]. Many studies have been carried out to improve the economic and technical efficiency of thin-walled processing. Authors in [10] developed an analytical approach to investigate the dynamic chip thickness variation in the thin-walled milling process. A general model of the removal volume is calculated by considering the individual axial depth of cut, the radial depth of cut, and the circumferential cross-section of the tool radius contact for each tool step performed. Authors in [6] presented a technique to improve the surface quality and production rate in the thin-walled milling process. The results show that double-side milling leads to reduce about 50% in cutting time and a decline in the surface roughness and flatness deviation of the milling products, simultaneously. The quality of thin-walled products when machined can also be improved by selecting and using the right jigs and fixtures [11]. Finding suitable cutting parameters can also reduce vibration, thereby reducing deformation during milling. This can be solved through experimentation [12, 13], or mathematical modelling [14]. Authors in [8] present a methodology of performing the optimization of the entire cutting process for thin-walled parts based on the relatively changing kinematics of the machining system. According to the comparison between the dynamics of the machine tool and the variable thickness part, the critical thickness is investigated by an iterative algorithm. This method can be used for many other machining processes.

There are many other studies on machining thin-walled parts in general, and aluminum alloys in particular. These studies can be applied to improve the quality of processed products in practice. However, due to the increasing competitive pressure from the global market, the manufacturers not only have to improve the quality of processing but at the same time have to increase machining productivity and tool life. Those are scientific multi-objective optimization problems and Multiple Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods such as the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) and Multi-Objective Optimization on the basis of Ratio Analysis (MOORA) have been introduced to face them [15-19]. They are often applied due to their simplicity. However, these methods have a common disadvantage, which is the optimal value set is one of the experimental values. This means that these techniques select one of the data sets that have been used, and in many cases, they are not the best [18-20].

With the development of computers, many new algorithms have been researched and applied, e.g. ANFIS [21], Desirability Function Approach (DFA) [22], etc. Many publications have demonstrated the effectiveness of these methods in comparison with MCDM. In this study, DFA and Minitab computed software were applied to solve the multi-objective optimization problem at hand. The research aims to find the optimal cutting parameters set to simultaneously maximize the machining productivity MRR, and minimize the roughness R_a and flatness deviation FL.

A. MATERIALS AND METHODS

B. 6061 Aluminum Alloy

As mentioned above, 6061 Aluminum Alloy was selected because it is largely used. All the specimen workpieces were milled with dimensions of $100 \times 50 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$. The chemical composition and mechanical properties of the workpieces are shown in Tables I and II [23]. The experiments were conducted on a DMU50 CNC Machine. To perform thin-walled milling operations, a 3-flute square namely YG ALU - CUTTER E5D70100 (15329040K) was used (Figure 1). The Taguchi orthogonal array was applied to reduce the number of experiments but still ensure reliability in the predictive analysis, with the number of input variables being 3, the number of levels for each variable being 3, and the number of experiments to be performed being 27. The values of the input variables corresponding to the levels are depicted in Table III. The range of the cutting parameters is chosen based on the cutting tool manufacturer's recommendations.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF 6061 ALLOY

Al (%)	Mg (%)	Si (%)	Cu (%)	Cr (%)	Others (%)
97.9	1	0.60	0.28	0.20	0.02

TABLE II. THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 6061 ALLOY

Tensile strength	310MPa
Yield strength	276MPa
Shear strength	207MPa
Fatigue strength	96.5MPa
Elastic modulus	68.9GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.33
Elongation	12-17%
Hardness	95 HB

TABLE III. INPUT VARIABLE LEVELS

Parameters	Symbol	Unit	Level		
			-1	0	1
Cutting speed	V_c	m/min	120	150	180
Feed rate	f_z	mm/tooth	0.04	0.05	0.06
Width of cut	a_r	mm	0.8	1.0	1.2

C. Experimental data acquisition

The experimental set up is shown in Figure 2. In this work, 3 thin-walled cutting responses, including the surface roughness R_a , material removal rate MRR, and flatness deviation FL are optimized simultaneously by applying the Desirable Function Approach (DFA). Based on the EN ISO 4287 standard, surface roughness R_a is calculated by:

$$R_{ax} = \frac{R_{ax1} + R_{ax2} + R_{ax3} + R_{ax4} + R_{ax5}}{5} \quad (1)$$

$$R_{ay} = \frac{R_{ay1} + R_{ay2} + R_{ay3} + R_{ay4} + R_{ay5}}{5} \quad (2)$$

$$R_a = \frac{R_{ax} + R_{ay}}{2} \quad (3)$$

where R_{ax} is the arithmetical mean roughness in the x-direction and R_{ay} is the mean roughness depth in the y-direction.

Fig. 1. The experimental setup.

Fig. 2. a_1 : Negative local flatness deviation, a_2 : Positive local flatness deviation, 1: least squares reference plane (STN P CEN ISO/TS 12781-1: 2008).

Fig. 3. Measurement systems. (a) Renishaw Equator 300 CMM - High-Speed Comparative Gauge System, (b) Non-contact flatness deviation measurement system.

TABLE IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Run	V_c m/min	f_z mm/	a_r mm	R_a μ m	MRR mm ³ /min	FL mm
1	120	0.04	0.8	0.228	8025.48	-0.031
2	120	0.05	1	0.128	14331.21	-0.060
3	120	0.06	1.2	0.152	20636.94	-0.044
4	150	0.04	0.8	0.294	10031.85	0.100
5	150	0.05	1	0.274	17914.01	0.063
6	150	0.06	1.2	0.345	25796.18	0.131
7	180	0.04	0.8	0.157	11369.43	-0.015
8	180	0.05	1	0.170	20302.55	-0.045
9	180	0.06	1.2	0.271	29235.67	0.039
10	180	0.04	1	0.150	16242.04	0.050
11	180	0.05	1.2	0.205	24363.06	0.085
12	180	0.06	0.8	0.206	17054.14	0.029
13	120	0.04	1	0.190	11464.97	0.033
14	120	0.05	1.2	0.172	17197.45	0.048
15	120	0.06	0.8	0.170	12038.22	-0.023
16	150	0.04	1	0.275	14331.21	0.085
17	150	0.05	1.2	0.300	21496.82	0.192
18	150	0.06	0.8	0.300	15047.77	0.130
19	150	0.04	1.2	0.292	17197.45	0.368
20	150	0.05	0.8	0.279	12539.81	0.058
21	150	0.06	1	0.309	21496.82	0.055
22	180	0.04	1.2	0.175	19490.45	0.253
23	180	0.05	0.8	0.163	14211.78	-0.050
24	180	0.06	1	0.227	24363.06	-0.046
25	120	0.04	1.2	0.196	13757.96	0.234
26	120	0.05	0.8	0.181	10031.85	-0.084
27	120	0.06	1	0.161	17197.45	-0.099

In this experiment, the surface roughness value of each experiment was measured 3 times on a Renishaw Equator 300 CMM - High-Speed Comparative Gauge System (Figure 3) according to the EN ISO 4287 standard. The flatness deviation (FL, mm) is measured using a non-contact measurement system (Figure 3). According to STN P CEN ISO/TS 12781-2: 2008 standard, the flatness zone was divided into negative and positive (Figure 2) local zones based on the least squares reference plane, which is a plane such that the sum of the squares of the local flatness deviations is minimum. The measured results are summarized in Table IV.

The Material Removal Rate-MRR (mm³/min) of each experiment is calculated by:

$$MRR = a_p \times a_e \times N \times S \times f_z \quad (4)$$

where a_p is the depth of cut (mm). In this experimental work, $a_p=10$ mm for all runs. a_r is the width of cut (mm), N is the number of cut flutes ($N=3$), S is the spindle speed (rpm), and f_z is the feed of tooth (mm/tooth).

The matrix of the experiment design with the input factors and the response data is presented in Table IV. These data were utilized to develop the regression models for R_a , MRR, and FL.

D. The Optimization Problem

The machining parameters, i.e. cutting speed V_c , feed rate f_z , and width of cut a_r , and their corresponding levels are listed in Table III. The target of this research is to decrease the flatness deviation FL and improve the MRR concerning the predefined R_a . Consequently, the optimizing issue can be described as (5):

Find $X=\{V_c, f_z, a_r\}$ to minimize $\{R_a, FL\}$, and maximize MRR subjected to $120 \leq V_c \leq 180$ (m/min); $0.04 \leq f_z \leq 0.06$ (mm/tooth) and $0.8 \leq a_r \leq 1.2$ (mm) (5)

To solve this multi-object problem, the DFA was adopted. The desirability package contains S3 classes to optimize multiple variables simultaneously using the DFA of Harrington [24-26] (1965) with the functions described in [24, 25]. Basically, the method is to translate the functions to a common scale ([0, 1]), combine them using the geometric mean and optimize the overall index. For each function R , an individual "desirability" function is constructed to be high when $f_r(x)$ is at the desired level (such as maximum, minimum, or target) and low when the $f_r(x)$ is at an unwanted level value. Authors in [27] proposed three forms of these functions, corresponding to the type of optimization goal. To maximize $f_r(x)$, d_r^{max} , d_r^{min} are obtained for maximization and minimization purposes, while d_r^{target} represents for the best solution.

$$d_r^{max} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } f_r(x) < A \\ \left(\frac{f_r(x)-A}{B-A}\right)^S & \text{if } A \leq f_r(x) \leq B \\ 1 & \text{if } f_r(x) > B \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$d_r^{min} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } f_r(x) > B \\ \left(\frac{f_r(x)-B}{A-B}\right)^S & \text{if } A \leq f_r(x) \leq B \\ 1 & \text{if } f_r(x) < A \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$d_r^{target} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{f_r(x)-A}{t_0-A}\right)^{S1} & \text{if } A \leq f_r(x) \leq t_0 \\ \left(\frac{f_r(x)-B}{t_0-B}\right)^{S2} & \text{if } t_0 \leq f_r(x) \leq B \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Regression models

The regression models for R_a , MRR, and FL were generated using Minitab Software. Equations (9)-(11) show the fully developed regression models.

$$R_a = -1.609 + 0.04550V_c - 38.20f_z - 1.066a_r - 0.000188V_c^2 + 173.9f_z^2 + 0.2767a_r^2 + 0.1307V_c f_z + 0.002964V_c \cdot a_r + 2.53a_r f_z \quad (9)$$

$$MRR = 16932 - 115.4V_c - 338641f_z - 17516a_r - 0.0000V_c^2 + 0.0000f_z^2 + 0.0000a_r^2 + 2309V_c f_z + 119.43V_c \cdot a_r + 340318a_r f_z \quad (10)$$

$$FL = -2.390 + 0.05237V_c - 33.26f_z - 1.267a_r - 0.000188V_c^2 + 465.7f_z^2 + 1.470a_r^2 + 0.0490V_c f_z + 0.00407V_c \cdot a_r - 26.42a_r f_z \quad (11)$$

To assess the adequacy of these models, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was adopted. The ANOVA was conducted with 95% of confidence and 5% significance. The ANOVA results for the predictive models are presented in Tables V-VII.

The coefficients of mathematical regression models, including "R²", "adjusted R²", and "predicted R²", reveal the accuracy of the developed models. In this work, the values of "R²", "adjusted R²", and "predicted R²" for R_a , MRR, and FL are fluctuated in the range of [96.66%, 99.93%], [94.89%,

99.89%], and [89.78%, 99.76%] mean a good fitting between the experimental and the predicted values. Hence, it is concluded that the developed models of R_a , MRR, and FL can be used for predicting the optimal process parameters.

TABLE V. ANOVA FOR THE PREDICTIVE MODELS OF R_a

Term	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Regression	9	0.102879	0.011431	54.64	0
V_c	1	0.039154	0.039154	187.14	0
f_z	1	0.006102	0.006102	29.16	0
a_r	1	0.003528	0.003528	16.86	0.001
$V_c * V_c$	1	0.079044	0.079044	377.8	0
$f_z * f_z$	1	0.001814	0.001814	8.67	0.009
$a_r * a_r$	1	0.001452	0.001452	6.94	0.017
$V_c * f_z$	1	0.012573	0.012573	60.09	0
$V_c * a_r$	1	0.004044	0.004044	19.33	0
$f_z * a_r$	1	0.000413	0.000413	1.97	0.178
Error	17	0.003557	0.000209		
Total	26	0.106436			

"R²"=96.66%, "Adjusted R²"=94.89% and "predicted R²"=89.78%

TABLE VI. ANOVA FOR THE PREDICTIVE MODELS OF MRR

Term	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Regression	9	728005304	80889478	2553.25	0
V_c	1	199266	199266	6.29	0.023
f_z	1	720212	720212	22.73	0
a_r	1	1209228	1209228	38.17	0
$V_c * V_c$	1	1999162	1999162	63.1	0
$f_z * f_z$	1	0	0	0	1
$a_r * a_r$	1	4602114	4602114	145.26	0
$V_c * f_z$	1	3998324	3998324	126.21	0
$V_c * a_r$	1	6685664	6685664	211.03	0
$f_z * a_r$	1	9204227	9204227	290.53	0
Error	17	538577	31681		
Total	26	728543881			

"R²"=99.93%, "Adjusted R²"=99.89% and "predicted R²"=99.76%

TABLE VII. ANOVA FOR THE PREDICTIVE MODELS OF FL

Term	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Regression	9	0.315328	0.035036	97.42	0
V_c	1	0.058999	0.058999	164.04	0
f_z	1	0.002633	0.002633	7.32	0.015
a_r	1	0.006217	0.006217	17.28	0.001
$V_c * V_c$	1	0.08127	0.08127	225.96	0
$f_z * f_z$	1	0.013011	0.013011	36.17	0
$a_r * a_r$	1	0.03372	0.03372	93.75	0
$V_c * f_z$	1	0.001546	0.001546	4.3	0.054
$V_c * a_r$	1	0.000111	0.000111	0.31	0.585
$f_z * a_r$	1	0.054928	0.054928	152.72	0
Error	17	0.006114	0.00036		
Total	26	0.321442			

"R²"= 98.10%, "Adjusted R²"=97.09% and "predicted R²"=96.09%

B. Multiple Objective Optimization results

As mentioned above, the DFA was adopted for solving the multiple objective problem (Figure 4). The Composite Desire Values (D) corresponding to 27 experiments were computed using the Minitab 19 software with the constrain from (5). The results are shown in Table VIII.

Fig. 4. Surface plot of (a) FL, (b) R_a , (c) MRR vs V_c, f_z, a_r .

TABLE VIII. COMPOSITE DESIRABILITY VALUE (D)

Solution	V_c	f_z	a_r	FL fit	MRR fit	R_a Fit	D
1	120	0.060	1.131	-0.07	19829.00	0.145	0.769
2	120	0.060	1.180	-0.04	20596.40	0.149	0.763
3	120	0.060	1.199	-0.03	20866.70	0.151	0.758
4	120	0.060	1.200	-0.03	20879.10	0.151	0.757
5	180	0.058	1.052	-0.04	24881.10	0.223	0.718
6	180	0.060	1.034	-0.04	25165.70	0.233	0.699
7	180	0.060	1.012	-0.04	24533.80	0.230	0.698
8	180	0.060	1.137	0.00	27867.10	0.255	0.662

The higher the value of D, the more optimal the experiment is. In this study, the optimal parameter set $V_c = 120\text{m/min}$, $f_z = 0.06\text{mm}$, $a_r = 1.13131\text{mm}$ correspond to $R_a = 0.144601\mu\text{m}$, $\text{MRR} = 19829\text{cm}^3/\text{min}$, and $\text{FL} = -0.00699460\text{mm}$.

Comparing the optimization results with the resurged results shown in Table I, it is easy to see that the optimization results are quite close to the experiment number 27. However, the difference is that the predicted a_r value is larger than the selected a_r value, at 1mm and 1.131mm, respectively. This increase in the width of the cut led to an increase in production rate by about 15.30%, from 17197.45 to 19829 cm^3/min . At the same time, the surface roughness value R_a decreased by 13.10%, from 0.1613 to 0.1446 μm and the FL also decreased by -0.07mm, a decrease of 29.65%.

The results of this study show the advantages of DFA in comparison with DCDM. The disadvantage of DCDM is that the optimal parameter set is calculated, ranked, and selected

from one of the experimental runs, in this case, experiment number 27. With the DFA method, the optimal parameters do not necessarily coincide with the selected parameters. The comparison results are clearly depicted in Table IX.

TABLE IX. OPTIMIZATION RESULT COMPARISON

	Cutting parameters			Responses		
	V_c (m/min)	f_z (mm)	a_r (mm)	R_a (μm)	MRR (cm^3/min)	FL (mm)
Actual value	120	0.06	1	0.1613	17197.45	-0.0995
Predicted value	120	0.060	1.131	0.145	19829.00	-0.07
Comparison				↓13.10%	↑15.30%	↓29.65%

III. CONCLUSION

Due to the increasing competitive pressure from the global market, the need to maintain or increase product quality while simultaneously increasing productivity is important. This is a multi-objective optimization problem. In this article, the multiple objective optimization issue in thin-walled milling of 6061 aluminum alloy for reducing flatness deviation FL and surface roughness R_a while improving production rate MRR simultaneously, has been addressed. Predictive mathematical regression models of the three responses have been developed to model the highly non-linear relations between the cutting parameters (i.e. V_c, f_z , and a_r) and the machining responses. The Desirability Function Approach (DFA) was employed to

generate the optimum parameters. The main results of this work can be concluded, as follows:

The "R²", "adjust-R²" and "predicted-R²" of R_a, MRR, and FL fluctuated around 90-99%, illustrating the good relationship between cutting parameters and response. Hence, these mathematical regression models could be applied in the actual manufacturing process to predict the cutting parameters set corresponding to the desired response. The obtained optimal cutting parameters set of thin-walled milling of 6061 aluminum alloy processes is (V_c=120m/min, f_c=0.06mm, and a_r=1.13434mm), corresponding to the R_a, MRR, and FL values of 0.14269μm, 19614.6mm³/min, and -0.0653mm, respectively.

The findings in this research work can contribute to a broader understanding of aluminum alloy thin-walled milling and can be extended to research with other materials and machining processes. In future works, other cutting parameters such as tool nose radius, tool coating material, lubrication method, number of inserts, number of flutes, and other responses including cutting force, cutting variation, tool wear, and tool life will be taken into consideration.

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Huffman Encoding with White Tailed Eagle Algorithm-based Image Steganography Technique

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ABSTRACT

Since the Internet is a medium for transporting sensitive data, the privacy of the message transported has become a major concern. Image steganography has become a prominent tool for hiding data to ensure privacy during transfer. An efficient steganography system is essential to accomplish the best embedding capacity and maintain the other parameters at a satisfying level. Image encryption systems provide a secure and flexible system to maintain the privacy of image conversion and storage in the transmission system. Many existing image steganography methods can be attacked by various techniques, or do not support many image formats for embedding. To resolve these shortcomings, this study presents the Huffman Encoding with White Tailed Eagle Algorithm-based Image Steganography (HEWTEA-IS) technique, aiming to achieve secrecy with no compromise in image quality. The HEWTEA-IS method uses Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) for the decomposition of images into different subbands, and Huffman encoding to determine the embedding bits on the decomposed blocks and offer an additional layer of security. Moreover, the WTEA resolves the problem of imperceptibility by identifying the optimal probable position in the cover image for embedding secret bits. The proposed algorithm was simulated and examined in terms of different measures, and an extensive experimental analysis ensured that it is superior to other methods in several aspects.

Keywords-image steganography; embedding process; Huffman encoding; image decomposition; security

I. INTRODUCTION

Steganography is the procedure for embedding secret or confidential data in cover media such as video, text, image, and audio files. Cover mediums with a higher level of redundancy are more suitable for steganography [1, 2]. A digital image can be used as a cover medium to transmit confidential data embedded in the Least Significant Bit (LSB) of a pixel. Steganography can be utilized to securely transmit and store data and can have other applications, such as content authentication, copyright protection, and data integrity assurance [3]. Various data-hiding methods have been explored and several valuable steganographic methods have been proposed to improve security and protect data against unauthorized access [4, 5]. In information-hiding mechanisms, the three quality parameters considered are robustness, capacity, and imperceptibility [6]. These parameters are very important in image steganography. Robustness determines the degree of security from hackers or eavesdroppers during data transmission, imperceptibility means that the hidden information and the original cover image are indistinct, and capacity defines the amount of hidden data or image size that is transferred [7-10].

An image steganography method is generally assessed from five different aspects: computational costs, perceptual transparency (visual quality), temper resistance, payload (embedding) capacity, and security. Visual quality is regarded as good whenever the variance between the stego and the original image can be invisible to the Human Vision System (HVS) [11]. The embedding capacity is determined by the volume of data hidden in the cover images and can be measured by Bits Per Pixel (BPP). A high payload permits a high confidential data insertion into the host images. Security is the capacity of a mechanism to protect confidential data from any intruder. Image steganography can provide superior imperceptibility and payload [12]. Steganography methods having less distorted stego images are much more secure compared to others with more distortion, as they do not allure the attention of an intruder [13-15]. An ideal steganographic method must have a large embedding capacity and outstanding visual quality. But, as visual quality can be the inverse proportion of embedding capability, increasing one variable results in massive compromise on the other.

In [16], a higher-capacity image steganography method was introduced utilizing GA. This method used LSB replacement steganography to embed confidential data. But confidential

data can be modified and rearranged by previously encoding them in the LSBs of cover imageries. The variables utilized for rearranging and modifying the confidential data could be managed by the GA. A unique idea named flexible chromosomes was presented, which permitted GA to interpret chromosome values in distinct techniques. GA tried to discover the optimal variable values that have a high visual quality in the stego images. In [17], an image steganography method related to Integer Wavelet Transform (IWT) was presented. Using IWT, the cover image was converted to suppress the confidential message into the HL, HH, and LH frequency bands of the cover image. According to their Most Significant Bits (MSBs), the coefficients of these bands were labeled into 6 classes. All coefficients from various bands belonging to the same class were gathered. The embedding procedure was initiated from the highest class by supervising the coefficients to match the secret message size. In [18], an image steganography method was presented that used LSB and secret map methods by implementing 3D chaotic maps, such as 3D logistic and Chebyshev maps, to improve security. This approach utilized the idea of performing random insertion and choosing a pixel from a host image. In [19], a novel hybrid technique named Compressed Encrypted Data Embedding (CEDE) was presented. In this method, the confidential data were initially compressed with the Lempel-Ziv-Welch (LZW) compressing method. The compressed secret data were encoded using Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) symmetric block ciphers. In the final stage, the encoded data were encoded into 512x512 pixel images. The encoded and compressed secret data bits were split into sets of two bits, and the cover image pixels were also ordered in four pairs. In [20], a steganography method was presented that utilized chaos theory and PSO targeting to identify the optimal pixel in the cover image to hide confidential data while maintaining the prominence of the resulting stego images. To enhance embedding capacity, the secret and host images could be split into blocks that stored a suitable amount of secret bits. In [21], a DL-related steganography method was presented, using a deep supervised edge detector and CNN to retain more edge pixels than traditional edge-detection methods. The cover images were preprocessed by masking the latter 5 bits of all pixels, and the edge detector was used to obtain a grayscale edge map. In [22], emphasis was placed on improving the secret-sharing approach to enhance security along with simplicity and fast computation. This study solved certain published flaws in the share reconstruction stage by suggesting a new distribution method to increase security and authenticity.

The current study proposes Huffman Encoding with White Tailed Eagle Algorithm for Image Steganography (HEWTEA-IS). This method uses the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) to decompose images into different subbands, Huffman encoding to determine the embedding bits on the decomposed blocks and offer an additional layer of security, and White Tailed Eagle Algorithm (WTEA) to resolve the problem of imperceptibility by identifying the optimal probable position in the cover image to embed secret bits. The proposed method was simulated and examined with various measures.

II. PROPOSED MODEL

The proposed HEWTEA-IS method aims to achieve secrecy without compromising image quality. The HEWTEA-IS method encompasses different subprocesses, namely DWT-based image decomposition, embedding, Huffman encoding, WTEA-based pixel selection, and extraction.

A. Image Decomposition

The cover image is decomposed into different subbands. Wavelet Transforms (WT) can be used to identify individual locations in host images to hide confidential data [23]. These regions of the host image that are minimum sensible to HVS are recognized as frequency bands. The hidden data in these bands do not degrade the quality of the visual image significantly. These bands continuously comprise data on texture, edge, and sharp transitions of images. The Haar DWT coefficient was calculated horizontally and vertically. In horizontal, an image was decomposed to High-(H) and Low-(L) frequency bands, where L was computed by taking the average of 2 sequential pixels horizontally, and H by taking the variance between them. In vertical, L and H were again decomposed into 4 distinct subbands using High-Low (HL), Low-Low (LL), High-High (HH), and Low-High (LH) by taking the average and the variance between two vertically sequential pixels. The superior magnitudes of the wavelet coefficient show the most important data of the images. The magnitudes of the LL coefficients were superior to the other subbands (HH, LH, and HL) and comprise the smooth and plane region of an image that is extremely sensitive to human eyes. Thus, embedding even little data into the LL subbands results in maximum distortion. The other three subbands comprise edge details and sharp transitions in images. So, the data should be embedded in these three subbands. The Haar DWT coefficient was computed using pairwise average and variance as shown in (1) and (2):

$$S_{1,n} = \frac{(S_{0,2n} + S_{0,2n+1})}{2}; \quad D_{1,n} = S_{0,2n+1} - S_{0,2n} \quad (1)$$

The inverse of Haar DWT was computed by:

$$S_{0,2n} = S_{1,n} + \frac{D_{1,n}}{2}; \quad S_{0,2n+1} = S_{1,n} - \frac{D_{1,n}}{2} \quad (2)$$

At this point, $S_{0,2n}$, $S_{0,2n+1}$ are the sequential pixel values of cover images.

B. Embedding Process

Normally, the WTEA begins the search with an arbitrarily selected initial population. Using a fitness function, these randomly generated solutions are evaluated throughout iterations and are enhanced via a set of formulas until an ending condition is met. However, despite the differences between population-based methods, this technique shares baseline data. In this study, the search procedure was divided into exploration and exploitation stages [24]. Exploration includes searching the region for an open location that is farther from the existing location. The exploration phase takes place when a metaheuristic algorithm tries to find a better area. At the same time, exploitation explores the near-optimum point, focusing on the neighborhood of high-quality answers inside the search space. Executing exploration alone might lead to a

novel location with a poor degree of precision, while exploitation increases the risk of getting trapped in local optima. Several studies emphasized the importance of balancing exploitation and exploration in metaheuristic algorithms. Consequently, it is crucial to achieving an accurate balance between these two phases. This study used two different stages to carry out efficient exploitation and exploration. The WTEA step-by-step method can be described as:

- Step 1 - Population initialization: WTEA, begins the investigation via a set of randomly produced components (a set of eagles with a random location):

$$E_i = lb_i + rand \times (ub_i - lb_i); \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

where E_i is the location of the i -th eagle, ub_i and lb_i are the lower and upper boundaries, respectively, and $rand$ represents a random number within $[0,1]$.

- Step 2 - Population assessment: In this stage, the randomly generated solution is evaluated through a fitness function, and the eagle with optimal fitness value is selected as E_{Best} .
- Step 3 - Searching phase (exploration): White-tailed eagles search for prey within the search region they have chosen and move in diverse directions to accelerate their hunt. This process explores different regions using its randomized operator. Every eagle collaborates with the best and randomly interacts with others to upgrade the location. Figure 1 shows the steps involved in WTEA. This behavior is determined by:

$$E_i(t+1) = \begin{cases} E_i(t) + 2 \times r_1 \times (E_r(t) - E(t)) & \text{if } r_2 < 0.5 \\ E_i(t) + 2 \times r_1 \times (E_{Best}(t) - E_j(t)) & \text{if } r_2 \geq 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $E_i(t)$ is the location of i -th eagle in the search space at iteration t , E_{Best} is the location of the better eagle (adjacent to the prey), and r_1 and r_2 are random numbers within $[0,1]$.

- Step 4 - Improving phase (exploitation): Every eagle gets knowledge from the best candidate in the population. To improve the quality of the WTEA solution, every eagle interacts with the better eagle of the swarm E_{Best} , which has the highest influence on others to discover the prey:

$$E_i(t+1) = rand \times E_{Best}(t) + rand \times (E_{Best}(t) - E_i(t)) \quad (5)$$

- Step 5 - Movement limitation: In all iterations, WTEA alters the distance every eagle moves through every dimension of the scratch region. Equations (4) and (5) show that eagle movement is a stochastic parameter and could allow the eagle to follow a large distance. Consequently, to accomplish this oscillation and prevent the eagle divergence, any eagle that goes beyond the search space limit would be reproduced based on:

$$E_i = \begin{cases} lb_i & \text{if } E_i \leq lb_i \\ ub_i & \text{if } E_i \geq ub_i \\ E_j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

This model is used to select the best pixels to hide private information [25]. The optimum location is found by using the WTEA approach that implements initialization by arbitrarily

choosing particles and later searching for the better fit by upgrading each particle position. Initially, the population is chosen at random, and the location is upgraded through the objective function. Next, the better solution gets recognized to embed information. The original cover image is considered as O with $M \times N$ dimensions. Usually, the image can be described by a spatial representation. DWT is applied to convert them into a frequency domain. Then, the image undergoes sampling and decomposition to provide a higher degree of robustness as:

$$[O_1 O_2 O_3 O_4] = DWT(O) \quad (7)$$

where O_1 represents the coefficient of the lower frequency band and comprises each substantial data of the image, O_2 , O_3 , and O_4 indicate the higher-frequency bands and represent data such as edges of the image. The O_j band is carefully chosen for additional processing and the coefficient is extracted as:

$$[O_1^{LL} O_1^{LH} O_1^{HL} O_1^{HH}] = DWT(O_1) \quad (8)$$

where O_1^{LL} indicates the low-frequency subband, and O_1^{LH} , O_1^{HL} , and O_1^{HH} denote the high-frequency subbands of O_1 . Then, the stego image is created by:

$$C_1^{*j} = C_1^j + (D_j \times P_{opt}) \quad (9)$$

where D_j indicates the secret textual information, and P_{opt} is the optimal location for embedding the information. Inverse DWT is executed to characterize the image after data hiding:

$$O_1^{**} = IDWT(O_1^{*LL} O_1^{*LH} O_1^{*HL} O_1^{*HH}) \quad (10)$$

The embedded secret information with the adapted band is:

$$O^{**} = IDWT(O_1^{**} O_2 O_3 O_4) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 1. Steps involved in WTEA

C. Huffman Encoding

Huffman coding is a lossless data compression technique. Its objective is to allocate parameter-length code to input characters, as the length of the assigned code depends on the

frequency of the characters [26]. The more common character gets a smaller code, and the less common character gets a larger one. The parameter length code assigned to each input character is a prefix code, which implies that a code is assigned so that it is not the prefix assigned to any other. Huffman coding ensures that there is no ambiguity while decoding the bit stream.

1. Generate a leaf node for all input characters and construct a minimum heap of each leaf node.
2. For the minimum heap, obtain the topmost two nodes (N1 and N2) with the least frequency.
3. Generate a novel internal node N3 with a frequency equivalent to the sum of frequencies of nodes N1 and N2. Make N1 the left and N2 the right child of N3. A new node N3 is added to the minimum heap.
4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until the minimum heap has a single node.

D. Extraction Process

The objective is to successfully extract the secret messages from the input stego images on the receiver. The stego image undergoes DWT to transform it from spatial to frequency representation. The stego images are indicated as O^{**R} :

$$[O_1^{**R} O_2^{**R} O_3^{**R} O_4^{**R}] = DWT(O^{**R}) \tag{12}$$

The modified band is O_1^{**R} , therefore the coefficient of the sub-band is:

$$[O_1^{LL*} O_1^{LR*} O_1^{HL*} O_1^{HR*}] = DWT(O_1^{**R}) \tag{13}$$

Next, match the secret key and once it matches, the original secret message is extracted. WTEA is applied to locate the position of hidden information, and Huffman decoding is applied to extract the secret message. Thus, the stego image is attained in binary format. When the secret keys don't match, an encrypted image is received. The encrypted images are produced for adding another level of security to the system.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examines the security performance of the HEWTEA-IS algorithm on several images from the USC-SIPI repository [27]. The experimental values were assessed under varying Message Sizes (MS). Table I shows a result analysis of the HEWTEA-IS method under variable message sizes and images. The HEWTEA-IS model showed a good performance in all images. Figure 3 provides the results of the HEWTEA-IS method with different message sizes using Image 1. In this image, the HEWTEA-IS method gained an average MSE of 0.00012, an average PSNR of 126.36dB, an average BER of 0.033, and an average SSIM of 0.9993.

Figures 4, 5, and 6 show the results of the HEWTEA-IS method with different message sizes in Images 2 and 3. In these images, the HEWTEA-IS system achieved average MSE of 0.00011, 0.00013, and 0.00012, average PSNR of 127.05, 126.18, and 126.94dB, average BER of 0.035, 0.0034, and 0.032, and average SSIM of 0.9995, 0.9994, and 0.9995, respectively.

TABLE I. RESULTS ANALYSIS OF HEWTEA-IS APPROACH WITH DISTINCT IMAGES AND MEASURES

Images	Message size (KB)	MSE	PSNR (dB)	BER	SSIM
Image 1	50	0.00012	126.55	0.028	0.9992
	100	0.00011	127.30	0.035	0.9993
	150	0.00014	125.21	0.031	0.9995
	200	0.00015	124.61	0.042	0.9991
	250	0.00010	128.13	0.031	0.9994
Average		0.00012	126.36	0.033	0.9993
Image 2	50	0.00011	127.30	0.038	0.9994
	100	0.00010	128.13	0.034	0.9992
	150	0.00014	125.21	0.038	0.9998
	200	0.00011	127.30	0.029	0.9995
	250	0.00011	127.30	0.036	0.9996
Average		0.00011	127.05	0.035	0.9995
Image 3	50	0.00011	127.30	0.039	0.9991
	100	0.00015	124.61	0.037	0.9998
	150	0.00013	125.85	0.032	0.9997
	200	0.00011	127.30	0.030	0.9992
	250	0.00013	125.85	0.034	0.9992
Average		0.00013	126.18	0.034	0.9994
Image 4	50	0.00010	128.13	0.032	0.9998
	100	0.00015	124.61	0.029	0.9992
	150	0.00011	127.30	0.034	0.9997
	200	0.00012	126.55	0.031	0.9994
	250	0.00010	128.13	0.036	0.9992
Average		0.00012	126.94	0.032	0.9995

Fig. 2. Classification analysis of the HEWTEA-IS algorithm in Image 1: (a) MSE, (b) PSNR, (c) BER, (d) SSIM.

Table II shows the comparative results of the HEWTEA-IS with other recent methods, and Figure 7 shows a visual PSNR analysis of HEWTEA-IS with them. The HEWTEA-IS achieved the highest PSNR value of 126.634dB, HPSO and Huffman-PSO models had close PSNR values, while the PSO-DWT and PSO algorithms had the least PSNR values.

Figure 8 shows a comparative SSIM investigation of the HEWTEA-IS. The HEWTEA-IS had the highest SSIM of 0.9994, the HPSO and Huffman-PSO algorithms had close SSIM values, while PSO-DWT and PSO had the least SSIM.

Fig. 3. Classification analysis of the HEWTEA-IS algorithm in Image 2: (a) MSE, (b) PSNR, (c) BER, (d) SSIM.

Fig. 4. Classification analysis of the HEWTEA-IS algorithm in Image 3: (a) MSE, (b) PSNR, (c) BER, (d) SSIM.

Fig. 5. Classification analysis of the HEWTEA-IS algorithm in Image 4: (a) MSE, (b) PSNR, (c) BER, (d) SSIM.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF HEWTEA-IS WITH OTHER METHODS

Methods	MSE	PSNR (dB)	BER	SSIM
HEWTEA-IS	0.00012	126.634	0.0338	0.9994
PSO	4.26800	35.526	0.0520	0.9597
HPSO	0.00200	102.110	0.0492	0.9857
PSO-DWT	0.73000	50.864	0.0498	0.9764
Huffman-PSO	0.00020	122.110	0.0413	0.9935

Fig. 6. PSNR analysis of the HEWTEA-IS with recent methods.

Fig. 7. SSIM analysis of the HEWTEA-IS with other methods.

Figure 9 shows a detailed BER comparison of the HEWTEA-IS. The HEWTEA-IS had the least BER of 0.0338, while PSO, HPSO, PSO-DWT, and Huffman-PSO had increased BER of 0.0520, 0.0492, 0.0498, and 0.0413, respectively. These results affirmed the superiority of the HEWTEA-IS method.

Fig. 8. BER analysis of the HEWTEA-IS with other methods.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study presented the novel Huffman Encoding with White Tailed Eagle Algorithm for Image Steganography (HEWTEA-IS) with the purpose of achieving secrecy without compromising image quality. The proposed method used Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) for the decomposition of images into different subbands, Huffman encoding to determine the embedding bits on the decomposed blocks and offer an additional layer of security, and WTEA to resolve the problem of imperceptibility by identifying the optimal positions in the cover images for embedding secret bits. The proposed method was experimentally analyzed and compared to other recent methods in several aspects, showing its superiority. In the future, the HEWTEA-IS can be extended to audio messages.

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Context-Based Aspect-Oriented Requirement Engineering Model

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ABSTRACT

Mobile applications are context-oriented systems that involve the use of context information while operating. Mobile applications demand tackling context information in the early phase of software engineering. A context-aware system demands a different approach to handling the influence of the context on a system's requirements. Aspect-oriented Requirement Engineering separates concerns throughout requirements, called crosscutting concerns, in the early phase of software development to improve the modularity of complex applications. Capturing requirements embedded within context is a challenging procedure. This study aimed to identify such contextual characteristics of requirements in the early phase of software engineering, using natural language processing techniques, by proposing Context-Based Aspect-Oriented Requirement Engineering (CB-AORE) to visualize the existence of crosscutting concerns. CB-AORE performs context modeling to analyze the context dependency with base requirements and helps the analyst to visualize the correlation of functional and non-functional requirements with context. A case study analyzed the identification of context and its use to identify crosscutting concerns.

Keywords-context; context-aware system; crosscutting concern; aspect; aspect-oriented requirement engineering

I. INTRODUCTION

Requirement engineering is one of the important phases in software engineering, which includes a set of functional requirements specifying what functions a system should perform and a set of non-functional requirements specifying the performance characteristics of the functional features. Functional requirements present the operational view to both the client and the developer and must be satisfied in terms of ease of use and less cost. Due to their context-sensitive nature, mobile applications have some unique requirements that are less common in traditional software applications [1]. These requirements, including sensor handling, potential interactions with other applications from different sources, and embedded hardware devices [2], increase the complexity of mobile application development. Software engineering analysis specifies what the system is currently doing, and design specifies what a new or modified system will do [3]. System design includes a top-down approach, coupling, cohesion, span

of control, size, and sharing of modules. The top-down approach means understanding the problem at the top level and trying to exploit it at lower levels, which is also known as modularization. Object-Oriented Software Development (OOSD) handles the complexity of an application using modularization and abstraction [4]. In [5], a formal aspect-oriented requirement specification language was proposed, traced with the structural model, for complex system analysis. In [6], a role-based requirement modeling technique was proposed to facilitate analysis in the development of large and complex systems involving a large number of stakeholders.

OOSD aims to provide independence between modules, improve reusability, faster development, and reduced cost. However, Aspect-Oriented Software Development (AOSD) does these in a much better way [7] and is possible by separating concerns. Aspect-Oriented Programming (AOP) introduces a new term called aspect, which represents crosscutting concerns as a module [8]. Usually, concerns refer

to the functionality offered by the system. AOP can be used for complex cryptographic modeling and security simulation without changing legacy code [9]. Aspect-Oriented Requirements Engineering (AORE) is an early phase in AOSD that identifies crosscutting concerns at the level of requirements [10]. The process of separating concerns is called crosscutting concerns [11, 12], which is required in applying AOSD methods.

This paper proposes a requirement modeling process using additional context-specific requirements from a software requirement specification document and identifies crosscutting functional and non-functional requirements. Engineering context-aware software systems, such as mobile applications, face many challenges [13]. Context is any information that can be used to characterize the situation of an entity, such as a person, place, or object, necessary for the interaction between the user and the application [14]. This model was inspired by the multidimensional approach for separating concerns and identifying homogeneous crosscutting concerns [15-16]. Homogeneous cross-cutting concerns are concerns that add the same behavioral variation at multiple points in the program [11]. Moreover, the multi-dimensional approach treats all concerns at the same level and visualizes them from meta-concern and system spaces. A contribution matrix, developed from the compositional intersection of concerns, provides trade-off points that help to make architectural choices for the system [15]. However, the multidimensional approach lacks explicit relationship interaction [17].

The proposed Context-Based Aspect-Oriented Requirement Engineering (CB-AORE) method provides immediate traceability at a high level of design. The future scope of CBAORE specifies the articulation of the dependency relationship structure. This model contends that context-relevant data must be gathered from the standard set of requirements. There is a need for decomposing requirements based on context to identify context-based functional and non-functional requirements. The aim of the paper is twofold: classify typical requirements into functional and non-functional and then apply the proposed CB-AORE technique to identify crosscutting concerns in the early phase of software development.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed model used context-related requirement elements by studying requirements less commonly found in traditional software [1]. This was a two-fold activity. At first, a survey was conducted with a sample questionnaire to identify the need for a context-based model for requirement engineering. The second activity primarily focused on the extraction of mobile applications' specific requirements exhibiting special characteristics related to context. These requirements were extracted from 20 requirements documents for various mobile applications. The various contexts identified in the literature and SRS documents of earlier projects were Sensors Context, Device Context, Transactional Context, Network Context, Mobility Context, Social Context, and Third Party Software Integration [18]. The special requirements for mobile applications were the use of sensors for human interactions, the use of embedded devices, and various

transactions using a network. Based on special requirements, the sample questions to investigate the need for context categories, relevant context elements, and activity of the mobile application are:

- Q1: Do you find that requirement analysis based on context consideration in mobile applications will help programmers?
- Q2: Do you find the context-based requirement model understandable?
- Q3: Were you able to identify individual functional requirements and their relevant context?
- Q4: Do you agree that the implementation of mobile context-sensitive applications can be facilitated by the context-based requirement model?
- Q5: Do you think that the development of mobile context-aware applications can be facilitated by a model that enables the automatic production of classes and methods?
- Q6: Do you agree that exposing the context dependencies with the functional requirements makes it easier to explain to a business user of the app?
- Q7: How does the application adjust to the context?
- Q8: Do you find interdependency in the context?
- Q9: Were you able to identify non-functional requirements from context?

As there is not a specific set definition for context, everyone can provide his perspective on it, which can be categorized into different classes. The proposed model was inspired by the multidimensional approach to the separation of contexts in requirement analysis, which applies uniform treatment to different types of requirements [17]. The proposed CB-AORE model overcame the drawbacks of the multidimensional approach, such as exhibiting a lack of explicit relationship interaction among different requirements. Seven context dimensions were identified and were embedded in the CB-AORE model, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. CONTEXT CATEGORIES

Context	Context elements	Activity description
Device context	Camera, microphone, speaker, battery	Accessing camera, microphone, speaker, battery, device infrastructure/facilities such as time,date etc.
Sensor context	Accelerometer, proximity	Accessing sensors functionality/services
Transactional context	Internal storage, External storage (cloud)	Accessing data/information on/off mobile device, modify, add, delete data with I/O
Network context	Internet, wifi, Bluetooth	Accessing web server through Internet connection or Bluetooth
Mobility context	GPRS, GPS	Accessing map and location and provide navigation facility
Social context	Sharing, notification	Sharing information among users through social networks
Third party Software Integration	API	Integrating app with third party services such as newsfeed service, payment gateways etc.

Fig. 1. Engineering model of CB-AORE.

These dimensions are:

- Device context: Contains mobile device features that allow users to access information about any web domain area. The features of a mobile device can be broken down into its technological, functional, and physical attributes [19-20]. Physical attributes include weight, overall size, screen size, and resolution [21], functional attributes include input processes, gestures, and output mechanisms, technological attributes include CPU speed and storage capacity, and functional attributes include elements such as camera, microphone, etc. [22].
- Sensor context: Mobile e-health apps use a variety of sensors, including an accelerometer, a low-pass filter, and a magnitude filter, to track the body's diabetes levels while the user is moving, walking, or running [23-24]. The motion, posture, and location of a mobile device can be identified by the 3D accelerometer, digital compass, etc. Dedicated context-aware frameworks were developed to integrate sensor data, complex events, and data storage [25].
- Transactional context: It is important for taking any kind of input data and analyzing them [26]. Such mechanisms transfer data to and from internal or external storage.
- Network context: Characterizes the ability of a wireless mobile device to move from one area to another while still being able to access the data connection network facility from anywhere inside the network zone [24]. The present, growing wireless network technologies and mobile applications depend on it in fundamental ways.
- Mobility context: Applies to the attributes and functionalities of mobile applications that use network and location elements [27].
- Social context: Characterizes the activity that involves the exchange of information from one user to another through social media [19]. This context determines social relations through social media tools such as wikis, content hosting, social networking platforms, blogs, and podcasting.

- Third-Party Software Integration (TPSI) context: Captures elements of mobile apps and devices on the integration of extended functionality deployed on multiple platforms [21].

III. THE CB-AORE MODEL

In software engineering, a software requirement specification document represents requirements at a higher level of abstraction [3]. Context analysis is performed on user requirements with the help of a context repository. Then, context interdependency analysis activities are mainly carried out by using syntactic analysis with natural language processing techniques. Further dependency analysis of context with requirements is used to identify dependencies among aspects. Dependency analysis is carried out by establishing dependency links among contexts and between contexts and requirements. Contexts are extracted and analyzed from textual requirements. However, this requires understanding the effects of context on different requirements with reasoning [28]. Therefore, the context model can be expressed as follows:

- Definition 1: A Context Model is 2-tuple $CM = (C, DL)$, where:

C is a finite set of contexts, $C \neq \Phi$;

$DL \subset (C \times C)$ is a set of dependency links.

- Definition 2: c is one context of the set C with the following properties:

1. $c.dec$ represents the decomposition of context based on functional and non-functional requirements.
2. $c.level$ represents the level of context. The value set of $c.level$ is $\{user, system\}$, representing that c is *user* or *system* context, respectively.
3. $c.link$ represents whether *context* c has links to FR, NFR, and other contexts. The value set of $c.link$ is $\{1,0\}$.
4. $c.type$ represents the type of context. The value set of $c.type$ is $\{Sensor\ context, System\ context, Transactional\ context, Network\ context, Mobility\ context, Social\ context, Third\ party\ Software\ Integration, GUI, Search, Misc\}$

The potential relationship and dependency links are conceptualized using the CB-AORE model. The model is represented with the help of ROADMAP and I* notations, as shown in Tables II and III. Table IV shows sample sets of text requirements from the inSEption mobile application. This mobile application was developed to guide students who have just arrived on campus.

TABLE II. ROADMAP NOTATIONS

Notation	Role description
	Nonfunctional requirement
	Context
	Role

TABLE III. I* NOTATIONS

Notation	Role description
	Context
	Nonfunctional requirement
	Actor
	Context dependency

TABLE IV. REQUIREMENT TEXT

R1	The user should be able to search for a certain point of interest and navigate from a specific location to another.
R2	The application should provide a map view of the campus.
R3	The application shows all upcoming events regarding the university as provided in an RSS feed
R4	Any event should be presented in a calendar form and should be searchable.
R5	The application shows news items regarding the university as provided in an RSS feed.
R6	The application enables the student to read the student handbook
R7	Facebook link directs the students to the facebook page of the university/ability to view other facebook pages related to university/ furthermore uses facebook functionalities such as 'Like', 'Share'.
R8	Twitter application directs student to the twitter page of the university.
R9	The user can search for personnel information available on the university server.

NLP techniques were applied in stages for context realization. Context repository extracted the context categories from the requirements text. In the second step, context initiation either by the system or user was identified. Context dependencies with non-functional requirements are established through text processing and mapping. The mapping function of any subject clause x in non-functional requirements that matches the vocabulary of a context category is:

$$f_{map(NF_m, C_n)}(x) = 1 \tag{1}$$

where m is the number of the non-functional requirement and n is the number of the context category. Similarly, for functional requirements:

$$f_{map(F_m, C_n)}(x) = 1 \tag{2}$$

Requirements R1 to R9 are either initiated by the user or the system. The "view map" functionality in R1 requires the network context, so the mobility context depends on it. In R9, when accessing personnel information from a server, the transactional context depends on the networking context. Functional requirements are passed through NLP processes to identify contexts initiated by actors. As shown in the diagram, mobility context is captured from activity descriptions such as 'search location' or 'navigate' in R1. Similarly, R2 realizes

mobility context. However, context is initiated by the user in the first case and by the system in the latter.

Figure 2 shows context realization through context elements for the actor. R1 and R2 depend on mobility context. Mobility context depends on network context, as it requires a data connection context element for map view. To provide updated news, the system depends on TPSI which is possible using an API context element and the network context's Internet context element. Every context element specifies a nonfunctional requirement so that realization can successfully satisfy the requirement. In this scenario, to provide a map view, network context must provide a network context element with the required speed and bandwidth, i.e. reliability and availability. Likewise, all requirements are mapped with their related context element.

Figure 3 shows the dependency between a context element and a functional requirement. A context element related to a functional requirement exhibits the latter's dependency on the context. For example, 'R8: redirect to Facebook' and 'R7: redirect to Twitter' are functional requirements related to social media activity and depend on Wi-Fi or the internet connection context element. Figure 3 visualizes the dependencies of the functional requirements R7 and R8 with the social context and the network context. Thus, context elements through specific services fulfill functional requirements and also specify the needed non-functional requirements to successfully execute it.

Fig. 2. Context and nonfunctional requirement dependencies.

Fig. 3. Context and functional requirement dependencies.

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CB-AORE WITH OTHER AORE MODELS

Numerous methods have been proposed to identify early aspects using different techniques. In [29], an extensive comparative analysis on the Theme/Doc approach and Multidimensional Separation of Concerns for Requirements Engineering (MDSOCRE) was performed, concluding that MDSOCRE focuses on the analyst's domain knowledge, and Theme/Doc analyses the requirements language while looking for the concern name [29]. The performance of the proposed method was verified by comparing it with goal-based AORE [16], viewpoint-based AORE [1], and multidimensional separation of concerns in requirements engineering [15] methods. Table V shows a brief comparison.

TABLE V. CB-AORE COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS

Parameters	CB-AORE	GEA Goal based [16]	PREView View point based [1]	Multi-Dimensional Separation of Concerns in Requirements Engineering [15]
Applicability for mobile application	Yes	No	No	Yes
Requirement modeling	Mobile context-based	Goal and soft goal based	Viewpoint based	Multi-dimensional
Composability	Per context element and requirement	Per goal and softgoal	Per view	Per meta concern space and system space
Handling of functional and non-functional concern	Both	Functional	Non-functional	Both
Stakeholder scope	Mobile device, developer, system, and user	Analyst, developer		Not applicable
Methodology	Natural language analysis	Fuzzy logic, clustering technique	Fuzzy logic	XML-based composition specification language to specify the composition rules

A detailed comparison highlights the following:

- Use of requirement elicitation artifact: Goal-based AORE uses a case model by analyzing goal interaction, where the structure of goals considers various facets of requirements. The viewpoint-based approach divides requirements using a viewpoint to derive candidate aspects in the analysis phase. The proposed CB-AORE model relies on functional and non-functional requirements from any requirement document and realizes context by mapping the requirements with the context repository.
- Candidate early aspect realization technique: In the Goal-based approach, early aspects are identified by grouping goal interactions using a clustering algorithm. In the viewpoint approach, each candidate's early aspect is qualified with the help of concerns that are non-functional

requirements. A candidate's early aspect is the concern that cuts across multiple viewpoints. In CB-AORE, context is the candidate aspect that cuts across functional and non-functional requirements.

- Software application domain: The Goal-based approach targets software system applications that have large concentration of only functional and nonfunctional characteristics to describe the requirements of the application. The Viewpoint-based approach also relies on the functional and non-functional characteristics of any software system. So both approaches fail to accommodate context characteristics exhibited by mobile software applications. The CB-AORE approach helps to envision the interactions not only between functional and non-functional requirements but also context.

V. DISCUSSION

Many initiatives have been proposed to collect and relate aspect-oriented requirements in the early stages of software development [4, 11-12, 16, 29-30]. However, the proposed method decomposes the requirements based on contexts, which are special characteristics of a mobile application's functional and non-functional requirements. The further decomposition of contextual requirements into heterogeneous and homogeneous was not considered. Furthermore, it would be interesting to focus on tracking contextual aspects in architectural decisions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed the possibility of using context in mobile applications to derive dependencies among functional and non-functional requirements in the early phase of requirement engineering. Requirement engineering of mobile applications can utilize context characteristics to achieve better modularity for developing mobile software applications using an emerging AOSD paradigm. A case study of the presented CB-AORE gave an insight into how context dependencies of functional and non-functional requirements can identify crosscutting concerns and early aspects. Future work should articulate dependency structure for describing relationships among context, functional, and non-functional requirements and also aim to strengthen the composition ability of aspects.

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Computation of Limit Loads for Bending Plates

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to present a method for calculating the upper bound limit loads of plate bending using a conforming Hsieh-Clough-Tocher (HCT) element. These limit loads can be obtained from Koiter's kinematic shakedown theorem for the case of one load vertex instead of using the kinematic limit theorem. When combining this theorem with the approximated displacement field, the limit analysis turns into an optimization problem and can be effectively solved by Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP). Several benchmark plate problems such as square, rectangular, and L-shape plates are investigated to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed solution. The results of the proposed method show good agreement with the results of previous studies. The maximum error is only 2.91% for the fully clamped rectangular plate problem.

Keywords-plate bending; limit analysis; second-order cone programming; plates; shakedown

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant issues in structure engineering is the determination of the safety load factors. Limit analysis is a well-known efficient approach for resolving the issue. These limit loads can be calculated by using the lower- or upper-bound theorems of limit analysis. However, it is very difficult to apply these two theorems to tackle general problems when using analytical methods [1]. Therefore, the current research is mainly concentrated on computational methods. Authors in [2, 3] carried out experimental tests in order to understand the punching shear behavior of concrete slabs reinforced by steel collars and hybrid fibers. Author in [4] studied the limit state of local instability of steel column structures under axial compression using the energy method combined with the finite element method using fiber beam-column elements. Authors in [5] employed the shaft-grouted method to improve the bearing capacity of barrette piles for high-rise buildings in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. Authors in [6] developed a new effective finite element modeling for predicting the ultimate strength of concrete-filled steel tube columns under axial compression. Authors in [7, 8] studied steel frames under static and earthquake loadings with limit load analysis methods. Various discretization techniques have been developed to treat the limit problems such as finite elements [9-12], meshfree methods [13-17], and isogeometric analysis [18].

Limit analysis of plate bending has been extensively investigated, analytically and numerically [19, 20]. In [19],

limit loads of plate bending were studied in both Kirchhoff and Mindlin plate models based on the upper bound theorem and the finite element method. A dual algorithm combined with DKQ elements for limit and shakedown analyses of plate bending was proposed in [21]. One of the most efficient methods to conduct plate bending limit analysis was developed by Canh [12, 17], where SOCP was utilized in conjunction with conforming the HCT element or the meshless Element-Free Galerkin (EFG) method. Based on this approach, the aim of this research is to provide a solution to determine the upper bound load factors of plate bending with the combination of the HCT element and SOCP. However, the limit loads will be determined from Koiter's kinematic shakedown theorem for the case of one load vertex instead of using the kinematic theorem of limit analysis as in [12]. The advantage of this approach is that it can be easily extended to the shakedown problem. In addition, having calculated the stress components, it is possible to determine the failure mode of structures such as alternating plasticity for non-shakedown problems [22].

II. LIMIT ANALYSIS FORMULATION OF PLATE BENDING BASED ON THE SHAKEDOWN APPROACH

Consider a rigid-perfectly plastic plate that has a closed boundary with plane area A . Let ∂A_σ and ∂A_ϵ denote static and kinematic boundaries respectively. Neglecting the shear deformation, the kinematic relations of thin plates can be described as:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\kappa}_{xx} & \dot{\kappa}_{yy} & 2\dot{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \nabla^2 \dot{w} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}$ denotes the curvature rate vector, \dot{w} is the transversal velocity, and the operator ∇^2 is expressed by:

$$\nabla^2 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} & \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} & 2\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \end{bmatrix}^T$$

Let $\mathbf{m} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{xx} & m_{yy} & 2m_{xy} \end{bmatrix}^T$ and p be the vector of bending moments and the transversal load, respectively. The equilibrium relation can be defined as:

$$\left(\nabla^2\right)^T \mathbf{m} - p = 0 \quad (2)$$

In this study, the von Mises yield condition is adopted, and the internal dissipation power of the plate bending (or the dissipation rate) can be described as:

$$D^p(\dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}) = m_p \sqrt{\dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}^T \mathbf{Q} \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 2 & 0 \\ 2 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

and $m_p = \sigma_y h^2/4$ is the plastic limit moment per unit length of a plate section in which h and σ_y denote the plate thickness and the yield stress, respectively.

Next, consider a structure simultaneously submitted to NL linearly independently varying loads $\hat{P}_k = (k = 1, 2, \dots, NL)$ which form a convex polyhedral load domain. According to Koiter's theorem [23], by applying mathematical programming theory, an upper bound of the shakedown load factor α^+ can be rewritten in the form of non-linear programming as follows (the superscript p of dissipation rate function is skipped for simplicity):

$$\alpha^+ = \min \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \int_A D(\dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_k) dA$$

$$s.t \begin{cases} \Delta \boldsymbol{\kappa} = \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_k = \nabla^2 \dot{w} \\ \dot{w} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial A_u \\ \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \int_A \mathbf{m}^e(x, \hat{P}_k)^T \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_k dA = 1, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{m}^e is the fictitious elastic moment vector of the point x on the domain A .

Note that, when $NL = 1$ the problem (5) reduces that of limit analysis. Then, the formulation for the upper bound limit load is determined as follows:

$$\alpha^+ = \min \int_A D^p(\dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}) dA$$

$$s.t \begin{cases} \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} = \nabla^2 \dot{w} \\ \dot{w} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial A_u \\ \int_A \mathbf{m}^e \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} dA = 1, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Compared to the kinematic theorem of limit analysis as presented in [12], the difference of (6) is that the work rate of the applied load constraint is replaced by the external work rate constraint. In general, problem (6) is complicated because it has to calculate the stress components. However, as mentioned above, it can be advantageous to develop the shakedown problem. In addition, the failure mode of alternating plasticity can be determined easily when the structure is subjected to repeated loads.

III. HCT-BASED KINEMATIC FORMULATION

The conforming HCT element has been detailed in [12, 24]. The key idea of the HCT element is to divide an original triangular element into three sub-elements as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. HCT element.

The number of the total degrees of freedom of the element is 12 including 3 degrees at each corner node and 3 degrees at three mid-side nodes. In terms of area coordinates $\zeta = (\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$, at each sub-triangle, we can express the displacement expansion $w^{(k)}$ as follows:

$$w^{(k)}(\zeta) = \left(\mathbf{L}_e^{(k)}(\zeta) + \mathbf{L}_0^{(k)}(\zeta) \mathbf{F} \right) \mathbf{q}_e, \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{q}_e is the element displacement matrix and the partitions $\mathbf{L}_e^{(k)}(\zeta)$ and $\mathbf{L}_0^{(k)}(\zeta)$ denote the interpolation functions, respectively. \mathbf{F} is the matrix determined from compatible conditions. Then, the curvatures can be defined by:

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}^{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{xx}^{(k)} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{yy}^{(k)} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{xy}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_{e,xx}^{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_{0,xx}^{(k)} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{L}_{e,yy}^{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_{0,yy}^{(k)} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{L}_{e,xy}^{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_{0,xy}^{(k)} \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_{e,xx}^{(k)} \\ \mathbf{B}_{e,yy}^{(k)} \\ \mathbf{B}_{e,xy}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}_e \quad (8)$$

and we can obtain the plastic dissipation of the plate as:

$$D = m_p \sum_{j=1}^{ne} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^{NG} \xi_j \sqrt{\dot{\mathbf{k}}^T(\zeta_j) \mathbf{Q} \dot{\mathbf{k}}(\zeta_j)} \quad (9)$$

where ne and NG are the total number of elements and Gaussian points, respectively.

The upper-bound limit analysis based on the shakedown approach of plate bending is now described as:

$$\alpha^+ = \min m_p \sum_{j=1}^{ne} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^{NG} \xi_j \sqrt{\dot{\mathbf{k}}^T(\zeta_j) \mathbf{Q} \dot{\mathbf{k}}(\zeta_j)} \quad (10)$$

$$s.t \begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{k}}(\zeta_j) = \mathbf{B}_j \dot{\mathbf{q}} \\ \sum_{j=1}^{ne} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^{NG} \xi_i \mathbf{m}_j^e \dot{\mathbf{k}}^T(\zeta_j) = 1 \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial A_u \end{cases}$$

By formulating the objective function to a form comprising a sum of norms, the optimization problem (10) can be re-expressed as a standard SOCP as follows [25]:

$$D = m_p \sum_{j=1}^{ne} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^{NG} \xi_j \|\mathbf{J}^T \dot{\mathbf{k}}(\zeta_j)\| \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{J} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \sqrt{3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

It can be seen that \mathbf{J} is also the Cholesky factor of \mathbf{Q} . Finally, by establishing supplementary variables $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{ne \times 3 \times NG}$, problem (10) can be stated as follows:

$$\alpha^+ = \min m_p \sum_{k=1}^{ne \times 3 \times NG} \xi_k x_k \quad (13)$$

$$s.t \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^{ne} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^{NG} \xi_j \mathbf{m}_j^e \dot{\mathbf{k}}^T(\zeta_j) = 1 \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial A \\ \boldsymbol{\rho}_k = \mathbf{J}^T \dot{\mathbf{k}}(\zeta_k) \\ \|\boldsymbol{\rho}_k\| \leq x_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, ne \times 3 \times NG \end{cases}$$

where $\|\boldsymbol{\rho}_k\| \leq x_k$ denotes quadratic cones and the $\boldsymbol{\rho}_k$ are supplementary variables.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

To illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed solution, in this section we investigate various benchmark problems that have numerical or analytical solutions. The following parameters are adopted for all examples: length $a = 10\text{m}$ and plate thickness $h = 0.1\text{m}$. The first example considers a square plate with side length a , and restraints on all edges that are

either simply supports or clamped. The plate is subjected to uniform pressure p , as shown in Figure 2. Due to symmetry, we only modeled the upper-right quarter of the plate as illustrated in Figure 3. The results of the proposed method, normalized with m_p/a^2 , are presented in Table I. It can be observed that when the number of the elements increases, the collapse load factors reduce and converge. When compared with previous results, the present results are in good agreement with those obtained numerically in [18, 19, 21], in which the EFG method, a C_1 continuity plate element, and the the DKQ element were used, respectively. In addition, Table I also shows that the results of the proposed method are similar to the results obtained analytically in [20, 26]. The yield patterns in terms of plastic dissipation distribution are plotted in Figure 4. It can be seen that they are very consistent with the experiment, for both simply supported and clamped plates.

Fig. 2. Square slabs: geometry and loading. (a) Simply supported plate, (b) clamped plate.

Fig. 3. Square slab: finite element mesh.

TABLE I. LIMIT LOAD FACTOR OF THE SQUARE PLATE (pa^2/m_p)

Method	Simply supported		Clamped		
	UB	LB	UB	LB	
Proposed	$N_e = 50$	25.18	-	51.83	-
	$N_e = 200$	25.06	-	48.17	-
	$N_e = 800$	25.03	-	46.19	-
	$N_e = 1800$	25.03	-	45.58	-
[19]	25.02	-	45.29	-	
[17]	25.01	-	45.07	-	
[21]	25.04	25.04	45.06	45.06	
[20]	26.54	24.86	49.25	42.86	
[26]	27.71	23.81	52.01	-	

N_e : number of elements, LB – Lower bound, UB – Upper bound

Fig. 4. Square slabs: plastic dissipation distribution. (a) Simply supported plate, (b) clamped plate.

Fig. 5. Rectangular slab: geometry and loading.

Fig. 6. Rectangular slab: finite element mesh.

TABLE II. LIMIT LOAD FACTOR OF THE RECTANGULAR PLATE (pab/m_p)

Method	Simply supported	Clamped
Proposed	29.90	56.20
[19]	29.88	-
[17]	29.88	54.61

Fig. 7. Rectangular slabs: plastic dissipation distribution. (a) Simply supported plate, (b) clamped plate.

Next, we consider the rectangular slab of Figure 5 (dimensions $a \times b$ and $b/a = 2$). Similar to the previous example, only the upper-right quarter of the plate is modeled by 800

elements (Figure 6). Limit load factors are reported in Table II. When compared with the previously obtained results, the proposed method provides better solutions than in [17, 19] by 0.07% and 2.91% for the case of simply supported and clamped edges, respectively. The plastic dissipation distribution of rectangular slabs is plotted in Figure 7.

The last example is an L-shape plate, investigated in the case of uniform load. The geometry and uniform mesh of the L-shape plate are shown in Figure 8 and the limit load factors are shown in Table III. Again, the results of the proposed method show good agreement with previous studies. The maximum error is only 2.59% for the case of clamped edges. The plastic dissipation distribution using 2400 elements is plotted in Figure 9.

Fig. 8. L-shape plate. (a) Geometry, (b) Mesh.

TABLE III. LIMIT LOAD FACTOR OF THE L-SHAPE PLATE (pa^2/m_p)

Method	Simply supported	Clamped
Proposed	6.20	16.24
[10]	6.29	-
[15]	6.17/6.04	15.83/15.69

Fig. 9. L-shape slabs: Plastic dissipation distribution. (a) Simply supported, (b) clamped.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a numerical solution for the computation of the limit loads of bending plates. Using von Mises yield criterion and the conforming HCT element, the upper bound limit load can be derived from Koiter's kinematic shakedown theorem for the case of one load vertex instead of using the upper bound theorem of limit analysis. Based on this approach, the work rate of the applied load constraint in the kinematic theorem of limit analysis is replaced by the external work rate constraint. The formulation based on Koiter's kinematic shakedown theorem is more complicated than the

formulations for the upper bound of the limit load, however, it can be developed to the shakedown problem and the failure mode of alternating plasticity can be determined easily. One benefit of this research is that the problems can be formulated as SOCP, so that they can be solved rapidly, even when many variables are involved. The accuracy and reliability of the proposed solution method were proven by numerical examples.

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A Theoretical-Experimental Study on the Influence of FDM Parameters on the Dimensions of Cylindrical Spur Gears Made of PLA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of a theoretical-experimental study on the influence of FDM parameters (height of the deposited layer at one pass H_s and percentage of filling P_v) on the dimensions of cylindrical spur gears made of PLA (shaft diameter d and bore diameter D). In this context, we designed the 3D model of a cylindrical gear with module $m=1$ and $z=60$ spur teeth, which we used for FDM 3D printing of 27 PLA parts with different values of coating height deposited at a pitch H_s of 0.10, 0.15, 0.20mm and different values 50, 75, and 100% of filling percentage P_v . The 324 values obtained from measuring the diameters d and D of 27 cylindrical spur gears made of PLA and the calculated values of statistical indicators (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, dispersion) were used to determine the dimensional accuracy of the analyzed parts. The study results show that the percentage of filling has a greater influence than the shaft diameter on the dimensional accuracy of cylindrical spur gears made of PLA.

Keywords-3D printing; FDM parameters; experimental test; spur gears

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, production processes are undergoing transformations in terms of flexibilization according to market requirements, the main objective being to reduce costs in order to strengthen market position and maintain sustainable competitive advantage [12-17]. Additive manufacturing technologies are a viable solution for many industries such as automotive, aerospace, and defense due to advantages in comparison with formative and subtractive manufacturing technologies, e.g. the manufacturing costs are significantly reduced, complex geometries are achieved without special base and fixing elements, simplicity in use, material waste is negligible, use of bio materials, etc. [1, 6, 11].

Fused deposition modeling is one of the most popular manufacturing technologies due to its affordability, the wide range of materials used, and the possibility of customization for printed parts. However, this technology has certain limitations such as run time and surface quality. Depending on the field of use of the manufactured part, the limitations can be adjusted from the process parameters: the height of the layer deposited in one step, the filling percentage, the printing speed, etc. [9, 10]. The materials used for FDM are thermoplastics, the most popular among them being PLA (polylactic acid), ABS (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene), PET (polyethylene terephthalate), Nylon, and PC (polycarbonate) [3]. The study of the influence of 3D printing parameters has attracted the scientific interest. Authors in [1] showed a comparative study about dimensional accuracy from errors of FFF printed spur

gears using PLA and Nylon and authors in [11] showed a development of a prediction system for 3D printed part deformation using SLS technology.

The novelty of this work consists in the theoretical-experimental determination of the influence of FDM parameters on the dimensions of cylindrical spur gears (shaft diameter d and bore diameter D) made of PLA. The greater influence between the two studied parameters H_s and P_u is found with statistical calculations following the measurements.

II. 3D PRINTING OF CYLINDRICAL SPUR GEARS

The quality of the parts manufactured additively by thermoplastic extrusion is influenced by the material type and the 3D printer used, [9, 10]. In this context, PLA filament with a diameter of 1.75mm (Verbatim brand) and the Creality CR-X 3D printer with a printing volume of 300x300x400mm and XY positioning accuracy of ± 0.10 mm were used to manufacture all cylindrical spur gears. Figure 1 shows the steps taken to perform the experimental study on the influence of FDM parameters on the dimensions of cylindrical spur gears R_d made of PLA.

Fig. 1. Stages of the experimental study on the influence of FDM parameters on the dimensions of cylindrical spur gears fabricated from PLA.

Using the Solidworks 2022 software, the 3D model of a cylindrical spur gear with module $m=1$ and $z=60$ was designed using the ToolBox function and was converted from SLD to STL format, [6, 7, 20]. The 3D model was the basis for the 2D drawing shown in Figure 2 of [6]. Using the STL format file, corresponding to the spur gear with spur teeth shown in Figure 2, and the Creality Slicer of the Creality CR-X 3D printer, we inserted the printing parameters shown in Table I and generated the G-Code file [6, 7]. The FDM 3D printing parameters of PLA spur gears (R_d) with module $m=1$ and $z=60$ spur teeth, shown in Table I, fall into two categories, constant parameters and variable parameters, [5-8]. We transferred the G-Code file to the Creality CR-X printer and fabricated 27 cylindrical gears R_d from PLA with modulus $m=1$ and $z=60$ spur teeth. Figure 3 shows the cylindrical toothed wheel R_d made of PLA with $m=1$ and $z=60$ in Creality Slicer, generated by using the height of the deposited layer at one pass $H_s=0.10$ mm, filling percentage $P_u=50\%$, printing speed $V_p=80$ mm/min, and filling pattern type line oriented at 45° [8].

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF 3D FDM PRINTING OF R_d SPUR GEARS WITH $m=1$ AND $z=60$

Constant parameters	Variable parameters		Coding of the gear set	Material
Part orientation X, Y	Height of the deposited layer H_s (mm)	Filling Percentage P_u (%)	R_{di}	PLA
			$(i = 1... 9)$	(parts)
Temperature of the extruder, $T_e=210^\circ\text{C}$	0.10	100	R_{d1}	3
		75	R_{d2}	3
		50	R_{d3}	3
	0.15	100	R_{d4}	3
		75	R_{d5}	3
		50	R_{d6}	3
Table temperature, $T_b=60^\circ\text{C}$	100	R_{d7}	3	
	75	R_{d8}	3	
	0.20	50	R_{d9}	3
Printing speed, $V_p=80$ mm/s				
Filling pattern - Lines 45°				

The mass of the cylindrical gear with modulus $m=1$ and spur teeth $z=60$, shown in Figure 2, is 14g (equivalent to 4.957m of PLA filament) and its running time is 2 hours and 53 minutes. The G-Code file of the cylindrical gear shown in Figure 2 contains 108500 control lines [8].

Fig. 2. R_d PLA cylindrical gear with $m=1$ and $z=60$ spur teeth ($H_s=0.10$ mm, $P_u=50\%$, $V_p=80$ mm/min, 45° oriented line fill pattern) in Creality Slicer.

III. DETERMINATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF FDM PARAMETERS ON THE DIMENSIONS OF SPUR GEARS MADE OF PLA

A. Working Methodology

For the experimental study we used 324 values obtained by measuring with a digital caliper the diameter of the shaft ($d=62\pm 0.1$ mm) and the diameter of the bore ($D=20.2\pm 0.1$ mm) of 27 cylindrical gears made of PLA, with $m=1$ and $z=60$, additively manufactured by thermoplastic extrusion (using the parameters in Table I). Each part was measured as shown in Figure 3. The 324 values are used to determine the arithmetic mean (1), standard deviation (2), and dispersion (3), corresponding to each set of cylindrical gears R_{di} in PLA with $m=1$ and $z=60$ [1, 18, 19]:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x_1+x_2+\dots+x_n}{n} \tag{1}$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n}} \tag{2}$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \tag{3}$$

A set of cylindrical gears $R_{d,i}$ made of PLA, with $m=1$ and $z=60$, contains 3 parts characterized by the same 3D printing parameters (see Table I). Two sets of measurements were performed for each part, resulting in 12 values - 6 values for shaft diameter d and 6 values for bore diameter D , as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Measuring points of the diameters of cylindrical gears R_d made of PLA with modulus $m=1$ and spur teeth $z=60$.

B. Results

The 324 values resulting from the measurement of the diameters of the 27 cylindrical gears R_d made of PLA, additively manufactured by thermoplastic extrusion, are graphically represented in Figures 4-21. Tables II-XIX show the results obtained from the calculation of statistical indicators arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and dispersion. The variation of the values of the arithmetic means \bar{x} of the shaft diameter d for each set of $R_{d,i}$ gears ($i= 1...9$) is shown in Figure 23. The variation of the values of the arithmetic means \bar{x} of the bore diameter D for each set of gears $R_{d,i}$ ($i= 1...9$) is shown in Figure 22.

Fig. 4. Values of shaft diameter d for gear set R_{d1} . ($H_s = 0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u = 100\%$).

TABLE II. VALUES OF THE STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR WHEELS R_{d1}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s = 0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u = 100\%$	mm 61.95	mm 0.086	mm 0.007

Fig. 5. Values of shaft diameter d for gear set R_{d2} . ($H_s = 0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u = 75\%$).

TABLE III. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d2}

Variable Parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s = 0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u = 75\%$	mm 61.95	mm 0.093	mm 0.009

Fig. 6. Values of shaft diameter d for gear set R_{d3} . ($H_s = 0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u = 50\%$).

TABLE IV. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d3}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s = 0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u = 50\%$	mm 61.99	mm 0.111	mm 0.012

Fig. 7. Values of shaft diameter d for spur gear set R_{d4} . ($H_s = 0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u = 100\%$).

TABLE V. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d4}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s = 0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u = 100\%$	mm 61.98	mm 0.070	mm 0.005

Fig. 8. Values of shaft diameter d for spur gear set R_{d5} . ($H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$).

TABLE VI. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d5}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$	mm 62	mm 0.047	mm 0.002

Fig. 9. Values of shaft diameter d for spur gear set R_{d6} . ($H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$).

TABLE VII. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d6}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$	mm 61.99	mm 0.063	mm 0.004

Fig. 10. Values of shaft diameter d for spur gear set R_{d7} . ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$).

TABLE VIII. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d7}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$	mm 61.96	mm 0.062	mm 0.004

Fig. 11. Values of shaft diameter d for spur gear set R_{d8} . ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$).

TABLE IX. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d8}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$	mm 62.02	mm 0.113	mm 0.013

Fig. 12. Values of shaft diameter d for spur gear set R_{d9} . ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$).

TABLE X. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d9}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$	mm 61.95	mm 0.061	mm 0.004

Fig. 13. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d1} . ($H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$).

TABLE XI. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d1}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$	mm 20.29	mm 0.058	mm 0.003

Fig. 14. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d2} . ($H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$).

TABLE XII. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{D2}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$	mm 20.32	mm 0.077	mm 0.066

Fig. 15. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d3} . ($H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$).

TABLE XIII. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{D3}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$	mm 20.25	mm 0.117	mm 0.014

Fig. 16. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d4} . ($H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$).

TABLE XIV. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{D4}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$	mm 20.28	mm 0.091	mm 0.008

Fig. 17. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d5} . ($H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$).

TABLE XV. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{D5}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$	mm 20.31	mm 0.088	mm 0.008

Fig. 18. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear R_{d6} . ($H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$).

TABLE XVI. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{D6}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$	mm 20.29	mm 0.068	mm 0.005

Fig. 19. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d7} . ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$).

TABLE XVII. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{D7}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$	mm 20.07	mm 0.152	mm 0.023

Fig. 20. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d8} . ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$).

TABLE XVIII. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d8}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$	mm 20.13	mm 0.120	mm 0.014

Fig. 21. Values of bore diameter D for spur gear set R_{d9} . ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$).

TABLE XIX. VALUES OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE SET OF SPUR GEARS R_{d9}

Variable parameters	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation σ	Dispersion σ^2
$H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$	mm 20.13	mm 0.130	mm 0.017

Using the values of the arithmetic means \bar{x} of the shaft diameter d and of the bore diameter D (see Tables II-XIX) for each set of gears R_{di} ($i=1..9$), the graphs in Figure 22 and 23 were constructed, respectively.

Fig. 22. Variation of the arithmetic mean values \bar{x} of the shaft diameter d for each set of gears R_{di} ($i=1..9$).

Fig. 23. Variation of the arithmetic mean values \bar{x} of the bore diameter for each set of gears R_{di} ($i=1..9$).

C. Discussion

The study was carried out using the 162 values resulting from the measurement with the digital caliper of the shaft diameter $d=62\pm 0.1\text{mm}$ (see Figure 3) and the 162 values resulting from the measurement with the same instrument of the bore diameter $D=20.2\pm 0.1\text{mm}$ (see Figure 3) of the 27 cylindrical spur gears made of PLA, with modulus $m=1$ and spur teeth $z=60$, additively manufactured by thermoplastic extrusion (using the parameters in Table I), certify the significant influence on their dimensions of the height of the layer deposited at one pass H_s and the percentage of filling P_u .

In this context, analyzing the graphs in Figures 4-23 and the result summary in Tables II-XIX the following results are issued:

1) For Shaft Diameter $d=62\pm 0.1\text{mm}$

- The best values were obtained by measuring the set of spur gears R_{d5} ($H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$), the calculated mean being $\bar{x}=62\text{mm}$ and dispersion $\sigma^2=0.002$ (see Figure 9 and Table VI).
- The largest deviations were obtained in the measurement of the spur gear set R_{d2} ($H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$), the calculated mean average being $\bar{x}=61.95\text{mm}$, and dispersion $\sigma^2=0.0087$ (see Figure 5 and Table III);
- 100% of the values obtained in the measurement of the spur gear set R_{di} ($i=1..9$) are within the tolerance of $\pm 0.10\text{mm}$, the best values being obtained for 3D printing with the height of the deposited layer at a pitch $H_s=0.15\text{mm}$ (see Figure 22).

2) For Bore Diameter $D=20.2\pm 0.1\text{mm}$:

- The best values were obtained in the measurement of the spur gear set R_{d3} ($H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$), the calculated mean being $\bar{x}=20.25\text{mm}$, and dispersion $\sigma^2=0.014$ (see Figure 15 and Table XIII).
- The largest deviations were obtained in the measurement of the spur gear set R_{d7} ($H_s=0.20\text{mm}$, $P_u=100\%$), the calculated average being $\bar{x}=20.07\text{mm}$, and dispersion $\sigma^2=0.023$ (see Figure 19 and Table XVII).
- Only 66.6% of the values obtained in the measurement of the spur gear set R_{di} ($i=1..9$) fall within the tolerance of $\pm 0.10\text{mm}$, very close to the upper and lower limits (see Figure 23).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The current paper presents the results of a theoretical-experimental study on the influence of FDM parameters (height of the deposited layer at one pass H_s and percentage of filling P_u) on the dimensions (shaft diameter d and bore diameter D) of cylindrical spur gears made of PLA. Cylindrical spur gears were printed on Creality CR-X 3D printer using PLA filament - Verbatim brand.

Regarding the shaft diameter d , all values obtained in the measurement of FDM 3D printed spur gears are within the required tolerance of ± 0.10 mm.

Regarding the bore diameter D , one third of the measured values were outside the tolerance limits. The difference between the extreme values of the arithmetic mean is 0.25mm.

The theoretical-experimental study demonstrates that of the two FDM parameters analyzed, the P_u filling percentage has a greater influence on the dimensional accuracy of spur gears made of PLA.

The results of the study are useful for optimizing FDM parameters for additive manufacturing of PLA spur gears by thermoplastic extrusion within specified dimensional tolerances. The study can be extrapolated to other types of materials used in additive manufacturing technologies.

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An Experimental Study of the Influence of Carburizing Treatment Holding Time on the Structure and Hardness of 16NC6 Steel

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ABSTRACT

Low carbon steel with carbon content ranging from 0.15% to 0.3% cannot be hardened through quenching and tempering processes and there is little to no martensitic transformation occurring upon quenching. To improve the surface hardness, carburizing is commonly employed. Through this treatment, the surface composition of the low-carbon steel is altered by the diffusion of carbon, resulting in a hard outer casing with good wear resistance. This work investigates the effect of the carburizing treatment temperature and holding time on the crystallographic structure, hardness, and hardened surface layer dimension of commercial low-carbon steel 16NC6. The steel was carburized at 900°C for different holding times of 1, 2, and 3 hours. After the carburizing and quenching processes, the hardness values and the morphology of the crystallographic structure were measured and characterized.

Keywords-carburizing; quenching; low carbon steel; structure; hardness

I. INTRODUCTION

Heat treatment processes can be used to modify the surface and structural properties of low carbon steel in order to have a hard outer surface and a ductile and tough inner core, which is beneficial for engineering applications such as cams, gears, and shafts. These properties assist the resistance in wear and shock, thus extending the life of the component [1-3]. Carburizing is an ancient thermo-chemical heat treatment used to harden the surface of low carbon steel by diffusing carbon into it. The steel typically must be subjected to quenching in order to achieve the desired hardness [4, 5]. Carburizing is used to introduce carbon into the surface layer of steel. The process involves heating the steel in a carbon-rich environment, typically a carbon-rich gas or a bath of molten carbon-rich compounds, at a temperature above the steel's critical temperature. This allows carbon to diffuse into the surface layer of the steel, creating a hard, wear-resistant surface layer known as the case. The influence of carburizing treatment

holding time on the structure and mechanical properties of low carbon steel can be significant. Holding time is the time period that the steel is exposed to the carbon-rich environment during the process. A longer holding time will result in a deeper case and a higher carbon concentration in the surface layer, improving hardness, wear resistance, and other mechanical properties. However, it is important to note that holding time should not be too long, as excessive carburizing can lead to the formation of carbides and other undesirable structures. These structures can reduce the toughness and ductility of the steel and make it more brittle. As a result, it is important to carefully control holding time during the carburizing process in order to achieve optimal results. In summary, carburizing treatment can greatly improve the structure and mechanical properties of low carbon steel, but it is important to control holding time in order to achieve optimal results. The influence of holding time on the structure and hardness of low carbon steel is an important topic of research, and a deeper understanding of this relationship can

lead to the development of better carburizing processes and more advanced materials [6-11].

This study aims to investigate the effects of carburizing treatment on low carbon steel and to produce cemented steel through this process. Carburizing treatment involves exposing the low carbon steel 16NC6 to a carbon-rich environment for different periods, using holding time as a parameter. The study aims to examine how variations in carburizing treatment temperature and holding time affect the crystallographic structure, hardness, and dimensions of the hardened surface layer. In addition, the study seeks to provide insight into the chemical composition of the steel before and after carburizing treatment. The study aims to provide valuable information for industrial applications, such as the manufacturing of gears and other mechanical components. During the carburizing process, carbon diffuses into steel and reacts with iron to form iron carbide compounds. The study aims to examine the impact of carburizing time and temperature on the transformation rate of low carbon steel into cemented steel layers. Optical microscopy was used to analyze micrographs of the samples and the thickness of the carburized areas, and micro Vickers was used to measure the microhardness of cross-sectional samples of the cemented steel [11-16].

II. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The low carbon steel used in this study was procured from the local market (AFNOR 16NC6) and underwent chemical analysis according to ASTM E 415-99a using spectroscopic methods. The results showed that the chemical composition of the steel, in weight percent, was: 0.17% C, 0.26% Si, 0.67% Mn, 0.92% Cr, 1.2% Ni, 0.027% Mo, and 0.228% Cu. The samples were machined into cylindrical shapes with 18mm diameter and 5mm length. To prepare the samples for carburizing, all specimens were mechanically polished to reduce roughness to a level of $R_a = 0.25\mu\text{m}$, using sandpaper. The steel substrates then underwent pack carburizing treatment at various parameters. The samples underwent carburizing at a temperature of 900°C for time periods of 1, 2, and 3 hours. After carburizing, the specimens were immediately quenched in oil and tempered at a low temperature to further improve their behavior. After the carburizing treatment, the cross-sectional samples were prepared and polished. These samples were etched in a solution consisting of 100ml water, 2ml of 40% HF, and 5ml of 30% H_2O_2 . This type of etching is widely used to highlight the different zones of cemented steel [9-18]. A Zwick Roell microscope was used to examine the metallographic preparation and observe the morphological details and thickness of the cemented layers. The hardness profile of the samples was measured across the cross-sections using a Zwick Roell microindenter with a load of 500gf.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Structure

Figure 1 displays the optical micrographs of the microstructure of the steel before undergoing the carburizing treatment. Figures 2-4 display the optical micrographs of the microstructure after undergoing carburizing at 900°C and quenching for each holding time treatment.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of the steel before the carburizing treatment.

Fig. 2. Micrograph after carburizing at 900°C and quenching for 1h. (a) Surface zone, (b) inner area.

Figure 2 displays the micrographs of the surface zone and inner area of steel that was carburized for 1 hour at 900°C . In this case, the thickness of the cemented steel region was estimated to be 1mm and was divided into an outer zone of approximately 0.5mm and an inner diffusion layer of 0.5mm.

Figure 3 displays the micrographs of the steel that was carburized for 2h at 900°C . The thickness of the cemented steel region was estimated to be 1.4mm and was divided into an outer zone of approximately 0.7mm and an inner diffusion layer of 0.7mm.

Fig. 3. Micrograph after carburizing at 900C° and quenching for 2h. (a) Surface zone,(b) inner area.

Fig. 4. Micrograph after carburizing at 900C° and quenching for 3h. (a) Surface zone, (b) inner area.

Figure 4 shows the micrographs of the steel that was carburized for 3h at 900°C. In this case, the thickness of the cemented steel region was estimated to be 1.9mm and was divided into an outer zone of approximately 0.9mm and an inner diffusion layer of 1mm.

As observed, the diffusion of carbon atoms to the surface of low steel leads to the formation of new phases with carbon atoms in the surface area. A martensitic microstructure is evident in the surface zone of the samples, and the temperature has the most significant effect on the structures and the development of the carburized layer. The thickness of the carburized zone of steel increases when the treatment holding time increases.

B. Chemical Composition

For each treatment holding time, the sample underwent chemical analysis according to ASTM E 415-99a using spectroscopic methods. The results, shown in Table I, indicate the chemical composition of the steel in weight percent.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AFTER CARBURIZING

	C %	Si %	Mn %	Cr %	Ni %	Mo %	Cu %
1h	0.63	0.25	0.65	0.91	1.188	0.031	0.222
2h	0.81	0.26	0.64	0.90	1.17	0.028	0.232
3h	1.03	0.27	0.63	0.90	1.22	0.029	0.225

C. Hardness

Figures 5-7 show the hardness versus depth for steel carburized at 900°C for 1, 2, and 3 hours and Figure 8 summarizes the results. In Figure 8, it is observed that the hardness profile curve has three regions. The first region, corresponding to the outer layer, has a very high hardness due to the formation of hard martensitic compounds and new iron carbides during the carburizing treatment. The second zone, corresponding to the diffusion zone, exhibits a decrease in hardness values, which can be attributed to the reduced rate of carbon diffusion into the steel substrate. The third zone has a fixed hardness value, corresponding to the hardness of the steel substrate.

Fig. 5. Hardness of steel carburized at 900°C for 1h.

Fig. 6. Hardness of steel carburized at 900°C for 2h.

Fig. 7. Hardness of steel carburized at 900°C for 3h.

Fig. 8. Hardness of steel carburized at 900°C for 1, 2, and 3 hours.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results and the analysis presented in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The carburizing treatment of low carbon steel can effectively increase the surface hardness and produce a hardened layer, which is composed of a combination of martensite and expanded austenite.
- The hardness of the carburized layer increases with increasing treatment holding time, with the thickness of the layer also increasing with time.

- The crystallographic structure of the carburized layer is greatly affected by the temperature and holding time of the carburizing treatment, with a transition from ferrite and pearlite to martensite and new iron carbides observed in the outer layer.
- The chemical composition of the steel is also affected by the carburizing treatment, with increase in the percentage of carbon observed after treatment.
- The carburizing treatment provides a useful method for improving the wear resistance and durability of low carbon steel components, particularly in applications where high hardness and resistance to wear are critical.

Overall, this study provides valuable insight into the effects of carburizing treatment on low carbon steel, with important implications for industrial applications such as the production of gears and other mechanical components.

It is recommended that further research should be conducted to explore the optimization of the carburizing treatment temperature and holding time in order to improve the hardness and crystallographic structure of the carburized steel. In addition, it would be interesting to investigate the impact of different quenching methods on the hardness and structure of the carburized steel. Furthermore, it would be valuable to evaluate the performance of carburized steel in various applications, such as wear resistance and corrosion resistance, to fully understand the benefits of this treatment for practical use.

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An Experimental Study of a Combined Oblique Cylindrical Weir and Gate Structure

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, the effects of different oblique angles and diameters on the cylindrical weir and below a gate as a combined device have been studied experimentally. For this purpose, sixteen models of combined cylindrical weir-gate structures have been tested in a laboratory flume. These models had four different oblique angles α (30° , 45° , 60° , and 90°). For each angle, the diameter of cylindrical weir-gate changed four times (4, 7.3, 9, and 11cm). The results of all models indicate that the theoretical discharge (Q_{th}) is inversely proportional to the ratio of diameter to height (D/h) and length to height (L/h). As the diameter increases and oblique angles decrease, the actual discharge (Q_{act}) increases. A general expression was established linking $Q_{th}/g^{1/2}h^{5/2}$ and the discharge coefficient C_d with D/h, L/h, and α . The discharge coefficient ranged from 0.55 to 0.99 for various oblique angles and decreased as the angle increased. A strong correlation was observed between the estimated and the calculated values.

Keywords-combined flow; cylindrical weir; gate; discharge coefficient; theoretical discharge

I. INTRODUCTION

Weirs and gates are the most commonly used and important structures for measuring water flow, regulating flow in irrigation channels, and redirecting it from the main channel to secondary channels [1]. Weirs are structures that regulate water surface and flow control in water conveyance channels and hydraulic structures. One of their demerits is that they need to be cleaned of sediment and trash periodically. Gates are used extensively for flow control and water measurement. One disadvantage of the gates is that they retain floating materials. In order to maximize their advantages, weirs and gates can be combined together in one device, so that water could pass over the weir and below the gate simultaneously. It may reduce the effect of sediments and floating materials upstream and may affect scoring downstream [2-4]. One such combination is the cylindrical weir-gate structure. Regarding the form of the combined cylindrical weir-gate structures, it has some advantages including easy design, sediments and floating material flow, higher flow discharge coefficient, lower cost, and the combination of those structures in one device can minimize the disadvantages of separate use of each device.

The performance of this combination has been studied extensively. Authors in [5] presented the effects of hydraulic and geometrical parameters, viscosity, and surface tension in the combined flow over rectangular weirs and rectangular sharp-crested gates. They found that the trend of variation in sloping bed cases was similar to that in horizontal beds. Authors in [6] studied the characteristics of free flow through a combined triangular weir and rectangular gate. They found that the values of theoretical discharge were inversely proportional to the geometrical dimensionless parameters and directly proportional to the distance between the bottom of the weir and the upper edge of the gate. Authors in [7] investigated the coefficient of discharge (C_d) for a combined rectangular weir with semi-circular gate. They showed that the value of C_d increases when the width of the weir increases and that the average value of C_d was equal to 0.695. Also, it was found that the value of C_d increases with increasing distance between the weir and the gate with an average value of C_d equal to 0.74. Authors in [8, 10] proposed new methods to improve the performance of sharp crested triangular and curved plan form weirs. In these studies, the authors varied the vertex angles and

kept the weir height constant, and conducted tests to determine the discharge coefficients. Based on the results of these tests, they proposed two empirical equations for estimating the discharge coefficients. Authors in [11] studied the flow over a sharp crested weir and under a gate in a combined oblique structure as flow measurement structure. They found that the major parameters affecting significantly on discharge coefficient were h/a , α , L/B , D/a , while the value of C_d ranged from 0.623 to 0.403. Authors in [12] experimentally studied the effects of canal size on the discharge coefficients of cylindrical weir-gate by using two flumes. They found that the value of C_d in large canals ranged from 0.75 to 1.05 and in small canals from 0.55 to 0.9. Authors in [13] studied the effect of vertical movement of a cylindrical weir-gate on free flow hydraulics. The experimental results showed that the gate opening change was in inverse relation with the discharge coefficient change, so that the maximum and minimum discharge coefficient were visible in the cylindrical weir and cylindrical gate, respectively. Furthermore, in a constant diameter and constant discharge, discharge coefficient changes had an increasing process by the decreases of the gate opening height. Besides, in a constant discharge and gate opening height, the discharge coefficient decreased with an increase in the structure diameter.

Authors in [14] investigated the effect of weir height on the performance of sharp crested rectangular plan form weirs. They found that weirs with lower heights had higher capacity and better performance compared to those with higher heights. Authors in [15] experimentally examined the behavior of sharp crested triangular plan form weirs under free flow conditions using a range of weir models that varied in vertex angle and weir height. They found that the discharge coefficient decreases with an increase in the relative head above crest and that weirs with small vertex angles have low discharge coefficients. They presented an empirical equation for predicting discharge coefficients based on the relative head above crest and vertex angle, and concluded that weirs with small vertex angles and low heights have higher efficiency and better performance. In an extensive experimental study, authors in [16] evaluated the hydraulic performance of circular crested triangular weirs under free flow conditions using multiple models with different vertex angles, weir heights, and crest diameters. They found that the discharge coefficient decreases with an increase in the relative head above crest, and that weirs with small vertex angles, low heights, and small crest diameters have better performance. They presented a simple power equation for estimating the discharge coefficient based on the ratio of water depth above crest to weir height, the ratio of head above crest-to-crest diameter, and the vertex angle. In a more recent study, authors in [17] examined the performance of semi-circular crested normal and oblique weirs with flood embankments and found that the discharge coefficient decreases when the crest radius and height increase. Authors in [18] conducted an optimization study on the shape of labyrinth spillways in order to minimize construction costs and determine the discharge coefficient in terms of side wall angle and relative head above crest. Noori, [19] attempted to increase the discharge capacity of oblique weirs by rounding their crests. He presented an empirical expression to determine C_d in terms of H/P , H/D , and α (in radians), with a correlation

coefficient of 0.90 and a standard error of 0.01. The weir with the highest discharge capacity had $a = 20$, $P = 20$ cm, $D = 4$ cm, and a D/P ratio of 0.2, and showed a percentage increase in discharge ranging from 147% to 175% compared to a sharp crested normal weir. Noori's results indicate that circular crested oblique weirs generally have higher discharge capacity than other weir shapes.

The main goal of the current research is to study the impact of various oblique angles and diameters on the hydraulic properties of a combined cylindrical oblique weir and gate structure. Additionally, this study aims to establish relationships for the prediction of flow rate and the coefficient of discharge.

II. THEORETICAL DISCHARGE

The total theoretical discharge through a combined cylindrical weir and gate structure for free flow conditions can be obtained by adding the discharge under the gate to the discharge over the weir.

$$Q_{th} = Q_g + Q_w \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{th} = La\sqrt{2gH} + \frac{2}{3}L\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}g}h^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

where Q_{th} is the total theoretical discharge, Q_g is the discharge passing under the gate, Q_w is the discharge passing over the weir, and $H = h + d + a$ the total head above the flume bed L . The variables used in the dimensional analysis were chosen to represent the experimental conditions, see Figure 1. Therefore, the factors affecting the flow in a combined structure are expected to be:

$$Q_{th} = f_1(h, a, D, L, B, g, \rho, \mu, \sigma, \alpha) \quad (3)$$

where Q_{th} is the total theoretical discharge (L^3/T), a is the gate height (L), D is the diameter of the weir or vertical distance between the lower edge of the weir and the upper edge of the gate (L), L is the length of the weir (L), B is the width of the flume (L), g is the acceleration due to gravity (L/T^2), ρ is the mass density of the fluid (M/L^3), μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid (M/TL), σ is the surface tension (M/T^2), and α represents the oblique angles from the direction of flow in degrees.

The general relationship among all variables is:

$$f_2(Q, h, a, D, L, B, g, \rho, \mu, \sigma, \alpha) = \text{constant} \quad (4)$$

Using the Buckingham's Pi-theorem, and selecting h , Q , and ρ as repeating variables, (4) becomes:

$$f_3\left(\frac{a}{h}, \frac{D}{h}, \frac{L}{h}, \frac{B}{h}, \frac{\sigma h^3}{\rho Q^2}, \frac{\mu h}{\rho Q}, \frac{h^5 g}{Q^2}, \alpha\right) = \text{constant} \quad (5)$$

where $\mu h/\rho Q$ is the Reynolds number R_e and $\sigma h^3/\rho Q^2$ is the Weber number (W_e). The values of the Weber number and Reynolds number can be neglected at turbulent flow due to the neglected surface tension and viscosity. The values of B and a are constant during the experimental program, therefore can be dropped. Inversing and taking the square root of $h^5 g/Q^2$, (5) can be written as:

$$\frac{Q_{th}}{\sqrt{gh^{5/2}}} = f_4 \left(\frac{D}{h}, \frac{L}{h}, \alpha \right) \quad (6)$$

The coefficient of discharge (C_d) is determined by comparing the amount of fluid that is actually discharged in an experiment to the amount of fluid that would be discharged under ideal conditions.

$$C_d = \frac{Q_{act}}{Q_{th}} \quad (7)$$

where C_d is the coefficient of discharge, and Q_{act} is the actual discharge (L^3/T). Equation (7) can be written as:

$$C_d = f_5 \left(\frac{D}{h}, \frac{L}{h}, \alpha \right) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 1. Combined weir and gate structure.

TABLE I. DETAILS OF THE TESTED CYLINDRICAL WEIR-GATE MODELS

Model No.	Oblique angle (α)	Diameter (cm)
1	90°	4
2		7.3
3		9
4		11
5	60°	4
6		7.3
7		9
8		11
9	45°	4
10		7.3
11		9
12		11
13	30°	4
14		7.3
15		9
16		11

III. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

The laboratory experiments were carried out in a rectangular free surface water flume, having a 2.5m long working section with a prismatic cross section 7.6cm wide and 25cm deep with toughened plastic walls as shown in Figure 2. The flow rate was measured by a flow meter with a range of 0.5-2.5L/s. During the experimental program, 16 combined

weir-gate models, made from PVC pipe, with 4 different oblique angles to the longitudinal axis of the channel (30°, 45°, 60°, and 90°), were tested. For each angle, the diameter of cylindrical weir-gate changed 4 times ($D = 4, 7.3, 9, \text{ and } 11\text{cm}$). Details of the experimental program are shown in Table I. Each model was placed at 1cm above the flume bed, at 1.32m distance from the upstream of the flume. In each run, the flow rate was recorded and the flow head over the model crest, using a point gauge, was measured at a distance of (3-4) h upstream of the model. The zero on the gauge must correspond to the level of the model crest. A total of 173 experiments were conducted.

Fig. 2. A model sample during operation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Variation of Q_{act} with H

After all models were tested and the data were collected the relationships between Q_{act} and total upstream head H for different oblique angle and diameter values are shown in Figure 3. It is indicated that the discharge passing the cylindrical weir gate increases with the increase of the total upstream head H and decreased oblique angle.

B. Variation of Q_{th} with D/h and L/h

The variation of Q_{th} with D/h and L/h was studied for all models with different oblique angles ($\alpha = 90^\circ, 60^\circ, 45^\circ, \text{ and } 30^\circ$). The results are plotted in Figures 4 and 5 for D/h and L/h , respectively. From the obtained figures, one may observe that the decrease in the value of the discharge due to the increase in D/h and L/h is an inevitable result when the diameter of the pipe and the angle α (the structure length L) are constant. The increase of these two variables follows a decrease in the load over the weir (h) and thus the discharge decreases. Similar curve patterns were obtained experimentally in [6, 12].

Fig. 3. Relation between the actual discharge and the total head H for different oblique angles and diameters.

C. Predication of Combined Discharge

The relationship between the variation of $Q_{th}/\sqrt{gh^{5/2}}$ and the structural parameters D/h and L/h for a flow in a combination of different oblique angles was represented as a function in (6). To investigate the impact of D/h and L/h on $Q/\sqrt{gh^{5/2}}$, the results of experiments on flow in a combination

of cylindrical weirs and gates of varying diameters and angles were used as input in a regression analysis program. This led to the development of the following empirical power expression:

$$\frac{Q_{th}}{\sqrt{gh^{5/2}}} = 0.252 \left(\frac{D}{h}\right)^{0.714} \left(\frac{L}{h}\right)^{1.729} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 4. Relation between Q_{th} with D/h for different angles.

Equation (9) was obtained with a determination coefficient (R^2) = 0.998. A comparison between values of Q_{th} predicted by (9) and those observed experimentally show quite good agreement, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Relation between Q_{th} and L/h for different angles.

Fig. 6. The correlation between the predicted and the observed values from the experiments.

D. Variation of C_d with the Combined Effects of L/h , D/h , and α

The values of C_d from combined flow condition were calculated based on (8) and are discussed for the case when the oblique angle of weir and gate structure increase and C_d decreases. The obtained average values of C_d were 0.50, 0.69, 0.72, and 0.98 for $\alpha = 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ,$ and 90° , respectively. The experimental results of the 16 combined weir-gate models are utilized as input data in the regression program SPSS in order to acquire an empirical power expression of the form:

$$C_d = 0.0448 (\alpha)^{0.602} \left(\frac{D}{h}\right)^{0.052} \left(\frac{L}{h}\right)^{0.088} \quad (10)$$

with a correlation coefficient $R = 0.88$. A comparison between the values of C_d predicted by (10) and those observed experimentally are shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Predicted vs experimentally observed values of C_d for all test runs.

V. CONCLUSION

The current work aimed to experimentally study the effect of oblique angle and diameter on the flows over oblique cylindrical weir-gates. Sixteen models were designed and tested with angles varying 4 times from 30° to 90° and diameters from 4 to 11cm. The discharge ranged between 0.5 and 2.5LPM. The results from the study were discussed and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The main parameters that effect $\frac{Q_{th}}{\sqrt{g} h^{2.5}}$ and C_d were $\frac{D}{h}, \frac{L}{h},$ and α .

- The theoretical discharge Q_{th} decreases with increasing D/h and L/h for different angles and diameters.
- The actual discharge increases as the diameter of combined weir -gate increases and the oblique angle decreases.
- When the oblique angle increased, the discharge coefficient decreased, with a range of values from 0.5 to 0.98.
- The values produced by the developed equation were found to closely match the observed values.
- Two empirical expressions, (9) and (10), in the form of power functions were obtained with correlation coefficients of 0.998 and 0.88, respectively.

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Expanding the Data Normalization Strategy to the MACONT Method for Multi-Criteria Decision Making

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ABSTRACT

The Mixed Aggregation by Comprehensive Normalization Technique (MACONT) is a well-known Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) method with significant benefits compared to traditional approaches. The key difference that distinguishes this method from most others is the use of data normalization techniques and aggregation approaches. MACONT uses three different data normalization techniques simultaneously along with two aggregation approaches throughout its evaluation process. This reduces the derivation of evaluation values and enhances the reliability of the final decision results, making the process more precise and convergent. However, the original MACONT emphasizes the integration of multiple normalization techniques of the same type of criteria that might perform badly in some circumstances. This paper proposes combination strategies of six normalization techniques to be coupled with the MACONT to help the normalized data synthetically reflect the original information and solve different types of data, criteria, and alternatives. The proposed approach was applied in four case studies. In all studies, the ranking results were compared with the other MCDM methods, producing the same best alternatives and overcoming the cases when the original MACONT did not work properly.

Keywords-MCDM; MACONT method; data normalization

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) is a common action in various fields to select the best option among available alternatives [1-4]. Data normalization is one of the most important tasks in the MCDM process. However, since the process of data normalization in each MCDM method differs, the final ranking of alternatives based on different MCDM methods also varies [5]. In addition, using the same MCDM method but combining different data normalization algorithms could produce different outcomes [6]. Mixed Aggregation by Comprehensive Normalization Technique (MACONT) is a recent MCDM method that differs from most others, especially in data normalization. In contrast to the majority of other MCDM methods, the MACONT utilizes three data normalization procedures simultaneously: linear sum-based normalization (N1), linear ratio-based normalization (N2), and linear max-min normalization (N3). With this distinction, the MACONT can reduce mistakes in comparison to other MCDM systems that employ a single data normalization method [7, 8]. This strategy has been successfully applied to the selection of supply chain management [7] and retirement service providers [8]. However, the N1 and N2 normalization procedures cannot be utilized if there is a criterion that is as minimal as feasible and whose value at some variant is zero. If the highest value of a particular

as large as the feasible criterion is zero, N2 will likewise not be applied. Therefore, the MACONT approach cannot be used by just employing N1, N2, and N3. To overcome these issues, this paper proposes combination strategies from six normalization methods for coupling with the MACONT. The proposed approaches were examined and compared in 4 case studies, with different types of data, criteria, and alternatives.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Data normalization plays an important role in MCDM. This process is conducted using mathematical formulas to transform the factors that have different units into dimensionless [9]. The 6 normalization methods (N1 to N6) that have been widely used for MCDM problems are [10]:

- Linear sum-based normalization (N1).

For criteria where the biggest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^1 = \frac{y_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m y_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

For criteria where the smallest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^1 = \frac{\frac{1}{y_{ij}}}{\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{y_{ij}}} \quad (2)$$

- Linear ratio-based normalization (N2).

For criteria where the biggest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^2 = \frac{y_{ij}}{\max y_{ij}} \tag{3}$$

For criteria where the smallest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^2 = \frac{\min y_{ij}}{y_{ij}} \tag{4}$$

- Linear max-min normalization (N3).

For criteria where the biggest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^3 = \frac{y_{ij} - \min y_{ij}}{\max y_{ij} - \min y_{ij}} \tag{5}$$

For criteria where the smallest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^3 = \frac{y_{ij} - \max y_{ij}}{\min y_{ij} - \max y_{ij}} \tag{6}$$

- Linear max normalization (N4)

For criteria where the biggest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^4 = \frac{y_{ij}}{\max y_{ij}} \tag{7}$$

For criteria where the smallest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^4 = 1 - \frac{y_{ij}}{\max y_{ij}} \tag{8}$$

- Half-linear vector normalization (N5).

For criteria where the biggest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^5 = \frac{y_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m y_{ij}^2}} \tag{9}$$

For criteria where the smallest value is the best.

$$n_{ij}^5 = 1 - \frac{y_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m y_{ij}^2}} \tag{10}$$

- Linear max-min sum-based normalization (N6).

For criteria where the biggest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^6 = 1 - \frac{\max y_{ij} - y_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m (\max y_{ij} - y_{ij})} \tag{11}$$

For criteria where the smallest value is the best:

$$n_{ij}^6 = 1 - \frac{y_{ij} - \min y_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_{ij} - \min y_{ij})} \tag{12}$$

In these methods, y_{ij} is the value of criterion j in the alternative i , $i=1 \div m$, $j=1 \div n$, and n_{ij}^k is the normalization method number k . Previous studies combined more than one normalization methods in coupling with different MCDMs to solve certain decision-making problems. Methods N1 to N5 were used in combination with Combinative Distance-based Assessment (CODAS) to rank robots, air quality in an office, and lathe processing, while the results showed that N1, N2, N3, and N5 were suitable for use with the CODAS method [11]. The Proximity Indexed Value (PIV) method was used with N1, N3, N4, and N5 in [12], and the results showed that the PIV method provided reliable decisions only when combined with

N3 [12]. In a study on ranking the financial state of companies, the results showed that all methods were not suitable using the Range of Value (ROV) method [13]. Among N1, N3, N4, and N5, only N4 was proven to be suitable for coupling with the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method to rank smart car parking [14]. In food processing decisions, N1, N2, N3, and N5 were used with Weighted Aggregates Sum Product Assessment (WASPAS) and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) methods [15]. N1, N3, and N5 were applicable in coupling with the Weighted Sum Product (WISP) method when studying the rank of random numeric sets [16]. In a study to investigate the landing methods of unmanned autonomous vehicles, of the considered N1, N2, N3, and N5, only N2 was compatible with TOPSIS [17]. When combining the N2, N3, and N5 with the "Vlsekriterijumska optimizacijal Kompromisno Resenje" (VIKOR) method to rank a wifi network, the results showed that only N3 was applicable [18]. However, when ranking products based on the responses of the clients, only N5 among N1, N2, N3, and N5 was suitable for coupling with the VIKOR method [19]. In a study to combine N1, N3, N4, and N5 with WASPAS to classify different types of robots, N3 was determined as the most suitable [20].

Using a data normalization method in a certain MCDM process is a complex problem, as normalization methods only solve the problem in certain cases. Therefore, investigating the suitability of combination normalization methods with certain MCDM methods is important and must be carried out before applying it to rank alternatives. The MACONT has been recently developed as an MDCM method with numerous advantages. However, this technique uses simultaneously three normalization methods, and therefore it is necessary to study the suitability of the normalization methods for MACONT.

III. MACONT METHOD

This section presents the MACONT method for ranking alternatives as follows [7]:

- Establish a decision-making matrix with m alternatives and n criteria. Supposing y_{ij} is the value of criterion j in the alternative m , where $i=1 \div m$ and $j=1 \div n$.

- Normalize data using N1, N2, and N3.

- Calculate normalized balance values using:

$$n_{ij} = \lambda \cdot n_{ij}^1 + \mu \cdot n_{ij}^2 + (1 - \lambda - \mu) \cdot n_{ij}^3 \tag{13}$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ and $\mu \leq 1$. Normally, $\lambda = \mu = 1/3$.

- Determine $S_{1(a_i)}$, $S_{2(a_i)}$ as:

$$S_{1(a_i)} = \delta \frac{p_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (p_i)^2}} + (1 - \delta) \frac{Q_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (Q_i)^2}} \tag{14}$$

$$S_{2(a_i)} = \vartheta \cdot \max \left(w_j (n_{ij} - \bar{n}_{ij}) \right) + (1 - \vartheta) \cdot \min \left(w_j (n_{ij} - \bar{n}_{ij}) \right) \tag{15}$$

where and $\delta \geq 0$ and $\vartheta \leq 1$. Normally choose $\delta = \vartheta = 0.5$. The factors p_i and Q_i in (14) and (15) are calculated using:

$$p_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \cdot (n_{ij} - \bar{n}_{ij}), i = 1 \div m \tag{16}$$

$$Q_i = \frac{\prod_{\gamma=1}^n (n_{ij} - \bar{n}_{ij})^{w_j}}{\prod_{\eta=1}^n (n_{ij} - \bar{n}_{ij})^{w_j}}, i = 1 \div m \tag{17}$$

where $\gamma=1 \div n$ are the criteria that satisfy $n_{ij} < \bar{n}_{ij}$, and $\eta=1 \div n$ are the criteria that satisfy $n_{ij} \geq \bar{n}_{ij}$.

- Calculate the score of the alternative using:

$$S_{(a_i)} = \frac{1}{2} \left(S_{1(a_i)} + \frac{S_{2(a_i)}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (S_{2(a_i)})^2}} \right) \tag{18}$$

- Rank the alternatives using the rule that the higher score, the better the alternative.

IV. COMBINING STRATEGIES OF NORMALIZATION METHODS

In the original MACONT, the N1, N2, and N3 data normalization methods were used simultaneously. Nonetheless, these methods cannot be used if the value of y_{ij} becomes zero. This paper proposes normalization combination strategies for coupling with the MACONT to solve the alternative ranking problems. Each combination strategy T involves three independent techniques selected from N1 to N6. Table I shows the detailed combinations, where the combination T1 belongs to the original MACONT version.

TABLE I. STRATEGIES FOR COMBINING NORMALIZATION TECHNIQUES

Combination Strategy	Normalization Techniques					
	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5	N6
T1 (Original MACONT)	√	√	√			
T2	√	√		√		
T3	√	√			√	
T4	√	√				√
T5		√	√	√		
T6		√	√		√	
T7		√	√			√
T8			√	√	√	
T9			√	√		√
T10			√		√	√
T11				√	√	√

V. CASE STUDIES AND DISCUSSION

In the case studies, the criteria were divided into two categories: Category B defines the criteria related to benefit and positive effectivity with high optimal value, while category

C defines the criteria related to cost and negative aspects with low optimal value.

A. Case Study 1

Table II shows the information on 8 logistics providers [7]. Three groups of criteria were applied to evaluate the general quality of these providers. A series of evaluation criteria were established from three dimensions of sustainability as follows:

- The basis group: quality (C1), lead time (C2), cost (C3), delivery and services (C4), relationship (C5), and innovativeness (C6).
- The expanding group: pollution controls (C7), resource consumption (C8), remanufacture and reuse (C9), green technology capability (C10), and environmental management system (C11).
- The human care group: health and safety (C12), employment stability (C13), customer satisfaction (C14), reputation (C15), respect for the policy (C16), and contractual stakeholders' influence (C17).

Only C2, C3, and C8 belong to category C where the optimal value is small, while the rest belong to category B. The weights of these criteria were calculated as 0.048, 0.067, 0.085, 0.026, 0.017, 0.034, 0.098, 0.087, 0.065, 0.113, 0.046, 0.079, 0.047, 0.025, 0.072, 0.080, and 0.011, respectively [7]. The objective of MCDMs was to identify a logistics provider that simultaneously ensured that C2, C3, and C8 were the smallest variables while the remaining criteria were considered the highest (Category B). This procedure was completed using the T1 normalization strategy [7]. In addition, this case study also employed ten more combination strategies (T2-T11). Steps to rank the options according to MACONT were applied, and Table III and Figure 1 present their ranking results. The order of the alternatives with different strategies was extremely similar. In particular, all 11 combination strategies implied that option A8 was the best and option A7 was the second best. In other words, they can be applied to find the optimal solution in this case.

B. Case Study 2

This study evaluated the quality of several robot models. A series of evaluation criteria were established, including loads (C1), maximum speed (C2), time response (C3), memory storage (C4), and working distance for the operator (C5). In these five criteria, only C3 belongs to category C, and the rest belong to B. The weights of these criteria from C1 to C5 were calculated as 0.036, 0.326, 0.192, 0.326, and 0.120, respectively.

TABLE II. DETAILED FIGURES OF CASE STUDY 1 [7]

Alt.	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15	C16	C17
A1	22	22	850	34	3.5	13	17	11039	46	6	7	27	3.8	78	5	57	3.4
A2	34	38	1450	67	7.9	6	4	14326	37	3	2	63	5.9	89	6	66	6.8
A3	27	30	1068	29	5	21	11	12765	41	5	4	64	7.3	80	4	74	4.3
A4	19	41	729	37	4.3	26	9	10343	16	7	5	82	4.1	67	3	85	3.7
A5	15	76	697	45	2.8	8	13	6390	32	4	3	45	6.3	56	4	90	3.2
A6	32	25	1371	74	6.7	5	8	15789	24	2	4	38	5.2	92	7	69	7.5
A7	28	68	1190	63	5.4	23	14	13270	62	8	2	50	6.4	82	5	73	4.6
A8	17	64	798	42	3.1	19	16	8356	58	6	3	57	4.7	34	8	92	3.9

TABLE III. RANK ALTERNATIVES ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT DATA NORMALIZATION STRATEGIES

Alt.	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	T11
A1	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	3
A2	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	7	7	7	8
A3	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	5	5
A4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4
A5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6	6
A6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	8	8	8	7
A7	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
A8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Fig. 1. The graphical of the alternative ranking.

Table IV presents the figures for seven robot models [21, 22]. The best alternative was the one where C3 was the smallest and the other four criteria had the highest values. In this instance, the CODAS [21], Ranking of the attributes and alternatives (R), and Collaborative Unbiased Rank List Integration (CURLI) [22] methods were also used to determine the best one. Table V and Figure 2 illustrate the alternate rankings when the MACONT was combined with 11 data normalization combination methods, along with other MDCMs.

The ranking alternatives using the MACONT with all forms of data normalization combination strategies were identical and

correspond to the results obtained by employing R and CURLI. In addition, A2 was determined to be the optimal selection in every circumstance, even when using the CODAS method. When paired with the MACONT method, all these data normalization methods were found to be adequate.

TABLE IV. FIGURES OF CASE STUDY 2 [21, 22]

Alt.	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
A1	60	0.4	2540	500	990
A2	6.35	0.15	1016	3000	1041
A3	6.8	0.1	1727.2	1500	1676
A4	10	0.2	1000	2000	965
A5	2.5	0.1	560	500	915
A6	4.5	0.08	1016	350	508
A7	3	0.1	1778	1000	920

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the alternative ranking.

TABLE V. RANK ALTERNATIVES ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT DATA NORMALIZATION COMBINATION STRATEGIES

Alt.	MACONT											CODAS	R	CURLI	
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	T11				
A1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2
A2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
A3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
A4	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3
A5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
A6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
A7	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6

C. Case Study 3

This study was based on data collected from multiple grinding procedures, where the performance was measured and assessed based on three criteria: the arithmetic average of the absolute values of the profile heights (C1), the average value of the absolute values of the heights of the five highest-profile peaks and the depths of the five deepest alleys (C2), and the material removal capacity (C3) (Table VI). C1 and C2 belong to category C, in contrast to C3 which belongs to Category B

[23]. The Weighted Sum Model (WSM), the Weighted Product Model (WPM), and TOPSIS were also used for the MCDM with the weights of C1, C2, and C3 being 0.1932, 0.1998, and 0.6070, respectively [23]. Table VII and Figure 3 show the rankings using the MACONT with 11 combination strategies and the WSM, WPM, and TOPSIS methods. Table VII and Figure 3 show that the results of ranking alternatives using the MACONT with different strategies are similar. In addition, A10 was determined to be the optimal choice in every

circumstance, even when using the CODAS method. In other words, when paired with the MACONT, all 1 data normalization methods were found to be adequate in this scenario, and equivalent to WSM, WPM, and TOPSIS. Hence, each data normalization combination strategy can be used to precisely identify the optimal solution in this case study.

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of the alternative ranking

In general, there are substantial differences between the 3 case studies listed above, including distinct fields, number of possibilities, and number of criteria. However, it is remarkable that the optimal solution was always determined when the MACONT was applied with various strategies. The best choice chosen by the MACONT was similar to the best alternative determined by other decision-making methods. Moreover, the

MACONT method was compatible with each strategy, pointing out its applicability and convenience.

TABLE VI. THE FIGURES OF CASE STUDY 3 [23]

Alt.	C1	C2	C3
A1	2.6	12.6	0.75
A2	3.1	14.2	3
A3	3.7	15.3	6.75
A4	1.8	6.4	3
A5	2.3	9.8	9
A6	2.8	12.8	4.5
A7	0.9	4.1	6.75
A8	1.6	7.6	4.5
A9	2.1	9.7	13.5

D. Case Study 4

Assuming that there is a ranking problem for 5 alternatives (A1-A5), each alternative involving 4 criteria (C1-C4). Table VIII presents the calculated values of the criteria. C1 and C2 belong to category B, whereas C3 and C4 belong to C. Without losing generalization, the weights of the 4 criteria were chosen equal to 0.25. As shown in Table VIII, the value of C1 in alternative A2 was zero, which was the highest value among the 5 alternatives. Therefore, neither (3), (7), and (8) nor N2 nor N4 can be used. The normalization combinations T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, and T11 do not function properly due to their dependence on N2 and N4. This phenomenon shows that in some divergent cases, the MACONT method cannot be used to rank the alternatives when only using T1.

TABLE VII. RANK ALTERNATIVES ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT DATA NORMALIZATION COMBINATION STRATEGIES

Alt.	MACONT											WSM	WPM	TOPSIS
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	T11			
A1	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
A2	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	5	6	8
A3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	2	2	4
A4	6	6	7	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	7	8	8	7
A5	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2
A6	7	7	6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	6	4	4	6
A7	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	6	5	3
A9	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7	7	5
A10	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

TABLE VIII. THE CRITERIA VALUES

Alt.	C1	C2	C3	C4
A1	-4	2.2	5	32
A2	0	1.8	1	19
A3	-3	2.4	4	41
A4	-3	2.5	0	35
A5	-1	1.6	-6	21

Since C3 at A4 is zero, (2) and (4) along with N1 and N2 cannot be used, the combinations T1 through T7 fail. In other words, the MACONT cannot be used to rank alternatives if the T1 normalization combination is used alone. According to the two scenarios analyzed above, only T10 can be coupled with MACONT to rank this problem. To verify the MACONT coupling strategy with T10, the ranking result was compared with the results of the TOPSIS and PIV methods. These methods were chosen because they do not use (2), (3), (4), (7), and (8). Furthermore, TOPSIS is considered the most popular

MCDM [24, 25], and PIV was proven to have a lower reverse phenomenon rate [26, 27]. Both TOPSIS and PIV methods are only used (1) for normalizing data. Detailed procedures for these methods can be found in [24-27]. Table IX shows the ranking results for this problem. The comparison shows that the ranking result using the MACONT algorithm with the normalization combination T10 was the same as the TOPSIS and the PIV. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed combination of MACONT and T10 to classify problems when the other methods cannot be used.

TABLE IX. RANKING RESULTS COMPARISON AMONG DIFFERENT METHODS

Alt.	MACONT + T10	TOPSIS	PIV
A1	5	5	5
A2	2	2	2
A3	4	4	4
A4	3	3	3
A5	1	1	1

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed 10 combination strategies of normalization techniques for integration with MACONT. Four case studies were conducted independently, in which the type of data, the number of criteria, and the alternatives varied to assess the efficiency and the response capacity of the proposed methods. The conclusions are drawn as follows:

- When combining all 11 data normalization strategies with the MACONT method, the optimal solution was always the same as the optimal solutions when using the other MCDM methods.
- When $y_{ij} = 0$, the normalization strategy T1 cannot be adapted to determine the final result. To overcome this issue, a new normalization strategy (T10) was presented, which can be applied to rank alternatives.
- This study combined and investigated only 6 data normalizing methods that result in 11 distinct data normalization combination strategies. Future research should focus on other data normalization techniques, such as Jüttler-Korth, Peldschus, and Z-score, to develop more suitable combination strategies and evaluate them with the original MACONT method.

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A New Approach for Optimizing the Extraction of Association Rules

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ABSTRACT

Association rule methods are among the most used approaches for Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD), as they allow discovering and extracting hidden meaningful relationships between attributes or items in large datasets in the form of rules. Algorithms to extract these rules require considerable time and large memory spaces. This paper presents an algorithm that decomposes this complex problem into subproblems and processes items by category according to their support. Very frequent items and fairly frequent items are studied together. To evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm, it was compared with Eclat and LCMFreq on two actual transactional databases. The experimental results showed that the proposed algorithm was faster in execution time and demonstrated its efficiency in memory consumption.

Keywords-KDD; data mining; association rules; frequent itemset

I. INTRODUCTION

Association rule methods [1, 2] are widely used in data mining [3, 4] which is the heart of Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD) [5, 6]. This approach was introduced to analyze the shopping cart or transaction data [2]. As each database transaction contains all items purchased by a customer, an association rule method identifies attributes or items that are often purchased together and discovers some meaningful dependencies and relationships between items sold for making predictions or decisions [7]. These relations are in the form of a rule: if X , then Y ($X \rightarrow Y$ (75%)), where X is the condition of the rule and Y is its conclusion. In addition, 75% support of the rule indicates that 75% of the customers who buy item X also buy item Y at the same time. These rules provide a decision support tool [8] in many areas, including the commercial sector. The association rule extraction is an

essential two-step process that discovers frequent item set lists and generates association rules from these. The first step is the most costly in terms of execution time and memory space [9]. In databases that contain thousands of items, the larger the number of items, the larger the number of generated itemsets. This condition produces an explosion in the number of association rules. In a database that contains n items, $2^n - 1$ itemsets can be generated [10], producing a very large number of rules.

Each item or itemset is characterized by its support (Supp) [7]. The Apriori algorithm [11] minimizes calculations and the number of itemsets based on the support value. It only maintains frequent itemsets, where Supp is above a predefined threshold by the user (minimal support, MinSupp). MinSupp belongs to the interval $[0,1]$, varies in decreasing order from 1 to 0, and depends on the database characteristics. The complexity of extracting frequent itemsets is sensitive to

MinSupp, as it increases rapidly when it decreases, given that more items exist. Therefore, the number of generated itemsets increases, which implies more complexity in terms of computation time and memory space. Several methods were developed to extract frequent itemsets and restrict search memory space and computation time. These methods can be grouped into two categories: the candidate generation approach and the pattern growth approach [12].

The candidate generation approach generates a list of candidate itemsets of size k to find the list of sets of frequent k -itemsets. Then these itemsets are generated to build a list of new candidate itemsets of size $k+1$. This procedure is repeated until the set, $k+1$ -frequent itemsets, is empty. This method allows a decrease in the amount of search memory space required based on the antimonotone property. If an itemset is not frequent, then all its super-itemsets are also not frequent. The Apriori algorithm [11] is the most well-known algorithm of this family. Nevertheless, other algorithms that belong to the same category are DHP [13], DIC [14], Eclat [15], and Bitmap [16]. The main drawback of these algorithms is the scanning of the transactional database several times.

The pattern growth approach suggests removing the need to generate candidates to extract frequently occurring itemsets. This approach uses certain data structures, in particular trees, to accurately describe the transactional database. One of the most well-known algorithms in this family is the FP (Frequent Pattern)-Growth [17], which uses a specialized data structure called FP-Tree. The H-Mine [18], AFOPT [19], MFIs [20], and LCMFreq [21] are other methods that apply this approach. Recently proposed ideas employ prefix trees as a data structure to find frequent itemsets [22-26]. These approaches have the benefit of not performing candidate generation and avoiding multiple database scans. On the contrary, the data structures used in these algorithms result in significant memory consumption, and the development of these algorithms is more complex than in the candidate solution approach.

This study proposes a new algorithm based on Apriori because it is the foundation of other algorithms and is regarded as a reference. The proposed algorithm reduces the amount of memory space and time required for the discovery of frequent itemsets.

II. BASIC NOTIONS

Let $I = \{i_0, i_1, \dots, i_n\}$ be a set of n items, $T = \{t_1, \dots, t_m\}$ a database of m transactions, where each transaction t_i has a unique identifier and is a subset of items $t_i \subseteq I$.

- Definition 1: An itemset X is any item subset of I . For example $\{i_1, i_5, i_8\}$ is an itemset composed of three items.
- Definition 2: A k -itemset is a set of itemsets, where each itemset is composed of k items. For example, the itemset $\{i_1, i_5, i_8\}$ is considered an element of the 3-itemset.
- Definition 3: The support $\text{Supp}(X)$ of an itemset X is the frequency of appearance of this itemset in the transactions of a database T or the ratio between the number of transactions t containing X ($X \subseteq t$) and the total number of transactions in the database T .

$$\text{Supp}(X) = \frac{|t_i \in T / X \subseteq t_i|}{|T|} \quad (1)$$

where $||$ is the cardinal operator in the sets theory.

- Definition 4: An itemset X is frequent in a database T if its support is greater than or equal to a given threshold: $\text{Supp}(X) \geq \text{MinSupp}$.
- Definition 5: An association rule is an implication expression among itemsets of the form $X \rightarrow Y$, where $X \subset I$, $Y \subset I$, and $X \cap Y = \emptyset$.

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. Example

In a transaction database that contains n frequent items, the Apriori algorithm can generate a large number of itemsets k -itemset (a subset of items of size k), which is equal to all possible combinations C_n^k . For example, for $n=100$ items, 3921225 itemsets of size 4 can be generated. The proposed algorithm can reduce the number of generated k -itemsets by studying the items by category according to their support. To better understand the proposed algorithm, its principle of operation is illustrated through the following example: Table I shows the transaction base T , which contains 10 transactions and 14 items ($a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, m, n, p, x, y, z$), where each transaction contains one or more items.

TABLE I. EXAMPLE OF TRANSACTION DATABASE

Transaction ID	Items
1	a, b, f, n, x
2	a, n
3	b, c, d, f, g, h, m
4	b, c, g, h, m, n
5	a, b, f, z
6	a, f, g, y
7	a, b, c, f, g, n
8	a, c, d, e, h, y, n, p
9	a, f, n
10	a, d, e, g, h, y, p

The support of each item is: $\text{Supp}(a) = 0.8$, $\text{Supp}(f) = \text{Supp}(n) = 0.6$, $\text{Supp}(b) = \text{Supp}(g) = 0.5$, $\text{Supp}(c) = \text{Supp}(h) = 0.4$, $\text{Supp}(d) = \text{Supp}(y) = 0.3$, $\text{Supp}(e) = \text{Supp}(m) = \text{Supp}(p) = 0.2$, $\text{Supp}(x) = \text{Supp}(z) = 0.1$.

The following parameters are used: MaxSupp_i is the greatest support, MinSupp_i is the first minimum support, MinSupp is the minimum support, and a parameter $\alpha \in]0, 1[$. In this example, $\text{MaxSupp}_i = 0.8$, $\alpha = 0.72$, $\text{MinSupp}_i = 0.35$, and $\text{MinSupp} = 0.2$. Then, instead of processing all items that are greater than MinSupp at the same time as the majority of the algorithms do, the items are considered by the group of intervals $[\text{MaxSupp}_i, \text{MinSupp}_i]$, and the intersection between two successive intervals must be non-empty. The following equations are used to find the MaxSupp_i and MinSupp_i :

$$\text{MaxSupp}_i = \alpha * \text{MaxSupp}_{i-1} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{MinSupp}_i = \alpha * \text{MinSupp}_{i-1} \quad (3)$$

Table II shows the items obtained in each interval. Table III shows the complexity of (C_n^k) to generate the 2- and 3-itemsets by the proposed and the Apriori algorithms:

TABLE II. EXAMPLE OF THE NEW ALGORITHM

Step (i)	MaxSupp _i	MinSupp _i	Items of each interval	Number of items
1	0.8	0.35	a, f, n, b, g, c, h	7
2	0.576	0.252	b, g, c, h, d, y	6
3	0.414	0.181	c, h, d, y, e, m, p	7
STOP MinSupp = 0.181 < 0.2				

TABLE III. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY

Algorithm	k=2	k=3
Proposed	$C_7^2 + C_6^2 + C_7^2 = 21 + 10 + 21 = 42$	$C_7^3 + C_6^3 + C_7^3 = 35 + 20 + 35 = 90$
Apriori	$C_{12}^2 = 66$	$C_{12}^3 = 220$

The Apriori algorithm builds up to 220 3-itemsets, whereas the proposed algorithm builds 90. Thus, the proposed algorithm reduced the number of generated itemsets, implying a reduction in the number of product association rules and, therefore, reducing calculation time.

B. Constraints

The parameters α and $MinSupp_1$ must be selected in a way to have acceptable and non-disjoint intervals to maintain the association between the items of the different intervals.

- Disjoint intervals: for example, $\alpha = 0.6$, $MaxSupp_1 = 0.7$, and $MinSupp_1 = 0.6$ gives the first interval $[0.7, 0.6]$. $MaxSupp_2 = \alpha \times MaxSupp_1 = 0.6 \times 0.7 = 0.42$ and $MinSupp_2 = \alpha \times MinSupp_1 = 0.6 \times 0.6 = 0.36$ gives the second interval $[0.42, 0.36]$. Therefore, the items that support the interval $[0.6, 0.42]$ are ignored and the association between the items of the two intervals $[0.7, 0.6]$ and $[0.42, 0.36]$ is lost.
- Acceptable intervals: avoid intervals that are sufficiently close to each other to ignore the same items (repetitive intervals). For $MaxSupp_1 = 0.7$, $MinSupp_1 = 0.6$, and $\alpha = 0.98$, the next interval is $[0.686, 0.588]$. Therefore, the same items of the interval $[0.7, 0.6]$ can be studied.

The selection of α and $MinSupp_1$ must be studied.

C. The Proposed Algorithm

The principles of the proposed algorithm are:

- The following parameters are set in advance: $MaxSupp_1$, $MinSupp_1$, $MinSupp$ ($MinSupp_1 > MinSupp$), $\alpha \in]0, 1[$.

- The Apriori algorithm is applied to the items with support in $[MaxSupp_1, MinSupp_1]$ to find the generated k -itemsets.
- Step 2 is repeated for the intervals $[MaxSupp_i, MinSupp_i]$ until $MinSupp > MinSupp_i$, using (2) and (3).

The final global set of k -itemsets obtained is the union of the sets of k -itemsets obtained in each interval. The pseudocode representation for this algorithm is:

```

Algorithm frequent_itemsets
Input: T,  $\alpha$ , MinSupp1, MaxSupp1, MinSupp
//Knowing that MinSupp < MinSupp1 < MaxSupp1, 0 <  $\alpha$  < 1
Output: List of Frequent Itemsets (LFI)
1. Repeat
2.  $L_{ii} =$  list of items  $\in [MaxSupp_i, MinSupp_i]$ 
3. Apply the Apriori algorithm on  $L_{ii}$  to find the  $LFI_i$  list that represents the set of frequent  $k$ -itemsets in the interval  $[MaxSupp_i, MinSupp_i]$ 
4.  $i++$ 
5.  $MaxSupp_i = \alpha \times MaxSupp_{i-1}$ 
6.  $MinSupp_i = \alpha \times MinSupp_{i-1}$ 
7. Until ( $MinSupp > MinSupp_i$ )
8. LFI =  $\cup_i LFI_i$ 
    
```

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND EVALUATION

A. Dataset Description

To measure the performance of the proposed against the Apriori algorithm, their computational complexity was compared on two real benchmark databases of different sizes (i.e. different numbers of items and transactions) [27]. Table IV shows the characteristics of these databases.

TABLE IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Dataset name	Number of items	Number of transactions
Chess	75	3196
Mushroom	119	8124

B. Experiments and Validation

Different values of α , $MinSupp_1$, and $MinSupp$ were examined for each database to find the lower computational complexity. Table V presents the obtained experimental results.

TABLE V. DATABASE TEST RESULTS

Dataset	Minimum support ($MinSupp$)	Apriori algorithm	Proposed algorithm		
		Number of frequent items	Settings α , $MinSupp_1$	Intervals	Number of items in the interval $[MaxSupp_i, MinSupp_i]$
Chess	0.6020	34	$\alpha = 0.9$ $MinSupp_1 = 0.85$	$[0.9997, 0.85]$	16
				$[0.8998, 0.765]$	9
				$[0.8098, 0.6885]$	8
				$[0.7288, 0.6020]$	10
Mushroom	0.0666	66	$\alpha = 0.55$ $MinSupp_1 = 0.4$	$[0.9654, 0.4]$	21
				$[0.5310, 0.22]$	28
				$[0.2921, 0.121]$	25
				$[0.1607, 0.0666]$	20

The computational complexity according to the k items appearing in the itemsets for the two algorithms was studied. Table VI shows the results of applying the two algorithms on the two datasets, pointing out the performance of the proposed algorithm in the reduction of the number of generated itemsets, indicating time-saving. For example, the number of 3-itemsets generated from the Mushroom database was 45760 itemsets for Apriori and 8046 itemsets for the proposed algorithm. Further experiments were carried out to compare execution time and memory space required by the proposed algorithm, Eclat, and LCMFreq. The total runtime was determined in seconds (s) and the memory space in megabytes (MB) at the end of each algorithm for the two databases. Tables VII and VIII show the obtained results.

TABLE VI. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY COMPARISON FOR $k=2$ AND $k=3$

Dataset	Computational complexity (C_n^k)			
	$k=2$		$k=3$	
	Apriori	Proposed	Apriori	Proposed
Chess	561	229	5984	820
Mushroom	2145	1078	45760	8046

TABLE VII. TOTAL RUNTIME COMPARISON

Dataset	Proposed	Eclat	LCMFreq
Chess	15.054	17.565	52.245
Mushroom	26.192	40.419	81.292

TABLE VIII. USED MEMORY SPACE COMPARISON

Dataset	Proposed	Eclat	LCMFreq
Chess	312.33	743.16	631.90
Mushroom	531.14	814.19	749.27

Figures 1 and 2 show the execution time and the memory space used by the three algorithms applied to the two transaction databases. Figure 1 shows that the time obtained by the proposed algorithm is less than the other two algorithms with times of ~15s and ~26s for the Chess and Mushroom databases, respectively. Figure 2 shows that the proposed algorithm is more efficient in terms of memory space used during execution, as it consumed only ~312MB and ~531MB for the Chess and Mushroom databases, respectively.

Fig. 1. Total runtime of each algorithm.

Fig. 2. Memory consumption of each algorithm.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new, based on Apriori, algorithm that allows the optimization of the extraction of association rules from databases. This optimization was based on the classification of items by categories according to their support. Experiments were carried out using the two transactional databases Chess and Mushroom [27] to compare the performance of the proposed algorithm with the Eclat and LCMFreq algorithms, showing that the proposed algorithm was faster in both cases and consumed less memory space. For example, the proposed algorithm can save more than half of the memory on the Chess database compared to the Eclat and LCMFreq algorithms. In future extensions of this study on improving the process of extracting frequent itemsets, the best value of the parameter α and the optimal number of intervals for reducing computational complexity in terms of execution time and memory consumption should be determined automatically. Furthermore, data structures, such as trees, could be investigated for the data representation of each interval of the transaction database instead of generating itemsets.

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The Effects of Resistance Spot Welding Parameters on the Mechanical Behavior of Stainless Steel

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ABSTRACT

The resistance spot welding process is a promising method for welding thin sheets of similar and dissimilar materials, principally stainless steel. Resistance spot welding is ensured using the combined effect of mechanical pressure and electric current through the thin sheets. In this experimental study, 304L stainless steel sheets were welded by resistance spot welding at various welding parameters. The welding parameters were welding effort, welding time, and welding current. Welding current varied from 10kA to 16kA, welding time varied from 10 to 13 cycles, and welding effort was fixed to 8 bars. The results showed that welding time had little effect on the mechanical properties compared to the welding current. The experimental results also showed that welding current is an important parameter for joining sheets and their mechanical strength. The external aspects of the spots were examined to determine the influence of welding parameters on the welded joints.

Keywords-RSW; welding parameters; welding current; mechanical strength; stainless steel 304L

I. INTRODUCTION

The Resistance Spot Welding (RSW) process is widely used in the manufacturing industry for joining metal sheets. Spot welding is the predominant joining process in several industries, especially in assembling automobile components. However, other products such as aerospace, furniture, and domestic equipment are joined using RSW [1]. RSW is one of the primary methods to join sheet metals on automotive components [2]. Stainless steel sheets are increasingly used in several applications due to their high corrosion resistance and good weldability [3]. The RSW process can be described by many parameters, such as time, current, and welding effort. Welding current is the most effective and common parameter to influence the welding result of a given material configuration. Welding time is important when calculating heat generation and resulting welds formation. Additionally, the

force magnitude is another variable that affects the outcome of the weld.

Many RSW studies showed that the formation of nuggets in any welded material depends on the optimized combination of parameters [4-7]. Weld quality is affected by several welding parameters: current intensity, welding time, force applied by the electrodes, contact resistance, and electrode size [8]. In [7], the effect of current and weld time with constant force on nugget growth was investigated in 304 austenitic stainless steel RSW. In [9], an attempt was made to optimize the welding parameters, namely welding current and time, in the RSW of AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel sheets. The static tensile shear test is the most common laboratory test used in the determination of weld strength due to its simplicity [10]. In [11-12], the most important factor affecting the tensile shear load-bearing capacity was the size of the weld nugget, as it depended mostly on the weldin

g current. The effect of welding current at constant welding time is considered in the evaluation of nugget size and tensile-shear load-bearing capacity of jointed materials. The influence of the RSW process parameters on 316 stainless steel was studied in [13]. The effects of welding parameters on the tensile shear strength of the joints were investigated in [14]. The effect of 3-9kA welding current on the structure and mechanical properties of welded joints was investigated in [5] for stainless and low-carbon steel. An increase in the tensile strength of the weld coupon was noticed when the welding current increased. Otherwise, the variation in welding current had no significant effect on the hardness value, as it mainly affected the size of the fusion zone and the heat-affected zone. In [15], the resistance of 304 stainless steel plates assembled by RSW was studied, along with the formation of nuggets under the effect of welding parameters in a DP600 dual-phase steel. In [16], the relations between nugget diameter and welding current and hardness along the welding zone of austenitic stainless steel 304 were studied. The results showed that the weld nugget increased with increasing welding current. In [17], assembled AISI-1008 steel sheets were welded by RSW, showing that the welding current was the most effective parameter controlling the weld tensile strength and the nugget diameter. In [18], weld current was the major governing factor affecting the tensile shear strength of resistance spot welded specimens in dissimilar joints formed by stainless steel 304 and galvanized steel, as it presented a high percentage compared to welding time and force. In [19-20], it was shown that using a high welding current, the material can exhibit high mechanical properties, and the tensile shear load-bearing capacity increased as the welding current increased.

This paper presents an experimental study to determine the effect of RSW parameters on tensile-shear strength of homogeneous lap joints in Stainless steel 304L with a thickness of 2mm and the geometric aspect of the welded points under the variation of welding current and time.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

This study used 304L stainless steel sheets with a thickness of 2.0mm. Tables I and II show its chemical composition and mechanical properties, respectively.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF 304L

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni
<0.03	<1.00	<2.00	<0.045	<0.015	17.5-19.5	8-10

TABLE II. MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF 304L

	E (GPa)	σ_e (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	A%	HRB
Provider data	200	310	520-670	45	80 max
Tested specimens	190	336	655	43.2	60

Figure 1 shows the stress-strain curve of 304L stainless steel, and Figure 2 shows the shape of the specimens, which were prepared with a size of 115×20×2mm. The overlap dimension A was equal to 20mm. The spot welding machine ARO FIX TYPE MC was used to join the overlapped samples. The settings of the RSW parameters directly depend on the application and are usually determined by testing. The welding

parameters used in this study were the recommended for 304L stainless steel; welding current varied from 10 to 16kA, welding time varied from 11 to 13 cycles, and the applied electrode force was equal to 8 bars with a diameter equal to 6mm.

Fig. 1. Stress-Strain curve of 304L stainless steel.

Fig. 2. Welding specimen by RSW.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on tensile shear tests, this study evaluated the maximum tensile shear force value for the joint that allows a fracture to occur [21]. Moreover, the diameter's dimension and the depth of spot welded points were determined under varying welding parameters. Figure 3 shows the load versus displacement curves obtained from the tensile-shear test performed on specimens with acceptable RSW joints under varying welding currents and time. Figure 3 shows the variation of the load versus the displacement until the fracture of the welded assembly by RSW for 8 bar welding force at $t=11$ cycles. The increase in current intensity increased the area of plastic deformation. This figure highlights several points by type. Points A present little distorted points. At points B, rotation occurred to align the sheets in the direction of loading and necking starts. Points C show the maximum breaking loads. Points D show the maximum effort achieved when the fracture propagated across the thickness in the neck region of one of the sheets, the propagation of the fracture in the base metal, and the tear around the point of the specimen to the final fracture.

Figure 4 shows the effect of welding current and welding time on the maximum breaking load (points C) for 8 bar welding force. Welding current varied from 11 to 16kA, and the time ranged from 11 to 13 cycles. The appearance shows an

increase in maximum tensile shear load bearing when increasing the welding current. Statistical tests are necessary on the fracture surfaces to better understand some interactions of welding parameters and random phenomena. In addition, the medium effect of welding time was noticed and the differences in the maximum tensile shear load-bearing for all welding currents varied from 0.18 to 2kN.

Fig. 3. Effect of welding current on the mechanical behavior of the welded assembly by RSW at 8 bar welding force and 10 cycles welding time.

Fig. 4. Effect of welding current and welding time on maximum tensile shear load bearing for welding force F=8 bar.

Figure 5 shows the effect of the welding current on the external diameter of the RSW point. An increase in weld current increases the external diameter of RSW for all welding times. For all welding currents and times, the maximum difference of the external diameter was 0.4mm, observed at welding current I=11kA, while the minimum was observed at I=16kA. This result shows that the effect of welding time is very small.

Figure 6 shows the effect of welding current and welding time. A minimum depth, equal to 0.6mm, was produced at I=10kN and t=12 cycles, and the maximum depth of 1.12mm was produced at 13 cycles. This graph shows a random effect. Statistical analysis is required to investigate the effect of welding parameters on the geometric parameters of RSW.

Figure 7 shows the fracture of welded 304L steel sheets plate by RSW under tension/shear loads. The fracture was initiated in the heated affected zone and propagated in the base metal. This propagation was made according to the mode I of fracture.

Fig. 5. Effect of welding current and welding time on the external diameter of RSW for welding force F=8 bar.

Fig. 6. Effect of welding current on maximum tensile shear load bearing for welding force F=8 bar.

Fig. 7. Effect of welding parameters on the fracture modes in RSW for applied load F= 8 bar: (a) I=10kA, t=10 cycles, (b) I=10kA, t=11 cycles, and (c) I=10kA, t=13 cycles.

IV. CONCLUSION

An RSW process was applied on 304L stainless steel to experimentally investigate the external parameters of the RSW joints and the maximum tensile shear load bearing of the joints. Furthermore, the influence of welding parameters, including welding current and welding time at fixed welding force, on the

maximum tensile shear load bearing of the joints was studied using a factorial test. The conclusions deduced from this study are summarized as follows:

- The diameters of the RSW joints increased with increasing welding current and time.
- Welding time has a medium effect on the external diameter and the depth of RSW.
- An increase in welding current allows the increasing the depth of RSW.
- Tensile/shear tests show that the welding current is the dominant parameter in the evolution of the load/displacement curves.
- Increasing welding intensity increases the plastic deformation zone and the maximum tensile shear load bearing of joints.

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Modeling and Optimization of Piston Pumps for Drilling

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ABSTRACT

This study highlights the operational and practical advantages of using triplex mud pump systems in favor of duplex systems to optimize drilling capabilities under specific operational conditions. Additionally, the material selection of the piston subassembly was analyzed and simulated under operational parameters in SolidWorks to determine the advantages of using HNBR over NBR elastomer materials.

Keywords-pumps; piston; elastomer; finite element method; analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Mud pumps ensure the flow required for the drilling rig process within the circulation system, as shown in Figure 1. Mud pumps are powerful machines that pull the drilling fluid from the tank, inject it through the drill rods to and from the foot of the well, and bring the fluid loaded with detritus resulting from the drilling process to the surface [1]. In optimal operating conditions, mud pumps consume more than 60% of the power used in the rotary drilling process. Two, to four mud pumps are normally used in drilling rigs, mainly in turn, while others are kept as spare parts in the event of a failure at the main working pump. Sometimes the pumps are tied together to lift large amounts of mud to the surface [1-4]. Modifications to the construction type of pump are required by the drilling process, such as types 3.1, 2.2, and 6.1. Pumps 3.1 and 6.1 are high-flow and medium-pressure, and 2.2 are high-pressure pumps with a smaller and more uniform flow. Mud pumps must be able to achieve a pressure of 1400 bar, within the individual power limit of 1830KW.

II. TECHNICAL AND THEORETICAL BASES OF MUD PUMP CALCULATION

Mud pumps generate hydraulic energy to achieve efficient and optimized drilling [1]. Research conducted in rock dislocation laboratories to develop a new drilling technology led to the practical conclusions shown in Table I.

A. Piston Size Calculation

The piston metal disc is calculated as a circular plate embedded in the cylindrical hub of diameter $D_p=80\text{mm}$, under pressure $p_r=8.6347\text{MPa}$, and a contour load given by the

friction force between the piston and the cylinder, $F_f=108\text{N}$. The maximum unit efforts are calculated for circular with interior diameter constraint [1]:

$$\sigma_{rmax} = K_{r1} \frac{F_f}{h^2} \frac{p_r \cdot r^2}{t1} \frac{1}{h^2} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{r1} = -0.405, \quad K_{t1} = -0.121, \quad K_{r1}^p = -0.71, \quad \text{and} \quad K_{t1}^p = -0.213.$$

where σ_{rmax} is the maximum radial tension, K_{r1} is the stiffness constant of the plate in the radial direction, F_f is the load force, h^2 is the thickness of the plate, K_{t1} is the stiffness constant of the plate in the axial direction, p_r is pressure, and r^2 is the radius. The area of maximum stress is the upper area of the hub. The unitary efforts are:

$$\sigma_1 = -\frac{2655}{h^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_2 = -\frac{1512}{h^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_3 = -86.347 \quad (4)$$

where σ_1 , σ_2 , and σ_3 are the main tensions, and thickness h is calculated according to the energy theory of rupture:

$$\sigma_{echiv} = \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 + \sigma_3^2 - (\sigma_1\sigma_2 + \sigma_2\sigma_3 + \sigma_3\sigma_1)} \leq \sigma_a \quad (5)$$

where σ_{echiv} is the equivalent stress in the stress resistance theory. The piston is made of E355 steel, which is a high-strength and low-alloy steel, good for manufacturing. It is allowed $\sigma_a = 120\text{N/mm}^2$. Equation (2) admitted $h=20\text{mm}$ to calculate the sizing of the lantern lid. The cover of the lantern is required by a uniformly distributed pressure corresponding to

the test pressure. The lid can be assimilated with a double-recessed circular plate $p_b=19.4\text{MPa}$ and $R=100\text{mm}$.

TABLE I. WORKING PARAMETERS OF PUMPS

Column [in]	16 ³ / ₄ "	13 ³ / ₈ "	9 ⁵ / ₈ "	6 ⁵ / ₈ "
Q [dm ³ /s]	104	69.60	34.20	16.50
p [MPa]	8.6347	12.8860	7.56512	12.91255

Fig. 1. Circulation system diagram: 1: battle, 2: suction pipe, 3: mud pump, 4: pushing pipe, 5: shock absorber, 6: charger, 7: hydraulic hose, 8: hydraulic head, 9: drilling rig, 10: screed holes, 11: annular space, 12: gutter system, 13: cleaning device.

Fig. 2. Piston calculation scheme.

Fig. 3. Lantern cover calculation scheme.

$$T = -\frac{p_b \cdot r}{2}$$

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{d}{dr} \cdot (r\phi) \right] = -\frac{T}{D} \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{d}{dr} \cdot (r\phi) \right] = -\frac{p_b \cdot r}{2 \cdot D}$$

where T is the cut force, p_b is the pressure on the gross surface of the piston, r is the radius, d is the rod diameter, and D is the cylindrical bending stiffness of the plate [1]:

$$M_\theta = -\mu \cdot D \cdot \frac{d\phi}{dr}$$

$$\Rightarrow M_\theta = -\mu \cdot D \cdot \frac{p_b}{16 \cdot D} \cdot (R^2 - 3 \cdot r^2) \tag{7}$$

$$M_r = -D \cdot \frac{d^2\phi}{dr^2} \Rightarrow M_\theta = -D \cdot \frac{p_b}{16 \cdot D} \cdot (R^2 - 3 \cdot r^2)$$

where M_θ, M_r is the bending moment in the tangential or radial direction of the circular plate. Table II shows the results for $r=R$.

TABLE II. RESULTS FOR $r = R$

Efforts in plate	M_θ	M_r
Values[kN]	-8.08	-24.25
Unitar Tensions in plate	σ_θ	σ_r
Values relations calculus for thickness h [kPa]	14.550/ h^2	4.848/ h^2

The resistance condition is given by:

$$\sigma_r \cdot \sigma_\theta > 0 ; |\sigma_r| \leq \sigma_a ; |\sigma_\theta| \leq \sigma_a \tag{8}$$

The lantern cover is made of E355, AISI/SAE/ASTM 1024, with $\sigma_a=180\text{N/mm}^2$ and $h=35\text{mm}$. Double-acting mud pumps have two-sided active pistons, and single-acting pistons use either plunger-type pistons or single-sided active pistons. A single-sided active piston has only one construction seal that is structurally similar to that of a two-sided active piston and removable seals. This lining is met on the back with a thick cloth insert that stops discharge. The piston rod connects the piston and the crosshead. At both ends of the piston, the rod ends with a conical and a cylindrical threaded part that connects to the piston body and the cross-head or with the extending rod [5-6]. The rod and the piston have parts such as the connecting thread, the conical head of the rod, and the interchangeable piston hole, as regulated by the API 7K norms.

B. Determination of the Efforts in the Piston Rod

Figure 4 shows the forces acting on the piston rod.

Fig. 4. Piston rod loading scheme.

$$F_t = F_p + F_f \tag{9}$$

where F_t is the total force acting on the piston rod for the single-acting triplex pump, F_p is the force due to pressure on the active face of the piston, and F_f is the friction force that appears between the jacket and the piston.

$$F_p = \frac{\pi \cdot D^2}{4} \cdot p \tag{10}$$

where p is the pressure acting on the piston face.

$$F_f = \mu \cdot N \cdot D \cdot l1 \tag{11}$$

where μ is the coefficient of friction, $\mu = 0.02 \dots 0.1$, N is the normal reaction of the cylinder-piston interaction, D is the piston diameter, and $l1$ is the length of the sealing element.

C. Calculation of Piston Thickness

The thickness of the piston metal disc is calculated by considering the disc as a circular plate embedded in the cylindrical hub of diameter d_b subjected to pressure. Figure 5 shows the piston loading diagram. This problem can be solved by considering the symmetrically charged flat plates, as in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Piston rod loading pattern.

Fig. 6. Charging scheme corresponding to symmetrically charged plates.

Fig. 7. Piston-cylinder concentricity for mud pumps: 1: the insertion end of the piston, 2: piston lining; a - nominal diameter tolerance.

III. MODELING AND SIMULATION

A. The 7K API Recommendations for Design Basics

According to the API 7K standard, mud pumps are piston pumps that have certain construction bases. The most important considered for this study are:

- The main load-bearing components perform the pump discharge pressure, except for consumables and shut-off components such as gaskets, pistons, piston rods, seals, valves and seats, caps, clamps, bushings, and fasteners.
- Pressure-evaluated components must be subjected to a test pressure 3.5 times higher than the operational working pressure. Hydraulic testing is performed according to API Chapter 8.7.
- The design of the suction components of the mud pump of the hydrostatic circuit must take into account that the suction pressure during the test will have a value twice higher than the one required by the applicant.
- For double-acting pumps, the fluid outlets from the mud pump cylinders and from the piston body.
- Mud pump pistons must match the standard concentricity of the piston rod. The outer diameters of the piston must be suitable for the use of gaskets or cylinders with increases or changes in diameter.

The standardized dimensions of the main components of mud pumps are presented in the appendices of the API 7K standard. For example, Annex C provides recommendations for the mud pump piston, terminology, and maintenance, while the provisions regarding the outlet area of the drilling fluid in Annex C.3 are very important. The recommendations for mud pump piston standardize the terminology for the main parts of the mud pump, except for a relatively small number of related parts. This provides a common language for the industry, which is especially important for communication.

B. 3D Modeling of the Piston

Mud pump piston modeling is performed using 3D graphic modeling and a finite element calculation program. This piston was made of low alloy medium carbon steel 34CrMo4 in SR EN 10083-3 and made of an NBR elastomer with an elastic modulus of 3.99MPa [7-9]. According to [10], the material yield strength is $\sigma_c=450$ MPa. The pump piston was machined in steps and its diameter varied in different sections [8]. The piston assembly had 190.5mm outer diameter and 100mm thickness. The function 'sketch' was used to model the metal part of the piston and choose the drawing plan, as seen in Figure 9. After that, a circle was drawn on the front plane, which would be extruded to obtain a cylindrical body to represent one of the steps of the drive piston. The 2D sketch of the lower diameter was made, after which the extrusion was to create the 3D shape of the metal part of the piston, as seen in Figure 10. Then, the piston elastomer was made using the same steps. Instead of the 'Extrude' function, the 'Cut Extrude' was used to get the desired shape for the metal piston, as seen in Figure 11. Finally, an assembly was made that consisted of the metal part of the piston and the elastomer.

Fig. 8. Drawing plane of the piston.

Fig. 9. Metallic part of the piston.

Fig. 10. Piston elastomer.

Fig. 11. Complete assembly of the piston.

C. Finite Element Analysis of 3PN-1000 Pump Piston Strain Study to Rated Operating Pressure

A simulation was performed to complete the study. The piston components were: the metal piston had a material of 34CrMo4 and the elastomer was Nitrile Butadiene Rubber (NBR) [8, 12]. A full 3D model was chosen for the finite element analysis [13]. A fixed face was established, that

defined the metal part of the piston as fixed. This action can be done from the study toolbar by right-clicking on "Fixture", then choosing the "Fixed geometry" module [14].

Fig. 12. Defining the fixed face of the piston.

Fig. 13. Pressure applied to piston elastomer (rear).

Fig. 14. Pressure applied to the piston elastomer (outside).

The next step was to define the nominal pressure to which the piston would be subjected, namely the pressure between the elastomer and the top cover of the piston jacket. The nominal pressure was set to 156MPa. The same procedure was applied to the upper part of the elastomer for the pressure between the piston sleeve and the elastomer. Then a simulation was performed to examine how the piston deforms under the assigned loads. As can be seen in Figures 15-18, the deformation of the piston was free, that is, the piston deformed in an open space but not inside the cylinder. Due to this deformation, there is a possibility of fluid leakage between the piston sleeve and the piston. Table III presents the principal properties of the NBR material for the first simulation [2, 5, 9]. The dimensions for the finite element analysis were $D=133/5\text{mm}$, $d=80\text{mm}$, and $h=40\text{mm}$, which impact the results obtained from the analysis. The area that suffers the most

deformation is marked in red. The images show the initial position of the piston elastomer and how it deformed.

TABLE III. MATERIAL OF THE NBR ELASTOMER [11]

Property	Value	Units
Elastic modulus	3990000	N/m ²
Poisson ratio	0.49	N/A
Shear modulus	2900000	N/m ²
Mass density	1000	kg/m ³
Tensile strength	13787100	N/m ²
Compressive strength		N/m ²
Yield strength	9237370	N/m ²
Thermal expansion coefficient	0.00067	/K
Thermal conductivity	0.14	W/(m·K)

Fig. 15. Deformation of the NBR piston at 1/2 from the nominal pressure.

Fig. 16. Deformation of the piston with NBR at nominal pressure.

TABLE IV. MATERIAL OF THE HNBR ELASTOMER

Property	Value	Units
Elastic modulus	3430000	N/m ²
Poisson ratio	0.49	N/A
Shear modulus	2900000	N/m ²
Mass density	1200	kg/m ³
Tensile strength	20787100	N/m ²
Compressive strength		N/m ²
Yield strength	9237370	N/m ²
Thermal expansion coefficient	0.00067	/K
Thermal conductivity	0.14	W/(m·K)

In terms of stress, a "strain" graph can be used to determine the most requested point of the piston when operating at a

pressure of 15.6MPa. Table V shows the deformation details of the piston with the NBR and HNBR materials.

Fig. 17. Equivalent strains of HNBR elastomer.

Fig. 18. Deformation of the piston with HNBR.

TABLE V. RESULTS OBTAINED FROM THE PROCESSING OF FEA DIAGRAMS

No.	Type parameter FEA	Pressure in pump (MPa)	NBR (mm)	HNBR (mm)
1	Equivalent strain (ESTRN)	35	2.84	1.94
		15.6	2.499	1.447
2	Resultant displacement (URES)	15.6	6.708	9.016
		7.8	3.354	4.508

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated new types of rubber-to-gasket piston connections, namely NBR and HNBR. The mechanical performance of both was systematically studied using theoretical and finite element analysis methods. Compared to the traditional criteria, the following conclusions were obtained:

- Simulations of NBR and HNBR piston elastomer materials [9] showed that in a mud pump with large diameter pistons operating at low pressures, the NBR can be used as it deforms sufficiently so that fluid losses are not high and the friction between the jacket and the piston is optimal.
- In the case of mud pumps with small diameter pistons and high pressures, the HNBR elastomer can be used because it

deforms much more easily than the NBR, the liquid losses will be lower, but instead, there would be more friction between the piston and the cylinder, but in no case excessive.

- The operating season of the mud pump can be taken into account. For example, in winter, the HNBR can deform much more easily at low temperatures compared to NBR, while in summer both can be used. The stresses on the HNBR elastomer are distributed differently than those on the NBR. In the case of the HNBR elastomer, there are no longer stresses on the contact surface between the elastomer and the metal piston.
- The SolidWorks software can perform finite element analysis studies of both parts and assemblies to validate rig performance. This capacity enables the custom rig manufacturer to improve the strength and performance of its equipment while decreasing weight, material usage, and associated costs in the process.
- The material and weight of the rigs should be reduced because they are frequently assembled on the back of a truck. Using professional software, linear static stress analyses can run not only on critical components but also on each sub-assembly of the piston pump. This capability allows for reducing the weight of the rigs by a small percentage while maintaining strength and performance.

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Reutilizing Single-Use Surgical Face Masks to Improve the Mechanical Properties of Concrete: A Feasibility Study

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ABSTRACT

The coronavirus outbreak (COVID-19) has caused a sharp increase in the use of Single-Use Surgical Face Masks (SUSFMs) as personal protective equipment. These eventually end up in waste disposal facilities causing environmental pollution. Those that end up in the water bodies fragment into microplastics that affect marine life. Since the SUSFM materials are made from polypropylene, a thermoplastic polymer material that takes a long time to degrade, it is important to develop sustainable mitigation measures to remove them from the environment. This study investigated the feasibility of reutilizing SUSFMs in concrete. SUSFMs were shredded and added to C30/37 grade concrete in various percentages, 0%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%, 2.5%, and 3.0%, by mass of cement content. The specimens were cured for 28 days before being tested for compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, and ultrasonic pulse velocity. The compressive strength decreased with an increase in the length and dosage content. The least decrease of 10.4% was observed at 0.5% content of 30mm length of SUSFM material. The results showed that concrete improved regarding splitting tensile strength, with the highest increase of 15.2% at 0.5% content of 30mm SUSFM. In addition, the overall quality of concrete remains at UPV values of more than 4000m/s registering good quality concrete. The results underscore the use SUSFM material in concrete in order to improve its quality while at the same time reducing waste.

Keywords-covid-19; polypropylene; surgical face masks; personal protective equipment

I. INTRODUCTION

With the outbreak of coronavirus disease (covid-19), a sharp increase in the use of Single-Use Surgical Face Masks (SUSFMs) occurred globally [1]. The daily use of SUSFMs in Africa and Asia is currently over 700 million pieces and 2.2 billion pieces, respectively [2]. In June 2020, it was estimated that the SUSFMs that were discharged into the environment every month were 129 billion pieces [1]. With the use of the model developed in [2], 6.9 billion pieces, or 0.2 million tons of SUSFMs are generated globally per day. These eventually

end up in waste facilities or water bodies and landfills. The SUSFMs are mainly made from polypropylene, a thermoplastic polymer, which remains in the environment for a long time (over 25 years) [1]. Those that end up in water bodies fragment into microplastics causing problems to marine life [3] and probably end up in the food chain. Authors in [4] deduced that the effects of this environmental pollution will continue to have an impact on human life long after the Covid-19 pandemic.

In Kenya, the Government made mandatory wearing face masks in public. So, there has been a massive use of SUSFMs

leading to a massive generation of waste. Despite the Government putting in place systems, especially in health facilities, to ensure the safe disposal of SUSFMs, hand gloves, and other pieces of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), some are finding themselves in the environment. At the household level, there is a haphazard disposal of SUSFMs. They are disposed of along with normal household disposables, hence they end up in landfills or are dumped directly into open fields, roadsides, and walkways and are eventually washed away into water bodies. In addition, they are often flushed through toilets into the sewer lines, blocking the sewer reticulation systems and causing overflows.

To mitigate this global problem, several studies have been undertaken to examine the re-utilization of SUSFMs in the construction of infrastructure to not only reduce pollution, but also offer green solutions [5]. Concrete is strong when subjected to compressive forces and weak to tensional forces. Authors in [6] deduced that adding uniformly dispersed, small, and closely spaced fibers to concrete would not only control dry shrinkage cracking, but also enhance tensile strength, fatigue resistance, and ductility. Studies are active in areas of reutilizing waste materials to generate green concrete [7]. Authors in [8] used SUSFMs with Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCA) to produce a blend material that can be used as a base and/or subbase for road construction. 1% of SUSFM material content mixed with RCA gave the best values of unconfined compressive strength and resilient modulus. Authors in [9] used shredded plastic fibers from beverage bottles in concrete. The results showed that there was an increase in compressive strength by 43.4% at 1.5% fiber content. Further, there was a notable increase of 82.2% in the flexural strength at a fiber content of 1.75% and improved Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV) of concrete by 44.4% at 0.25% fiber dosage. Authors in [10], while evaluating permeability and plastic shrinkage of polypropylene fiber reinforced concrete, concluded that increasing the polypropylene fiber content in concrete decreases compressive strength. The highest decrease in compressive strength of 10% was recorded at 0.3% fiber content while the least decrease of 2% was recorded at 0.1% fiber content. There was a noticeable increment in the tensile strength with the highest increase of 39% at 0.1% polypropylene fiber content. It was also concluded that plastic fibers reduce shrinkage cracking by more than half.

Authors in [11] used green and white recycled polypropylene fibers in concrete. It was found that with 1% green polypropylene fiber content, there was an increase of 69.7% in compression strength, 276.0% in flexural strength, and 269.4% in split tensile strength. At the same content of 1% white polypropylene fibers, an increase of 39.4% compressive strength, 162.4% flexural strength, and 254.2% split tensile strength was reported. Authors in [12] used industrial waste plastic fibers in concrete. It was deduced that the highest compressive strength was registered at fiber content at 0.5% of 50mm fibers while the highest flexural strength was recorded at 1.0% fiber content of 50mm length. They concluded that the optimum dosage of 50mm waste plastic fibers was 0.75%. Authors in [13] studied the influence of the length of polypropylene fibers on compression and flexural strength. It

was observed that an increase in the length of polypropylene fibers increased flexural strength but decreased the compressive strength of concrete.

Much research has been conducted on the effect of waste plastic materials on concrete. However, there are no conclusive studies on the use of waste SUSFM material in new concrete. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the possibility of the use of SUSFM material in concrete production. The objective was to evaluate the effect of the addition of SUSFM material on concrete's compressive strength, UPV, and splitting tensile strength. The results can guide the concrete consumers on how to incorporate SUSFMs in order to enhance the quality of concrete and at the same time break the landfill lifecycle of SUSFMs.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of strength class CEM1/42.5N conforming to Kenyan standard (KS EAS 18-1:2001) was used in the mixes. The coarse aggregates were obtained from Nzoia Quarry Ltd. The used coarse aggregates had granular sizes ranging from 10mm to 20mm with flakiness index of 16.5 and water absorption of 1.9%. The fine aggregates were river sand sourced from river Malakisi. They had maximum size of 5mm, specific gravity of 2.7, fineness modulus of 2.8, and a bulky density of 1510kg/m³. The particle size gradation obtained through sieve analysis showed that fine aggregate particle distribution was within the grading limits.

Fig. 1. A single-use surgical face mask.

For commercial consumption of the recycled SUSFMs, there must be an elaborate disinfection process to avoid cross-infection of the covid-19 virus. Several methods of cleaning surgical face masks have been proposed, such as ultraviolet germicidal irradiation [14]. It was also reported that the covid-19 virus can be destroyed in SUSFMs by heating at 70°C for 60 minutes [15]. However, with the current covid-19 restrictions, the use of recycled SUSFM materials in the study was not allowed, hence unused SUSFMs were utilized. Promo-Kings 3-ply surgical face masks (Figure 1) were sourced from a local

chemist in Bungoma town with the properties shown in Table I. The SUSFM fibers were produced by cutting off the nose strip and ear loops before cutting up into rectangular fibers of 5mm width and varied lengths of 20mm, 30mm, and 40mm (Figure 2). Sika plastiment 40 KE with a density of 1.05kg/m^3 was used as a plasticizer to achieve the desired workability in all concrete mixes where 1kg SUSFM fibers for every 100kg of cement dosage was adopted as per manufacturer's specifications. Ordinary drinking tap water supplied by the local water service provider was used in all mixes and specimen curing. The mix design adopted the Department of Environment (DOE)'s concrete design to produce C30/37 concrete. The mix material proportions are shown in Table II.

Fig. 2. Shredded single-use surgical face masks.

The fine and coarse aggregates were batched in saturated dry conditions by weight. Fine aggregates, coarse aggregates,

and cement were weighed and mixed on a dry metallic non-absorbent pan manually by using a spade until the mix was uniform. Half of the mixing water was added and mixing continued until the mix was uniform. The remaining half of the mixing water was mixed with sika plastiment 40KE plasticizer before adding it to the concrete mixture to avoid the cement paste from reacting directly with the plasticizer. The mixing continued until a uniform mix was achieved. The shredded SUSFMs were added slowly while mixing to allow even distribution and avoid clumping (Figure 3). Testing specimens from a total of 7 concrete mixes were used with cut-up SUSFM material in proportions of 0% as the control mix, 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%, 2.5% and, 3.0% by weight of cement in concrete for of 20mm, 30mm, and 40mm length of SUSFM fibers. This range is consistent with [11]. Despite the increase in the scope of the study, this aggregate range enabled the determination of both optimum volume and size of the SUSFM fibers in concrete in agreement with [12]. Using one set of aggregates (fiber) would not have yielded meaningful results for analysis.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF SUSFMs

Physical properties	
Size of SUSFMs	172.5mm by 97.0mm
Width of SUSFM fibers	5mm
Length of SUSFM fibers	20mm, 30mm, 40mm
Thickness	0.35mm
Aspect ratio	20m – 29; 30mm – 43; 40mm – 58
Density	0.166kg/m^3
Weight	3.5g
Shape	Rectangular

TABLE II. DESIGN MIX PROPORTION OF CONCRETE CONSTITUENTS PER m^3 OF CONCRETE

Batch No.	00	05	10	15	20	25	30
Cement (kg)	404	404	404	404	404	404	404
Water (kg)	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
Fine aggregates (kg)	679	679	679	679	679	679	679
Coarse aggregates (kg)	1107	1107	1107	1107	1107	1107	1107
SUSFM content (% of cement weight) %	0	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
SUSFM content (kg)	0	2.02	4.04	6.06	8.08	10.1	12.12

To prepare specimens for casting, the concrete molds were cleaned, dried, and lubricated with a thin coat of mold oil to aid in the removal of specimens. For the preparation of compressive strength and UPV test specimens, 150mm cubes were adopted, while for splitting tensile strength tests, specimens were cast in 100mm diameter and 200mm height cylinders. The prepared concrete was poured into molds in 3 layers while compacting with a poker vibrator for 20s to allow the concrete to settle and fill up all the voids. The concrete in the mold was levelled with a trowel and left undisturbed for 24 hours at room temperature under shade. The specimens were then de-molded by pressure from a compressor and were then submerged in the curing tank for 28 days (Figure 4). The test specimens of hardened concrete were removed from the curing tank and then were allowed to air dry before being tested. The same process was repeated for all the mixes.

A. Compressive Strength Testing

Compressive strength testing was conducted on a Universal Testing Machine, Basic wizard type with digital readout unit model no. 00701/A in accordance with EN 12390-3:2019. The

specimens were placed on the bearing surfaces of the testing machine between the platens central to the loading axle. A uniform rate of loading was applied until the tested specimen failed. The maximum load to the nearest 0.1N/mm^2 and the compressive strength were recorded. Three specimens were tested for each concrete regime and the average was considered as the compressive strength of the batch with the respective SUSFM material dosage.

B. Split Tensile Strength Testing

Split tensile strength testing was conducted on the same Universal Testing Machine in accordance with EN 12390-6:2009. The cylindrical test specimens were placed horizontally between the loading surface of the test machine and the load was gradually applied until the cylinder failed along the vertical diameter, as shown in Figure 5. The split tensile strength of the concrete cylinder specimen was recorded. Three specimens were tested for each concrete regime and the average was considered as the split tensile strength of the concrete batch with the SUSFM material.

Fig. 3. Mixing of concrete with added SUSFM fibers.

Fig. 4. Curing of concrete specimens.

Fig. 5. Concrete split tensile strength testing.

C. Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Testing

UPV was conducted on the samples using MATEST UPV testing machine model no. C372M in accordance with EN 12504-4:2004 (Figure 6). The ultrasonic pulse was generated by a pulse generator transmitted to the concrete surface. The time taken for the pulse to travel through the concrete and be

received by the transducer on the opposite side of the concrete specimen was measured. To ensure good contact, a thin film of solid jelly was applied between the interface of the concrete specimen surface and the transducer. UPV was determined to evaluate the relative quality of the concrete specimens with SUSFM material. Three specimens were tested for each concrete regime and the average was considered as the UPV of the concrete batch.

Fig. 6. UPV testing equipment.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compressive strength results are shown in Figure 7. The results indicated that the re-utilization of SUSFM materials in the manufacture of concrete leads to a systematic decrease in compressive strength. The compressive strength of the control specimen was 50.1N/mm^2 . The lowest decrease in compressive strength was 10.4% at 0.5% of 30mm length of SUSFM fibers, 11.6% at 0.5% of 20mm length, and 20.8% at 0.5% of 40mm length. The optimum dosage to yield the least negative impact on compressive strength was 0.5% content of 30mm length fibers. These results are in agreement with [10] in which it was concluded that increasing polypropylene fiber content in concrete decreases compressive strength. Similarly, a decrease in compressive strength was recorded in [16] when expanded polystyrene beads were added to the concrete. The reduction in compressive strength can be attributed to the low specific gravity of SUSFMs induced in concrete [12] and the presence of weak interfacial bonds between the binder material and SUSFM materials [4].

A total of 57 test cylindrical specimens were used in split tensile strength tests. The results, as represented in Figure 8, have shown that at 20mm length, split tensile strength decreases progressively from 9.1% at 0.5% dosage to the highest of 24.2% at 2.0% dosage. This shows a gradual decrease in split tensile strength with an increase in SUSFM material content in the concrete matrix. For 30mm length, the split tensile strength increased, compared to the control specimen, by 15.2% at 0.5% dosage and 3.0% at 1.0% dosage before dropping off and starts decreasing gradually at 1.5% dosage to the lowest decrease of 27.3% at 3.0% dosage. For 40mm length, split tensile strength registered an equal value to the control specimen of 3.3N/mm^2 at 0.5% SUSFM material dosage before decreasing gradually from 3.0% at 1.0% dosage to the lowest of 21.2% at 3.0% dosage.

Fig. 7. Compressive strength of concrete with different contents and lengths of SUSFM fibers.

Fig. 8. Split tensile strength of concrete with different contents and lengths of SUSFM fibers.

The specimens with SUSFM material of 30mm length at 0.5% and 1.0% dosage and with 40mm length at 0.5%, registered increased split tensile strength in comparison with the control specimen. These results showed that the best mix with regard to the highest split tensile strength was 0.5% dosage of 30mm length SUSFM fibers. The results obtained were in agreement with [10], where the split tensile strength was found to be more than the control specimen's when polypropylene fibers were added to normal concrete mix in percentages up to 0.25%. Above this dosage, the split tensile strength decreased in comparison with the control specimen. This also affirms to the results obtained in [17]. The increase in split tensile strength may be a result of filling of the micro-cracks developed in the concrete matrix by the fibers, hence preventing their propagation. They may have caused the cracks to meander and hence demand more energy to propagate and therefore increasing the ultimate tensile load [17]. The reduced split tensile strength could be a result of insufficient binder

matrix around the fibers for transfer of stresses from concrete fibers through bonding.

The results of the UPV test are shown in Figure 9. The UPV value for the control specimen was 4436m/s. For 20mm length of SUSFM material, UPV values increased by 1.4% at 1.0% dosage, after which the values dropped off at 1.5% dosage and progressively decreased to the lowest 4011m/s at 3.0% dosage representing a 9.6% decrease. For 30mm length of SUSFM material, UPV values increased at 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% dosages by 1.2%, 2.0%, and 0.3% respectively before gradually decreasing. For 40mm length, the UPV values increased by 1.7% at 0.5% dosage before starting to reduce progressively to the lowest of 4026m/s. Concrete with 30mm length SUSFM material had higher values of UPV compared to the same dosages of 20mm and 40mm lengths. The optimum dosage was 1.0% of 30mm length of SUSFM material. The UPV values for 20mm length SUSFM material ranged between 4320 and 4011. For the 30mm length, the UPV values ranged from 4487 to 4152 while for 40mm the values ranged from 4509 to 4026. All values were more than 4000m/s indicating that the quality of concrete is very good [9], whereas concrete that has UPV values greater than 4500m/s is considered of excellent quality [18]. High UPV indicates concrete with no voids and cracks as a result of fibers limiting the micro-cracks in the concrete matrix [19]. Other dosages registered reduced UPV values, decreasing with an increase in the SUSFM material content. This may be attributed to the reduced bonding of SUSFM materials and concrete [9].

Fig. 9. UPV of concrete with different contents and lengths of SUSFM fibers.

IV. CONCLUSION

Compressive strength results indicated that the re-utilization of SUSFM fibers in the production of concrete leads to a systematic decrease in compressive strength. Among all the concrete-SUSFM mixes, the concrete incorporating 0.5% dosage of 30mm SUSFM fiber length gave the lowest reduction in compressive strength. The compressive strength of more than 40N/mm² can be produced with additional SUSFM

material at a content of 0.5% by mass of cement material of 20mm or 30mm lengths.

The split tensile strength of concrete with 30mm and 40mm length SUSFM materials at 0.5% and 30mm length at 1.0% dosage was registered higher than that of the control concrete mix, indicating the benefits of SUSFM fibers. The optimum observed dosage was 0.5% of 30mm length of SUSFM fibers.

Concrete mixes with 20mm SUSFM fibers at 1.0%, 30mm at 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, and 40mm at 0.5% registered higher UPV values than the control concrete mix. The optimum dosage observed was at 1.0% of 30mm SUSFM fibers. Therefore, the addition of SUSFM material in concrete has positive benefits regarding the UPV.

Summarizing, the reutilization of waste SUSFMs creates green concrete with improved quality and at the same time sustainably removes this waste from the environment.

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A Deep Learning Model for Predicting Stock Prices in Tanzania

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ABSTRACT

Stock price prediction models help traders to reduce investment risk and choose the most profitable stocks. Machine learning and deep learning techniques have been applied to develop various models. As there is a lack of literature on efforts to utilize such techniques to predict stock prices in Tanzania, this study attempted to fill this gap. This study selected active stocks from the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange and developed LSTM and GRU deep learning models to predict the next-day closing prices. The results showed that LSTM had the highest prediction accuracy with an RMSE of 4.7524 and an MAE of 2.4377. This study also aimed to examine whether it is significant to account for the outstanding shares of each stock when developing a joint model for predicting the closing prices of multiple stocks. Experimental results with both models revealed that prediction accuracy improved significantly when the number of outstanding shares of each stock was taken into account. The LSTM model achieved an RMSE of 10.4734 when the outstanding shares were not taken into account and 4.7524 when they were taken into account, showing an improvement of 54.62%. However, GRU achieved an RMSE of 12.4583 when outstanding shares were not taken into account and 8.7162 when they were taken into account, showing an improvement of 30.04%. The best model was implemented in a web-based prototype to make it accessible to stockbrokers and investment advisors.

Keywords-deep learning; stock price prediction; Tanzania; Dar es Salaam stock exchange

I. INTRODUCTION

A stock is a security that represents the ownership of part of a company. Stock units are called shares and are traded in a stock exchange [1]. The desirable scenario with stocks is to buy when there is a good chance that a stock's price will rise and sell when there is a chance that it will decrease to gain profit from the difference between the selling and buying prices. In a nutshell, an investor aims to know when to buy and sell stocks to realize profit [2]. Many studies have been conducted to predict stock prices [3], and machine learning has been proven an effective method for this [4]. Ensemble techniques [5] and support vector machines [6] are some of the machine-learning

techniques used in stock prediction. However, recent advances in computational power and machine learning have led to deep learning methods [7]. Such methods can compute non-linear relationships among features and improve prediction accuracy [4]. Deep neural networks were used to forecast stock prices showing that they can improve prediction performance.

In Tanzania, the only stock exchange is the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), which was incorporated in 1996 and began trading operations in 1998 [8]. The low financial literacy of most citizens is one of the challenges that DSE faces [9]. This results in low stock market uptake and infrequent activity [10]. Nevertheless, machine learning and deep learning

techniques can be used to confront this challenge. Such methods have been used to predict stock prices in various countries, such as Morocco [11], Nigeria [12], and the United Kingdom [13]. This study was conducted due to the lack of similar efforts to predict stock prices in Tanzania. Furthermore, this study selected active stocks from DSE, and instead of developing a separate model for each company, it developed one dataset and a single (joint) model to predict next-day closing prices. Since each stock has a different number of outstanding shares, this study also examined whether it is significant to account for the number of outstanding shares of each stock when constructing the model.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) are deep learning methods designed to handle time-series data, such as stock data [14-15]. Unlike traditional recurrent neural networks, LSTM and GRU can memorize previous information for a long time as they do not suffer from vanishing and exploding gradients [16-17], making them a good fit for stock market predictions since stock market trends tend to repeat over time [18]. Numerous studies used LSTM, GRU, and other techniques to predict stock prices. LSTM was compared with Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Support Vector Regression (SVR), and Random Forest (RF) models to predict the closing prices of the iShares MSCI United Kingdom exchange-traded fund [13]. The results showed that LSTM performed better than the other models, but this study used only the previous closing price as predictive input. In [19], the daily closing prices of selected listed companies on the Colombo Stock Exchange were predicted using GRU, LSTM, Simple Recurrent Neural Network (SRNN), and Feedforward, and the previous closing, high, and low prices as predictive input. The results showed that SRNN and LSTM produced less errors compared to Feedforward in most cases. This study used only historical stock prices as features. In [2], different machine learning methods were used to forecast the daily closing price of companies listed on the NASDAQ stock exchange, concatenating data from multiple companies to form a single dataset for weekly and monthly predictions. Concatenation was performed on a sector basis, where companies from one sector formed one dataset, and models were developed for each sector/dataset. Linear Regression, Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, Ada Boost, Random Forest, Bagging, and K-Nearest Neighbors were used. The results showed that linear regression performed better than the other methods. However, the study did not employ a deep learning algorithm and did not consider outstanding shares. In [20], LSTM and SVR models were developed to predict the daily closing price of companies listed in the Dow Jones Index. The predictive inputs were the oil and gold prices and the previous closing price. The findings showed that the LSTM model outperformed the SVR. However, this study used only historical prices as features. In [21], 8 sectors of the Indian National Stock Exchange were chosen to develop the corresponding LSTM models and optimum risk portfolios for each sector. The actual returns yielded by the optimum risk portfolios were calculated and compared with the predicted by LSTM. The actual returns yielded by the optimum risk portfolios closely matched those predicted by LSTM. However, this study used only the previous closing price as predictive

input. In [22], a deep learning approach was used in a high-frequency database containing billions of transactions of US equities, finding that prediction accuracy could neither be improved by building company-specific models nor by building sector-specific models. On the other hand, including price and order flow history over many past observations improved forecast accuracy. This indicated that the patterns learned by the model are universal and not company or sector-specific. However, this study did not consider outstanding shares. In [23], a mobile application that included a stock price prediction model was developed for East African stock markets. The model was developed using LSTM and the predictive input was the previous closing price. However, the study used data from the NASDAQ stock exchange, which is a US stock market, and did not state whether the resulting model was tested on actual data from East African stock markets. In [24-26], several methods were incorporated to predict future stock prices and currency exchange rates.

As none of these studies attempted to study the importance of accounting for the number of outstanding shares of each stock when developing a joint model to predict the stock prices of multiple stocks, this study was conducted to address this gap.

II. METHODS

A. Data

Daily stock data was collected from the DSE for the period from January 2018 to April 2022. The data comprised of the features: opening price, low price, high price, previous closing price, volume, outstanding bids, outstanding offers, and price change. The "price change" feature was the difference between the closing and the opening price. In addition, the study examined the outstanding shares of each company and derived the features: "volume/outstanding shares", "outstanding bids/outstanding shares", and "outstanding offers/outstanding shares".

B. Experimental Setup

1) Experiment 1

This experiment did not take into account the number of outstanding shares of each stock. Therefore, the following features were employed: opening price, low price, high price, previous closing price, volume, outstanding bids, outstanding offers, and price change.

2) Experiment 2

This experiment considered the number of outstanding shares of each stock/company. As a result, the features "volume/outstanding shares", "outstanding bids/outstanding shares", and "outstanding offers/outstanding shares" were used instead of volume, outstanding bids, and outstanding offers, respectively. Therefore, the features used were: opening price, low price, high price, previous closing price, volume/outstanding shares, outstanding bids/outstanding shares, outstanding offers/outstanding shares, and price change.

C. Selection of Active Companies

Since DSE is a developing stock exchange, some companies have been inactive over time with zero or very low trading volumes [1]. This study ignored such companies to focus on companies that attract investors' attention. To identify companies with active shares, the study took the average "volume/outstanding shares" of each company over the last year. According to the study's dataset, the last year was between April 2021 and April 2022. Companies whose average of "volume/outstanding shares" was greater or equal to 0.005% were selected [27]. Table I shows companies whose average volume/outstanding shares was greater or equal to 0.005%.

TABLE I. COMPANIES WITH AVERAGE OF VOLUME/OUTSTANDING SHARES $\geq 0.005\%$

Company	Volume/Outstanding Shares (%)
CRDB	0.0137
DSE	0.0520
NICO	0.0151
NMB	0.0099
SWIS	0.0310
TBL	0.0089
TCC	0.0091
TCCL	0.0230
TOL	0.0214

Data visualizations were applied to the closing price attribute of each company in Table I. TBL and TCC were eventually dropped since their closing prices were observed to be static for more than two years. According to stockbrokers, this was due to block trades that dominated their shares [28]. Following the DSE regulations, block trades are reflected in volume statistics but are not used to update the closing price of the stock [29]. For this reason, the "volume/outstanding shares" average of these companies appeared above the threshold but there were no corresponding price movements. This study did not use these companies to avoid distracting the model's learning. On the other hand, TPCC was appended even though its average volume/outstanding shares was 0.0034%, below the threshold of 0.005%, as its price was increasing since 2020 and therefore it was desirable for prediction. Figure 1 shows the closing price history of TPCC. Therefore, eight (8) companies were selected: CRDB, DSE, NICO, NMB, SWIS, TCCL, TPCC, and TOL.

Fig. 1. Closing price history of TPCC.

D. Model Construction

The LSTM and GRU deep learning methods were used to

build the model. The model was developed in Google Colab using Keras with a TensorFlow backend. To ensure that all features are on a similar scale, the study utilized MinMaxScaler to scale all the features in a range between 0 and 1. In total, the dataset consisted of 8668 rows of data, where 80% were used for training and the remaining 20% for testing. The Adam optimizer was used together with the mean squared error as the loss function. The KerasTuner Bayesian optimization algorithm was used to tune the number of hidden layers, hidden units, and batch size. The regression evaluation metrics Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) were used to evaluate the performance of the models.

E. Model Deployment

The extreme programming model was adopted to develop a web-based prototype to embed the model and make it accessible to stockbrokers and investment advisors. This method was chosen because it ensures rapid delivery at minimum cost while promoting stakeholder participation in the development process [30]. Figure 2 shows the lifecycle of the extreme programming technique.

Fig. 2. Extreme programming lifecycle.

The planning phase is where requirements are gathered based on user stories describing various use case scenarios. Figure 3 shows the use case diagram of the system. At this stage, the work was broken down into iterations (small releases) based on which functionalities needed to be delivered first. Table II shows the iterations. The design, coding, and acceptance testing phases were performed iteratively. That is, after completing the designs for the first iteration, the study continued to implement them before proceeding to design the next iteration. After completing the first iteration, acceptance testing was performed, and adjustments were made per users' reviews. Thereafter, designing for the next iteration resumed, and the cycle was repeated. The design phase involved designing the user interface and logic. Figure 4 shows the flow chart of the make predictions use case. The coding phase involved the actual implementation of the designs, unit testing,

and continuous integration, while acceptance testing involved users' validation of the implemented functionalities. The release phase involved the delivery of a complete system to end users, where new requirements were noted for future directions.

TABLE II. FUNCTIONALITIES GROUPED INTO ITERATIONS

Iteration	Functionalities
First Iteration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload and manage stock data • Run model to make predictions • View predictions
Second Iteration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • View market analytics
Third Iteration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Logout • Change password • Add and manage users

Fig. 3. Use case diagram.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the make predictions use case.

The backend was implemented using Python and the Django framework due to its rich collection of libraries for performing different tasks, consistent documentation, and the active developer community [31]. This framework also helped to ensure the quick development of the system while aligning with security standards. The django-plotly-dash library was used to provide interactive visualizations, and MySQL was employed as the database engine. The system's frontend was built using HTML, CSS, and the Bootstrap framework. Furthermore, a datatable plugin was used to render interactive tables.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Model Performance Results

Tables III and IV show the results of experiment 1 and experiment 2, respectively.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENT 1 RESULTS

MODEL	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
LSTM	10.4734	6.9094	0.6359
GRU	12.4583	8.8794	0.8663

TABLE IV. EXPERIMENT 2 RESULTS

MODEL	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
LSTM	4.7524	2.4377	0.2147
GRU	8.7162	5.8629	0.5802

The results show that accounting for the outstanding shares of each stock significantly improved the prediction accuracy. In particular, the RMSE of LSTM improved from 10.4734 to 4.7524 when outstanding shares were considered, which was an improvement of 54.62%. On the other hand, the RMSE of GRU improved from 12.4583 before accounting for outstanding shares to 8.7162 when outstanding shares were considered, which was an improvement of 30.04%. The results confirm that, for a dataset consisting of multiple stocks, taking the ratio of outstanding bids, outstanding offers, and volume of each stock to its corresponding number of outstanding shares significantly helps the model to learn from the dataset more effectively. In general, the LSTM model performed better than the GRU. This could be because GRU keeps track of both long- and short-term dependencies through only one memory cell, called the hidden state, while LSTM utilizes two memory cells, one for long-term dependencies and the other for short-term [16]. Therefore, this could make LSTM more efficient at learning and memorizing patterns than GRU. However, these results contradict the results of [1] where GRU performed better than LSTM in predicting the daily closing prices of selected companies from the National Stock Exchange of India. One reason for this could be that the nature of the stock dataset used in this study was best captured by LSTM.

B. The developed prototype

The prototype developed consisted of eight web page interfaces that included the login page, the data entry page, the page to manage the entered data, the page to run the model, the view predictions page, the page to view market analytics, and the change password page. On the other hand, there was a page for the administrator to add or remove users. Figure 5 shows the view predictions page.

Company	Today	Next Day	Change	% Change
CRDB	380.00	379	-1.00	↓ 0.26%
DSE	1500.00	1429	-71.00	↓ 4.73%
NICO	610.00	596	-14.00	↓ 2.30%
NMB	2700.00	2703	+3.00	↑ 0.11%
SWIS	1000.00	998	-2.00	↓ 0.20%
TCCL	1960.00	1996	+36.00	↑ 1.84%
TOL	560.00	558	-2.00	↓ 0.36%
TPCC	4100.00	4126	+26.00	↑ 0.63%

Fig. 5. Predictions page.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study developed a deep-learning model to predict the next-day closing prices of selected active companies in Tanzania. Two deep learning methods, namely LSTM and GRU, were used and the results showed that the LSTM model performed better than the GRU. Therefore, the LSTM model was deployed in a web-based prototype application for stockbrokers or investment advisors. The study laid a foundation for more research to predict stock prices in Tanzania, showing how active stocks can be chosen and how the model can be developed and deployed.

Specifically, this study examined whether it is significant to account for the number of outstanding shares of each stock when developing a joint model to predict the stock prices of multiple stocks. The results showed that accounting for the number of outstanding shares of each stock significantly improved prediction accuracy. Specifically, the RMSE of LSTM decreased by 54.62%, while that of GRU decreased by 30.04% as a result of accounting for outstanding shares. Therefore, these findings indicate that it is significant to account for the number of outstanding shares of each stock when developing a joint model to predict the stock prices of multiple stocks. These results are useful to researchers who may require to concatenate together data of several stocks to realize a sizeable dataset for stock price prediction.

Future studies could explore other prediction ranges, such as the next hour, week, or month. Moreover, in addition to embedding a model to predict stock prices, a model can also be embedded to classify the risk tolerance level of an investor, to enable the system to provide an automated advisory tailored to his financial position. On the other hand, the use of new promising features, such as investors' sentiments, can be explored. Moreover, new deep learning architectures or combinations of hybrid models can also be investigated.

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An Experimental Study of the Dielectric Parameters of PVC Nano-Composites under Corona Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Poly-Vinyl Chloride (PVC) is a commonly used material used in cable insulation sheaths, but its dielectric properties can be negatively impacted by electric aging. This study investigates the use of nano-fillers, specifically alumina (Al_2O_3), titanium dioxide (TiO_2), calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), and barium titanate (BaTiO_3), in order to improve the dielectric properties of PVC. Films of PVC were doped with nano-fillers and were then exposed to an alternating voltage of 15kV for various time periods (1, 2, and 3 hours). The dielectric properties of PVC were measured using an impedance analyzer, and the results indicated that the use of these nano-fillers had a positive effect on the dielectric characteristics of PVC.

Keywords-PVC; polymer composite; dielectric parameters; corona discharge

I. INTRODUCTION

Polymeric electrical insulation is subjected to electric fields and thermal stresses in distribution power lines, making it crucial to develop new insulation coordination procedures to improve electric insulation parts in substations. In recent years, nanotechnology has been increasingly utilized in the synthesis of polymer-nano-composites, which have shown improved mechanical, electrical, and chemical properties [1-4]. Dielectric spectroscopies in time and frequency domains are useful tools for evaluating and diagnosing electrical insulation and understanding the dynamics of complex solid polymer systems [5-7]. Metal oxide nanoparticles in polymers have been studied as alternative materials for electrical applications [8-11]. Studies have demonstrated that the incorporation of nanoparticles in similar systems can have both positive and negative effects on breakdown strength [12-14]. Furthermore, it has been established that the production of artificial reinforcement fillers can lead to either an increase or decrease in the dielectric strength of polymeric composite insulation, which is utilized in high voltage outdoor applications [15]. Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) is a commonly used polymer in

industrial and communication applications. It is preferred due to its ease of production and processing, good adhesion with reinforcing elements, and resistance to corrosive environments. In addition, PVC has ductile electrical performance and excellent dielectric strength, low dielectric permittivity, low loss factor, and favorable thermo-mechanical behavior. PVC has been utilized as electrical insulators in distribution for a long time due to these properties [16].

A study of PVC's compression behavior was conducted in which its dielectric reaction was evaluated within the frequency range of 20Hz-1GHz [17]. Various research efforts have focused on developing high-performance materials with exceptional dielectric properties [18-23]. Modern polymer nano-composites have gained significant attention for their expanded applicability. There has been a growing interest in utilizing nanotechnology to improve the dielectric properties of materials. In this regard, research has been conducted to investigate the impact of different nanoparticles, such as clay, fumed silica, zinc oxide, and titanium dioxide, on the electric and dielectric loss performance of PVC in experimental settings. As the field of polymer nano-composites continues to

advance, this study examines how the type and concentration of nanoparticles at various voltages and frequencies (10Hz-10KHz) affect the electric and dielectric characteristics of PVC [24-32].

Corona discharge is a significant factor that can have a notable impact on the properties of polymeric insulating materials like PVC. Several studies have investigated the effect of corona discharge on the surface properties of RTV and HTV silicone rubber filled with micro-sized alumina trihydrate (ATH) fillers, utilizing various corona generation techniques [34, 35]. Authors in [36, 37] reported improved corona resistance performance of silicone rubber composites. The focus of the current paper is to examine the impact of different types of nano-fillers and their loading on the dielectric characteristics of PVC composites when subjected to AC corona discharge.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Table I provides information on the composition of the samples analyzed in this study. The main component of the samples was PVC resin of the 4000M type, which is commonly used in the Algerian industry. An antioxidant (Barium-Zinc) was added to ensure thermal stability, and dicumyl peroxide was used as a linking agent, along with lubricant and Plasticizer DOP (Di-Octyle Phthalate) from Zhengzhou P&B Chemical Co., Ltd (99.5%). According to [38], two types of samples were prepared: standard PVC and 4 ceramic-doped PVC samples with 10% of BaTiO₃, Al₂O₃, TiO₂, and CaCO₃, respectively. The formulation was mixed in a two-roll mixer at a temperature of 160°C for 10 minutes. The resulting mixture was then formed into sheets of predetermined thickness, which were subsequently cut into 10cm×10cm squares with a thickness of 0.3mm. Some of the composite samples were subjected to electric discharge at 15KV for 1, 2, and 3 hours, as shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I. SAMPLES USED

1	2	3	4	5
Pure PVC	PVC + 10% BaTiO ₃	PVC + 10% Al ₂ O ₃	PVC + 10% TiO ₂	PVC + 10% CaCO ₃

Fig. 1. Samples before and after electric aging.

The electrical aging of the specimens was performed in the high voltage test chamber of the HV laboratory at the Mouloud Mammeri University of Tizi-Ouzou. The experimental setup for electrical aging is shown in Figure 2(a), and the test protocol involved the following steps [39]:

- The test protocol for electrical aging involved placing the specimen between 2 flat-tip electrodes, with the upper

electrode connected to the high voltage and the lower electrode connected to the ground. The electrodes were carried by a bakelite support designed to be perfectly opposite and perpendicular to the plane, and to facilitate adjustment of the inter-electrode distance and ensure good contact with the sample. An alternating voltage of 15kV was applied to the specimen for 1, 2 and 3 hours.

- To avoid the phenomenon of contentment, a green plastic plate or other material with a surface area greater than that of the sample was placed between the contact electrode (lower) and the test specimen, as shown in Figure 2(b).
- After placing the specimen between the electrodes and the plastic plate, the chamber door was closed, and the main circuit breaker for the faraday chamber was powered on.
- Next, the manual circuit breaker of the control console was powered on.
- After powering on the circuit breaker of the control console, the green button was pressed to power the system. The voltage was varied and monitored on a voltmeter until it reached the desired voltage of 15kV, which was obtained by using the autotransformer located in the control panel. This process was repeated for 1, 2, and 3 hours of electrical aging.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for electrical aging

Impedance analyzers are commonly used to measure the electrical properties of materials, such as capacitance and resistance, as a function of frequency. In this case, the RLC 817 meter was used to measure the dielectric response of the samples up to 10MHz. The samples were placed between two plane electrodes made of copper, and an alternating electric field of 1V/m was applied. From these measurements, tgδ (dissipation factor), ε_r (relative permittivity), and loss index were calculated. The measurement error was to be ±0.05%.

Fig. 3. Samples in electric aging.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this research, the dielectric parameters $\text{tg}\delta$, ϵ_r , and loss index were measured at frequencies ranging from 10Hz to 10KHz for all the manufactured samples, including the standard PVC.

A. Relative Permittivity

Figure 4 shows that for all types of PVC samples, the relative permittivity initially increases with frequency up to a certain point, and then decreases with further increase in frequency. Additionally, the magnitude of the relative permittivity peaks varies with aging time and type of nanoparticle filler. It is worth noting that the observed behavior in the low frequency range (12Hz - 500Hz) may be related to the presence of electrode polarization effects, which can lead to inaccurate measurements of the material's dielectric properties in this frequency range.

Fig. 4. Variation of the relative permittivity as a function of frequency and aging time. (a) Pure PVC, (b) PVC+10% Al₂O₃, (c) PVC+10% TiO₂, (d) PVC+10% CaCO₃, (f) PVC+10% BaTiO₃.

B. Dissipation Factor

The values of $\text{tg}\delta$ come directly from the RLC meter. Figure 5 represents the variation of the dissipation factor as a function of frequency and aging time.

Fig. 5. Variation of the dissipation factor $\text{tg}\delta$ as a function of frequency and aging time. (a) Pure PVC, (b) PVC+10% Al₂O₃, (c) PVC+10% TiO₂, (d) PVC+10% CaCO₃, (f) PVC+10% BaTiO₃.

The analysis of the results of the evolution of the dissipation factor allowed us to note that it decreases with the increase in frequency (500hz-10Khz) and increases with the increase in the duration of application of the stress (electric corona discharge).

C. Dielectric Losses

The variations of dielectric losses as a function of frequency and aging time for the 5 considered types of PVC are shown in Figure 6. We notice that all the curves show almost the same pace, with a peak at low frequencies (between 50-80Hz) and then stabilize for the other frequencies. Losses increase with increasing corona discharge time but with a slight difference (especially for high frequencies > 1KHz). Figure 7 shows a comparison between the results of relative permittivity, dissipation factor and dielectric losses of all nanocomposites after electric aging for 3 hours. It is observed that the curves have the same pace (increase in the low frequencies and consequently decrease until they stabilize in high frequencies). It seems that BaTiO₃ is the most effective dopant among the 5 tested, with the smallest values for dielectric losses. Al₂O₃ comes second, followed by CaCO₃. This information can be useful for selecting the most appropriate dopant for improving the electrical properties of PVC.

Fig. 6. Variation of dielectric losses as a function of frequency and aging time. (a) Pure PVC, (b) PVC+10% Al₂O₃, (c) PVC+10% TiO₂, (d) PVC+10% CaCO₃, (e) PVC+10% BaTiO₃.

Fig. 7. Comparisons between nanocomposites after electric aging for 3 hours of: (a) Relative permittivity, (b) dissipation factor, (c) Dielectric losses.

IV. DISCUSSION

In general, the existing literature indicates that the dielectric constants and loss tangents of insulators are influenced by various physical, chemical, and structural changes that occur during their use [8, 19-22]. In order to enhance the performance of insulators, new polymeric composites have been developed that incorporate ceramic powders. To assess the impact of different nano-fillers such as BaTiO₃, CaCO₃, Al₂O₃, and TiO₂, as well as the aging under corona discharge conditions, the dielectric properties of PVC were analyzed.

Incorporating nano fillers into the PVC matrix allows for the modification of the composite's dielectric parameters. These values are dependent on the type of filler, the integration rate, and the dielectric parameters of the fillers themselves [1, 21, 35]. Specifically, in our study, the dielectric constant (ϵ_r) increased and the loss tangent ($\text{tg}\delta$) decreased as the nano-filler content increased, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. As demonstrated in Figure 4, for a frequency of 100Hz, the values of ϵ_r for BaTiO₃, TiO₂, CaCO₃, and Al₂O₃ decrease by approximately 57%, 50%, 35%, and 37%, respectively, compared to the value of ϵ_r for pure PVC prior to aging. These findings are in agreement with the findings of [13, 25, 33], and can be validated through (1) [1]:

$$\frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_c}{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_b} \left(\frac{\epsilon_b}{\epsilon_c} \right) = 1 - P_{\text{Par}} \tag{1}$$

where ϵ_b , ϵ_1 , and ϵ_c represent the relative permittivity's of PEI, BaTiO₃ nano-particles, and the nano-composite, respectively, P_{Par} is the volume fraction of the particles, and μ is a parameter that depends on subtleties of the microstructure such as particle clustering and surface roughness.

The doped samples exhibit greater resistance than pure PVC to the aging process. Specifically, at a frequency of 100Hz, the values of ϵ_r for BaTiO₃, TiO₂, CaCO₃, and Al₂O₃ increase by 45%, 14%, 18%, and 16%, respectively. The observed reduction in space charge in the PVC matrix, as evidenced by the capturing behavior of ceramics, supports the findings of [16, 40]. The primary current carriers were attributed to free ions generated from ingredients used in the polymerization reaction of PVC, such as the stabilizer, as well as ingredients in the plastifier itself. Additionally, the similarity in the shape of the curves of all the sample types of PVC/doped PVC can be attributed to interfacial polarization and rearrangement of the molecular structure. This relaxation is reflected in the peaks observed in the ϵ_r curves, which are consistent with those reported in [5, 29-31, 41].

The dielectric parameters of the composites are affected by aging, as demonstrated by the decrease in ϵ_r values and the increase in $\text{tg}\delta$ values over time for all composites. However, the incorporation of the load helps to slow down the electrical aging effect and alter the dielectric parameter values. Composite aging is characterized by a broadening of the peak in the low-frequency region, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. This result is consistent with previous research on BaTiO₃ doped PVC [28], where a peak in the dielectric constant curve was observed around 50Hz, and a second peak was detected at 500Hz. The same relaxation phenomena were also observed in our previous work [1, 28] and in [29]. Specifically, the first and

second relaxation phenomena occurred at low frequencies around 50 and 500Hz, respectively, as shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Based on the analysis of Figure 7 and a comparison of the various doped PVC samples, it is observed that an increase in nano filler content resulted in an increase in ϵ_r values and a decrease in $\tan\delta$ values. Among the different nano fillers studied, BaTiO₃ exhibited better resistance to aging. This can be attributed to the reduction of space charge, which is a result of the capturing behavior of ceramics in the PVC matrix [25, 43]. The main carriers present in the samples were attributed to free ions from the ingredients used in the polymerization reaction of PVC, such as the stabilizer, as well as ingredients in the plasticizer itself.

In addition, the breakdown strength of the samples, as shown in Figure 7, was found to be dependent on the ceramic content, with values decreasing as the ceramic content increased up to a certain practical limit, as reported in [27-28]. The formation of void defects and the resulting electromechanical stress led to the formation of cracks, which played a crucial role in the injection of electrons from the electrodes, providing them with enough energy to increase the probability of macromolecule ionization and the initiation of electron avalanche. This process accelerated the development of conducting channels and ultimately led to breakdown, as reported in [29-31]. This phenomenon can be explained by the reduction of space charge due to the capturing behavior of ceramics in the PVC matrix [26, 42-44].

V. CONCLUSION

It is important to note that the choice of nanoparticles and their concentration should be carefully considered to avoid any negative impact on other properties of the insulation material, such as mechanical strength, thermal stability, and moisture resistance. Additionally, the production process of the nanocomposites should be optimized to ensure homogeneous dispersion of the nanoparticles in the polymer matrix, which is crucial for achieving consistent and reliable electrical insulation performance.

Overall, the use of nanoparticles in electrical insulation materials shows a great potential for improving the electrical properties and performance of the materials, and can lead to more efficient and reliable electrical power systems.

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Recognition of Suspicious Human Activity in Video Surveillance: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few years, there has been a noticeable growth in the use of video surveillance systems, frequently functioning as integrated systems that remotely monitor key locations. In order to prevent terrorism, theft, accidents, illegal parking, vandalism, fighting, chain snatching, and crime, human activities can be observed through visual surveillance in sensitive and public places like buses, trains, airports, banks, shopping centers, schools, and colleges. In this paper, a review of the state-of-the-art is provided, showing the overall development of identifying suspicious behavior from surveillance recordings over the past few years. We give a quick overview of the issues and difficulties associated with recognizing suspicious human activity. The purpose of this publication is to give this field's scholars a literature evaluation of several suspicious activity recognition systems along with their general structure.

Keywords-suspicious activity; video surveillance; human activity; deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Suspicious Human Behavior (SHA) recognition through video surveillance is a well-known topic of research in the fields of image processing and computer vision and involves classifying human activity as normal and abnormal. Unusual or suspicious behaviors, which are rarely displayed by persons in public settings, can be classed as abnormal. Today, more and more people are using video surveillance to keep an eye on human activity and stop any questionable behavior. During the recent years, human activity recognition has been realized by a wide variety of applications in military, intelligence, mass-transit agencies, and research and academia as a measure to counter crime and terrorism, public health monitoring, detection of public violent protests and attacks, etc. [1-3]. Due to the technological improvement, the means of surveillance are easily available, yet the means of continuously and effectively processing, analyzing, and detecting are not. Intelligent systems that can detect and classify suspicious human activities have been established as a crucial means to carry the necessary counter-action mechanisms, for controlling the situation, and/or for post situation/scenario analysis [4].

In general, SHA recognition involves identification of human activities that can be classified as normal and abnormal.

The first classification refers to the common human activities at public places. Normal activities are the typical human behaviors that occur in public spaces, such as hand-waving, applauding, jogging, boxing, and walking. The latter category includes behaviors like leaving bags behind, dodging crowds, robbing, fighting and attacking, vandalism, crossing borders, etc. [5]. The focus is to employ efficient techniques/systems to identify the abnormalities in human activities which can be used to predict/decide the appropriate course of action. The abnormalities can be of several kinds and be mixed with normal activities. For example, in the first category, while running, a person might drop a bag with explosives, while a walking person might point a weapon towards another person, and so on. On the other hand, in the second category the abnormalities can be classified incorrectly, e.g. a running crowd in a marathon does not need to be identified as a negative behavior.

There is a wide range of activities to be identified in SHA recognition [5], as shown in Figure 1. Explosives left in unattended objects by terrorists in crowded places or secluded places have a complex range of tasks to be looked into before making appropriate decisions. Illegal parking on roads causing traffic jam or accidents needs quick decisions in real life applications. Activities involving violence such as street

fighting, vandalisms, etc. also require quick action to ensure minimum damage of life and property. Manual monitoring and intervention fail to deal with such situations. Thus, fully automatic, effective intelligent surveillance systems that are efficient enough to handle real-time scenarios are important to develop and install. This survey provides a comprehensive detail regarding the different aspects of developing such systems, discusses existing works, and finally puts forward the prospects.

Fig. 1. Activity recognition.

II. SOLUTION APPROACHES AND DISCUSSION

The following approaches are used by the existing solutions for SHA recognition:

- **Object tracking and detection by background subtraction:** This is the most common initial phase rule followed by the existing solutions for SHA recognition. In this phase, items are tracked and identified using changes in the order of the frames, and then the foreground objects are retrieved. Tracking-based or non-tracking-based methods are used to identify objects in video frames [6].
- **Feature extraction:** Certain features of objects such as motion and shape are extracted using various algorithms to identify objects [7].
- **Object classification:** In this step, a method is used to distinguish between the various things in the video, such as people, guns, cars, etc. Various methods, including SVM, Bayesian, Haar-classifier, KNN, face recognition, and skin color detection are used.
- **Suspicious activity detection:** The final stage after classifying the items in the video stream is a comparison with several threshold values categorically to check for aberrant behavior.

The specifications as to what can a suspicious event be are discussed below.

- **Loitering individuals:** We have loitering when a person is present at a particular location for a longer period than required. The related mathematical formulations can be quantified depending on the applications type [8].

- **Unattended/missing objects:** The suspicious objects have to be detected in the video frames. However, identification of abandoned/unattended object is very difficult in video frames in crowded environment. To tackle the problem different techniques have been proposed, such as frame differencing, optical flow, and background subtraction [9, 10].
- **Intruder detection:** Intruder detection approaches utilize multiple cameras for SHA analysis in cases such as bank robberies, chain snatching, etc. Another proposed technique is based on Ontology, and is also used in airports and banks to recognize SHA. The optical flow technique is employed to detect the snatch theft from crowd movement pedestrian video footage.
- **Abnormal activity/behavior:** It includes fall detection, accident detection, crowd detection, fire detection, etc. Fall detection is predominantly used in the health monitoring system. Herein, static cameras are used for patient care in hospitals and unattended elderly people at home in modern times [11].

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section we discuss the relevant works regarding SHA recognition.

Author in [12] considered the current camera surveillance systems that simultaneously capture dynamic images from areas using multiple web cameras. These images are matched against the enormous amount of dynamic images, which makes the process very tedious for the observer. Meanwhile, if some of the images are missed by the observer, the system will fail. Authors in [13] proposed a DCNN model called DIATRadHARNet designed for SHA classification. The following concepts serve as the framework for the scheme: depthwise separable convolutions, channel weighting (CHW) based on importance, multiple filter sizes in the depthwise section, and application of various size kernels to the same input tensor. Authors in [14] proposed an object detection algorithm for video surveillance and real-time security camera systems. To do this, a modified version of the Kanade-Locus-Thomasi extraction algorithm was presented for object tracking. The proposed scheme detects and analyzes a small number of features instead of a large number of objects. The problem of noise creation is dealt with a Kalman filter. Authors in [15] proposed a real-time SHA recognition scheme based on a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and 2D pose estimation technique which is beneficial in a wide range of surveillance areas. The skeletal images of humans are extracted from the input frames of the video through 2D pose estimations. Then, these are then fed to a pre-trained CNN to categorize them into different human activities like fall or not fall, trespassing or no trespassing, etc. Finally, based on the classification, appropriate action can be taken, such as sending messages on mobile phones, triggering alarms, etc. Authors in [16] proposed an SHA recognition technique known as YOLOv3, which handles the complex problem of human detection. For this, the video is first converted into a few frames then, each frame is analyzed to recognize and detect any suspicious activity.

In [17], the authors handle the complexity of associating the skeleton inputs for recognition of both abnormal human activity and daily activity by reducing the number of features of the datasets through an RNN-based approach. Moreover, an LSTM model was used to classify suspicious activities in medical applications. In [18], a hierarchical approach was used to detect different SHAs such as fainting, loitering, unauthorized entry, etc. At first, all SHAs are defined using a semantic approach. Then, background subtraction is employed to detect the object. Then, a correlation technique is used to track the objects. Authors in [19] based their method on two features: shape moments and Histogram of Normalized Distances (HND) from the center of gravity and contour points of the object shape. For categorizing human activities, Naive Bayes classifier and Multi-class Support Vector Machine were utilized. Authors in [20] focused on detecting gun-based crimes and abandoned luggage based on a deep neural network model capable of detecting handguns in images. In [21], the authors provided an SHA detection and tracking recognition system based on artificial neural networks. The silhouette pattern of the human blob created through segmenting the camera-captured video is used in this technique. In [22], the authors combined the Bi-LSTM network with Skeleton Activity Forecasting (SAF) to create a deep learning-based SHA recognition system. The pose estimation in this case uses the human skeletal joints, which are viewed as points. On a streaming video from an IP networked camera, the skeleton tracking and places of interest are approximated.

In [23], a deep learning based approach is used for SHA recognition wherein, at first, the features are calculated from video frames. Then, a feature classifier is used to predict whether the activity is suspicious. In [24], at first the videos were broken down into frames. Then these frames were analyzed using background subtraction to detect humans. Then, after using a CNN to extract features from the frames, a Discriminative Deep Belief Network (DDBN) was used. The DDBN is also given some labeled movies of various SHAs, and its associated features are also retrieved. The two sets of features are then compared to determine if there are normal or suspicious behaviors. In [25], a 63 layer-deep CNN model called L4-BranchedActionNet is proposed. The framework is first trained using an object detection dataset called CIFAR-100 with the help of the SoftMax function. After that, the dataset for SHA recognition is then input to the trained model to obtain a set of features. These are then improved utilizing an ant colony system and coded features with an entropy-based structure. To produce the final results, a variety of SVM and KNN-based classifiers are fed with the optimized features. Authors in [26] proposed an algorithm for tracking a moving object by the video samples captured during movement. This method consists of multiple subparts including video sample creation, an experimental setup for capturing the data, and applying the object tracking algorithm using mean shift algorithms. This system can be used for calculating vehicle speed, number of vehicles passed, etc. and it has been tested over multiple frame rates. The results were not compared with the existing work.

Suspicious activity detection will be a major breakthrough in the video surveillance for behavior identification, action

recognition, activity classification, etc. Authors in [27] proved the usability of automated surveillance systems. Surveillance plays an important role in maintaining law and order and in detection of possible threat. Usually, this process happens manually and requires a significant amount of manpower, which can be reduced if we automate the process. Authors in [28] explored the Situation Awareness (SAW) which is used for many crucial applications. The main challenge in SAW is faced during the instant changes while identifying objects. It also becomes challenging, whenever it focuses on huge video frames. The developed system is question-answer based, and chooses content as per interest. The interest-based traits can be more intricate in some situations than the facial features. Authors in [25] developed a CNN model having 63 deep layers. The given name of the model is L4-Branched-ActionNet. The AlexNet has been modified using four branched sub-structures. It is first turned into a network that has already been trained using the CIFAR-100 object detection dataset and the SoftMax algorithm and the crucial details are spotted. To optimize feature subsets, these features are used. Entropy is employed to code these traits initially, and an ant colony optimization method is then applied. Different variants of SVM and KNN were used for classification. Cubic SVM provides the highest efficiency of 0.99. Several machine learning approaches as described in [29-37] can be utilized in a similar way. Authors in [38] proposed a classroom activity detection approach using video surveillance. This method's drawback is that it is difficult to differentiate between students and teacher in the class and to develop a generalized model for all scenarios. Also, data from real surveillance can be noisy and of low-quality. The proposed work was tested on real environment using Siamese neural network for classification from classroom recordings. Authors in [39] also worked to improve the classroom learning outcome. A brief comparative summary of the relevant works is shown in Table I. Similar work has been done in [40-42].

IV. MOTIVATION AND CHALLENGES

The motivation of adopting smart and intelligent video surveillance systems is mainly to identify human activities which are suspicious in nature. In various highly sensitive places these systems will aid in the prevention of thefts, terrorist acts, hooliganism, fighting, and attacks, and fire. The following areas are shielded against shady behavior via intelligent video surveillance [7]:

- Universities and other academic institutions utilize video surveillance to keep an eye on student activity to protect property from theft and vandalism. Additionally, they assist in preventing student fighting and inappropriate behavior. When exams are being given, video surveillance may be also utilized.
- Video surveillance helps to prevent theft, vandalism, fighting, disease identification, growing crowds, and explosive attacks to protect the population and public infrastructures including borders, laboratories, jails, military bases, temples, etc.
- The use of video surveillance to identify SHA is expanding in the retail sector, both for internal security in places like

warehouses and stores as well as for external security in places like parking lots. Even tiny businesses are using cameras to keep an eye on people and record video proof in case of theft or an incident.

- In every nation, the safety of travelers, runways, and aircrafts is paramount in airports, which are highly sensitive security zones. Such security-sensitive places are protected with high levels of protection thanks to a real-time system that detects SHA in video monitoring.
- In the banking industry, video monitoring is crucial for ensuring security. The use of weapons during armed robberies and assaults is prevented by the presence of cameras. Automated banking devices are frequently targeted by criminals. One way a security camera can help in the identification of fraud is by installing a device to read the magnetic information on bank cards.
- Recognizing suspicious behavior from video surveillance can assist in finding frauds, heists, and other crimes. Intelligent video surveillance is an intriguing technique to assist security officers because monitoring a casino necessitates seeing human movement in a congested setting.
- In hospitals, video surveillance is also used to keep an eye on patients. At home, it can be used to keep an eye on elderly or children.

TABLE I. SHA LITERATURE REVIEW SUMMARY

Ref	Object detection method	Noise removal method	Remarks
[12]	Background subtraction	Smoothing filter	Finds the detection point of SHA and evaluates the corresponding degree of risk
[13]	Lighweight deep CNN	Spatial filter	Efficient classification with high accuracy
[14]	KLT and Kalman filter		Efficient real time tracking
[15]	2D pose estimation and CNN		Effective response system
[16]	YOLOv3		Quick processing, accurate detection
[17]	Multilayer LSTM network		Less training data, better cross-view and cross-subject evaluation
[18]	Background subtraction	A thresholding technique	Less complexity, high accuracy
[19]	Naïve Bayes classifier		Effective and accurate detection and prediction
[20]	Deep neural network		Gun-crime and abandoned luggage detection
[21]	ANN		High accuracy and robustness
[22]	Bi-LSTM network	Adaptive thresholding	Skeleton tracking
[23]	CNN and RNN		Apriori detection, simple, yet powerful
[24]	CNN and DDBN		High accuracy
[25]	Entropy-coded ant colony system		High accuracy
[26]	Mean shift algorithm		Efficient object tracking. Box and image sequence segmentation
[27]	Faster region-based CNN inception V2 framework		SHA detection in public places
[28]	I-ViSE and deep neural networks	Smoothing filter	Emphasis is given on ensuring that the photos analyzed have significant content and good quality
[29]	Siamese neural framework	Textual windows across segment	Superior prediction performance for online and offline classrooms
[30]	Deep fully connected convolutional and recurrent neural network		Precise estimates of the total amount of time spent in classes or activities

To develop an intelligent video surveillance system that can automatically detect SHA, there are several issues and challenges to overcome [7]:

- Moving object recognition is challenging to accurately process due to dynamic fluctuation in natural environments, such as slow illumination changes brought on by day-to-night shifts and quick illumination differences brought on by weather changes.
- The look of an object is altered by its shadow, making it difficult to track and identify the specific object in a video. Characteristics like shape, movement, and background, are more delicate for a shadow.
- Occasionally, noises made by swaying tree branches make it difficult to identify an object in a video.
- Finding the object in a busy location is a difficult process. It is quite challenging to discover abandoned objects, theft, or violence in such a circumstance.
- Full or partial object occlusions occur occasionally, the objects in video are entirely or partially obscured, making identification difficult.
- It might be quite difficult to identify foreground items in low-resolution films. Identification of object boundaries becomes extremely challenging.
- The creation of a real-time, intelligent monitoring system is the more difficult task. When extracting and tracking the foreground objects from films with complicated backgrounds, processing time increases.
- Since background subtraction in abandoned object detection only recognizes moving things as the foreground, static object detection is a difficult task.

V. MEASURES TO DETECT SHA

In general, the measures used to detect SHA follow a hierarchical structure as shown in Figure 2. At first the video is split into a sequence of frames. Then, background subtraction is used to detect changes in the sequences of the frame and then extraction of foreground objects. Following this, the different types of objects are attempted to be extracted by the system. Then, the different obstructions in the form of noise, shadow etc. are removed from the frame containing the object. Finally, the recognizable object is obtained from the surveillance

footage. Figure 3 represents the specific steps regarding the general steps in entity (object) detection in SHA recognition. The first step is the identification of the different kinds of steps. To stop terrorist bomb attacks, suspicious activity detection also includes the detection of abandoned objects. Background approaches in video surveillance treat stationary items as the background and moving things as the foreground. Therefore, a newly arrived object is absorbed into the backdrop when it becomes static.

Fig. 2. General steps in entity detection.

Fig. 3. Specifications regarding the general steps in entity (object) detection in SHA recognition.

Finding foreground objects that are free from noise, illumination, or shadow is incredibly challenging in computer vision. Noise makes it difficult to identify an object, illumination produces false detection, and shadow alters the object's appearance, making object tracking particularly challenging. The right features must be chosen in order for video surveillance to automatically detect anomalous activity. Finding the most valuable information in the captured video is the main goal of feature extraction. After determining whether there are foreground-moving or still objects in a frame, the object categorization stage is used to determine whether the behavior is normal or abnormal. A static human is distinguished from a static abandoned object, a fight is distinguished from a boxing match, a face is distinguished from an object that has skin color, fire is distinguished from a flashlight, the sun, or any other artificial light source, and so on.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The current paper reviews various intelligent and automatic SHA recognition surveillance techniques. The reviewed papers cover a wide range of applications associated with real-time implementation. The applications range from health-care systems to perimeter monitoring in war fields. The techniques and dataset used are the most common ones pertaining to the

SHA domain. Note that recognition of human behavior is a complex process, and monitoring and analyzing human activities is difficult. Despite the complex nature of the problem, it is also required in day-to-day life in order to improve safety in modern society. On the other hand, recognition of suspicious activity of non-living things is relatively less complex but requires a great deal of expertise to deduce correct results. We discussed the related works and mentioned their shortcomings. The weaknesses can be significantly improved and pave the way for a wide range of open research.

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Multi-Goal Feature Selection Function in Binary Particle Swarm Optimization for Power System Stability Classification

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ABSTRACT

The input feature is vital for power system stability classification. Feature selection can reduce the size of the input feature, making classifier training easier, and the small size of the input feature subset also reduces the cost of purchasing sensor measurement equipment. Therefore, feature selection works require an efficient seeking method. Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (BPSO) is a simple and easy-to-implement evolutionary calculation technique. While the classification accuracy of BPSO is essential, it is also needed to drive the algorithm to minimize the number of variables. The proposed approach is to apply a multi-objective function to help the BPSO algorithm identify the subset of features that can achieve the minimum number of variables and the highest classification accuracy. The k-nearest neighbor classifier is employed in the experiments to evaluate the classification performance on the IEEE 39-bus dataset.

Keywords-feature selection; classification; power system stability; BPSO; K-nearest neighbor classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

Stability analysis of electrical systems is a highly complex problem [1]. Stability losses of electrical system cause widespread power outages and often significant economic damage [2]. The load growth is outpacing the investment in transmission lines and power generation. As a result, incidents can easily lead to power system instability and outages [3, 4]. Therefore, rapid detection of power system instability is crucial [1], but traditional analytical methods cannot achieve it. This difficult requirement can be resolved using a recognition method [5-7]. Once trained on input-output data, operating modes, and stability modes of the electrical system, the recognition system will quickly detect the instability of the electrical system [8]. However, the abundance of input data is a significant obstacle for the recognition system in learning and operation, adding a high cost of measuring sensor data and collecting data. Therefore, in recognition problems, the important issue is to make the input variables accurate and straightforward. In recognition of the stability analysis of

electrical systems, previous studies have proposed solutions for the primary variable selection process, mainly using ranking methods to select variables. The Relief method and the divergence criterion are applied in [9]. In [9-10], the Fisher criterion is applied. Ranking methods are based on statistical criteria but do not consider the recognition error and are not optimal. Advanced calculation techniques can help optimally expand the search space. Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (BPSO) is a simple and easy-to-implement candidate computational optimization algorithm for feature selection in the stable electrical system classification problem. In this, the important objective function is the classification error. However, more than one objective functions based solely on classification error are required to guide the BPSO algorithm toward selecting small and low-dimensional inputs [11]. This paper proposes the application of a multi-objective feature selection function based on the minimum classification error with minimum size of feature-subset or the highest classification accuracy with the least number of input feature-subset. The K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN) algorithm is

recommended for assessing the classification performance in the BPSO algorithm. The proposed method is tested on the IEEE-39 bus power system data.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Goal Function

1) Correct Classification

In the steady-state power system classification, the Correct Classification is calculated according to (1):

$$CC(\%) = \frac{CSC}{TSC} 100(\%) \quad (1)$$

where CSC (Correct Sample Classification) is the number of correctly classified samples and TSC (Total Sample Classification) is the total number of samples in the sample set.

2) Error Classification

Error Classification is calculated by:

$$EC(\%) = 1 - CC(\%) \quad (2)$$

3) Multi-Objective Selection Function

In BPSO (Figure 1), the total number of variables in the data set is the size of the search space. A binary string represents each candidate (a particle). The bits '1' and '0' correspond to the selected and unselected variable, respectively.

```

Begin
  Data set, k-fold; D: dimensionality of search space
  N : the population size; T : maximum iterations;
   $c_1, c_2, v_{max}, w$ 
  Randomly initialize the position and velocity of each particle;
  while  $t \leq T$ 
    evaluate fitness of each particle according to (6);
    for  $i=1$  to N
      update the  $p_{best}$  of particle  $i$ ;
      update the  $g_{best}$  of particle  $i$ ;
    end
    for  $i=1$  to N
      for  $d=1$  to D
        update the velocity of particle  $i$  according to (2);
        update the position of particle  $i$  according to (4) and (5);
      end
    end
    end
    calculate the classification error of the selected feature subset;
    return the position of  $g_{best}$  (the selected feature subset);
    return the classification error of the selected feature subset;
end
    
```

Fig. 1. The BPSO algorithm.

The single objective function (2) only contains the classification error, which can lead the BPSO algorithm to converge to a solution with many variables. There are two main objectives in variable selection: the lowest classification error and the smallest number of selected variables. Therefore, the variable selection objective function (3) combines these two objectives. In practice, the number of selected variables (SF) is

larger than the classification error (EC). To balance these two quantities, the second quantity of the objective function is the ratio of the number of selected variables to the total number of variables, which is aimed at converting the second quantity into the sequence (0, 1].

$$GF = EC + \frac{SF}{TF} \quad (3)$$

The objective function (3) reflects the importance of the misclassification error and the minimum number of variables having equal weighting or a weighting ratio of 1:1. If we want to consider the importance of the classification error rate and the number of selected variables differently, the α weight is introduced into (3) to become:

$$GF = \alpha \cdot EC + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \frac{SF}{TF} \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. For $\alpha \in (0.5, 1]$, the classification error has a higher weight than the number of selected variables, while the opposite takes place when $\alpha \in (0, 0.5)$ and when $\alpha = 0.5$ the importance of the classification error and the number of selected variables is equal.

B. BPSO Algorithm

The PSO algorithm is a nature-inspired approach proposed for solving continuous optimization problems [12]. The BPSO algorithm was developed for discrete optimization problems [13]. A matrix representing the stability of an electric system is presented below. This data matrix is represented by the vector x_i . The vector $x_i = (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{iD})$ used in the BPSO represents the position of the i^{th} sample. The vector $v_i = (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{iD})$ is used to represent the velocity of the i^{th} sample. The size of the search space is designated as D. Throughout the search process, the optimal position of each individual is recorded as p_{best} . The global best position, representing the most advantageous location for the entire herd, is referred to as g_{best} . The individuals in the herd are randomly generated from the population. The objective is to find the optimal solution by iteratively updating the position and velocity of each individual based on (5) and (6).

$$x_{id}^{t+1} = x_{id}^t + v_{id}^{t+1} \quad (5)$$

$$v_{id}^{t+1} = w * v_{id}^t + c_1 r_{1i} (p_{id} - x_{id}^t) + c_2 r_{2i} (p_{gd} - x_{id}^t) \quad (6)$$

where t is the t^{th} iteration of the search process, $d \in D$ is the size in the search space, c_1, c_2 are acceleration constants, r_{1i}, r_{2i} are random values, valid in the range (0,1), p_{id} and p_{gd} represent p_{best} and g_{best} particles of size d , w is the inertial weight, v is the velocity, limited to the maximum velocity v_{max} , and $v_{idt} \in [-v_{max}, v_{max}]$.

The velocity in BPSO represents the element that can take the value 1. Equation (6) is still used to update the velocity while x_{id}, p_{id} get the value 0 or 1. The sigmoid function $s(v_{id})$

is used to convert the value of v_{id} into a range of values in (0,1). The BPSO updates each sample's position using (7) and (8). The rand() function is a random number generator with a uniformly distributed output between 0 and 1.

$$x_{id} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } rand() < s(v_{id}) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$s(v_{id}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-v_{id}}} \quad (8)$$

III. STEPS TO IMPLEMENT VARIABLE SELECTION IN THE STABILITY CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM OF THE POWER SYSTEM.

The methodology for selecting variables in the stability classification of power systems involves the steps depicted in Figure 2: Initial variable selection analysis, data collection, the proposed variable selection method, and, lastly, the implementation and results.

Fig. 2. Steps to implement variable selection.

Step 1: Initial variable selection analysis. Analysis for system stability assessment found that major disturbance events, such as short circuits, have a high potential to cause system instability. Thus, short circuits are of particular concern. Examining these input variables is crucial for the determination of their impact on the stability of the electrical system. This allows for the selection of variables that are strongly correlated with system stability, and facilitates the identification of key initial variables while eliminating unnecessary ones. The goal of variable selection is to minimize the number of variables used in the analysis, while maintaining the highest level of accuracy in the classification process. The selection of initial variables is a preliminary screening step to make the subsequent steps easier. The selected variables must have a low cost of sensor measurement. Suppose all variables related to the electrical system are considered. In that case, the number of variables is very large, such as the powerful effect of branches, the power resistance of branches, the powerful effect of generators, the power resistance of generators, generator voltage current, generator speed, the relative angle deviation of the generators from the standard machine, etc. The analysis of the electrical system's stability reveals a direct correlation between the loss of stability and changes in active power and voltage. Therefore, it is imperative to consider these variables.

Step 2: Collect and organize data. The initial data collected can be historical data stored in the data collection system when operating the power system, or they can be simulated using specialized software to build the initial data

set. The data consist of input and output data. The data set is stored as a matrix of data. The input data includes data columns containing information about variables, and the data matrix rows contain the variables' parameters. The output data is a matrix containing information on whether the system is stable or unstable, assigned binary labels, matrix y (bit '1' is stable, and bit '0' is unstable). Figure 3 presents the organization of the input and output data matrix.

Fig. 3. Input and output matrix.

Step 3: Proposed variable selection method. As presented above, studies on stability recognition of electrical systems mainly apply statistical standards to rank variables. The result is that the ranking method still does not give the result of how many variables are selected and what they are. The automatic and optimal selection of variables is still a big question. The BPSO algorithm is a promising candidate for variable selection in the stability classification of electrical systems and the use of one multi-objective function to guide the BPSO algorithm to find the best results is proposed. The multi-objective function is introduced in Section II.A.3. When selecting recognition sets to evaluate classification accuracy, they must meet the requirements of simplicity without considering computational time. Through our experiment, we found that the K-NN tool meets this criterion.

Step 4: Implementation and results. Choosing the optimal set of variables is a challenging problem as it depends on too many factors. Thus, many aspects must be considered to choose the best possible set of variables. Therefore, the multi-objective function (4) is suggested to be applied for variable selection in the implementation step.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

The experiment was conducted on the IEEE 39 bus system, which comprises 39 buses, 10 of which are dedicated to generation. Additionally, the system consists of 12 transformers, 10 generators, 34 transmission lines, and 19 loads. Ten generators are connected from bus 30 to bus 39, where bus 39 is chosen as the reference bus, 9 buses are PV buses, and the remaining 29 buses are PQ buses, with two different voltage levels of 345kV and 20kV. The IEEE 39 bus system diagram is shown in Figure 4. A HP Probook Laptop, Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 8th Gen, 8GB RAM was used.

Initial variable selection analysis: The input variables are in the dynamic state containing information about the established operating mode and the fault mode, combined with expert opinions to select the initial variables, including voltage deviation at the buses {delVbus}, load power deviation {delPload}, and transmission line power deviation {delPflow}. The input and output variables are x and y. The survey on the diagram has 39 voltage deviation variables at the buses, 19 load power effect variables, and 46 branch power effect variables. The total number of input variables is 104 and there is only 1 output variable.

FIG. 4. IEEE 39 bus system diagram.

Data collection: Offline simulation was conducted using Powerworld 18 software to collect data for power system stability assessment. In this experiment, the load level considered is 100% of the base load, and the fault scenario is a short circuit. In the load flow examination, the software computes the optimal power distribution and the corresponding power flow. The faults considered are three-phase short circuits, one phase to ground, and two phases at all busbars, and along all transmission lines, with each spacing of 5% of the length of the transmission line. The cutting time of the short circuit is 50ms [14]. The state of the power system is stable when the rotor angle deviation of any two generators does not exceed 180°, and it is not stable when it does. The simulation results show that the data set contains 317 samples, 177 stable and 140 unstable.

BPSO Algorithm and multi-objective variable selection: The K-NN (K=1, 1-NN) classifier is selected as the partitioning method. The accuracy of 1-NN classification was evaluated with the cross-validation method with k-folds=10. It involves dividing the dataset into 10 equal parts or "folds." The model is then trained on 9 of the folds and tested on the remaining 1 fold. This process is repeated 10 times, each time using a different fold for testing, while the other 9 folds are used for training. The result is the average of these 10 times. The calculation functions are supported by Matlab 2018b. The BPSO-1-NN algorithm is applied to execute the variable

selection. The considered values to evaluate the importance of components in the multi-objective optimization variable selection function (4) are: $N = \{10, 20, 30, 40, 50\}$, $w = 0.9$, $T = 100$, $c_1 = 2$, $c_2 = 2$, while α is considered to have values in (0,1] with a step of 0.1. The convergence trajectory of the algorithm is illustrated in Figure 5. The results of the variable selection, objective function value, and classification accuracy are presented in Table I.

B. Discussion

The algorithm selected 11 variables with corresponding values of α weight of 0, 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4. Among them, $\alpha=0.2$, $N=20$, and SF=11 achieved 95.6% accuracy in the testing phase.

Fig. 5. The convergence characteristics of the algorithm.

V. RESULTS

The accuracy when $\alpha=0.8$, $N=30$, and $SF=19$ was 97.1%. The accuracy when $\alpha=0.9$, $N=50$, and $SF=24$ was 96.8%. The accuracy when $\alpha=1$, $N=20$, and $SF=46$ was 97.1%. This shows that as the value of α in the objective function (4) increases, the importance of the classification error decreases and the accuracy of the classification increases, but with a larger number of variables. In the case of $\alpha=1$, the objective function (4) becomes a single objective, and only the single objective of the classification error remains. There, 46 variables were selected, with the number of selected variables decreasing by 55.7%, while in the case of $\alpha=0.2$, only 11 variables were selected, with the number of selected variables decreasing by 89.4%. In terms of classification accuracy, the case of 11 variables had accuracy only 1.5% lower than that of the case of 46 variables, while the number of selected variables decreased by 33.7%. A classification accuracy of 95.6% is considered acceptable for stable power system classification [15–17].

TABLE I. RESULTS OF THE BPSO ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTATION

α	N	SF	Best GF	CC (%)	α	N	SF	Best GF	CC (%)
0	10	17	0.1635	92.1	0.1	10	18	0.1624	93.4
	20	15	0.1442	94.6		20	14	0.1265	94.6
	30	11	0.1058	94.0		30	10	0.0925	94.3
	40	14	0.1346	94.6		40	13	0.1166	95.9
	50	11	0.1058	94.0		50	14	0.1256	95.6
0.2	10	18	0.1549	91.8	0.3	10	15	0.1208	93.4
	20	11	0.0934	95.6		20	15	0.1152	95.3
	30	14	0.1172	95.3		30	14	0.1026	94.9
	40	11	0.1035	90.1		40	11	0.0901	94.6
	50	13	0.1076	96.2		50	12	0.0997	93.7
0.4	10	15	0.1093	94.3	0.5	10	17	0.1133	93.4
	20	16	0.1138	94.6		20	14	0.0910	95.3
	30	12	0.0894	94.9		30	13	0.0925	94.0
	40	12	0.0919	94.3		40	15	0.0942	95.6
	50	11	0.0912	93.1		50	14	0.0862	96.2
0.6	10	15	0.0766	96.8	0.7	10	20	0.0842	96.2
	20	17	0.0900	95.9		20	18	0.0784	96.2
	30	12	0.0821	94.0		30	20	0.0820	96.5
	40	16	0.0843	96.2		40	17	0.0733	96.5
	50	16	0.0861	95.9		50	14	0.0691	95.9
0.8	10	25	0.0758	96.5	0.9	10	27	0.0572	96.5
	20	26	0.0727	97.1		20	31	0.0582	96.8
	30	19	0.0593	97.1		30	25	0.0496	97.1
	40	24	0.0663	97.5		40	28	0.0553	96.8
	50	24	0.0689	97.1		50	24	0.0515	96.8
1.0	10	47	0.0252	97.4	1.0	40	45	0.0284	97.1
	20	46	0.0284	97.1		50	54	0.0252	97.4
	30	50	0.0252	97.4					

The results show that when applying the BPSO algorithm for variable selection in the problem of classifying stable electrical systems, the single-objective function considering only the classification error, drives the algorithm to select a large number of variables. Therefore, applying the multi-objective function (4) for the variable selection problem in the classification of stable electrical systems is appropriate when using the BPSO algorithm.

VI. CONCLUSION

The paper proposed the application of the multi-objective function for the BPSO algorithm in selecting variables in the power system stability classification problem. The results from the experiment conducted on the IEEE-39 bus system demonstrated the success of the variable reduction technique. Reduction from 104 to 11 variables with the accuracy of up to 95.6% has significant economic implications, such as significantly reducing the cost of measuring devices to collect data. The proposed method opens up the direction of applying advanced computational techniques in selecting input parameters for the problem of classifying power system stability.

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A Neural Network Controller Design for the Mecanum Wheel Mobile Robot

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ABSTRACT

Advanced controllers are an excellent choice for the trajectory tracking problem of Wheeled Mobile Robots (WMRs). However, these controllers pose a challenge to the hardware structure of WMRs due to the controller's complex structure and the large number of calculations needed. In that context, designing a controller with a simple structure and a small number of computations but good real-time performance is necessary in order to improve the tracking accuracy for the WMRs without requiring high hardware architecture. In this work, a neural network controller with a simple structure for the trajectory-tracking of a Mecanum-Wheel Mobile robot (MWMR) based on a reference controller is proposed. A two-layer feedforward neural network is designed as a tracking controller for the robot. The neural network is trained with a sample input-output data set so that the error between the neural network output and the reference control signal of the supervisory controller is minimal. The neural network parameters are trained to update over time. The simulation results verified the effectiveness of the neural network controller, whose parameters are tuned adaptively to ensure a fast convergence to the desired Bézier trajectory.

Keywords-mecanum wheel mobile robot; tracking control; neural networks; Bézier trajectory

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a considerable scientific interest in the area of Wheeled Mobile Robots (WMRs), and especially Mecanum-Wheeled Mobile Robot (MWMRs), which have been widely applied to many fields due to their maneuverability and superior motion ability [1-3]. For control engineers, the trajectory tracking control problem of MWMR has always received significant attention. Trajectory tracking control is the key to realizing the autonomous movement of the MWMRs. However, the trajectory tracking control of the WMRs is a challenging study area because WMR systems are typically subjected to non-holonomic constraints, random disturbances

and uncertainties. Many researchers studied control design and development with different controllers to improve the tracking control performance of the MWMRs. A time-varying parameter PID controller has been proposed in [4] to control a four-MWMR along a desired trajectory with minimal error. An advanced intelligent adaptive motion controller was designed in [5] using fuzzy wavelet networks for Mecanum Wheeled Omnidirectional Robots (MWORs) with parameter variations. Authors in [6] presented a novel neural network adaptive sliding mode control system for an omnidirectional vehicle with four mecanum wheels. Network weight adaptation was based on the analysis of the Lyapunov stability. Other

controllers used for MWMR for trajectory tracking control used adaptive integral terminal sliding mode [7], robust adaptive control [8], adaptive fuzzy tracking control [9-11], PID controller with time-varying parameters [12], adaptive back stepping control using neural networks [13], predictive control [14], self-tuning fuzzy-PID control [15], and fuzzy adaptive PID control [16]. For robots to operate in a dynamic working environment and meet the required safety, accuracy, and reliability, advanced intelligent control systems are a valuable solution for the trajectory-tracking control problem [17-19]. The use of neural networks for the control of mobile robots has received attention from many researchers because they are self-learning and provide a real-time approximation of nonlinearities in a mathematical model of a robot using network weight adaptation [20-22]. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are increasingly used to solve trajectory tracking problems, such as the adjustment of control coefficients, the choice of the direction of motion, speed correction, and identification of information from sensors.

The above discussion verified that the advanced controllers have excellent trajectory-tracking performance. Even so, they have the disadvantage that the complex controller structure leads to many complex calculations requiring high hardware structure. Therefore, it is necessary to design a controller with a simple structure, a small number of computations and good real-time performance to improve trajectory-tracking performance with a minor error for MWMR. Therefore, this work focuses on designing a simple computational ANN-based model reference controller to accommodate the trajectory tracking of the MWMR with minor errors, simultaneously reducing the hardware's processing speed and capacity versus advanced controllers.

II. KINEMATIC ERROR MODEL OF MWMR

A. Kinematic Model

Consider an MWMR moving along the Bézier trajectory Σ with the assumption of no longitudinal and lateral slip in the global coordinate system $\mathcal{G}_f \{O_f x_f y_f\}$, as shown in Figure 1. The angular velocities relationship of wheels to the linear and angular velocities of the MWMR are determined by [4]:

$$\omega = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{Q}^T(\varphi)\dot{\mathbf{q}}_f \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\omega = [\omega_1(t) \ \omega_2(t) \ \omega_3(t) \ \omega_4(t)]^T$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/r & 1/r & -(L+d)/2r \\ 1/r & -1/r & (L+d)/2r \\ 1/r & 1/r & (L+d)/2r \\ 1/r & -1/r & -(L+d)/2r \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{Q}(\varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varphi(t) & -\sin \varphi(t) & 0 \\ \sin \varphi(t) & \cos \varphi(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_f = [\dot{x}(t) \ \dot{y}(t) \ \dot{\varphi}(t)]^T = [V_x \ V_y \ \Omega]^T$$

and r, L and d are the radii of the wheel, the distance in the x_R -axis and the y_R -axis of two wheels, V_x, V_y , and Ω are the linear and angular velocities of the MWMR in the global coordinate \mathcal{G}_f , respectively.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the kinematic error of MWMR.

From (1), the forward kinematics equation of the MWMR is given by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_f = \mathbf{Q}(\varphi)\dot{\mathbf{q}}_R = \mathbf{Q}(\varphi)\mathbf{J}^+ \omega \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{J}^+ = (\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J})^{-1} \mathbf{J}^T$ is the pseudo-inverse of \mathbf{J} .

B. Kinematic Error Model

The error model describes the variation in position and orientation of the MWMR when moving along the desired trajectory Σ , defined by the position error vector \mathbf{e} [23]:

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{q}_d - \mathbf{q}_f = [e_x \ e_y \ e_\varphi]^T \quad (3)$$

$\mathbf{q}_d = [x_d(t) \ y_d(t) \ \varphi_d(t)]^T$ and $\mathbf{q}_f = [x_f(t) \ y_f(t) \ \varphi_f(t)]^T$ are the MWMR's desired and actual motion pose vectors in the global coordinate \mathcal{G}_f . The kinematic error model of the MWMR in the local coordinate system $\mathcal{G}_R \{G_{x_R} y_R\}$ attached to the MWMR is given by:

$$\mathbf{e}_R = [e_{x_R} \ e_{y_R} \ e_{\varphi_R}]^T = \mathbf{Q}^T(\varphi)\mathbf{e} \quad (4)$$

Derivative (4) is obtained by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{e}}_R = \tilde{\mathbf{\Omega}}\mathbf{e}_R + \mathbf{A}\dot{\mathbf{q}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{q}}_f \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{\Omega}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \Omega(t) & 0 \\ -\Omega(t) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos e_\varphi & -\sin e_\varphi & 0 \\ \sin e_\varphi & \cos e_\varphi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

III. NEURAL NETWORK CONTROLLER DESIGN FOR THE MECANUM WHEEL MOBILE ROBOT

The proposed Neural Network (NN) control system to track the desired motion trajectory is described in Figure 2. The control system consists of the NN controller, the kinematic model of MWMR, the reference controller and the desired trajectory Σ . The NN's parameters are adapted online according to the reference model described in Figure 2, in which the reference controller is the kinematic controller proposed in [23] to generate the reference control signals \mathbf{u}_r , to determine the reference linear and angular velocities (V_{rR}, Ω_{rR}) for the MWMR to follow the desired trajectory Σ . In [23], the control gains K_1, K_2 and K_3 of the reference controller are time-varying parameters for MWMR to achieve high tracking accuracy. The parameters for the proposed ANN controller are given in Table I. The inputs to the ANN are the position errors of MWMR \mathbf{e} , and the ANN's outputs are \mathbf{u}_n (the velocities of MWMR).

TABLE I. THE NEURAL NETWORK PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Number of input neurons	3
Number of output neurons	3
Number of hidden layers	2
Number of neurons in hidden layer 1	3
Number of neurons in hidden layer 2	3

$f_1(n) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-n}}$ and $f_2(n) = n$ are the activation functions of the 1st and 2nd hidden layer, respectively. The output \mathbf{u}_n is compared with the reference control signal \mathbf{u}_r , and the error is

used to adapt the weights W and bias b in order to reduce the NN's error on the output:

$$\mathbf{e}_u = (\mathbf{u}_r - \mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow 0 \tag{6}$$

$f_1(n) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-n}}$ and $f_2(n) = n$ are the activation functions of the 1st and 2nd hidden layer, respectively. The output \mathbf{u}_n is compared with the reference control signal \mathbf{u}_r , and the error is used to adapt the weights W and bias b in order to reduce the NN's error on the output:

$$\mathbf{e}_u = (\mathbf{u}_r - \mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow 0 \tag{6}$$

IV. NEURAL NETWORK CONTROLLER

A. The Neuron Network Controller Model

It is defined by:

$$\mathbf{u}_n = f_2(\mathbf{W}_2^T f_1(\mathbf{W}_1^T \mathbf{e}^T + \mathbf{b}_1^T) + \mathbf{b}_2^T) \tag{7}$$

where $\mathbf{W}_2, \mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2$ are the weight matrix and bias vector of the NN, respectively, and \mathbf{e} is given by (2). On the other hand, considering the MWMR's local coordinate system, we have:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_n = \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{dR} - \mathbf{u}_n \tag{8}$$

where:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_{dR} = \mathbf{T}\dot{\mathbf{q}}_d \text{ with } \mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T$$

Fig. 2. Structure of neurocontrolled MWMR with supervised learning.

B. Neural Network Training

The parameters of the NN, including the weight matrix \mathbf{W} and the bias vector \mathbf{b} , are updated as the time by the back-propagation method according to the following law:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{W}_m(k+1) = \mathbf{W}_m(k) - \alpha \mathbf{s}_m \mathbf{a}_{m-1}^T \\ \mathbf{b}_m(k+1) = \mathbf{b}_m(k) - \alpha \mathbf{s}_m \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}_m(k) &= \dot{\mathbf{F}}_m(\mathbf{W}_m \mathbf{a}_{m-1} + \mathbf{b}_m) \mathbf{W}_{m+1}^T \mathbf{s}_{m+1}, \\ \dot{\mathbf{F}}_m(n_m) &= \text{diag}[\dot{f}_m(n_{m,1}), \dot{f}_m(n_{m,2}), \dots, \dot{f}_m(n_{m,sm})], \\ \mathbf{a}_n &= f_n(\mathbf{W}_n \mathbf{a}_{n-1} + \mathbf{b}_n), \end{aligned}$$

$$\dot{f}_m(n_{m,i}) = \frac{\partial f_m(n_{m,i})}{\partial n_{m,j}}$$

where $m = 1, 2, \dots, N$, N is the number of layers of the NN, $a \in [0, 1]$ is the learning rate, f_n is the activation function of the m^{th} layer. The weights values of the NN are adjusted so that the cost function given by (10) is minimized:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{e}_u^T \mathbf{e}_u \rightarrow \min \quad (10)$$

V. SIMULATION SETUP

A. The MWMR Dimension Setup

The dimensions of the MWMR are: length \times width \times height of 380mm \times 260mm \times 165mm, $L = 316$ mm, $d = 270$ mm, and $r = 30$ mm is the radius of wheels.

B. The Bézier Moving Trajectory of the Robot

The Bézier curve [24] is defined by trajectory interpolation points and is given by:

$$P(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n B_i J_{n,i}(t), 0 \leq t \leq 1 \quad (12)$$

where B_i represents the coordinates of interpolated points, as described in Figure 3, i is the ordinal number of the interpolation points, and $J_{n,i}(t)$ is a Bernstein polynomial of degree n , given by:

$$J_{n,i}(t) = \binom{n}{i} t^i (1-t)^{n-i} \quad (13)$$

where $\binom{n}{i} = \frac{n!}{i!(n-i)!}$ is the the Pascal coefficient, and n is the

Bernstein polynomial degree and the curve's degree. From the above Bézier curve design method, we have the desired moving trajectory of the robot shown in Figure 3 with the points A_i ($i = 1-14$) being the interpolation points.

Fig. 3. The desired Bézier trajectory of the MWMR.

C. MWMR Linear and Angular Velocity Determination

The desired velocity $V_d(t)$ of the MWMR is determined by the Bézier motion trajectory \mathcal{S}_d as follows:

$$V_d(t) = \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta t} = \frac{\sqrt{(x_i - x_{i-1})^2 + (y_i - y_{i-1})^2}}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \quad (14)$$

The desired angular velocity Ω_d of the MWMR is determined by:

$$\Omega_d(t) = V_d(t) / \rho(t) \quad (15)$$

where $\rho_i \in [\rho_{\min}, \rho_{\max}]$ is the radius of the desired trajectory ($i = 1, 2, \dots$), obtained by:

$$\rho_i = \left| \frac{(\dot{x}_i^2 + \dot{y}_i^2)^{3/2}}{\dot{x}_i \ddot{y}_i - \dot{y}_i \ddot{x}_i} \right| \quad (16)$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_i = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = \frac{x_i - x_{i-1}}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \\ \dot{y}_i = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta t} = \frac{y_i - y_{i-1}}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \ddot{x}_i = \frac{\Delta \dot{x}}{\Delta t} = \frac{\dot{x}_i - \dot{x}_{i-1}}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \\ \ddot{y}_i = \frac{\Delta \dot{y}}{\Delta t} = \frac{\dot{y}_i - \dot{y}_{i-1}}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \end{cases}$$

Clearly, from (14)-(16) and the data of the trajectory interpolation points given in Figure 3, we have the desired linear velocity V_d and angular velocity Ω_d of the MWMR described in Figure 4 when the MWMR moves along the Bézier trajectory \mathcal{S} with $\Delta t = 0.1$ s and maximal allowed speed $V_{dmax} = 0.3$ m/s. Thus, the desired $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_d$ vector is defined by

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_d = [V_d \quad \Omega_d]^T$$

Fig. 4. The desired linear and angular velocities of the MWMR.

D. Setting Parameters of Neural Network Training

The initialization values at the input/output of the NN while training are: $\mathbf{a}_0 = \mathbf{e}$, $\mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{u}$ and $\mathbf{s}_2(k) = -\hat{\mathbf{F}}_2(\mathbf{W}_2 \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2) \mathbf{e}_u$. The learning coefficient $\alpha = 1$ is determined by trial and error, and is such that the jump does not exceed the optimal value. The parameter matrices are updated online to control the MWMR trajectory tracking with a minor tracking error.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The installed parameters consist of (1) the size of the MWMR, (2) the parameters and the training parameters of the neural network, and (3) the motion trajectory and the

parameters of MWMR. The motion trajectory of the MWMR, after 1072 online training updates, is depicted in Figure 5, with the orange line as the desired trajectory and the blue line as the motion trajectory of the robot controlled by the proposed neural network controller. The position and posture errors of MWMR are depicted in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. The moving trajectory of the MWMR.

Fig. 6. The position error of the G-point and posture error of the robot.

Figure 6 shows that the proposed controller has the maximum error in the x-direction ($e_{x_{max}}$) not more than 11mm, and the maximum position error in the y - direction ($e_{y_{max}}$) is 17mm at position 9. The maximum posture error of the robot $e_{\phi_{max}}$ does not exceed 0.34° . The points marked from 1 to 9 in Figure 6 correspond to where the MWMR changes direction in Figures 5 and 3. In general, significant position errors often occur at the points where the MWMR changes direction. These are the points where the MWMR changes from clockwise to counterclockwise rotation and vice versa. Figures 5 and 6 clearly show that the proposed controller can track the desired trajectory with minor errors.

Figure 7 shows the cost function value when training the neural network to update the weight matrices \mathbf{W} and bias vector \mathbf{b} in real time. From Figure 7, it is easy to see that at the

points where the direction of the MWMR change, the control signal of the neural network has a deviation from the signal of the reference control model. Still, it was trained in time to minimize the error to asymptotically reach zero.

Fig. 7. The cost function.

Fig. 8. The network parameters of the first hidden layer: (a) The network bias \mathbf{b}_1 , (b) The network weight matrix \mathbf{W}_1 .

Figures 8 and 9 verify the online updating of the network weight matrix \mathbf{W} and bias vector \mathbf{b} of the proposed controller for the MWMR to follow the Bézier trajectory. The NN weights from zero initial values changed during the adaptation process and stabilized at specific values. Since the neural network structure is rather simple, the proposed neural network can find the optimum values of the network parameters quickly and accurately. Figure 10 shows that the velocities of the MWMR are adjusted around the desired value such that the MWMR position to an asymptote value is '0'. Figure 10 shows that the velocity error \mathbf{V}_{xr} ranges from 0 to 0.0011m/s, the velocity error \mathbf{V}_{yr} is adjusted around the desired value 0 to 0.0009m/s, and the maximum angular velocity error of MWMR is more than 0.00054rad/s. Figure 10 shows that the proposed controller is precisely following the reference linear and angular velocities. Figures 11 and 12 show that the angular velocities of the wheels always follow the desired values, and the angular velocities error varies from 0 to 0.05rad/s. The angular velocity errors were limited and had the most significant values at the beginning and at the points where the MWMR changed direction.

Fig. 9. The ANN parameters of the second hidden layer 2: (a) The network bias b_2 , (b) The network weight matrix W_2 .

Fig. 10. Linear and angular velocities of the MWMR.

The efficacy of the proposed controller can also be proved from the velocity and error curves, which show that the control system based on the NN controller can track the desired trajectory with minimum tracking error, and the control inputs strictly follow the reference velocities. Additionally, the neural network has overcome the disadvantages of our previous studies [4], where the time-varying PID controller was used to control the MWMR, such as (i) the time-varying PID controller requires the linear model of the robot and (ii) the PID controller needs to know the functions of the controller gains and the gains are often assumed as the linear function of the robot error.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be derived from the results and discussion of the current study.

An artificial neural network-based model reference controller for the Bézier trajectory tracking of the mecanum-wheeled mobile robot with a minor tracking error is proposed in this paper. Compared to other controllers, the neural network in the proposed controller has a simple structure, but it effectively improves performance with minor error. This primarily ensures that a small number of computations increases the convergence speed to update the control gains

online. The adapted gains are derived by satisfying the condition that the error between the actual and controller outputs is zero asymptotically.

Fig. 11. The angular velocities of the four wheels.

Fig. 12. The angular velocity error of four wheels.

The simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed controller. They show that the errors in the x- and y-directions do not exceed 11mm and 17mm, respectively, and the direction error does not exceed 0.34° . In addition, the position and orientation errors of the MWMR are often significant at the points where the MWMR changes direction to the desired trajectory tracking. We believe this will yield guarantees on the tracking performance of the MWMR. Additionally, the proposed controller exhibited motion error,

including the linear velocity error, limited to 0.0014m/s and angular velocity error limited to 0.00054rad/s.

Likewise, the proposed controller can be applied to any desired trajectory with minimal control action and perfect orientation with low hardware structure cost. Nevertheless, this research does not account for the longitudinal and lateral slip, friction at the wheel-ground contact points, friction between the roller rotation and the roller's shaft on the wheels, and inertia forces. These are considered parts of our future research goals.

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Mechanical Characteristics of Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents and evaluates a new method for producing Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete (SIFCON). A study was carried out to investigate the impact on the mechanical properties of SIFCON, where several cubes, cylinders, and prisms were cast to compare the proposed gradual and the traditional multi-layer method using the same mixing proportions: 6% straight steel fiber, cement, sand, 10% silica fume replacement, and 2.4% superplasticizer. The results showed that when using the proposed gradual mix method, compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, and modulus of rupture improved by 15.21%, 8.06%, 9.07%, and 5.26% compared to the traditional multi-layer method.

Keywords-SIFCON; straight steel fiber; compressive strength; splitting tensile strength; modulus of elasticity

I. INTRODUCTION

Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete (SIFCON) is one of the most popular repair materials, as it is similar to reinforced concrete in terms of dimensional changes, hardness, and durability. SIFCON can be employed in difficult-to-reach areas, the fibers between the old and new concrete produce a strong bond, and several repair approaches can be used to gain strength quickly [1]. In [2], various SIFCON slurry combinations were examined for their ability to penetrate fibers using flow cone and plate cohesion meters to forecast infiltration. SIFCON is created by first inserting fibers or a fiber mat into a mold. In some cases, the application of external vibrations may be difficult [3]. The fiber content should be spread or distributed on the surface of the formation to provide an acceptable degree of uniformity, by saturating the previously placed fibers with a paste or mortar slurry that is fluid enough to permeate the whole fiber network [4].

Four primary components should be considered when creating SIFCON: slurry quality and fiber volume, arrangement, and type. Fiber volume depends on the type of fiber used and the vibration exertion required for the appropriate compaction. Short fibers may pack denser than longer fibers, and higher fiber volumes can be accomplished with cautious and adequate vibration [5]. The compressive

strength of cement mortar without fibers is approximately 28-35MPa after 1 day and reaches 50-70MPa after 28 days, while adding iron fibers increases its compressive strength to 40-80 and 90-160MPa, respectively, depending on the volume of the friction of steel fiber added [6]. The tensile strength of SIFCON is about twice the strength of the matrix, i.e. about 14MPa, and can reach more than 20MPa. In [7], the tensile strength obtained for various combinations of matrix composition, fiber types, and fiber volume fractions were between 4-16.1MPa. Stronger tensile properties can be achieved using a lower water-to-cement ratio due to the improved matrix bonding. The modulus of elasticity of SIFCON is slightly lower than in ordinary concrete due to the absence of coarse aggregates and the higher cement content in SIFCON matrices. The relationship between compressive strength and strain between 0 and 20% of the final stress was studied in [8-9].

The current study aimed to produce SIFCON in a faster and easier way and investigate the effect of the proposed method on mechanical properties such as compressive strength, modulus of elasticity, tensile strength, and modulus of rupture.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Portland Cement

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) produced in Iraq under the Al Mass brand, conforming to Iraqi standards [10] was used.

B. Fine Aggregates

Natural sand from the region of Al-Ukhaider was used as fine aggregates. As this natural sand has a larger particle size to be used in mortar making, it was sieved using a 600 μ m sieve to separate the coarser particles, according to the IQS 45/1984 limitation zone 4 [11]. This size of sand proved to be successful for all mortar mixes during the experimental work.

C. Micro Silica Fume (SF)

SF is an ultra-fine material with spherical particles having approximately 0.15 μ m diameter. SF improves the cement paste microstructure and makes it more resistant to any form of external impact. In this study, MasterRoc MS610 SF, compatible with [12], was used at 10% replacement of cement weight.

D. High-Range Water Reducing (HRWR) Admixture

HRWR admixture was used to provide higher workability to the slurry and sufficiently liquify it to flow through the thick fiber without creating honeycombs. This study used the DCP Master Glenium 54 high-performance concrete superplasticizer, which is free from chlorides and is compatible with [13].

E. Straight Steel Fibers

This study used straight micro-steel fibers made by the Ganzhou Daye Metallic Fibers Co. Ltd, China (Figure 1). Table I shows its chemical composition and properties.

Fig. 1. Steel fibers used.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF STEEL FIBERS*

Property	Value
(D) Diameter(mm)	0.20
(L) Average length (mm)	13.0
Aspect ratio (L/D)	65
Tensile strength(N/mm ²)	2850
Density(kg/m ³)	7860
Color	Golden

*according to the manufacturer

F. Mix Proportions

In [14], many trial slurry mixtures were produced to find the mix proportion that has the best fresh state characteristics regarding fluidity, filling ability, and viscosity without bleeding, separation, or pockets in the dense fiber network to decrease the mechanical properties of SIFCON, since there are no standard guidelines yet for the production of SIFCON mixtures. Several studies have investigated the production of SIFCON mixtures. In most situations, the proportions of sand to cement were 1:1 by weight, so this ratio was adopted. Furthermore, several studies used cement content ranging from 800 to 1000kg/m³ and recommended a weight ratio of less than 0.41 to produce the slurry. After many trials, specimens were cast with various mixes and tested after 7 days using standard Portland cement amounts of 973kg/m³ with 10% replacement of SF. The water/binder (w/b) ratio was kept at 0.28 by the weight of the cementitious material, and the amount of water for each 1m³ was 272.44kg/m³. The Master Glenium R 54 HRWR was used at a ratio of 2.4% by weight of the cementitious material, and 6% of straight steel fiber. Table II shows the optimal mixes and their weight proportions for 1m³. The concrete was poured into many layers before compacting with a tamping rod or a vibrating machine to exclude as much air as possible [15-17].

TABLE II. MIX PROPORTIONS FOR THE SIFCON.

Mix proportions	
Cement (Kg/m ³)	875.7
Sand (Kg/m ³)	973
Silica fume (Kg/m ³)10% rep	97.3
Gravel (Kg/m ³)	-
Steel fiber (%)	6
w/b or w/c ratio	0.28
SP (by wt. of binder) (%)	2.4
V-funnel test (sec)	10
Mini slump flow (mm)	260

Fig. 2. Slump flow and V-funnel test.

G. SIFCON Producing Procedure

An increased mixing period is significant to achieve the desired efficiency and homogeneity of the slurry and allow the HRWR to reach its maximum capacity and get complete disposal of Silica Fumes (SF) by breaking up any agglomerated particles. An electrical drill mixer with a suitable pan was used for all specimen mixes. After cleaning the mixer of any residual hard and fresh materials, the sand was mixed with 1/5 water to hydrate it, followed by mixing the total amount of HRWR with 1/3 of water in 0.5 minutes, the binder material (cement with SF) was mixed in the mixer for 1 minute to

spread the SF particles within the cement particles, and finally, the blinder was added to the mortar. Two thirds (2/3) of the mixing water was added to the mix and mixed for one minute. HRWR with 1/3 of a cup of water was mixed for about three minutes to achieve the best mix and the necessary flowability. Mixing the slurry took another minute.

1) Multi-Layer Method

In this method, a layer of slurry is applied, followed by steel fiber sawing, a layer of mortar, and some fibers. This process was repeated until the fibers permeate the slurry [18]. After casting the cubic, cylinder, and prism forms, they were cured for 7 and 28 days, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Casting SIFCON using the multi-layer method.

2) Gradual Mix Method

In this method, steel fiber was mixed with the slurry, where the calculated amount of fiber was added to the sample to be cast and added gradually with mixing until the mixture becomes homogeneous and the fibers permeate well with the slurry. Cubics, cylinders, and prisms were cast by this method and cured for 7 and 28 days, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Casting SIFCON using the gradual mix method.

III. TESTING HARDENED SIFCON

A. Compressive Strength Test

Three 50×50×50mm cubes cast with both methods and cured for 7 and 28 days were used to investigate the compressive strength. A digital compression tester was used

(1950kN) with 0.31MPa/sec rate of loadings, following the BS.1881:part 116 [19], as shown in Figure 5.

B. Splitting Tensile Strength Test

Samples of 100.0mm in diameter and 200.0mm in length were used for the splitting tensile strength test. A testing device with a capacity of 1950kN was used, and the tests were conducted following the ASTM C496/C496M 2017, as shown in Figure 6.

C. Modulus of Elasticity Test

The modulus of elasticity was measured using cylinders with diameters of 150.0mm and 300.0mm, following the ASTM C469, 2014. To avoid any weakening, the upper part of the cylinder was expertly completed and smoothed using an electric grinding machine. The samples were put in a hydraulic device that could handle 1950kN. The concrete cylinders were compressed to 40% of their ultimate compressive strength as seen in Figure 7.

Fig. 5. Compressive strength test.

Fig. 6. Splitting tensile test.

Fig. 7. Modulus of elasticity test.

D. Flexural Strength (Modulus of Rupture)

This test was carried out under [20], using 100×100×400mm prismatic beams tested as simply supported beams with third point load, with a steady loading rate of about 0.015MPa/sec with a maximum load of 150kN, as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Flexural strength test.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table III shows the results for all tests.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF HARDENED SIFCON TESTS

	Compressive strength (MPa)		Splitting tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	Modulus of rupture (MPa)
	7 days	28 days	28 days	28 days	28 days
Curing period (days)					
Multi-layer method	78.2	93	18.6	23.7	28.5
Gradual mix method	92.1	106	20.1	25.85	30

Each table value represents the average of 3 samples. Figure 9 shows the results in compressive strength of SIFCON between the two casting methods for 7 and 28 days of curing. The results of the sample tests show that the proposed gradual-mixing method of steel fiber with mortar is better than the traditional multi-layered. The compressive strength increased by 18.93% and 15.21% after 7 and 28 days, respectively, as fibers were distributed in a homogeneous way for the cubic volume, reducing the appearance of cracks and giving an equal dispersal for both internal and external stresses due to the progression of reinforcing network. Fibers filled the pattern size in the slurry, so the compressive strength of SIFCON increased. The purpose of the splitting tensile strength test was to examine the behavior of the SIFCON specimens in terms of strength and hardness. The splitting results were lower than the compression test for the same SIFCON cylinder [15]. The force on the area where the load is applied causes cracks to emerge faster, leading to the failure of the sample. The splitting test results of the SIFCON created using the proposed gradual mixing method were better than the multi-layer because the fibers were more homogeneous in distribution with the slurry, which linked the fibers to each other in the network. This reduced the appearance of cracks, provided additional strength,

and improved the mechanical properties of the SIFCON. The difference between the two methods was 8.06%, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9. Compressive strength of SIFCON.

Fig. 10. Splitting tensile strength of SIFCON.

Fig. 11. Cylinder after test.

The elastic modulus is very important because it describes the hardness of the material and is affected by the type of concrete, the proportions of the materials used, and their quality [22]. Figure 12 shows the modulus of elasticity for both the production methods used. It can be observed that there is a clear improvement of 9.07% when using the SIFCON gradual mixing pouring method. This also shows that the coefficient of elasticity is in fact stress on strain because stress includes strength. SIFCON produced by gradual mixing homogenized the fibers with the slurry without leaving a weak area for the premature failure of the sample, as the fibers occupied the width of the crack after the failure of the sample. Figure 13 shows the modulus of the rupture of prisms cast by the two methods. The gradual mix method gave higher results than the multi-layer method by 5.26%, as the steel fibers in the matrix slurry intertwined with each other in the prism, making it difficult to crush. Figure 14 shows that the interlacing of the fibers with each other in the crack area reduced the crack width.

Fig. 12. SIFCON modulus of elasticity.

Fig. 13. Modulus of rupture results.

Fig. 14. Prism after test.

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a faster and easier casting method for SIFCON using straight steel fibers. The experimental investigation showed that the proposed gradual mixing method improved compressive strength by 15.21%, splitting tensile by 8.06%, modulus of elasticity by 9.07%, and modulus of rupture by 5.26% compared to the traditional multi-layer method. Although the fibers are small and light in weight, the proposed mixing method made the mixture homogeneous and prevented them from descending. The fibers were distributed in a way that increased SIFCON's bearing capacity. The failure mode for both casting methods was the same.

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Implementation and Evaluation of a Low Speed and Self-Regulating Small Wind Turbine for Urban Areas in South Africa

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ABSTRACT

A low-cost small 500W wind generator was used as a basis for the prototype development. The research was primarily focused on the determination of the type of aerofoil for improved rotor blades and pitch angle, and for adapting the number of blades in order to optimize the power output from the prototype, for low wind-speed inland conditions in Soweto. NACA-4412 type aerofoil was chosen as a departure point for the blade design, and a variation of the maximum pitch angle of 6°, 10°, and 12° at an optimum angle of attack of 5°, 7°, and 9° were implemented respectively for Designs 1, 2 and 3. With the Soweto area having an average wind speed of 2.3 m/s (8.28 km/h), 3-, 5-, and 7-blade sets were subsequently developed, implemented, and tested. Prototype 1 produced a maximum output power of 8.2 W at 4.2 km/h wind speed. Prototype 2 yielded a maximum output power of 12.5 W at 4.2 km/h, and Prototype 3, generated a very useful power output of 39.5 W during testing. The maximum power output was achieved at an average wind speed of 1.17 m/s (4.2 km/h). Moreover, the developed prototype designs were also tested for self-regulation in case of high-speed gust conditions. Prototype 3, with a 12° maximum pitch angle during operation in high gust conditions, had its blades control high speed. A drawback pressure occurred on the back side of the blades and tangent drag was developed normally to the blade rotation direction, consequently limiting the maximum speed of the rotor and acting as a self-regulation mechanism with regard to maximum achievable speed. The other two designs suffered from over-speeding tendencies in high gust speed conditions, also causing noise and turbulence.

Keywords-SWT design prototypes; self regulation; experimental results

I. INTRODUCTION

Population and technology use growth result in increased energy consumption and increased emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHGs). The use of fossil fuels in the generation of electricity contributes significantly to GHG emissions, which

contribute to climate change [1, 2]. Utilizing renewable energy as an alternative energy source will reduce environmental problems, essentially GHG emissions and air pollution [3]. Wind energy has seen a dramatic increase in development during the last 20 years [4]. This development occurred especially in the implementation of small-scale wind farms at

households and business premises in urban areas, and in huger large-scale wind turbines in far off rural areas, where high wind speeds prevail. Large scale wind turbine systems are complex and expensive technology and energy has to be transported over large distances, while small scale wind turbines in urban areas can be implemented in an autonomous and low-cost basis. A preliminary review on recent designs and developments on Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs) will be discussed below.

Small wind turbines are characterized as having an output power of less than 50kW and operating at low wind speeds and low Reynolds numbers, which is common in the industry. The rotor blades are considered as the most critical component, as their aerodynamic efficiency has a direct effect on the turbine system's overall performance [5]. The blade design is influenced by various parameters, the most important of which is the aerofoil, which dictates the cross-sectional geometry of the blade. Numerous aerofoils have been designed expressly for small wind power generation [6-8]. Numerous methods and techniques have been developed over the last few years to increase the efficiency (performance) of wind turbines. These methods and techniques were supported by the empirical analysis and optimization of the wind turbine blade design characteristics. Blade Element Momentum (BEM) theory is a critical method for simulating and optimizing the performance of wind turbine blades [9].

A small wind turbine blade was designed and optimized to maximize blade number and tip speed ratio for solidity in [10]. In [11], a variety of BEM parameters for the design and optimization of small (less than 1 kW) wind turbine blades at rated wind speed of 8.4m/s, was simulated in QBlade, and plots of CP and power versus tip speed ratio were shown. The SG6043 airfoil was selected because it had the maximum lift coefficient of 1.63. QBlade was used to simulate a 1.2 m blade length. Authors in [12] investigated the performance of the rotor blade (horizontal axis) of a small wind turbine. The wind turbine was considered to operate ideally at low wind speeds and low Reynolds number (5×10^5). The rotor had a 2 m diameter and 3 blades. The blade model was built utilizing 3 aerofoils (DU86-084, E387, and SD2030) with a tip speed ratio of 7. E387 outperformed the other two simulated aerofoils.

It is necessary to ensure that the turbine's protection is not compromised by turbulence and vibration effects. Thus, a critical feature of a wind turbine is power control, which prevents the wind turbine from being damaged at extremely high wind speeds [13].

In this article, the results of the undertaken work on the low cost mechanically self-regulating HAWTs, that were optimally designed and eventually implemented and tested in a residential area in Soweto, Johannesburg, South Africa, is presented. These test prototypes can be implemented at large volumes in middle-income households and can make a significant contribution to the generation of clean energy in South Africa.

II. METHODS

The methodologies applied in this project considered different perspectives and routes. The plan of action was eventually taken after a thorough literature review. Basic

design choices would be made based on known considerations [13, 14].

A. BEM Theory Considerations [12]

In this analysis, the theoretically inter-relationships between pitch angle, blade solidity, maximum power coefficient, and tip speed ratio were studied. The study was conducted using the following theoretical considerations: a fixed experimental design route was chosen and implemented and predictive data were derived. One twisted blade design, fixed chords and varying number of blades (3, 5, and 7) mounted on a rotor diameter of 0.95m, were considered. The derived conclusion was that the optimum power coefficient is mainly dependent on pitch angle and tip speed ratio for the dimensions chosen in our design.

B. Chosen Design Procedure

The basic design choices considering low wind speed operating conditions were [15]:

- Not too large rotor diameter since noise, turbulence, and vibration, would be the primary functions of blade radius size.
- High pitch angle of the blades near the hub region of the blade. This approach would maximize the torque on the rotor axis at low wind speeds, while it would not cause an excessive apparent wind on the outer edges of the rotor. The optimum power coefficient is mainly dependent on the pitch angle and tip speed ratio.
- Since many physical and dynamic parameters, such as apparent wind speeds, apparent wind directions, and stall speeds are quite difficult to derive theoretically, it was decided to primary focus on designing and investigating the effect of (i) the number of blades and (ii) the pitch angle of the blade and the variation of these along the blade radius as a primary variation parameter. Increasing the radius and number of blades on the rotor, would increase the total wind capture area of the blades and the total power transfer.
- After reviewing the published specifications of commercially available wind turbines on the market, it was decided to implement a known and proven design within the NACA 44 family, and then vary the blade radius and the attack angle along the radius of the blade, and adapt these to the specific conditions in Soweto.
- Using the BEM theory and blade specifications of the NACA 44 family, it was derived that the electrical power output goal of about 380, 420, and 430 W could be a reasonable output choice for a 3-, 5-, and 7-bladed, 1m radius systems, respectively.

These power levels seemed to be enough to generate and store a few kWh per day and power basic essential appliances in a medium scale house for a day or two.

C. Flow Chart of the Proposed Research

The flowchart of the undertaken research can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The flowchart of the followed methodology.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The Soweto Small Wind Turbine (SWT) set contained a three-phase 500W synchronous generator which was used as a basis for optimizing the power output of the designed blades (3, 5, 7). The performance testing steps of the rotor-blade prototypes required the assembly of the following equipment associated with the wind turbine:

- Charge controller
- Two 12 V batteries connected in series
- An off-grid inverter
- Output load
- Unit-B anemometer and power wattmeter

These components were coupled to the designed prototypes that were implemented. Figure 2 shows a block setup test diagram for the Soweto project. The prototypes were tested under conditions of full load (discharged batteries) and the experimental data were collected. All the tests were done at output voltage of approximately 19.0 V, corresponding with a charger state of approximately 70% of the storage batteries. The same reference voltage of 19.0V was used at the start of each test. Appliances (LCD TV, sound equipment, DSTV decoder, and camera) were connected to the storage batteries, output controller, and off-grid inverter, especially during non-charging periods. Load conditions varied with power usage during the day and the passive resistive load was added. The tests were always initiated in early afternoon when wind speeds were picking up in Soweto. These provided the most practical conditions for testing and were nearest to true operational conditions. The 3-blade wind turbine system (Prototype 1) was implemented, as shown in Figure 3 and the experimental data shown in Table I were collected. Figure 4 illustrates the 5-Blade wind turbine system (Prototype 2) implementation. Table II provides the experimental data collected for Prototype 2. Figure 5 illustrates the implementation of Prototype 3 (7-blade wind turbine system) and Table II shows the collected experimental data.

Fig. 2. Block setup test diagram for the Soweto project.

Fig. 3. 3-bladed system design view with maximum blade pitch angle of 6°.

A. Power Performance Comparison

During the design of the wind turbine blade for Prototype 3, it was predicted that the rated output should be 40 W at rated

Fig. 4. 5-bladed system design view with maximum blade pitch angle of 10°.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR PROTOTYPE 1

Wind speed (km/h)	Measured current (A)	Turbine speed (rpm)	Measured Voltage (V)	Real Power (W)	Calculated Power (W)
1.2	0.069	61	19.3	1.33	0.049
1.4	0.072	72	19.4	1.4	0.051
0.9	0.015	35	19.0	0.285	0.009
2.8	0.15	85	19.2	2.88	0.12
1.9	0.1	75	19.0	1.9	0.065
0.8	0.016	34	18.9	0.302	0.008
3.1	0.2	142	19.3	3.86	0.19
2.9	0.16	86	19.3	3.088	0.13
1.5	0.073	73	19.5	1.42	0.052
3.2	0.21	141	19.3	4.05	0.2
1.5	0.073	73	19.4	1.41	0.053
2.0	0.11	76	19.1	2.10	0.075
0.9	0.017	35	19	0.323	0.009
1.6	0.074	74	19.6	1.45	0.053
4.2	0.41	165	19.8	8.2	6.42
2.1	0.12	77	19.2	2.31	0.085
1.6	0.074	74	19.4	1.44	0.053
1.4	0.072	72	19.4	1.4	0.051
0.9	0.015	35	19.0	0.285	0.009
0.8	0.016	34	18.9	0.302	0.008
1.2	0.069	61	19.3	1.33	0.049
1.6	0.074	74	19.6	1.45	0.053
1.7	0.075	75	19.5	1.46	0.054
1.9	0.1	75	19.0	1.9	0.067
1.5	0.073	73	19.5	1.42	0.053

Fig. 5. 7-bladed system design view with maximum blade pitch angle of 12°.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR PROTOTYPE 2

Wind speed (km/h)	Measured current (A)	Turbine speed (rpm)	Measured Voltage (V)	Real Power (W)	Calculated Power (W)
1.2	0.085	55	19.7	1.67	0.221
1.4	0.095	99	19.5	0.175	0.212
0.9	0.019	66	19.2	0.36	0.009
2.8	0.19	45	19.5	3.70	0.102
1.9	0.098	135	19.7	1.93	0.27
0.8	0.058	125	19.9	1.15	0.068
3.1	0.24	85	19.8	4.75	0.75
2.9	0.15	98	19	2.85	0.36
1.5	0.096	89	19.1	1.83	0.145
3.2	0.23	141	19.4	4.46	0.68
1.5	0.096	89	19.1	1.83	0.155
2.0	0.099	136	19.8	1.96	0.27
0.9	0.019	25	19	0.361	0.015
1.6	0.1	90	19.7	1.97	0.156
4.2	0.64	179	19.6	12.5	9.25
2.1	0.12	114	19.2	2.30	0.28
1.6	0.1	85	19.3	1.93	0.156
1.4	0.095	35	19.5	1.85	0.154
0.9	0.057	65	19.7	1.123	0.067
0.8	0.056	45	19.4	1.08	0.066
1.2	0.069	141	19.7	1.35	0.221
1.6	0.1	129	19.4	1.94	0.156
1.7	0.187	102	19	3.55	0.157
1.9	0.196	35	19.9	3.9	0.27
1.5	0.152	45	19.5	2.96	0.155

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR PROTOTYPE 3

Wind speed (km/h)	Measured current (A)	Turbine speed (rpm)	Measured Voltage (V)	Real Power (W)	Calculated Power (W)
1.2	0.14	141	19.7	2.75	1.25
1.4	0.12	99	19.5	2.34	1.58
0.9	0.1	121	19.2	1.92	0.089
2.8	0.15	123	19.5	2.93	1.36
1.9	0.13	101	19.7	2.56	1.58
0.8	0.09	112	19.9	1.79	1.989
3.1	0.43	85	19.8	8.55	1.997
2.9	0.33	99	19	6.9	1.37
1.5	0.28	102	19.1	5.5	1.57
3.2	0.39	141	19.4	7.58	1.898
1.5	0.27	126	19.4	5.3	1.58
2.0	0.36	123	19.2	6.9	1.59
0.9	0.16	99	19	3.2	0.088
1.6	0.31	75	19.7	6.1	1.55
4.2	0.98	225	19.6	39.5	28.5
2.1	0.37	110	19.2	7.2	1.61
1.6	0.28	99	19.9	5.6	1.59
1.4	0.26	141	19.5	5.2	1.58
0.9	0.16	121	19.7	3.2	0.089
0.8	0.16	113	19.4	3.1	0.090
1.2	0.21	121	19.7	4.2	1.25
1.6	0.31	99	19.4	6.1	1.55

soweto wind speed of 2.3 m/s (8.28 km/h) [15]. As can be seen in Figure 6, during the comparison of the three prototypes, 40 W was achieved at an average wind speed of 1.17 m/s (4.2 km/h). Figures 7-9 illustrate the delivered output power observed at different pitch angles as implemented in the prototype designs. Prototypes 1, 2 and 3 were respectively implemented with a maximum pitch angle of 6°, 10°, and 12° near the rotor of the turbine and were tested for wind speed

values of 0, 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2, 2.4, 2.8, 3.2, 3.6, 4, and 4.2 km/h. It can be seen in Figure 9, that Prototype 3, which was designed for a 12° pitch angle, generated a maximum power output of 39.5W when compared with Prototype 2 (Figure 8), which was designed for pitch angle of 10°, whereas maximum power output of 12.5 W was observed.

Fig. 6. Wind speed vs. real power.

Fig. 7. Prototype 1, delivered power vs variation of maximum pitch angle.

Fig. 8. Prototype 2, delivered power vs variation of maximum pitch angle.

Fig. 9. Prototype 3, delivered power vs variation of maximum pitch angle.

For Prototype 1 (Figure 6), which was designed for pitch angle of 6°, the maximum power output was only 8.2 W. The results shown here are of course also dependent on the number of the blades. Nevertheless, a deduction can be made that the high pitch angle setting in Prototype 3 had a substantial impact on the higher power delivery observed in Figure 9.

B. Prototype Energy Delivered versus Time of day/month

Figure 10 shows the delivered energy versus time for a 24-hour period. It can be seen that Prototype 3's performance significantly outclassed those of Prototypes 2 and 1 during the day as there was a consistent generation of energy. Figure 11, shows the energy production of Prototypes 1, 2 and 3 per month during operation at Soweto. It can be seen that Prototype 3 outclassed Prototype 1 and 2 in terms of energy generated per month. Prototype 3 achieved 39.5 W output for a wind speed of 1.17 m/s and was predicated to generate a maximum 40 kWh per month.

Fig. 10. Delivered power vs time per day.

Fig. 11. Predicted total energy delivered per month in Soweto.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results showed that a Prototype 3 with a 7-blade design and with a maximum pitch angle of 12° produced maximum output power of 39.5 W during testing, achieved at about 1.17 m/s (4.2 Km/h) wind speed. The Prototype 2, with a 5-blade design and blade pitch angle of 10°, produced maximum output power of 12.5 W at 4.2 km/h wind speed, and Prototype 1 with a 3-blade design and a pitch angle of 6°, produced a maximum power output of 8.2W at 4.2 km/h wind speed. The results, furthermore, confirm that increasing the pitch angle from the

standard 6° used for NACA 4412 specifications to 10° and 12° near the hub and tapering/twisting to lower angles of the tip of the blade, and optimizing the attack angle to about 5° , 7° , and 9° along the section of the blade radius for 1, 2, and 3 designs, respectively, definitely increased the power delivery and the total energy capture of the rotor. These settings were derived from the available specifications and the published literature. The 7-blade prototype with NACA-4412 blade design is an original implementation in Soweto, Johannesburg environment. Derivation of the results and predictions for other areas in South Africa (specifically, Soweto and Port-Elizabeth) [16], contributed to new knowledge created within the field of the study.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The current study is primarily focused on determining and adapting low-cost technologies applicable to South African conditions. This included the choice of the type of aerofoil, the number of blades, and optimizing the pitch angle along the blade radius in order to maximize the power output for low wind speed conditions in Soweto. The main conclusions derived from the current study are:

- In Soweto area, having an average wind speed of 2.3 m/s (8.28 km/h), 3-, 5-, and 7-blade sets were developed and tested. The obtained results definitely indicate that for very low wind speed conditions, the implementation of more blades on single rotor/hub increased the captured power and energy significantly.
- Moreover, the developed prototype designs were also tested for self-regulation in case of high speed gust conditions. The results showed that the blades of Prototype 3, with 12° maximum pitch angle during operation in high gust conditions, would control high speed, then cause a drawback pressure on the back side of the blades and tangent drag developed normally to the blade rotation direction, consequently limiting the maximum speed of the rotor and acting as a self-regulation mechanism of the maximum achievable speed. The other two designs suffered from over-speeding tendencies in high gust speed conditions, also causing noise and turbulence.
- Finally, it can be deduced that the power derived from the 7-blade system would be close to the expected optimum power that would be delivered for the designed 1m blade rotor system. Any implementation of a higher pitch angle along the blades would, according to the theoretical considerations, probably lead towards an excessive angle of attack.

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Optimized Wind Turbine Emulator based on an AC to DC Motor Generator Set

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an Optimized Wind Turbine Emulator (OWTE) based on a DC generator driven by a three-phase Induction Motor (IM). The IM speed is varied using an AC drive that converts fixed RMS voltage and frequency to variable ones due to v/f control. The frequency reference of the control was calculated through optimized equations of a wind turbine model for maximum power and torque. The overall system was simulated on Matlab/Simulink using a wind speed profile scenario. An experimental test bench controlled by a TMS320F28379D card was set up in the laboratory to confirm the effectiveness of the obtained simulation results.

Keywords-wind power conversion system; Wind Turbine Emulator (WTE); induction motor; DC generator; Variable Frequency Drive (VFD)

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in using wind energy has led many researchers to experiment with emulators instead of real power

systems, due to the high investment cost of setting up a wind turbine and the slow dynamics of wind speed. Emulators are used to reproduce the characteristics developed by wind turbines for given wind speed profiles [1-2], and several

different emulators have been suggested. Some are based on permanent magnet synchronous machines [3], DC, or induction motors to replace the mechanical part [4-6]. Many electrical machines have been considered for the generator part, such as self-excited induction generators [7-8], permanent magnet synchronous generators [9-10], or DC generators [11]. The study of emulators focuses on several parameters such as the generator speed, pitch angle, maximum power, and torque [12]. Digital circuits, including FPGAs, microcontrollers, and DSP cards are used to apply efficient control algorithms with these emulators [13-14].

This work was based on an electromechanical system designed to achieve an efficient model of the conversion system as an Optimized Wind Turbine Emulator (OWTE). The OWTE was made up of a DC generator driven by an induction motor monitored through a v/f control. The speed reference was generated from the derived equations of power and torque in the maximum states. The model was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink and analyzed to test its effectiveness. In addition, an experimental setup was set up in the laboratory, where the adopted control was implemented on a Texas Instruments digital signal processing cardboard to provide more credibility and experimental verification of the results.

II. DESCRIPTION AND MODELING OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Figure 1 shows the structure of the proposed system, which is composed of an Optimized Wind Turbine Model (OWTM), a Variable Frequency AC Drive (VFD), and an AC to DC Motor Generator Set (M-G).

Fig. 1. The proposed system of the OWTE.

A. Wind turbine Model

A Wind Turbine (WT) transforms the kinetic energy taken by the blades into mechanical torque at the rotor shaft. However, the geometry of the turbine, the wind speed (V_w), and the pitch angle (β) of the blades have an essential influence on its performance [15]. The aerodynamic power depends on the wind power and the power coefficient C_p :

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} A \rho V_w^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the air density, and A is the area swept by the rotor blades given by πR^2 and R is the turbine radius. $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ is the ratio between P_w and V_w , which depends on β and λ being the pitch angle and the Tip-Speed-Ratio (TSR), respectively. λ can be obtained from:

$$\lambda = \frac{\Omega R}{V_w} \quad (2)$$

where Ω is the angular velocity.

Moreover, many studies have been conducted to define the appropriate expression of C_p , while others proposed functions that can approximately represent the real curve of the power coefficient. Polynomial, sinusoidal, and exponential function models are usually used to model the power coefficient [16]. The sinusoidal and exponential function models are related to λ and β to control the required C_p . The polynomial function model assumes that the attack angle of the wind turbine blade is constant. This model makes C_p a simple function that depends on a specific λ [17]. The adopted model is based on the exponential function expressed by:

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = c_1 \left(c_2 \frac{1}{\lambda^i} - c_3 \beta - c_4 \beta^{c_5} - c_6 \right) e^{-c_7 \frac{1}{\lambda^i} + c_8 \lambda} \quad (3)$$

with:

$$\frac{1}{\lambda^i} = \frac{1}{\lambda + a_9 \beta} - \frac{a_{10}}{\beta^3 + 1} \quad (4)$$

Some studies adjusted the exponential function model to obtain a specified C_p curve by choosing the coefficient values c_i [18]. An ideal wind turbine can obtain only 59.25% mechanical energy from the overall kinetic wind energy, known as the Betz limit [19]. However, the aerodynamic torque of the wind turbine T_w is a relation between the mechanical power and the angular velocity:

$$T_w = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pi \rho R^2 V_w^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta)}{\Omega} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2 shows the mechanical model of the WT conversion system. Turbine blades and the electromechanical converter are among the main components of the WT system, as well as the gearbox with its gain G , which is a mediator between the low-rotation shaft Ω_t and the high-rotation shaft Ω_m [20-21].

Fig. 2. Mechanical model of the WT conversion system.

Equation (6) describes the basic mechanical equation Ω_m for the high-speed shaft tied to an electrical generator, whereas (7) expresses the equivalent inertia J acted on the high-speed shaft, i.e., the generator side [21]:

$$\frac{T_t}{G} - T_g = J \frac{d\Omega_m}{dt} \quad (6)$$

$$J = \frac{J_t}{G^2} + J_g \quad (7)$$

where T_t and T_g are the corresponding turbine and generator torques and J_t and J_g are the low-speed (turbine side) and high-speed (generator side) inertia shafts, respectively. Figure 3

shows the static and dynamic characteristics based on the above equations to provide a realistic WT model [21-22]. The adopted model was verified in Matlab/Simulink based on the parameters in Table I. Figure 4 shows the obtained curve of C_p based on (3), where the chosen c_i values are listed in Table II.

Fig. 3. Overall wind turbine model.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE WIND TURBINE MODEL

Parameters	Values
Rated power	10KW
Cut-in wind speed	3.0m/s
Rated wind speed	10m/s
Rotor diameter	7.1m
Gear	7
Number of blades	3

Fig. 4. Curve of the power coefficient C_p .

TABLE II. PARAMETERS OF THE POWER COEFFICIENT

c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5
0.5175	116	0.4	0	0
c_6	c_7	c_9	a_9	a_{10}
5	21	0.0068	0.08	0.035

Fig. 5. Wind turbine power versus angular speed.

As shown in Figure 4, several curves were deployed based on various pitch angles. However, only the curve corresponding

to $\beta=0^\circ$ will be considered in this paper with $\lambda=8.1$ that will be defined as the optimal λ_{opt} , as a result of the achieved maximum value of the power coefficient $C_{pmax}=0.48$ [23]. Figures 5 and 6 show the mechanical power and torque characteristics of the wind turbine model used versus the angular speed. The Maximum Power (MP) and Torque (MT) curves shown in Figures 5 and 6 are the main structure of the OWTM.

Fig. 6. Wind turbine torque versus angular speed.

B. Variable Frequency AC Drive

Figure 7 shows the major components of a PWM-based VFD: non-controlled three-phase rectifier, DC bus/filter, and the three-phase inverter with its control unit.

Fig. 7. Structure of a PWM-based VFD.

The VFD varies the speed of the induction motor based on v/f control to keep the torque constant [24]. Figure 8 presents the variation of the stator voltage of IM versus frequency. The linear zone in the range $[f_{min} - f_{rated}]$ will be used to generate an adequate v/f profile for the control unit.

Fig. 8. Variation of IM voltage versus frequency.

C. AC to DC Motor Generator Set

The M-G set used consists of a three-phase induction motor (squirrel-cage) coupled directly to a DC generator (DC-G). The

IM will produce a variable speed to the DC-G. This latter will produce a variable power according to the wind speed profile.

Fig. 9. The M-G set association.

III. THE ADOPTED CONTROL METHOD

Figure 10 shows the adopted OWTM with the VFD and the M-G set, which operates at the optimal $C_{pmax}=0.48$ and $\lambda_{opt}=8.1$.

Fig. 10. Block diagram of the proposed OWTM.

The maximum torque and power expressions obtained from Figures 5 and 6, using the curve fitting tool in Matlab, are:

$$T_{max} = 5.437 V_W^2 - 1.506 * 10^{-13} \quad (8)$$

$$P_{max} = 0.857 \Omega_{opt}^3 + 3.505 * 10^{-13} \quad (9)$$

The sensed angular speed Ω_{fed} of the IM and the wind profile speed were employed to obtain the maximum power using (8). Then, the reference angular speed Ω_{opt} was obtained according to (9). After that, the frequency reference f_{ref} of the VFD was generated for the three-phase inverter. The v/f profile was determined for a rated frequency and voltage of 50Hz and 380V. Three sinusoidal reference signals were generated and compared with a carrier triangular signal to control the inverter switches.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed system was modeled in Matlab/Simulink, as shown in Figure 11, using an M-G set of 1.5KW and a load of 122Ω. This simulation aimed to analyze the response of the optimized wind turbine emulator when it is exposed to a variable wind profile scenario between 4-9m/s. Figures 12-15 show the results obtained for 12s.

Fig. 11. Simulink model diagram of the proposed OWTM.

Fig. 12. Simulation results: (a) V_w (m/s), (b) Ω_{opt} and Ω_{fed} (rad/s), (c) f_{ref} (Hz).

Fig. 13. Simulation results: (a) N_{IM} (rpm), (b) U_{AC} (V).

Fig. 14. Simulation results: (a) I_{IM} (A), (b) Torque (Nm).

Fig. 15. Simulation results (a) V_{DC} (V); (b) I_{DC} (A); (c) Power (W).

As shown in Figure 12, the optimal speed Ω_{opt} follows the wind speed scenario. The difference between Ω_{opt} and the speed produced by the induction motor Ω_{fed} is justified by the slip. The calculated f_{ref} , which varied between 20-50Hz, was used to control the VFD. The output AC voltage of the VFD has three levels with a variable frequency and RMS value, as shown in Figure 13. The rotational speed N_{IM} varied between 600-1430rpm. However, the obtained torque, shown in Figure 14, was almost constant due to the v/f control. The same remark was noted for the IM current, which was also sinusoidal in shape. According to Figure 15, the generated power of the DC-G pursued the different variations of wind speed, which provided the main outcomes of the OWTE. The DC voltage varied in the 85-200V interval. The DC current changed from -1.6 to -0.6A, the negative values were due to the generator operating mode in Simulink, whereas the power variation was between 55-300W. These results show that the system effectively reproduced the static and dynamic characteristics of the wind turbine for the maximum value under different wind conditions.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 16 shows the proposed hardware rig of the OWTE, consisting of a variable speed drive, namely Altivar 18, and a 1.5KW three-phase induction motor coupled to a DC machine that fed a resistive load of 122Ω. A TMS320F28379D launchpad card was used to control the VFD. Current and velocity hall-effect sensor cards were used to sense voltage. Data acquisition in real-time was carried out in Matlab using a NI 6009 card.

Fig. 16. Test bench of the proposed system.

The proposed system was verified experimentally using the same wind profile scenario as the simulation. Figures 17 and 18

illustrate the main results for 60s. The rotational speed N_{IM} , shown in Figure 17, varies with the wind profile between 500-1430rpm. In the same figure, the AC voltage with three levels has a variable frequency and RMS value, and the IM current is sinusoidal in form. Figure 18 shows the variation of the generated DC power across the load between 10-320W. The DC voltage was established in the 10-210V interval and the DC current was between 0.4-1.7A. The experimental results confirmed the simulations and validated the proposed emulator.

Fig. 17. Experimental results: (a) N_{IM} (rpm), (b) U_{AC} , (c) I_{IM} .

Fig. 18. Experimental results: (a) V_{DC} , (b) I_{DC} , (c) Power.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an efficient structure of a wind turbine emulator based on an optimized model. This emulator system consists of an induction motor connected directly to a DC generator to reproduce the same dynamic behavior of a wind turbine, such as the torque, mechanical power, and angular speed. Considering the turbine model with a fixed pitch angle, the used control extracts the maximum power using simple fitting equations of power and torque curves. Based on the simulation and experimental results, the proposed WTE can effectively emulate the behavior of a real wind turbine, and the control method achieved good tracking of wind speed variation. In future work, the proposed OWTE will be developed by testing other structures and controls with the possibility of injecting energy into the grid.

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Additives Influence on the Properties of Asphalt Binders: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of using modified bitumen binders and additives to enhance the physical characteristics of asphalt mixtures at high, medium, and low temperatures. Both basic and rheological characteristics of the bituminous binders were tested by adding Styrene-Butadiene-Styrene, a type of thermoplastic elastomer, as a chemical additive to asphalt mixtures at various fractions (3.5%, 4%, and 4.5%), and two kinds of modified Bitumen: Kraton styrene block copolymers and Europrene (SOL T 6302). The following methods were used to test the properties of the binders: needle penetration, ductility, softening point, resistance to hardening when exposed to heat and air, Pressure Aging Vessel test dynamic (PAV), Shear Rheometer (DSR), Bending Beam Rheometer (BBR), direct tension test, and storage stability. The results showed that the best properties of the asphalt concentration were observed when using 4% of additives, while the penetration of Bitumen was reduced to 27.2% and 30.3% when adding Kraton and Europrene SOL T6302, respectively. The influence of adding 4.0% additives decreased the bulk specific gravity to 2.395. Laboratory tests showed how the mentioned chemical additives directly affect the properties of the mixture and the binder by increasing their viscosity.

Keywords-performance grade; Kraton styrene; Europrene styrene; bitumen; asphalt

I. INTRODUCTION

Additives are frequently used to increase the physical and mechanical characteristics of materials such as oil and asphalt at various temperatures [1-2]. As asphalt is made to sustain outside conditions such as low and high temperatures, water, or loads, some additives are mixed usually with it to increase its strength, such as two distinct types of the Styrene-Butadiene-Styrene (SBS) chemical additives: Kraton styrene block copolymers and Europrene (SOL T6302). SBS is considered a good choice to mix with concrete as it exhibits elastic behavior at ambient temperatures and can be treated similarly to plastic at higher temperatures (thermoplastic elastomer). SBS and other thermoplastics can be stored as rubbers and easily molded

into useful objects [3]. In [4], the deformation of rubberized asphalt blended with repeated load conditions was simulated, concluding that adding rubber crumbs to the asphalt mixture can reduce its rut depth by 55%. An experimental analysis was carried out in [5] to improve the mechanical properties of asphalt binders by mixing chemical WMA additives with nano clays, showing that the addition of these modifiers can postpone the aging of asphalt binders. In [6], the free surface energy method was used to examine the impact of additives on asphalt mixtures. The proposed method was validated and can be used accurately to quantify the influence of additives on the asphalt mixtures. Adhesion promoters were used in [7] to reduce moisture-related pavement degradation such as cracking and raveling, and to strengthen the bond between asphalt and

aggregates. The performance, structural stability, damage growth, and durability of asphalt pavement are strongly affected by the adhesive bonding between the modified asphalt binder and the aggregates. Furthermore, the interaction between the bitumen and the aggregates can be improved, but the performance of binders in bituminous mixtures is not impaired, as shown in [8].

The cracking resistance and the long-term deformations of modified asphalt mixtures can be assessed using several tests and methodologies. This study aimed to investigate the physical and mechanical properties of asphalt binders after blending them with a certain number of chemical additives and examining how this process can improve compatibility. The geological properties of conventional and modified binders and the properties of the asphalt concrete mixture were evaluated using different tests to determine how to improve the quality of the binder and the asphalt concrete mixture. Furthermore, the different ratio percentages of the additives were compared to choose the best ratio and kind of additives. The findings of this study will benefit the road and pavement industry.

II. EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND FRACTIONS

A. Bitumen

This study used conventional bitumen (AC 40/60) with 0.1mm penetration and two types of modified bitumen: Kraton styrene block copolymers (KRA 40/60) and Europrene SOL T 6302 (EUR 40/60). Both types were mixed with the conventional bitumen and were chosen as a sample of the asphalt binder. The conventional binder type 40-60 was initially assessed using the following tests: Penetration, Ductility (PD), Rolling Thin-Film Oven (RTFO) test, and softening point test. The aim of the chosen bitumen 40-60 was to confirm these chemical additives under evaluation. The bitumen was analyzed to understand its mechanical behavior and adaptability. The modified bitumens by KRA 40/60 and EUR 40/60 were tested by: RTFOT, Pressure Aging Vessel (PAV) test, Dynamic Shear Rheometer (DSR) test, Bending Beam Rheometer (BBR) test, and direct tension test (Recovery). Table I shows the results of these tests.

B. Additives

Kraton SBS (KRA 40/60) and Europrene SOL T 6302 (EUR 40/60) were used as additives, as shown in Figure 1. These additives work at the point where aggregates and bitumen meet, reduce internal friction forces, and ensure that the mixtures are more workable and compatible at lower temperatures [9]. The characteristics of both additives were examined at various percentages (3.5%, 4.0%, and 4.5%) of the binder weight. These additives are classified as thermoplastic elastomers, a type of substance that is similar to plastic but functions more like rubber. These additives were added to the binder. Kraton SBS copolymers act as a surface-active agent that can increase manufacturing temperatures by approximately 180°C, which is required during melting with bitumen AC 40/60 in solid form with a density ranging from 0.864 to 0.878gr/cm³ at a temperature of 56°C and a flashpoint of 198°C. This additive was considered a helper to avoid strong adhesion between aggregates in [9-10], acting as a lubricant during the mixing, laying, and compacting processes.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL TEST RESULTS FOR UNMODIFIED AND MODIFIED BITUMEN

Properties	AC 40/60	Modified Bitumen					
		Kraton KRA 40/60			Europrene EUR40/60		
		3.5%	4%	4.5%	3.5%	4%	4.5%
Pen at 25 ^o C- ASTM D5-13 (1/10mm) (%)	41.8	31.2	27.2	25	34	32.6	30.3
Softening point- ASTM D36-09 (°C)	52.5	62.3	65.9	67.2	63	69.2	70.9
Bitumen ductility - ASTM D113 (cm)	160	58	35	30	56	34	32
Penetration after heating- ASTM D1754-04 (%)	63.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ductility after heating- ASTM D1754-04 (cm)	91	-	-	-	-	-	-
RTFO test (gm)	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-
Resistance of hardening under the influence; Change in weight (Δ Mass %) of heat and air (RTFO test) -ASTM D1754-04		-0.28	-0.3	0.33	0.33	-0.3	-0.285

Kraton

Europrene SOL T6302

Fig. 1. Chemical additive materials.

The chosen chemical additives do not affect the properties of bitumen [11] and do not contract its viscosity [12]. Several tests were conducted to study the performance of hot mixes with these additives, including dynamic modulus, tensile strength, fatigue, flow, and rutting. The addition of KRA 40/60 reduced the aging of the mixture, increased rutting depth without eliminating it at a flash point of 198°C and density of approximately 0.875g/cm³ [13]. According to [14], this ingredient acts as a lubricant during mixing and compacting operations to prevent strong adhesion between the aggregates. The performance of the hot bituminous mixture including KRA 40/60 was evaluated and compared with the standard additive stated in [15]. This additive was tested for rutting resistance, fatigue life, and moisture sensitivity, showing that hot bituminous mixes performed similarly, and occasionally even better, in terms of fatigue resistance [16]. The EUR 40/60 is a surfactant agent with active adhesion-promoting qualities, has an antioxidant impact, and is capable of lowering manufacturing and compaction temperatures.

C. Mineral Aggregates

Mineral aggregates were examined according to the ASTM C136-06 using: Los Angeles test, sieve analysis of fine and coarse aggregates, and specific gravity and absorption of coarse or fine aggregate. Three different sizes of coarse aggregates,

25, 19, and 12.5mm, were used in this study. The coarse aggregate fractions according to the mentioned nominal sizes were 10, 17, and 27%, respectively, and the crushed aggregate percentage reached 88.3, 94.0, and 96.7%. In addition, the coarse aggregates were mixed with 42% crushed sand and 4% filler. The specific gravity of the three different sizes of coarse aggregates was 2.656, 2.660, and 2.674, and the specific gravity of the crushed sand and the filler was 2.618 and 2.710, respectively, following ASTM C127-12 and C128-12.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Characterization of Binders

The following tests were used to evaluate the properties of the binders: needle penetration at 25°C by ASTM D5-13, ductility test by ASTM D113-07, softening point (ring and ball method) by ASTM D36-09, resistance to hardening by ASTM D1754-04, PAV dynamic test by ASTM D6373/ASTM D8239, DSR by ASTM D7175, BBR by ASTM D6648, direct tension test elastic recovery of modified bitumen by ASTM D6084, and storage stability by ASTM D6927-06.

The collected data were translated into kinematic viscosity measurements using a rotational viscometer approach [17] on conventional and modified bitumen additives with 1.035 and 1.043Kg/m³ density, respectively. The test samples were prepared using ASTM D7175 and heated at 175°C for both KRA 40/60 and EUR 40/60 additives. Homogenization was carried out using a glass rod and manually stirring for 2 or 3 minutes after the melting process was finished, which could take up to 4 hours. Finally, the samples were transferred to containers in homogenous liquid form. The experimental protocol was used to determine whether the additives affect the properties of the binders, and the tests were completed quickly to avoid heating-cooling cycles and bitumen aging. Table II shows the test results.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL TEST RESULTS FOR MODIFIED BITUMEN

#	Properties	Modified bitumen					
		Kraton KRA 40/60			Europrene EUR40/60		
		3.5%	4%	4.5%	3.5%	4%	4.5%
1	Viscosity (135C°) - ASTM D4402; (CP; Max 3000 CP).	1938	2365	2401	2005	2138	2625
2	Direct tension (Recovery) ASTM D6084 (%).	77	83.5	85	74	78.5	79.5
3	DSR (G*/sinδ) ASTM D7175 (KPa) at 82°C at 88°C	1.22	1.93	2.1	1.22	1.88	1.97
		0.66	0.80	0.95	0.82	0.87	0.88
4	RTFOT (change in weight) (%) ASTM -D1754-04	-0.28	-0.3	0.33	0.33	-0.31	-0.28
5	DSR (G*/sinδ) ASTM D7175 (KPa) at 82°C at 88°C	3.45	3.81	4.5	2.7	3.36	3.97
		1.69	1.69	2.3	1.7	1.75	1.85
6	DSR (G*/sinδ) ASTM D7175 (KPa) at 40°C	993	980.9	1000	1380	1500	1372
7	BBR test - ASTM D6648 Stiffness(MPa) at 0°C M-Value	63.7	76.9	82	62	64.7	60.8
		0.33	0.31	0.29	0.35	0.344	1.85

B. Mixture Characterization

KRA 40/60 and EUR 40/60 additives were selected to create a bituminous mixture at lower temperatures to confirm their impact. Three additive percentages, i.e. 3.5, 4.0, and 4.5%, were mixed with AC 40/60 bitumen, as shown in Figure 2, and were evaluated using: theoretical maximum specific gravity by ASTM D2041-11, bulk specific gravity by ASTM D2726-11, and Marshall test by ASTM D6927-06.

Fig. 2. Marshall specimens for three different additive percentages.

This study examined the modulus of asphalt concrete which is utilized in the base and intermediate course of road pavements. The bituminous mixture was created using limestone aggregates and an AC 40/60 conventional bitumen at 0.1mm, as shown in Table III.

TABLE III. VALUES OF UNMODIFIED AND MODIFIED ASPHALT CONCRETE MIXTURE

#	Properties	Unmodified	Modified	
		Ref. AC 40/60	Kraton KRA40/60	Europrene EUR40/60
1	Theoretical maximum specific gravity - ASTM D 2041 -11 (Gmm)	2.512	2.512	2.494
2	Bulk specific gravity (Gmb)- ASTM D2726-11 (Gmb)	2.409	2.395	2.394
3	Marshall test ASTM D6927-06 Optimum asphalt content Pb (%) Air Void (%)	4.45	4.6	4.6
		4	4	4
4	Voids in mineral aggregate VMA (%) Void filled with asphalt VFA (%)	13.05	13.75	13.65
		68	70	72
5	Stability (N) Flow (0.25mm)	17600	23900	24000
		11	11.4	11.2
6	Tensile Strength Ratio (TSR) (%)	85.76	90.75	90.3

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the characterization results of unmodified and modified bitumen with various percentages of KRA 40/60 and EUR 40/60.

A. Using Standard Bitumen

As seen in Table I, the vast majority of the test results were within the limits, satisfying the requirements for bitumen certification. The penetration was less than 50%, the ductility was more than 100cm, and the softening point was less than 55°C. After the penetration was raised to more than 60%, ductility decreased to less than 100cm (ASTM D1754-04).

B. Using KRA 40/60 with Asphalt

Bitumen samples were tested with additive percentages of 3.5, 4.0, and 4.5%. Only AC 40/60 bitumen samples were used

and mixed with asphalt for 180 minutes. The mixture sample was put in the oven for 8 hours at 180°C. Table I shows the results from using the needle penetration and the softening point of all the examined samples. The results show that when the percentage of additives increased, the ductility and penetration of the samples decreased slightly and the softening point slightly increased. The elastic recovery percentage of the samples increased as the additive percentage increased. Table II shows that the viscosity at 135°C increased at the same additive percentages, and Table III shows that the storage stability increased as the percentage of additives increased. This test is important to predict how bitumen will behave after storage and transportation. Finally, the results showed that the additive was still homogenous.

C. Using EUR 40/60 with Asphalt

These samples were also tested at various additive percentages of 3.5, 4.0, and 4.5% after 180 minutes of mixing and 8 hours in the oven at 180°C. Table I shows that penetration decreased slightly and softening point increased when the additive percentage increased. The elastic recovery percentage increased as the additive percentage increased. The risk of polymer compaction during the dynamic viscosity test is high because the normal stability significantly affects the viscosity of the additive. All percentages of additives increased in the RTFO test in terms of penetration and softening point. As the samples were as original bitumen, they cracked before reaching 100mm of extension elastic recovery. The viscosity of the reference AC 40/60 is more affected by the examined samples of EUR 40/60. Figure 3 shows the direct tension test used.

Fig. 3. Marshall specimens for three different additive percentages.

V. RESULT ANALYSIS

The penetration of the specimens with EUR 40/60 showed a significant influence over those with KRA 40/60, and both decreased as the proportion of additives increased. The softening point for both additives increased as their percentage increased, but samples with EUR 40/60 increased more than those with KRA 40/60. The complex shear modulus G^* can be considered the sample's total resistance to deformation when repeatedly sheared. The phase angle δ is the gap between the applied shear stress and the resulting shear strain. An asphalt binder appears stiffer to sustain rutting; therefore, $G^*/\sin\delta$ showed a higher complex shear modulus elastic part. The stiffer the asphalt binder is, the greater the G^* is. To evaluate the rutting of the two additives compared to the standard bitumen, the values of $G^*/\sin\delta$ of fresh asphalt were recorded as greater than or equal to 1.0KPa. For the RTFO test residue, the stated values of $G^*/\sin\delta$ were greater than or equal to 2.2KPa. The lower value of δ lied to the greater elastic portion

of G^* . Figure 4 shows the relations of the elastic part of the shear complex modulus. For the KRA 40/60 at 82°C, the shear complex modulus increased more than for EUR 40/60 with increasing additive percentage and pressure to more than 1KPa. The curve graph of KRA 40/60 raised less than EUR 40/60 when pressure was less than 1.0KPa at 88°C.

Fig. 4. Variations of complex shear modulus elastic portion with chemical additive percentage.

The shear complex modulus of KAR 40/60 gradually increased with increasing the additive percentage, as shown in Figure 5. At 82°C, the KRA 40/60 results were higher than those of EUR 40/60 and more than 2.2KPa. In other words, the graph line of the shear complex modulus of KRA 40/60 gradually raised with increasing its percentage. At 88°C, the shear complex modulus of KRA 40/60 for 3.5 and 4% was less than 2.2Kpa and EUR 40/60. An asphalt binder became elastic while it is still reasonably flexible to withstand fatigue cracking.

Fig. 5. Variations of complex shear modulus elastic portion with chemical additive percentage after changing weight percent.

The values of $G^* \times \sin\delta$ of the complex shear modulus viscous part were at lower values. The maximum value of the viscous component of the complex shear modulus is used when fatigue cracking is most concerning. Figure 6 shows that the $G^* \times \sin\delta$ value was less than or equal to 5000KPa when evaluating the fatigue distress of typical pavement temperature in the field and the lab at a temperature of 40°C. The fatigue

behavior of KRA 40/60 was lower than that of EUR 40/60, and both gradually increased with increasing additive percentages. The complex shear modulus of 4% EUR 40/60 decreased, as shown in Table II.

Fig. 6. Variations of complex shear modulus viscous portion with chemical additives percentage.

Fig. 7. Variations of air voids with asphalt content percentage.

Fig. 8. Variations of stability with asphalt content percentage.

Creep stiffness was computed based on the recorded deflection and the standard beam characteristics. The creep stiffness values observed were less than or equal to 300MPa, and the changing rate of stiffness (*M*-value) was more than or equal to 0.3. The direct tension test was performed to determine compliance with the Performance Grade (PG) standards for asphalt cement if the maximum stiffness is between 300 and

600MPa and the changing stiffness rate is greater than 0.30. The EUR 40/60 samples increased to 4% of additive and then started to decrease. The creep stiffness values of KRA 40/60 samples were greater than those of EUR 40/60. The creep stiffness of both additives was less than 300MPa. The changing rate of the stiffness additives was greater than 0.30, and the *M*-value of the KRA 40/60 samples was lower than that of the EUR 40/60, as shown in Table II. Comparing KRA 40/60 with AC 40/60, its values of variation air voids with the percentage of asphalt content were larger.

Fig. 9. Variations of percent voids filled with asphalt content.

Fig. 10. Variations of unit weight with asphalt content.

The crack propagation of asphalt is rutting at high temperatures, fatigue cracking at intermeddle temperatures, and thermal cracking at low temperatures. According to Figure 7, all curves of air voids decreased as the proportion of asphalt content increased. Figure 8 compares the percentage values of asphalt of the reference bitumen AC 40/60 to the variance stability of the two other additives. As shown in Figure 8, the flow value (0.25mm) of the additives is higher than the reference bitumen AC 40/60. Figure 9 shows that the variance Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA) rise at increasing values of asphalt percentages, and when this result is compared to the AC 40/60, as shown in Figure 10, that significantly raises the weight of both additive types.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the outcomes of this study, the tensile strength ratio of modified asphalt with two types of chemical additives

KRA 40/60 and EUR 40/60 showed better properties compared to unmodified asphalt with AC 40/60 bitumen. Adding 4.0% of chemical additives to the AC 40/60, increased its stiffness in parallel with the penetration index and reduced the brittleness of the binder and its temperature sensitivity. This improves rutting resistance, thermal cracking resistance, and resistance to moisture damage. The best additive concentration was observed at 4% additive, which led to less penetration and ductility, and an increased softening point. The penetration of bitumen was 41.8% without additives, reduced to 27.2% with adding KRA 40/60 and 30.3% EUR 40/60, as shown in Table I. The degree of softening increased in both additives, at 65.9°C for Kraton and 70.9 °C for Europrene SOL T6302, compared to 52.5°C for the AC 40/60. Adding 4.0% of additives increased the asphalt content to 4.6% and decreased bulk specific gravity to 2.395. The maximum specific gravity of Eurprene SOL T6302 decreased to 2.494Kg/m³, while it was not affected for Kraton. Air voids remained unchanged by adding additives while stability increased.

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Differential Gene Expression Analysis of Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer Samples to Classify Candidate Genes

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ABSTRACT

Differential gene expression is an analysis of gene data, in which the RNA sequence data after next-generation sequencing are to be visualized for any quantitative changes in the levels of the experimental data set. This work aims to derive the transcript statistics on a gene transcript file with a fold change of genes on a normalized scale, in order to identify quantitative changes in gene expression of the difference between the reference genome and Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) samples. This insight makes a clinical impact in assessing and characterizing candidate genes. The pipeline comprises tuxedo protocol and programming language R with the standard ballgown package. The resultant data set and the plot displays depict the candidate genes in their respective location which are significant in expressing their changes in NSCLC samples. The samples are compared with prominent gene labels of NSCLC samples. The results explain the differential expression of particular samples across samples from both genders.

Keywords-differential gene expression; next-generation sequencing; RNA sequence; machine learning; non-small cell lung cancer; classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is the leading type of cancer worldwide. About 1.76 million deaths were caused by lung cancer during 2019. The disease is caused by lung malignancies. There are a lot of advances in lung cancer therapies, but, despite the advancement the prognosis of the disease is unfavourable [1], because after the diagnosis the survival rate is less than 15% for the next five years. The understanding of molecular characteristics leading to identifying cancer will speed up the diagnosis. Cancer is one of the most challenging diseases [2]. The recent advancement of next-generation sequencing of the human gene has created opportunities to use gene expression information for decision making [3]. Lung cancer can be categorised into NSCLC, which are about the 85% of the cases, and as small cell lung cancer. The study of molecular signature shows that carcinogenesis is caused by oncogenic drivers. This has led the research to oncogenic driver identification rather than clinical parameter studies [4]. The most common types of NSCLC are squamous cell carcinoma, large-cell carcinoma, and

adenocarcinoma, with several other types occurring less frequently. All types can occur in unusual histologic variants and as mixed cell-type combinations [5]. The lack of early detection of NSCLC leads to an increased mortality rate, specifically in developing countries. Cancer is globally considered as a leading cause of death [6]. It was reported that 1 in 6 deaths in 2018 happened due to cancer. The lung cancer accounts for about 2.09 million cases worldwide. In India, about 70 thousand cases of lung cancer are reported every year [7]. Depending on the stage of cancer, the general condition of the person, age, reaction to chemotherapy, and other considerations, such as the possible side effects of the procedure, more than one methods of treatment are used. Usually, NSCLC patients are categorized as patients with early, non-metastatic disease (stages I and II, and pick type III tumors) and patients with locally advanced thoracic cavity-bound disease (e.g. large tumors). Several facets of cancer science are now being reshaped by the many implementations and uses of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technologies. As a result of aberrant mutagenesis and its contribution to

carcinogenesis, these technologies have enabled researchers to explain improvements in any degree of regulation carried out in a cell [8].

Usage of RNA sequencing to understand and characterize the genes involved in cancer diagnostics and therapy has become a well-used tool. The reduced cost of sequencing and its advantages over microarrays have made it accessible to everyone, which is improving the time taken to detect and treat cancer patients. RNA sequencing provides a view of the transcriptome of gene incomprehensive structure [9]. It is not dependent on any prior sequence knowledge and it can detect structural variations such as alternative splicing events and gene fusion, but the data storage and the analysis are more complex and it does not use any standard protocol, while it is also an expensive process. The most significant factor in NSCLC is that its identification is delayed, causing NSCLCs to have the lowest survival rate. Researchers have concluded that faster diagnosis happens by understanding gene expression at a molecular level, as gene sequence expression plays a very significant role in NSCLCs [10]. As the latest NGS sequencing provides us with a comprehensive genome structure with high throughput, identifying the candidate genes by analyzing the RNA sequence data set allows focusing on those sets of genes. The candidate genes mark a subset of biomarkers [11] or

signatures of this biological condition. The present study aims to analyze and map the significant mutations in the genes responsible for NSCLC, something that might help biomarker identification, leading to early detection and helping adjuvant therapies in personalised medicine which increases survival rate. The DNA analysis at nucleotide level is a new research area [12], and the research on the identification of biomarkers not only supports the medication treatment, but also predicts the proteins which create and activate post gene expression [13].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Datasets

This work is based on real biological samples' data, the dataset is available on the Sequence Read Archive database maintained by the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). Data from the project SRP117020 were selected for analyzing representative samples on both genders with age bigger than 50 years. The data consisted of RNA sequences with the distribution of poor to well-differentiated adenocarcinomas and squamous cell cancers which were sequenced using Illumina Hiseq2500 [14]. The details of the sequence run according to the accession number are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. DETAILS ABOUT SEQUENCE ARCHIVE RUN (SRR) ACCESSION, WITH ACTUAL SEQUENCING DATA FROM THE PARTICULAR SEQUENCING EXPERIMENT [15]

Run	Average spot length	Bases – giga basepairs	Size	Histology	Date published	Access type	Gender (age > 50 years)
SRR6013475	199	6.3Gbp	3.86Gb	Squamous cell carcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Male
SRR6013476	199	6.16Gbp	3.84Gb	Squamous cell carcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Male
SRR6013477	199	5.46Gbp	3.33Gb	Adenocarcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Male
SRR6013479	199	6.00Gbp	3.65Gb	Adenocarcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Male
SRR6013492	199	5.56Gbp	3.38Gb	Adenocarcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Female
SRR6013502	199	6.82Gbp	4.20Gb	Adenocarcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Female
SRR6013508	199	5.56Gbp	3.45Gb	Adenocarcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Female
SRR6013509	197	7.97Gbp	4.86Gb	Adenocarcinoma	2018-08-03	Public	Female

B. Data Analysis

The analysis of the dataset was carried out by raw sequencing data in fastq format. The reference genome was obtained from the assembly resources of the NCBI.

1) Quality Check

The quality of the RNAseq reads was validated with the FastQC software [16].

2) Read Alignment and Assembly of Transcripts

RNA-seq reads were aligned to the human reference genome using a fast and sensitive alignment programme called HISAT2 [17]. The visual exploration and differences in the expressions were obtained using the Ballgown R package. The experiment is carried out using a standard protocol of tuxedo suite tools which is useful in the analysis of RNA-seq data. The protocol is described by different processes which are more convenient in analyzing raw sequences [18] of large data. The detailed flow chart of the processes is depicted in Figure 1. The hardware environment utilized to run the tuxedo protocol was a 64-bit computer run in Linux environment with 8Gb RAM.

3) Differential Gene Expression and Pathway Analysis

The transcripts and expression levels obtained from Stringtie were subjected to the differentially expressed genes which were performed using the Ballgown package [18]. The package uses statistical methods to get the differentially expressed genes. The obtained list of all the differentially expressed genes was subjected to pathway and gene ontology analysis. This was carried out using KOBAS 3.0 annotation module [19]. The annotation module accepts gene sequences in FASTA format or Gene ID as input and presently covers 5944 different species to run the annotations.

4) Enrichment Analysis

From the pathway analysis results, only genes involved in NSCLC disease pathway were taken and functional enrichment analysis was performed using KOBAS 3.0 enrichment module [19]. Enrichment gives gene ontologies that are significant statistically. This gives an output based on the hypergeometric distribution.

5) Obtaining the Candidate Genes

To obtain the main candidate genes responsible for NSCLC, the mutations responsible for NSCLC were obtained using the ClinVar database [20]. The genes involved in mutations were taken into account and their corresponding expression values obtained from the ballgown package were evaluated to shortlist the candidate genes.

Fig. 1. The protocol to produce tables and plots and obtain differentially expressed genes.

III. RESULTS

A. Data Analysis

The experimental data were analyzed as shown in Table II.

1) Quality Check

Analysis of the raw reads in FastQC format gave a quick impression of the dataset with various features including sequence quality, GC content, N content, and statistics. A brief overview of the obtained results is shown in Table II.

2) Read Alignment and Assembly of Transcripts

Read alignment of the reference genome is a very important step. When the alignment does not occur properly, transcriptome reconstruction becomes difficult, especially for

genes expressed at lower levels. The alignment of the reads to the human reference genome gave SAM files whose alignment rates were above 70% which were later converted to BAM, which is the compressed binary version of SAM, files. When the alignment files were subjected to transcriptome reconstruction using StringTie, annotation files were obtained with all the expression levels of all genes and transcripts.

3) Differential Expression and Pathway Analysis

The relevant packages under Ballgown were loaded, and the phenotype data were loaded in .csv format which contained sample ID and gender of the sample. Ballgown gives two tables with differentially expressed genes and transcripts between genders, giving 3 types of values. One, the fold change value referring to the ratio between expression levels in male and female. The values that are <1 indicate that it is expressed at a lower level and values >1 indicate that it is expressed at a higher level. Second, the p-value to get the idea of spotting data if no difference existed. Third, the q-value which is the adjusted p-value obtained by applying the false discovery rate. The gene abundance, measured in terms of FPKM (fragments per kilobase of the model per million reads mapped) distribution across all samples is visualised in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Distribution of FPKM values across 8 samples.

TABLE II. OVERVIEW OF THE FASTQC RESULTS [15]

	SRR6013475	SRR6013476	SRR6013477	SRR6013479	SRR6013492	SRR6013502	SRR6013509	SRR6013508
Basic stats (total sequences)	3,15,05,786	3,08,90,798	2,74,86,767	3,00,87,832	2,79,04,343	3,42,10,392	4,02,79,600	2,78,67,756
Per base sequence quality average score for all bases	32-40	34-40	32-40	34-40	34-40	34-40	34-40	34-39
Sequence quality score (Phred mean)	Ave 2-32	Ave 2-30	Ave 2-32	Ave 2-30	Ave 2-30	Ave 2-30	Ave 2-28	Ave 2-28
Sequence GC content	46	48	47	45	44	45	43	45
Base N content	0-2	Nil						

The y-axis shows the log2 transformation of FPKM and the x-axis shows the accession numbers of the data. Additionally, structure and expression levels of isoforms of KRAS were obtained from Ballgown which is shown in Figures 3-4. The KRAS gene belongs to a set of genes known as oncogenes. When mutated, normal cells with these oncogenes have the potential to cause cancer [21]. Figure 3 shows the structure and isoforms of the KRAS gene in sample SRR6013502. The expression levels are shown in varying colors (from yellow to red). The isoform expressed in a higher level is shown in a darker shade. The x-axis indicates the genomic position of the KRAS gene. Figure 4 describes the expressions and structure comparison of KRAS gene in male and female samples. The y-axis indicates the genomic position. The darker color indicates higher expression level which means the KRAS gene is expressed at a higher rate in females than in males. When all the differentially expressed genes were subjected to pathway analysis setting the organism as homo sapiens and the method as gene symbol ID mapping, a total of 5071 genes in different pathways were involved. The results showed different sections of output for a particular gene: the pathways the gene was involved in, the diseases the genes were involved in, and the gene ontology indicating the biological functions the genes were related to.

Fig. 3. Structure and expression level of KRAS gene in SRR6013502.

4) Enrichment Analysis

Out of the 5702 hits from the pathway analysis, the genes specifically related to NSCLC were chosen and were again

subjected to pathway analysis to see the commonality between breast cancer and small-cell lung cancer. The complete pathway analysis of these genes is provided as a supplementary document. The genes involved in NSCLC and their involvement in breast and small cell lung cancer are shown in Table III.

Fig. 4. The structure and expression of KRAS in male and female samples.

The genes responsible for NSCLC and their involvement in breast cancer and SCLC are indicated in Figure 5 and Table III. Figure 5 indicates that 20% of the genes are involved in both NSCLC and breast cancer, 22% are involved in NSCLC and SCLC, and 58% are involved only in NSCLC. The genes given in Table III were subjected to enrichment analysis. The detailed table of the functional enrichment is computed in the functional enrichment of the genes involved in NSCLC.

The enrichment analysis and the corrected p-values are conducted using a hypergeometric distribution which is used for over-representation analysis of genes. The barplot representation of functional enrichment is shown in Figure 6. Each row represents an enriched function, and the length of the bar represents the enrichment ratio, which is calculated as input gene number/background gene number. The indicated color codes are based on the module number which has been assigned based on the enrichment ratio. The functional annotation with the same module number is grouped and indicated by the same color.

Fig. 5. Pie chart for genes involved in different cancers.

TABLE III. GENES INVOLVED IN NSCLC AND THEIR COMMONALITY WITH BREAST CANCER AND SCLC. THE HIGHLIGHTED GENES ARE THE ONES INVOLVED ONLY IN NSCLC

GENE name	Disease1	Disease2	Disease3
ABCC4	Breast Cancer	NSCLC	
AGER		NSCLC	
AKT1	Breast Cancer	NSCLC	
AKT2		NSCLC	
ARAF	Breast Cancer	NSCLC	
BAD		NSCLC	
BAK1		NSCLC	SCLC
BAX		NSCLC	SCLC
BRAF		NSCLC	SCLC
CASP9		NSCLC	SCLC
CCND1		NSCLC	SCLC
CDK4		NSCLC	SCLC
CDK6		NSCLC	SCLC
CDKN1A		NSCLC	SCLC
DCBLD1		NSCLC	SCLC
DDB2		NSCLC	SCLC
DLST		NSCLC	SCLC
E2F3		NSCLC	SCLC
EGFR	Breast cancer	NSCLC	SCLC
EIF4E2		NSCLC	SCLC
EML4	Breast cancer	NSCLC	SCLC
ERBB2	Breast cancer	NSCLC	SCLC
ETS2	Breast cancer	NSCLC	SCLC
FHIT		NSCLC	SCLC
FOXO3		NSCLC	SCLC
KRAS		NSCLC	SCLC
MAP2K1		NSCLC	SCLC
NRAS		NSCLC	SCLC
GADD45A		NSCLC	SCLC

The circular enrich network of the functional annotation is shown in Figure 7. Each node represents an enriched term, and the edges represent the connections between two enriched terms that have a gene-overlapped ratio more than a specific cut-off (default > 0.5). Different modules in different colors represent nodes belonging to specific topologic communities in a structured network, which were defined using the Infomap algorithm. The network is in a circular layout according to the gravity of the two nodes. The color of the bar in the bar plot is the same as the color in the circular network, which represents different modules and their interactions [19].

5) Obtaining the Candidate Genes

The results obtained from ClinVar database considered only single nucleotide polymorphisms and the corresponding expression analysis from Ballgown. It is seen that the genes BRAF, NRAS, KRAS, EGFR, and MAP2K1, involved in multiple mutations, are computed in the single nucleotide polymorphisms involved in NSCLC, which gives a vast idea about the SNPs. Table III provides detailed information about the nucleotide change and the corresponding amino acid change, chromosome number and the position in the human genome (GRCh38). The expression values of genes involved in mutations are highlighted in Table IV.

TABLE IV. GENES INVOLVED IN MULTIPLE SNPS (AMINO ACID CHANGES)

Gene	Fold change	p-value	q-value
BRAF	0.8108669	0.5386988	0.9979959
MAP2K1	1.004441	0.9728909	0.9993876
KRAS	0.7801372	0.2109766	0.9979959
EGFR	0.4406753	0.1661845	0.9979959
NRAS	1.0061834	0.9705951	0.9993876

Fig. 6. Barplot representation of functional enrichment.

Fig. 7. Circular enrichment network.

IV. DISCUSSION

The epidermal growth factor receptor was the first oncogenic target uncovered in NSCLC (EGFR). 40% of Asian patients have EGFR mutations, compared to 11-17% of Caucasian patients. Almost all EGFR mutations involve exons 18 to 21. Around 40-50% of EGFR mutations are represented by small in-frame deletions in exon 19 (del 19), whereas p.Leu858Arg amino acid substitutions in exon 21 account for 30-40% [22]. BRAF mutations are found in 2%-8% of people with NSCLC. The BRAF exon 15 p.Val600Glu activating mutation is the cause of 50% of all BRAF mutations. Additional mutations are discovered in exons 11 and 15 and are classified as either triggering (p.Gly469X, p.Leu597Arg, or p.Lys601Glu) or faulty (p.Gly466Val, p.Asp594X, p.Gly596Cys). As predicted by melanoma results [23], single BRAF inhibitors (i.e. vemurafenib or dabrafenib) elicit cell cycle arrest and death in p.Val600Glu-mutated-NSCLC. KRAS-activating mutations are detected in around 30% of the cancer population and are being employed as an exclusion biomarker. In smokers, KRAS-mutated tumours are more prevalent and host other drug-related drivers less frequently. The precise type of KRAS mutation may provide information regarding the aggressiveness of a disease or its sensitivity to certain drugs [24]. For instance, the G12D mutation in NSCLC has been linked to a more favourable prognosis than the G12V or G12R variants [25]. MAP2K1 mutations are infrequent in NSCLC and are assumed to be mutually exclusive with known driver mutations. MEK1 cascade activation is believed to play a major role in the resistance to selective treatment regimens, and the MAP2K1 K57 N mutation has been associated with resistance in preclinical animals [26]. The fold change value for MAP2K1 and NRAS is greater than 1, indicating that these two genes are much more expressed than BRAF, KRAS, and EGFR. BRAF and KRAS are also expressed with values close to 1, although EGFR has a relatively low expression value. PIK3CA, ROS1, and FGFR1 are additional prevalent genes whose mutations are associated with NSCLC, with PIK3CA and FGFR1 being much more expressed than ROS1.

The functional enrichment employed in the research focuses on a novel classification strategy for biomarker genes across 3 major illnesses, such as breast cancer, NSCLC, and SCLC.

V. CONCLUSION

The differential gene expression of the human genome (GRCh38) identifies the most frequently mutated genes as candidates. Mutated genes BRAF, NRAS, KRAS, EGFR, MAP2K1, PIK3CA, MET, ROS1, and FGFR1 were found to be expressed more in the selected data of lung adenoma cancer patients. The knowledge gained from genomic profiling can be utilized to clinically correlate and target medicine for diseases caused by genomic abnormalities. By examining the gene mapping for the specific activity, it is possible to classify these medicines as tumour suppressors or chemotherapy resistant.

To comprehend and categorize the common genes associated with breast cancer and other malignancies, the employed enrichment technique has identified mutant genes as candidates. After a comprehensive validation of mutant genes, potential genes were identified. The discovery of a drug's interactions is prompted by a process of validation that must be carried out to match clinical therapy. The process of chemotherapy and tumor suppression can be revisited with a decreased dose to make the therapies less hazardous.

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Wind Power Potential Assessment at Different Locations in Lebanon: Best-Fit Probability Distribution Model and Techno-Economic Feasibility

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the current paper is to evaluate Lebanon's wind energy generation potential as an alternative solution to the electricity supply to households and to enhance sustainable technological development. Firstly, the paper aims to investigate the appropriateness of 44 distribution function models for the evaluation of wind speed characteristics and compared them with popular models at 12 locations in Lebanon for the first time. The results showed that Wakeby and Beta distribution functions gave the best fit to the actual data for most locations. Secondly, the techno-economic and environmental feasibility assessment for 10MW grid-connected wind farms was developed based on variations in financial parameters using RETScreen Experts software. The findings demonstrate that the proposed power plant is both technically and financially feasible. It was found that Ain ed Dabaa is the most viable location for the installation of a wind farm.

Keywords-Lebanon; distribution function; wind energy potential; grid-connected; RETScreen

I. INTRODUCTION

Wind energy has known increasing exploitation in power generation [1]. The use of wind as an energy source is imperative nowadays due to the lack of fossil fuel resources, particularly in developing countries like Lebanon. Wind energy is a clean, inexhaustible, and environmentally friendly energy source. The generation of electricity from wind energy will be an essential part of Lebanon's future development.

In general, analyzing wind speed characteristics is essential to assess the potential of wind energy in a given location. Probability Distribution Models (PDMs) are utilized to

describe wind speed observations [2]. Thus, finding the most suitable PDM is considered the first step for evaluating the wind power potential at a specific location. Two-parameter Weibull and Rayleigh distribution functions are the most used for modeling the wind speed at specific locations [2]. Many studies focus on analyzing wind characteristics using various distribution models. Authors in [3] utilized parametric models, mixture models, and one non-parametric model to evaluate the potential of wind energy in the United Arab Emirates. The results demonstrated that one-component parametric distributions provided the best fit to the wind speed data for all sites. Authors in [4] analyzed the distribution of wind speed in Northern Cyprus using 2-parameter Weibull (2p-W), Gamma

(G), Lognormal (Ln), Logistic (L), Log-Logistic (LL), Inverse Gaussian (IG), Generalized Extreme Value (GEV), Nakagami (Na), Normal (N), and Rayleigh (R) distribution functions. The authors found that GEV showed the best fit for most selected locations. Authors in [5] evaluated the wind energy potential at different locations in Pakistan using various distribution functions and GEV was identified as the best. Authors in [6] analyzed the wind speed characteristics of 5 locations in Iran using 8 PDMs. The authors concluded that Na and 2p-W gave the best fit to the actual data. Authors in [7] used 2p-W, G, and Inverse Gamma (IG) to study the characteristics of wind speed in Peninsular, Malaysia. G and 2p-W gave the best fit for the actual data. Authors in [8] utilized 37 distribution functions for evaluating the wind energy potential at the Güzelyurt region in Northern Cyprus. The authors concluded that Burr (4P), Wakeby, and GEV provided the best fit. Authors in [9] assessed the wind speed distribution at different locations in India using 9 PDMs. The results showed that GEV provided the best fit for the majority of the sites. Authors in [10] evaluated the wind energy potential at 17 locations in Sudan using 37 PDMs. The authors found that the Wakeby distribution function provided the best fit for the wind speed data for all locations. Authors in [11] studied the accuracy of several PDMs for modeling the wind speed distribution at different locations in Algeria. The results showed that the GEV and Gamma models were the most appropriate. Wais [12] studied the accuracy of 2p-W and 3-parameter Weibull (3p-W) in analyzing the wind speed characteristics at 3 locations in Poland. The author concluded that 3p-W gave a better fit to the wind speed data.

TABLE I. PREVIOUS STUDIES RELATED TO WIND ENERGY POTENTIAL IN LEBANON

Ref.	Location	PDMs used	Best
[13]	Klaiaat, Cedars, Daher El Baydar, Marjyoun, and Quaraoun	2p-W	-
[14]	Beirut, Sidon, and Tripoli	2p-W, G, Ln, L, LL, IG, GEV, Na, N and R	LL
[15]	Klaiaat, Les Cedres, Daher El Baydar, Quaraoun, and Marjyoun	2p-W	-
[16]	Rayak	2p-W	-
[17]	Beirut, Zahleh, Sour, and El-Abdeh	R	-
[18]	Beirut, Sidon, and Tripoli	2p-W	-
[19]	Younine, Birket Aarous, Ain ed Dabaa, Mqaybleh, Ras Ouadi Ed Darje, Kfardebian, Qaraoun, Khartoum, Iskandarounah and Beirut	2p-W	-
[20]	Abboudiye, Tal ker, Darine, Heke El Dahri, Saadine, Semmaqiye, TalAbbas and Tal El Bireh	G, 3p- G, IG, 3p-IG, LL, 3p-LL, Ln, 3p-Ln, Na, 2p-W, 3p-W	3P-W and 3p-LL
[21]	Akkar, Baalbek, Beirut, Zahlé, Baabda, Nabatieh, Tripoli, and Sidon	2p-W	-
[22]	Qlariat, Ksara, Cedres, Dahr El Baydar, Marjayoun, Beirut, Khaldeh, Tripoli, Riq	2p-W	-

Numerous studies have evaluated the wind energy potential in Lebanon using various distribution models as shown in Table I. Based on the findings, the most used distribution function for analyzing the wind speed distribution is 2p-W. Moreover, wind energy has been widely utilized globally to generate electricity and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

Authors in [4] conducted a techno-economic analysis for the generation of power utilizing a small-scale vertical axis wind turbine in 8 locations in Northern Cyprus. Authors in [13] assessed and analyzed the electricity that 116 wind turbines in Lebanon might produce.

The number of studies related to the analysis of wind speed characteristics using various distribution functions is limited. Furthermore, as a continuation of our study on the statistical investigation of wind characteristics in Lebanon, the present paper aims to evaluate for the first time the best-fit distribution function to describe the wind speed data at 12 locations in Lebanon. To fulfill this objective, 44 distribution functions were used to model the wind speed characteristics at the selected locations. The parameters of these distribution functions were estimated using the maximum likelihood method. Additionally, 3 goodness-of-fit test statistics were applied to determine the best-fit PDFs. The present study was performed on power produced by a wind turbine at a maximum of 10MW that may be installed in Lebanon.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area and Data Collection

The wind speed characteristics of 12 locations in Lebanon should be fully understood in order to evaluate the wind power potential (Figure 1). Table II lists the geographical coordinate’s latitude, longitude, and elevation of the selected locations. The monthly wind speed data from 2010 to 2017 were collected from the meteorological service.

B. Probability distribution functions

In this study, 44 Probability Distribution Functions (PDFs) are utilized to represent the wind speed frequency distribution (Table III). The number of parameters for the selected PDFs is within the range of 1-4. The probability density functions of the selected PDFs can be found in [8-10, 23].

Fig. 1. Map showing the selected locations. © Mapa GISrael.

TABLE II. INFORMATION ON THE SELECTED LOCATIONS IN LEBANON

Location	Latitude [°N]	Longitude [°E]	Elevation [m]
Younine	34.0776	36.2750	1198
Birket Aarous	34.2911	36.1456	2766
Ain ed Dabaa	34.4431	35.8992	296
Mqaybleh	34.6460	36.3577	330
Ras Ouadi Ed Darje	34.2533	36.5775	1555
Kfardebian	34.0017	35.8349	1670
Qaraoun	33.5669	35.7193	913
Khartoum	33.4079	35.3751	305
Iskandarounah	33.1550	35.1685	53
Beirut	33.8938	35.5018	40
Khiam	33.3294	35.6148	697
Hekr El Dahri	34.6306	36.0237	10

C. Goodness-of-Fit Test

In this research, Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test is employed to select the best-fit DF. The description of these tests is given below [10].

$$D = \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} \left(F(x_i) - \frac{i-1}{n}, \frac{i}{n} - F(x_i) \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$F_n(x) = \frac{1}{n} \times (\text{Number of observations} \leq x) \quad (2)$$

TABLE III. SELECTED DF MODELS AND NUMBER OF PARAMETERS (NP)

Model No.	Model Name	NP	Model No.	Model Name	NP
DF#1	Beta	4	DF#23	Log-Gamma	2
DF#2	Burr	3	DF#24	Logistic	2
DF#3	Burr	4	DF#25	Log-Logistic	2
DF#4	Cauchy	2	DF#26	Log-Logistic	3
DF#5	Dagum	3	DF#27	Lognormal	2
DF#6	Dagum	4	DF#28	Lognormal	3
DF#7	Erlang	2	DF#29	Log-Pearson 3	2
DF#8	Erlang	3	DF#30	Nakagami	2
DF#9	Exponential	1	DF#31	Normal	2
DF#10	Exponential	2	DF#32	Pareto	2
DF#11	Gamma	2	DF#33	Pareto 2	2
DF#12	Gamma	3	DF#34	Pearson 5	2
DF#13	Generalized Extreme Value	3	DF#35	Pearson 5	3
DF#14	Generalized Gamma	3	DF#36	Pearson 6	3
DF#15	Generalized Gamma	4	DF#37	Pearson 6	4
DF#16	Generalized Logistic	3	DF#38	Pert	3
DF#17	Generalized Pareto	3	DF#39	Rayleigh	1
DF#18	Gumbel Max.	2	DF#40	Rayleigh	2
DF#19	Gumbel Min.	2	DF#41	Reciprocal	2
DF#20	Inverse Gaussian	2	DF#42	Wakeby	5
DF#21	Inverse Gaussian	3	DF#43	Weibull	2
DF#22	Kumaraswamy	4	DF#44	Weibull	3

D. RETScreen

A techno-economic assessment was made for the generation of electricity using 3 wind turbines with various specifications in the selected locations using RETScreen software. RETScreen Expert is a clean energy management tool developed by the Canadian government. It is a decision support tool that is utilized to determine the potential of energy,

costs, savings, greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction, and economic viability. The RETScreen utilizes the long-term monthly average meteorological data from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) database as a source of meteorological information for the specific location. Recently, RETScreen has been commonly employed to explore the feasibility of grid-connected wind and PV power systems. Capacity factor, annual power production, GHG reductions, and economic indicators are determined using RETScreen [10].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Description of Wind Speed Data at a Height of 10m

The descriptive statistics of each location are listed in Table IV. Moreover, the monthly variation of wind speed for all the selected locations is illustrated in Figure 2. It is found that the mean wind speed varied between 2.81m/s and 4.90m/s (Table IV). The values for mean speed and standard deviation (SD) indicate that the wind behavior is quite consistent. The coefficients of variation (CV), which range between 6.52 and 17.25%, are relatively low. The minimum and maximum values are recorded in Younine and Ain ed Dabaa, respectively. For the majority of the chosen locations, the skewness (S) values are negative, indicating that all distributions are left skewed. Additionally, the values of kurtosis (K) vary from -1.46 to -0.19, and they are also moderately low.

Fig. 2. Monthly average wind speed for the selected locations (2010-2017).

TABLE IV. DESCRIPTIVE WIND SPEED DATASET

Location	Mean	SD	CV	Min	Max	S	K
Younine	2.90	0.45	15.37	2.32	3.51	0.03	-1.46
Birket Aarous	3.01	0.31	10.14	2.44	3.45	-0.56	-0.26
Ain ed Dabaa	4.90	0.53	10.79	4.00	5.82	-0.15	-0.41
Mqaybleh	2.91	0.30	10.14	2.36	3.34	-0.56	-0.26
Ras Ouadi Ed Darje	3.19	0.45	14.05	2.54	4.03	0.52	-0.19
Kfardebian	3.48	0.41	11.66	3.04	4.22	0.82	-0.75
Qaraoun	2.86	0.19	6.52	2.51	3.08	-0.54	-0.81
Khartoum	2.81	0.18	6.52	2.47	3.03	-0.54	-0.81
Iskandarounah	3.32	0.57	17.25	2.72	4.27	0.42	-1.46
Beirut	3.48	0.41	11.66	3.04	4.22	0.82	-0.75
Khiam	2.81	0.18	6.52	2.47	3.03	-0.54	-0.81
Hekr El Dahri	2.91	0.30	10.14	2.36	3.34	-0.56	-0.26

B. Wind Resource Assessment at a Height of 10m

The deep assessment of wind resources using various wind speed probability functions at 12 locations in Lebanon is investigated in this paper. According to [24], selecting the best-

fit DF is an essential step in determining the average wind turbine power production. Therefore, the most suitable distribution that best fits the actual wind speed is assessed using the K-S test. Figure 3 shows the statistic value of K-S for all the selected distributions. It should be noted that the best fit to the wind speed has the lowest statistic value of K-S. Based on the K-S test (Figure 3 and Table V), Wakeby distribution has the lowest value, so it is considered the best distribution function to study the average monthly wind speed characteristics for Younine, Birket Aarous, Mqaybleh, and Hekr El Dahri. Moreover, Beta is among the distributions giving better fits to investigate the distribution of wind speed at Khiam, Iskandarounah, Khartoum, and Qaraoun. Gumbel Min and Gen. Logistic provide the best fit to wind speed at Ain ed Dabaa and Ras Ouadi Ed Darje, respectively. Additionally, to explore the distribution of the average monthly wind speed at Kfardebian and Beirut, 3p-Log-Logistic is one of the distributions offering the best fit for wind speed.

Fig. 3. Statistic and rank for various locations based on K-S value.

The essential characteristic of skewness (S), which is defined as the third central moment, measures asymmetry [11]. When the long tail is on the peak's negative (positive) side, there is a negative (positive) skew. Kurtosis (K) is a measure of tailedness, defined as the fourth central moment, if the data have higher [11]. A higher (lower) K value indicates that there

are more (fewer) extreme values or fatter tails (middles) on the data curve. Table V compares the S and K values calculated using the best DFs distributions. These values are compared with widely used DFs (Weibull, Rayleigh, and GEV) to show the efficacy of the selected DF models. Some PDF figures can be seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Statistic and rank for various locations based on K-S values.

C. Wind Power Density (WPD) Calculation at 10m Height

WPD is the expected value for the potential wind energy at a specific location. WPD for a region can be calculated by:

$$\frac{P}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^3 f(v) \tag{3}$$

where P is wind power density (W), v is the wind speed (m/s), A is swept area (m^2), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3) and $f(v)$ is the PDF.

Additionally, the mean WPD can be determined by:

$$\frac{\bar{P}}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \bar{v}^3 \tag{4}$$

where \bar{P} is the mean wind power density and \bar{v} is the mean wind speed.

In the literature, the air density value is $1.23kg/m^3$. Using (4), the WPD was calculated and tabulated in Table VI. It is found that the value of WPD is within the range of 13.26 (Kham and Khartoum) - 72.64 (Ain ed Dabaa) W/m^2 . According to the wind power density classification [5], the wind energy potential in the selected locations is classified as class 1 (poor). Based on the findings, a small-scale wind

turbine can use wind energy to generate electricity at the selected locations.

D. Summary

The findings of this study are significant for the installation of wind farms and many wind energy applications in the future. No single distribution can accurately describe the wind speed distribution based on the summary of previous scientific studies. The 2p-W is a common tool used in the assessment of wind energy for a specific region. Accordingly, the distribution function is chosen based on the available wind speed data and the utilized statistical methods. The main aim of this study is to evaluate the suitability of different probability functions for estimating wind speed characteristics at different locations in Lebanon. In this study, various distribution functions with a various number of parameters are utilized for the first time to estimate the characteristics of wind speed. Based on the findings, Wakeby, Beta, and GEV are considered effective, since they provide the best fits for the actual wind speed data for all locations. The annual values of WPD were calculated using the best distribution functions. Based on the findings, the WPD at the selected locations can be exploited using a small-scale wind turbine.

TABLE V. DESCRIPTIVE WIND SPEED DATASET

Location	DF	Parameter	Mean	V	SD	S	K	Statistic	Rank
Yotmine	Actual		2.90	-	0.45	0.03	-1.46	-	-
	Beta	$\alpha_1=0.38225 \alpha_2=0.40879 a=2.32 b=3.512$	2.90	0.20	0.45	0.06	-1.58	0.15	3
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.25596 \sigma=0.4583 \mu=2.7263$	2.86	0.22	0.46	0.07	-0.26	0.16	5
	Gen. Pareto	$k=-0.93858 \sigma=1.501 \mu=2.1217$	2.90	0.21	0.46	0.05	-1.18	0.13	1
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.3107$	2.90	2.29	1.51	0.63	0.25	0.40	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=1.501 \beta=0.93858 \gamma=0 \delta=0 \xi=2.1217$	2.90	0.02	0.46	0.05	-1.18	0.13	2
Weibull	$\alpha=6.5369 \beta=3.0351$	2.83	0.26	0.51	-0.42	0.12	0.16	4	
Birket Aarous	Actual		3.01	-	0.31	-0.56	-0.26	-	-
	Dagum	$k=0.31321 \alpha=33.389 \beta=3.2552$	3.01	0.09	0.30	-0.83	1.52	0.12	2
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.56484 \sigma=0.34662 \mu=2.9426$	3.01	0.11	0.32	-0.80	0.62	0.16	4
	Gen. Logistic	$k=-0.14575 \sigma=0.17083 \mu=3.0521$	-	-	-	-	-	0.12	3
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.4017$	3.01	2.48	1.57	0.63	0.25	0.40	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=3.8783 \beta=4.3227 \gamma=0.08856 \delta=0.20184 \xi=2.1705$	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	1
Weibull	$\alpha=9.9843 \beta=3.1091$	2.96	0.13	0.36	-0.64	0.57	0.21	5	
Ain ed Dabaa	Actual		4.90	-	0.53	-0.15	-0.41	-	-
	Dagum	$k=0.41765 \alpha=25.218 \beta=5.2488$	4.91	0.29	0.54	-0.50	1.22	0.13	3
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.3961 \sigma=0.57967 \mu=4.7359$	4.90	0.30	0.55	-0.35	-0.15	0.12	2
	Gumbel Min	$\sigma=0.41251 \mu=5.1387$	4.90	0.28	0.52	-1.14	2.40	0.12	1
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=3.9101$	4.90	6.56	2.56	0.63	0.25	0.41	5
	Weibull	$\alpha=10.146 \beta=5.0377$	4.80	0.32	0.57	-0.64	0.59	0.18	4
Mqaybleh	Actual		2.91	-	0.30	-0.56	-0.26	-	-
	Dagum	$k=0.31334 \alpha=33.401 \beta=3.1518$	2.92	0.09	0.29	-0.83	1.52	0.12	2
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.56493 \sigma=0.33539 \mu=2.8494$	2.91	0.10	0.31	-0.80	0.62	0.16	4
	Gen. Logistic	$k=-0.14579 \sigma=0.16529 \mu=2.9553$	-	-	-	-	-	0.12	3
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.3256$	2.91	2.32	1.52	0.63	0.25	0.40	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=3.7758 \beta=4.3574 \gamma=0.08812 \delta=0.19228 \xi=2.1008$	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	1
Weibull	$\alpha=9.9875 \beta=3.0105$	2.86	0.12	0.34	-0.64	0.57	0.21	5	
Ras Ouadi Ed Darje	Actual		3.19	-	0.45	0.52	-0.19	-	-
	Burr	$k=0.73124 \alpha=14.691 \beta=3.0386$	3.19	0.22	0.47	1.19	4.69	0.09	3
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.07482 \sigma=0.40347 \mu=2.9829$	3.19	0.22	0.47	0.75	0.88	0.10	4
	Gen. Logistic	$k=0.12273 \sigma=0.25573 \mu=3.1353$	-	-	-	-	-	0.09	1
	Log-Logistic (3P)	$\alpha=5.5837 \beta=1.3577 \gamma=1.7727$	3.20	0.25	0.50	2.04	15.48	0.09	2
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.5435$	3.19	2.78	1.67	0.63	0.25	0.39	6
Weibull	$\alpha=8.2109 \beta=3.2847$	3.10	0.20	0.45	-0.55	0.36	0.14	5	
Kfardeblian	Actual		3.48	-	0.41	0.82	-0.75	-	-
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=0.14286 \sigma=0.28756 \mu=3.2647$	3.48	0.22	0.46	-2.43	14.54	0.14	4
	Gen. Pareto	$k=-0.16182 \sigma=0.58192 \mu=2.9767$	3.48	0.19	0.44	1.30	1.69	0.12	2
	Log-Logistic (3P)	$\alpha=1.4625 \beta=0.30081 \gamma=3.0211$	3.79	-	-	-	-	0.12	1
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.7747$	3.48	3.30	1.82	0.63	0.25	0.45	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=0.58192 \beta=0.16182 \gamma=0 \delta=0 \xi=2.9767$	3.48	0.19	0.44	1.30	1.69	0.12	3
Weibull	$\alpha=9.3692 \beta=3.5804$	3.40	0.19	0.43	-0.61	0.50	0.20	5	
Qaraoun	Actual		2.86	-	0.19	-0.54	-0.81	-	-
	Beta	$\alpha_1=0.7163 \alpha_2=0.45516 a=2.514 b=3.077$	2.86	0.03	0.19	-0.42	-1.23	0.12	1
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.61707 \sigma=0.21637 \mu=2.8216$	2.86	0.04	0.20	-0.94	0.98	0.13	4
	Gen. Pareto	$k=-1.8226 \sigma=1.1791 \mu=2.4405$	2.86	0.04	0.19	-0.55	-0.97	0.13	2
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.2806$	2.86	2.23	1.49	0.63	0.25	0.46	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=1.1791 \beta=1.8226 \gamma=0 \delta=0 \xi=2.4405$	2.86	0.04	0.19	-0.55	-0.97	0.13	3
Weibull	$\alpha=15.456 \beta=2.9261$	2.83	0.05	0.22	-0.80	1.03	0.16	5	
Khartoum	Actual		2.81	-	0.18	-0.54	-0.81	-	-
	Beta	$\alpha_1=0.71911 \alpha_2=0.45588 a=2.473 b=3.028$	2.81	0.03	0.18	-0.43	-1.23	0.13	1
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.61795 \sigma=0.21306 \mu=2.7767$	2.81	0.04	0.20	-0.94	0.99	0.13	4
	Gen. Pareto	$k=-1.825 \sigma=1.1626 \mu=2.4011$	2.81	0.04	0.19	-0.55	-0.97	0.13	3
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.2442$	2.81	2.16	1.47	0.63	0.25	0.46	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=1.8650E+5 \beta=77661.0 \gamma=1.1613 \delta=-1.8236 \xi=0$	-	-	-	-	-	0.13	2
Weibull	$\alpha=15.442 \beta=2.8795$	2.78	0.05	0.22	-0.80	1.03	0.16	5	
Iskandarounah	Actual		3.32	-	0.57	0.42	-1.46	-	-
	Beta	$\alpha_1=0.28827 \alpha_2=0.45156 a=2.719 b=4.27$	3.32	0.33	0.57	0.44	-1.40	0.11	1
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.00205 \sigma=0.48503 \mu=3.0443$	3.32	0.38	0.62	1.13	2.34	0.15	2
	Erlang	$m=33 \beta=0.09894$	3.27	0.32	0.57	0.35	0.18	0.17	3
	Weibull	$\alpha=5.9937 \beta=3.4797$	3.23	0.39	0.63	-0.37	0.03	0.20	4
Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.6516$	3.32	3.02	1.74	0.63	0.25	0.41	5	

Location	DF	Parameter	Mean	V	SD	S	K	Statistic	Rank
Beirut	Actual		3.48	-	0.41	0.82	-0.75	-	-
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=0.14286 \sigma=0.28756 \mu=3.2647$	3.48	0.22	0.46	-2.43	14.54	0.14	4
	Gen. Pareto	$k=-0.16182 \sigma=0.58192 \mu=2.9767$	3.48	0.19	0.44	1.30	1.69	0.12	2
	Log-Logistic (3P)	$\alpha=1.4625 \beta=0.30081 \gamma=3.0211$	3.79	-	-	-	-	0.12	1
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.7747$	3.48	3.30	1.82	0.63	0.25	0.45	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=0.58192 \beta=0.16182 \gamma=0 \delta=0 \xi=2.9767$	3.48	0.19	0.44	1.30	1.69	0.12	3
Khiam	Weibull	$\alpha=9.3692 \beta=3.5804$	3.40	0.19	0.43	-0.61	0.50	0.20	5
	Actual		2.81	-	0.18	-0.54	-0.81	-	-
	Beta	$\alpha_1=0.71911 \alpha_2=0.45588 a=2.473 b=3.028$	2.81	0.03	0.18	-0.43	-1.23	0.13	1
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.61795 \sigma=0.21306 \mu=2.7767$	2.81	0.04	0.20	-0.94	0.99	0.13	4
	Gen. Pareto	$k=-1.825 \sigma=1.1626 \mu=2.4011$	2.81	0.04	0.19	-0.55	-0.97	0.13	3
	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.2442$	2.81	2.16	1.47	0.63	0.25	0.46	6
Hekr El Dahri	Wakeby	$\alpha=1.8650E+5 \beta=77661.0 \gamma=1.1613 \delta=-1.8236 \xi=0$	-	-	-	-	-	0.13	2
	Weibull	$\alpha=15.442 \beta=2.8795$	2.78	0.05	0.22	-0.80	1.03	0.16	5
	Actual		2.91	-	0.30	-0.56	-0.26	-	-
	Dagum	$k=0.31334 \alpha=33.401 \beta=3.1518$	2.92	0.09	0.29	-0.83	1.52	0.12	2
	Gen. Extreme Value	$k=-0.56493 \sigma=0.33539 \mu=2.8494$	2.91	0.10	0.31	-0.80	0.62	0.16	4
	Gen. Logistic	$k=-0.14579 \sigma=0.16529 \mu=2.9553$	-	-	-	-	-	0.12	3
Hekr El Dahri	Rayleigh	$\sigma=2.3256$	2.91	2.32	1.52	0.63	0.25	0.40	6
	Wakeby	$\alpha=3.7758 \beta=4.3574 \gamma=0.08812 \delta=0.19228 \xi=2.1008$	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	1
	Weibull	$\alpha=9.9875 \beta=3.0105$	2.86	0.12	0.34	-0.64	0.57	0.21	5

TABLE VI. WPD (W/m²) VALUE FOR EACH LOCATION (L)

L	DF	WPD	L	DF	WPD
Younine	Actual	14.94	Qaroun	Actual	14.36
	Beta	14.94		Beta	14.36
	Gen. Extreme Value	14.34		Gen. Extreme Value	14.36
	Gen. Pareto	14.94		Gen. Pareto	14.36
	Rayleigh	14.93		Rayleigh	14.36
	Wakeby	14.94		Wakeby	14.36
Birket Aarous	Weibull	13.92	Khartoum	Weibull	13.91
	Actual	16.77		Actual	13.69
	Dagum	16.82		Beta	13.69
	Gen. Extreme Value	16.77		Gen. Extreme Value	13.69
	Gen. Logistic	-		Gen. Pareto	13.69
	Rayleigh	16.77		Rayleigh	13.69
Ain ed Dabaa	Wakeby	-	Iskandarounah	Wakeby	-
	Weibull	15.91		Weibull	13.26
	Actual	72.40		Actual	22.57
	Dagum	72.64		Beta	22.57
	Gen. Extreme Value	72.38		Gen. Extreme Value	22.57
	Gumbel Min	72.38		Erlang	21.41
Mqaybleh	Rayleigh	72.38	Beirut	Weibull	20.69
	Weibull	67.83		Rayleigh	22.57
	Actual	15.23		Actual	25.87
	Dagum	15.27		Gen. Extreme Value	25.87
	Gen. Extreme Value	15.23		Gen. Pareto	25.87
	Gen. Logistic	-		Log-Logistic (3P)	33.54
Ras Ouadi Ed Darje	Rayleigh	15.23	Khiam	Rayleigh	25.87
	Wakeby	-		Wakeby	25.87
	Weibull	14.45		Weibull	24.10
	Actual	19.93		Actual	13.69
	Burr	19.93		Beta	13.69
	Gen. Extreme Value	19.92		Gen. Extreme Value	13.69
Kfarebian	Gen. Logistic	0.00	Hekr El Dahri	Gen. Pareto	13.69
	Log-Logistic (3P)	20.24		Rayleigh	13.69
	Rayleigh	19.92		Wakeby	-
	Weibull	18.27		Weibull	13.26
	Actual	25.87		Actual	15.23
	Gen. Extreme Value	25.87		Dagum	15.27
Kfarebian	Gen. Pareto	25.87	Hekr El Dahri	Gen. Extreme Value	15.23
	Log-Logistic (3P)	33.54		Gen. Logistic	-
	Rayleigh	25.87		Rayleigh	15.23
	Wakeby	25.87		Wakeby	-
	Weibull	24.10		Weibull	14.45

E. Techno-Economic Feasibility

This section aims to encourage governments to develop wind farms to achieve sustainable energy infrastructures, particularly in developing countries like Lebanon. The investigation of changing tariffs influencing the wind energy market in Lebanon is discussed by proposing 9 scenarios as shown in Table VII. Moreover, the capital, operation, and maintenance costs associated with turbines can be assumed based on previous scientific studies [25]. In this study, the technical viability of 3 wind turbine models (WTMs) is evaluated. Generally, wind farm performance in terms of wind power production and capacity factor is affected by the geographic location and wind speed distribution. Thus, the Electricity Exported to the Grid (EEG) and the Capacity Factor (CF) were estimated for Younine (it has the lowest monthly wind speed) and Ain ed Dabaa (it has the maximum monthly wind speed) for the selected location. The mean EEG monthly value of for all the proposed models is shown in Figure 5. It is observed that the EEG is within the range of 604.38-3999.537MWh. The lowest value of EEG is recorded at Younine using WTM#1, while the highest value is recorded at Ain ed Dabaa using WTM#. It is noticed that WTM#2 produced the highest EEG. Moreover, for Younine location, the annual value of EEG of the proposed system is 14057.47MWh for WTM#1, 17152.08 for WTM#2, and 18268.02 for WTM#3. For Ain ed Dabaa, the annual value of EEG of the proposed system is 32030.96, 38252.56, and 37642.62MWh for WTM#1, 2, and 3, respectively. The annual CF was calculated for all wind turbines as shown in Figure 6. It is observed that the annual CF varied from 16.05% to 43.67%. The results demonstrate that among all wind turbines, the capacity factor of WTM#2 was the highest. These results can be supported by previous scientific studies. For instance, authors in [26] found that the CF values of the proposed wind farms varied from 9.79% to 51.93% and authors in [27] found that the CF values of the proposed farms were within the range of 5-42%. Authors in [28] found that the proposed farm projects in Pakistan have a CF ranging from 19% to 34%. The

economic analysis is essential when one wants to know if the project is economically viable and sustainable. Thus, the techno-economic feasibility of the proposed projects was evaluated using RETScreen for different Scenarios as shown in Table VII. The used financial parameters include inflation rate (2.9%), discount rate (5.4%), reinvestment rate (9%), project life (25 years), debt ratio (70%), debt interest rate (8.9%), and debt payments (15 years) as input parameters, assumed based on previous studies. Based on these input parameters, NPV, ALCS, SP, EP, LCOE, and the internal rate of return (IRR) were estimated using RETScreen software.

TABLE VII. THE DEVELOPEPD THREE SCENARIOS TO SHOW THE IMPACT OF POLICY CHANGES ON THE FINANCIAL VIABILITY OF WIND POWER PLANTS IN LEBANON

Input	Scenario A1	Scenario B1	Scenario C1
Capacity	10MW		
Turbine model#1	AAER-A-2000 - 100		
Project Life	20 years		
Array Losses	4%		
Airfoil Losses	2%		
Miscellaneous Losses	6%		
Availability Factor	98%		
Electricity Export Cost [US Cents]	6.75	10.45	13.52
Input	Scenario A1	Scenario B1	Scenario C1
Capacity	10MW		
Turbine model#2	DW 52 - 500kW - 75m		
Project Life	20 years		
Array Losses	4%		
Airfoil Losses	2%		
Miscellaneous Losses	6%		
Availability Factor	98%		
Electricity Export Cost [US Cents]	6.75	10.45	13.52
Input	Scenario A1	Scenario B1	Scenario C1
Capacity	10MW		
Turbine model#3	W2E100/2000 - 100m		
Project Life	20 years		
Array Losses	4%		
Airfoil Losses	2%		
Miscellaneous Losses	6%		
Availability Factor	98%		
Electricity Export Cost [US Cents]	6.75	10.45	13.52

The NPV was determined for each location and each value of Electricity Export Rate (EER) and is illustrated in Figure 7. It is found that the value of NPV for each value of EER is positive, which indicated that the project is potentially feasible [29, 30]. Besides, it is noticed that there is a strong correlation between NPV and EER. Moreover, IRR is estimated to evaluate the economic viability of the project. The IRR provides the true return of interest over the life of the project. The results showed that increasing rate of exporting electricity led to an increase in the value of IRR. In addition, it is observed that the value of IRR of all locations is higher than the required rate of return of the project. Furthermore, ALCS is calculated by using NPV, discount rate, and project lifetime. It is found that ALCS is within the range of 67438-6790429 USD/year for all proposed projects.

According to previous scientific studies, the economic viability of a project is estimated by determining the payback period, which indicates the time required to recover the initial investments, with net positive income. Figure 7 shows the payback period including EP and SP for all selected locations based on various scenarios. It is found that the EP and SP are within the range of 1.1-16.1 and 2.9-15.7 years, respectively. WTM#2 has the lowest value of EP and SP compared to other models. The results reveal that the increase in EER will lead to a decrease in EP and SP. Moreover, the Electricity Production Cost (EPC) is found within the range of 0.038-0.104-0.038 USD/kWh. The EPC is lower compared to previous studies [25, 31] and the electricity tariff in the country [19].

Fig. 5. Monthly average electric production.

Fig. 6. Annual CF.

F. Climate Co-benefit Assessment

The climate co-benefits in terms of GHG emission reduction were calculated using RETScreen software for each location and are listed in Table VIII. The results indicate that a large amount of CO₂ emissions can be avoided by implementing the developed wind project in each location. It is noticed that the Wind Farm (WF) using WTM#3 (WF-WTM#3) has the highest amount of CO₂ emission reductions. The total amount of CO₂ emissions reduction for each location is determined based on the electricity generated annually [32].

Fig. 7. Economic performance of the developed wind project in Younine and Ain ed Dabaa.

TABLE VIII. NET ANNUAL REDUCTION OF GHG EMISSIONS (tCO₂)

Location	WF-WTM#1	WF-WTM#2	WF-WTM#3
Younine	9244.15	11279.21	12013.05
Ain ed Dabaa	23142.37	27637.47	27196.79

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the wind speed distribution and the potential of wind energy were assessed at 12 locations in Lebanon. For

wind speed distribution, 44 distribution models were utilized to analyze the wind speed characteristics in the selected locations. The results demonstrated that Wakeby and Beta distribution functions gave the best fit to the actual data for most locations. Moreover, a 10MW wind farm's viability was examined for the climate conditions of various locations in Lebanon using RETScreen software. The results indicated that the proposed wind farms are feasible both technically and economically. Ain ed Dabaa is the most suitable location for installing a wind farm in the future.

The developed projects provide a significant insight into the economic feasibility of the project for all locations. Wind energy exploitation is able to solve the chronic problem of the lack of electricity and reduce the electricity import cost in Lebanon.

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Chaos Control of Doubly-Fed Induction Generator via Delayed Feedback Control

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ABSTRACT

With the increasing wind power penetration, wind farms are directly influencing the power systems, so the need to improve the quality of the system is an open research topic. A Doubly-Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) is often used in wind power systems. However, DFIG has a complex structure and often works in harsh environments, so potential faults may occur. Faults can cause the system to fall into a chaotic working state, which is a harmful phenomenon for DFIG, since it makes the operating quality of the system worse, even leading to system destruction if not fixed on time. This study presents simulations of the chaotic phenomenon that occurs for a DFIG under specific working conditions based on Lyapunov's exponents. The delay feedback controller is designed, and along with the selection of the appropriate controller parameters, the chaotic phenomenon is quickly eliminated, bringing the system back to stable operation.

Keywords-chaos; chaos control; DFIG; DFC; Lyapunov's exponents

I. INTRODUCTION

Chaos can be beneficial as it may speed up chemical reactions, enhance mixing, provide a powerful mechanism for heat and mass transfer, etc. However, in many situations, chaos is an undesirable phenomenon, it can lead to increased mechanical fatigue for irregular oscillations, and non-convection energy absorption in a turbulent regime can lead to system parameters exceeding the safe level. Chaos is a phenomenon that only occurs in nonlinear systems, sensitive to initial conditions, and non-periodic but obeying certain laws. A dynamic system with chaotic motion needs to meet the following conditions [1-2]:

- The system has at least three independent variables.
- The equation of motion must have nonlinear terms. In addition, the phase space of the system must have a dimension of not less than 3 to ensure the existence of

divergent trajectories, be confined to a finite domain of the dynamics space, and ensure uniqueness of the orbit.

First of all, we need to note that in a linear dynamic system, chaos never occurs. So, when we talk about chaos, we mean nonlinear systems. However, not all nonlinear systems have chaotic motion. There are different methods of detecting chaos such as the Fourier analysis method, time responses, phase portraits, bifurcation diagram of the maximum value of the state variable over time, and calculations of Lyapunov exponents used to illustrate the chaotic behavior when changing the characteristic value. The main interest of this paper is focused on the Lyapunov exponent because it can be calculated with relative ease and it provides confirmation of the presence of chaos in the observed data [3]. When the average Lyapunov exponent is calculated as positive, it indicates chaotic behavior occurring in the system. From that, the chaotic working area of the object is drawn, and a control method is proposed to bring the system to a stable working state,

extinguishing the self-sustaining oscillations with high amplitude and abnormal changes.

Due to the harsh working environment of wind farms, the DFIG parameters can change with temperature, time, load conditions, etc. DFIG is prone to faults such as gearbox faults, power converter faults, stator winding faults, rotor winding faults, velocity sensor faults, etc. [4-7], from which the system may fall into a state of chaotic operation, leading to poor working quality, which can be the cause of problems and failures. Among electrical failures, insulation failures in the stator windings cause the majority (30%-40%) of induction machine failures, including DFIGs [8-10]. Although a DFIG has a complex structure, prone to failure, it is still the most used structure in wind power systems due to its outstanding advantages. Therefore, there have been many research works put forth to improve the quality and performance of the system [6, 11-16]. The research on bifurcation and chaos for the DFIG system is very limited [17-23] and does not cover all the potential risks. The above studies have shown that, under certain operating conditions, a DFIG can be chaotic. Authors in [18, 20] evaluate that phenomenon based on computer simulations but have not evaluated it on a solid theoretical basis, or do not give specific conditions on which parameter changes in the system lead to chaos [20]. Authors in [21] analyzed the phenomenon of chaos and presented several risks that make the DFIG system chaotic. On the basis of theoretical analysis (algorithm to test 0-1) and through simulation, authors in [23] evaluated the stability and chaos of the system. The study also gives specific conditions of the parameter set causing chaos for the DFIG, however the condition of 3 simultaneous faults (stator winding fault, rotor winding fault, and rotor speed sensor fault) rarely occurs in practice.

This study demonstrates that DFIG faces a chaotic phenomenon when the system parameters change in case of stator winding failure, based on theoretical analysis and simulations. From there, the delay response controller will be designed to eliminate chaos, return the system to stability and avoid possible risks.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF DFIG, CHAOS CONTROL, AND DELAY FEEDBACK CONTROL METHOD

A. Mathematical Model of DFIG

One of the main control objectives for the DFIG is the independent control of active and reactive power through decoupled control of rotor currents i_{rd} and i_{rq} [24]. The starting point for deducing the state-space model of the DFIG is the voltage equations for the stator and rotor windings [24-25]:

Stator voltage in stator winding system:

$$u_s^s = R_s i_s^s + \frac{d\psi_s^s}{dt} \tag{1}$$

Rotor voltage in rotor winding system:

$$u_r^r = R_r i_r^r + \frac{d\psi_r^r}{dt} \tag{2}$$

Rotor and stator flux:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_s = L_s i_s + L_m i_r \\ \psi_r = L_m i_s + L_r i_r \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} L_s = L_m + L_{\sigma s} \\ L_r = L_m + L_{\sigma r} \end{cases}$$

Converting (1) and (2) to the dq coordinate system, for any internal rotation with angular speed ω_s we get:

$$\begin{cases} u_s = R_s i_s + \frac{d\psi_s}{dt} + j\omega_s \psi_s \\ u_r = R_r i_r + \frac{d\psi_r}{dt} + j\omega_r \psi_r \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

where $\omega_s = \omega + \omega_r$

The generator stator is connected to the grid with constant voltage and frequency. Since the stator frequency is always identical to the grid frequency, the voltage drop across the stator resistor can be neglected in comparison with the voltage drop across the mutual inductance L_m and the dissipation inductance $L_{\sigma s}$ stator, which can be written as follows:

$$u_s = R_s i_s + \frac{d\psi_s}{dt} \Rightarrow u_s \approx \frac{d\psi_s}{dt} \text{ or } u_s \approx j\omega_s \Psi_s \tag{5}$$

From (3), we obtain:

$$i_s = \frac{1}{L_s} (\Psi_s - L_m i_r)$$

$$\Psi_r = L_m i_s + L_r i_r$$

After suppressing the stator current i_s and the rotor flux Ψ_r , from system (4) we get:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{di_r}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) i_r - j\omega_r i_r \\ + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_s} + j\omega \right) \Psi'_s + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_r + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} u_s \\ \frac{d\Psi'_s}{dt} = \frac{1}{T_s} i_r - \left(\frac{1}{T_s} + j\omega_s \right) \Psi'_s + \frac{1}{L_m} u_s \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

where $\Psi'_s = \Psi_s/L_m$, $\sigma = 1 - L_m^2/(L_s L_r)$, $T_s = L_s/R_s$, $T_r = L_r/R_r$.

After decoupling both equations into real and imaginary components, we obtain the complete system of electrical equations of DFIG (7).

$$\begin{cases} \frac{di_{rd}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) i_{rd} + \omega_r i_{rq} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_s} \Psi'_{sd} - \omega \Psi'_{sq} \right) + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_{rd} - \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} u_{sd} \\ \frac{di_{rq}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) i_{rq} - \omega_r i_{rd} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_s} \Psi'_{sq} + \omega \Psi'_{sd} \right) + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_{rq} - \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} u_{sq} \\ \frac{d\Psi'_{sd}}{dt} = \frac{1}{T_s} i_{rd} - \frac{1}{T_s} \Psi'_{sd} + \omega_s \Psi'_{sq} + \frac{1}{L_m} u_{sd} \\ \frac{d\Psi'_{sq}}{dt} = \frac{1}{T_s} i_{rq} - \frac{1}{T_s} \Psi'_{sq} - \omega_s \Psi'_{sd} + \frac{1}{L_m} u_{sq} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

In grid voltage, the orientated coordinates are: $u_{sd} = u_s$, $\Psi'_{sd} = 0$, $\Psi'_{sq} = \Psi'_s$.

Summarizing the equation system (7) yields the following state space model for the DFIG in the grid voltage orientated reference frame (8):

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \mathbf{A}x + \mathbf{B}_s u_s + \mathbf{B}_r u_r \tag{8}$$

with: State vector $x^T = [i_{rd}, i_{rq}, \Psi'_{sd}, \Psi'_{sq}]$, stator voltage vector $u_s^T = [u_{sd}, u_{sq}]$, as the input vector on the stator side, and stator voltage vector $u_r^T = [u_{rd}, u_{rq}]$ as the input vector on the rotor side.

The system matrix \mathbf{A} , the rotor input matrix \mathbf{B}_r and the stator input matrix \mathbf{B}_s may be written as:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) & \omega_r & \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma T_s} & -\frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \omega \\ -\omega_r & -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) & \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \omega & \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma T_s} \\ \frac{1}{T_s} & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_s} & \omega_s \\ 0 & \frac{1}{T_s} & -\omega_s & -\frac{1}{T_s} \end{bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

$$\mathbf{B}_s = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} \\ \frac{1}{L_m} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{L_m} \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{B}_r = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

B. Chaos Control and Delayed Feedback Control Method

Every parameter of the system has the potential to cause bifurcation and chaos, the idea of control is to bring these two properties towards its purpose, by adjusting the system parameters, or to hit the target by methods such system parameters transformation, changes in the structure of the system, input stimulus from outside, change the controller, or a control method based on the system's strange attractor set when a chaotic phenomenon occurs, bringing the trajectory to the target orbit with the new set parameter combination compatible with the old parameter. To do so, it is necessary to know the rate at which chaos or exponential growth increases and the oscillation amplitude of the system state variable. From there, a way to approach is by using accurate measurement equipment of system state variables and thus determining the stable and unstable working parameter areas, thereby determining the appropriate control method and the way to change the structure of the system if necessary. There are many methods of chaos control applied to electric drive systems and they have certain effects. The chaotic control method based on the delay feedback controller has been studied extensively [1, 26-30]. The delayed feedback control method, described in [31], is:

$$F(t) = K[y(t - \tau) - y(t)] = KD(t)$$

where τ is the delay time. If this time coincides with the period of i^{th} periodic orbit $\tau = T_i$, i.e. $y(t) = y_i(t)$, it does not change the periodic orbits in the system. Choosing the appropriate

weight K of the feedback, we can achieve the stabilization of the system.

The delayed feedback control method is less complex and more responsive than other control methods. It allows for non-invasive stabilization in the sense that the control force disappears when the state has reached the target. Authors in [32] showed that the simple self-feedback delay controller gives better results than the sliding mode self-feedback delay controller when applied to control chaotic behavior in the IFOC of a 3-phase induction motor. Today, the DFC has become one of the most popular methods in chaos control research [33]. So far the number of published works on chaos control for DFIG is very limited and has not covered all the problems. To the best of our knowledge there are no works that apply DFC method to control the DFIG. This study aims to fill that gap.

III. CHAOTIC PHENOMENA AND CHAOS CONTROL FOR DFIG

A. Chaotic Behavior Analysis of DFIG

It can be seen from (7) that DFIG is a multivariable and nonlinear system (which is a necessary condition for a chaotic motion system). DFIG contains many parameters and the system works in harsh environments, therefore, the parameters can vary according to temperature, time, and system operating conditions. When the parameters of the system change, the system may appear to be chaotic. To clarify this issue, this study presents the chaotic phenomenon that occurs in DFIGs in cases of stator winding failure (this is the problem that accounts for the majority of electrical problems for DFIGs [8-10]). From the equation of motion of the rotor [6, 17], we combine with the first two equations of (7) to obtain a system of equations representing the rotor currents (i_{rd}, i_{rq}) and the rotor speed of DFIG as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{di_{rd}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) i_{rd} + (\omega_s - \omega) i_{rq} - \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \omega \frac{\Psi_s}{L_m} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_{rd} - \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} u_s \\ \frac{di_{rq}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right) i_{rq} - (\omega_s - \omega) i_{rd} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \frac{1}{T_s} \frac{\Psi_s}{L_m} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_{rq} \\ \frac{d\omega}{dt} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{n_p^2 L_m \Psi_s}{J L_s} i_{rd} - \frac{D}{J} \omega - \frac{n_p}{J} T_L \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

From that, the structure diagram of the system is obtained as can be seen in [34], with: $x_1 = i_{rd}; x_2 = i_{rq}; x_3 = \omega;$

$$c_1 = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_s} \right); c_2 = \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m} \Psi_s; c_3 = \frac{1}{\sigma L_r}; c_4 = \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m}; c_5 = \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma L_m T_s} \Psi_s; c_6 = \frac{3n_p^2 L_m \Psi_s}{2J L_s}; c_7 = \frac{D}{J}; c_8 = \frac{n_p}{J}.$$

Equation (10) will be abbreviated to:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = c_1 x_1 + (\omega_s - x_3) x_2 - c_2 x_3 + c_3 u_{rd} - c_4 u_s \\ \dot{x}_2 = c_1 x_2 - (\omega_s - x_3) x_1 + c_5 + c_3 u_{rq} \\ \dot{x}_3 = c_6 x_1 - c_7 x_3 - c_8 T_L \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

The system's main parameters used in our simulations are listed in Table I [25].

TABLE I. MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE DFIG SYSTEM

Rated power (P)	1.5MW
Grid voltage (U)	690V
Grid frequency (f)	50 Hz
Moment of inertia (J)	2kgm ²
Pole pairs (n_p)	3
Damping coefficient (D)	0.001Nm/rad/s
Load torque (T_L)	3N.m
Stator resistance (R_s)	2.139m Ω
Stator inductance (L_s)	4.05mH
Rotor resistance (R_r)	2.139m Ω
Rotor inductance (L_r)	4.09mH
Mutual inductance(L_m)	4mH

From the structural model of the system above, simulations in MATLAB were conducted with the following algorithm: first, simulate with the system's parameter set in normal mode, and then, simulate the case of stator winding failure, in order to be able to clarify the stable working state of the system in normal mode and the system falling into a chaotic state when the parameters of the stator windings change.

In the normal operating mode, the simulation results show that the phase trajectories of i_{rd} , i_{rq} and ω oscillated at the beginning, but soon they stabilized (Figures 1 and 2). The results of calculating the Lyapunov exponent also show that all 3 Lyapunov exponents are negative (Figure 3). Thus, with a normal set of parameters, the system is stable.

Fig. 1. Time series diagrams of i_{rd} , i_{rq} , ω .

Fig. 2. Phase trajectory diagram x_1, x_2, x_3 (i_{rd}, i_{rq}, ω).

Fig. 3. Variation of Lyapunov's exponent over time when the system is operating under normal conditions.

When stator winding failures occur, the inductance of the coil changes to other values. Through the simulation on MATLAB with the variation of the inductance parameter of the stator winding, the results in Figures 4-7 show that the orbit is attracted to the basin of attraction, but it is not stable there. The phase orbit is confined, which is possible to approach arbitrarily close to some point of the basin of attraction, but never to repeat the same at a later point in time. At the same time, the results of calculating the Lyapunov exponent (Figure 8 and Table II) show that the system always has 2 positive Lyapunov's exponents. Thus, the DFIG system is chaotic.

Fig. 4. Phase trajectory diagram showing chaotic orbits at $L_s = 3.8$ mH.

Fig. 5. Phase trajectory diagram showing chaotic orbits at $L_s = 3.3$ mH.

Fig. 6. Phase trajectory diagram showing chaotic orbits at $L_s = 2.7$ mH.

Fig. 7. Phase trajectory diagram showing chaotic orbits at $L_s = 2.2$ mH.

Fig. 8. Variation of Lyapunov's exponent over time when the system is chaotic.

TABLE II. LYAPUNOV'S EXPONENT

Time	λ_1	λ_2	λ_3
0.05	3713.00	3.13	-794.31
0.15	3713.90	3.10	-862.60
0.25	3714.08	3.09	-866.10
0.35	3714.16	3.09	-848.98
0.45	3714.20	3.09	-831.52
0.55	3714.23	3.09	-852.85
0.65	3714.25	3.09	-849.68
0.75	3714.27	3.09	-859.42
0.85	3714.28	3.09	-858.06
0.95	3714.28	3.09	-854.43
1.00	3714.29	3.09	-852.66

B. Chaos Control for DFIG

As described above, the controller's structure aimed to eliminate the chaos that has occurred for DFIG is:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = c_1x_1 + (\omega_s - x_3)x_2 - c_2x_3 \\ \quad + c_3u_{rd} - c_4u_s + K_1[x_1(t - \tau_1) - x_1] \\ \dot{x}_2 = c_1x_2 - (\omega_s - x_3)x_1 \\ \quad + c_5 + c_3u_{rq} + K_2[x_2(t - \tau_2) - x_2] \\ \dot{x}_3 = c_6x_1 - c_7x_3 - c_8T_L \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where K_1, K_2 are the experimentally tunable weights of the perturbation. We provide the following operating schedule: When the system is chaotic, at 0.1s a delay feedback controller will be added to the system. The system achieved different results during the conducted simulations with different selected values of K_1, K_2 and τ_1, τ_2 . The simulation results in Figure 8 with $K_1 = 22, K_2 = 25, \tau_1 = 0.001$, and $\tau_2 = 0.01$ show that the first time the phase trajectory of the system wanders in the confined space domain, then (when the controller is inserted) it is attracted to the equilibrium point and stabilizes there. Similarly, with different values of K_1, K_2 , and τ_1, τ_2 , the trajectory of x_1 in the time domain also shows that the stability of the system is different corresponding to the selected parameter set (Figures 9 to 14).

Fig. 9. Phase trajectory diagram between x_1, x_2 and x_3 with: $K_1=15, K_2=10, \tau_1=0.001, \tau_2=0.01$.

Fig. 10. Time plot with $K_1=15, K_2=10, \tau_1=0.005, \tau_2=0.0001$

Fig. 13. Time plot with $K_1=25$, $K_2=10$, $\tau_1=0.005$, $\tau_2=0.0001$

The above simulation results show that, with the designed control law based on the delayed feedback control method, the system eliminated the chaotic phenomenon and returned to a stable state. By choosing the values of the appropriate parameters K_1 , K_2 , and τ_1 , τ_2 , the system will achieve optimum quality.

IV. CONCLUSION

Chaos is harmful to DFIG. If this phenomenon is not detected and eliminated in time, the system's working quality will be poor, and the error can spread and cause great damage. This study has demonstrated the chaotic phenomenon that occurs for the DFIG when the stator winding is faulty, which is confirmed by calculating the Lyapunov exponent that always has two positive exponents, and simulation results show that the system has revealed the nature of chaos. This study proposes a control method to eliminate chaos for DFIG. The delay feedback control method is selected and designed. Before 0.1s, the curve shows strong fluctuations. At 0.1s a delay feedback controller was added to the system, the chaos was quickly eliminated, the system returns to stability, which can prevent further damage to the DFIG.

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Preliminary Site Investigation based on RGB Electromagnetic Energy of Landsat-7 Images in Wadi Fayidah, Saudi Arabia

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, geostatistical analysis of digital image processing data efficiently contributed to the preliminary site investigation and geotechnical mapping of Wadi Fayidah, Saudi Arabia. 3D modeling, clustering, and chart pattern changes were used to analyze the spectral electromagnetic energy reflected values in red, green, and blue (RGB) ranges on false color composite Landsat-7 images. Therefore, from upstream to downstream, a series of measurements were carried out on a 70km dendritic drainage pattern at 78 stations. Wadi Fayidah was found to have a dominant structural lineament of 56° to 84°. Furthermore, as a preliminary engineering geology mapping, Wadi Fayidah has 9 lithofacies that may differ in engineering geological properties.

Keywords-structural lineaments; lithofacies; statistical analysis; image processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Site investigation is an essential step in any engineering project in order to identify and quantify ground conditions affecting a structure's viability, design, or construction. As a preliminary site investigation tool, remote sensing aims to acquire a general engineering geological understanding of the project area or site. Hence, it gathers information about lithology, structure, and geomorphology without physical contact [1]. Remote sensing and digital image processing techniques are essential in mineral and groundwater exploration, lithological discrimination, and structural mapping [2]. Remote sensing, high-resolution imagery, and GIS have become essential tools for locating and selecting the best sites of mineral deposits by detecting the locations of alteration zones [3]. The mineral deposits usually occur along or are adjacent to the geologic structures and alteration mapping, as mineral deposits are commonly associated with hydrothermal alteration of the surrounding rocks [4-5]. Image processing of digital data has been used for lithological and structural interpretation [6-11]. Authors in [12] used remote sensing techniques for geological mapping. Authors in [13] utilized Landsat images to assess construction materials, while authors in [14] employed statistics and enhanced RGB images in surface water interpretation. The differences in soil color from an RGB camera were investigated at different distances, times,

and illumination levels obtained from loam soil over four weeks of data acquisition [15]. Authors in [16] studied Munsell's soft color and soil reflectance in the visible spectral bands of Landsat MSS and TM Data. RGB values appear to be strongly correlated with the soil reflectance measured in the corresponding spectral bands of Landsat sensors.

As a different approach for a preliminary site investigation of Wadi Fayidah, this work uses geostatistical analysis such as 3D modeling, clustering, and phenomena chart tracking of Landsat-7 ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus) digital satellite data. Consequently, this study aims to achieve a method of interpreting drainage patterns, structural lineaments, and lithofacies. The aim is to produce an engineering special-purposed geological map.

II. GEOLOGICAL SETTING

Wadi Fayidah is located in the Northern Makah region, between latitudes 21°50' and 21°59'N and longitudes 39°20' and 39°55' E (Figure 1). The investigated area belongs to the Arabian Shield, shielded by Precambrian metasediments and metavolcanics. These rocks are covered by Quaternary sediments and intruded by dioritic rocks. It is a basin among the deformed, weakly metamorphosed, post-amalgamation volcano-sedimentary sequence in the Arabian Shield, Saudi Arabia [17].

Fig. 1. Location map.

According to [18], the geology of Wadi Fayidah falls into four groups: (1) Proterozoic crystalline basement, (2) Tertiary sedimentary rocks, (3) Tertiary volcanic rocks, and (4) Quaternary sediments. The Proterozoic basement comprises volcanic and volcano-sedimentary formations of various ages and compositions, intruded by plutons of diverse composition but with strong granodiorite affinities. Tertiary sedimentary rocks consist of Shumaysi, Khulays, and Khulaysiyah [18, 20] and Hammar formation [21]. It comprises Tertiary clastic and carbonates rocks that crop out over a minimal area. However, they are thought to underlie the Quaternary sediments and Late Tertiary basalts in much of Wadi as Sukkah (As Suqah), Wadi al Aghran, and the coastal plain [21]. The Shumaysi to Ubhur formations has been tilted, faulted, and linked to the significant Red Sea rifting [21].

III. METHODOLOGY

The multispectral digital satellite data of Landsat-7 ETM+ were downloaded from the USGS website. They were radiometric and geometrically corrected to UTM 37N (WGS-84 datum) by the USGS EROS Center. This information is used for regional geotechnical surveys of the study area. Advanced remote sensing software such as ERDAS Imagine and PCI Geomatica provide various image-processing techniques such as geometric correction and image enhancement. This study uses digital image processing techniques with the statistical analysis of digital satellite data. A geometric correction has been applied to the data because geometric errors are caused by the sensor or scanner's geometry, the earth's curvature and rotation, etc. [22]. These data (Landsat-7 ETM+) comprise bands B1-B3 (visible rays), bands B4, B5, and B7 (infrared rays), band B6 (thermal rays), and a panchromatic band (B8). These bands are of 30m spatial resolution except band 6 (60m) and band 8 (15m). In addition, to make the processed images interpretable, histogram equalization and smooth filtering were applied [22]. The geostatistical analysis of the extracted lineaments, visible green enhancement band (EG), and the digital number (DN) values of RGB pixels (Landsat ETM+ bands 7, 4, 2, in red, green, and blue, respectively), along Wadi Fayidah, are summarized in the flow-chart approach shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Graphical abstract of the workflow.

Landsat-7 ETM+ digital data were processed to yield a False-Color Composite (FCC) image on a scale of 1:100000. The best band combination obtained for this FCC image consists of ETM band 7 (SWIR), band 4 (NIR), and band 2 (visible green) in RGB, based on the selection of the most significant variance bands with the minor correlation. In addition, it shows a regional view of the study area, the main rock units, and Wadies. The Landsat images cover a large area (185 by 170km) and illustrate its regional geology and topography. Extraction of lineaments from the digital Landsat data is carried out to show the structural analysis of the Wadi Fayidah area. It is also very useful in the seismic and risk of landslide evaluation [22]. Lineaments usually reflect linear structural features in the rocks or artificial features like roads or buildings. Lineament extraction is usually carried out by using digital data of satellite either manually [23-24] or automatically [25-26]. The automatic lineament extraction technique is applied in this work to interpret and extract the structural lineaments from the digital SPOT-5 data of the study area.

IV. RESULTS

Seventy-eight stations were placed at spaced distances (about 70Km long) with the Wadi Fayidah. These stations begin at the highest valley (upstream) on the east and end at the mouth of the Wadi (downstream) on the west (Figure 3). The statistical analysis of the relationship between interfaces, distance separations, and frequencies (the total number of stations in each distance) was carried out. Figure 4 shows the normal distribution of a histogram of the relationships between the distance separations between stations and their frequencies. Each station has taken various measurements, such as location coordinates and RGB spectral values of Landsat color composite images for raw and enhancement data in the three bands (bands 7, 4, and 2, in red, green, and blue). In addition, rock type, geomorphological type, and the trends and lengths of the structural lineaments were also taken at each station (Figure 5).

Table I describes the lithologic unit types in the 78 stations along Wadi Fayiddah. The symbols and descriptions of the lithologic units with their codes (arranged from 1-the oldest rock units to 23-the youngest rock units) are also listed.

Fig. 3. Locations of the 78 stations along Wadi Fayidah, on false color composite Landsat image.

Fig. 4. Frequencies of the distance separations between stations.

Long	Lat	Long	Lat	Dist. M	RR	RG	RB	FR	FG	FB	Rock Type	Geomorf.	Sr. Trend	Length
1	595910.063	2428171.5	3945043.87137E	0	43	48	54	30	62	46				257
2	595907.813	2427987	3945015.45387E	930	53	50	59	86	72	73				
3	59485.313	2427558.25	3945015.45387E	807	53	53	61	62	88	84				
4	593772.563	2427024.38	3945429.11847E	672	50	50	59	55	73	73				
5	593223.038	2426604	3945409.90777E	713	54	51	61	70	77	84				
6	592074.313	2425912.88	3945404.55047E	593	68	61	68	138	128	122			48	345
7	592067.188	2425335	3945404.55047E	673	56	57	61	78	108	84			50	268
8	592038.688	2424366.75	3945402.99227E	862	54	59	57	70	118	61			270	343
9	592096.438	2424088.68	3945402.99227E	1090	51	50	54	58	72	56			56	60
10	591692.063	2423882.25	3945315.96047E	358	67	63	62	123	139	89			71	137
11	590608.063	2423960.63	3945318.31117E	1084	63	50	56	106	72	56			94	70
12	589768.313	2423993.5	3945303.52777E	809	60	67	64	135	164	101				
71	541774.313	2423461.88	3942416.07327E	1224	59	60	61	86	123	84			317	88
72	541026.188	2423219.63	3942249.97247E	790	66	67	68	117	160	122				
73	540576.438	2423796.75	3942270.86047E	811	59	60	62	86	123	89				
74	540107.063	2424580.5	3942118.05997E	860	48	51	58	43	77	67			51	80
75	539266.313	2424201.63	3942274.76397E	856	48	49	57	43	67	62			330	343
76	538617.038	2424043.63	3942276.33177E	790	60	57	61	91	108	84				
77	537855.563	2423731.38	3942159.64367E	850	65	57	68	112	108	122			41	115
78	537029.063	2423694	3942130.88637E	1073	62	61	60	99	128	78			20	242

Fig. 5. Some RGB data acquired from the Landsat image on the 78 stations along Wadi Fayidah.

TABLE I. LITHOLOGICAL UNIT TYPES OF THE 78 STATIONS ALONG WADI FAYIDAH

Station No.	Symbol	Code	Rock Type	Description
1-5	ibmv-p€	2	Meta-Andesitic to Metabasaltic	
6-8	todr-p€	11	Tonalite	
9-11	gr-p€	13	Granite	
12-14	gdmo-p€	12	Granodiorite	
15-18	mdgb-p€	1	Metadiorite and Gabbro	
19-32	todr-p€	11	Tonalite	
33-35	sscg-t	15	Sandstone and Conglomerate	
36	ss-t	16	Sandstone and Oolitic iron ore	
37	sscg-t	15	Sandstone and Conglomerate	
38-51	ibvs-p€s	3	Samran group, Volcanosedimentary rocks	
52-54	sscg-t	15	Sandstone and Conglomerate	
55	ibvs-p€s	3	Samran group, Volcanosedimentary rocks	
56, 57	gv-Q	22	Gravel	
58, 59	sscg-t	15	Sandstone and Conglomerate	
60	gv-Q	22	Gravel	
61 to 78	clss-t	14	Clay, sandstone and tuff	

V. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The study area's Landsat-7 color composite images (bands 7, 4, 2 in RGB) were processed. The study area is dissected by

some significant Wadies running from the East to the West, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. False color composite Landsat-7 ETM+ image, showing Wadi Fayidah area.

A. Drainage

The image processing technique was applied to extract a subset of the false color composite Landsat image for the exact boundary of Wadi Fayidah Basin, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. False color composite Landsat-7 ETM+ image of Wadi Fayidah Basin.

Figure 8 shows the dendritic drainage pattern of Wadi Fayidah as interpreted from the FCC Landsat-7 ETM+ image in Figure 7. The Wadi Fayidah is one of the longest, more than 70km long, Wadies in the area. A dendritic drainage pattern that looks like the branching pattern of tree roots develops in regions underlain by homogeneous material. The availability of this pattern reflects the similarity of resistance to weathering, so there is no apparent control over the direction the tributaries take.

Fig. 8. The dendritic drainage pattern of Wadi Fayidah.

B. Lithofacies

As illustrated in Figure 5, numerous variables were measured at the 78 stations for classification purposes. The statistical analysis was performed in three steps.

1) Step-1: 3D Visual RGB Clustering

Figure 9 shows the 3D layout of the raw data's Red, Green, and Blue bands. The plotting indicates that the data can be

categorized into two groups. The stations of the first category were clogged on the map with yellow color (Figure 10). In addition, it was observed that stations located close to each other, are classified as one zone with the same lithofacies properties. Therefore, the study area can be categorized into two zones with different lithological properties.

Fig. 9. Two views of the same 3-D plot showing two RGB clusters (A and B).

Fig. 10. The first cluster of 3D RGB stations (yellow color).

2) Step-2: EG (Enhancement Green) Fluctuation

The EG spectrum was selected to reflect the highest intensity and reflectance compared to other spectra. Based on the different properties from one location to another, the change in EG values is shown in Figure 11. It offers three distinct clusters. These categories are discriminated in the profile and satellite image as Zone-I, Zone-II, and Zone-III (Figure 12).

Fig. 11. EG profile through distance, along Wadi Fayidah.

3) Step-3: EG and 3D_RGB Merging

After merging the RGB clusters and the EG zones, Wadi Fayidah can be categorized into 7 zones. Each zone depicts different lithofacies, which may reflect different engineering

properties. Alternatively, this classification will organize the sampling area rather than reducing or expanding it.

Fig. 12. Zones of EG fluctuation (blue, red, and green ellipses).

C. Lineaments

Automatic lineament extraction was carried out from the digital data of FCC Landsat image of Wadi Fayidah basin. Visual editing was done to delete the false lines (not structural lines) for the extracted lineaments to construct the Wadi Fayidah basin's structural lineaments, as shown in Figure 13. It was interpreted from a False color composite Landsat-7 ETM+ image.

Fig. 13. Structural lineament map of Wadi Fayidah area.

Figure 14 illustrates the relationship between the structural lineaments (frequency) and trend ranges. It concludes that Wadi Fayidah's dominant structure tends to be between 56° and 84°. The relationships between the directions of the lineament's structure (X-axis) and their lengths (Y-axis) are shown in Figure 15, which reflects the availability of two lineament clusters.

Fig. 14. Histogram of the predominant structural lineaments trend.

Fig. 15. Structural lineament evaluation of Wadi Fayidah.

Both clusters offer a positive relationship between length and direction. However, the first cluster, which covers fewer stations, shows more significant lengths than the second one. Otherwise, the trends in the first cluster are limited compared to the second cluster. The second cluster covers most stations in Wadi Fayidah. It has shorter lengths, with greater directions than the first one. Generally, the second cluster trend is predominant in the Wadi Fayidah. The relationship between the length and azimuth of the structural lineaments is positive. From a geology engineering point of view, keeping the construction far from the structure locations and short length of constructions walls or foundation perpendicular to lineament trends is recommended. Circular or curved design may also be recommended for equality stress distribution.

In a lineament structure of about 200m long, the study area can reflect two zones, as shown in Figure 15. The remaining shorter lineaments will cover the other stations. So, if these 2 zones are added to the previous 7 zones, we get 9 engineering geological zones (Figure 16).

Fig. 16. Zones of the study area.

D. Engineering Geological Mapping

To ensure that the approach used in this document is practical, the analysis and interpretation of the Landsat images were compared with the geological map of [21]. It was found that the 9 zones explored through this research match the changes in rock types of [21]. Table II summarizes the lithofacies and structure length of each zone. Consequently, an engineering geological map was introduced (Figure 17).

Previous works, such as the applicability of Landsat-8 and regression analysis in developing models for estimating water

quality parameters explored in [14], did not utilize the beneficial approach used in the current research, i.e. the RGB spectral value characterization of Landsat ETM+ data and the clustering method in the 3-D plot of the RGB data, to classify and identify the spectral enhanced data into different zones. The current study produced an engineering geological map with 9 lithofacy zones in Wadi Fayidah. To the best of our knowledge, the technique of RGB electromagnetic energy processing is presented in this study for the first time.

TABLE II. LITHOLOGICAL UNIT TYPES OF THE 9ZONES ALONG WADI FAYIDAH

Zone No.	Stations (St.)	No of St.	Rock Type		Structure Length
			Symbol	Description	
Zone-1	1-8	9	ibmv-p€ todr-p€	2 Meta-Andesitic to metabasaltic Tonalite	≥ 200 m
Zone-2	9-16	8	gdmo-p€ gr-p€	12 Granodiorite Granite	≤ 200 m
Zone-3	17-32	16	todr-p€	11 Tonalite	≤ 200 m
Zone-4	33-39	7	sscg-t sssh-t	15 Sandstone and Conglomerate	≥ 200 m
Zone-5	40-51	12	ibvs-p€s	3 Samran group, Volcanosedimentary rocks	≤ 200 m
Zone-6	52-56	5	sscg-t	15 Sandstone and Conglomerate	≤ 200 m
Zone-7	57-59	3	Gdma-p ss-t	Granodiorite Sandstone and Oolitic iron ore	≤ 200 m
Zone-8	60-64	5	clss-t	14 Clay, sandstone and tuff	≤ 200 m
Zone-9	65-78	14	clss-t	14 Clay, sandstone and tuff	≤ 200 m

Fig. 17. Engineering geological map showing the 9 lithofacy zones of Wadi Fayidah (a) Landsat image view, (b) clear view.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on Landsat-7 RGB electromagnetic energy and statistical data analysis, Wadi Fayidah has been primarily investigated for engineering geological purposes in this paper. The resulting conclusions of the current research are:

- With a length of 70km from upstream to downstream, Wadi Faydah is classified as a dendritic drainage pattern that reflects the similarity of resistance to weathering for the subsurface.
- The primary trend of the lineament structure of Wadi Fayidah ranges between 56° and 84°.
- Based on geology, structural lineaments, and RGB analysis, Wadi Fayidah is classified into 9 different lithofacies.
- For more emphasis on validity and reliability, applying the geostatistical analysis approach to RGB data in other studies is recommended.

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Fuzzy-ZRP: An Adaptive MANET Radius Zone Routing Protocol

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ABSTRACT

A Mobile Ad-hoc Network (MANET) is a group of active mobile nodes wirelessly connected in a self-configuring and self-healing network without a preexisting centralized infrastructure. Several studies have been conducted to improve the stability and lifetime of routes for communicating between source and destination nodes, integrating new techniques with existing protocols. This paper presents a fuzzy-based approach to improve the performance of the standard Zone Routing Protocol (ZRP) by selecting the optimal value of the zone radius. Each node has a fuzzy inference system that is periodically fed with parameters, such as the remaining energy and mobility of the node, to calculate the optimal value of the zone routing radius, which makes the node autonomous and intelligent. The simulation results obtained using the NS-2 simulator showed that the proposed fuzzy radius approach outperformed the standard ZRP, OVBAZRP, and PSOZRP routing protocols in all measures considered: PDR, NRL, and E2ED.

Keywords-ad hoc; MANET; hybrid routing protocol; ZRP; fuzzy logic; radius

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs) are becoming a significant technology in telecommunication networks and have attracted considerable attention over the past decades. Most MANET applications are suitable in a wide range of fields that require rapid deployment, such as military battlefields, emergency searches, rescue sites, classrooms, and conferences where participants dynamically share information using their mobile devices [1-2]. A MANET is a set of active mobile nodes that organize and configure themselves dynamically to form a wireless network without an administrator. Each node can communicate with others directly, if within transmission range, or indirectly, by relaying by intermediate mobile nodes. MANET nodes can move at any speed and in any direction independently. Moreover, they can join or leave the network arbitrarily. Due to the main characteristics of MANETs, such as high mobility, low bandwidth, and low power, developing an efficient routing protocol is a critical task [3-4]. The three main types of routing protocols in MANETs are proactive, reactive, and hybrid [5-6]. Proactive routing saves the network topology by keeping the route to each node in a particular routing table and updating it continuously [7], which speeds up sending packets from the source to the target. On the other hand, reactive routing protocols send control messages only upon request, providing a

route to send a packet from a source to a specific target [8], reducing network overload. Finally, hybrid-routing protocols combine the advantages of proactive to deliver packets to nodes within the network while using reactive techniques to forward packets to nodes outside the network [9-10].

Among the MANET protocols that handle the above problems [11-12], ZRP [13] has an advanced position. ZRP is a hybrid wireless routing protocol that offers the advantage of adapting to various network conditions. Typically, ZRP is designed to speed up delivery and reduce processing costs by applying a proactive paradigm inside a zone and a reactive paradigm outside it. In the proactive scheme, the ZRP collects neighborhood information in a local region of the network called the routing area. In contrast, reactive routing operates globally, where an on-demand routing protocol does not require neighborhood information [14-15]. To optimize the network's performance, ZRP uses an essential factor, the zone radius (by default 2), which plays a critical role between the network's overload and the delay in transferring packets by dividing the network into zones. Therefore, decreasing the radius value reduces proactive routing and increases the area of reactive routing, thus reducing network load and increasing delay in the message routing process, and vice versa [1].

The node's mobility significantly impacts the network's performance and depends mainly on speed and pause factors.

For example, for a high-mobility network with fast nodes and low pause time, the topology will constantly change, increasing the network's routing load and energy consumption because of the significant loss of communication between nodes due to the departure of the node. On the contrary, for a stable network with low-speed nodes and high pause times, the network topology will become more stable and the chances of communication between the nodes will increase. Therefore, reducing the network's routing load reduces energy consumption.

The Independent Zone Routing Protocol (IZRP) depends on the local network conditions that vary considerably due to the movement of the nodes [1-5]. Using this protocol, each node in the network can fine-tune its optimal area radius, making it independent and adaptable. IZRP is based on a hybrid scheme that combines minimum search and adaptive traffic estimation schemes [1]. This hybrid scheme aims to create a minimal amount of extra overhead by dynamically adjusting and reconfiguring the optimal zone radius of each node in a distributed manner, which allows network nodes to adapt quickly to any changes in the network's characteristics. The minimum search scheme iteratively estimates the radius of the routing area of a node by incrementing or decrementing it by one hop. At first, the amount of routing traffic passing through the node in the current estimation interval is measured and compared to the previous interval. If it is smaller, the radius of the area is incremented/decremented in the same direction. If not, the direction of the zone radius change is reversed. This process continues until a minimum is detected. The adaptive traffic estimation scheme relies on $\Gamma(\rho)$, represented by the ratio of reactive to proactive traffic of the zone radius during a specific estimation interval, by comparing it with a predetermined threshold Γ_{thres} . If $\Gamma(\rho) > \Gamma_{thres}$, an increment or decrement of the radius ρ will be triggered to decrease the routing of reactive/proactive traffic respectively, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. (a) Min searching algorithm, (b) ZRP zone routing radius optimization.

The Enhanced Zone Routing Protocol (EZRP) is more efficient than ZRP [16], as it avoids network congestion by reducing the number of IERP packets using a fixed value for the area radius, mobility, and packet size. Velocity-Based Adaptive ZRP (VBAZRP) is an enhancement of ZRP in ad hoc networks [17], which allows nodes to select the radius of the area based on their respective mobility and reduces the discovery delay resulting from the incorporation of an asymmetric request and response mechanism to maintain the routing area. The speed-optimized adaptive ZRP (OVBAZRP)

performed better than ZRP in increasing network traffic loads by allowing the zone radius to be selected according to the mobility speed of the node [18]. Particle Swarm Optimization Intelligence-independent ZRP (PSO-IZRP) dynamically determines the zone radius based on the velocity and location of the nodes by tracking the optimum in the space of solutions that satisfies the constraints of the objective function to calculate the radius at each interval [19]. Another improvement of ZRP was proposed in [20], by a novel technique named Zone-based Energy-aware Hybrid Multicast Routing Protocol (ZEHMRP), which selects stable routes for multicast packet delivery based on the residual energy of nodes in areas along the route to reduce control overhead and delay in packet delivery. The energy-efficient zone routing algorithm [21], improves the clustering mechanism by using the energy loss rate of the nodes in the zone and considering the nodes with the highest residual energy as cluster heads in each iteration. In ZRP fuzzy-based scheduling and load balance [22], the service cycles of the border nodes are adaptively adjusted according to the state of the queue, the expected residual energy, and the distance to the border nodes. In [23], a logic-based control (FLC) method was proposed to improve QoS for MANETs. As in ZRP, the mobility of the network nodes was used to establish probabilistic QoS.

This paper proposes a zone radius determination algorithm based on a fuzzy inference system, named Fuzzy-ZRP, that improves the routing performance of the standard ZRP in wireless ad-hoc networks. Furthermore, simulations showed that Fuzzy-ZRP outperformed the standard ZRP. Fuzzy-ZRP tunes the radius value of each zone by estimating it based on the node's residual energy and speed, leading to increased network lifetime and reduced overload regardless of network conditions. This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- An adaptive algorithm where each node can rapidly adapt to network conditions.
- A multi-constraint fuzzy logic controller that makes the algorithm autonomous in the sense that it can automatically estimate the optimal value of the radius zone based on the node's residual energy and speed.
- Different realistic scenarios with different mobility models were considered to study the performance of Fuzzy ZRP in terms of packet delivery rate, routing overhead, and end-to-end delay.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the modification of the classical ZRP to improve the radius selection scheme and enhance network performance by using a fuzzy logic inference system.

A. Standard ZRP

The standard ZRP is based on the division of the network in zones. Each zone consists of nodes within the maximum hop distance r . The radius is defined as a circle around the node with the value r (default=2). It should be noted that the zone is defined in hops, not as physical distance [13]. ZRP uses the proactive paradigm within the zone by applying the intra-zone routing protocol (IARP) [15]. In contrast, the reactive paradigm

is provided by the interarea routing protocol (IERP). A route to a destination in the local area can be established from the source routing table proactively cached by the IARP; therefore, if the source and the destination are in the same area, the packet can be delivered immediately.

The hybrid zone routing protocol can adapt to a wide variety of network scenarios by proactively adjusting the range of nodes and maintaining routing zones. Large routing areas are preferable when the demand for routes is high and/or the network is composed of many slow-moving nodes. In the extreme case of a fixed topology, the ideal routing area radius would be infinitely large. On the other hand, smaller routing areas are appropriate in situations where route demand is low and/or the network consists of a small number of nodes that move quickly relatively to each other. In the worst case, a one-hop radius routing area is the best, and ZRP defaults to a traditional reactive flooding protocol [13]. For a particular network scenario and proper configuration, ZRP performs at least as well (and often better than) its purely proactive and reactive constituent protocols. In situations where network behavior varies across different regions, ZRP's performance can be fine-tuned by individual adjustment of each node's routing zone [24].

B. Proposed Fuzzy-ZRP

In traditional ZRP, the value used for each area radius is a constant p , manually initialized by an expert (the default is 2). It is not enough to obtain the best performance of the protocol for a given scenario either the state of the network is stable or unstable. In the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP, important node metrics, such as node residual energy and mobility, are considered to automatically estimate the radius zone's value. Furthermore, a faster speed means that a node has to reduce its radius to guarantee the stability of the network connection, while a slower speed increases it. This is accomplished by iteratively fine-tuning the value of radius p after calculating residual energy and speed. The decision to start the process is made during a fixed period by a fuzzy logic system [25].

1) Energy and Speed Calculation

At the initial stage, each network node starts to calculate the information needed to feed the system inference, which is represented by:

- Energy (EN): represents the remaining energy in the battery of the node in question, valued as a percentage (%).

$$Energy(EN) = \frac{RE(t)}{IE} \tag{1}$$

where $RE(t)$ is the remaining energy of the node at time t , and IE is the initial energy of the node at time t_0 .

- Speed (SP): represents the speed at time t valued in m/s.

2) Radius Zone Selection Using Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic is suitable for problems that require a decision [26]. A fuzzy system describes the relationship between fuzzy input and output variables using *if-then*-based rules [27]. As shown in Figure 2, the system consists of fuzzification, defuzzification, and a fuzzy inference engine. Fuzzification represents the decisive input variables in fuzzy set membership

functions. In contrast, defuzzification converts the fuzzy output into decisive values using a mathematical formula. At the same time, the inference engine calculates the fuzzy output according to the rules listed in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Fuzzy system architecture.

To work with a fuzzy inference system, the input and output variables must be defined as membership functions. Then fuzzy rules are proposed to relate input to output memberships [28]. The membership functions should be represented by a graphical interpretation of the input and output linguistic variables. In this case, the inputs are the node's residual energy and speed, and the output is the node's radius value. Equations (2) and (3) illustrate triangular and trapezoid membership functions that describe the input and output membership degrees of the input and output variables for fuzzy inference. The residual energy of the nodes is treated as a critical input value, which directly impacts the network's lifetime and communication through the transmission and reception of packets and internal computational processes [29]. The node speed input parameter also significantly affects the stability of the network, as nodes with higher speeds increase the probability of route failure and control overhead.

$$\mu_{A_1}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq a_1 \\ \frac{x-a_1}{b_1-a_1} & a_1 \leq x \leq b_1 \\ \frac{c_1-x}{c_1-b_1} & b_1 \leq x \leq c_1 \\ 0 & x \geq c_1 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

$$\mu_{A_2}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq a_2 \\ \frac{x-a_2}{b_1-a_2} & a_2 \leq x \leq b_2 \\ 1 & b_2 \leq x \leq c_2 \\ \frac{c_2-x}{c_2-b_2} & c_2 \leq x \leq d_2 \\ 0 & x \geq d_2 \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

The fuzzy inference engine relies on a knowledge base of rules that define the input and output membership functions. As shown in Table I, the proposed system consists of nine rules calculated by multiplying the number of membership functions characterized by each input variable. These memberships are associated using a particular fuzzy operator represented by the AND. For example, selecting the ninth rule, which supposes that the node's residual energy and speed are high, the node radius value should be very low. If the node's residual energy is low and the speed is high, the output of the inference is very high. Defuzzification is a weighted average mathematical approach to extract a net output value from the aggregation of the fuzzy output representation. Several approaches have been proposed to find crisp output, and this method used the centroid

defuzzification method that has the following mathematical expression:

$$COG = \int \frac{u_A(x).x \, dx}{u_A(x).d_x} \tag{4}$$

where $u_A(x)$ is the weight of the output membership function defined in (2) and (3), x denotes the centroid of each output membership function, and COG (Center Of Gravity) indicates the crisp value of the defuzzified output[26-30].

TABLE I. FUZZY BASE RULE SET

RULES	SPEED	ENERGY	RADIUS
1	LOW	HIGH	VERY HIGH
2	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
3	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
4	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH
5	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM
6	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW
7	HIGH	HIGH	VERY LOW
8	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW
9	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM

Fig. 3. Membership function of the residual energy input.

Fig. 4. Membership function of the node speed input.

Fig. 5. Output membership function of the node radius.

C. Description of the Proposed Fuzzy Logic Algorithm

The description of the proposed algorithm can be summarized in four basic steps: fuzzification, *if-then* rule evaluation, output aggregation, and defuzzification to calculate the crisp value. These steps can be described as:

- Step 1: The fuzzification of the crisp input parameter values represented by the residual energy and the node velocity is defined by their membership functions, as shown in Figures 3-5. Each input's membership degree is found by mapping the input value with the membership function.
- Step 2: The membership degrees found in the first step will be evaluated from the rules to determine the fuzzy output set. The AND operator selects the minimum membership values from the input membership values.
- Step 3: The system collects all output from the previous step in union form and constructs a new aggregate fuzzy set by selecting the maximum evaluating values using the OR operator.
- Step 4: The defuzzification process is performed using the centroid method (center of gravity) with the new aggregate function obtained in step 3 to calculate the node radius value using (4).

III. PERFORMANCE METRICS

The performance of the proposed algorithm was compared with the standard ZRP, the OVBAZRP, and the Practical Swarm-Optimized ZRP (PSOZRP) considering the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), the End-to-End Delay (E2ED), and the Network Routing Load (NRL).

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE OF ZRP AND PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Parameters	ZRP algorithm	Proposed algorithm
PDR	AVG	HIGH
NRL	HIGH	LOW
E2ED	HIGH	LOW

- PDR is the fraction of the data packets successfully delivered to the destination [31]:

$$PDR = \frac{\sum \text{packets received by destination}}{\sum \text{packets sent by the source}} \times 100 \tag{5}$$

- NRL is the ratio of routing packets transmitted to data packets delivered [32]:

$$NRL = \frac{\sum \text{transmitted routing packets}}{\sum \text{packets received by the destination}} \tag{6}$$

- E2ED is the average end-to-end delay, calculated by summing the times taken by all received packets divided by their total numbers[32]:

$$E2ED = \frac{\sum (\text{packets received time} - \text{packets send time})}{\sum \text{packets received by the destination}} \tag{7}$$

IV. SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

A. Simulation Parameters:

The simulation study considered a network area of 1000x1000m² and 50 wireless mobile nodes randomly distributed throughout the simulation area with a maximum speed of 50m/s. Tables III and IV show the speed scenarios and simulation parameters.

TABLE III. SPEED SCENARIOS

Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
5m/s	10m/s	30m/s	40m/s	50m/s

TABLE IV. PARAMETERS OF SIMULATION SCENARIO

Parameters	Value
Simulation time	300s
Simulation area	1000x1000m ²
Node speed	0-50m/s
Propagation model	Two Ray Ground
Mobility model	Random waypoint
Radio frequency	2.47GHz
Channel bandwidth	2 Mbps
Mac protocol	IEEE 802.11
Type dataflow	CBR
Number of nodes	50
Assigned energy	20J
Transmit power	0.8W
Receive power	0.5W

B. Simulation Metrics:

The performance of MANET routing protocols can be evaluated using many quantitative metrics. This study used Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), End-to-End Delay (E2ED), and Normalized Routing Load (NRL) to evaluate the performance of the proposed routing protocol simulation, as shown in (5)-(7).

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The NS-2 simulator [33] was used to simulate and compare the performance of the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP with ZRP, OVBAZRP, and PSOZRP, based on different speed scenarios.

A. Packet Delivery Ratio

Figure 6 shows the packet delivery ratio for the compared protocols with variable speeds of the nodes. It is clear that the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP protocol outperformed the other protocols and achieved a higher PDR. However, the PDR of all protocols decreased with increasing speed, due to the increasing number of broken links in the network which increased by the mobility rate. The proposed Fuzzy-ZRP algorithm achieved the highest PDR mainly due to the dynamic area radius determination adopted, which balances the IARP and IERP routing overhead. Thus, channels and bandwidth are available for data traffic, improving the PDR. The PSOZRP dynamically determines the radius of the zone based on the speed and location of the nodes. It searches the entire space for the best optimum that satisfies the constraints of the objective function to calculate the radius at each point in time, generating additional traffic that decreases the bandwidth needed for the actual data transfer. For the OVBAZRP, the determination of the radius is based only on the speed of the node and completely ignores local parameters such as the remaining energy, which is an important factor in determining the stability of the route. The ZRP uses a static radius value for all nodes as a mechanism without taking into account local network parameters. This radius value setting causes an imbalance between IARP and IERP, leading to a reduction in packet transfer rates. Figure 7 clearly shows the PDR gain for the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP compared to the others for all speed scenarios. The PDR ranged from 6.02 to 13.15% for Fuzzy-

ZRP and conventional ZRP, the gain of Fuzzy-ZRP over OVBAZRP was between 4.30 and 10.40%, the gain of Fuzzy-ZRP with PSOZRP was between 1.80% and 6.20%.

Fig. 6. Packet delivery ratio vs speed.

Fig. 7. Packet delivery ratio gain.

B. Average End-To-End Delay

As shown in Figures 8-9, Fuzzy-ZRP had a lower average delay than ZRP, OVBAZRP, and PSOZRP in all speed scenarios. This is because ZRP uses a static zone radius regardless of the network state. However, for a stable network, the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP algorithm increased the area radius, forcing a larger area to be covered by the IARP protocol. Therefore, the IERP protocol only controls a smaller area to reduce the latency incurred by the route discovery process. On the other hand, by increasing mobility, a smaller area radius forces the IERP to take care of a larger area to minimize the IARP overhead involved in updating and maintaining the routing table.

For PSOZRP, the transfer time is influenced by the time taken to search for the best value of the zone radius at each timestamp. Additionally, OVBAZRP suffers from the inability to determine an unstable route in a short time. As shown in Figure 9, the gain obtained by incorporating the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP in the zone radius estimation over ZRP varied between 2 and 53%, over OVBAZRP varied between 1.80 to 30%, and over Fuzzy-ZRP and PSOZRP varied from 0.8% to 20%.

Fig. 8. End-to-end delay vs speed.

Fig. 9. End-to-end delay gain.

Fig. 10. Normalized routing load vs speed.

C. Normalized Routing Load

Figure 10 shows the effects of node mobility on routing control packets in the two routing scenarios used in this study. As can be seen, the overhead of routing packets increases with the speed of the nodes. Although Fuzzy-ZRP minimizes the number of control packets transmitted to the network, it maintains a different zone radius for each node depending on mobility speed and energy. The nodes in different zones have different views of the current network topology. Thus, nodes can establish more stable and reliable routes by minimizing the zone radius. PSOZRP iteratively performs the process of finding the optimal value of the zone radius, generating additional control packets to determine information on the speed and location of each node. As shown in Figure 10, the

gain obtained by applying the Fuzzy-ZRP protocol compared to ZRP varied between 21% and 46%, the difference between Fuzzy-ZRP and OVBAZRP was 12-38%, and for Fuzzy-ZRP compared to PSOZRP was 4-8%.

Fig. 11. Normalized routing load gain.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the problem of adjusting the radius of the ZRP by proposing a fuzzy-based approach that provides an auto-tuning method to automatically adjust the radius. The simulation results showed that, compared to other approaches such as PSOZRP, OVBAZRP, and classical ZRP, the proposed fuzzy-based ZRP method effectively improved the overhead of control traffic without sacrificing other performance metrics, such as packet delivery ratio and average end-to-end delay, and without requiring manual configuration. Compared to classical ZRP, the proposed approach improved PDR by 6.02-13.15%, NRL by 21-46%, and E2ED by 2-53%. The proposed protocol achieved a significant gain compared to OVBAZRP in PDR by 4.30-10.40%, NRL by 12-38%, and E2ED by 1.8-30%. Finally, the proposed Fuzzy-ZRP outperformed PSOZRP with gains of 1.80-6.20% in PDR, 4-8% in NRL, and 0.8-20% in E2ED.

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Economic Viability of a 6.5kW Off-grid Solar PV with Various Sun-Tracking Systems in Northern Cyprus: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an in-depth analysis of small-scale PV in Northern Cyprus is conducted for the first time at 37 locations in Northern Cyprus. No previous study has investigated the viability of off-grid PV systems with various sun-tracking systems in Northern Cyprus. In order to achieve this, NASA POWER data were used for the evaluation of the solar resource in the selected locations. The results showed that the selected locations are suitable for the installation of various scales of PV systems due to the high global horizontal solar radiation. The mathematical modeling method was utilized for the design and analysis of PV systems with various sun-tracking systems and for the assessment of their economic viability and feasibility. Energy production, capacity factor, payback period, and cost of energy production were calculated. The results indicate that the proposed systems are very promising for all the selected locations. The PV projects with a 2-axis sun-tracking system produce a large amount of energy and have a low electricity cost. It was found that the electrical energy cost of the developed systems was within the range of 0.4851-0.6641TL/kWh. The payback periods varied from 4.57 years to 8.49 years, depending on the type of solar PV panel and sun-tracking system. This study provides some useful recommendations for decision-makers regarding the development and deployment of PV energy technology in the country in order to achieve sustainable development goals.

Keywords-Northern Cyprus; solar energy potential; off-grid; small-scale PV system; sun-tracking system; mathematical modeling method

I. INTRODUCTION

Population growth and the rising of people's living standards have led to the growing global demand for energy, primarily electrical, from fossil fuels. It is known that environmental pollution impacts human health through the

emissions of harmful gases caused by conventional energy generation from fossil fuels. Thus, finding alternative energy sources to reduce fossil fuel consumption and environmental pollution is essential [1]. Solar energy has been widely utilized globally to generate electricity and reduce harmful gas emissions. It is clean energy from an inexhaustible and

environmentally friendly energy source. Generally, solar photovoltaic (PV) panels produce electrical power directly from the sunlight. Authors in [2] found that solar power will reduce gas emissions by about 69-100 million tons of CO₂, 68-99 thousand tons of NO_x, and 126-184 thousand tons of SO₂ by 2030. Authors in [3] reported that solar energy has a significant potential to meet the global electricity requirements in the future. Authors in [4] found that solar energy technologies have a huge potential to mitigate climate change by reducing energy-related emissions. The solar power system is most commonly used today due to improvements in the harvesting of solar energy [5], greater awareness about this energy [6], and low electricity cost compared to feed-in tariffs [7]. Generally, PV power systems are classified into two types (on-grid and off-grid PV systems). They, especially small-scale PV systems, are an effective solution to generate electricity for urban and rural regions [8, 9]. Globally, the share of PV generation capacity could be increased from 2% in 2017 with nearly 400GW installed to 10% in 2040 due to falling PV costs [10].

In Northern Cyprus, fossil fuels are the main source of electrical energy. The electrical energy is produced by steam power plants (Tekneçik Steam Unit No. 1 and Tekneçik Steam Unit No. 2), diesel electricity generating plants (Kalecik Diesel and Tekneçik Diesel), and Serhatköy PV plant [11]. According to Cyprus Turkish Electricity Authority (KIB-TEK), 44.17%, 26.53%, 11.67%, and 11.95% of electricity is generated by Kalecik Diesel, Tekneçik Diesel, Tekneçik Steam Unit No. 1, and Tekneçik Steam Unit No. 2, respectively, whereas the rest of the energy is produced by Serhatköy PV plant (0.1%) in 2021. The total electricity production increased from 1444.01GWh in 2015 to 1551.06GWh in 2019 with an average annual increase percentage of 7.41%. Furthermore, the average annual increase is approximately 3.4% in terms of electricity consumption per capita. Besides, the total installed capacity for these plants is 482.3MW according to KIB-TEK and Northern Cyprus Renewable Energy Board (YEK-Kurulu). Recently, Northern Cyprus has experienced outages with duration of more than one to two hours [12] due to the fast growth of population and constructions. According to T-VINE [13], Northern Cyprus has suffered multiple blackouts due to outages at the power plants inability to produce sufficient electricity to cope with the excessive demands during the intense summer heat. In addition, approximately 30% of total energy consumption and 20% of electricity consumption are spent on residential and commercial buildings, respectively, according to KIB-TEK. Table I lists the costs of electricity in Northern Cyprus according to KIB-TEK. KIB-TEK utilizes the net metering system for allowing end users to generate and export energy surplus to the utility grid.

Four new solar PV plants have been constructed and utilized at various locations in Northern Cyprus [14]. Northern Cyprus's climate is moderate and suitable for investing in solar energy, as there are 300 sunny days throughout the year. This increases the efficiency of relying on solar energy as an energy source. Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) and Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI) values are within the range of 4.80-5.44kWh/m²/day and 4.89-6.15kWh/m²/day, respectively according to the solar atlas map. Numerous studies have

investigated the solar energy potential in various locations in Northern Cyprus as shown in Table II. Based on the results of the previous studies, the following can be concluded: (1) solar energy is expected to contribute to electricity generation in Northern Cyprus in the future, (2) PV systems can be a good solution for reducing the fossil fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions in the island, (3) the use of solar power systems could help the island to become more independent from fossil fuels, and (4) PV systems have the ability to reduce the household electricity bills in Northern Cyprus.

TABLE I. ENERGY COSTS IN NORTHERN CYPRUS

Before March 2022	
Energy consumption based on time	
Period	Cost
0.7:00-17:00	0.98 TL/kWh
17:00-22:00	1.29 TL/kWh
22:00-07:00	0.65 TL/kWh
22:00-00:00 (Weekend)	0.98 TL/kWh
Presently	
Energy consumption based on kW	
Energy consumption	Cost
0-250 kW	0.98 TL/kWh
250-500kW	1.70 TL/kWh
501-750 kW	2 TL/kWh
751-1000kW	2.25 TL/kWh
Greater than 1000kW	3.3TL/kWh

Therefore, this paper represents a first effort to use a strategic perspective to explore how viable solar energy systems are in Northern Cyprus. The present study aims to investigate the techno-economic and environmental sustainability of rooftop PV systems and large-scale PV in various locations in Northern Cyprus. To achieve this, the solar radiation data are analyzed to classify the solar resource in the selected locations. Moreover, the techno-economic viability of an off-grid PV system with different sun-tracking systems including fixed tilt and 2-axis systems is evaluated using the mathematical modeling approach.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed methodology aims to assess the solar energy potential in 37 locations in Northern Cyprus to identify suitable locations for future installations of solar PV systems. The economic viability of these PV systems is evaluated. Figure 1 illustrates the methodology used in this study.

A. Study Area

This study aims to identify the best locations for installing solar PV power systems in Northern Cyprus. Figure 2 shows the selected locations. Table III provides the names and geographical coordinates of the selected locations. Due to the lack of actual weather data, satellite database helps in estimating the potential of wind and solar energy. It has led to the development of satellite-generated or interpolated synthetic meteorological data, which are available in grids with various spatiotemporal resolutions [39]. The gridded database NASA/POWER provides global coverage of complete weather data with a horizontal resolution of 1° of latitude and longitude [40] thus being a potential source for the study of the potentiality of renewable (wind and solar) energies [41, 42].

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF PREVIOUS STUDIES FOCUSING ON SOLAR ENERGY POTENTIAL IN NORTHERN CYPRUS

Reference	Year	Description/aim	Remarks and Key Findings
[15]	2011	Investigation of the feasibility of a 1M grid-connected PV plant in 3 locations (Lefkoşa, Güzelyurt, Dipkarpaz) in Northern Cyprus.	The feasibility of the developed system increased when the 2-axis PV system was utilized.
[16]	2012	Assessment of the performance of Parabolic Trough (PT) and Fresnel PV systems in Northern Cyprus.	Fresnel systems have higher absorption of solar radiation, lower CO ₂ emissions, and operating cost compared to PT systems.
[17]	2014	Installation of 30MW hypothetical solar chimney power plant under Northern Cyprus conditions.	The annual electricity production of the proposed system was found to be 94.5GWh, which can provide for the annual electricity needs of over 22,128 residences without any CO ₂ , NO _x , and SO _x emissions.
[18, 19]	2015	Build 1.275GW PV plant in Serhatköy site.	The plant will improve the electricity sector and will be able to reduce emissions to an acceptable level.
[20]	2016	Design and techno-economic analysis of a standalone PV system to meet the electricity of a house in the rural fringe of Famagusta.	The electricity generation cost was found to be 0.43TL/kWh and the developed system is a viable technology for the electrification of a house in Cyprus.
[21]	2016	Techno-economic and environmental feasibility of 40MW PV power plant and 40MW PT power plant in Nicosia and Famagusta.	Power plants in Nicosia have higher profitability than in Famagusta and the utilizing solar power plant will reduce large amounts of CO ₂ emissions.
[22]	2017	Development of a hybrid system to generate electricity for a household in Nicosia	The PV-wind hybrid system needs less capital cost, which is considered a more attractive option to set up in the selected location.
[11]	2018	Development of a 12MW grid-connected wind farms and fixed-tilt PV power plants in Lefkoşa and Girne.	The selected locations were found suitable to build a PV system for energy production and reduce the fuel consumption
[23]	2018	Proposing a 1MW grid-connected PV power plant with various sun-tracking systems in Lefke town.	The electricity cost was found within the range of 0.109-0.150 \$/kWh and annual GHG emission reduction varied from 1321 to 1829 tCO ₂ .
[24]	2018	Investigation of the utilization of solar energy in Famagusta.	Famagusta has a huge solar energy potential, but the city is not able to generate the required amount of solar energy due to its inappropriate urban design.
[25]	2018	Finding the best location for installing a PV power plant based on the highest profitability of the project.	Among 19 locations, Güzelyurt was the best to install a PV power plant due to the net present value, payback period and internal rate of return, and leveled cost of electricity.
[26]	2018	Proposal of a 4.85 kW grid-connected PV rooftop systems in Nicosia, Morphou, and Dipkarpaz	All selected locations have a high solar energy potential.
[27]	2019	Development of a 6.4kW grid-connected PV wind system for a household in Lefkoşa, Girne, and Gazimağusa	The PV systems are a more economical option for generating electricity in the selected locations compared to wind systems due to the low electricity production cost
[28]	2019	Proposition of a 45kW rooftop-building grid-connected PV power system in Lefke town.	The electricity cost of the proposed system was found to be 0.056\$/kWh, which is lower than the energy cost of traditional energy (0.15\$/kWh)
[29]	2019	Using of PV as a shading device for solving the heating problems in the residential sector in Famagusta.	Utilizing the PV as a shading device can provide up to 50% of the electricity demand of the single-family building and raises the comfort level of the building by about 20%.
[30]	2019	Evaluation of the performance of a 110kW grid-connected PV system with different PV technologies based on performance ratio, CF, and energy cost.	CdTe PV system has a higher performance ratio compared to other PV technologies and the proposed system can help reduce green gas emissions and supply electricity to the Near East University.
[31]	2019	Evaluation of the performance of a 110kW grid-connected PV system in 25 locations.	The annual average performance ratio was within the range of 75-80%.
[32]	2019	Techno-economic feasibility evaluation of a solar-powered seawater desalination plant in Güzelyurt.	Solar desalination could be a profitable investment with governmental incentives and can be considered a sustainable option for solving water scarcity and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.
[33]	2019	Technical, environmental, and economic aspects for developing PV/wind hybrid system in the Middle East Technical University Northern Cyprus Campus	The proposed system will reduce the annual fuel consumption of the island by 9920 barrels which will also reduce the annual CO ₂ emissions by 3622 tons.
[34]	2020	Development of a 30kW grid-connected PV system for Near East University grand library with various types of PV systems used in building PV technologies.	The performance of a freestanding mounting position system with thin film (CdTe) was found better than building-integrated PV.
[35]	2020	Techno-economic feasibility of 100MW grid-connected PV system in Lefkoşa.	The proposed system would reduce fuel consumption, electricity tariffs, and greenhouse gas emissions.
[36]	2020	Development of a 6kW PV-wind hybrid system to meet a single household electricity demands in Güzelyurt.	The proposed system provided alternative incentives to the consumers and it is economically feasible.
[37]	2021	Investigation of the techno-economic feasibility of small-scale PV systems with different sun-tracking systems for producing household electricity and desalination systems in the Güzelyurt region.	The small-scale grid-connected PV systems will reduce the electricity bill.
[14]	2021	Design of a PV system for covering the power demands in Near East University Hospital	The PV system will help solve the electricity crisis and reduce the fossil fuel consumption.
[38]	2021	Evaluation of the techno-economic feasibility of a PV-battery system for a house in Güzelyurt.	The electricity generation cost is less than the grid tariff rate.

TABLE III. SUMMARY OF PREVIOUS STUDIES FOCUSING ON SOLAR ENERGY POTENTIAL IN NORTHERN CYPRUS

Location No.	Name	Elevation [m]	Latitude [°N]	Longitude [°E]	Optimum orientation angles			
					Fixed-tilt		Vertical	Inclined
					Slope angle [°]	Azimuth angle [°]	Slope angle [°]	Slope angle [°]
1	Akdeniz	89	35.300	32.965	31.0	2.0	52.0	34.0
2	Camlibel	277	35.316	33.071	31.0	3.0	52.0	33.0
3	Lapta	168	35.336	33.163	29.0	-5.0	51.0	31.0
4	Girne	10	35.342	33.331	31.0	-1.0	52.0	33.0
5	Beylerbeyi	225	35.297	33.354	28.0	-22.0	46.0	29.0
6	Bogaz	300	35.288	33.285	31.0	0.0	52.0	34.0
7	Tatlisu	168	35.225	33.451	32.0	-3.0	52.0	34.0
8	Kantara	480	35.401	33.914	31.0	-4.0	51.0	33.0
9	Esentepe	183	35.333	33.579	31.0	0.0	52.0	33.0
10	Guzelyurt	52	35.189	32.982	31.0	0.0	52.0	34.0
11	Gaziveren	19	35.173	32.922	31.0	0.0	52.0	34.0
12	Lefke	129	35.097	32.841	30.0	-8.0	52.0	32.0
13	Yesilirmak	20	35.166	32.737	30.0	-2.0	52.0	33.0
14	Ercan	119	35.159	33.502	32.0	-4.0	52.0	34.0
15	Serdarli	111	35.252	33.610	32.0	-5.0	52.0	34.0
16	Degirmenlik	168	35.253	33.472	31.0	-1.0	51.0	33.0
17	Gecitkale	45	35.233	33.729	32.0	-2.0	52.0	34.0
18	Gonendere	75	35.270	33.657	32.0	-3.0	52.0	34.0
19	Vadili	54	35.139	33.652	32.0	-2.0	52.0	34.0
20	Beyarmudu	87	35.047	33.696	31.0	0.0	52.0	34.0
21	Cayirova	67	35.349	34.031	31.0	2.0	52.0	34.0
22	Iskele	39	35.286	33.884	31.0	0.0	52.0	34.0
23	Mehmetcik	99	35.422	34.078	31.0	2.0	52.0	34.0
24	Gazimagusa	10	35.136	33.936	31.0	2.0	52.0	34.0
25	Salamis	6	35.181	33.897	31.0	1.0	52.0	34.0
26	Alevkaya	623	35.286	33.535	31.0	2.0	51.0	33.0
27	Zumrutkoy	129	35.174	33.049	31.0	0.0	52.0	34.0
28	Alaykoy	166	35.185	33.257	32.0	-2.0	53.0	34.0
29	Lefkosa	134	35.196	33.352	32.0	-3.0	52.0	34.0
30	Ziyamet	82	35.454	34.125	30.0	3.0	51.0	33.0
31	Dipkarpaz	136	35.599	34.379	31.0	5.0	51.0	33.0
32	Yenierenkoy	123	35.536	34.189	31.0	5.0	52.0	33.0
33	Dortyol	54	35.179	33.759	32.0	-1.0	52.0	34.0
34	Kalecik	7	35.334	33.981	29.0	49.0	55.0	36.0
35	Sımrüstü	28	35.276	33.856	34.0	49.0	55.0	36.0
36	Sadrazamköy	68	35.383	32.949	32.0	51.0	54.0	35.0
37	Selvilitepe	879	35.321	33.158	27.0	49.0	54.0	35.0

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology.

Fig. 2. The selected locations.

B. Classification of Solar Potential

The potential of solar energy is divided into two classifications, namely geographical potential and technical potential [43]. In general, the annual amounts of total solar radiation at a specific location, factoring in existing geographical, social, environmental, and cultural constraints, are the factors that define the geographical potential. At the same time, the technical potential of a specific location is defined as the amount of geographical potential that can be translated into electricity using a PV [43]. According to [44], the solar energy potential was classified based on the annual value of GHI and DNI. In general, global solar radiation is considered applicable for the evaluation of the energy generation for the flat PV system. Table IV shows the classification of solar energy.

TABLE IV. CLASSIFICATION OF SOLAR ENERGY

Class	Annual GHI [kWh/m ²]	Annual DNI [kWh/m ²]
1 (poor)	<1191.8	<936.9
2 (marginal)	1191.8-1419.7	936.9-1255.7
3 (fair)	1419.7-1641.8	1255.7-1546.8
4 (good)	1641.8-1843.8	1546.8-1840.9
5 (excellent)	1843.8-2035.9	1840.9-2149.9
6 (outstanding)	2035.9-2221.8	2149.9-2533.7
7 (superb)	>2221.8	>2533.7

TABLE V. DEFINITION OF THE FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION TYPE ACCORDING TO THE RANGE OF THE SKEWNESS AND KURTOSIS VALUES

Distribution type number	Distribution curve	Skewness range	Kurtosis range
I	Normal	-0.4 < S < 0.4	-0.8 < K < 0.8
II	Almost normal with positive tail	S ≥ 0.4	-0.8 < K < 0.8
III	Narrow peak with positive tail	S ≥ 0.4	K ≤ -0.8 K ≥ 0.8
IV	Almost normal with a negative tail	S ≤ -0.4	-0.8 < K < 0.8
V	Narrow peak with negative tail	S ≤ -0.4	K ≥ 0.8
VI	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak	-0.4 < S < 0.4	K ≤ -0.8

C. Statistical Analysis

Different distribution functions have been utilized to study the characteristics of solar radiation. For example, authors in [11] utilized normal, logistic, Nakagami, and Rician

distribution models to analyze the characteristics of global solar radiation in urban regions in Northern Cyprus. Authors in [45] determined the best probability distribution (gamma, generalized extreme value, Weibull, extreme value, logistic, normal, and lognormal) for analyzing the global solar radiation of Ibadan, Nigeria. Authors in [46, 47] defined the frequency distribution type as a function of the range of the skewness and kurtosis values of solar radiation at two locations in Cyprus.

In this study, the best frequency distribution type for modeling the monthly solar radiation is selected based on the range value of Skewness and Kurtosis as shown in Table V.

D. Off-grid Photovoltaic System

The off-grid solar PV system is a common configuration. This system requires a battery for storing the remaining produced energy. Therefore, evaluating the daily electrical load and daily solar energy are important parameters for performing the optimal modeling of the PV array. The peak power of PV (P_{PV}) is the first parameter that should be estimated. According to [48], PV power array ($P_{PV(t)}$) depends upon solar radiation and it can be expressed as:

$$P_{PV(t)} = P_{PV(rate)} \times f_{loss} \times \frac{G_{sr}(t)}{IP} \tag{1}$$

where $P_{PV(rate)}$ is the nominal power of the panel under standard test conditions (STC), f_{loss} is the derating factor of the solar PV panel due to shade, dirt, temperature, and so on, $G_{sr}(t)$ is the hourly/daily/monthly global solar radiation at the surface of the solar PV panel in kWh/m² and IP is the standard incident radiation (1 kW/m²).

Additionally, $P_{PV(t)}$ depends on absorption capacity, panel area, and cell temperature [49]:

$$P_{PV(t)} = \frac{G_{sr}(t)}{IP} \times P_{PV(rate)} \times \eta_{PV} \times [1 - \beta_T(T_C - T_{C,STC})] \tag{2}$$

where η_{PV} is the percentage of the power reduction factor of the PV panels, $T_{C,STC}$ is cell the temperature under STC, β_T is the PV temperature coefficient, and T_C is the cell temperature under operating conditions:

$$T_C = \frac{G_{sr}(t)}{800} \times (NOCT - 20) + T_{amb} \tag{3}$$

where $NOCT$ is the Normal Operation Cell Temperature and T_{amb} is the ambient temperature.

Furthermore, the $P_{PV(t)}$ can be expressed as [50]:

$$P_{PV(t)} = G_{sr}(t) \times A_{surface} \times f_{activ} \times \eta_{cell} \times \eta_{invert} \times N[1 - (t - 1) \times d_{PV}] \tag{4}$$

where $A_{surface}$ is the net surface area of PV modules, f_{activ} is the fraction of the surface area with active solar cells, η_{cell} is the module conversion efficiency, which can be determined from the manufacturers' specifications, η_{invert} is the inverter conversion efficiency, N is the quantity of the PV modules, t is the time expressed in years ($t \geq 1$), and d_{PV} is the degradation rate of the PV system.

The power output of the PV array can be estimated by [17]:

$$P_{PV(t)} = A_{surface} \times \eta_{PV} \times \eta_{invert} \times f_{loss} \times [B_T + R_T + D_T] \quad (5)$$

where η_{ref} is the referenced efficiency of the PV panels, B_{ref} is the temperature coefficient of the PV panel, I_{NOCT} is the incident solar radiation for the *NOCT* test, T_a is the ambient temperature, T_{ref} is the reference temperature of the PV panels, T_{NOCT} is the nominal operating cell temperature at test conditions, $T_{a,NOCT}$ is the ambient *NOCT*, B_T , R_T , and D_T are the hourly beam, reflected and diffuse component of the solar radiation on a tilted surface, and η_{PV} is the efficiency of the solar panels provided by:

$$\eta_{PV} = \eta_{ref} \left[1 - B_{ref} \left[T_a - T_{ref} + (T_{NOCT} - T_{a,NOCT}) \frac{I_T}{I_{NOCT}} \right] \right] \quad (6)$$

$P_{PV(t)}$ is considered the first parameter that needs to be estimated. It can be expressed as [51]:

$$P_{PV(t)} = \left(\frac{E_{AC}}{G_{sr} T_c \eta_{PV} \eta_{inv} \eta_B} \right) P_i \eta_{PV} \quad (7)$$

where η_{PV} is the PV modules efficiency, η_{inv} is the inverter efficiency; T_c is the temperature coefficient, and η_B is the battery efficiency.

Moreover, designing a battery system is required due to the limitation of daily hours of sunshine and the stochastic nature of solar energy and to support electricity generation sustainability and energy storage [52]. Consequently, the number of autonomy dat (N_{ad}), the battery efficiency (η_B), the inverter efficiency (η_{inv}), the depth of discharge (D_{dod}), and the size of the electrical load (E_{AC}) should be considered for designing the battery system. Equation (18) is used to determine the Battery Storage Capacity (*BSC*) in Wh [51]:

$$BSC = \frac{E_{AC} N_{ad}}{D_{dod} \eta_{inv} \eta_B} \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, the number of autonomy hours (N_{ah}) can be determined by [53]:

$$N_{ah} = \frac{K_B \eta_{invert} \eta_{dech} D_{dod}}{E_{AC}} \quad (9)$$

where η_{dech} is the battery storage system discharging efficiency (%), D_{dod} is the battery storage system depth of discharge, V_B is the voltage of the battery block, and K_B is the battery storage system's nominal capacity in kWh provided by:

$$K_B = \frac{N_{ah} E_{AC}}{\eta_{inv} \eta_{dech} D_{dod}} \quad (10)$$

Additionally, a Charge Controller (CC) has been designed to support the battery of the off-grid system. The CC should be designed with at least 25% more of the $P_{P(PV)}$ current to permit cold temperatures [20]. The CC is equipped with a Maximum Power Point Tracker (MPPT) that is required to charge and protect the batteries avoiding both the risk of overcharging and reaching excessive discharge level [20]. The main function of CC is to support electrical load power consumption and promote the battery's lifespan [54].

As mentioned above, an inverter is a component of the system. The capacity of the inverter should be higher than $P_{P(PV)}$ by 20% in order to be able to handle the maximum power of electric loads [55].

E. Off-Grid Photovoltaic System

In the literature, several methods and software simulations have been utilized for the evaluation of the life cycle cost of standalone and hybrid PV systems [17, 20, 51, 55-59]. For instance, authors in [17] developed an economic model to evaluate the cost-benefit of an off-grid PV system in rural Gusau, Nigeria. Author in [20] used mathematical modeling to assess the techno-economic feasibility of an off-grid PV system to electrify a house in the rural fringe of Famagusta, Cyprus. Authors in [51] examined the feasibility of an off-grid PV system to drive the electricity consumption of a residential building in Jos, Nigeria using mathematical modeling. Authors in [58] used HOMER software to evaluate the feasibility of wind-PV-diesel hybrid power systems for a village in Saudi Arabia. Authors in [57] investigated the economic viability of a hybrid system that can be used to supply electricity to a rural community in Sri Lanka using HOMER. Authors in [58] evaluated the performance of residential solar PV systems with utility backup in Nagpur, India using mathematical modeling and software simulation. Authors in [55] utilized mathematical modeling to evaluate the feasibility of an off-grid PV system for the electrification of a single residential household in Faisalabad, Pakistan. Authors in [59] investigated the techno-economic feasibility of a stand-alone solar PV system for an isolated locality in Bangladesh using spreadsheet modeling.

The mathematical equations that are used in the current study to evaluate the life cycle analysis, which covers all the PV system life stages including the initial capital cost or acquisition cost and the operation and maintenance costs, are expressed below.

Cost of a PV array (C_{PV}) in US\$:

$$C_{PV} = P_{P(PV)} \times \text{unit price of PV module} \quad (11)$$

Initial cost of batteries (*ICB*) in US\$:

$$ICB = BSC \times \text{unit price of battery} \quad (12)$$

Present worth of the battery for various battery lifespans (*N*):

$$ICB = CB \times \left(\frac{1+i}{1+d} \right)^N \quad (13)$$

where i is the inflation rate, d is the discount rate, and CB is the cost of the battery in US\$.

Cost of an inverter system (C_{inv}) in US\$:

$$C_{inv} = P_{P(PV)} \times \text{unit price of inverter} \quad (14)$$

Cost of a charge controller (C_{CC}) in US\$:

$$C_{CC} = \text{Size of charge controller} \times \text{unit cost of charge controller} \quad (15)$$

Cost of a PV installation (C_{PVI}) is US\$:

$$C_{PVI} = 10\% \times \text{initial cost of PV} \quad (16)$$

Maintenance cost (C_m):

$$C_m = 2\% \times \text{initial cost of PV} \quad (17)$$

Furthermore, the Present Worth (PW) of the C_m is estimated by considering the depreciation rate, the inflation rate, and the PV system life span.

$$PWC_m = \left(\frac{\text{Month}}{\text{year}}\right) \times \left(\frac{1+i}{1+d}\right) \times \left(\frac{1-\left(\frac{1+i}{1+d}\right)^N}{1-\left(\frac{1+i}{1+d}\right)}\right) \quad (18)$$

where d is the depreciation rate percentage.

Levelized cost (LCC) in US\$:

$$LCC = C_{PV} + CB + C_{inv} + C_{CC} + C_m + C_{PVI} \quad (19)$$

Annualized life cycle cost ($ALCC$):

$$ALCC = LCC \left(\frac{1-\left(\frac{1+i}{1+d}\right)}{1-\left(\frac{1+i}{1+d}\right)^N}\right) \quad (20)$$

Unit electricity cost (U_{EC}) in US\$/kWh:

$$U_{EC} = \frac{ALCC}{365 \times E_{AC}} \quad (21)$$

Annual Savings (AS) in US\$:

$$AS = \text{Annual Energy Generation} \times \text{feedin tariff rate for solar power purchase} \quad (22)$$

Payback Period (PP):

$$PP = \frac{\text{Initial Investment}}{AS} \quad (23)$$

F. Solar Panel and Inverter

A large number of PV modules with different specifications are available on the market. Mono-crystalline PV modules have the highest efficiency compared to poly-crystalline cells and amorphous silicon modules [54]. Furthermore, cell type, system cost, warranty, size, and power are important factors to select the best PV panel [60]. Therefore, a selection criterion is needed to select a specified PV module to be used in a specific project. A survey of the characteristics of most of the available PV modules from different manufacturers and technologies is done (Table VI). Based on the previous studies, several Panel Selection (PS) criteria are used to select the suitable PV module:

$$PS = \frac{\text{PV module capacity} \times \text{Module efficiency}}{\text{module price} \times \text{frame area of module}} \quad (24)$$

$$PS = \frac{\text{PV module capacity}}{\text{Frame area of module}} \quad (25)$$

$$PS = \frac{\text{PV module capacity}}{\text{module price} \times \text{frame area of module}} \quad (26)$$

$$PS = \frac{\text{Cost of 1kW PV system}}{\text{Energy production of 1 kW PV system}} \quad (27)$$

Based on the calculations (Figure 3), UZ158MHC340-60, AE410HM6-72, and NS-290P6 solar modules offer a better ratio compared to other models. It should be noted that these models have been selected based on the selection criteria among the PV modules surveyed.

TABLE VI. CHARACTERISTICS OF MOST AVAILABLE PV MODULES

Module No	Manufacturer	Module type	Maximum Power [W]	Efficiency	Module area [m ²]	Module Price [€]
1	Jinko	JKM330M-60-V	330	19.78	1.668	115
2	Solar Fabrik	-	340	20.14	1.687	237
3	Panasonic	-	325	19.4	1.674	257
4	Ankara Solar	AS-M60-310W	310	19	1.63	77
5	AXITEC	AC-430MH/144V	430	19.33	2.174	120.4
6	Suntech	STP325-24/ Vfw	335	17.2	1.944	81
7	SunLink	-	435	20	2.1073	105
8	AE Solar	AE410HM6-72	410	20.69	1.674	115
9	Tide Solar	-	450	20.4	2.208	90
10	Regitec Solar	RMH60/380S1	380	20.9	1.853	110
11	Austa Energy	AU410-27V-MHB	410	20.97	1.955	99
12	Horay Solar	HS166-380-120M	380	20.5	1.823	84
13	München Energieprodukte GmbH	-	440	19.9	2.209	110
14	Fortunes Solar	FDS-M6M-60-355BK	355	19.26	1.868	82
15	Sunket	SKT375M6-20/HC	375	20.1	1.868	90
16	Smart Solar System	HCM60X9-345W	345	20.4	1.689	72.75
17	Mysolar	MS400PM5-66SA	400	21.3	1.876	83.51
18	AE solar	AE M6-60 320W	320	19.27	1.661	62.42
19	UzinSemi	UZ158MHC340-60	340	20.1	1.695	57
20	Betop (EU) Tech GmbH	SR-325-340-120M	340	20	1.6873	64.89
21	Exiom Solution	EX340M-120	340	20.1	1.692	70.98
22	EnergyPal	ASP345P6-72	345	17.8	1.94	64.02
23	Betop (EU) Tech GmbH	NS-290P6	290	17.8	1.626	47.24
24	Ankara Solar	AS-P60-290W	290	17.83	1.63	30
25	Ankara Solar	AS-P72-345W	345	17.78	1.94	35
26	Ankara Solar	AS-B60 -320W	320	21	1.61	47
27	Canadian Solar	mono-Si - CS6X-300M	300	15.63	1.919	249
28	Canadian Solar	poly-Si - CS6X-310P	310	16.16	1.918	248

Fig. 3. PS criteria and efficiency of the surveyed PV modules.

Furthermore, output AC power, DC-AC conversion efficiency, and capital cost of the inverter are the main factors to select a suitable inverter. As mentioned above, this study aims to design a small-scale on-grid and off-grid PV system, thus, a hybrid inverter, the combination of an on-grid and off-grid solar inverter, is selected in this study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mathematical modeling methods and RETScreen Expert software were utilized to evaluate the viability of small-scale rooftop and large-scale PV systems in different locations in Northern Cyprus.

A. Solar Irradiation Characteristics Analysis

In this section, the GHI data were analyzed. GHI is an essential parameter to analyze the solar resource at the project location to evaluate power generation for flat-panel PVs [51, 61]. The statistical description of GHI for the period of 2005-2020 is listed in Table VII. The description includes the mean, standard deviation (SD), coefficient of variation (CV), minimum (Min.), maximum (Max.), Kurtosis (K), and Skewness (S). It can be seen that the mean monthly value of GHI is within the range of 142.0-162.3kWh/m². The maximum and minimum values of mean GHI are recorded in Ercan and Beylerbeyi, respectively. The CV values are moderately low, ranging from 36.6% to 47.53%. Additionally, all S values are negative, indicating that all distributions are left skewed. The K values varied from -1.7 to -1.68. Moreover, Type VI, which is bimodal, and symmetrical with a flat peak, characterizes the mean monthly GHI. Figure 4 illustrates the annual value of GHI for all selected locations. It is seen that the annual GHI values varied from 1704.07 (Beylerbeyi) to 1948.00 (Ercan) kWh/m², respectively. Furthermore, the solar resources at project locations are categorized as good, excellent, outstanding, and superb as shown in Table VIII. Based on the

value of GHI, it is observed that the solar resource of all selected locations except Beylerbeyi is categorized as class 5 (excellent). It is concluded that the selected locations are suitable for the installation of large- or small-scale PV systems due to the values of GHI and DNI. Accordingly, all selected areas are suitable for the installation of PV/flat panels and CSP systems.

Fig. 4. Annual value of GHI for all selected locations.

Fig. 5. Sun's path over a year for some selected locations.

TABLE VII. STATISTICAL ESTIMATORS OF THE MONTHLY GHI IN KWH/m² FOR THE 2005-2020 PERIOD

Location	Mean	SD	CV	Min.	Max.	S	K	Distribution type
Akdeniz	159.5	61.1	38.3	75.4	238.2	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Camlibel	159.9	61.1	38.23	75.8	238.7	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Lapta	155.4	65.7	42.29	63.6	238.2	-0.15	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Girne	160	61	38.1	76.1	238.5	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Beylerbeyi	142	67.5	47.53	51.5	227.8	-0.09	-1.7	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Bogaz	159.9	60.5	37.84	76.4	237	-0.12	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Tatlisu	162	60.5	37.33	78.2	239.2	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Kantara	156.5	57.2	36.55	76.1	227.7	-0.16	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Esentepe	160.5	60.8	37.87	76.2	238.6	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Guzelyurt	160.8	60.8	37.79	77.3	239.2	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Gaziveren	160.8	60.8	37.81	77.3	239.4	-0.1	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Lefke	160.4	60.3	37.61	77.3	237.2	-0.12	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Yesilirmak	159.7	60.1	37.66	76.8	236	-0.12	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Ercan	162.3	60.2	37.11	78.4	238.8	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Serdarli	160	60.6	37.86	76.2	237.3	-0.12	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Degirmenlik	159.7	60.7	37.99	75.8	237	-0.12	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Gecitkale	162.2	60.3	37.17	78.1	238.7	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Gonendere	160.4	60.7	37.86	76.2	238.3	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Vadili	162.3	60.2	37.13	78.2	238.7	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Beyarmudu	162.2	60.2	37.13	78.2	238.6	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Cayirova	159.2	60.2	37.81	75.6	235.7	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Iskele	160.3	60.6	37.78	76.2	237.8	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Mehmetcik	159.2	60.2	37.82	75.6	235.7	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Gazimagusa	161.8	60	37.1	77.8	237.5	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Salamis	161.8	60	37.1	77.8	237.5	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Alevkaya	160.5	60.8	37.88	76.3	238.6	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Zumrutkoy	161.2	60.7	37.66	77.7	239.3	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Alaykoy	160.5	60.8	37.88	76.3	238.6	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Lefkosa	162.1	60.4	37.28	78.6	239.3	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Ziyamet	159	60.2	37.85	75.5	235.2	-0.12	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Dipkarpaz	158	60	38	74.2	232.9	-0.13	-1.69	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Yenierenkoy	157.8	60.4	38.29	74	234.6	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Dortyol	161.9	60	37.09	77.9	237.5	-0.13	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Kalecik	160.3	60.6	37.8	76.1	237.7	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Simrüstü	160.3	60.6	37.78	76.2	237.8	-0.12	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Sadrazamköy	159.5	61.1	38.33	75.4	238.3	-0.11	-1.68	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak
Selvilitepe	155.5	59	37.96	74.9	230.4	-0.11	-1.74	Bimodal, symmetrical with a flat peak

TABLE VIII. SOLAR ENERGY CLASSIFICATION FOR ALL LOCATIONS BASED ON THE ANNUAL GHI IN KWH/m².

Location	GHI	Class	Location	GHI	Class
Akdeniz	1914.023	5	Beyarmudu	1946.873	5
Camlibel	1918.425	5	Cayirova	1910.374	5
Lapta	1865.277	5	Iskele	1923.826	5
Girne	1920.575	5	Mehmetcik	1910.203	5
Beylerbeyi	1704.069	4	Gazimagusa	1941.646	5
Bogaz	1919.021	5	Salamis	1941.734	5
Tatlisu	1944.539	5	Alevkaya	1925.431	5
Kantara	1877.795	5	Zumrutkoy	1933.877	5
Esentepe	1925.804	5	Alaykoy	1925.431	5
Guzelyurt	1929.479	5	Lefkosa	1945.419	5
Gaziveren	1929.953	5	Ziyamet	1908.114	5
Lefke	1925.094	5	Dipkarpaz	1896.059	5
Yesilirmak	1916.061	5	Yenierenkoy	1893.448	5
Ercan	1948.001	5	Dortyol	1942.426	5
Serdarli	1920.338	5	Kalecik	1923.242	5
Degirmenlik	1916.306	5	Simrüstü	1923.958	5
Gecitkale	1946.526	5	Sadrazamköy	1913.993	5
Gonendere	1924.809	5	Selvilitepe	1866.323	5
Vadili	1947.005	5			

The sun's direction for one year is illustrated in Figure 5 for some selected locations. The gray fills represent the terrain

horizon, while the unit horizon (represented by blue fill) may have a shading effect on solar radiation. The black dots represent true solar time, while the blue markers indicate the local hourly time. A gray line is used in the illustration to depict three paths of the sun in three curves. The sun's lowest gray path is at the winter solstice, the mean curvature at the equinox, and the upper curvature at the summer solstice. The curves of the sun show that in winter, the sun has a low horizon and in summer, the sun has a high horizon.

B. Electric Energy Production and Capacity Factor of 6.5kW Off-Grid PV Systems

In this study, the PV system is designed according to the minimum value of GHI to satisfy the occupants' electricity demands for the whole year for the selected household. Based on the previous section, the maximum PV power is estimated to be 14.783kWh based on the minimum value of GHI on the horizontal surface for Beylerbeyi. According to the renewable energy board (Yek-Kurulu), the customers can install 5kW single-phase grid-connected and up to 8kW three-phase grid-connected PV systems. Consequently, the capacity of the developed system is assumed to be 6.5kW. Accordingly, the economic viability of off-grid PV systems with various sun-

tracking systems is discussed in this section. Based on the selection criteria, UZ158MHC340-60, AE410HM6-72, and NS-290P6 with 340W, 410W, and 290W peak capacity are selected in this study. In the following sections, the results obtained from the mathematical model are summarized.

The performance of the PV systems in terms of PV output and Capacity Factor (CF) is dependent on the orientation angles [14]. Thus, the Electric Energy Production (EEP) and CF were estimated for the different sun-tracking systems. It should be noted that EEP and CF for the fixed-tilted, vertical axis and inclined system are determined at the optimum orientations angles. The mean annual values of EEP for all selected locations are shown in Figure 6. It is found that the maximum and minimum values of EEP are recorded in Sadrazamköy and Beylerbeyi, respectively. It should be noted that the monthly (MPVP) and annual (APVP) PV energy production can be determined by (28) and (29), respectively. As an example, the annual PV electrical energy production for Beylerbeyi and Sadrazamköy is shown in Figure 7.

$$MPVP = \eta_{PV} \times A_{PV} \times \text{Monthly GHI} \quad (28)$$

$$APVP = \sum_{i=1}^{12} \eta_{PV} \times A_{PV} \times \text{Monthly GHI} \quad (29)$$

Fig. 6. Annual EEP value of all selected locations.

Among the PV models, the results indicate that the highest monthly/annual EEP is achieved when NS-290P6 is used, as shown in Figure 7. Besides, the solar tracking system can increase the annual energy production up to 20% and 40% using single-axis and 2-axis systems, respectively according to [62, 63]. It can be noticed that the amount of output power increases when the sun-tracking system is used. These results are supported by the findings in [54, 64].

As mentioned above, CF is an important parameter to evaluate the performance of PV systems. Figure 8 illustrates the annual value of CF for all selected locations. It is found that the CF values range from 22.43 to 39.77%. The highest average annual value of CF was recorded in Sadrazamköy while the lowest value was obtained in Beylerbeyi for a 2-axis PV system and a fixed-tilted PV system, respectively. Other researchers who analyzed the performance of off-grid PV systems in terms of CF can support these observations. Authors in [65] found that the annual value of CF for the solar off-grid system is 24.6%. Authors in [66] found that the CF values of

off-grid PV/hydrogen fuel cells are within the range of 16.4–31.2%. Moreover, authors in [67] found that the value of CF lies in the range of 16.2-30.3%. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the value gained during the current study for each location is consistent with the accepted values. Thus, it is technically sustainable to install off-grid PV systems at all the selected locations in Northern Cyprus.

Fig. 7. Monthly PV energy production using UZ158MHC340-60 for Beylerbeyi and Sadrazamköy with various sun-tracking systems.

C. Economic Viability of 6.5kW Off-Grid PV Systems

The performance of the proposed systems is evaluated by estimating the economic factors of each system. In this study, the value of T_c is assumed to be 80% due to a 15–20% loss in efficiency as a result of increasing cell temperature to around 60°C [20]. Moreover, the efficiency of the selected battery is 85% and the efficiency of the PV panels is listed in Table VI.

Fig. 8. Annual CF value of all selected locations.

Additionally, the required BSC is determined based on the assumption value of the N_{ad} as 2 days and maximum D_{dod} as

80%. Moreover, Trojan SAGM batteries were utilized in this study (nominal voltage = 12V, round trip efficiency = 85%, throughput = 2285.1kWh, capital cost = 538 USD, replacement cost = 500USD, and operating and maintenance cost = 8 USD/year).

Fig. 9. Unit electricity cost for all the proposed PV systems (the prices are estimated based on the US dollar exchange rate during the writing of the paper).

Generally, assessing the economic viability of the proposed system is important. Based on the mathematical modeling method, the costs of PV modules, inverter, battery, charge controller, installation, and operation and maintenance were calculated. Further, the LCC, ALCC, PP, and U_{EC} are mathematically estimated for various PV technologies and sun-tracking systems. It should be noted that the initial investment, battery replacement, and operation and maintenance of the system are determined using current market prices. Additionally, the financial parameters inflation rate and discount rate are 8% and 6%, respectively. The total Life Cycle Cost (LCC) of the proposed PV systems including the initial investment cost, the present value of battery replacement cost, and the present value of operation and maintenance cost was estimated. It was found that LCC values are within the range of 286903.39-656408.00 USD. Moreover, Figure 9 illustrates the value of PP and U_{EC} for all selected locations. It was found that

the U_{EC} values varied from 0.4851TL/kWh to 0.6641TL/kWh. The lowest U_{EC} value of 0.4851TL was obtained from the proposed system with a 2-axis system. These values are compared with the current electricity prices in Northern Cyprus (see Table I) and [20]. Authors in [20] estimated U_{EC} to 0.43TL/kWh. Therefore, it is clear that the price of the electricity generating by PV systems is less than that of a conventional system. It can be concluded that the developed systems provide a significant insight into the economic feasibility of the project for all locations.

Moreover, the PP for the off-grid PV systems with various sun-tracking systems and PV technologies is determined. It should be noted that the feed-in tariff rate varied from one country to another. For example, the value of the feed-in tariff during the first year after the system installation in Iran is 0.247\$/kW for a PV system with a capacity smaller than 20kW [68]. According to [69, 70], the feed-in tariff for PV systems in Turkey is 13.3 \$ cents/kWh, for an application period of 10 years. In this study, the feed-in tariff rate for solar power purchase is assumed to be 0.133 USD/kWh. It is observed that PP values varied from 4.57 to 8.49 years, depending on the type of the panel and the sun-tracking system, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Payback period of all the proposed PV systems.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The current study is one of the first attempts to assess the techno-economic validity of using an off-grid PV system with various sun-tracking modes in Northern Cyprus. To fulfill this objective, NASA POWER data were used to categorize the solar resource in the selected locations. Additionally, the mathematical modeling method was used to estimate the energy production, capacity factor, payback period, and the cost of energy production of the proposed systems. The main results of the current study are:

- Ercan is the most suitable location for the installation of various sizes of PV systems.
- The conducted analysis showed that the development of the proposed 6.5kW off-grid PV power system is very promising in all the selected locations.
- An economic comparison between different tracking modes revealed that the use of a 2-axis tracking system is the most economical option for all locations.
- The electricity price of the developed systems was found within the range of 0.4851-0.6641TL/kWh for off-grid PV systems. These values were compared with the current electricity prices in Northern Cyprus and previous scientific studies regarding Northern Cyprus (0.43TL/kWh [20], 0.286-0.826TL/kWh [27], 1.376TL/kWh [35], 1.617-2.217TL/kWh [23], and 1.711-1.788TL/kWh [38]).

The results demonstrated that the technical and economic viability of the proposed systems for power production can serve as a model for the successful development of real applications of the systems. Further, the model can encourage the stakeholders in the renewable sector to provide support mechanisms for the adoption of PV systems in residential buildings.

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